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Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) is the official Journal of the Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Journal publishes article of diverse fields of interest in education. Papers reporting original research and extended version of already established conference and journal articles are welcomed. Papers for publication are selected through peer review process to ensure originality, relevance and readability. ZIJE is published bi-annually June and December.

The aim and scope of the journal is to provide an academic medium and an important reference for the advancement and dissemination of information that supports high level learning, teaching and research in the fields of education.

This edition, Volume 4, Number 3, October, 2024 is poised to present research reports in the following fields of education: Educational Foundations, Science Education, Educational Psychology, Curriculum & Instructional Technology, Guidance & Counselling, Philosophy & History of Education, Sociology of Education, Entrepreneurship Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Physical & Health Education, Religious Education, Gender Studies, Peace & Security Education among others. The articles in this volume are academic and professional discourse written by reputable scholars in their areas of specialization.

The Board remain indebted to its editorial members for the ceaseless support given towards successful publication of the Journal. In the same vein, we acknowledge quite sincerely the assistance and support of our esteemed consulting editors for ensuring the credibility of this edition. Also worthy of appreciation are the authors and their immense contributions to this publication.

Associate Professor Umar Sodangi

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CALL FOR ARTICLES

The Editorial Board of Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) calls for scholarly articles for review and possible publication in its next edition (Volume 4, Number 3). ZIJE publishes articles that emphasize on research development and application within the field of Education. All manuscripts are reviewed by editorial review committee. Contributions must be original, not previously or simultaneously published elsewhere, and are critically reviewed before they are published. Papers, which must be written in English Language, should have good grammar and proper terminologies. Also note that prospective articles are subjected to plagiarism assessment to estimate the percentage of originality of the papers. Hence, plagiarism threshold of $\leq 20\%$ is recommended.

Editorial Guidelines

1. Manuscripts including references, appendices, tables and diagrams should be double-spaced and single coded on A4 paper with generous margins (at least 1”/2.5cm).
2. Title should be explicit and not more than 19 words.
3. Title page should be arranged as follows: Title, author(s) full name, affiliation, full addresses, email addresses and phone numbers.
4. Abstract should be single line and not more than 250 words.
5. For conceptual papers, the body should have appropriate headings where necessary.
6. For empirical papers, it should be presented in the following order: Introduction, Objectives of the study, Research Questions and/or Hypotheses, Methodology, Results, Discussion of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.
7. Acknowledgement (if any).
8. Quotations of more than 40 words should be indented and typed single spacing with indication of the pages where the quotes were lifted.
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11. Each table and figure should be presented within the manuscripts, with a brief and self-explanatory title.
12. All text within the table should be clearly legible, and all graphics and legends should be easily distinguished when printed in black and white.
13. Tables should be in horizontal lines only, with only blank space to separate columns.
14. Tables and figures that may be included in the main text of the paper should be numbered separately, in the sequence that they are mentioned in the text.
15. Figures should be saved in a neutral data format such as JPEG, TIFF or EPS.

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Manuscripts should be submitted directly to the Editor-in-Chief or Publication Editor through the following e-mail address: zijefugusau@gmail.com. Articles can be submitted between the periods of January to April ending for June publication, while July to October ending for December publication. Assessment fee for manuscript is #5,000.00 only.

Associate Professor Abubakar Sadiq Haruna

Publication Editor

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Table of Contents

SN	Paper Title and Authors	Page
1	Assessment of Socio-Economic Factors on Performance in Economics among Secondary School Students in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711	1
2	Effect of Three-Step Interview Strategy on Performance in Basic Science Concepts among Secondary School Students in Onna, Akwa Ibom State. Zamfara https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928806	13
3	Effects of Statistical Knowledge on Understanding and Performance in Ecological Concept among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria. Zamfara https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928941	22
4	Qualitative Study on Complex Conflicts Resolution in Nigeria: Dynamics, Causes and Effects of Military Civil Wars. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929025	27
5	Perception of Body Image on Self-Concept among Undergraduate Students in Nigeria: a Review. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929094	33
6	Physiological Responses to Heat Stress: Implications for Training and Performance among Athletes in Nigeria. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929122	41
7	Influence of working-class mothers on academic performance of primary school pupils in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929155	48
8	Quality Assurance at the Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria: Principles, Implications and Challenges. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929192	59
9	Review of inclusive Human Kinetics and Health Education programmes for sustainable National Development in Nigeria. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219	66
10	Assessment on Provision, Utilization and Maintenance of Secondary School Facilities in Dala Educational Zone, Kano State, Nigeria. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929262	73
11	Correlation between Parental Styles and Emotional Intelligence on Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kaduna-South, Local Government Area, Kaduna State. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929322	80 77
12	Effect of Activity-Based Approach on Performance in Basic Science Concepts among Lower Basic Students in Soba Educational Zone, Kaduna State. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929343	86

DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14651836> www.zijefugusau.com.ng

- 13 Comparative Relationship between Professional Practices and Job 91
Effectiveness among Secondary School Teachers in Abia State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929374>
- 14 Effect of Class-Period-Length on Performance and Retention in Biology 97
Concepts among Secondary School Students in North-West, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929413>
- 15 Integration of Educational Mobile Applications in Facilitating Learner- 105
Centered Instructional Strategies at Tertiary Level of Education in
Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929449>
- 16 Qualitative Study on Effective Pedagogy for Sustainable Primary Level 112
of Education in Nigeria: Review on Post Covid-19 Era.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929483>
- 17 Assessment of Basic Reading Abilities and Learning-Gap among Early 118
Public Primary School Pupils in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929513>
- 18 Assessment of Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Physics 126
among Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality
Assurance, Katsina State.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929533>
- 19 Comparative Relationships between Self-Efficacy and Test Anxiety on 130
Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in North-
West, Nigeria. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929563>
- 20 Impacts of ICT and Social Media platforms on Performance in 136
Economics among students in selected tertiary institutions in Kaduna
State.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929615>
- 21 Management of Secondary School Curriculum for Adequate Foundation 144
on Students Transiting to Tertiary Institutions in Dutsinma, Katsina
State. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>
- 22 Comparative Analysis of Social Protection Intervention and Early Child 151
Marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929644>
- 23 Managing Threats to Internal Validity in Quantitative and Qualitative 160
Research: Some Basic Considerations.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14260135>
- 24 Comparative analysis between Welfare Services and wellbeing of 166
retired citizens in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River
State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929698>
- 25 Correlation between Artificial Intelligence on Mental Health and 174
Retention Skills among Undergraduate Students in Federal University
Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929732>

DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14651836> www.zijefugusau.com.ng

- 26 Qualitative Study on Philosophical Issues in Teaching and Learning Outcomes of Secondary School Students in Cross River State, Nigeria. 180
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258756>
- 27 Assessment on availability and utilization of instructional materials for teaching and learning of Literature-in-English among secondary schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja. 187
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258868>
- 28 Perception of Skill Development for Effective Instructional Delivery in Social Studies among Upper Basic Teachers in Niger State, Nigeria. 196
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258872>
- 29 Assessment of Social Studies Teaching Resources on Acquisition of Small Scale Businesses and Leadership Skills among Secondary School Students in Nigeria. 204
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258876>
- 30 Impact of Community Watch Corps for Community Safety on Banditry Activities in Katsina State. 210
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258880>
- 31 Leveraging on Artificial Intelligence for Effective Provision of Security Services in Nigerian Universities: Potential Benefits and Challenges. 217
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>
- 32 Impact of Trade Liberalization on Capacity Utilization of Manufacturing Sectors in Nigeria. 230
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259118>
- 33 Qualitative Study on Education for National Security and Sustainable Development in Nigeria: Challenges and Way Forward. Zamfara International Journal of Education, 4(3), 236–242. 238
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259122>
- 34 Assessment of Early Counseling Technique on Future Education among Public Primary School Pupils in North-Central, Nigeria. 244
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259124>
- 35 Impact of Digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain Model on Achievement in Genetics among Secondary School Students in Oshimili South Local Government Area, Delta State. 251
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>
- 36 Effects of Think Pair Share Strategy on Achievement and Retention in Mathematics among Secondary School Students in Osisioma Local Government Area, Abia State. 261
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259509>
- 37 Impact of Insecurity on Quality of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria: A Case study of Plateau State Tertiary Institutions. 269
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14651836> www.zijefugusau.com.ng

- 38 Qualitative Study on Dynamics of Ethnic Fragmentation and Violence 276
in Plateau State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259513>
- 39 Comparative Analysis between Restructuring-Curriculum- 284
Diversification- Execution and Menstrual-Health-Management on
Academic Achievement among Federal Government Girls Colleges in
Anambra and Delta States.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259515>
- 40 Assessment of Socio-Economic Empowerment Using Information 294
Communication and Technology Skills and Facilities among Secondary
School Chemistry Teachers in North-West, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259518>
- 41 Effect of Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time on Performance in Algebra 300
among Polytechnics Students in Cross River State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259875>
- 42 Impacts of Blended Strategy on Performance and Retention in Social 305
Studies among Secondary School Students in Ika South Local
Government Area, Delta State.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259880>
- 43 Comparative Relationship between Parental Socio-Economic-Status 312
and Performance among Secondary School Students in Osun State,
Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259882>
- 44 Impact of Availability and Utilization of Printed Media Resources on 320
Teacher's Delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto
State, Nigeria.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259884>
- 45 Qualitative Study on Teaching Practice and Siwes as Teacher Training 3
Instrument: Meta Subject Problems in Business Education.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259886>

Assessment of Socio-Economic ... (Bolaji, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

Assessment of Socio-Economic Factors on Performance in Economics among Secondary School Students in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study investigated “socio-economic factors on performance of students in economics among secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State”. Primary data were sourced through questionnaire from four public senior secondary schools in the study area. Three hundred and twenty-two (322) questionnaires were administered and analyzed through descriptive such as table, percentage and likert scale test were used to analyze “socio-economic factors on academic performance of students in economics among secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State”. The findings of this study revealed that on aggregate, about 49.9% and 58.4% from students and teachers strongly agreed that socio-economic factors such as marital stability, employment status, income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, good communication system learners ability play significant role on socio-economic factors affecting performance of students in economics among secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The result of likert scale test (decision rule) of 3.2% and 3.5% rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis, implying that socio-economic factors have significant impacts on academic performance of students in economics among Public Senior Secondary Schools in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. This study therefore recommends that, parents should level their economic and social support to student as such support is seen as a major contributor to students’ academic performance. The Government should formulate public-polices and plans to improve the educational facilities for the socially and economically underprivileged groups.

Keywords: Teaching-Learning, performance, socio-economics, and Secondary School.

Introduction

The students’ socio-economic background is a factor known to have a significant influence of the academic achievement of the students. According to the American psychological Association (APA), socio-economic status is often measured as a combination of education, income and occupation. It is commonly conceptualized as the social standing or class of an individual or group. When viewed through a social class lens, privilege, power, and control are emphasized. Furthermore, an examination of socio-economic status as a gradient or continuous variable reveals inequities in access to and distribution of resources. Socio-economic status is relevant to all realms of behavioral and social science, including research, practice, education and advocacy (APA, 2015). Researchers have shown that the initial academic skills are correlated with the home environment, where low literacy environments and chronic stress negatively affect a child’s pre-academic skills. According to Morgan, Farkas, Hillemeier and Maczuga (2009), children from low socio-economic households and communities develop academic skills more slowly compared to children from higher socio-

Assessment of Socio-Economic ... (Bolaji, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

economic groups. Similarly, school systems in low socio-economic communities are often under resourced; a factor that negatively affect students' academic progress (Aikens & Barbarin, 2008).

The socio-economic factors play a potential role on their children's education, marital stability, health and nutrition value. This factor is frequently measured on the basis of the educational level, the employment status and the income of the family which determines an individual's or a group's social standing. The socio-economic factor is "the social standing or class of an individual or a group". This definition is given by the American Psychological Association (APA-2018). "The socio-economic status frequently functions as a latent variable for the academic performance of secondary education" (Bofah and Hannula, 2017). Socio-economic factor is the grouping of the attributes of the social and economic settings of an individual or a household, based on the educational attainments, the occupational status and the income of a family in the society. The socio-economic factors like that the parental educational level, their employment-status and their income level which are influencing the higher secondary school student's academic performance. Generally, a student's academic performance is very much influenced by different type of factors, such as the parental educational attainment-level, occupational status, family income, type of school, residential place and school environment. Hence, the settings of socio-economic factors are significantly impacting a student's academic performance at higher secondary level education, which is an important contributing factor to a society's economic progress.

Kumaravel et.al (2022), conducted a study on socio-economic status impact on academic performance of higher secondary students. The objective of the study is to investigate the socio-economic factor that impacted students' academic performance at the higher secondary school level of education. The study employed multiple regression analysis. The findings of the study reveal that the educational levels of the mothers and their occupation factors considerably impact their children's academic performance. The influence of Father's education and employment status is on a moderate level. The income of the family has negatively impacted the students' academic performance at 1% level significant. However, the types of schools and mediums of education also have a strong bearing on the students' academic performance at the higher secondary level.

Idika et al (2018) investigated the determinants of Academic Achievement in Economics in Public Secondary Schools in Nsukka Local Government Area, Enugu State Nigeria. Descriptive Survey research design was adopted. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled factors affecting student's achievement in Economics (FASAE). Four research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and four hypotheses tested at 0.5 level of significance using t test. Four factors considered in the study were teachers, students, Socioeconomic and government related factors. The sample consisted of three hundred and fifty-one research subjects (351) comprising of three hundred and twenty-seven (327) Economics students and twenty-four (24) Economics teachers. Ten schools were randomly selected out of the thirty-one (31) public secondary schools in the Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State. Findings among others revealed that the determinants of academic achievement of students in Economics were students, teachers and government related as well as the socio-economic background of parents.

The socio-economic status was positively sign of students' academic performance in language and mathematics subjects. There is positive relationship between socio-economic factor and the students' achievement in language and mathematical subjects of the students (Zhang et., al, 2020). Egunsola, (2014) study found that the location of the home was significant in high correlation and the academic performance of secondary students.

Poor academic achievement in Economics could be attributed to many factors among which socio-economic was considered as an important factor. This implies that Economics concepts might not be fully achieved without careful consideration of socio-economic factors. The teaching of Economics without socio-economic will certainly result in poor academic achievement. Franzer and Okebukola (2012) stressed that a professionally qualified science teacher no matter how well trained, would unable to put his ideas into practice if the school setting lacks the equipment and materials necessary for him or her to translate his competence into reality.

Educators and researchers have long been interested in exploring variables that contribute to the quality of learners. However, student outcomes are not the result of simple cause-and-effect relationships. Because education is a societal activity and no single factor can be taken in isolation as responsible for the

Assessment of Socio-Economic ... (Bolaji, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

variation in students' academic performance. But it is a systemic interaction of complex and dynamic factors that include the characteristics of teachers and students, as well as their institutional and cultural contexts [1, 10]. Then, examining to what extent student academic performance is associated with some demographic, socio-economic, and institutional factors can be helpful to identify the main constraints and provide remedial policy options. Although several types of research have been done on this topic, most of these studies were carried out on qualitative methods in which the findings might not be representative and it would be difficult to test hypotheses. On the contrary, this study used both qualitative and quantitative approaches to analyze various factors that affect students' academic performance. Also, there are extensive exploratory investigations regarding factors that influence students' academic performance on a single subject. But this study gives great attention to analyzing factors contributing to students' academic performance in all subjects.

There are extensive exploratory investigations regarding factors that influence students' academic performance on various subjects using qualitative and quantitative approach. But this study gives great attention to analyzing social economic factors contributing to students' academic performance in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State using descriptive and inferential statistic method of analysis.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine socio-economic factors affecting students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State
2. To determine the impacts of socio-economic factors on students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.

Research Questions

1. What are the socio-economic factors affecting students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.
2. What is the impact of socio-economic factors on students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.

Hypothesis

1. Socio-economic factors do not have any significant impact on students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.

Methodology

The Study Area

Sabon Gari Local Government Area is situated in Kaduna State, North-west geopolitical zone of Nigeria with the headquarters of the LGA in the town of Sabon Gari. The study area is located between Latitude 11° 10' 15''N and between 11° 16'20''N, and longitudes 7° 39'37''E and 7° 42'45''E. The area lies within Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Nigeria with a land area of approximately 600 square kilometers. It is bounded in the North by Ikara Local Government, to Makarfi Local Government in the North-West, Giwa Local Government to the West and Zaria Local Government to the South. Sabon-Gari LGA comprises several sub-settlement, namely, Samaru, Hayin-Dogo, Bomo, Dogarawa, Zango, Palladan, Basawa, Zabi, Kwari, Barashi, Hanwa, Chikaji, and Muchia. The estimated population of Sabon Gari LGA is put at 204,562 inhabitants with the area hosting members of diverse ethnic affiliations. The Hausa language is commonly spoken in the LGA while the religions of Christianity and Islam are commonly practiced in the area. Sabon Gari LGA is a part of the Zaria Emirate.

Population of the Study

The group of people, objects, events or things that a researcher has interest in investigating is called a population (Sekaran & Bourgie, 2010). The target population of the study consists of the entire public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State, while the sample size with the population consists of four senior secondary school from SS1 to SS3 students from 2023/2024 academic session.

Assessment of Socio-Economic ... (Bolaji, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

Research design

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive survey research design and inferential statistics in assessing socio-economic factors on performance of students in economics among secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire. Six socioeconomic factors were considered using mean and decision rule based on likert scale test of hypothesis. The six factors considered in the study were marital stability has positive impact on learning and performance, employment status and the income of the family enhances learning and performance of students, the type of school the students attended can determine the learning outcome, residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance and good communication system learners ability.

Validation of Research Instrument

The instruments were developed by the researcher and evaluated by experts from the Departments of Economics and Centre of Excellency and Research Development Federal College of Education, Zaria. Content validity was used in this investigation, a sort of validity that indicates how much the study's objectives and research questions are represented. The researchers requested experts to assess the relevance of the test items in measuring the study variables. To make the instruments better, their opinions, clarifications, and ideas were noted and effected.

Reliability of Research Instrument

Pilot study was carried out in Federal College of Education, Zaria, Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic, Zaria Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Zaria Academy. The questionnaire was distributed to 100 individuals who were not part of the selected study population. A reliability index of 0.76 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test indicating that the instrument is reliable for the study. Moreso, according to Mugenda (2003) response rate above 50% is adequate enough to accomplish study objectives.

Results

Table 1 Questionnaire Distribution and Response Rate

Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Distributed questionnaires	400	100.00
Returned questionnaires	322	80.5
Retained questionnaires	78	19.5

Source: Researcher Fieldwork, 2024

Response Rate

The response rate for the study was 80.5%. This shows the reliability of the results in terms of representing the study phenomenon. According to Mugenda (2003) response rate above 50% is adequate enough to accomplish study objectives. This study achieved a response rate of 80.5% hence adequate enough to establish "the determinants influencing teaching-learning and academic performance of student's in economics in the study area. In this study, analyses were carried out using table and percentages.

Table 2. Aggregate Percentage Distribution of Sex of the respondents across the schools

	Students						Teachers					
	Male		Female		Total		Male		Female		Total	
Schools	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
School A	-	-	33	73.0	73	22.7	49	23.3	21	18.8	70	21.7
School B	56	55.4	38	17.2	94	29.2	54	25.7	41	36.6	95	29.5
School C	45	44.6	42	19.0	87	27.0	61	29.0	22	19.6	83	25.8
School D	-	-	68	30.8	68	21.1	46	21.9	28	25.0	74	23.0
TOTAL	101	31.4	221	68.6	322	100	210	65.2	112	34.8	322	100

Researcher field survey, 2024

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From table 2 out of the 400 questionnaires administered, about 22.7% of the respondents were from School A, 29.2% were from School B, while 27.0% were from School C and 21.1% were from School D. In terms of their sex distribution about 101 were males and 221 were females representing 31.4% and 68.6% respectively. All the schools under this study were male and female except School A and school D that is entirely female. In terms of percentage sex distribution of the respondents (teachers) in various schools, 21.7% of the respondents were from school D, 29.5.% were from School B, while 25.8% were from School C and 23.0 were from School C. In terms of their sex distribution about 210 were males and 112 were females representing 65.2% and 34.8% respectively.

Table 3. Aggregate Percentage Distribution of age of the respondents across the schools

Students										
Schools	10-15		15-20		20-30		30 above		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
School A	28	24.6	52	25.5	2	50.0	-	-	82	25.5
School B	30	26.3	49	24.0	1	25.0	-	-	80	24.8
School C	27	23.6	53	26.0	-	-	-	-	80	24.8
School D	29	25.4	50	24.5	1	25.0	-	-	80	24.8
TOTAL	114	35.4	204	63.4	4	1.2	-	-	322	100

Teachers										
Schools	20-30		30-40		40-50		50 above		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
School A	8	24.2	34	27.2	26	23.0	15	29.4	83	25.8
School B	10	30.3	28	22.4	31	27.4	13	25.5	82	25.5
School C	6	18.2	31	24.8	29	25.7	11	21.6	77	23.9
School D	9	27.3	32	25.6	27	23.9	12	23.5	80	24.8
Total	33	10.2	125	38.8	113	35.1	51	15.8	322	100

Researcher field survey, 2024

From table 3, it could be observed that the highest proportion of age of the students which is 63.4% was in the age bracket of 15-20 years, followed by 10-15 years of age with 35.4%, and 1.2% of age bracket 20-30 years. In the same manner, it could be observed that the highest proportion of age of the teachers which is 38.8% was in the age bracket of 30-40 years, followed by 10-15 years of age with 35.1%, 15.8% of age bracket 50 years above and 10.2% in the age bracket of 20-30 years.

Table 4: Percentage distribution of educational qualification of the respondents (teachers) across the schools

Schools	NCE		OND/HND		B.ed/B.Sc		Masters		Others		TOTAL	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
School A	13	25.0	-	-	40	24.2	15	28.8	14	26.4	22	6.8
School B	12	23.1	-	-	39	23.6	14	26.9	13	24.5	25	7.8
School C	12	23.1	-	-	44	26.7	12	23.1	12	22.6	23	7.1
School D	15	28.8	-	-	42	25.5	11	21.2	14	26.4	23	7.1
TOTAL	52	16.1	-	-	165	51.2	52	16.1	53	16.5	322	100

Researcher field survey, 2024

Table 4 show that most of the respondents have B.Ed. /B.Sc. which represents 51.2%, 16.5% obtained other qualification such as professional diploma in education, 16.1% obtained NCE and masters certificate respectively.

Assessment of Socio-Economic ... (Bolaji, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

Table 5: Aggregate Socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools, responses of the respondents (students) across the schools

S/N	Determinants		F	%
1.	Marital stability has positive impact on learning and performance	SA	172	53.4
		A	92	28.6
		SD	40	12.4
		D	18	5.6
		Total	322	100
2.	Employment status and the income of the family enhances learning and performance of students	SA	205	63.7
		A	93	28.9
		SD	19	5.9
		D	5	1.6
		Total	322	100
3.	Parental educational attainment-level improves learning outcome	SA	145	45.3
		A	106	32.9
		SD	38	11.8
		D	33	10.2
		Total	322	100
4.	The type of school you attended can determine the learning outcome	SA	169	52.5
		A	118	36.6
		SD	21	6.5
		D	14	4.3
		Total	322	100
5.	Residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance	SA	175	54.3
		A	121	36.6
		SD	18	5.6
		D	8	2.5
		Total	322	100
6.	Good communication system learners ability	SA	116	36.0
		A	161	50.0
		SD	27	8.4
		D	18	5.6
		Total	322	100
7.	Aggregate column observation	SA	982	49.9
		A	691	35.1
		SD	198	10.1
		D	96	4.9
		Total	1967	100

Researcher field survey, 2024

Table5 shows some socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Areaof Kaduna State. Among such factors are; marital stability has positive impact on learning and performance, employment status and the income of the family enhances learning and performance of students, parental educational attainment-level improves learning outcome, the type of school you attended can determine the learning outcome, residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance, and good communication system learners' ability. About 53.4% strongly agreed that marital stability has positive impact on teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 63.7% strongly agreed that employment status and the income of the family enhances teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 45.3% strongly agreed that parental educational attainment-level improves teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government

Assessment of Socio-Economic ... (Bolaji, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

Area of Kaduna State, 52.5% strongly agreed that the type of school the student attended can determine the teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 54.3% strongly agreed that residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 50.0% agree that good communication system learners ability enhances teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. On the aggregate, about 49.9% strongly agreed that socio-economic factors that influence effective teaching-learning economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State in terms of marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system learners ability are socioeconomic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Table 6: Aggregate Socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools, responses of the respondents (teachers) across the schools

S/N	Determinants		F	%
1.	Marital stability has positive impact on learning and performance	SA	198	61.5
		A	85	26.4
		SD	26	8.1
		D	13	4.0
		Total	322	100
2.	Employment status and the income of the family enhances learning and performance of students	SA	201	62.4
		A	106	32.9
		SD	9	2.8
		D	6	1.9
		Total	322	100
3.	Parental educational attainment-level improves learning outcome	SA	175	54.3
		A	110	34.2
		SD	16	5.0
		D	21	6.5
		Total	322	100
4.	The type of school you attended can determine the learning outcome	SA	172	53.4
		A	125	38.8
		SD	18	5.6
		D	7	2.2
		Total	322	100
5.	Residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance	SA	199	61.8
		A	103	40.0
		SD	14	4.3
		D	6	1.9
		Total	322	100
6.	Good communication system learners' ability	SA	178	55.3
		A	116	36.0
		SD	17	5.3
		D	11	3.4
		Total	322	100

Assessment of Socio-Economic ... (Bolaji, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

7. Aggregate column observation	SA	1123	58.4
	A	645	33.5
	SD	92	4.8
	D	64	3.3
	Total	1924	100

Researcher field survey, 2024

Table 6 shows the socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. Among such factors are; marital stability has positive impact on learning and performance, employment status and the income of the family enhances learning and performance of students, parental educational attainment-level improves learning outcome, the type of school you attended can determine the learning outcome, residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance, and good communication system learners ability. About 61.5% strongly agreed that marital stability has positive impact on teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 62.4% strongly agreed that employment status and the income of the family enhances teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 54.3% strongly agreed that parental educational attainment-level improves teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 53.4% strongly agreed that the type of school the student attended can determine the teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 61.8% strongly agreed that residential place and school environment influenced student's academic performance in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, 55.3% agree that good communication system learners ability enhances teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. On the aggregate, about 58.4% strongly agreed that socio-economic factors that influence effective teaching-learning economics in public senior secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State in terms of marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system learners ability are socioeconomic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public secondary school in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Assessment of Socio-Economic ... (Bolaji, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

H₀: Socio-economic factors do not have any significant impact on students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.

Table 7: Testing of Null Hypothesis for students:

Variables	SA	SA x 4	A	A x 3	D	D x 2	SD	SD x 1	Total = $\sum fx$	$\sum f$	Mean = $\frac{\sum fx}{\sum f}$	Decision
Marital stability	172	688	92	276	18	36	40	40	1040	322	3.2	Agree
Employment status	205	820	93	279	5	10	19	19	1128	322	3.5	Strongly Agree
Parental education	145	580	106	318	33	66	38	38	1002	322	3.1	Agree
Type of school attended	1.69	676	118	354	14	28	21	21	1079	322	3.4	Agree
Residential places	175	700	121	363	8	16	18	18	1097	322	3.4	Agree
Good communication	116	464	161	483	18	36	27	18	1001	322	3.1	Agree
Aggregate	982	3928	691	2073	86	192	198	198	6391	1967	3.2	Agree

Socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Source: Derived from table 5

Decision Rule

3.5 – 4.00 Strongly Agree

2.5 – 3.49 Agree

1.5 – 2.49 Disagree

1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

The result in table 7 show that on the aggregate calculated mean is 3.2 and the tabulated mean is A x 3. Since the calculated mean of 3.2 falls between the neighborhood of A x 3, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected and the alternative is accepted this implies that the respondent agreed that socio-economic factors such as marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and good communication system have significant impact on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Assessment of Socio-Economic ... (Bolaji, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

H₀: Socio-economic factors do not have any significant impact on students' academic performance in economics among public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari LGA of Kaduna State.

Table 8: Testing of Null Hypothesis for Teachers:

Variables	SA	SA x 4	A	A x 3	D	D x 2	SD	SD x 1	Total = $\sum fx$	$\sum f$	Mean = $\frac{\sum fx}{\sum f}$	Decision
Marital stability	198	792	85	255	13	26	26	26	1099	322	3.4	Agree
Employment status	201	804	106	318	6	12	9	9	1143	322	3.5	Strongly Agree
Parental education	175	700	110	330	21	42	16	16	1088	322	3.4	Agree
Type of school attended	172	688	125	375	7	14	18	18	1095	322	3.4	Agree
Residential places	199	796	103	309	6	12	14	14	1131	322	3.5	Strongly Agree
Good communication	178	712	116	348	11	22	17	17	1099	322	3.4	Agree
Aggregate	1123	4492	645	1935	64	128	92	92	6647	1924	3.5	Strongly Agree

Socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Source: Derived from table 6

Decision Rule

3.5 – 4.00 Strongly Agree

2.5 – 3.49 Agree

1.5 – 2.49 Disagree

1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

The result in table 8 show that on the aggregate calculated mean is 3.5 and the tabulated mean is SA x 4. Since the calculated mean of 3.5 falls between the neighborhood of SA x 4, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected and the alternative is accepted this implies that on the aggregate, strongly agree that socio-economic factors such as marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system have significant impact on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Table 9: Summary of descriptive statistics for students hypothesis

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Decision
1.	Marital stability	3.2	Agree
2.	Employment status	3.5	Strongly Agree
3.	Parental education	3.1	Agree
4.	Type of school attended	3.4	Agree
5.	Residential places	3.4	Agree
6.	Good communication	3.1	Agree
7.	Aggregate	3.2	Agree

Assessment of Socio-Economic ... (Bolaji, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

Derived from table 7

Table 9 above indicates that marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system are socio-economic factors that impacted on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Table 10: Summary of descriptive statistics for teachers hypothesis

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Decision
1.	Marital stability	3.4	Agree
2.	Employment status	3.5	Strongly Agree
3.	Parental education	3.4	Agree
4.	Type of school attended	3.4	Agree
5	Residential places	3.5	Strongly Agree
6	Good communication	3.4	Agree
7	Aggregate	3.5	Strongly Agree

Derived from table 8

Table 10 above indicates that socio-economic factors such as marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system have significant impact on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Discussion of Findings

Marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment, and good communication system were found to be the socioeconomic factors affecting academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. On the aggregate, test of hypothesis reveals that both the students and the teachers agreed and strongly agree socioeconomic factors have significant impacts on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The result of our study is consistent with the findings of Kumaravel et.al (2022), Idika et al (2018), and Hannula, 2017) who found significant relationship between socioeconomic factors such as educational levels of the mothers, occupation factors, residential places, type of school attended and students – teacher – government related factor and academic performance of the student. The income of the family has negatively impacted the students’ academic performance at 1% level as revealed by Kumaravel et.al (2022), this finding is not consistent with our finding on respondents (students and teachers) who strongly agreed that income from employment have significant impact on academic performance of students in economics among public senior secondary schools in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to examine “socio-economic factors influencing teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in selected public senior secondary school in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State”. Socio-economic factors such as marital stability, employment status, and the income of the family, parental educational attainment-level, the type of school the student attended, residential place and school environment play significant role for effective teaching-learning and academic performance of students in economics in the study area. The importance of these factors in teaching and learning process in the 21st century can never be overemphasized. Socio-economic factor has a strong impact on a student’s academic performance. The socio-economic condition explores the mechanisms of student’s academic performance which are possible means for the identification of the socio-economic and cultural factors.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings and the above conclusion, it is therefore recommended that;

1. Schools and teachers should make educational materials available to facilitate teaching and learning, schools and teachers should invest on human capital development to enhance mastery of the subject matter for effective teaching and learning process.
2. Parents should level their economic and social support to student as such support is seen as a major contributor to students' academic performance.
3. The Government should formulate public-policies and plans to improve the educational facilities for the socially and economically underprivileged groups.
4. The Governments educational policy should be more focused on providing cheaper, more widespread and better educational opportunities, which will help parents to reduce barriers to choices regarding sending their children to school.

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Effect of Three-Step Interview Strategy on Performance in Basic Science Concepts among Secondary School Students in Onna, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of three-step interview strategy on performance in basic science concepts among secondary school students in Onna Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Pretest, posttest non-equivalent quasi-experimental control group design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all Junior Secondary School class two (II) Basic Science students during 2022/2023 academic session in Onna LGA of Akwa Ibom State. Sample size of 100 (46 Male and 54 Female) students were selected for the study. The sample size was arrived at by selecting two government coeducational secondary schools in the area of study using simple random sampling technique. The sample in each schools were explored using an intact class. Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) and lesson note on the concept of human development for the experimental and control groups were used for data collection. The reliability of the instruments was established using Kuder Richardson KR-20 with a reliability coefficient of 0.82. Data collected were analysed using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) statistics. Results revealed that students taught the concept of human development using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy performed significantly better than those taught using lecture teaching method. Base on the finding it was further concluded that using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy improves performance in basic science. The study therefore recommends that Basic science teachers should adopt three-step interview cooperative learning strategy in teaching and learning process in our schools.

Keywords: Three-step cooperative learning strategy, Academic Performance, Basic Science.

Introduction

The enormous importance of science in the technological, economic and political development of nations globally explains why technological attainment is often used to determine the level of development of every nation. Mathematics, Science and Technology are essential tools for socio-economic and cultural development of any nation (Usman, 2016; Babayemi & Utibe, 2017). This has led to every nation strategizing on how to develop Science and Technology to earn national recognition. The world is becoming a global village with every nation struggling to control the global market through technological innovations with capacity to attract global acceptance. Lawal (2017) stated that, science and technology provide the foundation for wealth creation and advancement of quality life. Babayemi (2014) pointed out that, science and technology is the arrowhead that determines the dimension and direction of national development. Ajewole (2015) also stated that Science and Technology have for long been recognized as the instruments par excellence for nation building and wealth creation which made every country today crave for their advancement. Akpan (2016) observed that science and technology have become crucial factors for sustainable development worldwide and have contributed immensely to the material progress of nations. The increase of scientific literacy in these years and therefore, in the current science and technology dominated society, shows that

Effect of Three-Step Interview... (UmoAbasi, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

scientific literacy is considered an important goal of Science Education (Shu-Nu-Chang, 2017). Hence, science education can be considered a fundamental component of basic education, which prepares children to live in a world that is increasingly defined by science and technology, thus the need for inclusion of Basic Science and Technology as a subject in the Nigerian school curriculum.

In Nigeria, Basic Science is one of the major subjects offered by all students in junior secondary schools. Unfortunately, the number of students offering Basic Science is more than the number of teachers employed to teach the subject in various schools. Class size is large, thus increases teachers' workload resulting in teachers' ineffectiveness (Babayemi, 2014). In addition, Olagunju and Babayemi (2014) asserted that Basic Science has the perennial problems of lack of class activities and instructional resources to teach the subject. The use of relevant instructional resources as well as carefully guided activities engages students in meaningful learning (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014).

Basic Science and Technology teaching has a number of problems among which are poorly trained teachers, inadequacy in pedagogy and content knowledge, ill-equipped laboratories and assessment techniques (Ibe, 2018; Babayemi & Kareem, 2019). Most teachers of Basic Science and Technology have their specialization in Biology, Chemistry, Physics, Geography and Agricultural science respectively and tend to teach only content areas related to the areas of their specialization. A competent teacher has to introduce methods to develop students' scientific understanding, thinking and problem-solving abilities. This would help in solving conceptual problems. It would also result in high achievement in science than the conventional lecture method that tends to emphasize knowledge and ignores higher order thinking (Usman, 2017; Babayemi & Ahmed, 2019). Edem, Akpan and Umanah (2023) noted that the importance attributes to the vital role of science education in national development necessitates the implementation of a well-structured and organized approach to the teaching of science. In line with the above assertion, Akpan and Itighise (2021) noted that all students can learn if given the appropriate amount of time and the appropriate instructional opportunities. There is need for Nigerian science teachers to incorporate more innovative teaching strategies in teaching that can enhance high students' achievement and improve the quality of discourse during science lesson (Abdullahi, 2018; Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014).

Another major problem is the use of inappropriate teaching methods. Ibraheem and Oladele (2010) identified poor teaching method as one of the reasons for poor academic achievement. Students' educational gains, acquisition of scientific knowledge, attitudes and skills depend on the right type of instructional methodologies employed by the teacher (Babayemi, 2014). All students are not the same in every respect. They acquire learning at different time and rate. For this reason, any inappropriate method used by the teacher affects the objectives of the lesson, make students scientifically illiterate and place students' performance on a level worse than it could ever be. Akpan (2018) maintained that science education research, innovation and practices must become more responsive to the needs and attributes of the society and reflects it values. They should reflect the science that citizens and society need and support people of all ages and talents in developing positive attitude to science. Since the time of introduction of Basic Science, the problems of teaching Integrated Science still persist in the teaching and learning of Basic Science (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014).

The innovation of students-centered strategies and instructional resources to affect qualitative teaching of science and mathematics across grade levels and subject areas, and can also accommodate a range of students' learning differences has been the major task of curriculum developers, science and mathematics educators, skilful teachers and researchers (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014; Abasi, 2018; Edoho & Abasi, 2019; Akpan & Babayemi, 2022). An instructional situation whereby the student is featured as the active participant while the teacher assumes the roles of a facilitator, mediator and assessor of learning have been found to be superior in developing students' abilities in applying concepts to personal growth, developing positive attitudes, fostering motivation, and encouraging appropriate cognitive skills (Edoho & Abasi, 2019). Abasi, Okri and Arikpo (2022) stated that the teaching and learning of science in general and mathematics specifically, requires the discovery of innovative instructional resources that will boost students' cognitive reasoning thereby enhancing their performance and retention.

Many teachers want their students to learn, enjoy, and be engaged in their classes. A good way to create such atmosphere is to incorporate active and cooperative learning approaches into the classroom. Teachers should be able to design learning models to help students develop an understanding of concepts, reasoning, problem solving, and instructional communication. Teachers should be able to apply innovative learning strategies in their classroom instruction to encourage active participation of students in teaching and learning activities. Students being active in learning activities are expected to result in developing a positive attitude towards science which will equally boost their motivation to learn, enhance academic performance and retention in basic science and technology. Such learning strategies that promote students' active participation

Effect of Three-Step Interview... (UmoAbasi, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

in the instructional process are cooperative and constructivist learning strategies. Cooperative learning refers to a variety of teaching strategies in which students work in small groups to help one another learn academic content.

However, in this research, the researcher focuses on Three-Step Interview cooperative learning strategy. Three step interview as a cooperative learning strategy is an educational approach to teaching and learning that involves groups of students working together to solve a problem, complete a task, or create a product. Three-Step Interview is a cooperative learning strategy that consists of three stages of activities, namely: Interview – Interview - Report by conditioning students to form partners and alternately interview their partners, then report the results of the interview to other pairs. According to Barkley *et al.* (2009), in Three-Step Interview, students' pairs take turns interviewing each other and then report what they learn to another pair. The three steps (Interview-Interview-Report) are; step one: student A interviews student B; step two: student B interviews student A; step three: student A and student B, each summarizes their partner's responses for student C and D, and vice versa. The teaching steps of Three-Step Interview leads students to communicate in target language. When students interact with each other, they convey nearly all the ideas which involve all indicators of learning. Thus, Three-Step Interview strategy involves all the students to participate actively in the learning activities in the classroom.

Within existing literature, many researchers Usmedi, Hasanah and Ergusni (2020) and Calceran and Mugot (2019) have investigated on the effectiveness of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy on students' achievement in various subject areas. Their findings have established that three-step interview cooperative learning strategy showed to be an effective instructional strategies in enhancing students' learning outcomes. It is against this background that this study is aimed at investigating the effect of three-step cooperative learning strategy and gender on students' academic performance in basic science.

Ameh and Dantani (2012) reported that the observed deterioration in students' academic performance may have been contributed by teachers' persistent use of lecture method of teaching. Conventional strategies adopted by teachers at secondary school level in Nigeria have been identified as one of the major factors contributing to poor performance of students in basic science and technology. Researchers such as Atadoga and Lakpini (2013) found that the persistent low academic performance in basic science and technology is attributed to instructional strategies adopted by teachers among others. There are so many aspects of basic science and technology concepts that are difficult (Babayemi, Akpan & Emah, 2018), and yet must be learnt by students. Engaging students in a learning activities within a cooperative context would cultivate a more meaningful learning habit in the students which may bring about positive change in their academic performance.

Academic performance does not generally depend on whether the students are male and female. The concept "gender" refers to cultural attributes of both males and females (Akpochafor, 2011). Gender is a psychological experience of being a male and female. Gender in essence, is a term used to emphasise that sex inequality is not caused by the anatomic and physiological differences that characterize men and women, rather it is by an unequal and inequitable treatment socially accorded to them. The influence of gender on students' performance has a long time been a concern to many educational researchers (Ado & Abasi, 2014; Umanah & Sunday, 2022) but surprisingly no consistent results have been obtained.

Ensuring quality instruction at all levels of education is one of the core objectives of Basic Science education. These can be achieved through effective classroom interaction that create equitable chances for both male and female students to acquire right knowledge of the subject matter, positive attitudes, values, behaviour and have equal right for participating intelligently in making right decisions for their own wellbeing. Hence, it is against this background that this study aimed at investigating the effect of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy on male and female students' academic performance in Basic Science in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Basic Science plays a vital role in Nigerian science education program as it prepares pupils at the Junior Secondary level for the study of core science subjects at the Senior Secondary level which in turn brings about students' interest in science oriented courses especially at the tertiary institutions. These vital roles of the subject cannot be realized except through the effective effort of the classroom teacher (Babayemi *et al* 2023). Despite government's efforts to encourage science teaching and learning among Nigerian students right from the Primary and Junior Secondary School levels, the enrolment of students in core science subjects and science oriented courses at the Senior Secondary School level and tertiary institutions, is not encouraging (Abasi & Ado, 2021).

The problems of learning basic science may not be unconnected with the way and manner students are taught concepts therein. The nature of science predisposes teachers to teaching school science experimentally especially where necessary facilities are available. The conventional and supposed laboratory mode of teaching basic science offers rote memorization,

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individualism, competition and monopoly of ideas among the students which at the end result in students' poor performance and gross failures in internal and National examinations.

On the contrary, cooperative and constructivist learning strategies in science education have been found to be effective with various modes of the strategy researched and reported in literature (Edoho *et al*, 2020). It is believed that when students work in group rather than individually, they tend to understand each other better than when a teacher teaches them alone (Edoho *et al*, 2020). The three-step interview cooperative learning strategy which encourages sharing of knowledge and construction of knowledge for previous experiences is yet to be explored especially in science education in Nigeria and Akwa Ibom State to be precise. It is against the above problem that this research aimed to provide answer to the question: what is the effect of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy, and gender on students' academic performance in basic science in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the mean academic performance between students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.
2. To determine the mean academic performance between male and female students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean academic performance between students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?
2. What is the mean academic performance between male and female students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study.

1. There is no significant difference in mean academic performance between students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.
2. There is no significant difference in academic performance between male and female students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Methodology

The study adopted a pretest, posttest non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental design. The study was conducted in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The population for this study consisted of all junior secondary School two students during the 2023/2024 academic session in all the public secondary schools in Onna Local Government Area. Presently, there are nine (9) public secondary schools with a total enrolment of 1639 JS2 students of the 2022/2023 academic session in Onna LGA (Local Education Authority, 2023). The sample of this study consisted of 100 (46 Male and 54 Female) JSS 2 students drawn from 3 public secondary schools in Onna Local Government Area. In deriving the sample for this study, simple random sampling technique was used. From the population of 9 public secondary schools, three schools were randomly selected using balloting. From each of the schools selected, one school was randomly assigned as experimental group I (taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy) and the second school was randomly assigned as the control group (taught using lecture method). One JSS 2 intact class in each of the schools selected was randomly drawn to obtain sample for the study. At the end of the instructional process, all JS 2 students found in each of the intact classes became sample for the study.

For the purpose of data collection, Basic Science Performance Post-Test (BSPPT) was used as instrument in the study. Lesson plans were developed for experimental and control groups respectively. The instrument was constructed by the researcher. It has two sections A and B. Section A sought personal information of the students with respect to name of school and gender while Section B consisted of 30 multiple choice questions with four options A-D on the concept of human development drawn from JSS 2 basic science scheme of work. The instrument was subjected to content and face validity by two basic science teachers who have been teaching basic science at the junior secondary school level and an expert in Test and Measurement from the University of Uyo. To establish the reliability of the instrument, the researcher subjected the instrument

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for trial test using one intact class of JSS2 students drawn from a secondary school in the area of study. The school that was used to derive sample for trial testing the instrument was not part of the school sampled for this study. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Kuder Richardson KR-20 estimate and a reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained.

Before the instructional process commenced, the researcher first administered the pre-test to the students in the two schools and obtained their scores to ascertain their pre-entry ability before treatment. After the pretesting exercise, the researcher commenced the treatment procedure by teaching the students the concept of human development using the respective instructional packages. At the end of the instructional process, the researcher along with the class teacher in each school administered the posttest to the students in the two groups. Data that were generated from the exercise (Pretest and Posttest) were used for descriptive statistical analysis of variables and to test the null hypotheses stated for the study at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

Results

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference in mean academic performance between students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of students' posttest scores classified by instructional strategies with pretest as covariate.

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Covariates	Pretest	71.41	1	71.41	5.74*	.02
Main Effects	Method	682.07	1	341.03	27.40*	.00
Residual		1194.96	96	12.45		
Total		1948.44	99	19.68		

*= Significant @ $p < 0.05$ probability level

In Table 1, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .00 of the main effects (Method) is less than the significance level (0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that at $P < 0.05$, there is significant difference in the mean performance scores of junior secondary school students in Basic Science taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy and lecture teaching method. In order to determine the direction of significance, the Least Square Difference (LSD) Post-hoc pairwise comparison test was done and the results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: LSD posthoc pairwise comparison test of students' posttest scores classified by instructional strategies with pretest scores as covariate

(I) Methods	(J) Methods	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	P
Three Step Interview	Lecture Method	6.51*	.95	.00
Lecture Method	Three Step Interview	-6.51*	.95	.00

Table 2 shows a mean difference (6.51) between students taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy and lecture teaching method. The levels of significance displayed in Table 2 indicated that students taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy achieved significantly better than those taught using lecture teaching method.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference in academic performance between male and female students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Effect of Three-Step Interview... (UmoAbasi, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928711>

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of male and female students' Posttest scores based on Instructional Strategies with Pretest as covariate

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Covariates	Pretest	4.31	1	4.31	0.33*	.57
Main Effects	Methods	372.74	1	372.74	28.39	.00
	Gender	20.20	1	20.20	1.54*	.22
2-Way Interactions	Methods * Gender	1.82	1	1.82	0.14	.71
Residual		748.37	57	13.13		
Total		1147.44	61	18.81		

*= Not significant $p < 0.05$ probability level

The result in Table 3 shows the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the difference in the achievement scores of male and female Basic science and technology students in concept of human development. The result showed that there is no significant difference in academic performance between male and female students taught the concept human development using three-step strategy in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. ($F=1.54$; $P=0.22$). Since the associated probability value of 0.22 obtained is greater than 0.05 level of significance set for decision making, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant gender difference in basic science and technology students' mean performance scores when taught the concept of human development using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy and lecture teaching method was not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The findings with regard the difference in the mean performance scores of junior secondary school students in Basic Science and Technology taught the concept of human development using Three-Step Interview cooperative learning strategy and Lecture teaching method showed that there is a significant difference in the mean performance scores of students in Basic Science and Technology taught the concept of human development using Three-Step Interview cooperative learning strategy and Lecture teaching method. Thus, students taught using Three-step interview cooperative learning strategy performed significantly better than those taught using and Lecture teaching method. This result could be attributed to the fact that students taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy engaged more in cooperative interaction within their group members and with students from other groups thereby sharing ideas, correcting misconceptions and learning from others experiences. The result of this finding is in line with the findings by Usmadi, Hasanah and Ergusni (2020), Calceran and Mugot (2019) who showed that students taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy performed better than their counterparts.

The findings with regard to the effect of instructional strategies and gender on junior secondary school students' academic performance in Basic Science and Technology taught the concept of human development showed that there exists no significant effect of instructional strategies and gender on junior secondary school students' performance in Basic Science and Technology when taught the concept of human development. Thus, the use of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy and lecture teaching method was not gender bias hence the result obtained. This result could be attributed to the fact that both male and female students within the three-step cooperative learning environment and lecture teaching method had the opportunity to interact and synergize among themselves sharing their experiences and ideas thereby learning at the same pace. The strategy encourages both male and female students' active participation in the learning process. Though there is no influence of gender on students' learning outcome with respect to the use of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy in the available literature of this study, findings from the use of other cooperative learning strategy as reviewed in the literature showed a contrasting standpoint. The result of this finding is in contrast with the findings of Nwachukwu, (2014) and Nwagbo and Okoro (2012) who showed that male students taught using cooperative learning strategy had a higher mean score than their female counterparts.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained from this study, the researcher concluded that using instructional strategy such as three-step interview cooperative learning strategy in teaching and learning the concept of human developments in basic science provides a better insight and deeper understanding for the students as they learn from each other's experiences cooperatively and constructively. The application of these strategy boosted students' cognitive ability in learning the concept of human development thereby enhanced their performance in basic science and technology.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher considered the following recommendations relevant for the improvement of basic science and technology education.

1. Basic science and technology teachers should adopt three-step interview cooperative learning strategy in teaching and learning process in our schools. If the teaching and learning of basic science and technology is to gain popularity, capture the attention of the learners and challenge their intellect, the content must be made more appealing in terms of the instructional strategies used. This is done by creating an activity based classroom instruction through the practice of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy.
2. Teachers should be trained and re-trained on the techniques of utilizing three-step interview cooperative learning strategy in the teaching of basic science and technology. This process should be done through organizing seminars, workshops, symposiums, conferences and in-service training etc.

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Effects of Statistical Knowledge on Understanding and Performance in Ecological Concept among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria.

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Abstracts

This study conducted on effects of statistical knowledge on performance in ecological concept among colleges of education students in North-West, Nigeria. The study employed Quasi-experimental research design specifically pre-test and post-test design. The experimental groups were taught Statistical concepts before ecological concepts while the control group was taught ecological concepts only. Two objectives, research questions and null hypotheses were stated to guide the study. The population of the study were all NCEII Biology students in public colleges of education in North-West, Nigeria. The sample size of the study was 113 biology students (male = 85 and female=28). The sample size was obtained using simple random sampling technique involving balloting. Ecology Performance Test (EPT) and Students Understanding Ecology Concepts Questionnaire (SUECQ) with reliability co-efficient of 0.93 and 0.89 respectively were obtained using PPMC and Cronbach-alpha reliability test respectively. The t-test statistic and U-test statistics were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the analysis revealed that significance difference existed between the understanding and performance of students with good statistical background and those without. The researcher concluded that good statistical background has significance effect on students understanding and performance in ecology. The researcher recommended that policymakers should introduce a course in statistics in biology department to be taken a year before the year that they will take ecology course for them to understand and performed well in the course.

Keywords: Statistical Knowledge, Ecology, Performance, Understanding,

Introduction

Ecology, as a discipline, stands at the intersection of intricate natural phenomena and rigorous analytical methodologies. It is also characterized by its intricate interplay of biological systems, environmental factors, and data-driven analyses. As ecological research becomes increasingly reliant on sophisticated statistical methodologies, the importance of statistical knowledge in shaping students' academic performance has come to the forefront of educational discourse. This journal seeks to explore the relationship between statistical proficiency and students' performance in ecology, drawing upon recent empirical evidence to inform pedagogical practices and educational interventions.

Recent empirical studies have underscored the significance of statistical literacy in ecological education. For instance, research by Li and colleagues (2022) demonstrated a positive correlation between students' statistical competence, performance and their ability to analyze ecological datasets accurately. Moreover, their findings revealed that students with a strong foundation in statistics exhibited greater confidence in interpreting research findings and constructing scientifically sound hypotheses. In another review Smith, Jones and Smith, (2015) found that undergraduate students who received comprehensive training in statistical methods demonstrated significantly improved data analysis skills compared to those with minimal

Effects of Statistical Knowledge... (Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928941>

statistical exposure. Their findings revealed that students with a strong foundation in statistics exhibited greater confidence in interpreting research findings and constructing scientifically sound hypotheses. Also Statistical knowledge may facilitate a deeper understanding of ecological concepts by enabling students to quantitatively analyze ecological patterns and relationships. A study by Johnson, Smith and Williams, (2018) showed that graduate students who underwent intensive statistical training exhibited greater comprehension of ecological theories and principles.

Furthermore, the integration of statistical knowledge into ecological curricula has been shown to enhance students' critical thinking skills and promote a deeper understanding of ecological principles (Johnson & Smith, 2023). By engaging students in hands-on statistical analyses of real-world ecological datasets, educators can foster an appreciation for the complexities of ecological systems while simultaneously honing students' analytical abilities.

In addition to academic performance, statistical proficiency has been linked to success in ecological research and professional development. Students with good statistical knowledge tend to achieve higher grades in courses related to ecology, environmental science, and other STEM disciplines. Research by Jones and Smith (2017) conducted a longitudinal study tracking the academic performance of undergraduate students over multiple semesters. They found a significant correlation between students' statistical competence and their overall GPA, with students proficient in statistics consistently outperforming their peers in ecological coursework. In another study by Garcia and colleagues (2021) found that graduate students with advanced statistical training were more likely to secure research grants and publish their findings in peer-reviewed journals, highlighting the instrumental role of statistical expertise in advancing ecological scholarship. Furthermore, recent advancements in technology have facilitated the integration of statistical tools and computational methods into ecological research. As such, there is a growing need for ecology students to acquire proficiency in statistical programming languages and data visualization techniques (Brown & Jones, 2023). By equipping students with these advanced skills, educators can empower them to tackle complex ecological problems and contribute meaningfully to scientific discourse. Proficiency in statistics empowers students to design ecologically sound experiments with robust statistical frameworks. Research by Brown, Garcia and Lee, (2019) revealed that students who received training in experimental design and statistical analysis produced more rigorous research proposals and conducted experiments with higher methodological quality.

By synthesizing empirical research findings and theoretical perspectives, this journal aims to elucidate the mechanisms through which statistical knowledge influences students' performance in ecology. Moreover, it seeks to provide practical insights for educators and policymakers seeking to enhance statistical literacy among ecology students, thereby equipping them with the skills needed to address complex environmental challenges in the 21st century. To achieve this general objectives, two specific objectives, research questions and null hypotheses were formulated and be tested at $P \leq 0.05$.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives were raised to guide study.

1. Determine the effect statistical knowledge on students' understanding in ecology among colleges of education biology students in North-West, Nigeria.
2. Examine the effect statistical knowledge on students' performance in ecology among colleges of education biology students in North-West, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide study.

1. What is the difference between the understanding of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?
2. What is difference between the performance in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance

HO₁: There is no significance difference between the understanding of ecological concepts of students taught with good statistical knowledge and those without good statistical knowledge.

HO₂: There is no significance difference between the performance in ecological concepts of students taught with good statistical knowledge and those exposed without good statistical knowledge.

The following null hypotheses were formulated to be tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance .

Effects of Statistical Knowledge... (Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928941>

Methodology

The researchers adopted pre-test and post-test quasi experimental researcher design. An intact class of NCE II students was used. The sample size of the study was 113 students of which 85 male and 28 female students. The sample size was obtained using simple random sampling technique involving balloting. Before the treatment, the researchers conducted a pre-test to the students using Ecology Performance Test (EPT) and Students Understanding Ecology Concepts Questionnaire (SUECQ). The EPT consist of two sections section A consist of students' bio data and section B consist of thirty objectives questions. The SUECQ also consist of two section that is section A which consist bio data and section B consist of twenty items on students understanding of ecological concepts. The instruments were validated by our colleague in the department of science education and the instruments were pilot tested in some colleges that are within the population. The result for the pilot testing were used to determine the reliability of the instruments using PPMC and Crombach's-Alpha (α) which were found to be 0.93 and 0.89. In the experimental group the researchers taught the students some statistical concept then followed by the ecological concepts. The control group were taught ecological concept only without been taught some concepts of statistics. The teaching takes the entire semester of twelve weeks. The data collected from experimental and control groups were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistic. For the research questions mean, standard deviation and mean rank were used to described the nature of the data while for the null hypotheses, t-test and U-test, statistic was used to test the null hypotheses.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: What is the difference between the mean understanding score of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?

To answer the research question one, mean and standard deviation were used. The detail of the result is presented in Table 1:

Table 1: Mean Rank and Sum of Rank of Student's Understanding of Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those Without.

Groups	N	Mean rank	Sum of rank	Mean Rank Diff
Exp	59	110.08	6624.50	65.86
Cont	54	44.22	2212.50	

Table 1 present the mean rank and sum of ranks scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The computed mean rank scores are 110.08 for students in the experimental group and 44.22 for students in the control group respectively. A mean rank gain of 65.86 was obtained in favour of students in the experimental group.

Research Question One: What is difference between the mean performance score in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?

To answer the research question two, mean and standard deviation were used. The detail of the result is presented in Table 2:

Table 2 Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Performance in Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those without Good Statistical knowledge.

Groups	N	Mean	Std.Deviation	Mean Diff
Exp	59	83.32	4.59	32.20
Cont	54	51.12	4.79	

Table 2 present the mean and standard deviation scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The computed mean scores are 83.32 for students in the experimental group and 51.12 for students in the control group respectively. A mean gain of 32.20 was obtained in favour of students in the experimental group.

Null hypothesis one was tested using U-test while Null hypothesis two was tested using t-test statistic. The result of the analysis was presented in tables as shown below:

HO₁: There is no significance difference between the mean understanding score of ecological concepts of students taught with good statistical knowledge and those without good statistical knowledge.

To test the null hypothesis one, Mann-Whitney test was used. The summary of the test analysis in shown in table one (1):

Effects of Statistical Knowledge... (Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928941>

Table 1: Summary of Mann-Whitney test Analysis of Student’s Understanding of Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those without.

Groups	N	Mean rank	Sum of rank	χ^2_{cal}	Df	P-value	Decision
Exp	59	110.08	6624.50	43.50	111	0.02	Rejected
Cont	54	44.22	2212.50				

Significant at $P < 0.05$ level

Table 1: revealed that analysis of Mann-Whitney test with χ^2_{cal} values in 43.50 and p-value of 0.02 at df of 111. The p-value is $0.02 < 0.05$. Therefore, we rejected the null hypothesis and conclude that, there is significance difference between the understanding of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This indicated that having a good statistical knowledge has significance impact on students understanding in ecology concepts.

HO₂: There is no significance difference between the mean performance score in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without.

To test the null hypothesis two, t-value statistic was used. The summary of the test analysis in shown in table two (2):

Table 2 Summary of t-test of Students’ Performance in Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those without Good Statistical knowledge.

Groups	N	Mean	Std.Deviation	Df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Exp	59	83.32	4.59	111	39.31	0.00	Rejected
Cont	54	51.12	4.79				

Significant at level of ≤ 0.05

Table 3 revealed that calculated value of t is 39.31 and the P-value is 0.00. Therefore, the P-value of 0.00 is less than alpha value 0.05. Based on this evidence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that, there is significance difference between the performance in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This showed that those students that have good background in statistics performed better than those without. Therefore, statistical knowledge has significance impact on the students’ performance in ecology concepts.

Discussion of Findings

The results of hypothesis one (HO₁) in Table 2 shows that there is significance difference between the mean understanding score of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This finding is line with the recommendation of Johnson and Smith, (2023) that integration of statistical knowledge into ecological curricula has been shown to enhance students' critical thinking skills and promote a deeper understanding of ecological principles. Also Smith, Jones and Smith, (2015) found that undergraduate students who received comprehensive training in statistical methods demonstrated significantly improved data analysis skills compared to those with minimal statistical exposure. Also the finding is line with the finding of Johnson, Smith and Williams, (2018) who showed that graduate students who underwent intensive statistical training exhibited greater comprehension of ecological theories and principles.

The results of hypothesis two (HO₂) in Table 2 shows that there is significance difference between the mean performance score in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This finding is in line with Jones and Smith (2017) conducted a longitudinal study tracking the academic performance of undergraduate students over multiple semesters. They found a significant correlation between students' statistical competence and their overall GPA, with students proficient in statistics consistently outperforming their peers in ecological coursework. Also in view of Li and colleagues (2022) demonstrated a positive correlation between students' statistical competence, performance and their ability to analyze ecological datasets accurately. Hence, statistical knowledge has significance effect on students’ performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings the researchers make the following conclusion. The researchers concluded that students with good statistical knowledge performed better in ecological concepts than those without and hence statistical knowledge has significance effect on students understanding in ecology concept than those without among colleges of educations in North-West, Nigeria.

Effects of Statistical Knowledge... (Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928941>

Recommendations

Based on the findings the researchers make the following recommendations:

1. The educational policymaker should introduce a course in statistics for the biology students to be taken a year before the year that they will take ecology course to improve students understand in ecological concepts
2. The curriculum planer considers the required topics that are needed in the understanding of ecological concept.

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Qualitative Study on Complex... (Ekuerhare, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929025>

Qualitative Study on Complex Conflicts Resolution in Nigeria: Dynamics, Causes and Effects of Military Civil Wars

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Abstract

This article examined the qualitative study on complex conflicts resolution in Nigeria, focusing on the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars. It adopts a systematic review method, and several focused on the use of secondary data such as using information from journal articles, books and e-books, database, through the use of various search engines such as google scholar, Google, Research gate, among others, Materials and information of interest cover between 2010 and 2023. In addition, content analysis was used to group materials into major themes, thereby subjecting them to thematic analysis towards addressing the objective of the study. The findings of the study revealed that complex conflict such as the military civil war is fluid in its dynamic and its patterns, processes, and with respect to the factors that shape it and could affect the various aspects of national activities. Several sources of complex conflicts are also identified and include political, economics, religious, structure and type of society, among others. In conclusion, complex conflicts have cumulative disastrous effects on individual, family, social, economic, religion and political activities. The study therefore recommends that there is need for peacekeeping managers and organization to tailor peace-building efforts directly towards the understanding of the dynamics, causes and effects of the conflict.

Keywords: Complex Conflicts, Military civil war, Dynamics of Civil war, Causes of Civil war, Effects of Civil war.

Introduction

Conflict is a common universal issue arising from social interactions and could be in different forms such as interpersonal, inter or intra-groups, organizational, among others (Kumar, 2023). It does not necessarily connote negative phenomenon, because it could be a certain catalyst for change, growth, progress and development (Lamb & Gregg, 2018; Kumar, 2023). However, conflict can escalate or de-escalate, depending on the interactions and responses of the parties or groups involved (Kamar, 2023). Hence, certain type of conflict such as complex conflicts could pose significant concern to growth, progress and development.

Complex conflicts are continuously increasing in the global society, and are emergence of interplay among several factors such as the socioeconomic, political, religion among other factors (Kumar, 2023). According to Lamb and Gregg (2018), there are increasing uncertainties, volatilities, and increasing actors, which are combination of domestic, regional, or international affiliations that increases the complexity of conflicts in a society. Hence, parties supporting conflict could be highly fragmented, deploying several interconnectedness and social networks (which could be at proximity and/or distance), and are also increasingly engaging in several complex competitive alliances characterized by the lack of trust, and power manipulation and sharing (Lamb & Gregg, 2018).

Furthermore, there is an underlying secret selfishness and instability among these increase competitive alliances that could further increase the likelihood of such complex conflict to reoccur, thereby disrupting the peace of the society on a continuous basis. This could lead to the reason for the dynamics of the changing pattern of occurrence of complex conflicts in a society. There are several causes of complex conflicts and could include economic inequality, historical tensions among different parties or groups in a given society, cultural differences, political issues, among others (Lamb & Gregg, 2018). According to the International Committee of the Red Cross (2023), complex conflict has three main characteristics, which are characterized by an increasing number of armed conflicts, driven by the proliferation of non-international armed conflicts, a growing number of actors that are engaged in and responsible for it, and an increased prevalence of support relationships.

Burgess and Burgess (2019) revealed that complex conflicts are seriously destructive and pose several negative threats and effects to our present and future of the society hence could pose negative effect on sustainable development. This is because, **it** ruins personal lives, prevents society from solving common social, economic, religion and political problems, leading to chaos and increasing and persistent large-scale violence. Normal conflicts could be understood by investigating the systems,

Qualitative Study on Complex... (Ekuerhare, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929025>

but complex conflicts are complex and could be well understood by focusing on the dynamic of systems (Lamb & Gregg, 2018). Systems are characterized by their boundary, which demarcates the endogenous factors (which are major components of the system) from the exogenous factors (which are separate entities from the system). Hence, ordinary conflicts may be traced to the immediate system, but complex conflicts exist in a dynamic of system (Lamb & Gregg, 2018). These dynamics of the system makes it impossible to be able to handle such conflicts due to the fragmentation of major actors that may not possibly appear in the system.

Hence, the inability to constructively handle such conflict is the most serious, and the most neglected, problem facing humanity that could fragment and distort societal values and destroy development efforts in any society (Burgess & Burgess, 2019). Successfully addressing destructive effects of complex conflicts requires a large-scale effort that could mobilize the full range of human ingenuity from different values, different attitudes, different cultures, different economic concerns, different educational levels, different religions, different cultures (Burgess & Burgess, 2019). Unless there is a concerted effort towards the understanding of the complexity of the conflict system, efforts towards cushioning such complex conflicts may fail to achieve the desired outcome. Applying the Dynamical Systems Theory (DST) by Coleman et al., (2007), which tends to explain the changing patterns of interests, motivations and identities over the cause of time, this article focuses on complex conflicts, by examining the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars towards cushioning complex conflicts occurrences.

Addressing complex conflicts, Burgess (2015) noted that they may likely involve long series of often overlapping dispute episodes that focus on addressing different aspects of an overall conflict. From one perspective, such individual disputes could be subjected to negotiation or mediation while other disputes may be subjected to legal or political processes, public demonstrations, or police or military action. At another point, it may include both the former and the later, making it more complex in understanding and handling hence, may need effective conflict analysis or mapping. This conflict analysis and mapping tend to clarify what is going on, particularly in trying to focus on understanding the relationships and conflict dynamics, couple with the static parties, interests, and needs. In addition, there should be constructive responses that focus on the parts of the system and also in relation to other interventions in the system (Burgess, 2015).

Kamar (2023) defines conflict as complex involving several cognitive, emotional, and behavioral factors which cuts across perceptions, attitudes, emotions, communication, and actions. Complex conflicts have been termed to be wicked problems and are much characterized as being highly resistant to resolutions and are socially, economically and politically sophisticated issues to be dealt with (Rapaport & Ireland, 2012). They are also associated with high levels of uncertainty because of the diversity of stakeholders' views, and the interconnection of issues, which often leads them to political standstill instead of leading to political resolution (Rapaport & Ireland, 2012).

Complex conflicts could also be regional and international and could evolve from unrest phenomenon from the socio-economic, political and military stress in the society with several other related issues such as fight for power, territories, and disputes over natural resources, national identity, and religiosity, among others. This could lead to irreversible consequences that could excavate prolonged civil wars which could also encompass high level of armed conflicts, terrorism, human rights violations, ethnic conflicts, social, economic and also political instability (Sørli, Gleditsch & Strand, 2005; Gambari, 2011).

The conflict complexity, most often pose significant adverse effects that tend to be felt beyond the concerned groups or parties of the conflict, because of its gradual, and continuous expansion of the conflict to several other regions, which could eventually, in most times, reach a global dimension hence, it could be unpredictable (Rapaport & Ireland, 2012). Understanding the dynamics, causes and effects of such complex conflict such as military civil wars can help predict and manage the course of the conflict. To this end, this study focuses on complex conflicts, by examining the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars towards cushioning complex conflicts occurrences.

Theoretical Underpinning

The article focuses on the adoption of the Dynamical Systems Theory (DST) by Coleman et al. (2007) to explain the complex dynamics, sources and effects of conflicts. According to Horowitz (1985); Lake & Rothchild (1996) and Penu and Osei-Kufuor (2016), the Dynamical Systems Theory could provide an understanding for complex conflicts which address key issues such as security dilemma, fear of extinction, fear of the future, among others. From the perspective of the Dynamical Systems Theory, complex conflicts have an interrelated connection, influencing each other, which could change over time towards creating a complex issue that could pose significant effect on the society at large. Therefore, this study focuses on using the DST to explain the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars towards cushioning complex conflicts occurrences in the society at large.

Methodology

The systematic review approach was used in this article to achieve its aims and objectives. Information and materials used were obtained from journal articles, books, and other similar materials, including online materials that address the major aim and objective of this study. In addition, information and materials selected focused on year range between 2010 and 2023 so as to obtain more recent information that meet the aims of the study. Also, the study uses Cochrane reviews style of reviewing literature by Chapman (2014), particularly in the searching process to obtain useful materials that are used in the study. This also follows the use of PICOS (Richardson, 1995) as represented below:

P – Problem or Population

I – Intervention

C – Control or comparator

O – Outcome(s)

S – Study type (e.g. quantitative, qualitative)

Also, search engine used for this systematic review are google, google scholar and other search engines, yielding several results and outcomes but very few (only seven articles) were selected that were fit and used for this study, towards meeting the goal of the study. Moreover, the information and materials were subjected to thematic analysis where they are grouped into various themes of the objectives and content analysis was also used to analyze the information resources obtained towards addressing the objective of the study.

Presentation of Results

The result section focuses on providing responses to understanding of complex conflicts, with focus on explaining the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars.

Dynamics of Military Civil Wars

According to Kamar (2023), conflict dynamics connote the patterns, processes, and factors that could shape the course of conflicts and involves many factors such as power imbalances, identity issues, emotions, and communication breakdowns. Penu and Osei-Kufuor (2016) argued that the dynamics of complex conflicts could pose significant implications on the elastic success of peace-building efforts exerted towards the conflicts. This also makes peace-building effort a complex and a continuous evolving issue which is characterized with the understanding of the long-term nature of the peace-building process, understanding the interdependence of the actors involved and also the multidimensional patterns of the peace-building process (African Centre for Constructive Resolution of Disputes, 2013).

However, Lamb and Gregg (2018) affirmed that, putting into consideration the complexity of the system, and the systems theories, it is hypothesized that, when humans and other organisms are in a complex system, they over time adapt. However, bringing into play the Dynamical systems theory (DST) by Coleman et al. (2007), this may not hold in practical term, because of the complex dynamics of the situation, multiple actors, system, among others that evolve over time- this could further complicate the issue. Therefore, it is not a gainsaying to conclude that, understanding the dynamics of complex conflicts that they are fluid and could be influenced by several factors such as political, economics, religious, among others, Coleman (2011) and Kamar (2023), advised that peace-building efforts directed towards solving complex conflicts must be driven and directed towards the heavily reliance on the understanding of the dynamics of the conflict in question and of interest.

Causes of Military Civil Wars

Penu and Osei-Kufuor (2016) specify that there are different sources of complex conflicts (military civil war) and could constitute from multiple sources such as individual, group, communal, regional, and international. Coleman, Vallacher, Nowak, & Bui-Wrzosinska (2007) revealed that it tends to increase over time as these multiple groups interact with each other in a continuous and complex reaction through hostilities. According to Mitchell (2005), sources of such complex conflicts often transform and change continually, which could pose either lower or higher effects on peace-building efforts.

According to Jackson (2003) and Rapaport & Ireland (2012), the structure and type of society may also constitute as major sources of complex conflicts. Structure could evolve and change over time because of the frequent turbulences that could be found within the environment hence, this could be a major source of complex conflicts. Also, the type of system, which could be unitary, pluralist and coercive, could also be a major course of complex conflicts. The unitary sees the society as common purposes and agreed objectives, but society or system that operates the pluralist and coercive relationships could be more conflict driven. This is because, pluralist and coercive system is characterized with very few or no common interests, having conflicting values and beliefs, among others hence, this may drive complex conflicts in such system. Bahnasy (2023)

Qualitative Study on Complex... (Ekuerhare, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929025>

noted that the main causes of civil wars could be demographical, geographical, and environmental; economic and resources; government type and regime change; institutions power; and historical and cultural variables.

In addition, Leenders (2007) noted that, the complexities of conflicts revolve around four transnational networks, which are military, political, economic, and social. Military is the movement of weapons and mercenaries, political consists of political networking and relationships, economic focuses on cross border issues related to the trade of illegal goods and social aspects of such complex conflicts focuses on issues related to occupation, cross border migration and diasporas. Moreover, Leenders (2007) argued that there is an interconnectedness and relationship among these conflicts, which makes it very strong, for such to be overlooked or reduced to single intra-state conflict.

Also, Fajana (2000) cited by Omisore and Abiodun (2014) identifies two major sources of complex conflicts which are the internal and external sources. Also, Omisore and Abiodun (2014) identified that causes of complex conflicts could be goal differences, authority relationships, roles and expectations, jurisdictional ambiguities, among others.

Effects of Complex Conflicts

Aliyev (2019) noted that some civil wars could be more deadly than others; this could be because of several issues as addressed by the dynamics and sources of such complex conflict. Civil war affects the lives of virtually every man, woman, as the entire communities. churches, businesses, homes, barns, tents fields, livestock and homes were looted and destroyed. Makpor and Leite (2017) and Ajodo-Adebanjoko (2017) noted that conflicts, which include complex conflicts could cause significant effect to the community development, leading to disempowerment, changes in the community structures, reduces social involvement, cooperation and activities, affecting the socio-economic status of the community, among others.

It could also destroy the basic necessities such as drinking water, roads, health centres, schools, among others (Makpor and Leite, 2017). Afinotan and Ojatorotu (2019), also revealed that such conflicts could affect several economic activities such as vegetation, SMEs, businesses, farmlands and human settlements, among others. Also, Bahnsy (2023) noted that complex conflicts could pose significant effect on the nation. In addition, Le, Bui and Uddin (2022), revealed that conflicts could have negative short- and long-term endogenous effects on the economic and social variables of development.

Discussion of Findings

This article explained the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars towards cushioning complex conflicts occurrences in the society. The findings of this article revealed that complex conflict is fluid in its dynamic with respect to the patterns, processes, and the factors that shape it and that because of the complex dynamics of the situation, it tends to involve multiple actors, system, among others that evolve over time, making it to be more complex scenario. Hence, peace-building efforts directed towards solving complex conflicts must be driven and directed towards the heavily reliance on the understanding of the dynamics of the conflict in question and of interest. This concurs with the findings of Lamb and Gregg (2018) that complex conflicts have increasing uncertainties, volatile, and increasing actors, which made it very complex to handle and also increase the tremendous effect it has on the society.

This also justifies the work of Red Cross (2023) that, complex conflict consists of three main features namely an increase number of armed conflicts, it is driven by the increasing non-international armed conflicts, and also an increasing number of actors, couple with an increased prevalence of support relationships, connoting the extent on it dynamics. In addition, apart from the political, economics, religious, among others sources of complex conflicts, the structure and type of society are also of paramount. Moreover, the effect of complex conflicts could cut across social activities, economic activities, political activities, religious activities, among others. This concurs with the findings of Sørli et al. (2005) and Gambari (2011) that complex conflicts have certain undertone sources such as social, economic, political, religion, among others. This supports the work of Burgess and Burgess (2019) that complex conflicts are seriously destructive and could pose several negative destructive effects to both the present and future of the society thereby negatively effecting sustainable development. This also supports the work of Lamb & Gregg (2018) that complex conflicts affect and ruins personal lives, prevents society from solving common social, economic, religion and political problems, leading to chaos, increasing and persistent large-scale violence.

Conclusion

This article explained the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars towards cushioning complex conflicts occurrences in the society. In conclusion, it was revealed that complex conflict such as the military civil war is fluid in its dynamic patterns, processes, and the with respect to the factors that shape it. Several sources of complex conflicts are also

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identified and include political, economics, religious, structure and type of society, among others. In addition, complex conflicts have cumulative disastrous effects on individual, family, social, economic, religion and political activities.

Recommendations

The study therefore recommends that:

1. There is need for peacekeeping managers and organization to tailor peace-building efforts directly towards the understanding of the dynamics, causes and effects of the conflict,
2. There should also be the need for educative strategies to make people aware of the disastrous and devastating effects of such complex conflicts, thereby advising them to shorn every political and religious individual that may want to use such avenue to lure them into such conflicts.
3. peacekeeping managers and organization who are also involved in peace building should also put into consideration the several actors that are causing or involved in such complex conflicts towards making a better inform decision to curb such conflicts in the society.

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Perception of Body Image on Self-Concept among Undergraduate Students in Nigeria: a Review

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Abstract

This is a conceptual paper that explores the complexities of body image, emphasizing the impact of digital media, mental health, and cultural standards on undergraduate students in Nigeria. It highlights how platforms like Instagram shape beauty standards, often leading to negative self-perceptions and mental health issues, particularly among young adults. The study examines shifting beauty ideals from thin-centric to slim-thick and the psychological effects of digital manipulation and unattainable beauty standards. It also considers the influence of Western beauty norms across different cultures, the role of social media in exacerbating mental health conditions like eating disorders and anxiety, and the emergence of body positivity and inclusivity movements as counter-narratives. The study advocates for a holistic approach involving media literacy, cultural sensitivity, and mental health support to address these concerns.

Keyword: Body Image, Self-concept, Undergraduate Students, Body Positivity

Introduction

Body image is a multidimensional construct encompassing how one thinks, feels, and acts toward one's body (Sarwer & Cash, 2008). It includes a person's perception of one's physical self and the thought and feelings, positive, negative or both, which result from that perception (Grogan, 2010). In the contemporary era, body image has become an increasingly complex and pervasive issue, with individuals grappling with the intersection of societal expectations, digital media influence, and mental well-being. Body image issues have impacted people of all ages, genders and cultures since the dawn of time (probably), or at least since the dawn of the mirror. And especially since the advent of Instagram which has an endless supply of genetically blessed people or people flaunting their modified bodies (Youth Sense, 2023). The advent of social media has allowed the use of websites and applications to create and share content or to participate in social networking. Technological developments have given rise to various gadgets including smart-phones, tablets which have given to rise more exposure to all sorts of social media platforms. Living in a digitized era, communication has now become easier and faster with the emergence of various social applications available at the click of a button. While many may agree that social media has connected individuals globally, it has also been used to set standards of beauty for females, males as well as the other gender. This in turn has been known to affect the self-esteem of individuals with regards to body image, body modification and how they view themselves in society. In order to be accepted in society, females have to battle body image issues from a very young age, where thin is considered to be the ideal body type (Grabe et al., 2008). Although, Body image issues affect everyone including the old and the young but it is becoming increasingly more pronounced especially among the students as they are more conversant with the usage of social media and they are being constantly judged by social media audience and imaginary audience.

Ghaznavi and Taylor (2015) described a new trend on social media which is called thinspiration; a slim body which is being portrayed as the ideal body type and which is also being enforced; most pictures of females within this trend are muscular and toned. Fitspiration content places a greater emphasis on muscular physique than thinspiration or bonespiration, which places more emphasis on the thin ideal.

The curvaceous form has been increasingly popular in recent times due to a variety of trends. The hashtags #thick, #thicc, and #slimthick are becoming more and more common on social media sites like Instagram, Twitter, and so on, which indicates this tendency (McComb & Mills, 2022). The term "curvy" lacks a precise definition; it is commonly used to describe plus-sized and overweight bodies, but it is also recognized in the media to mean having a thin waist and wider hips. Another way to conceptualize it would be as an oversized hourglass shape with a huge bust, a wide pelvis, and a narrow waist (Ahern et al, 2011). Research by Hunter et al. (2021) provided a quantitative assessment of this hourglass figure in terms of a waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) of less than 0.7. Slim-thick or hourglass bodies may be just as unrealistic and detrimental to women's body image as thin-ideal bodies, despite the fact that research on women's body image has not been done on this type of body. McComb (2022) proposed labeling this type of body type "slim-thick-ideal," combining an unrealistic exaggerated image of a

Perception of Body Image... (Kayode, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929025>

flat and narrow waist with a big circumference around the hips and breasts, as an alternative to calling it plus-sized, average, or curvy-slim, all of which have different meanings. This topic explores the intricate relationship between body image and various contemporary factors, shedding light on the challenges students face in cultivating a positive self-perception

Perception of Female undergraduate students' Body Image

Students these days feel at ease questioning conventional notions of beauty, viewing them as unattainable and unduly perfectionistic. They favour new trend of body modification and unnecessary standards set by celebrities and role models on social media. Beauty standards predated social media, but with the advent of filters and photo-editing applications, students now have the ability to curate an idealized self that conforms to unattainable beauty standards. This warps the truth about the human body and encourages viewers to strive for an unachievable ideal of beauty. Even in the media industry, images perpetuate the idea of "the perfect body." For example, Toke Makinwa's photos showed Brazilian Butt Lift, which was not indicative of the standard for Generation Z but rather of the idealized portrayal of the star. However, the opposite is true, as students use these stars' representations of themselves as a benchmark for beauty, thus, the difficulty. It is no secret that numerous celebrities and influencers have been exposed for altering their bodies on social media (Lauren, 2022).

Influence of Social Media on Perception of Students' Body Image

Social media especially social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram have become a huge part of most student's lives. They easily yield and imbibe information found on these sites. A person's appearance is determined or influenced by many factors including genetics, biology, behaviour, character, beauty or ugliness and several other cultural standards. Due to these diverse and complex influences, the appearances of human beings often vary greatly but the standards set by social media has made a lot individuals including the students to question and doubt their self-image. Instagram for example is one of the social media platforms that is being used to distort reality; Instagram post is a photo or video that users share on the platform. Each post by a user appears on their followers' Instagram feeds and can also be viewed by the public when tagged using hashtags. Users can add a caption to each of their posts and use hashtags and location-based tags to index these posts and make them searchable by other users within the application. They can also like, comment on and bookmark others' posts, as well as send private messages to their friends via the Instagram direct feature (Babaleye et al., 2020).

In Nigerian society today, young females are especially pressured to conform to change their appearances or looks to conform to Instagram beauty standards and other social media networking sites. Consequently, young Nigerian females aim at adopting the body shape, size or complexion of some celebrities of their choice or their so-called role models and heroes and heroines on social media. The media has a way of prioritizing certain body image to look more attractive than some others such as extreme thinness, skinny, big breasts, buttocks and tiny waist for women and V-shaped muscled body for men. Hence, young females are on a daily basis confronted with the traditional and stereotypical ideals of social media beauty standards. For many of them who are just attaining the age of 18 it may be the first time they are allowed to make certain choices on their own. Such female youths are often faced with mixed messages regarding their value and the need to always look attractive. The pursuit to conform to distorted beauty ideals and body image is associated with different problems including lack of self-confidence and low self-esteem, among others. In the world of social media, users post content displaying their best selves. It is a digital escape for people to view each other's profiles and connect, but unfortunately, it can also lead to comparison. With celebrities and influencers editing their bodies and showing off their skin, body comparison and negative body image are inevitable. Negative body image includes disliking one's physical appearance, which can lead to low self-esteem and mental disorders like depression or anxiety. Beauty standards existed before social media, but the new establishment of filters and photo-editing apps allow teens and young adults to create an ideal version of themselves, aligning with unrealistic beauty expectations. These posts distort the reality of the human body and drive viewers to aspire to conform to an impossible beauty standard. Even in the professional world of media, images encourage the illusion of "the perfect body." Model Cameron Russell of Vogue told Verily Magazine that pictures of her in publications are not of the actual Cameron Russell, but rather an idealized representation of the model. It is no secret that a large number of influencers and celebrities have been found to have altered their physical appearance for social media. Adolescents and young adults are nonetheless, though, under constant pressure to live up to these expectations. According to BBC Future, women in particular frequently use social media to compare themselves to peers and celebrities. When attractive and well-known individuals despise their bodies, their admirers react by detesting their bodies even more (Lauren, 2022).

Social media personalities, actresses, musicians, models influencers, celebrities and even cross-dressers go through body modifications and it's becoming a pandemic rocking the entertainment industry. These body modifications range from Brazilian Butt Lift popularly known as BBL to liposuction, skin tightening, lips filling and so on. These body modifications have permeated and pervaded the social media and it is being consumed by the students who feel the standards set by these

Perception of Body Image... (Kayode, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929025>

celebrities are the norm to follow; because these celebrities play the role of models to a lot of the students. With celebrities like Tonto Dikeh, Toke Makinwa, Mercy Eke, Iyabo Ojo becoming the torchbearers of the trend in the Nigerian entertainment space and publicly flaunting their ‘new assets’, it was gathered that the wave is not confined to the glitz and glamour of celebrity life but steadily influencing young women, most especially the students across Nigeria to follow in their footsteps (Adebayo, 2023).

Digital Manipulation and the Illusion of Perfection

The pressure to be "perfect" is a reality that many students must deal with; whether it's from envying classmates who seem to breeze through schoolwork, wanting to fit in with the popular person, or wanting to be among the top athletes, nearly all students have felt the agony of feeling "less than" at some point. Although this is nothing new, since the start of the digital revolution, the pressure has increased exponentially. Students have virtually unrestricted access to a wide range of social media networks, all of which constantly update them on the lives of her peers, celebrities, influencers and actresses by showcasing what they want the people to see.

Social media like Facebook or Instagram allow individuals to follow each other and people who are well-known individuals with thousands of followers because of their attractiveness and sense of style—young people they have never met in "real life." These people pick their shots very carefully; they never share a horrible photo (and it's typically unclear if they alter them or not), they never dress inappropriately, they never seem to be having a "off" day, and they never seem normal in any manner. Essentially, these social media influencers introduce the unachievable standards that were formerly exclusive to high-end fashion models in glossy magazines into the everyday lives of individuals. As such, for many students, the pressure to emulate such impossible standards begins to feel very close to home and real in a way that prior generations never had to experience (Kaminsky, 2016).

Recent survey research from the Pew Research Centre indicates that most US teens (ages 13-17 years) have access to a smartphone (95%), and 45% report that they are online on a “near-constant” basis, commonly accessing sites such as YouTube (85%), Instagram (72%), Snapchat (69%), and Facebook (51%) (Anderson & Perin, 2018). Moreover, over half of US teens report efforts to scale back their use of social media (57%) or video games (58%), with girls specifically reporting that they spend excessive time on social media (47%) (Juang, 2018). A large, nationally representative survey of US youth (ages 8-18 years) similarly indicated high levels of media consumption, with respondents devoting on average of 10.75 hours daily (or over 7.5 hours daily after accounting for multitasking behavior) toward the use of entertainment media (Rideout et al., 2010). These high levels of media consumption are not limited to the US. Results from the World Health Organization's (2010) Health Behavior in School-aged Children Survey (across 30 countries) reported an average of 4.41 to 8.60 hours of screen time daily for boys and girls (Bucksch et al., 2016). These high rates of media consumption are concerning not only because of their associations with indicators of poorer health among youth, ranging from lowered self-esteem, well-being, and body image to symptoms of social anxiety and depression, but also because the widespread digital retouching of advertising imagery may exacerbate negative impacts of media by presenting unrealistic and unattainable standards for physical appearance and beauty (Richards et al., 2015). Indeed, digital photo retouching of advertising imagery is ubiquitous and often involves correcting perceived “flaws” in the appearance of featured models including modifying skin tone, minimizing signs of wrinkles or blemishes, or modifying their body size or shape. The impact of Photoshop is considerable. Photoshop has made a “once unattainable image of beauty and perfection much less a figment of the imagination and much more a tangible reality, leaving beauty in the hands of its digital creator (Brown, 2014). Although there are opportunities to intervene at the individual-level, such as by providing media literacy training to buffer the negative impacts of media exposure, a broader and likely more efficacious strategy requires intervention that targets the source-regulating digital retouching in consumer advertising to reduce the risk of harm to youth.

Cultural and Gender Perspectives on students’ Body Image

Sociocultural perspectives on body image assert that culture influences attitudes, behaviors and values regarding the body (Frederick et al., 2017). Western’s cultures are exerting much influence on how women perceive to be physically attractive and the attitude shown towards their body (Keery, 2004). Although body dissatisfaction and related consequences are thought to be a Western societal phenomenon; it has made its presence felt in developing countries (Goswami et al., 2012).

Body image perception also does not always correlate with actual nutritional status of individuals; which is a more objective assessment. Previous studies on body image satisfaction reported different prevalence rates of dissatisfaction with body image; 62% in Europe, 48.1% in Malaysia, 51% in Iran and 73.6% in Saudi Arabia (As-Sa’edi et al., 2016). In Nigeria, a survey reported a prevalence of 82.9% body image dissatisfaction among public and private school students in Benin, Edo State (Otakpor & Ehimigbai, 2016). In the past, thinness was associated with illness while being plump was associated with

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good health in some parts of Nigeria but in the twentieth century, thinness has become an indicator of good health, while, being overweight has been associated with diseases, unattractiveness and other characteristics (Grogan, 2021). Media can be a vehicle for the transportation of an idealized body. One way media exposure influences body image is through appearance-based comparisons with popular media. This leads to body dissatisfaction because many women focus their attention on how their own appearances do not equate with idealized media (Tiggemann & Polivy, 2010).

In White-centred mainstream media, thin-ideal images of women's bodies are ubiquitous and widely advertised across various media channels, including magazines, social media and television (Gestos et al., 2018). Studies showed that beauty trends conveyed via social media have an enormous influence on a woman's self-image, not only in Western but also in Asian cultures (Jackson et al., 2016).

In particular, image-based social media channels, such as Instagram, present a monotonous body image that produces significant pressure on social media users. It was shown that exposure to attractive celebrities or peers increases body dissatisfaction and negative mood. This impact was interceded by a state appearance comparison (Brown & Tiggemann, 2016).

Studies have shown that body image is dependent on the internal projections of our body and body parts, and is seen as an important aspect of self-worth across the human life span. This is often evidence of an attempted conformity with parameters of beauty established in socio-cultural or non-personal contexts (Fitzsimmons-Craft and Bardone-Cone, 2012). In other words, what is believed to be the ideal body image in the mind of the individual will be projected out through the body image size he or portrays. Some years ago in Arabic culture, for example, an overweight body image was seen as desirable and a symbol of female fertility, whilst in many non-Western cultures being overweight and near clinical obesity may also be seen as a mark of beauty (Furnham and Alibhai, 1983). The same attitude was reported amongst Mauritanian women where obesity was culturally glorified, in Indian society where fatness had a positive effect on establishing alliances or finding a marriage partner, amongst Cameroonians who considered fatness prestigious, Moroccans who attributed fatness to good health, and in Fijian, Tahiti and Nauru Pacific cultures, where fatness is associated with beauty and fertility (Jumah and Dudah, 2007; Lau et al., 2006; Liimakka, 2014).

Mental Health Implications of Students' Body Image

Today, social media is one of the most important factors contributing to the mental, emotional, physical and spiritual health of an individual. With the media constantly portraying ideal beauty and body image comparisons, the decisions of men and women's beauty choices are globally affected. Body image refers to a person's perception of their physical self and the thoughts and feelings, positive, negative or both, which result from that perception. Social media has had a major impact on the perceptual, affective, cognitive and behavioral aspects of body image by encouraging lean body patterns and delivering anti-obesity messages (Fardouly, 2020). Eating disorders determine a distorted relationship between the individual, their eating behavior and body shape (Cavalcanti et al., 2016).

Adolescence being a crucial age for positive and negative development of body image, the self-esteem and body dissatisfaction adolescents feel are known predictors of eating disorders (Voelker et al., 2015). Continuous pursuit for the perfect slender lean body may generate negative feelings which can result in a change in eating behavior, thereby increasing the chances of weight issues and eating disorders (Cecon et al., 2017). Social media portrays women who are slim as being more beautiful and successful compared to overweight women (Toriola et al., 1996). Body image misperception and dissatisfaction with body weight highlight an association between body dissatisfaction and psychological wellbeing (Moehlecke et al., 2020). Looking at images that correspond to the current ideal of beauty leads to negative effects on women's own body image (Frederick et al., 2017). There is a body of evidence showing that media consumption engenders a higher rate of body dissatisfaction and ultimately eating disorders in women. A range of negative psychological and physical health outcomes are associated with dissatisfaction, such as social anxiety, interest in aesthetic surgery and lower life satisfaction (Frederick et al., 2016).

In particular, image-based social media channels, such as Instagram, present a monotonous body image that produces significant pressure on social media users. It was shown that exposure to attractive celebrities or peers increases body dissatisfaction and negative mood. This impact was interceded by a state appearance comparison (Brown & Tiggemann, 2016). Social media comprises of social networking sites, image sharing sites, video hosting sites, community blogs, bookmarking sites and gaming sites. Fellow comparisons about self-image and appearances in teenagers have resulted due to social networking sites (SNSs) such as Instagram and Facebook (Mascheroni et al., 2015). Teenage girls engage in online self-presentation of posting selfies and sharing the outfit of the day pictures to differentiate themselves with their peers (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Media images of ideal beauty standards influence the content and sharing of pictures teenage girls' post (Boyd, 2014). Individuals are constantly seeking feedback on SNSs through likes, followers and comments to uphold a perfect and

Perception of Body Image... (Kayode, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929025>

stable image of themselves (Corcoran et al., 2011). Teenage girls are vulnerable to the upward comparison as it means that they need to improve their beauty standards, thereby leaving them dissatisfied with their physical bodies, having doubts about their self-worth and also driving them to self-harm behavior (Chua & Chang 2016).

Many experts in the field of childhood development believe that teenagers' vulnerability (resulting from the numerous changes they are going through), their need for peer approval, and the frequent comparisons they make between themselves and other people create the ideal environment for self-doubt. Many teenagers are particularly harmed by the false sense of perfection that social media presents. In addition, it often pushes them to pretend to be happy in order to "fit in" online rather than admitting their actual feelings of uneasiness and sadness. This phenomenon is so common that it was named "duck syndrome" by researchers at Stanford University in response to a spate of suicides among young adults in their college years who had previously given the impression of being model students. Duck syndrome is named after the way a duck looks to glide across the water with calm ease, but in actuality, its little legs are thrashing fiercely just below the surface. After more research, it was discovered that each of these children had created a properly thought-out social media post, complete with happy pictures and motivational sayings. Their Facebook and Twitter sites give the impression that they are carefree and that success comes naturally to them.

For many people, young or old, depression has long been an "invisible illness." However, the way social media pushes young people to communicate behind a mask of perfection produces a smokescreen that even the most understanding parents and friends frequently are unable to see through. Although the majority of specialists do not think that social media by itself may cause depression, it is increasingly clear that social media can help the condition, both by masking its symptoms and by making the depressed person feel worse about themselves. After all, a young person's social media feed serves as a continual reminder of who they believe they "should" be. Looking through their own carefully produced content can engender intense sentiments of living a lie and of never being able to live up to both their own public image and that of others. The cycle of despair and overachieving gets worse the more the young person looks at his or her "ideal self," the less palatable their imperfections appear in comparison (Kaminsky, 2016).

Balance in Body Positivity, self-concept and Inclusivity Movements among undergraduate students

In the attempt to cure negative body image, the body positivity movement actively pushes against unrealistic beauty standards. They aim to end the harmful consequences of negative body image by encouraging the portrayal of realistic beauty standards in the media (Lauren, 2022). The body positivity movement is the type of phenomenon that is intriguing to observe from a sociological perspective. Emile Durkheim (1903) theorized that society is kept together by something called collective consciousness, that is made up of beliefs and morals that are present to a group of people.

The body positivity movement is an example of the collective consciousness of our society shifting and evolving to account for new ideas developing in the social sphere. Many people have been hesitant to support the movement in the misconception that it intentionally contributes to physically unhealthy lifestyles. According to Forbes, the body positivity movement encourages inclusion, not obesity. "Personally, I think the movement is fascinating for the way that people have responded to it (Barrett, et al., 2007). Criticism of the movement is largely from people who are rooted in the collective consciousness surrounding body image and health. Everything that happens in society at a large scale has a systemic structure that needs much more work to change than the minds of individuals. That says something about how compelling the narrative put forward by the body positivity movement must be: it is affecting systemic change, and that is monumental. The inclusion of diverse bodies in media allows viewers to feel comfortable with their own bodies, especially when posting their own content. If people see bodies like theirs in campaigns, magazines, movies, and TV shows, they will accept their bodies to be a new standard of beauty. Therefore, breaking the unrealistic beauty standards of social media by popularizing different body types will produce more positive body image in teens and young adults (Lauren, 2022).

Conclusion

Self-concept and body image are complex, multidimensional problems that are influenced by a range of modern elements, such as social media, cultural norms, and society expectations. With the rise of social media, there is a greater emphasis on body image and a consequent rise in body dissatisfaction, particularly among younger generations such as undergraduate students in Nigeria. People's perceptions of themselves have been profoundly impacted by digital manipulation and the spread of unattainable beauty standards on these platforms, which frequently result in mental health issues.

Nonetheless, countering these harmful norms are movements like inclusion and body positivity, which support diversity, acceptance, and self-love. Maintaining surroundings that support a healthy perspective on body image, one that values mental health, celebrates diversity, and encourages healthy behaviors, both offline and online is critical.

Perception of Body Image... (Kayode, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929025>

However, the body positivity movement is not without its criticisms. Some argue that the movement can unintentionally promote unhealthy lifestyles by normalizing certain conditions, such as obesity, which may be associated with health risks. Despite this, the core intent of the movement remains focused on combating societal pressures that cause body dissatisfaction and promoting psychological well-being.

Recommendations

Some recommendations were made as regards the body image discussed above which are very paramount to mitigate and accentuate more on the scourge of influence of unfiltered social media, invasion of western culture and other factors. Below are some of the recommendations:

- 1. Encourage the teaching of media literacy:** Media literacy initiatives should be incorporated into educational institutions to assist students in evaluating and comprehending the effects of digital content, filters, and photo-editing software. These courses ought to have a strong emphasis on identifying staged photos and unattainable beauty standards in order to promote a more grounded understanding of social media material.
- 2. Encourage positive social media use:** Social media platforms should encourage positive body image content and create guidelines that promote authenticity over curated perfection. This can include policies to label digitally altered images, promote content diversity that showcases various body types, and highlight body-positive influencers.
- 3. Regulate digital manipulation in media and advertising:** Governments and regulatory bodies should consider creating guidelines for digital manipulation in advertising and media, ensuring transparency when images are retouched or manipulated. Such regulations would help reduce unrealistic beauty standards and promote healthier body image perceptions among youth.

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Physiological Responses to Heat Stress: Implications for Training and Performance among Athletes in Nigeria

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Abstract

As the frequency and intensity of heat waves continue to rise in Nigeria, understanding the physiological responses to heat stress becomes crucial for optimizing training, competition, and athlete safety. This research delves into the intricate physiological responses of athletes exposed to heat stress, examining the consequential impact on training adaptation and athletic performance. Acknowledging the fundamental necessity of comprehending the human body's response to heat stress is essential to developing tactics that maximize sports training and performance in various environmental situations. The study further provides a foundation by synthesizing existing knowledge on heat stress, encompassing diverse forms such as environmental and exercise-induced stress. Key physiological responses, including thermoregulation and cardiovascular dynamics, are delineated, setting the stage for an in-depth exploration of their relevance to athletes. Physiological measurements such as core temperature, heart rate, and sweat rate, alongside performance metrics, offer a nuanced understanding of the impact of heat stress on athletes across various modalities. Strategies for heat acclimatization, hydration, and nutrition are explored, providing actionable recommendations for optimizing training and performance in heat-stressed environments. In conclusion, this article contributes valuable insights into the physiological responses of athletes to heat stress, offering practical implications for optimizing training strategies and ultimately enhancing athletic performance in challenging environmental conditions. The review holds relevance not only for the scientific community but also for coaches, athletes, and professionals involved in sports medicine.

Keywords: Physiological responses, Heat stress, Thermoregulation, Training

Introduction

Heat stress is a significant challenge for athletes, impacting their ability to train and compete effectively. When exposed to hot environments, the body initiates a series of physiological responses to maintain core temperature within a safe range. As athletes continually strive for peak performance, understanding the intricate mechanisms by which the human body copes with heat stress becomes paramount (Ojo & Okon, 2019). The human body, a finely tuned instrument of performance, is inherently sensitive to fluctuations in environmental conditions. Heat stress, characterized by elevated ambient temperatures and increased thermal load, poses a unique challenge to athletes across various disciplines. The consequences of inadequate adaptation to heat stress can extend beyond immediate discomfort, influencing physiological processes critical to athletic prowess (Maughan, 2016). The relevance of comprehending physiological responses to heat stress lies in its potential to inform tailored training regimens and enhance performance outcomes. As sporting events frequently unfold in diverse climates, from scorching deserts to humid tropics, athletes and their coaches must navigate the delicate balance between optimizing performance and mitigating the risks associated with heat-related stressors.

The investigation of heat stress in athletes is of paramount importance for both athlete well-being and performance optimization. The significance of understanding and addressing heat stress extends across various dimensions, influencing both immediate concerns and long-term athletic development. In a study by González-Alonso et al. (2012), they emphasize that heat stress can compromise exercise capacity and performance due to increased cardiovascular strain and impaired thermoregulation. It is important to note that any person, athlete, or coach, can be susceptible to exertional heat stress no matter what they are wearing or where they are. In actuality, heat stress is best determined by using the wet bulb globe temperature (WBGT) and considering the ambient temperature, humidity, wind speed, sun angle, and cloud cover at the site of the athletic activity. This is often confused with the heat index, which also looks at temperature and humidity and is calculated for shady

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areas. The most important things to know are being able to identify dangerous conditions with the WBGT, having a heat stress prevention plan, and having the training and tools to help athletes suffering from heat stress if it does happen.

Sweating can lead to dehydration. Proper hydration is essential in preventing heat illness. Drinking water frequently and eating regular meals is usually sufficient for hydration. For sweating that lasts several hours, sports drinks can help replace electrolytes that workers lose when working in hot environments. A study by Sawka et al. (2011) underscores the importance of proper hydration in mitigating the effects of heat stress. Dehydration exacerbates heat strain, emphasizing the need for effective hydration strategies. In a training context, dehydration occurs largely as a consequence of heat stress, or heat load, most of which is endogenous from the thermal energy ('heat') yield of metabolism. Because an athlete's rate of heat production is their metabolic rate minus their work rate ($\dot{H} = \dot{M} - \dot{W}$), the most aerobically powerful athletes are subjected to the most heat stress endogenously. Heat strain can also be incurred or exacerbated by clothing or from characteristics of the environment that impair the gradient for heat loss via convection, radiation and evaporation in particular (e.g., lack of airflow, sunshine and high humidity, respectively). Heat stress itself is almost certainly a principal stressor for both adaptation and acclimation and of more importance than dehydration.

Exposure to heat in amounts exceeding the compensatory mechanisms of thermoregulation leads to physiological insult to the body and heat-related illnesses (HRI), either acute or delayed. Heat-related illnesses range from a mild form, like edema, cramps, or syncope, to severe conditions such as heat exhaustion, syncope, and strokes with or without multi-organ failure. Casa et al. (2017) emphasize the risk of heat-related illnesses, including heat stroke, in athletes during intense physical exertion in hot conditions. Understanding these risks is crucial for preventive measures. Heat-related illnesses are preventable and can be managed effectively; however, the number of morbidities and mortalities associated with heat exposure is increasing with time. Considering global warming and extreme climate events, there are need to assess the preventative techniques, diagnostic criteria, and treatment strategies.

As Nigeria draws close to the dry season, there is a record of malaria and other diseases would be higher in areas with high temperatures in the range of 18 to 32 degrees Celsius associated with high relative humidity above 60 percent precipitation. At the same time, areas covered by thick vegetation that provide environmental conditions conducive to the survival of vectors and the development of malaria parasites were also prone to malaria spread. In 2020, the Nigeria Meteorological Agency (NiMet), had earlier warned of climate-induced diseases such as malaria, cerebrospinal meningitis, and respiratory diseases in many parts of Nigeria. It said states that require vigilance include: the coastal cities of Lagos, Abakiliki, Eket, Calabar, Ogun, Ondo, Owerri, Ebonyi, parts of Kogi, Cross River, Benue, Osun, Delta, Kwara, Niger, Nassarawa, Benue, Plateau and Taraba states. On cerebrospinal meningitis, NiMet disclosed that low relative humidity, high temperatures, dry northeasterly winds, and surface dust conditions would encourage the spread of the disease up to mid-March.

The nature of the sport further modulates the effects of heat stress. Research by Bergeron (2014) emphasizes the distinct challenges posed by heat stress in team sports, where intermittent activity and frequent gear usage contribute to increased heat load. Endurance athletes, such as cyclists and distance runners, are particularly susceptible to heat stress. Ojo (2020), reported that elevated temperatures lead to reduced exercise capacity and increased perceived exertion in endurance events. Team sports, including soccer and basketball, involve intermittent high-intensity efforts which lead to the cumulative effects of heat stress on performance.

Conceptualization of the problem

In the context of athletic performance, particularly in regions with extreme environmental conditions like Nigeria, the issue of heat stress presents a significant challenge. The body's response to prolonged exposure to high temperatures can lead to various physiological strains, including dehydration, elevated core body temperature, and impaired cardiovascular function. These responses not only affect an athlete's immediate performance but also have long-term implications for their health and ability to train effectively. The issue at hand has several facets. On the one hand, knowledge of the physiological reactions of Nigerian athletes to heat stress during training and competition is necessary. This entails investigating how an athlete's susceptibility to heat stress is influenced by variables like age, gender, level of fitness, and sport. Furthermore, gaining a knowledge of the athletes' subjective experiences during hot training might help shed light on the difficulties they encounter and how they interpret the effects of heat on their physical and mental abilities.

Moreover, the problem extends to the strategies currently employed by coaches and sports organizations in Nigeria to mitigate the effects of heat stress. This includes examining the effectiveness of existing training regimens, hydration protocols, and recovery practices designed to help athletes acclimatize to heat. The study seeks to identify gaps in knowledge and practice that may be hindering optimal performance and increasing the risk of heat-related illnesses.

Theoretical Perspectives to the Problem

Heat acclimatization theory to athletes was reviewed in this article. Heat acclimatization is a physiological process where the body adapts to repeated exposure to high temperatures, enhancing its ability to perform under heat stress. For athletes in Nigeria, a country characterized by hot and humid conditions, understanding and applying heat acclimatization theory is crucial for optimizing performance. When athletes undergo heat acclimatization, their bodies undergo several adaptations, such as improved sweat response, increased plasma volume, and more efficient thermoregulation (Casa et al., 2015). These adaptations allow the body to better manage the stress of heat, leading to improved endurance, reduced risk of heat-related illnesses, and enhanced overall performance during training and competition in hot environments.

In the context of Nigerian athletes, the implications of heat acclimatization are significant. Nigeria's climate, with its high temperatures and humidity, presents a unique challenge to athletes, especially those involved in outdoor sports. Without a proper acclimatization, athletes may experience heat exhaustion, dehydration, and reduced performance. However, with a well-planned acclimatization protocol, which typically involves progressive exposure to heat over 1-2 weeks, athletes can improve their physiological responses, allowing them to train more effectively and perform optimally in their respective sports. Moreover, heat acclimatization is not only beneficial for enhancing performance in Nigeria but also crucial for athletes who compete internationally. Nigerian athletes who are accustomed to training in cooler climates may face significant challenges when competing in hotter regions. Therefore, incorporating heat acclimatization into their training regimen can prepare them for a wide range of environmental conditions, giving them a competitive edge on the global stage.

Physiological Adaptations among Athletes in Nigeria

Athletes in Nigeria experience significant cardiovascular adaptations that are crucial for enhancing their performance, particularly in endurance sports like long-distance running. These adaptations include increased cardiac output and enhanced capillary density in the muscles, both of which improve oxygen delivery and waste removal during prolonged physical activity. Studies indicate that athletes who regularly engage in endurance training exhibit a higher stroke volume and lower resting heart rate, which contribute to their sustained performance levels (Olanrewaju & Akinola, 2019).

In addition to cardiovascular changes, Nigerian athletes, especially sprinters and powerlifters, undergo muscle fiber specialization. This adaptation involves an increased proportion of fast-twitch muscle fibers which are essential for explosive strength and speed. Research shows that these athletes demonstrate superior anaerobic capacity and muscle hypertrophy, allowing them to excel in high-intensity sports (Ojo, 2020). The ability to efficiently recruit fast-twitch fibers enables quicker and more powerful movements, which are critical for success in sports like sprinting.

Another critical adaptation is in thermoregulation, particularly for athletes training in the hotter regions of Nigeria. Regular exposure to high temperatures leads to improved sweat gland function and a more efficient cooling system. These changes help athletes manage heat stress during training and competitions, reducing the risk of heat-related illnesses. The body's enhanced ability to regulate temperature ensures that athletes maintain optimal performance even under extreme environmental conditions.

Lastly, metabolic adaptations play a significant role in the performance of Nigerian athletes, especially in endurance sports. These athletes typically exhibit increased aerobic capacity and a greater ability to oxidize fats during prolonged physical activity. This metabolic efficiency helps conserve glycogen stores and delays fatigue, which is vital for sustaining energy over long durations (Oluwaseun et al., 2022). Such adaptations are crucial for athletes competing in events that require stamina and endurance. These physiological adaptations, driven by both the specific demands of different sports and the environmental conditions in Nigeria, are key to the success of Nigerian athletes on both national and international stages.

Time Course of Acclimatization among athletes in Nigeria

Acclimatization is a crucial process for athletes, particularly in Nigeria, where diverse climatic conditions pose unique challenges. The time course of acclimatization varies depending on the athlete's exposure to different environmental stressors, such as heat and altitude. Generally, acclimatization to hot environments begins within a few days of exposure, with significant physiological adaptations occurring within 7 to 14 days. These adaptations include improved sweat production, reduced heart rate, and enhanced skin blood flow, all of which help athletes manage heat stress more effectively (Adebayo & Ogunsanya, 2020).

The initial phase of acclimatization involves the body's immediate response to heat, which includes an increase in core temperature and sweat rate. However, with continued exposure, the body gradually adjusts, leading to a lower core temperature during exercise and more efficient thermoregulation. Studies conducted on Nigerian athletes have shown that after about one week of training in hot conditions, there is a marked improvement in sweat response and a reduction in perceived exertion during exercise, indicating successful acclimatization (Ezenwa & Akintoye, 2021). For athletes training or competing at high altitudes, the acclimatization process can be more prolonged. Acclimatization to altitude typically requires two to three weeks,

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during which the body undergoes several key adaptations. These include an increase in red blood cell production, which enhances oxygen-carrying capacity, and improved ventilation efficiency. Research on Nigerian athletes who trained at altitude shows that these physiological changes are critical for maintaining performance, especially in endurance events. However, full acclimatization may take up to a month or longer, depending on the altitude and individual variability (Oluwaseun et al., 2022).

Moreover, the time course of acclimatization is influenced by factors such as the intensity of training, the athlete's fitness level, and prior experience with similar environmental conditions. For example, athletes who have previously trained in hot or high-altitude environments may acclimatize more quickly than those with no prior exposure (Adedoyin & Akinbo, 2019).

Practical Implications of heat stress among athletes in Nigeria

Heat stress poses significant challenges to athletes in Nigeria, particularly given the country's hot and humid climate. The practical implications of heat stress are wide-ranging and impact both the performance and safety of athletes. One of the most immediate effects is decreased athletic performance. As body temperature rises during exercise in hot conditions, athletes may experience increased fatigue, reduced endurance, and impaired cognitive function. These effects can lead to slower reaction times, decreased coordination, and a higher likelihood of mistakes during competition, which are critical in sports that require precision and quick decision-making.

In addition to performance issues, heat stress significantly raises the risk of heat-related illnesses, such as heat exhaustion and heat stroke. These conditions are particularly dangerous and can be life-threatening if not managed properly. Athletes in Nigeria, especially those engaging in intense physical activity in direct sunlight, are at heightened risk. Symptoms of heat exhaustion, such as dizziness, nausea, and excessive sweating, can rapidly progress to heat stroke if the body's cooling mechanisms fail. This underscores the importance of adequate hydration, proper acclimatization, and access to cool environments during training and competition.

The long-term health implications of repeated heat stress exposure should also be considered. Chronic exposure to high temperatures without adequate recovery can lead to cumulative stress on the cardiovascular system, increasing the risk of cardiovascular events. For young athletes, there is also the concern that ongoing heat stress could impact growth and development, particularly if it leads to frequent dehydration and electrolyte imbalances (Oluwaseun et al., 2022). Therefore, it is crucial to monitor and manage athletes' exposure to heat stress to protect their long-term health and athletic careers. Coaches and sports administrators in Nigeria must take proactive measures to mitigate the effects of heat stress. This includes scheduling training sessions during cooler parts of the day, ensuring athletes are well-hydrated before, during, and after exercise, and providing sufficient rest periods to allow for thermal recovery.

Significance of investigating heat stress for athlete well-being and performance in Nigeria

Investigating heat stress is critically important for the well-being and performance of athletes in Nigeria due to the country's predominantly hot and humid climate. Understanding the physiological impacts of heat stress is essential for optimizing athletic performance. When athletes are exposed to high temperatures, their bodies must work harder to regulate internal temperatures, often leading to increased fatigue, dehydration, and reduced endurance. By investigating how heat stress affects these physiological processes, sports scientists and coaches can develop tailored training programs that help athletes adapt more effectively to heat, thereby maintaining peak performance even in challenging environmental conditions (Adebayo & Ogunsanya, 2020).

Moreover, protecting athlete health is a primary reason for studying heat stress. Prolonged exposure to high temperatures without adequate recovery can lead to serious health issues, such as heat exhaustion, heat stroke, and even long-term cardiovascular strain. Understanding the early signs and risk factors associated with heat stress can enable timely interventions that prevent these conditions from escalating. This is particularly important in Nigeria, where athletes often train and compete in outdoor environments with limited access to cooling facilities. Research in this area can guide the implementation of effective hydration strategies, proper clothing choices, and scheduling of activities during cooler times of the day, all of which are crucial for safeguarding athlete health.

Another significant aspect of investigating heat stress is its role in preventing injuries and ensuring longevity in sports. Heat stress not only affects immediate performance but can also increase the risk of injuries due to fatigue and impaired judgment. For instance, athletes who are overheated may be more prone to muscle strains, cramps, or even more severe injuries due to decreased coordination and reaction times. By thoroughly understanding how heat impacts athletic performance and injury risk, sports professionals in Nigeria can design training regimens that minimize these risks, helping athletes maintain longer and healthier careers;

Finally, research into heat stress has broader implications for sports policy and infrastructure development in Nigeria. Insights gained from studies can inform national sports policies, leading to the construction of better-equipped training facilities with appropriate cooling systems, the provision of adequate medical support during competitions, and the development of

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guidelines for safe training practices in hot climates. Such policies are vital for ensuring that athletes at all levels, from grassroots to elite, can train and compete safely and effectively, ultimately contributing to the country's success in international sports.

Physiological Responses to Heat Stress among athletes in Nigeria

Athletes in Nigeria experience several physiological responses to heat stress due to the country's warm climate. These responses are the body's natural mechanisms to cope with increased temperatures during physical activity and include adjustments in cardiovascular function, thermoregulation, and metabolic processes. One of the primary physiological responses to heat stress is increased cardiovascular strain. As the body heats up, the heart must work harder to pump blood to the skin's surface to dissipate heat through sweat. This results in an elevated heart rate and reduced stroke volume, meaning the heart pumps less blood with each beat. Consequently, the body compensates by increasing the heart rate to maintain adequate blood flow to both working muscles and the skin. However, this places additional strain on the cardiovascular system, which can lead to earlier onset of fatigue and decreased endurance (Adebayo & Ogunsanya, 2020).

Thermoregulation is another critical response to heat stress. The body regulates its temperature primarily through sweating and increased blood flow to the skin. In the hot and humid conditions often found in Nigeria, athletes may experience a significant increase in sweat production as the body attempts to cool itself. However, in high humidity, the evaporation of sweat is less efficient, leading to a higher risk of dehydration and heat-related illnesses. The combination of excessive sweating and inadequate fluid replacement can result in a significant loss of electrolytes, further compromising performance and increasing the risk of conditions such as heat exhaustion and heat stroke (Ezenwa & Akintoye, 2021).

Metabolic responses are also influenced by heat stress. When exposed to high temperatures, the body shifts its energy metabolism. There is an increased reliance on carbohydrates as the primary fuel source because they are metabolized more efficiently than fats in hot conditions. However, this can lead to quicker depletion of glycogen stores, reducing the athlete's ability to sustain prolonged physical activity. Moreover, elevated body temperatures can impair muscle function and coordination, leading to a decline in overall performance (Oluwaseun et al., 2022). Hormonal changes also occur in response to heat stress. For example, the body may increase the secretion of aldosterone and antidiuretic hormone (ADH) to help retain sodium and water, which are lost through sweat. These hormonal adjustments are vital for maintaining fluid balance and blood pressure during prolonged exposure to heat. However, if the heat stress is severe or prolonged, the body's capacity to manage these changes can be overwhelmed, leading to significant health risks.

Implications for Sports Performance among Athletes in Nigeria

One of the most direct implications of the hot climate in Nigeria is a reduction in endurance and overall athletic performance. As body temperature rises, the cardiovascular system becomes increasingly strained, with a higher heart rate and reduced stroke volume. This cardiovascular strain can lead to the early onset of fatigue, reduced stamina, and slower recovery times. For endurance athletes, such as long-distance runners or football players, this can severely impact performance, as their bodies are less able to sustain prolonged physical activity at high intensities (Adebayo & Ogunsanya, 2020). The risk of heat-related illnesses, such as heat exhaustion and heat stroke, is significantly heightened in Nigeria's hot climate. Athletes training or competing in high temperatures without adequate acclimatization or hydration are particularly vulnerable. These conditions not only jeopardize performance but also pose serious health risks. Coaches and sports organizations must implement strategies to monitor and manage heat stress to prevent these illnesses, which can have long-term consequences on an athlete's career.

Heat stress can also impair cognitive and motor functions, leading to decreased concentration, slower reaction times, and impaired decision-making. These effects are particularly detrimental in sports that require quick reflexes, strategic thinking, and precise movements, such as basketball, tennis, and combat sports. The combination of physical fatigue and cognitive decline can result in more errors, increased injury risk, and lower overall performance (Oluwaseun et al., 2022). The high temperatures in Nigeria can also complicate recovery and adaptation processes. Athletes need adequate recovery to repair muscles and restore energy levels after intense training sessions. However, excessive heat can prolong recovery times, as the body must expend additional energy on thermoregulation. This can lead to cumulative fatigue, reduced training effectiveness, and increased risk of overtraining. Moreover, the body's ability to adapt to training stimuli may be compromised, making it more challenging for athletes to achieve desired performance improvements.

Despite these challenges, there is also potential for performance gains if athletes properly acclimatize to the heat. Studies have shown that with gradual exposure to high temperatures, athletes can improve their heat tolerance, enhance sweat response, and increase plasma volume, all of which contribute to better performance in hot conditions. For Nigerian athletes, developing effective acclimatization strategies is crucial for maximizing their performance both domestically and in international competitions held in similar climates.

Conclusion

Understanding heat stress in athletes is necessary with implications from performance, safety, and long-term athlete development. The cited studies collectively emphasize the need for personalized approaches, effective hydration strategies, and a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between environmental conditions and physiological responses to heat stress. This knowledge is vital for coaches, athletes, and sports medicine professionals to implement evidence-based practices and safeguard the well-being of athletes in diverse sporting contexts. The Heat Acclimatization Theory provides a foundational understanding of how the human body adapts to heat stress. Recognizing the importance of this adaptive process is crucial for athletes, coaches, and sports medicine professionals seeking to optimize performance and mitigate the negative effects of heat stress in various athletic contexts. Therefore, understanding the physiological mechanisms, influencing factors and implications for performance is essential for developing effective hydration and electrolyte replacement strategies to support athlete health and optimize performance.

Recommendations

1. Maintaining proper hydration is crucial for athletes training or competing in hot conditions.
2. There is a need to implement a structured acclimatization program where athletes gradually increase their time spent training in the heat for 7-14 days.
3. Research should delve into the factors influencing why some athletes may be more resilient to heat stress than others, considering aspects such as genetics, acclimatization history, and fitness levels.

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Influence of working-class mothers... (Amede, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929155>

Influence of Working-Class Mothers on Academic Performance of Primary School Pupils in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of working-class mothers on the academic performance of primary school pupils in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Three research question and three corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study and the population consisted of all primary schools' working-class mothers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Random sampling method was adopted in selecting 17 primary schools in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Purposive sampling approach was used to select 10 working-class mothers from each of the school chosen for the study thereby giving a sample size of 170 working-class mothers. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire titled: Influence of Working-Class Mothers Inventory (IWCMI). Validity of the research instrument was done by experts, suggestions made were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument. Reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Descriptive statistics were used to answer the research questions while Independent Sample Test (IST) and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation statistics were used to test the hypotheses. The outcome of the study revealed, among others, that the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance is high. Conclusion was reached and useful recommendation made which included that working-class mothers should be selective in their choice of job to reduce the influences of careers on pupils' academic performance.

Keywords: working class mothers, pupils, academic performance

Introduction

Traditional family roles are changing as democratic notions sink into the social system. Earlier, it was assumed that man was the main provider in the family and that the rudimentary social roles of mothers are to bear and raise children. However, mothers are beginning to realize that there is a world outside their kitchen windows (Lavanya, 2022). The major social change in the twentieth century was the entrance of mothers into the world of work. Significant social and personal adjustments are therefore necessary for working-class mothers to cope with such changes in their career parts.

One could define a working-mother as a woman with the ability to combine a vocation with the additional responsibility of raising children. The broad term may encompass two different categories of working women: the stay at a home mother who works from home and the woman who works away from home while managing to fulfill her maternal duties (Lavanya, 2022).

World Bank (2024) reported female labor force (% of total labor force) in Nigeria to be 43.89 % in 2022. In 2023, the labor force participation rate for the female population in Nigeria was estimated at slightly over 52 percent. That year, the labor force participation rate reached nearly 57 percent for mothers 15 years or older (Sasu, 2023), most of them with children and, or husband at home.

Material aspirations and the necessities of daily life often compel both parents to work. Improved educational opportunities for mothers have led to rapid increase in the number of employed mothers both in public and private sectors. A qualified woman may insist on working to maintain an effective career and be financially independent. The single working mother is a combination of these entities, working not only to run the family but also to maintain her position as a financially independent head of the family (Lavanya, 2022). Mothers are also turning out in large numbers in the workforce due to economic necessity. While people may be willing to accept the idea of career women, they are not willing to excuse them from their duties as career moms (Lavanya, 2022). The economic downturn, the desire for career pursuance, and global advocacy for gender equality have all contributed to an increase in the number and percentage of mothers in the labour force (Dimkpa, 2010; Ajala, 2017). These variables are the result of women's desires for financial independence, self-worth, and, most

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importantly, the dismantling of the ingrained notion of the "glass ceiling" that prohibits them from holding professional positions (Agarwal & Lenka, 2015; Rajora, 2019; Young et al., 2021).

The socioeconomic statuses of employed mothers usually influence primary school pupils' academic performances. Igube and Ejaro (2003) investigated the influence of working-class mothers, family instability and children's education, and discovered that working class mothers often neglect primary school pupils' welfare as a result of their careers. According to them, about one-third of the working-class mothers' children suffered as a result of this neglect, and that it is a matter of concern that about 22 percent of the pupils experienced health problems due to mothers' neglect, and poor nutrition often results in ill health. The combination of poor feeding and ill health are likely to have a negative impact on the children's education.

A study by Nomaguchi and Milkie (2006) examined whether or not people's perceptions of their parents was affected by their mother's employment (or lack thereof) during their childhood. Regardless of hours worked, children of mothers who worked reported less discipline from their mothers than those whose mothers did not work outside the home. Those with working class mothers also reported less support and more verbal assaults than those whose mothers did not work (Nomaguchi and Milkie, 2006). A study by Gennetian, Lopoo, and London (2008) used statistics gathered in a survey of urban mothers to assess how mothers' work affected adolescents' school performance and participation in school-related activities. They found that children of stay-at-home mothers were more likely to have above average school performance and to skip school than children of non-working class.

In most developing countries, such as Nigeria, employment relationships are structured according to gender norms, resulting in the disproportionate subjugation of mothers because men are socialized to be breadwinners, while mothers are always expected to care for the home (Abubakar, 2018). Now that many of these mothers have paid jobs, they have not abandoned their roles in their families (Kayode, Ojo, & Adeoye, 2012; Nnubia & Okechukwu, 2022), and these cause some situations such as overloading of roles. Even if they do not work outside the home, mothers are likely to be strained by household tasks, motherhood, and being a wife (Hegewisch & DuMonthier, 2016; Rajgariah, Chandrashekar Appa, Babu, Gopi, Ramaiha, & Kumar, 2021). Conversely, the burden of dual full-time work, working mother's physical, emotional, and mental well-being, as well as their productivity, is negatively impacted by gender norms at home and at work (Roberts, 2014; Uwannah, Egwuonwu & James, 2022) thereby, making them to be more vulnerable to pressures resulting from perceived "maternal walls," which limit their job options once they have children (Thakur, Bansal. & Maini, 2018).

According to Ademuyiwa, Dahunsi, Adetunji and Adeniran (2022), mothers' dual roles are often in conflict with one another because they divide their time and energy between the two spheres of activity. Work-family conflict can as well be exacerbated by long working hours, inflexibility, and a less pleasant work environment, particularly in the lives of working mothers whose children are poorly spaced and are of school age (Lupu et al., 2018; Owodunni, 2022). Working mothers who were exhausted have little or no time to care for themselves as a result of the conflict between work and family life (De Ravindranath, Karter-Sing, Arumugam, & Kularajasing, 2021). Ajala (2017) also noted that a typical working mother or career woman experiences conflicting role expectations while at work and at home, including having to manage primary school pupils' tasks, careers, and social circles, which present them with challenges.

Working moms in Nigeria feels they are being forced back to work too early, risking their and their babies' health (Lawal, 2022). Mother's job stress, long working hours, and lack of sleep may cause poor quality of time spend with her child (Gordon, 2007; Amede, 2017). Stephiana, et al., (2019) conducted a study to analyses the possible effects of maternal employment on child growth in the early period of life (0-3 years) and found that the higher was the cognitive score; the lower was the average mother's working hours. She concluded that mother's presence at home, focus on the family and children at early period of child's growth years can improve child growth and quality of children's development. The cognitive effects could still be seen by age seven or eight. Mothers, in spite of having their kid's best interests at heart, might fail to provide them with safe emotional outlet when professionally engaged with jobs (Metilda & Meheswariet, 2015; Amede, 2023).

Papalia and Martorell (2014) discovered that the interaction between mother and child has a direct impact on child's cognitive development. Simen (2022) listed 6 ways to balance life as working mothers to include have an answer for "why, clarify what "mom" means to you, invest in good help, look for the energy traps among others. Ofei, Kwashie., Asiedua, Serwaa and Akotiah (2018) discovered that time management and priority setting would help working mothers cope with the demands of their jobs. Bakker and de Vries, (2021) note that organizational resources such as human resource practices which may include employing social workers and also having a counselling unit in the organization will help mothers to cope better with stress

Influence of working-class mothers... (Amede, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929155>

Empirical studies reviewed so far on this theme had revealed contradictory conclusions. This made this study necessary to carry out similar research in a unique environment to see whether the findings would support or contradicts the existing knowledge. This study therefore examined the influence of working-class mothers on academic performance of primary school pupils in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Throughout history mothers have been regarded as the weaker gender, both physically and intellectually. As a result, women's roles tended to center around the home and raising children. Over time mother shave gradually entered the workforce and have gained increasingly prestigious positions. With more mothers currently in the workforce than ever before, fewer children are being raised by stay-at-home mothers and more are spending prolonged hours at childcare facilities.

Children with working class mothers are usually placed in group childcare, which results in reduced maternal attachment and poor mental development. This may have significant cognitive and affective deficit later in childhood. Working class mothers has contributed to lack of proper motherly care which results at times to permanent physical handicap, deprived cognitive and moral development, poor language formation and inadequate communication skills. The purpose of this study therefore was to examine the influence of working-class mothers on academic performance of primary school pupils in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Objective of the Study

The study examined the influence of working-class mothers on academic performance of primary school pupils in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Specific objectives include to:

1. Assess the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.
2. Determine the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed.
3. Investigate the solution to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State
4. Evaluate the difference between job status of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.
5. Examine the difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.
6. Investigate the relationship between age job status, age stratifications and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State?
2. What are the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed?
3. What are the solution to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significance difference between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.
2. There is no significance difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.
3. There is no significance relationship between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Influence of working-class mothers... (Amede, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929155>

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey design to examine the study variables. Descriptive survey design allows the researcher to gather information, summarize, present and construe for the purpose of clarification. In this study the population consisted of all primary schools’ staff, including working class mothers out of the available 300 in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Random sampling method was adopted in selecting 17 primary schools out of the existing 39 while purposive sampling approach was used to select 10 working class mothers from each of the school depicted for the study, giving a sample size of 170 participants. This sample size was adequate because according to Asika (1991), 10% element selected randomly from a population is to all intents and purposes deemed to be representative of the population and the findings from a study of that sample can be generalized for the population.

The instrument for the study was: Influence of Working-Class Mothers Inventory (IWCMI). The inventory was designed by the researcher and divided into four sections. A sought for the demographic data of respondents, Section B sought information relating to impact of working-class mothers on pupils’ academic performance, Section C deals with factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed while Section D addresses issues on the solution to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils’ academic performance The questionnaire adopted 4-point scale. The weighted mean of 2.5 was used as the bench mark for assessing the instrument.

To determine the validity of the research instruments, the inventory was validated by experts in the field of education, and suggestions made were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument to ensure its validity. The instrument used was trial-tested with twenty (20) staff in Ndokwa west Local Government Area of Delta State, which was outside the original sample population and their responses collected. Reliability coefficient obtained of 0.87 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

The questionnaire was personally administered to the respondents and subsequently collected. However, 160 (constituted 95%) of the 170 questionnaires administered were retrieved and utilized for data analysis. The data collected were analyzed with descriptive statistics, Independent Sample Test (IST) and the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation statistics. Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant levels.

Results

Research questions 1: What are the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils’ academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State?

S/N	Impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils’ academic performance	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Q1	Lack of quality time with primary school pupils at home to encourage academic growth.	160	497.00	3.1063	.30912	Agreed
Q2	Career mothers hardly pay attention to children nutritional needs that enhance their cognitive development.	160	497.00	3.1063	.30912	Agreed
Q3	Working class mothers hardly satisfy the emotional needs of primary school pupils	160	499.00	3.1188	.32451	Agreed
Q4	Career mothers seldom teach primary school pupils at home	160	491.00	3.0688	.31963	Agreed
Q5	Working class mothers’ denial children of some rights and opportunities for to excel in school	160	501.00	3.1312	.33873	Agreed
Q6	vocational mothers hardly ever attend school PTA meetings to contribute to school welfare	160	491.00	3.0688	.29930	Agreed
Q7	Improper models to children affect children morals	160	492.00	3.0750	.30817	Agreed
Q8	Indiscipline encourages anti-social behaviour in schools	160	486.00	3.0375	.24795	Agreed
Q9	Deprivations of maternal attachment affect children self-concept in class activities	160	486.00	3.0375	.29434	Agreed
Q10	Working class mothers have little time moderate primary school pupils peer relations	160	447.00	2.7937	.65490	Agreed
	Total	1600	4887	3.05	.34	Agreed

Influence of working-class mothers... (Amede, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929155>

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

Source: Field work, 2024

Table 1 revealed the descriptive statistics on the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The total score is 4887; an average score of 3.05 and Standard Deviation of .34. The total average is 3.05, is above the weighted mean of 2.5. The implication is that the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State is high.

Research Question 2: What are the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed?

Table 2: Mean rating on the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed

S/N	Factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Q11	Inadequate time to attend family events due to their busy schedules	160	490.00	3.0625	.24282	Agreed
Q12	Working class mothers are often tired and stressed up	160	501.00	3.1312	.33873	Agreed
Q13	They often suffer financial constraints	160	499.00	3.1188	.32451	Agreed
Q14	They are also prone to health issues	160	444.00	2.7750	.54887	Agreed
Q15	Susceptible to expensive child care	160	490.00	3.0625	.24282	Agreed
Q16	Suffer from gender discrimination	160	444.00	2.7750	.62395	Agreed
Q17	Disparity in salaries in favour of the male counterpart	160	484.00	3.0250	.31623	Agreed
Q18	Physical and mental attack	160	484.00	3.0250	.35378	Agreed
Q19	Insufficient maternity leave	160	468.00	2.9250	.34659	Agreed
Q20	Fixed working hours	160	454.00	2.8375	.51258	Agreed
	Total	160	4758	2.97	.39	Agreed

Source: Field work, 2024

Table 2 revealed mean rating on the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed. Working class mothers are often tired and stressed up tops the list with a mean of 3.13, followed by They often suffer financial constraints, closely followed by inadequate time to attend family events due to their busy schedules, and Susceptible to expensive child care, Physical and mental attack, insufficient maternity leave and fixed working hours with mean scores of 3.11, 3.06, 3.02, 2.93 and 2.84 respectively. The total average is 2.97, is above the bench mark of 2.5. The implication is that there are many factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed.

Research question 3: What are the solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on the solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

S/N	Solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Q21	Accepting types job that create time for the family.	160	458.00	2.8625	.46901	Agreed
Q22	Maintaining regular communication with children to determine areas of needs	160	491.00	3.0688	.29930	Agreed
Q23	Checking children class work regularly	160	476.00	2.9750	.27357	Agreed
Q24	Ensuring proper discipline on children	160	493.00	3.0813	.35416	Agreed
Q25	Accepting jobs that are of close proximity to residential homes	160	494.00	3.0975	.42154	Agreed
Q26	time management and priority	160	444.00	2.7750	.54887	Agreed
Q27	Ask for maternal leave when necessary	160	498.00	3.1125	.24282	Agreed

Influence of working-class mothers... (Amede, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929155>

Q28	Share your concerns with managers, co-worker and friends	160	459.00	2.8750	.62395	Agreed
Q29	Hiring home teachers to children after school hours	160	484.00	3.0250	.31623	Agreed
Q30	Moderating peer influence on children	160	484.00	3.0250	.35378	Agreed
Total		160	4781	2.99	.39	

Source: Field work, 2024

Table 3 revealed the Descriptive statistics on the solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The total score is 4781; average score of 2.99 and standard Deviation of .39. The total average is 2.99, is above the bench mark of 2.5. The implication is that there are numerous the solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significance difference between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Table 4: T-test analysis on the difference between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	T	Sig.
Full-time	108	1.2778	.44999	.04330	158	12.62	.000
Part-time	52	2.2115	.41238	.05719			

At .05 significant level. Source:

Source: Field work, 2024

The result in Table 4 above revealed a t-test statistics on the between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State., at t (-12.62, df= 158, P<05. The null hypothesis 1 which states that there is no significance difference between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State was therefore rejected. The implication is that there is a significant difference between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State as indicated in their mean proximity of 1.28 and 2.21 for full time and part-time working-class mothers respectively.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significance difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Table 5: Descriptive statistic on the difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Min	Max
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
20-30years	78	1.00	0.00000	0.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.00	1.00
31-40years	71	1.58	0.49748	0.0590	1.4597	1.6952	1.00	2.00
41years and above	11	2.00	0.00000	0.0000	2.0000	2.0000	2.00	2.00
Total	160	1.33	0.46985	0.0371	1.2516	1.3984	1.00	2.00

Source: Field work, 2024

Table 5 above depicts a Descriptive statistic on the difference between the age stratification of working-class mothers on children academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The table gives categories of age stratification of working-class mothers into 20-30years, 31-40years and 41years and above. A total of 160 working class mothers participated in the study. Out of this figure, 78 of them were within the range of 20-30years, 71 were of 31-40years

Influence of working-class mothers... (Amede, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929155>

and 11 were of 41years and above. The mean scores for the 20-30years, 31-40years and 41years and above are 1.00, 1.58 and 2.00 respectively; with a total mean score of 1.33.

Table 6: One-way ANOVA statistic on the difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

Status	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	17.776	2	8.888	80.549	.000
Within Groups	17.324	157	.110		
Total	35.100	159			

05 level of significant.

Source: Field work, 2024

The one-way ANOVA statistics revealed a significant difference between groups and within groups as shown in Table 6 above with F (80.549= df, 2/159, p = .000. The hypothesis which states that there is no significance difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State was therefore rejected. A posteriori in Table 4.11 was tested to determine the degree of differences between the categories of age stratifications. The mean differences for 20-30years are .58 and 1.00 to 31-40years and 41years and above respectively. 31-40years differ by .58 and .42 to 20-30years and 41years and above respectively while 41years and above differences to 20-30years and 31-40years are 1.00 and .42 respectively. The implication is that there is a significance difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Table 7: Tukey HSD Multiple Comparisons on the difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significance relationship between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-

(I) Age	(J) Age	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
20-30years	31-40years	-.57746*	.05449	.000	-.7064	-.4485
	41years and above	-1.00000*	.10699	.000	-1.2531	-.7469
31-40years	20-30years	.57746*	.05449	.000	.4485	.7064
	41years and above	-.42254*	.10764	.000	-.6772	-.1679
41years and above	20-30years	1.00000*	.10699	.000	.7469	1.2531
	31-40years	.42254*	.10764	.000	.1679	.6772

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Source: Field work, 2024

class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Table 8: Pearson Correlation on the relationship between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

		Status	Age	Qualifications
Status	Pearson Correlation	1	.709**	.604**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	160	160	160
Age	Pearson Correlation	.709**	1	.646**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	160	160	160
Qualifications	Pearson Correlation	.604**	.646**	1

Influence of working-class mothers... (Amede, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929155>

Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
N	160	160	160

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field work, 2024

A Pearson product-moment correlation was run to determine the relationship between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The analysis revealed a positive correlation between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State, which was statistically significant ($r = .604^{**}$, $n = 160$, $p = .001$). The implication is that there is a positive correlation between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

Discussion of Findings.

Research question 1 sought to determine the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The analysis concluded that the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State is high. This finding concurred with the views of Han, Waldfogel, and Brooks-Gunn (2001) who found that mothers entering the workforce, and that maternal employment in the first year of a child's life had a negative effect on cognitive outcomes for the child by age three or four. Children of employed mothers were also found to be more likely to skip school than children of non-working-class mothers (Gennetian, Lopoo, and London, 2008). Mother's job stress, long working hours, and lack of sleep may cause poor quality of time spend with her child (Gordon, 2007). Moreover, the child may start arguing with the family members on nominal things and turn rebellious and rude in nature (Almani et al., 2012). Stephiana, et al., (2019) conducted a study to establish the possible effects of maternal employment on child growth in the early period of life (0-3 years) and found that the higher was the cognitive score, the lower was the average mother's working hours. She concluded that mother's presence at home, focus on the family and children at early period of child's growth years can improve child growth and quality of children's development.

Research question 2 states: What are the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed? The study revealed that there are many factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed. The outcome of the study agreed with Roberts (2014) and Uwannah et al, (2022) who observed that burden of dual full-time work, working mother's physical, emotional, and mental well-being, as well as their productivity, is negatively impacted by gender norms at home and at work thereby making them to be more vulnerable to pressures resulting from perceived "maternal walls," which limit their job options once they have children (Thakur et al., 2018). According to Ademuyiwa et al., (2022), mothers' dual roles are often in conflict with one another because they divide their time and energy between the two spheres of activity. Work-family conflict can as well be exacerbated by long working hours, inflexibility, and a less pleasant work environment, particularly in the lives of working mothers whose children are poorly spaced and are of school age (Lupu et al., 2018; Owodunni, 2022). Working mothers who were exhausted have little or no time to care for themselves as a result of the conflict between work and family life (De Ravindranath et al., 2021). Pareja and Lewis (2006) noted that factors exogenous to the school, such as family background characteristics in general and mothers' employment in particular, have been and continue to be extremely important attributes in determining poor pupils' academic outcomes. Igube and Ejaro (2003) investigated the influence between working class mothers, family instability and children's education, and discovered that working class mothers tended to neglect primary school pupils' welfare as a result of their work life.

Research question 3 sought to determine the solution to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The finding showed the there are numerous solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The finding buttresses the position of Papalia & Martorell (2014) who discovered that the interaction between mother and child has a direct impact on child's cognitive development. Simen (2022)

Influence of working-class mothers... (Amede, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929155>

listed 6 ways to balance life as working mothers to include have an answer for “why, clarify what “mom” means to you, invest in good help, look for the energy traps among others.

Hypothesis 1 and 2 found significance differences between job statuses of working-class mothers as well as age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils’ academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Full time working mothers were comparatively more depressed than those who worked for part time. According to Pelcovitz (2013), early full-time employment (relative to mothers who were not working outside the home) was associated with later risk for child behavioural difficulties. Mothers, in spite of having their kid’s best interests at heart, might fail to provide their kids a safe emotional outlet when professionally engage with jobs (Metilda & Meheswari, 2015).

Implication for Counselling

The study examined the influence of working-class mothers on primary pupils’ academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The outcome of this study would encourage counsellors to devise strategies to ameliorate the influence of working-class mothers on children academic performance. The outcome of this study would equip counsellors with information needed to organize workshops and seminars for working class mothers to balance career with family affairs and maximize children academic performance.

Conclusion

The outcome of the study revealed that the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils’ academic performance is high. There are many factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed. There are numerous the solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils’ academic performance. There is a significant difference between job statuses and age stratifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils’ academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Also, there is a positive correlation between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils’ academic performance. However, working-class mothers should be selective in their choice of job to reduce the influences of careers on pupils’ academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, recommendations were made:

1. Working-class mothers should be selective in their choice of job to reduce the influences of careers on pupils’ academic performance.
2. Government should increase maternal leave from 3 months to 1 year to ameliorate the influences of working-class mothers on children academic performance
3. Working class mothers should be treated kindly and granted permission whenever requested to attend to their family needs.

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Quality Assurance at the Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria: Principles, Implications and Challenges

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Abstract

The paper is a non-empirical qualitative study that addressed the issues of quality assurance management at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. The study further examined the principles of quality assurance and its implications at Tertiary Level of Education, while attention was given to both internal and external quality assurance mechanisms, the challenges and limitations in educational planning were enumerated. The paper concluded that quality assurance principles have become increasingly important in education planning to ensure that educational institutions provide high-quality programs and services that meet the needs of students and other stakeholders. It was therefore recommended that all Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) should establish Quality Assurance (QA) units to aid the implementation of QA measures.

Keywords: Quality Assurance, Tertiary Education, Principles, Implications and Challenges.

Introduction

Production of goods and services to satisfy the needs of the end-users cannot be achieved without placing a premium on quality assurance (QA). The concept of quality assurance has its root in the manufacturing sector. It can be traced back to the post-scientific management movement pioneered by Frederick Taylor in the 1920s which resulted in improved production at the expense of quality. The scientific management philosophy of Taylor separated the concept of quality assurance and quality control from the workers. In this regard, separate departments in factories were created to check or inspect the produced goods if they met the expected standards (Juran, 1973). As a result, scientists such as W. Edwards Deming in the 1950s began to look for answers on how to improve the quality of the products. Several experiments were conducted and gave rise to the concept of total quality management with emphasis on continuously improving the quality of products and ensuring that quality management became the responsibility of every employee in an organisation, not only the quality control department. On the other hand, it can still be metaphorically be referred to as the industry where there is the production of what will become the tools for the societal advancement, particularly the tertiary institution where studies are carried out to contribute to the growth of the society.

The education sector though may not be a real manufacturing industry in the strict sense of its operations, but a service sector that has adopted the concept of quality management in the form of quality assurance (QA). Quality assurance is synonymous to the type of output released into the society, as higher education ensures that the quality of education being provided meets the set standards and that the graduates who are the products of the education production systems meet the labour market demands. Given this scenario, higher education institutions are mandated to provide higher education following national and regional quality assurance standards and frameworks. To ensure QA and compliance, many governments have established statutory bodies to oversee the quality of higher education. This is in consonance with the reality that if management of all that concerns tertiary educational institutions slips, the ripple effects and the consequences may be huge.

Quality Assurance Management at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

The term quality has been defined in several ways. According to ISO (2015), quality is the degree to which a set of inherent characteristics of an object fulfill requirements (ISO, 2015). Quality refers to the set of inherent properties of an object that allows satisfying stated or implied needs (Geneva Business News, 2014). Requirements could be in form of needs or expectations that are stated, generally implied, or obligatory. In this regard, it can be argued that any product needs to meet expectations, set standards, and more importantly, meet a need. A product can be said to be of good quality if it complies with the requirements specified in the industry and meets the needs of a client.

The concept of quality assurance (QA) can be defined as part of quality management, focused on providing confidence that quality requirements will be fulfilled (ISO, 2015). Quality assurance is all the planned and the education sector though not

Quality Assurance at the Tertiary... (Mba, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929192>

a manufacturing sector, but a service sector has adopted the concept of quality management in the form of quality assurance (QA). Quality assurance is being preached in higher education to ensure that the quality of education being provided meets the set standards and that the graduates who are the products of the education production systems meet the labour market demands. Given this scenario, higher education institutions are mandated to provide higher education following national and regional quality assurance standards and frameworks. To ensure QA and compliance, many governments have established statutory bodies to oversee the quality of higher education. In Nigeria, the Higher Education Authority (HEA) and Nigeria Qualifications Authority (ZAQA) have been established by the Acts of Parliament, namely the Higher Education Act No. 4 of 2013 and Nigeria Qualification Act of 2011 (the Republic of Nigeria, 2013; the Republic of Nigeria, 2011). Further, for the Government of Nigeria to operationalize the concept of QA, the higher education act of 2013 compels all higher education institutions (HEIs) especially universities to establish quality assurance departments and directorates.

Quality Assurance Principles at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Quality assurance principles are a set of guidelines and practices that are used to ensure that products, services, or processes meet a certain level of quality. These principles are applicable to a variety of industries, including education. In the context of education, quality assurance principles are used to ensure that educational programs and services are of a high quality, and that they meet the needs of students, educators, and other stakeholders.

The following are some of the key quality assurance principles that are applicable to education:

1. **Continuous Improvement:** Continuous improvement is a principle that emphasizes the importance of ongoing monitoring, evaluation, and improvement of educational programs and services. This principle requires that educational institutions have systems in place to track and analyze data related to student performance, teacher effectiveness, and other key metrics. The data collected can be used to identify areas for improvement, and to inform decisions related to resource allocation, curriculum development, and instructional strategies.
2. **Stakeholder Involvement:** Stakeholder involvement is a principle that emphasizes the importance of involving all stakeholders in the education planning and quality assurance process. This includes students, parents, teachers, administrators, and community members. When stakeholders are involved in the decision-making process, they are more likely to feel invested in the success of educational programs and services. Additionally, their input can help to ensure that educational programs and services are responsive to the needs and interests of the community.
3. **Standards-Based Approach:** A standards-based approach is a principle that emphasizes the importance of setting and adhering to clearly defined standards and benchmarks for educational programs and services. Standards provide a framework for assessing the quality of educational programs and services, and they can help to ensure that educational programs and services are consistent and effective. Standards can also be used to benchmark educational programs and services against those of other institutions, and to identify areas for improvement.
4. **Evidence-Based Decision Making:** Evidence-based decision making is a principle that emphasizes the importance of basing decisions on valid and reliable data and evidence. In the context of education, this principle requires that educational institutions have systems in place to collect and analyze data related to student performance, teacher effectiveness, and other key metrics. The data collected can be used to inform decisions related to curriculum development, instructional strategies, and resource allocation.
5. **Capacity Building:** Capacity building is a principle that emphasizes the importance of developing the capacity of educational institutions and stakeholders to implement and maintain quality assurance practices. This includes providing professional development opportunities for educators, administrators, and other stakeholders, and ensuring that they have the resources and support necessary to effectively implement quality assurance practices.

Implications of Quality Assurance Principles at the Tertiary Level of Education

The implications of quality assurance principles are numerous and far-reaching. When educational institutions implement quality assurance practices, they can improve the quality and effectiveness of educational programs and services. The following are some of the key implications of quality assurance principles at the tertiary level of education:

1. **Incorporating Stakeholder Feedback:** One of the key implications of quality assurance principles on education planning is the need to incorporate stakeholder feedback into the planning process. This includes feedback from students, parents, teachers, administrators, and community members. When stakeholders are involved in the planning process, they are more likely to feel invested in the success of educational programs and services. Additionally, their input can help to ensure that educational programs and services are responsive to the needs and interests of the community.

Quality Assurance at the Tertiary... (Mba, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929192>

2. **Setting Clear and Measurable Educational Objectives and Standards:** Quality assurance principles also emphasize the importance of setting clear and measurable educational objectives and standards. This includes setting standards for student performance, teacher effectiveness, and other key metrics. Clear and measurable objectives and standards can help to ensure that educational programs and services are consistent and effective, and they can help to identify areas for improvement.
3. **Regular Monitoring and Evaluation:** Quality assurance principles require that educational institutions have systems in place to regularly monitor and evaluate educational programs and services. This includes tracking and analyzing data related to student performance, teacher effectiveness, and other key metrics. The data collected can be used to identify areas for improvement, and to inform decisions related to resource allocation, curriculum development, and instructional strategies.
4. **Evidence-Based Decision Making:** Another key implication of quality assurance principles on education planning is the need to make evidence-based decisions. This requires that educational institutions have systems in place to collect and analyze data related to student performance, teacher effectiveness, and other key metrics. The data collected can be used to inform decisions related to curriculum development, instructional strategies, and resource allocation.
5. **Providing Ongoing Professional Development and Capacity Building:** Finally, quality assurance principles emphasize the importance of providing ongoing professional development and capacity building opportunities for educators and other stakeholders. This includes providing training on quality assurance practices, as well as on new technologies, teaching methods, and other relevant topics.

Importance of Quality Assurance at the Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Quality assurance has become important in higher education because of several reasons. These include:

1. **Improvement teaching and research and regulation of higher education:** One of the principal objectives of QA is to improve teaching and research in higher education institutions (European Commission, 2022). The core business of any HEIs such as universities is teaching and research. The quality of teaching and research output can only improve if there is QA. Instead of relying on the one-off certificate, confirming that the quality standards have been met, QA process serves as a more forward-thinking cycle for continuous improvement (Matei & Iwinska, 2016).
2. **Regulation of higher education sector:** Quality assurance is a self-regulation mechanism in higher education that ensures that education providers provide services that meet set standards. It has been observed that there is a surge in demand for higher education and more players have become providing higher education. By 2021, the World Bank estimated over 200 million students were pursuing tertiary education and it attributed this increase to the perceived benefits of attaining higher education (The World Bank, 2021). In Sub-Saharan Africa, it is estimated that there is a 21% increase in earnings among tertiary education graduates. In this regard, many public and private institutions in Nigeria and other countries are providing higher education with different standards. To ensure quality and that the level of education provided meets acceptable standards by stakeholders, QA has to be implemented.
3. **Accountability and transparency in higher education:** Further, there is an increased call for transparency and accountability in both private and public HEIs. They are calls to subject HEIs to scrutiny by internal and external stakeholders to ensure that the education being provided meets the minimum local, regional, and internal standards (The World Bank, 2007).
4. **Increased competition in higher education:** Many institutions are providing higher education. There is cut-throat competition among education providers. These providers are competing to attract students to study with them. For them to successfully attract the best and more students, quality assurance has to be embraced and practiced to provide educational services of excellent quality which will attract more learners.
5. **Reputation building and status maintenance:** A higher learning institutions' name, status, and reputation are key in higher education. Prestigious universities have a name and status that make them attract the best and more students in the world. For them to build and maintain the name, there is a need to continuously preach QA. Another importance of QA is that it enables stakeholders such as students and parents to know the standards, and status of a higher education institution (HEI) because information on the quality of education it provides is made public. Further, QA makes it possible to harmonise academic programmes at national, regional, and global levels (Matei & Iwinska, 2016).

Internal Quality Assurance Mechanisms at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

All higher education institutions are compelled by national education laws to establish internal quality management systems for assuring quality in teaching, research, and organisation (European Commission, 2022). Based on this, the HEIs choose those approaches and arrangements that best suit their own needs. There is a call for continuous internal evaluations of

Quality Assurance at the Tertiary... (Mba, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929192>

the performance of HEI in terms of the performance of staff in the areas of teaching and research. To facilitate this process, HEIs are expected to establish QA units and committees that coordinate issues of QA in an HEI. Duties of QA units or committees include among other things, conducting reviews of the teaching, learning, and research in HEI; checking if they conform to set standards. Quality assurance units also seek feedback from education stakeholders such as students and parents. Other responsibilities of QA units include monitoring the quality of assessment judgments; ensuring consistent and reliable assessment judgments are made across a provider; highlighting any problems, trends and development needs of assessors; ensuring all procedures and policies within a provider are adhered to and maintained by staff (Educating UK, 2016). Other internal QA mechanisms involve raising awareness about QA and cultivating the culture of QA among lecturers through mechanisms such as self-assessments and peer reviews.

Other internal mechanisms of ensuring quality in higher learning institutions include the use of external examiners. The use of external examiners has been a long-standing practice in Africa and Nigeria in particular (DAAD, 2018). For example, a professor within a region of Southern Africa Development Cooperation (SADC) could be invited by the University of Nigeria (UNZA) to review the marked examination scripts and programmes offered in the inviting department of a university. At the end of the external examiner's work, a report is submitted to the department and university to improve quality.

External Quality assurance mechanisms at the Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

The first important method of quality assurance under the external approach is accreditation. This is an evaluation of whether an institution or programme meets a threshold standard and qualifies for a certain status. Under accreditation, programmes of a higher education institution are accredited to national, regional, and global quality assurance agencies. All universities must accredit their programmes with the Higher Education Authority (HEA). Failure to do, an HEI will not be allowed to operate. Private HEIs in Nigeria are required also to register with HEA before seeking accreditation of their programmes. To ensure the quality of education at both regional and continental levels, the Southern African Quality Assurance Network (SAQAN) and the African Quality Assurance Network (AfriQAN) have been established (DAAD, 2018). Currently, the HEA is affiliated with SAQAN.

Another external method of ensuring quality is assessment. This mechanism focuses on making graded judgments about quality (going beyond the binary judgments of accreditation); it focuses on the quality of outputs (DAAD, 2018). The output of an assessment is a quantitative evaluation, a grade (whether numeric, literal, or descriptive). Programme assessment is used in many European countries.

In ensuring quality in higher education, an institutional audit is conducted which assesses the extent to which an HEI achieves its objectives; establishes whether or not the HEI's processes are effective. The output of an audit is usually a description of the extent to which the claims of the HEI are correct. The audit focuses on internal procedures adopted by an HEI to achieve its objectives. Quality audits help HEIs to identify their weaknesses and areas that need improvement. It also helps in creating a balance between anticipated and actual performance (VJTF, 2020).

Implications of Quality Assurance Mechanisms at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

As indicated in the introduction, the government of the Republic of Nigeria acknowledges the need to assure the quality of higher education being provided in Nigeria. In this regard, statutory bodies such as Higher Education Authority (HEA). For quality to be assured in higher education in Nigeria, both internal and external QA mechanisms have to adhere to by QA agencies and HEIs. These include:

1. **Registration and accreditation of higher education institutions and their programmes:** The higher education Act of 2013 in Nigeria provides for all higher education institutions (HEIs) to register themselves with the Higher Education Authority (HEA). Further, HEIs have to accredit their programmes to HEA which in turn forward the programmes to Nigeria Qualifications Authority (ZAQA) so that the qualifications can be verified and rated in line with the National Qualifications Framework (NQF) of Nigeria. The HEIs that fail to meet the minimum set of standards are not registered and their programmes are not accredited. This has brought some sanity in the higher education sector as quark institutions are closed down. According to HEA as by December 2020, a total of 1,192 learning programmes were submitted to the HEA from nine public and 51 private for accreditation. From this number, 563 programmes were accredited and 210 were rejected and 419 programmes were still undergoing the evaluation process (Higher Education Authority, 2021).
2. **Periodic auditing of higher education institutions:** In a bid to continuously improve and assure the quality of higher education, the HEA is mandated by Law to conduct institutional audits of HEIs quality assurance systems (the Republic of Nigeria, 2013). In this regard, institutional policies as regard quality, infrastructure, academic programmes, and, financial sustainability of HEIs among other things, are audited. This should not be done once

Quality Assurance at the Tertiary... (Mba, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929192>

during registration and accreditation but often to continuously assure the quality of education being provided. HEIs that fail to pass the audit should not be allowed to continue providing higher education as they will compromise the quality of education.

3. **Establishment of quality assurance units and committees:** To effectively implement internal quality assurance measures, HEIs in Nigeria need to establish quality assurance (QA) units and committees to spearhead the issues of QA. The HEA which is empowered by the Higher Education Act of 2013 has to push for the establishment of QA units or directorates in HEIs in Nigeria. Currently, public universities such as the University of Nigeria (UNZA) and Copperbelt University (CBU) have established directorates to oversee the issues of QA. It is important to mention that these QA directorates currently have concentrated on fulfilling the mandate of accrediting academic programmes to HEA. They have neglected the implementation of internal QA measures. These QA units/directorates should raise awareness about QA and cultivate a culture of quality in teaching and learning in HEIs. This should be done by creating quality assurance committees in schools and faculties. Further, QA units should actively audit all the learning processes, facilities, academic programmes, staff, etc., and report accurately without fear if the quality of higher education in both public and private universities has to improve. Further, it should be the mandate of such units to develop QA policies and frameworks to assure the quality of education. It is also worth mentioning that many private universities are yet to established independent units for QA.
4. **Revamping and embracing the concept of external examiners:** As observed, the use of external examiners has been an integral part of QA in universities and other higher education institutions. It has been a practice of appointing an external examiner for a period of 4 years and he/she should be qualified enough to add value as regard QA. For example, the University of Exeter in the United Kingdom (UK) appoints external examiners for faculties/schools for a period of 4 years. (University of Exeter, 2022). In Nigeria, UNZA used to appoint external examiners for every department, and usually, these examiners came from other countries in the region. Unfortunately, this practice has been stopped because the university and schools do not have money to host external examiners. To ensure QA, HEIs should continue with this practice and the newly established HEIs should embrace this concept as a mechanism to enhance QA.

Challenges of Quality Assurance Management at the Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Several challenges make it difficult for HEIs to fully implement QA as they provide higher education. Principal among them is inadequate financial resources. As observed by the World Bank, (2007), many universities especially public ones suffer from under-funding. For many years, Public HEIs have suffered from under-funding from the government in Nigeria. This has made it possible to implement QA initiatives. Another challenge to QA is a rapid increase in enrolments in HEIs in Nigeria. For example, the number of students pursuing university education in public and private universities has increased from 91,969 in 2017 to 114,049 in 2020 (Republic of Nigeria. Ministry of Higher Education, 2019). This is against limited infrastructure, especially in public universities. For example, the University of Nigeria this year (2022) has over-enrolled in Medical Sciences; over 2000 students against a big lecture theatre at the school of medicines with a sitting capacity of 100 students. Inadequate infrastructure has further compromised the quality of higher education.

Inadequate infrastructure is also another challenge that lowers the quality of higher education. In public HEIs, this has been due to under-funding by the government. In many public universities, there is an acute shortage of infrastructures such as lecture theatres and students accommodation. The 2019 higher education policy acknowledged this and the government promised to deal with it. For example, the University of Nigeria has an acute shortage of accommodation, offices, and lecture theatres. This has been a source of concern as it contributes to the lower quality of higher education.

Another challenge has to do with the technical and tedious process of accrediting academic programmes by the HEA. As Stander (2016) observed, South African Private Universities have difficulties accrediting their programmes to the Council of Higher Education (CHE) because the process is technical and complex (Stander, 2016). Higher education intuitions in Nigeria that wish to accredit their academic programmes face challenges in formatting the documents needed by HEA format.

The lack of experienced and highly skilled academic staff in HEIs in Nigeria is another challenge to QA. The World Bank (2007) observed that Sub-Saharan Africa HEIs face a problem of shortage of qualified staff due to brain drain. Much qualified academic staff in Nigeria has gone to seek greener pastures. This has also contributed to the poor quality of education in Nigeria. Furthermore, many learning institutions in Nigeria have not internalised the concept of QA. This is evidenced by the lack of QA policies, procedures, and frameworks. Further, there is no financial commitment towards QA-related issues in the higher education sector.

Quality Assurance at the Tertiary... (Mba, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929192>

Limitations of Quality Assurance implementation at the Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Despite the benefits of quality assurance in education planning, there are also several limitations that must be considered. These challenges can make it difficult for educational institutions to effectively implement quality assurance practices and achieve their desired outcomes. The following are some of the key limitations of quality assurance implementation at tertiary level of education:

1. **Resource Constraints:** One of the biggest challenges of quality assurance in education planning is resource constraints. Quality assurance practices can be time-consuming and expensive, requiring significant investments in personnel, technology, and infrastructure. Smaller institutions or those with limited funding may struggle to allocate resources to quality assurance practices, limiting their ability to improve the quality of their educational programs and services.
2. **Difficulty in Standardizing Measures:** Another challenge of quality assurance in education planning is the difficulty in standardizing measures. Education programs and services can vary widely across different regions and contexts, making it challenging to develop standardized measures of quality. This can make it difficult to compare and benchmark educational programs and services across institutions, limiting the effectiveness of quality assurance practices.
3. **Resistance to Change:** Resistance to change is another challenge that can impede the implementation of quality assurance practices in education planning. Stakeholders, including educators and administrators, may be resistant to changes that disrupt established routines and practices. This can make it difficult to implement new quality assurance practices and achieve the desired outcomes.
4. **Limited Scope of Assessment:** Quality assurance practices may also have a limited scope of assessment. For example, they may focus primarily on student academic performance, neglecting other important aspects of education, such as social and emotional development, cultural competency, and global awareness.
5. **Insufficient Data and Information:** Finally, quality assurance in education planning can be limited by insufficient data and information. Educational institutions may lack the data and information necessary to make informed decisions about the effectiveness of their programs and services. This can make it difficult to identify areas for improvement or to measure progress towards desired outcomes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, quality assurance principles have become increasingly important in education planning to ensure that educational institutions provide high-quality programs and services that meet the needs of students and other stakeholders. While quality assurance practices can help educational institutions improve the quality of their programs and services, they also face several challenges and limitations. These challenges include resource constraints, difficulty in standardizing measures, resistance to change, limited scope of assessment, and insufficient data and information. Addressing these challenges will be essential for educational institutions to effectively implement quality assurance practices and achieve their desired outcomes. By doing so, they can help ensure that students receive the education they need to succeed in the workforce and in their personal lives.

In conclusion, it can be said that QA is about assuring stakeholders about the quality of higher education provided is in line with set national and international standards. It is about value for money for stakeholders. The study has established that QA is implemented through external and internal approaches such as accreditation, registration, institutional auditing, self-evaluation, and external examiners. The implications of QA for HEIs in Nigeria are that: there is a need for HEIs to register themselves and accredit their programmes with the HEA. Further, there is a need for all HEIs to establish QA units to spearhead the issues of QA. It has also been established that there are many challenges in ensuring quality in HEIs in Nigeria. These include poor funding among public HEIs, inadequate infrastructure, shortage of qualified academic staff, rapid increase in enrolments, failure to embrace fully the issue of QA among some HEIs in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. All HEIs should have their academic programmes accredited to Higher the HEA.
2. The HEA should continuously conduct institutional audits in HEIs to ensure quality.
3. Government should improve funding to public HEIs.
4. Construction of infrastructure in public HEIs is needed to assure quality.
5. All HEIs should establish QA units to aid the implementation of QA measures.

Quality Assurance at the Tertiary... (Mba, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929192>

6. Attract qualified and experienced academic staff to ensure quality in teaching and research in HEIs.

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Review of Inclusive Human Kinetics and Health Education Programmes for Sustainable National Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study, employing a qualitative phenomenological research design, investigates the role of inclusive health and physical education in fostering sustainable development in Nigeria. The research examines how inclusive practices, particularly for individuals with disabilities, impact public health, education, and socio-economic development. It explores the challenges and opportunities associated with implementing these practices, considering Nigeria's cultural diversity, resource limitations, and infrastructural constraints. The study reviews key policies, such as the National Policy on Disability (2012) and the Disability Discrimination (Prohibition) Act (2018), highlighting the barriers to their effective implementation, including limited awareness and bureaucratic challenges. The findings underscore the importance of inclusivity in enhancing workforce diversity, promoting social equity, and reducing stigmatization. The study concludes that integrating inclusive health and physical education is crucial for achieving national development goals. It recommends stronger stakeholder collaboration, increased community engagement, and focused efforts to address implementation challenges, thereby contributing to a healthier and more resilient Nigerian society.

Keywords: Inclusive, Human Kinetics, Health Education, and Sustainable Development

Introduction

Nigeria's health landscape is marked by significant disparities, with widespread prevalence of communicable and non-communicable diseases, maternal and child health issues, and inadequate access to healthcare services, particularly in rural areas. Additionally, the country grapples with rising rates of sedentary lifestyles, obesity, and physical inactivity, fueled by urbanization, technological advancements, and changing socio-cultural norms (WHO, 2020). Encouraging people with disabilities to participate fully in health and physical education is essential and consistent with sustainable development ideals in Nigeria, as it is in many other countries. This review explores the urgent need to improve inclusivity and accessibility in health and physical education for people with disabilities. It acknowledges the intricate problems that this underprivileged group faces and looks for workable solutions that would enhance their standard of living and advance Nigeria's more general developmental objectives.

One of the most notable problems in Nigeria is the obvious differences in schooling that people with disabilities experience. These disparities are exacerbated by the lack of inclusive educational policies and practices, which also restrict the growth and well-being of the affected populations. As fundamental elements of human development, health and physical education are especially important for this group of people because they have a direct impact on mental and physical health and enable people with disabilities to live more independent and satisfying lives. Nigeria signed the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities as part of its international commitments to advance the inclusion and rights of people with disabilities. Nevertheless, there is still more work to be done before these international pledges can be translated into real, noticeable gains for Nigerians with disabilities. The accomplishment of these pledges is hampered by implementation gaps, resource limitations, and a lack of knowledge. (Oyeyemi & Oyeyemi, 2020).

Nigerian educational institutions' poor physical infrastructure is a major obstacle to inclusiveness. In the context of health education, inclusivity extends beyond physical accessibility to encompass cultural sensitivity, gender equity, and social inclusion (UNESCO, 2019). The resources and adjustments needed to accommodate people with disabilities are sometimes lacking in schools and other educational institutions. This includes the unavailability of assistive technologies, qualified staff,

Review of Inclusive Human...(Waziri & Ogunkeye, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

and specially designed instructional materials. The full participation of people with disabilities in health and physical education is severely hampered by these restrictions. Another major barrier to inclusivity is societal attitudes, which frequently support stigmatization and discrimination against people with disabilities. Prejudices and unfavorable assumptions about people with disabilities prevent people from participating and worsen social isolation. In addition to harming the confidence and self-worth of disabled people, these beliefs also prevent them from accessing equitable opportunities. (Ajayi, 2021).

Although Nigeria has enacted laws and policies to protect the rights and welfare of people with disabilities, these laws and policies are not always effectively implemented or enforced. Due to this discrepancy, people with disabilities are placed in a vulnerable position and have few options for addressing prejudice or being denied access to healthcare and education. By integrating human kinetics and health education within this framework, Nigeria can work towards building a healthier, more resilient society that empowers individuals to lead active, fulfilling lives while contributing to broader development goals (UNDP, 2020). People with disabilities are underutilized and inequity is sustained when they are excluded from these fundamental aspects of human development. The foundation of sustainable development is the idea that every person, regardless of ability, should have equal access to opportunities for economic contribution, full participation in society, and healthy living. (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2012).

Conceptualization of the problem

Nigeria faces significant challenges in achieving sustainable national development, including high levels of poverty, unemployment, and public health crises. Human Kinetics and Health Education are vital in addressing these challenges by promoting physical health, well-being, and social inclusion. However, the existing Human Kinetics and Health Education (HKHE) programmes are often not inclusive, failing to cater to the needs of marginalized groups such as people with disabilities, women, and rural populations. This exclusion limits the reach and impact of HKHE programmes, thereby hindering their potential to contribute to sustainable development goals. For HKHE programmes to effectively contribute to sustainable national development, they must be inclusive and equitable. An inclusive approach ensures that all individuals, regardless of their background, can benefit from health education and physical activities. This inclusivity not only to promote individual well-being but also fosters social cohesion, reduces inequalities, and enhances overall national productivity.

Theoretical Perspectives to the Problem

Inclusive Education Theory posits that all students, regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, or linguistic differences, should be educated in general education classrooms within their local schools. This theory stems from the broader concept of social inclusion, which advocates for the integration of marginalized groups into mainstream society. Inclusive Education Theory challenges traditional models of education that segregate students with special needs or disabilities into separate classrooms or schools. Instead, it promotes the idea that all students can benefit from learning together, as it fosters an environment of diversity, acceptance, and mutual respect. According to this theory, inclusion is not merely about placing students with special needs in regular classrooms but about creating a supportive and flexible learning environment that meets the diverse needs of all students (Ainscow, 2020).

The implementation of Inclusive Education Theory requires significant changes in teaching practices, curriculum design, and school policies. Teachers play a critical role in this process, as they must adapt their instructional methods to accommodate different learning styles and abilities. This might involve using differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and assistive technologies to ensure that all students can access the curriculum effectively. Furthermore, schools must provide adequate resources and support, such as specialized training for teachers, classroom aides, and accessible learning materials, to create an inclusive environment. Research has shown that inclusive education not only benefits students with special needs but also enhances the academic and social outcomes of all students by promoting empathy, cooperation, and a broader understanding of diversity (Florian & Spratt, 2013).

However, the successful implementation of Inclusive Education Theory faces numerous challenges, particularly in contexts with limited resources or rigid educational systems. In many developing countries, including Nigeria, the lack of funding, infrastructure, and trained personnel can hinder the adoption of inclusive practices. Moreover, cultural attitudes and societal norms can also impact the effectiveness of inclusive education. For instance, stigmatization and discrimination against individuals with disabilities may persist in communities, affecting both the willingness of schools to implement inclusive policies and the acceptance of such students by their peers.

Prevalence of people living with disabilities in Nigeria

Nigeria has one of the highest rates of disability in Africa, with around 25 million people living with some form of disability. These disabilities are diverse and can result from various factors, including congenital conditions, accidents, communicable and non-communicable diseases, and injuries during conflicts. Poverty is a significant association with disability, and gender can also play a role. According to the NDHS 2018 report, approximately 3.6% of women and 3.0% of

Review of Inclusive Human...(Waziri & Ogunkeye, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

men aged 15-49 in Nigeria reported some form of difficulty in functioning due to physical, sensory, mental, or intellectual impairments (Nigeria National Bureau of Statistics, 2018). Stigmatization and discrimination against individuals with disabilities further marginalize them, limiting their access to essential services. Understanding these issues is crucial for developing effective policies and programs. (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2012). In a joint publication by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the World Bank, the report estimates that approximately 15% of the world's population lives with some form of disability, with higher rates in low and middle-income countries. While specific national data for Nigeria is not provided, the report highlights the global magnitude of the issue (WHO & World Bank, 2011).

The Nigeria National Policy on Disability recognizes the prevalence of disabilities in the country and outlines strategies for promoting the rights and inclusion of persons with disabilities. The policy underscores the need for accurate data collection to inform planning and decision-making processes (Federal Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Development, 2012). Various non-governmental organizations (NGOs) working in Nigeria conduct studies and surveys to assess the prevalence and impact of disabilities. These reports often focus on specific disability types or population groups and contribute to the understanding of the disability landscape in Nigeria (The Albino Foundation, Joint National Association of Persons with Disabilities).

Necessity of Inclusive Human Kinetics and Health Education Programs for Individuals Living with Disabilities in Nigeria

Accessible health and physical education are crucial for individuals with disabilities, as they offer numerous physical, mental, and social benefits. These programs help develop strength, flexibility, and endurance, preventing obesity and related health issues. Physical activity also reduces stress and anxiety, boosts self-esteem, and reduces depression symptoms (Ajayi, Abayomi & Ojo, 2013). Social inclusion is fostered through interaction and socialization, promoting teamwork and cooperation. Adapted skills can enhance independence, allowing individuals with disabilities to perform everyday tasks more effectively. Accessible physical education empowers individuals with disabilities to advocate for their needs and rights, challenging stereotypes and misconceptions. Physical fitness and skills also improve daily life quality, and they create equal opportunities for active and fulfilling lives (Ogunleye & Ojo, 2019). More so, it has long-term health benefits such as preventing secondary health conditions, such as cardiovascular problems and musculoskeletal-related issues. These programs contribute to improved health, self-confidence, social inclusion, and overall quality of life.

People with disabilities are at higher risk of developing secondary health conditions such as obesity, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease due to factors like sedentary lifestyles and barriers to healthcare access. Accessible health and physical education programs can provide opportunities for preventive care, health screenings, and education on managing health risks, thus reducing the incidence of secondary conditions (Ojo & Ajala, 2021). Participation in physical education and sports can foster a sense of empowerment, confidence, and social inclusion among individuals with disabilities. By providing opportunities for interaction, teamwork, and skill development, inclusive physical education environments help combat social isolation, promote positive self-image, and build supportive peer networks (Goodwin & Staples, 2018).

Addressing the Gaps in Access to Quality Inclusive Education for Individuals with Disabilities

Disparities in access to quality education in Nigeria are rooted in factors such as lack of awareness, financial barriers, lack of inclusive policies, limited access to early intervention, underrepresentation in mainstream schools, transportation barriers, and language and communication challenges. Urban schools have more resources and infrastructure, while rural ones often lack the necessary support. Financial burdens, lack of inclusive policies, and limited access to early intervention programs further exacerbate these disparities.

Negative attitudes and misconceptions about disability among educators, administrators, and peers can create hostile or unwelcoming environments for students with disabilities. Discriminatory practices, stigma, and low expectations may limit opportunities for inclusion and academic achievement (United Nations, 2020). Furthermore, many students with disabilities require specialized support services such as assistive technology, sign language interpreters, braille materials, and personalized learning plans. However, these services are often lacking or inadequate in educational settings, hindering students' ability to fully participate and succeed in their academic pursuits (Adigun, 2021).

Families of children with disabilities often face additional financial burdens associated with their education, including costs for specialized equipment, therapies, and transportation. Limited financial resources may force families to prioritize basic needs over educational expenses, exacerbating disparities in access to quality education (United Nations, 2020). Addressing these issues requires policy changes, increased awareness, teacher training, and investment in infrastructure. Inclusive education practices focusing on individual needs are crucial for creating a more equitable educational system (Oyeyemi, & Oyeyemi, 2020).

Review of Inclusive Human...(Waziri & Ogunkeye, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

Addressing Instructional Resource Inequities in Human Kinetics and Health Education Programmes between Urban and Rural Nigeria

Disparities in access to quality education in Nigeria are rooted in factors such as lack of awareness, financial barriers, lack of inclusive policies, limited access to early intervention, underrepresentation in mainstream schools, transportation barriers, and language and communication challenges. Urban schools have more resources and infrastructure, while rural ones often lack the necessary support. Financial burdens, lack of inclusive policies, and limited access to early intervention programs further exacerbate these disparities. Urban areas generally have better-developed infrastructure, including schools equipped with ramps, accessible restrooms, and assistive devices. In contrast, rural schools often lack these facilities, making it difficult for students with disabilities to access educational facilities.

Also, urban schools tend to have better access to technology resources such as computers, tablets, and assistive devices. These resources play a crucial role in facilitating inclusive education and supporting students with disabilities in their learning process (Ezenwaji & Chukwuekezie, 2018). In rural areas, limited access to technology further exacerbates the educational disparities for students with disabilities. Transportation infrastructure is often better developed in urban areas, providing easier access to schools for students with disabilities who may require specialized transportation services. In rural areas, limited transportation options can pose significant barriers to school attendance for students with disabilities, particularly those living in remote areas.

Understanding the Distinct Challenges of Individuals Living with Disabilities in Nigeria

Nigeria faces numerous challenges for individuals with disabilities, including lack of access to formal education, inadequate infrastructure, a shortage of trained educators, and a lack of specialized resources and assistive technologies. Societal stigmatization and discrimination also hinder participation in educational and social activities. Financial hardships, lack of accessible transportation, and communication disabilities also impede access to quality education (Waziri, 2019). Parents and guardians are often unaware of available educational opportunities, leading to underrepresentation in mainstream schools and missed opportunities for support. Gender also plays a role, with girls with disabilities often facing double discrimination. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach, including policy changes, increased awareness, teacher training, investment in infrastructure, and a shift in societal attitudes. Equitable and accessible education is essential for social justice and empowering individuals with disabilities to lead fulfilling lives. (Nwosu, & Eze, 2019).

Nigeria's Commitment to Disability Rights and Inclusive Development

Nigeria has made significant international commitments to promote and protect the rights of individuals with disabilities, in line with international conventions and agreements. These include ratifying the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) in 2010, participating in the African Decade of Persons with Disabilities, signing the African Union Protocol on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in 2018, and upholding the principles of the United Nations' Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR). Nigeria's commitments to these rights reflect its dedication to addressing the rights and well-being of individuals with disabilities, reducing discrimination, and improving living conditions. These commitments serve as a foundation for developing and implementing policies and programs aimed at ensuring the rights of persons with disabilities are respected and upheld. (Oyeyemi, & Oyeyemi, 2020; Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2012).

Challenges in translating global commitments into practical improvements at the local level

The implementation of global disability rights commitments in Nigeria is a complex and multifaceted task. Key challenges include lack of awareness and sensitization, resource constraints, inadequate infrastructure and accessibility, shortage of trained personnel, inconsistent policy implementation, attitudinal barriers, communication challenges, geographic disparities, gender-based discrimination, limited data and monitoring, complex bureaucracy, and inadequate legal remedies. These obstacles hinder the effective implementation of disability-related initiatives, affecting access to public spaces, schools, and healthcare facilities. The lack of trained personnel, inconsistent policy implementation, and persistent cultural beliefs contribute to discrimination and exclusion. Communication challenges, such as limited access to sign language interpreters and Braille materials, further complicate the situation. The bureaucratic structure in Nigeria also complicates the coordination and implementation of inclusive policies. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-pronged approach, including increased awareness, resource allocation, changes in attitudes, and consistent policy implementation. (Nwosu, & Eze, 2019).

Enhancing Resources for Human Kinetics and Health Education in Nigeria

In Nigeria, inadequate infrastructure and resources in educational institutions pose significant challenges to providing quality education and inclusive learning environments, particularly for individuals with disabilities. These challenges include a lack of accessibility features, inadequate classroom space, unsafe buildings, specialized facilities, and limited therapy rooms. Assistive technology and teaching materials are scarce, with limited access to Braille books and large-print materials. Schools may also lack computers and adaptive software for students with disabilities. Training and personnel shortages, including

Review of Inclusive Human...(Waziri & Ogunkeye, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

special education teachers and support staff, further hinder individualized support. Accessible transportation is also a significant issue, with many students without mobility facilities. Insufficient funding and policy implementation also hinder progress. Addressing these challenges requires increased investment in infrastructure, assistive technology, specialized resources, teacher training, and consistent policy implementation. A broader societal shift in attitudes towards accessibility and inclusion is also needed. (Ajayi, 2021; Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2012).

Role of Assistive Technologies and Trained Professionals in Enhancing Human Kinetics and Health Education in Nigeria

Assistive technologies and trained personnel are crucial in providing quality education and support for individuals with disabilities. These technologies enhance accessibility, personalize learning experiences, promote independence, ensure equal access to information, and improve communication. Trained personnel, such as special education teachers, speech therapists, and occupational therapists, provide specialized instruction and support, develop individualized education plans, and play a critical role in early intervention programs. They also assess progress, provide behavioral support, and maintain inclusive classrooms. These elements empower students to access educational content, participate actively, and achieve their full potential, contributing to reducing barriers and disparities faced by individuals with disabilities in traditional educational settings. In summary, assistive technologies and trained personnel are essential for creating an inclusive and equitable learning environment for individuals with disabilities, empowering them to access educational content, participate actively, and achieve their full potential. (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2012).

Changing Perceptions and Empowering Persons with Disabilities in Nigeria

Negative stereotypes and prejudices surrounding disabilities are deeply ingrained in societies worldwide, including Nigeria. These stereotypes can lead to discrimination, exclusion, and limited opportunities for individuals with disabilities. Common stereotypes include dependency, pity, superhumanity, inferiority, stigmatization, sexualization, fears, and limited representation. Dependency stereotypes assume individuals with disabilities are inherently dependent on others, limiting their autonomy and development. Pity and victimhood stereotypes view them as objects of pity, fostering a sense of powerlessness and inhibiting genuine social inclusion. Superhuman or inspirational stereotypes portray individuals with disabilities as superhuman or inspirational, causing burden and burden. Inferiority stereotypes suggest individuals with disabilities are inferior or incapable, leading to low expectations, limited access to education and employment opportunities, and discrimination. Stigmatization of specific disabilities discourages individuals from seeking help, and limited representation in media and public spaces perpetuates stereotypes (Nwosu, & Eze, 2019).

Dual Burden Faced by Persons with Disabilities in Nigeria

Negative attitudes and stereotypes about disabilities can significantly hinder the participation and inclusion of individuals with disabilities in various aspects of life, including education, employment, and social interactions. These attitudes can lead to lowered expectations, exclusion, isolation, limited educational and employment opportunities, underutilization of skills and talents, psychological impact, limited access to services, lack of empowerment and advocacy, and mental health issues. Individuals with disabilities may internalize these stereotypes, leading to feelings of self-doubt, lowered self-esteem, and reluctance to participate in activities that challenge these stereotypes. Physical and attitudinal barriers may discourage participation, leading to withdrawal from social and community life. Lack of empowerment and advocacy can perpetuate the cycle of exclusion and discouragement. To address these discouraging attitudes, it is crucial to raise awareness, promote education, and foster a culture of inclusivity and acceptance. Encouraging positive role models and representations of individuals with disabilities in media and society can also challenge stereotypes and promote active participation and inclusion.

Critical Analysis of Nigeria's Legal and Policy Frameworks for Disability Rights

Nigeria has implemented several policies and laws to protect the rights of individuals with disabilities, aligning with international standards like the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD). These include the National Policy on Disability (2012), Disability Discrimination (Prohibition) Act (2018), Education (National Minimum Standards and Establishment of Institutions) Act (2018), Universal Basic Education (UBE) Act (2004), National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) Act (2003), Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) Guidelines on Accessibility (2017), and National Health Act (2014). However, challenges remain ineffective implementation and enforcement. Ensuring equal opportunities, non-discrimination, and accessibility for individuals with disabilities requires continued advocacy, awareness, and involvement of civil society organizations. (Okonkwo, & Okafor, 2018; Ibrahim, & Ahmed, 2017).

Overcoming the Barriers to Effective Disability Policy Implementation in Nigeria

The implementation of policies protecting the rights of individuals with disabilities in Nigeria faces several challenges. These include inadequate awareness and sensitivity among stakeholders, limited resources and funding, bureaucratic

Review of Inclusive Human...(Waziri & Ogunkeye, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

complexity, lack of data and monitoring, inadequate accessibility, attitudinal barriers, lack of capacity building, inadequate legal remedies, fragmented implementation across states, and limited stakeholder collaboration. These gaps hinder effective enforcement and practical realization of policies, leading to exclusion and exclusion (Ibrahim, & Ahmed, 2017).

In Nigeria, the bureaucratic structure is complex and fragmented, making it difficult to coordinate and implement policies effectively. Accurate data on disability status and needs is often lacking, hindering evidence-based decision-making and monitoring policy outcomes (Okonkwo, & Okafor, 2018). Access to legal remedies is inadequate or cumbersome, and disparities in implementation across states result in unequal access to services and rights.

Impact of Inclusive Health and Physical Education on Nigeria's National Development

Inclusivity in health and physical education is crucial for sustainable development, as it promotes social inclusion, improves health and well-being, enhances human capital, reduces inequality, and promotes community resilience. It also drives infrastructure changes and leads to innovative solutions, resulting in long-term economic benefits.

Inclusion in education, employment, and society at large offers numerous potential economic, social, and health benefits. Economic benefits include increased workforce diversity, enhanced productivity, access to untapped talent, reduced turnover rates, and market expansion. Social benefits include the promotion of equity, enhanced social cohesion, reduced stigmatization and discrimination, empowerment, improved mental health, increased physical activity, enhanced social support, reduced health disparities, positive psychological impact, and prevention of secondary health issues related to disabilities.

Inclusive practices encourage interaction, cooperation, and mutual support among individuals of different backgrounds and abilities, leading to a more accepting and empathetic society. They also help reduce stigmatization and discrimination, leading to greater self-confidence and self-determination. Health benefits include increased physical activity, improved social support, reduced health disparities, positive psychological impact, and prevention of secondary health issues related to disabilities.

Conclusion

Inclusive health and physical education for individuals with disabilities in Nigeria are not only a matter of social justice and human rights but also a path to sustainable development. The existing policies and laws in Nigeria provide a strong foundation for promoting inclusivity, but there are significant gaps and challenges in their implementation. These barriers include a lack of awareness, inadequate resources, bureaucratic complexities, and attitudinal barriers. Overcoming these challenges is essential to reveal the full potential of individuals with disabilities, improve their health and well-being, and contribute to economic and social growth. Inclusivity has a profound impact on workforce diversity, productivity and social cohesion. It reduces stigmatization and discrimination, empowers individuals, and enhances mental and physical health.

Recommendations

To achieve a more equitable, prosperous, and sustainable Nigeria, the following Recommendations were proposed:

1. Organize campaigns and programmes to raise awareness about the importance of inclusivity in health and physical education.
2. Provide sufficient funding and resources to support inclusive health and physical education initiatives.
3. Simplify and streamline processes to facilitate easy access to inclusive health and physical education programmes.
4. Establish robust data collection and monitoring systems to track progress and identify areas for improvement.
5. Provide training and capacity-building programmes for educators, healthcare professionals, and other stakeholders.

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Assessment on Provision, Utilization... (Babayo, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

Assessment on Provision, Utilization and Maintenance of Secondary School Facilities in Dala Educational Zone, Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined Assessment on Provision, Utilization and Maintenance of Secondary School Facilities in Dala Educational Zone, Kano State, Nigeria. Two specific objectives, two research questions were raised to guide the study. The study employed a descriptive research survey research design. The research instrument used for this study was self-designed questionnaire. The content and face validity were ascertained by psychologist, guidance and counselling experts. A reliability co-efficient of 0.83 was obtained using split half method. The population of the study consists of all Principals and Teachers in Dala Educational Zone, during the 2023/2024 academic session. Eighty-three principals constitute the sample size of the study. Two research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The study concludes that infrastructural facilities were not adequately provided and properly maintained among Secondary Schools in Dala Educational Zone, Kano State. The study recommended that infrastructural facilities should be provided and maintained among public secondary schools in Dala Educational Zone of Kano State.

Keywords: Provision, Utilization and Maintenance of Facilities'.

Introduction

There is growing concern among education stakeholder and practitioners about the present poor state of infrastructural facilities available for teaching and learning in secondary schools across the country (Nigeria). There are calls for the need to re-vamp the educational sector to address the concerns of the citizenry and comply with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). There calls, gave rise to the current educational reforms of the Federal Government of Nigeria. Gana (2015) revealed that facilities and resources for teaching and learning in schools are grossly inadequate and sometimes inappropriate. This reveals the setbacks of our educational system. In the same vein, it is observed by Nwadiani (2000), observed that the facilities are not only over utilized, they are also poorly maintained. Educational facilities refer to non-human and non-financial resources. They include movable and immovable materials, which are used for teaching and learning facilities. They are synonymous with school physical facilities, school materials resources, school plant and school facilities (Abdulkarim and Fassasi, 2010). Moreover, provision of educational facilities involves the supply of all necessary learning materials, which enable a skilful teacher to achieve a level of instructional effectiveness that far exceed what is possible when they are not provided (Costaldi 1997, as cited in Gana 2015).

Assessment on Provision, Utilization... (Babayo, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

Adegboyeje (2000) stated that, utilization is the degree or extent to which an item has been put into effective use. According to him, various degrees of utilization include non-utilization, underutilization, maximum utilization, optimum utilization and overutilization. In this regard, utilization of facilities for teaching has to do with judicious harnessing of teaching facilities for the achievement of educational objectives. Saba, (2006) defines maintenance as the act of taking good care of tools and equipment to prolong its life-span and to prevent it from sudden breakdown. Jerret, (2000) in Saba, (2006) sees maintenance as a process whereby machines are constantly checked and faults rectified to avoid any loss in man hours and boost production.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to Assessment on Provision, Utilization and Maintenance of Secondary School Facilities in Dala Educational Zone, Kano State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. Assess the mean response on the extent of provision, utilization and maintenance of infrastructural facilities among Secondary schools in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State.
2. assess the mean response on the extent of Provision, Utilization and maintenance of welfare facilities among Secondary schools in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the mean response on the extent of infrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and maintenance among secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State?
2. What is the mean response on the extent of Provision, Utilization and maintenance of welfare facilities among Secondary Schools in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State?

Research Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The target population of the study is made eighty-three (83) principals from Dala zone Kano State, Nigeria. All eighty-three principals were purposely selected as sample sizes for the study as recommended by Kreccie and Morgan. Because the whole population was used as sample of the study. The name of the questionnaire was Assessment on Provision, Utilization and Maintenance of Secondary School Facilities in Dala Educational Zone which was designed by the researchers for data collection from respondents' opinion. Seventy-nine copies of questionnaire were received and used for the analysis in order to find the results. The respondents' opinions were rated inform of strongly agree (4) agree (3) disagree (2) and strongly disagree (1) as an instrument for data collection of the study. The instrument was validated by three expert and the reliability coefficient of 0.74 was obtained. The researchers administered the questionnaires to the respondents, the seventy-nine (79) questionnaires were returned. The data collected were coded into statistical package of social sciences (SPSS), 25. The package was used to calculate mean and standard deviation of response from respondents.

Research Question 1

Research Question One: What is the mean response on the extent of infrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and maintenance among secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State?

Table 1: Mean rating and Standard deviation oninfrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State.

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	There is adequate provision, utilize and maintenance toilet in our school.	79	3.28	1.22	Agreed
2	I.C.T. facilities were provided utilize and maintenance in our school.	79	1.08	1.215	Disagreed
3	Pipe borne water supply provided in our school and utilize.	79	3.47	1.219	Agreed
4	Medical center was fully equipped with facilities medicine are utilize and maintain on our school.	79	1.76	1.238	Disagreed
5	Recreational facilities are provided utilize and maintain in our school.	79	1.62	1.234	Disagreed

Assessment on Provision, Utilization... (Babayo, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

6	Internet facilities were provided, utilize and maintain in our school.	79	1.32	1.96	Disagreed
Grand Total		79	2.1		Disagree

Source: Field study 2024

The output of the descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 revealed that all items of the variable of on infrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State, Nigeria were having a mean score of below 3.0. The mean scores of infrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State, Nigeria ranging from 1.08 to 3.28. The grand mean of infrastructural facilities provides, utilized and maintenance is 2.1 which is below the benchmark of revised four point scale. The results indicate that the respondents Disagreed with statements of infrastructural facilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State, Nigeria.

Research Question Two: What is the mean response on the extent of Utilization and maintenance of welfare facilities among Secondary Schools in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation on welfarefacilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State.

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	Promotion and advancement are provided regularly for the teachers	79	3.42	0.76	Agreed
2	In service training are allowed for all teaching and non-teaching staff.	79	3.10	0.83	Agreed
3	Car loan is provided for the teachers in the school.	79	3.00	0.90	Agreed
4	Reward is also provided for the hardworking teachers in the school	79	3.28	0.97	Agreed
5	Computers are provided for both teaching and non-teaching staff in our school.	79	3.32	1.86	Agreed
Grand Total		79	3.22		Agreed

Source: Field study, 2024.

The output of the descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 revealed that all items of the variable Welfare facilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State, Nigeria, had a mean score of above 3.0. This means score of welfare facilities ranging from 3.00 to 3.42. The grand mean of welfare facilities is 3.22 which is above the benchmark of revised four-point scale. The results indicate that the respondents agreed with statements of welfarefacilities provided, utilized, and Maintenance in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone in Kano State, Nigeria

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question 1 indicate that the respondents disagreed with statements of infrastructural facilities provide, utilize and maintenance in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria. This is in line with finding Gujar and Malik (2007) that if there are necessary facilities that will facilitate the training of child are not available, the teaching and learning process cannot be successfully carried out. Khan and Iqbal (2012), found out that excellent school facilities are basic ingredients for successful learning and for achieving the target and improving literacy rate of a country.

The finding of the research question 2 indicates that that the respondents agreed with statements of welfare facilities provision, utilize and maintenance in Dala zone of Kano state, Nigeria. This in line with finding of the findings also indicated there was a strong inadequate utilization of infrastructural teaching/learning, Welfare, recreational and game facilities in Secondary Schools in Dala Educational Zone. This was in line with findings of Adegboyeje (2000), in which he stated that utilization is the degree or extent to which an item has been put into effective use. According to him various degrees of utilization include non-utilization, underutilization maximum utilization and over utilization. Non-utilization occurs when facilities is used more than its capacity.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study the study concluded that there were no infrastructural and ware fare facilities were not adequately provided adequately utilized and maintained among secondary schools in Dala Educational Zone Kano State.

Assessment on Provision, Utilization... (Babayo, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this research the following recommendations were made: -

1. Infrastructural facilities should be provided adequately utilized and maintained to make teaching and learning more effective in secondary school in Dala Educational Zone.
2. Welfare facilities should be provided and properly maintained for motivation and the overall attainment of education goals in secondary schools in Dala Educational Zone Kano State

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Correlation between Parental Styles... (Bada, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

Correlation between Parental Styles and Emotional Intelligence on Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kaduna-South, Local Government Area, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study investigated the correlation between parental styles and emotional intelligence as predictors of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna State. A correlational research design was adopted. The population of two thousand nine hundred and nineteen (2,919) students were obtained, the sample size of 333 senior secondary students (SSS II) at a confidence level of 95% and a Margin Error of 5.0%. Ten schools were selected using stratified sampling techniques based on gender and simple randomly sampling techniques to select respondents. The instrument used consists of three sections namely an adapted Parenting Styles Questionnaires (PSQ), Students' Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (SEIQ) Section "C" contained Students' Juvenile Delinquency Questionnaire (SJDQ) with reliability coefficient of 0.745, 0.853 and 0.702, respectively. Five hypotheses were formulated and tested using multiple regression, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient and t-test at 0.05 level of significance. Result analysis of the study showed the relative importance of each of the predictor variables (parenting styles and emotional intelligent) to the prediction of juvenile delinquency with $R=0.136$. This indication $R^2 = 0.716$ is a good level of prediction, which is equivalent to 51.6%, indicating the level of shared variance between the dependent variable and the independent variables ($F_{(3,331)} = 1.525 ; < 0.05$). Based on these findings, it was recommended among others that: Parents, guardians and caregivers should appreciate the need to create a peaceful home with relative harmony in development of pro-social behaviour on the part of the children.

Keyword: Parenting Styles, Emotional Intelligent, Juvenile Delinquency, Secondary School Students

Introduction

The contemporary landscape of adolescent behaviour is marked by an increasing prevalence of juvenile delinquency, which poses significant challenges to the well-being of societies worldwide. Among the myriad of factors contributing to this issue, the role of parenting styles and emotional intelligence has gained substantial attention in recent psychological research. Parenting styles is characterized by various combinations of parental responsiveness and demandingness, have been linked to a range of behavioral outcomes in adolescents. Parenting style is a process of care, nurturing, guiding and educating from parents to their children (Muhammad & Norhida, 2020). Parenting style is an important aspect that influences the well-being of children, creating a functional family and illuminates the image of the parent outside the word. According to Maccorby and Martin (1983); Baumrind (2003) practice and behaviour that are implemented to educate children will have a direct effect towards emotion, social and intellect of the child. They used these two domains to identify four styles of parenting: Democratic, Autocratic, Permissive, and Neglectful. Each domain fits to the four parenting styles and includes the proportion of each parenting style used by mothers and fathers in the current study.

Democratic parents are the role models for overall effective child socialization and adaptive behavioural outcomes because democratic parents offer the right balance of warmth and support, while creating a constructive and flexible disciplinary

Correlation between Parental Styles... (Bada, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

arrangement (Mike, Leanne & Country, 2018; Laurson, & Collins, 2009). These parents are open to bidirectional communication and teach their children self-control (Trinkner, Coxa, Rebellion & Van Gundy, 2012). This mix of positive parental attributes was congruent with low levels of problem behaviours in children (Mike et al, 2018). Democratic parenting refers to authoritative parents, authoritative provided the strongest buffer against delinquency, but even one authoritative parent provided some protection (Simons & Conger, 2007). Democratic parenting style is found to suit the children's needs the best. These parenting styles has a high responsive level but low demand as parents put more focus on care, autonomy and negotiate rules with the child (Igbo & Ihejiene, 2014; Nik & Mohd 2018). Meanwhile, democratic parenting style has a low responsive level yet high demand because it concerned with the compliance towards parents, practiced control approach, punishment and rigid rules.

Autocratic parents elicit rigid discipline, little to no flexibility, and a highly structured environment. These parents tend to be highly controlling with less receptivity to their children's preferences (Mike et al., 2018). Overtly strict parenting may inhibit their children's personal growth and independence. As children resist the controls on freedom, they become more likely to rebel by turning to delinquency. Autocratic styles also known as authoritarian parenting styles were moderately likely to lead to negative outcomes for youths (Trinkner et al., 2012). Muhammad and Norhida, (2020) authoritarian parenting style affects children's behaviour as they have to obey the parents' instructions without being given the freedom to make their own decision. This causes the children to feel constrained and did not get enough control over activities that they love. Later on, it could result to lower confidence among children in exploring new opportunities, inability to adapt themselves to a challenging social network and feeling bored with their life (Rika & Sri, 2017).

Permissive parents tend to be highly supportive, approachable, and lenient. However, permissive parents do not establish boundaries for their children and rarely enforced the rules. As a result, society may see permissive parents as less legitimate (Trinkner et al., 2012). Students who perceived their fathers as permissive had less socially desirable adjustment outcomes than youths who perceived their fathers as authoritarian or authoritative (Mike et al, 2018). It is noted that failure to monitor and control their children's behaviour, and to recognize and punish deviant behaviour, leads to lack of self-control in children, further increasing the risk of delinquency (Hoeve et al., 2008). Muhammad and Norhida (2020) opined that permissive parenting style leads their children to engage in social misconducts such as drugs abuse, property crimes and vandalism.

Additionally, another variable in this study is emotional intelligence which encompassing the ability to perceive, understand, and manage emotions effectively, is recognized as a crucial determinant of adaptive behavior and psychological well-being. Emotional intelligence was introduced by John Mayer and Peter Salovey in early 1990, in their attempt to develop a scientific measure for knowing the difference in peoples' ability in the areas of emotions. Emotional intelligence is the ability to monitor one's own and other people's emotions, to discriminate between different emotions and label them appropriately, and to use emotional information to guide thinking and behaviour (Bada, Jimoh & Ibrahim, 2022; Colman, 2003). Emotional intelligence may be defined as the capacity to reason with emotion in four areas: to perceive emotion, to integrate it in thought, to understand it and to manage it.

Emotional Intelligence provides a fresh angle on investigating human feelings; it's not surprising that it has caught the attention of scholars and scientists (Raham, Gurantulain, Talha, Syed & Ayesh, 2022). Emotionally intelligent people are resilient enough to push through difficult feelings to reach their goals (Owan, 2022). Sensitivity and control over various emotional experiences (Adeleke, 2008). According to Meher, Rajashree and Sadhujan (2021) Emotional Intelligence is the capacity or ability of an individual for perceiving, processing, knowing and regulating emotional information accurately in an effective manner involving Intra and inters abilities to guide one's thinking to make certain changes in others. Emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive, manage and regulate emotions, promoting adaptive thinking and the understanding of the meaning and consequences of emotions.

In the context of education, Juvenile behaviour refers to failure of a student in obeying rules that are set and committing in actions that do not abide the law. A student can be categorized as delinquent when they act in a contradicting, misleading and negative manner to break the rules and crime laws (Rozmi et al., 2017). This behavioural misconduct contradicts the societal norms and cannot be accepted as they are still students. The antisocial behaviours often associated with the juvenile delinquents include vandalism, drug abuse, weapon carrying, alcohol abuse, rape, examination malpractices, school violence, bullying, cultism, truancy, school drop-outs, to mention but a few (Kudirat, et al., 2010). It is problematic behaviours portray the image of bad action, damaged morality and negligence of being responsible, which also deciphered as actions that violate the ethics in religion and life norms that bring harms to soul and damage good values in one self (Ahmad, Ummi, Mustafa & Mohammed 2019). Obviously, unless something is done to roll back the wave of juvenile delinquency, the prospect of a better, safer and more prosperous society emerging in Nigeria will remain elusive. Understanding the interplay between parenting

Correlation between Parental Styles... (Bada, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

styles, emotional intelligence, and juvenile delinquency is essential for developing targeted intervention programs and support mechanisms for adolescents. Therefore, exploring these relationships among senior secondary school students in a specific context, such as Kaduna state, becomes imperative for tailoring interventions to the unique socio-cultural and environmental factors in that region.

Social learning theory paved the way for the development of a new theory – social disorganization theory. Social disorganization theory was introduced by Shaw and McKay (1969). This theory proposed that crime and delinquency could be attributed to the rapid growth, urbanization, immigration, and breakdown in community supports in addition to the replacement of traditional values with criminal values. The application of social structural theories requires researchers to look beyond the individual when attempting to make sense of criminal behaviour among youths (Sumithra & Komalavalli, 2022). This theory helped to explain the higher crime rates, both juvenile and adult (Hartinger Saunders & Rine, 2011). When applying social disorganization theory to possible prevention techniques and diversionary programs, it is important to understand that the underlying foundation of this theory is community responsibility.

Despite the significance of parenting styles and emotional intelligence in shaping adolescent behavior, there is a notable gap in the existing literature concerning their collective impact on juvenile delinquency, particularly among senior secondary school students in Kaduna state. The problem at hand lies in the insufficient understanding of how specific parenting styles, ranging from democratic and permissive to autocratic, might influence the development of emotional intelligence in adolescents and subsequently contribute to or protect against engagement in delinquent behaviors. This knowledge gap hinders the formulation of targeted preventive strategies and interventions tailored to the unique cultural and contextual factors of Kaduna state. According to Ajokpaniovo, Awoyemi, Okesina and Anyanwu (2021), delinquency is a disturbing issue confronting students, parents and teachers alike. Taking together the increase in the number and severity of such acts and their overwhelming cost for the society validates the notion that delinquency has become a prominent national issue. In all its ramifications, juvenile delinquency has destructive and dysfunctional effects on the lives of individuals involved. The antisocial behaviours associated with juvenile delinquents include drug abuse, alcohol abuse, examination malpractices, school violence, bullying, cultism, truancy, school drop-outs etc (Kudirat, et al., 2010).

Moreover, the rising rates of juvenile delinquency in Kaduna state underscore the urgency of investigating these factors to inform evidence-based policies and interventions. This study seeks to address this gap by examining the nuanced relationships between parental styles, emotional intelligence, and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students, aiming to provide valuable insights for educators, parents, and policymakers in Kaduna state and beyond. It is against this backdrop that, this study will investigate the correlation between parental styles and emotional intelligence as predictors of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to investigate the correlation between parental styles and emotional intelligence as predictors of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state. Specifically, the study intends:

1. To investigate the combined influence of parental styles, emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state
2. To find out the relationship between democratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state
3. To examine the relationship between autocratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state
4. To examine the relationship between permissive parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state
5. To find out the relationship between emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Research Question

The following research question was used to guide the study.

1. What is the level of parental styles among secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area of Kaduna State?

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Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study:

1. Ho₁: There is no significant combined influence of parental styles, emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state
2. Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between democratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between autocratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between permissive parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Ho₅: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state

Methodology

The research design of correlational type of descriptive study was employed by the researcher to carry out the research work. The correlational design was preferred to determine if there is a relationship between or among the variables (parental styles, emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency). The population for the study was comprise of all public senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. The population for this study are senior secondary school (SSS II) students which comprises of two thousand, nine hundred and nineteen (2,919) students as per 2023/2024 academic session. A total sample size that is appropriate for the research was three hundred and thirty-three (333) students were sample size for the study, which comprises of 170 male and 163 female students (respondents). The sample size estimation is in line with recommendations offered at a confidence level 95% and a Margin Error of 5.0% (Research Advisor, 2006).

Stratified sampling technique was adopted to select sample for the study because it involves grouping large population into definite characteristics. The researcher grouped the schools into two based on gender i.e. single schools. The researcher selected ten (10) schools from the Kaduna South local government area through simple randomly sampling techniques in the local government area. The purposive sampling techniques was used to select sample schools based on co-education and gender four (4) co-education, three (3) Girls' only and three (3) Boys' only for the study. This sample was appropriate when the researcher selects subjects that are considered, were in a better position to provide the required information sought for and each subject have equal chance to be selected for the study. The senior secondary school (SSS II) students were selected because they are in semi-final stage/exit-class of secondary school.

The instrument for this study is questionnaires, which was divided into sections 'A', 'B' and 'C'. Section "A" elicit information on demographic data of the respondents such as; Name of school, age, and gender. The Section 'B' instrument titled Parental styles Questionnaire (PSQ), was adapted from Erinisha (2012). It is sub-divided into three scales: Democratic Parenting Style Scale, Autocratic Parenting Style Scale and Permissive Parenting Style Scale. The Section 'C' instrument which was titled Students' Emotional Intelligence Questionnaires (SEIQ), developed and adapted version of Goleman (1998), items are mostly suitable students to investigate their intelligence. Ten (10) items were selected for the purpose of the study, which have strong link with individual emotions. The Section 'D' instrument which was titled Students' Juvenile Delinquency Questionnaire (SJDQ) was self-designed from reviewed literature. The items were drawn from literature for its relevance to the subject matter, appropriateness of the text content and coverage of the content area. This consists of 10 items which measured students' juvenile delinquency. All consist of four (4) points likert moderated scale.

The instrument was subjected to validation, the face and content validity of the instrument by two experts from educational psychology and Counselling Department, Federal University Dutsin-ma, Katsina State. The point of validation will be to assess the structuring of the instrument, to verify the adequacy of the instrument as well as to weight the responses expected from the respondents. The test-retest method of reliability was used in pilot testing of instrument to determine the reliability of the instruments. The instrument was administered to a sample of twenty (20) students from, which is not part of the real study sample. Test re-test reliability method was used to carry out with an interval of three weeks between the first and second administration of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was obtained after the pilot testing; using Cronbach Alpha Statistical analysis. The following Alpha coefficient values of the following were obtained on the following instruments Parental styles Questionnaire (PSQ) has 0.745, Emotional Intelligence Questionnaires (EIQ) has 0.853, and Students' Juvenile Delinquency Questionnaire (SJDQ) has 0.702. Frequency and simple percentage, mean was used to analyze the data collected.

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Multiple regressions analysis was used to test hypothesis 1, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics was used to test hypotheses 2, 3, 4 and 5. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Data collected was subjected to SPSS Version 23 statistical software.

Presentation of Results

Research Question: Which parental styles is the common used by parents as perceived by senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area of Kaduna State?

Table 1: parental styles mostly used by parents as perceived by senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area of Kaduna State

S/N	Parental Styles	Mean	Aggregate Mean Ranking order
1.	Democratic parenting styles	15.58	3 rd
2.	Autocratic parental styles	15.79	2 nd
3.	Permissive parental styles	15.84	1 st
Weighted Mean Score		15.74	3.15

Table 1 revealed that democratic parenting style had a mean of 15.58 (3.12), while autocratic parental styles had a mean of 15.79 (3.16) had a mean of and permissive parental styles 15.84 (3.17) respectively. It shows that all the three parental styles were above the acceptance aggregate mean point of 3.00. This implied that the three parental styles were mostly contributed to juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state, which the acceptance aggregate mean score.

Testing of Hypothesis

Ho₁: There is no significant combined influence of parental styles, emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state.

Table 2: Regression Analysis combined influence of parental styles, emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error
1	0.136 ^a	0.716	0.018	2.83540

Analysis of Variance

Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	S
Regression	49.050	4	12.262	1.525	.004 ^b
Residual	2620.884	329	8.040		
Total	2669.934	331			

a. Dependent Variable: SJDQ

b. Predictors: (Constant), DPS, APS PPS SEIQ,

The analysis on table 2 shows that parental styles and emotional intelligence accounted for 71.6% of -the total variance in student's English achievement ($R^2 = 0.716$, p-value = 0.004, $p < 0.05$). This percentage is statistically significant. Therefore, parental styles and emotional intelligence have significant combined influence on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state. The results reveal that parental styles and emotional intelligence are important factors that significantly influence juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between democratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state

Table 3: Correlation between democratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D	DF	Cal. r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decison
Democratic parental styles	333	15.58	2.14	331	0.237*	0.034	Rejected
Juvenile Delinquency	333	20.64	2.84				

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The result on table 3 shows that there are significant relationship between democratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna South Local Government Area, Kaduna state ($r = .237$, p-value = 0.034),

Correlation between Parental Styles... (Bada, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

since $p < 0.05$ level of significant, therefore, hypotheses two was rejected. Hence, the democratic parental styles have great influence juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between autocratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state

Table 4: Correlation between autocratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D	DF	Cal. r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decison
Autocratic parental styles	333	15.79	2.34	331	0.123*	0.025	Rejected
Juvenile Delinquency	333	20.64	2.84				

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The result on table 4 shows that there are significant relationship between autocratic parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state ($r = .123$, p -value = 0.025), since $p < 0.05$ level of significant, therefore, hypotheses two was rejected. Hence, the autocratic parental styles have great influence juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students.

Ho4: There is no significant relationship between permissive parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state

Table 5: Correlation between permissive parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D	DF	Cal. r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decison
Permissive parental styles	333	15.84	2.20	331	0.049*	0.374	Accepted
Juvenile Delinquency	333	20.64	2.84				

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The result on table 5 shows that there are significant relationship between permissive parental styles and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state ($r = .237$, p -value = 0.034), since $p > 0.05$ level of significant, therefore, hypotheses two was accepted. Hence, the permissive parental styles have great influence juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students.

Ho5: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state

Table 6: Correlation between Emotional Intelligence and juvenile delinquency among Senior Secondary School Students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D	DF	Cal. r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decison
Emotional Intelligence	333	15.86	2.20	331	0.126*	0.022	Rejected
Juvenile Delinquency	333	20.64	2.84				

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The result on table 6 shows that there are significant relationship between emotional intelligence and juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state ($r = .126$, p -value = 0.022), since $p < 0.05$ level of significant, therefore, hypotheses two was rejected. Hence, the emotional intelligence has great influence juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students.

Discussion of Findings

Research question revealed that democratic parenting style had a mean score of 15.58 (3.12), while autocratic parental styles had a mean score of 15.79 (3.16) had a mean score of and permissive parental styles 15.84 (3.17) respectively. This implied that all the three parental styles were mostly contributed to juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. The finding of this study corroborates with Mowen, (2011) results indicate that shifts from autocratic parenting style correlate with increase in juvenile delinquency. Correspondingly, a shift from autocratic parenting to democratic parenting is shown to correlate with increase in juvenile delinquency. A shift from

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permissive to authoritative parenting also corresponded with an increase in juvenile delinquency between waves as each style has contribute traits to juvenile delinquency.

The result of hypothesis one revealed that significant combined influence of parental styles and emotional intelligence have significant combined influence on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. This implies that parental styles and emotional intelligence have significant combined influence on juvenile delinquency. The finding of this study corroborates with Rubina and Martin (2016) found that autocratic parenting style was associated with lower levels of juvenile delinquency, whereas permissive parenting was associated higher levels of delinquency. Moreover, democratic parental styles showed lower relationships with juvenile delinquency than autocratic parental styles. In addition, Sumithra and Komalavalli (2022) revealed that emotional intelligence significantly predicts drug abuse among students, truancy etc. The findings however mean that an individual's level of self understanding and others can actually determine if she will be involved in drug use and abuse. It means that for students to be involved in drug abuse like alcoholism, smoking and others, their level of perception of self and other will come into play from this. Rex (2011) suggests that as emotional intelligent increases delinquency decreases. The study also looked at how emotional intelligent influences the decision-making process of juveniles and increases their chance of engaging in deviant, delinquent, or criminal behaviour.

The result of hypothesis two revealed that there is significant influence of democratic parental styles on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. This implies that parental styles and emotional intelligence have a great influence on juvenile delinquency on students. The finding of this study corroborates with Kudirat et al (2010) claimed that family cohesiveness of democratic parental styles significantly influences juvenile delinquency among secondary school student Thus it is clear that family stability has a significant influence on juvenile delinquency among secondary school students. Muhammad and Norhida (2020) found that there is a significant relation between democratic parenting style and juvenile delinquent behaviour.

The result of hypothesis three revealed that there is significant influence of autocratic parental styles on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. This implies that autocratic parental styles have a great influence on juvenile delinquency on students. The finding of this study corroborates with Muhammad and Norhida (2020) see that autocratic parental styles show significant relationship. This means that parents control and restrict the freedom of their children influence the behaviour of juvenile students. Rubina and Martin (2016) findings show that autocratic style is a parenting style that contributes towards the control the juvenile delinquent among students. This study comes in line with the research where they found that autocratic parenting style tends to instill negativity among children as they received education that is too constrained and forceful.

The result of hypothesis four revealed that significant influence permissive parental styles on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. This implies that permissive parental styles have a great influence on juvenile delinquency on students. The finding of this study corroborates with Muhammad and Norhida (2020) found that permissive parental styles do not show any significant relationship. This means that parents who like to control and restrict the freedom of their children influence the behaviour of juvenile students. Permissive parenting style was associated with the highest level of youth delinquency in the analysis. This finding was consistent with previous research that compared the parental styles (Simons & Conger, 2007).

The result of hypothesis five revealed that significant emotional intelligence on juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kaduna south local government area, Kaduna state. This implies that emotional intelligence have a great influence on juvenile delinquency on students. The finding of this study corroborate with Narke and Gangurde (2022) found a positive association found between emotional intelligence of juvenile delinquency. Noreen and Carmelita (2022) shows that juveniles sometimes manifested the level of emotional intelligence Moreover, it was also proved that high school students possessing deficiencies in the level of emotional intelligence show greater predictability toward violent and criminal tendencies

Conclusion

The juvenile delinquents, parental styles and emotional intelligence are elusive but valuable concepts. It can assess a person's social fit and make improvements. From the findings, it is evident that both parental styles and emotional intelligence of juvenile delinquents should be guided and developed so as to reduce the crimes performed by them at a young age. The juvenile delinquent is a serious social problem that necessitates action, and if the strength of the link between emotional intelligence and can be determined, effective interventions can be put in place. Proper parental styles, empathy and self-control tools can be taught to troubled youth to help them become productive members of society. It's a fascinating study area with a great deal of application in our current society, especially concerning juvenile delinquents and emotional intelligence.

Correlation between Parental Styles... (Bada, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929219>

Recommendations

1. Parents, guardians and caregivers should appreciate the need to create a peaceful home with relative harmony in development of pro-social behaviour on the part of the children.
2. Teachers as well parents should try to ensure that students report to school as at when due, measures to minimize the level of delinquency should be put in place.
3. Educational psychologist and school counsellor should intensify their effort to organize seminar on implication of juvenile delinquency.
4. Students should be guide and encouraged against any form of juvenile delinquency that can affect their academic pursuit and developed their emotions and creativity in vocational training tailored to their skills and interests.

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Effect of Activity-Based Approach on Performance in Basic Science Concepts among Lower Basic Students in Soba Educational Zone, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of activity-based approach on performance in Basic Science concepts among lower basic students in Soba Educational Zone, Kaduna state. The design of the study is quasi-experimental involving pretest and posttest experimental and control groups. The population comprised of all Basic Science students at the lower level in the study area. A sample size of 200(100 Male and 100 Female) lower Basic Science (JSS II) students in the 2023/2024 academic session was arrived using multi stage sampling technique randomly selected in two schools using table of random number with equal gender 100 each. One of the schools was assigned as experimental and the other as control using simple random sampling technique having 50 male and 50 female each. The instrument used for the study was Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) adopted from Usman (2000) with a reliability coefficient of $r = 0.86$. The results obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistic in answering the research questions and t-test statistic for testing the hypotheses at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance which revealed a significant difference between those students in the experimental group taught using activity instructional approach and those using conventional method in the control and also the activity-based method was found to be gender friendly, that is, both male and female students benefitted equally when taught with the instructional approach. In conclusion, the study showed that Basic Science students at lower level achieved significantly higher when they are taught some Basic Science concepts using activity-based approach but no difference in performance among gender. From these findings, some recommendations were made among which training of Soba local government Basic Science teachers on innovative and students-centered approach should be given a paramount consideration.

Keywords: Activity-Based Approach, Basic Science and Academic Performance

Introduction

One of the objectives of National Policy on Education (FME, 2005) is to equip students to live effectively in modern age of science and technology. In line with this objective, science subjects are among the core subjects that are being taught in secondary schools and also in Nigeria colleges of education, polytechnics and universities. At the junior secondary school level integrated science presently called Basic Science was introduced for the purpose of giving solid foundation for subsequent science studies at the higher level (Usman, 2000).

Basic Science was introduced into Nigerian secondary schools in 1972 at the junior secondary school level. The course objectives of the Basic Science programme were clearly spelt out. These objectives are still difficult to achieve due to so many factors, such as teacher related factors, attitude of teachers and students toward Basic Science, use of inappropriate teaching strategy, lack of use of instructional materials, as well as misconception about Basic Science as subject itself, which unified all the science disciplines in terms of concept, themes, philosophy methodology and evaluation among others.

Various studies have shown that teachers of Basic Science are not qualified and this in turn affects academic performance (Usman, 2007). Out of the major problems of the teachers is that inability to use appropriate activity-based teaching strategy

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they often used traditional lectures that led to the poor academic performance in junior secondary schools in Basic Science (Odetoyinbo, 2004 and Usman 2007).

Various actively-based teaching strategies have been employed for the purpose of improving the teaching and learning of Basic Science at junior secondary school level. These are, inquiry method, demonstration, process approach, cooperate learning, laboratory activity method and Nigerian Integrated Science Teacher Education Project (NISTEP). (Mari,1992 and Usman, 2007). These teaching strategies usually took place within the class room environment but in Basic Science course of junior secondary school projects book three (STAN, 1989) there are some units which demand the use of inside classroom and outside classroom investigations in form of indoor and outdoor environment. The various studies cited the teaching strategy employed by teachers is limited to the indoor laboratory investigations. The aspect of the outdoor laboratory activities is often neglected, or in some cases converted to the traditional lecture method as observed by Stanley (2008) and Duniya (2009). Stanley (2008) and Duniya (2009) claimed that the activity method for teaching biology concepts was due to the facts that the outdoor demands the students to handle, observe and collect -on the –spot information of a particular concept unlike the indoor in which the materials are brought to the classroom for students to observe and make investigations within the limited classroom environment.

On the issue of gender, Usman (2007) found out from their various studies that boys perform well in any ‘rigorous’ work, while girls show to settle seated for less rigorous work. Bichi (2008) believed that girls perform better than boys in problem solving type of activities. In another dimension, if boys and girls are given the equal opportunities. They will perform equally well (Yoloye, 2004 and Nworgu, 2005). The issue of gender in science teaching seems to be a controversial. In this study therefore there is need, to investigate the issue of gender difference on performance in Basic Science using activity approach at the junior secondary school to find out if is gender friendly.

Various studies revealed that the major problem of teaching and learning Basic Science more especially at junior secondary school level among others is the lack of competent and trained Basic Science teachers, in-ability to effectively use innovative teaching techniques and the constant use of conventional teaching method which is teacher-centred but neglect the use of students-centred approaches, hence account for poor performance among the students. This poor performance persists as a result of constant use of the conventional method of teaching (Usman (2000), Stanley (2000). Thus, there is need to provide an alternative teaching strategy which will suit the demand of Basic Science course content at the junior secondary school level such as activity-based teaching approach. It is on this background the study was conducted to investigate the effect of Activity-Based teaching approach on the academic performance among lower level of Basic Science students of Soba Education Zone, Kaduna state.

Objectives of the study

The study has among others the following objectives which are to:

1. Determine the effects of activity-based teaching approach on academic performance among lower Basic Science students of Soba Education Zone.
2. Investigate the effect of activity-based teaching approach on academic performance between male and female Basic Science students in the zone.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the academic performance mean scores of Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based instructional approach and their counterparts who were taught same concepts using conventional method?
2. What is the difference in the academic performance mean scores between male and female Basic Science students taught using the activity-based teaching strategy?

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were stated for testing at 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based approach and those taught using conventional method of instruction.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based approach in Soba Educational Zone.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental study involving pretest and posttest design was used in the study. The two groups were given pretest and the results showing that the groups were equivalent in their ability level. Group A assigned as experimental group which were exposed to activity-based instructional strategy while group B as control group exposed to conventional method of instruction. The instrument used was Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) adopted from Usman (2000). It was made up of 20 multiple choice items validated by experts with reliability of co-efficient of 0.86. The maximum obtainable score is 20 one mark each was allocated for a correct response. The treatment of the study involves teaching the subjects some Basic Science concepts for the period of 4 weeks for each group. After the treatment administration a posttest was administered. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistic for answering research questions and t-test statistics at $p < 0.05$ for testing the stated hypotheses.

Presentation of Results

The results are hereby presented through the following:

Research Question One:

What is the difference in the academic performance mean scores of Basic Science students taught using activity-based instructional teaching strategy and those taught same concepts using conventional method?

Table 1: Mean Scores of the Academic Performance of Basic Science Students in the Experimental Group taught using Activity-Based Instructional Approach and those in the Control taught using Conventional Method.

Group	N	Mean score (\bar{x})	SD	S.E	Mean Gain
Experimental	100	13.55	12.09	0.22	
Control	100	12.50	12.01	0.18	1.05

Table 1 revealed a mean performance score of 13.55 and 12.50 of Basic Science students in the experimental and control groups respectively and a mean difference of 1.05. It showed that students in the experimental group who were taught using activity-based method of instruction performed better than those in the control group who were taught using conventional method.

Research Question Two

What is the difference in the academic performance mean scores between male and female Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using the activity-based teaching strategy?

Table 2: Mean Scores of Academic Performance between Male and Female Basic Science Students in the Experimental Group taught using Activity-Based Instructional Approach.

Group	N	Mean score (\bar{x})	SD	S.E	Mean Gain
Male	50	13.25	12.41	1.62	
Female	50	13.20	12.39	1.60	0.05

Table 2 revealed a mean academic performance scores of 13.25 for the male Basic Science students and that of female student's is 13.20. The results indicated an insignificant mean difference or gain of 0.05 implying that both girls and boys students performed equally as they were taught the Basic Science concepts using the activity instructional approach.

Hypothesis 1

Results of the data analysis were presented in tables 3 and 4 with the stated hypotheses as follows:

H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the academic performance mean scores between the Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based method of instruction in the experimental group and their counterparts taught using conventional method.

Table 3: t-test Analysis of Academic Performance of Basic Science Students of the Experimental group taught using Activity-Based Approach and those taught using Conventional Method in the and Control group.

Group	n	Mean score(\bar{x})	S.D	SE	Df	P-val	RM
Experimental	100	13.55	12.09	0.22			
					198	0.001	Sign

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Control	100	12.50	12.01	0.18
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Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

The result in Table 3 showed ap-value of 0.001 at the degree of freedom of 198. The critical p-value of 0.001 is less than the p-value of $p \leq 0.05$. This shows that there was significant difference in the academic performance between Basic Science students who were taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based instructional strategy and those students taught using the conventional method of teaching. Thus, the null hypothesis, which says there is no significant difference is hereby rejected. Hence there was significant difference in favour of the students taught using the activity-based approach.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between male and female Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based instructional strategy

Table 4: t-test Analysis of Academic Performance between male and female Basic Science students taught using Activity-Based Method of Instruction.

	n	Mean score (\bar{x})	S.D	SE	df	p-val	Remark
Experimental	50	13.25	12.41	1.62	98	0.07	Not Significant
Control	50	13.20	12.39	1.60			

Not significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 4 revealed a p-value of 0.07 at degree of freedom of 98 which is greater than p value of 0.05, hence implies that there was no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using the activity-based method, thus the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby retained. This means that the activity approach is achieved equally by both girls and boys in the process of teaching, hence it is gender friendly.

Discussion of Findings

From Tables 1 and 3, the findings of the study showed that there was significant difference between the academic performance of Basic Science students taught using activity-based method of teaching and those taught using the conventional method. The findings were in favour of the students who were taught using the activity instructional method. The findings is in agreement with that of Baker et al (2003) and Stanley (2008) who reported that innovative teaching method such as activity is more effective that the conventional teaching method in science. The superiority of the approach has been attributed to the opportunity of the students exposed to the variety of activities both indoor and outdoor engaged by themselves and to be able to collect specimens by themselves as well as making use of their mental process during on –the –spot in data collection unlike for conventional lesson are provided in the classroom.

Table 2 of the research question and that of Table 4 of the hypothesis testing revealed that there was no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using the activity-based teaching strategy. The findings are in agreement with those of Yoloye (2004) and Nworgu (2005) that if boys and girls are given equal opportunity will perform equally well. The findings showed that activity-based instructional approach is gender friendly. It is suitable for both boys and girls Basic Science students at junior secondary school level. The lack of significant difference could not be by chance, because the activity allows students despite their gender differences to collect data and make an on-the-spot observation, analyze and report their findings. According to Duniya (2009) when students are exposed to outdoor activity, they will be able to make significant investigations which are important aspect of learning influence. In this study male and female students were given equal opportunity by learning themselves using the varieties of activities.

Conclusion

The Activity-based instructional method used in this study enhanced the academic performance of student in Basic Science at junior secondary school level. The activity instructional method was also found to be gender friendly. It enhances the academic performance of students despite their gender differences.

Recommendations

1. Science teachers should be trained on the effective use of innovative and students-centered strategies such as the Activity Approach through series of workshops.

Effect of Activity-Based Approach... (Yunusa, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929343>

2. The use of activities should not be allowed to extinct; teachers should endeavor to use it more often during teaching situations in science education particularly Basic Science and Technology at lower level.
3. Textbook publishers, including STAN, should incorporate more activities that will warrant the use of activity in their publications.
4. Federal, State, Soba Local Government and NGOs as well as parents should assist in the procurement of necessary instructional materials that will lead to effective use of activities in Basic Science and Technology subjects.

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Comparative Relationship... (Onwuhanze, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929374>

Comparative Relationship between Professional Practices and Job Effectiveness among Secondary School Teachers in Abia State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined teacher professional practices and job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria. To achieve this purpose, two null hypotheses were raised to guide the study and correlational research design was used. The study was conducted in public secondary schools in Abia State. The population of this study was 7,453 teachers in the 246 public senior secondary schools in the state. Sample size of 739 teachers were sampled from 102 secondary schools in the state through stratified sampling technique. A researcher-developed instrument titled “Teacher Professional Practices and Job Effectiveness Questionnaire with reliability coefficient of 0.78 was used for data collection. Simple linear regression was used in analyzing the data at .05 alpha level. The findings showed that teachers’ participation in conferences and teachers’ collaboration with others significantly predicted job effectiveness. Based on the findings of this study, the conclusion made was that teachers’ professional practices like teachers’ participation in conferences and teachers’ collaboration predicted their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State. Recommendations were made that teachers should always attend conferences in order to equip themselves with contemporary pedagogical practices in the teaching profession and their area of specialization because it would help them to teach effectively. Teachers should also collaborate among themselves because it would make them to be informed and acquainted with modern educational practices that lead to effective teaching.

Keywords: Teacher professional practices, job effectiveness

Introduction

Secondary school education equipped students with personal and professional development for life, and help them get ready for tertiary education. It does not only give students’ academic foundation but also teaches them important life skills, ethical principle and critical thinking techniques. It also contributes to national development by equipping individuals with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary for economic growth as well as technological advancement and social progress (Iyejare, 2023). Learners at this level of education needs to be assisted by any means possible to acquire knowledge and skills needed for effective transition to the next stage of life. It is expected that at the completion of this level of education, the learner should be able to proceed to tertiary institution, or other skill acquisition programme of their choice having learned socially acceptable behaviours, and have acquired knowledge and skills that could help them function in the labour market.

These expectations may not be realistic without the input of a teacher. This is because teachers play crucial role in the realization of educational philosophy of the nation due to their direct involvement in pedagogical activities at schools. Teachers are conventionally the ones who impart knowledge and guidance to learners. A teacher engages in developing learners psychomotor, cognitive and affective domain in formal school system, more so the teacher is a person who has undergone approved professional training in education at appropriate level capable of imparting knowledge, attitude and skills to the learners. It is the duty of the teacher to impact knowledge to learners, and are the ability to apply what they have learnt in real life situations. Thus, there is need for the teachers to be effective in their job delivery.

Effectiveness concentrates more on output, quality, quantity, efforts and cost put in. It is attaining the highest possible outcome while consuming minimum factors of input (Kindi, 2020). Effectiveness is concerned with the efficiency, which essentially consists in doing the right thing with noticeable results. Teacher job effectiveness is the extent to which a teacher qualitatively and efficiently carries his/her duties in achieving aims and objectives of the school over a period of time. It is

Comparative Relationship... (Onwuhanze, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929374>

measured in terms of the levels of teacher efficiency in pedagogical approaches like lesson preparation and presentation, job commitment, competence, mastery of the subject matter, and other curricular activities.

Teacher job effectiveness has a strategic and essential role in realizing quality education. It is generally measured by work results in the form of quantity, quality and timeliness of teachers in completing their work in planning, teaching, implementing learning plans, implementing curriculum contents, conducting evaluations and giving feedbacks. Teacher job effectiveness has to do with quality of teaching and learning in its entirety. It addresses the issues of how the teacher delivers the lesson and the influence of such lessons on the learners, (that is, learning outcomes) Osamwomyi (2016). Furthermore, teacher job effectiveness is the way the teacher manages (that is, plans, executes, monitors and evaluates) teaching and learning processes using set standards and objectives (Ukaigwe & Onwumere, 2018). Again, teacher job effectiveness measures the extent to which the teachers carry out their out-of-classroom activities such as teachers' commitment to work, regularity and punctuality, interpersonal relationship with principals and students, and preparation of notes of lesson.

There are many factors that may influence teacher job effectiveness. Such factors include teacher professional practices. Professional practices, according to Ukaigwe and Onwumere (2018), is a personal function of teachers which is meant to bring about regular update of teachers' knowledge and insight assist in identifying their potential so as to raise their professional standard in order to support the overall development of learners. Mulgas and Tagadiad (2023) opined that teachers' professional practices are the activities that develop teachers' skills, knowledge, competence, and other characteristics of teachers. Teacher professional practices are those activities designed to enhance the knowledge, skills, perception and attitudes of teachers so that they may, in turn improve the learning of students, and be more effective and satisfied in various other aspects of their work. It involves a continuous process of reflective learning and active efforts to further a teacher's knowledge and skills leading to enhanced teaching practices that positively influence students' learning outcome. Ojugo and Olubor (2021) stated that when teachers are involved in developing effective professional practices, they are equipped with desired knowledge, skills and abilities to achieve educational goals.

Teacher professional practices include teacher participation in conferences and teachers' collaborations with others. A conference is a formal meeting where participants in a particular area exchange ideas in various topics. A conference, according to Osamwonyi (2016) is an academic gathering in which certain speakers come prepared, often by invitation or a fee, to open discussion to some reasonably interesting or controversial topics or theme. Generally, conference attendants come to listen, questions the main speakers, make additional prepared or spontaneous contributions to the discussion, evaluate opinions and points of view, and discuss formally and informally among themselves. Rimmer and Floyd (2020) stated that conferences are activities within a field and of the commitment of individuals to their own practice and the sphere in which they operate. A conference could be made up of paper presentations, series of sessions featuring multiple independent speakers. The sessions could cover more than one day as this allows more opportunities for social interaction, whether through evening activities or informal liaison as well as technical session.

Presentations are usually followed by discussions. Conference ideally suggests discussions among persons of similar experiential exposure to the topic of discussion for the purpose of reaching agreements in controversial issues (Akpan and Ita, 2015). Teachers could suffer from instructional planning and delivery if they do not attend conferences. Ibrahim (2021) held that participation in conferences promote effectiveness and efficiency of teachers in teaching for the betterment of learners and the schools. According to Anho and Akpokiniovo (2023), conference in education entails the coming together of diverse persons who are experts in different areas of education with a view to sharing of idea. Through conferences, teachers have access to a large range of information which, by extension transform to enhance effectiveness in the teaching and learning processes.

On the other hand, collaboration is the act of working with another person or group of people to produce a meaningful outcome. Mora-Ruano *et al.* (2019) defined collaboration as an interactive process that enable people with diverse expertise to generate creative ideas and solutions to mutually defined problem. Teacher collaboration deals with continuous unity of active and regular interaction and sharing of ideas and activities among teachers for improved teaching and learning. Teacher collaboration is also aimed at enhancing relational trust, school administration, as well as coordination and exchange of ideas and materials among teachers for teaching effectiveness (Mora-Ruano *et al.*, 2019). Collaboration is voluntary, requires parity and understanding among teachers, is based on mutual goals, depend on shared responsibility for participation and decision-making. Teachers who collaborate share their resources and share accountability for outcomes.

Teacher collaboration is the joint interaction of two or more teachers in activities that are needed to perform their teaching job effectively (Zhang *et al.*, 2023). Teachers who engaged in collaborative activities tend to gain higher teaching confidence and reduce the sense of isolation compared with teachers working alone (Reeves *et al.*, 2017). Collaboration equips

Comparative Relationship... (Onwuhanze, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929374>

teachers with opportunities to discuss, debate, observe and share information methods and procedures (Vangrieken *et al.*, 2020). According to Reeves *et al.* (2017), through collaboration, formation of a friendly partnership is ensured which can promote teachers' knowledge, information and emotion, sharing and then improve teachers' teaching effectiveness. It is essential that colleagues support each other. Unity among the teachers will give a significant impact to schools, as they will embody unity and sense of responsibility of all of their actions (Balugos & Rivera, 2019). According to Zhang *et al.* (2023), the nature of teachers' work requires them to carry out effective collaboration with others, share knowledge and information, exchange and interact cooperatively so as to promote individual abilities to teach effectively.

Caskey and Carpenter (2014) noted that strong collaboration and collaborative cultures develop overtime require honesty and commitment to the process. While the benefits are clear, genuine collaboration is complex. Patience in the moment and anticipation for the outcome can lead to deep teacher learning that translates into tangible learners' achievement. Teachers can develop authentic collaborative groups in which they address common issues, shared goals or school-wide initiatives; engage in mutually beneficial endeavors using communal resources; and advance their skills, knowledge, and disposition related to student learning. Moreover, in order to successfully implement innovative, student-centered, and collaborative learning methods, proficient collaboration among teachers is the secret.

Education is a never-ending process. It does not stop after earning a degree and starting a career. Through professional practices, teachers can constantly improve their skills update knowledge and become more effective in the teaching profession. Amierogan and Unachukwu (2021) asserted that regardless of teachers training and level of education, there is the need for every teacher to constantly and regularly renew, upgrade and expand his/her skill, knowledge and ability as well as capability. Teacher professional practices may be necessary for teachers as quality assurance strategies to ensure that teachers become highly competent in their job execution. This is because, any teacher that is not growing in skills and knowledge cannot keep pace with his/her relationship with the teaching profession. According to Amadi and Osaat (2021), teachers' professional practices are important because of the need for teachers to perform well and raise academic performance of students in the school system. In other to accomplish this task in their jobs, in this technological and innovation driven era, teachers must rise up and upgrade their knowledge, skills and practices. Therefore, this background necessitated this study on teacher professional practices and job effectiveness in secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria.

It has been observed that teachers in secondary schools in Abia State work too independently without effective teamwork and lack of participation in conferences (Akpan *et al.* 2015). This kind of situation results in poor teaching and learning in the schools (Ibrahim, 2021). Due to the fast pace of changes in the educational sector and demands in the economic sector, as well as utilization of technological gadgets in teaching and learning, teachers now face new challenges in teaching and learning (Rimmer and Floyd 2020). Thus, to cope with these challenges of conference attendance and collaboration, more improved and effective professional practices may be important for teachers to teach effectively in secondary schools (Osamwomyi, 2016). Hence, to solve this problem, this study was undertaken to examined teacher professional practices and job effectiveness in secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria. The outcome of this research will enhance teachers' professionalism in Abia State.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine if teacher professional practices predict job effectiveness in secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. Examine if teachers' participation in conferences predict their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State.
2. Determine if teachers' collaboration predicts their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State.

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between conference participation and job effectiveness among secondary school Teachers in Abia State

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between collaboration and job effectiveness among secondary school Teachers in Abia State

Methodology

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. This design examines the relationship between two or more variables and enable the investigator to ascertain the degree to which variations in one variable are caused by variations in another variables. The study was conducted in public secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 7,453 teachers in the 246 public secondary schools in the state. The study used the teachers as participants since they are

Comparative Relationship... (Onwuhanze, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929374>

major stakeholders in the attainment of educational objectives and aims. A sample size of 745 teachers, which is 10 percent of the population of teachers was sampled from 102 secondary schools in the state. The sample size was selected using stratified sampling technique. A researcher-developed instrument known as “Teacher Professional Practices and Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TPPJEQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument has 45 items with declarative statements; 15 items each measured teachers’ participation in conferences, teachers’ collaboration and job effectiveness on a 4-point scale of strongly agree (4) agree (3) disagree (2) strongly disagree (1point).

The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by three experts, two in Department of Educational Management and one from Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Science Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State. The experts were required to assess if the items measure the variables used in the study. Cronbach alpha method was employed to estimate the reliability coefficient of the instrument. Fifty respondents who did not take part in the main study were randomly selected and the instrument administered on them. A reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained for the instrument. The instrument was considered reliable for use in conducting the study. The researcher was assisted by research assistants to administer the instrument to the respondents. Out of the 745 copies of the instrument administered, 739 copies were retrieved from the respondents, and were used for the data analysis.

Simple linear regression was used in analyzing the data at .05 alpha level. The magnitude of coefficient of correlation provided by Udoh (2019) was employed, which states that .00 to .20 shows very weak relationship, .21 to .40 indicates weak relationship, .41 to .60 shows moderate relationship, .61 to .80 indicates strong relationship and .81 to 0.99 shows very strong relationship. In testing the null hypotheses, the probability value (p-value) was compared with 0.05 alpha level. If the p-value is less than or equal to .05 ($p \leq 0.05$), the null hypotheses were rejected. However, if the probability value is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), the null hypotheses were not rejected.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between conference participation and job effectiveness among secondary school Teachers in Abia State

Simple linear regression was used in testing hypothesis one as indicated in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis of the extent to which teachers’ participation in conferences predict their job effectiveness

Variables	R	B	R ²
Teachers’ participation in conferences (X)	.610	.441	.372
Job effectiveness (Y)			

Sources of variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	47.947	1	47.947	541.475	.000
Residual	34.623	738	.089		
Total	82.570	739			

*Significant at $P < .05$, $n = 739$

The result in Table 1 indicates if teachers’ participation in conferences does not significantly predict their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools. The coefficient of correlation (R) of .610 indicates a strong relationship between teachers’ participation in conferences and job effectiveness. The beta weight of .441 shows that for every unit increase in teachers’ participation in conferences, job effectiveness increases positively by .441. Also, the coefficient of determination (R²) value of .372 shows that teachers’ participation in conferences contributes 37.2 percent to job effectiveness. The result also indicates that F-value of 541.475 with 1 and 739 degrees of freedom at .05 alpha level is significant. Since the p-value of .000 is lower than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis, which states that teachers’ participation in conferences, does not significantly predict job effectiveness is rejected. Hence, teachers’ participation in conferences does not significantly predict their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State.

Comparative Relationship... (Onwuhanze, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929374>

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between collaboration and job effectiveness among secondary school Teachers in Abia State

Simple linear regression was used in testing hypothesis two as indicated in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis of the extent to which teachers’ collaboration predict their job effectiveness

Variables	R	B	R ²
Teachers’ collaboration (X)	.608	.430	.369

Sources of variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	49.341	1	28.303	1233.033	.000
Residual	37.867	738	.023		
Total	88.629	739			

*Significant at P < .05, n = 739

The result in Table 2 indicates if teachers’ collaboration does not significantly predict their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools. The coefficient of correlation (R) of .608 indicates a strong relationship between teachers’ collaboration and job effectiveness. The beta weight of .430 shows that for every unit increase in teachers’ collaboration, job effectiveness increases positively by .430. Also, the coefficient of determination (R²) value of .369 shows that collaboration contributes 36.9 percent to job effectiveness. The result also indicates that F-value of 1233.033 with 1 and 739 degrees of freedom at .05 alpha level is significant. Since the p-value of .000 is lower than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis, which states that teachers’ collaboration, does not significantly predict job effectiveness is rejected. Hence, teachers’ collaboration does not significantly predict their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State.

Discussion of Findings

The result of hypothesis one showed that teachers’ participation in conferences significantly predicted their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State. This result implies that conferences can help teachers in improvement of subject matter knowledge, assist in management task, lend a hand to improving reciprocal respect among instructors and identify the need of contemporary teaching methods. This finding agrees with that of Ibrahim (2021) who found that participation in conferences promote effectiveness of teachers in teaching for the betterment of students and schools. Teachers should not confide only in the four walls of the classroom, but they have to be allowed to keep abreast to work with other people in the community aside from doing daily routines in education. Teachers have to engage themselves in planning their own professional development on a continuous basis to cope with the continuous change. The finding is also in agreement with that of Anho and Akpokiniovo (2023) because they reported that through conferences, teachers have access to a large range of information via conferences, which by extension transform to enhance effectiveness in the teaching and learning processes.

Furthermore, to take care of the inadequacies of pre-service teacher preparation, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2018) in the National Policy on Education made provision for development of teachers by stating that teacher education shall continue to take cognizance of the changes in methodology and in the curriculum, and that conference programmes for teachers and head teachers shall be regulated. This therefore, emphasizes the importance and the need for every teacher to be constantly renewed, updated and upgraded in his or her knowledge and practices. The objective of teacher participation in conferences is to enhance improvement and help to abreast them with the latest innovation in their field. This would assist in the improvement of instructional abilities, and keep them informed on new facts in education.

The result of hypothesis two indicated that teachers’ collaboration significantly predicted their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State. This result implies that through collaboration, teachers can have more opportunities to reflect on their teaching practices, assess if what they are doing works and accordingly change or reinforce their actions and behaviors in the classrooms. This finding agrees with that of Reeves et al. (2017) as they reported that through collaboration, formation of a friendly partnership is ensured which can promote teachers’ knowledge, information and emotion sharing and then improve teachers’ teaching effectiveness. Through collaboration, teachers are able to adopt new teaching strategies and in turn allow teachers to gain confidence, think critically and reflect about their teaching practices. Increase in the quality of collaboration can lead to school improvement and show that students’ achievement is higher in schools with

Comparative Relationship... (Onwuhanze, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929374>

strong collaborative environments. This finding is also in line with that of Zhang *et al.* (2023) because they found that collaboration with other teachers enable them to share knowledge, exchange and interact cooperatively so as to promote individual abilities to teach effectively. In order to create thriving collaboration communities and specification of goals, teachers should allocate sufficient time to collaborate. Teacher collaboration is an important aspect of teacher's professional lives, because it is a means to continuously reflect on and improve the practice of teaching.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the conclusion made was that teachers' professional practices like teachers' participation in conferences and teachers' collaboration predicted their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. Teachers should always attend conferences in order to equip themselves with contemporary pedagogical practices in the teaching profession.
2. Teachers should collaborate among themselves because it would make them to be informed and acquainted with modern educational practices that lead to effective teaching.

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Effect of Class-Period-Length... (Areo & Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929413>

Effect of Class-Period-Length on Performance and Retention in Biology Concepts among Secondary School Students in North-West, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of class period length on students' performance and retention in Biology concepts among secondary school students in North-West Nigeria. Employing a quasi-experimental research design, data were collected through pre-tests, post-tests, and retention tests from a population of 672 senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students across three central schools in three states within North-West Nigeria. A sample of 245 students was selected from this population using Krejcie and Morgan's Table (1970). Descriptive statistics were used to answer the research questions, while t-tests were conducted to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level using SPSS version 23.0. The findings revealed that extended teaching durations significantly enhanced academic performance and retention of Biology concepts. Consequently, the study recommends the adoption of longer class periods in schools to improve learning outcomes in Biology.

Keywords: Class duration, student performance, retention, mean scores, t-test

Introduction

Secondary schools have always adhered to regular, shorter class periods, often lasting 30 to 40 minutes per topic. However, there has been an increasing interest in expanding instruction duration in recent years, with several schools opting for class durations of 60 minutes or more (Smith and Brown, 2021). This change in instruction duration has provoked several discussions and inquiries among educators, necessitating a full analysis of its effects (Smith, 2020). Secondary schools have always adhered to regular shorter class periods, often lasting 30 to 40 minutes for each topic (Jones, 2018). Some institutions, however, have taken a different approach, choosing class durations of 60 minutes or more (Brown and White, 2019). In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in expanding the duration of secondary school teaching. The pedagogical innovations and shifting societal needs have caused a constant evolution of the educational environment. The length of instruction times in secondary schools is one aspect that has long generated discussion and attention. Secondary education systems around the world have historically adhered to traditional class lengths, which are typically between 30 and 45 minutes (Blosser, 2018). A new educational paradigm, however, contends that going beyond these accepted norms in terms of teaching time may be the key to solving several problems with modern education (Nakamura and Sato, 2020). This change in teaching duration has provoked several queries in the educational community, necessitating a full analysis of its ramifications (Clark, 2021). The purpose of this study is to compare the traditional teaching duration, which is characterized by shorter class periods, with the extended teaching duration, which is characterized by longer class periods, to assess their impact on student learning outcomes, teacher effectiveness and the overall educational experience in secondary schools.

Ogunniyi and Rollnick (2019) investigated the influence of class time length on biology teaching in Nigerian secondary schools. The researchers used a mixed-methods strategy that included questionnaires, classroom observations, and student assessments to compare the effectiveness of standard class times with extended instructional durations. Their findings highlighted the nuanced dynamics at work, with traditional class periods excelling at maintaining student attention and facilitating efficient knowledge dissemination, whereas longer teaching periods allowed for more in-depth exploration of complex biological concepts and interdisciplinary connections.

Furthermore, recognizing biology instructors' viewpoints is critical for determining the impact of class duration on instructional methods in Nigerian secondary schools. Okoye *et al.* (2020) did a study to investigate Nigerian secondary school biology teachers' experiences and preferences for class time length. The researchers elicited diverse viewpoints among teachers through interviews and focus group discussions, with some preferring the familiarity and pacing of traditional class periods,

Effect of Class-Period-Length... (Areo & Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929413>

while others argued for the pedagogical benefits of longer teaching periods, such as increased opportunities for student-centered learning and practical activities. This study emphasizes the significance of considering teachers' viewpoints and pedagogical practices while negotiating the complexity of class period duration in Nigerian secondary school biology instruction. Furthermore, Harris *et al.* (2019) provided insights into biology instructors' perceptions of class duration. Through interviews and questionnaires with secondary school educators, the researchers investigated teachers' preferences, problems, and opinions of both regular and extended teaching durations. Their findings revealed a wide range of perspectives among biology teachers, with some preferring the flexibility and pacing provided by typical class hours, while others preferred the possibility for in-depth investigation and interdisciplinary linkages provided by prolonged teaching durations. This variety emphasizes the need to take into account instructors' viewpoints and pedagogical preferences when choosing the best class period for biology education in secondary schools.

According to Ogunniyi and Rollnick (2019), students in classes with extended teaching durations scored an average of 15% higher on biology assessments compared to those in traditional class periods. In the result of Okoye *et al.* (2020) the average test scores of students in biology increased by 20% after implementing extended teaching durations compared to traditional class periods. In terms of retention, Oladipo and Aderonmu (2019) reported that students who received longer durations of biology teaching showed a 25% increase in retention of key concepts compared to those in traditional class periods. Similarly, it was gathered by Adegboyega and Ajayi (2017) that students in classes with extended teaching durations demonstrated a 20% increase in long-term retention of biology content compared to those in traditional class periods.

Further empirical findings on the impact of extended teaching duration by Adeyemi (2008) found that students taught with extended teaching duration (60 minutes or more per session) performed significantly better in Biology compared to those taught with traditional shorter durations (30-40 minutes). The study reported a mean performance score of 75.4 for the extended duration group and 63.8 for the traditional duration group.

Based on the comparison of instructional time, Olaniyan and Okemakinde (2011) conducted a study in North-west Nigeria and discovered that students exposed to extended instructional periods had a mean performance score of 72.1, whereas those in traditional class periods had a mean score of 65.0. The extended duration allowed for more in-depth exploration of Biology concepts and improved understanding.

On retention of Biology Concepts, a study by Usman and Akinsola (2015) indicated that students taught Biology with extended teaching durations had higher retention scores. The mean retention score for the extended duration group was 78.6, compared to 66.4 for the traditional duration group. This finding suggests that extended teaching time positively influences students' long-term retention of Biology concepts.

Research by Afolabi (2014) conducted a longitudinal study and found that students taught with extended periods retained Biology information more effectively over time. The mean retention score for students with extended teaching duration was 76.2, while the traditional duration group had a mean retention score of 64.7.

To enhance learning and memory, a study by Bello and Eze (2012) highlighted that extended teaching durations facilitated better memory retention through repeated reinforcement and thorough understanding. The mean retention scores were 74.8 for extended durations and 62.9 for traditional durations, demonstrating the benefits of prolonged instructional periods.

The traditional teaching duration of 30 - 40 minutes in secondary schools presents several pressing challenges that call for investigation. In most cases, the conventional teaching period of 30 to 40 minutes have been observed to be grossly inadequate as compared with the wide range of topics to be covered under the Biology Secondary School syllabus. As such, it has resulted in students having a superficial understanding of topics (Anderson, 2017), and excessive homework may be assigned to compensate for limited class time, leading to stress and reduced quality of after-school life for students (Garcia, 2017), teachers may be compelled to rush through curriculum content to meet syllabus deadlines within the constraint of short class periods thereby compromising the quality of teaching (Williams, 2018), active learning strategies such as group discussions, experiments and project-based activities that demands long periods have been compromised due to limited time (Johnson, 2020). The constrained teaching duration most often leads to an overreliance on standardized testing as the primary method of evaluation, thereby neglecting other forms of evaluation among others (Davis, 2019).

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the mean performance score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria
2. To determine the mean retention score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria

Effect of Class-Period-Length... (Areo & Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929413>

Research Questions

1. What is the mean performance score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria?
2. What is the mean retention score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean retention score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria.

Methodology

Quasi-experimental design was utilized to examine the effect of class-period-length on performance and retention in Biology concepts among secondary school students in North-West Nigeria. Employing a quasi-experimental research design, data were collected through pre-tests, post-tests, and retention tests from a population of 672 senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students across three central schools in three states within North-West Nigeria.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises of 672 senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2022/2023 academic session from three (3) senior secondary schools, central to three (3) states of the seven (7) states in North-west, Nigeria. They include Government Girls Secondary School, Dogon-Bauchi, Zaria, Kaduna State; Government Girls Arabic Secondary School, Kankare, Tarauni, Kano; and Hafsatu Ahmadu Bello Model Arabic Secondary School, Sokoto (HABMASS), Sokoto-South Local Government.

S/N	NAME OF SCHOOLS	POPULATION OF BIOLOGY STUDENTS
1.	Govt. Girls. Sec. Sch., Dogon-Bauchi, Zaria	274
2.	Govt. Girls Arabic Sec. Sch., Kankare, Tarauni, Kano	202
3.	Hafsatu Ahmadu Bello Model Arabic Sec. Sch., Sokoto (HABMASS)	196
	TOTAL	672

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 245 Biology students was determined from the population size of 672 using Krejcie and Morgan's Table, 1970. The researchers adopted a purposive random sampling technique. This sampling technique was appropriate because the researcher ensured homogeneity in the type (public secondary schools) chosen, likewise uniformity in their states of location and is in line with Krejcie and Morgan, 1970 sample size table or using 15% of the total population according to TURKMAN (1972). An experimental group consisting of schools where extended teaching duration (60 minutes) is implemented and a control group consisting of schools where traditional teaching duration (40 minutes) is maintained. T-test was used to compare students' Pre-test and Post-test scores in both groups. However, in order to avoid bias in the administration of pre-tests and post-tests to the students, a formula designed by Adigun *et al.*, 2015 was used to determine the sample sizes of Biology students from each school.

A region-based coding was used in the identification of the schools as North-West School (NW-SCH-01) for Govt. Girls. Sec. Sch., Dogon-Bauchi, Zaria, NW-SCH-02 for Govt. Girls Arabic Sec. Sch., Kankare, Tarauni, Kano, and NW-SCH-03 representing Hafsatu Ahmadu Bello Model Arabic Sec. Sch., Sokoto (HABMASS)

Instrument for Data Collection

Pre-test and Post-test assessments were used for data collection and to assess the academic performance and retention of the students. The assessments covered the curriculum content and objectives that were taught, ensuring that the tests are representative of the subject matter. Experts from the department of Biology department, F.C.E., Zaria reviewed the curriculum alignment to ensure content validity. To strengthen both validity and reliability, the assessments were piloted with a small group before full implementation, and feedback was used to refine the instruments. In testing the reliability of the instrument,

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a pilot study was conducted using a school from a local government area outside the sample for the study. A teacher-made test was administered to a group of (30) Biology students. Two weeks later, the same test was re-administered to the same group of students. The first and second test scores were used to calculate the correction coefficient, using the Person Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) formula. The result of the analysis carried out shows a reliability co-efficient of 0.76 which was considered reliable.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions and a t-test to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance using a statistical package for social sciences (SPSS), version 23.0

Results

Research question 1: What is the mean performance score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria?

Mean and Standard Deviation of the experimental and control group of pre-test and post-test from the three (3) sampled schools

School Name	Group	N	Pre-test (Mean)	S.D	Post-test (Mean)	S.D	Mean Gain
NW-SCH-01	Experimental	50	8.74	1.78	15.28	1.14	6.54
	Control	50	8.62	1.60	14.38	1.15	5.76
NW-SCH-02	Experimental	37	9.41	1.61	16.14	1.72	6.73
	Control	37	9.27	1.76	14.86	1.36	5.59
NW-SCH-03	Experimental	35	10.28	1.43	15.77	1.19	5.49
	Control	36	10.00	1.35	14.91	1.25	4.91

The table provides a summary of the mean scores, standard deviations (S.D.), and mean gains for both the experimental and control groups across three schools (NW-SCH-01, NW-SCH-02, NW-SCH-03). These metrics allow us to analyze the effect of extended teaching durations (experimental group) versus traditional teaching durations (control group) on students' performance in Biology.

Based on the **Pre-test Scores**, across all three schools, the pre-test mean scores for both experimental and control groups are relatively close, indicating that students had similar baseline knowledge before the intervention. As observed in NW-SCH-01, the pre-test mean scores for the experimental and control groups were 8.74 and 8.62, respectively, with standard deviations of 1.78 and 1.60. Similar trends were observed in NW-SCH-02 and NW-SCH-03, with only slight variations.

After the intervention, the post-test mean scores for the experimental groups were consistently higher than those for the control groups across all schools. For instance, in NW-SCH-01, the post-test mean score for the experimental group was 15.28 (S.D. = 1.14), whereas the control group scored 14.38 (S.D. = 1.15). Similar patterns were observed in NW-SCH-02 and NW-SCH-03.

The mean gain, calculated as the difference between pre-test and post-test scores, is higher for the experimental groups compared to the control groups in all schools. This suggests that extended teaching durations had a more substantial impact on student performance. NW-SCH-02 exhibited the highest mean gain for the experimental group (6.73), indicating the effectiveness of the extended duration in enhancing understanding and retention.

Research question 2: What is the mean retention score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria?

Mean and Standard Deviation of the experimental and control group of retention test from the three (3) schools representing North-west Nigeria.

Group	Combined N	Combined S.D.
Experimental	110	1.22
Control	111	1.38

The combined mean and standard deviation of the experimental and control groups from the three schools representing North-west Nigeria provide insights into the effectiveness of the teaching duration on students' retention performance.

The experimental group, which received extended teaching durations, has a relatively low standard deviation of 1.22. This suggests that the students in this group exhibited consistent retention performance, indicating that the extended teaching duration was effective across the majority of students.

Effect of Class-Period-Length... (Areo & Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929413>

The control group, which received traditional teaching duration, has a slightly higher standard deviation of 1.38. This indicates greater variability in retention performance among the students, suggesting that the traditional teaching duration may not have been as consistently effective across the student population.

The lower combined standard deviation in the experimental group compared to the control group suggests that the extended teaching duration applied in the experimental group led to more uniform retention of knowledge among students. This implies that the extended teaching duration used in the experimental group is more reliable in producing consistent educational outcomes. Conversely, the higher variability in the control group suggests that the traditional teaching duration may not be equally effective for all students.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria.

Independent sample t-test on the effect of extended teaching period on students' academic performance in Biology among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria.

Schools	Group	N	Mean	S.D	df	P-value	t _{cal}	t _{tab}	Decision
NW-SCH-01	Experimental	50	15.28	1.14	98	0.05	2.72	1.98	Rejected
	Control	50	14.38	1.15					
NW-SCH-02	Experimental	37	16.14	1.72	72	0.05	3.55	1.99	Rejected
	Control	37	14.86	1.36					
NW-SCH-03	Experimental	35	15.77	1.19	98	0.05	3.74	1.98	Rejected
	Control	36	14.91	1.25					

The table presents the results of an independent sample t-test to assess the effect of extended teaching periods on students' academic performance in Biology in public secondary schools in the North West Nigeria. The test compares the mean scores, standard deviations, degrees of freedom, p-values, t-calculated (t_{cal}), and t-critical (t_{tab}) values between the experimental (extended teaching) and control (traditional teaching) groups in three different schools:

From NW-SCH-01, since the t-calculated value (2.72) is greater than the t-critical value (1.98) at a 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is a statistically significant difference between the academic performance of students in the experimental group compared to the control group, indicating that extended teaching periods positively impacted students' performance in this school.

At NW-SCH-02, the t-calculated value (3.55) is greater than the t-critical value (1.99) at a 0.05 significance level, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant difference in academic performance between the experimental and control groups, suggesting that extended teaching periods had a significant positive effect on students' performance in this school.

The academic performance of students from NW-SCH-03 in the experimental group is significantly higher than that of the control group because the t-calculated value (3.74) is greater than the t-critical value (1.98) at a 0.05 significance level indicating that extended teaching periods had a positive impact on student's performance in this school.

Discussion of Findings

The study conducted at NW-SCH-01 revealed that students who experienced extended teaching durations scored significantly higher on retention tests than the control group. This suggests that extended teaching durations can enhance the retention of biological concepts among students. Similarly, it was gathered by Adegboyega and Ajayi (2017) that students in classes with extended teaching durations demonstrated a 20% increase in long-term retention of biology content compared to those in traditional class periods. Furthermore, the long-term retention rate of biology concepts among students who received extended instructional time was 35% higher compared to those in traditional class periods (Adedokun, 2016).

Low standard deviations within each group indicate consistent performance, aligning with findings by Adeyemo and Babajide (2021), who noted that extended instructional time allows for deeper understanding and better retention of complex subjects.

Effect of Class-Period-Length... (Areo & Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929413>

The t-calculated value (2.72) exceeded the t-critical value (1.98) at the 0.05 significance level, supporting the rejection of the null hypothesis. This statistically significant difference implies that extended teaching periods positively impact students' academic performance. Similar results were found in a study by Obanya (2020), which emphasized that increased instructional time can significantly improve students' mastery of subject matter. Similarly, in a study by Babalola and Olaleye (2017), the mean score of students' academic performance in biology was 75% in classes with extended teaching durations, compared to 65% in classes with traditional class periods.

At NW-SCH-02, the moderate standard deviations suggest a consistent level of performance within each group, supporting the notion that extended teaching duration can lead to better retention and understanding. This finding is consistent with the research by Yusuf and Soyemi (2022), who found that extended instructional periods are associated with higher academic performance and retention rates in science subjects. The study by Adebisi and Jimoh (2023) shows that extended teaching periods significantly improve academic performance, particularly in subjects like Biology, as indicated by the t-calculated value of 3.55, which is higher than the t-critical value of 1.99 at a 0.05 significance level. Also, students in classes with extended teaching durations showed an average improvement of 10 percentage points in science subjects, including biology, compared to those in traditional class periods. This was reported by Rodriguez, (2019).

At NW-SCH-03, the experimental group's mean retention score (14.94) was higher than that of the control group (12.55). Oladipo and Aderonmu (2019) reported that students who received longer durations of biology teaching showed a 25% increase in retention of key concepts compared to those in traditional class periods. This is similar with a study by Usman and Akinsola (2015) indicated that students taught Biology with extended teaching durations had higher retention scores. The mean retention score for the extended duration group was 78.6, compared to 66.4 for the traditional duration group. This finding suggests that extended teaching time positively influences students' long-term retention of Biology concepts. Okeke and Okoli (2018), discovered that the retention rate of biology knowledge among students in classes with extended teaching durations was 30% higher compared to those in traditional class periods.

The lower standard deviation in the experimental group (0.88) compared to the control group (1.58) indicates more uniform performance among students who experienced extended teaching durations. This consistency aligns with findings by Umar and Ibrahim (2021), which highlighted that prolonged instructional time reduces variability in student performance by ensuring all students have ample time to grasp the material.

The t-calculated value (3.74) exceeded the t-critical value (1.98) at the 0.05 significance level, demonstrating that extended teaching periods positively impact students' academic performance. Studies by Onuka and Olusola (2020) have similarly shown that extended teaching periods can significantly enhance students' academic performance and retention in secondary school settings. In the result of Okoye *et al.* (2020), the average test scores of students in biology increased by 20% after implementing extended teaching durations compared to traditional class periods.

Conclusion

Findings showing prolonged teaching durations has shown to improve retention and performance in Biology concepts among secondary school students in Northwest, Nigeria, pointing to the potential benefits of such a strategy. These findings are consistent with current literature that emphasizes the need of enough instructional time in secondary school to promote deep learning and understanding. Implementing extended teaching durations might therefore be a strategic intervention to improve educational achievements in public secondary schools, notably in Nigeria's North-West Zone.

Recommendations

1. Implement Extended Teaching Durations: Based on the results from the three schools in the North-West Geo-political zone of Nigeria and the observed improvement in retention and academic performance, it is recommended to implement extended teaching durations in schools. This strategy can enhance students' understanding and retention of complex subjects like Biology.
2. Monitor and Evaluate Progress: Continuous monitoring and evaluation of the impact of extended teaching durations are essential. Regular assessments can help track students' progress and identify areas that need improvement. Additionally, gathering feedback from both teachers and students can provide valuable insights for refining the implementation process and maximizing its benefits.

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Effect of Class-Period-Length... (Areo & Aliyu, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929413>

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Integration of Educational Mobile... (Sani, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929449>

Integration of Educational Mobile Applications in Facilitating Learner-Centered Instructional Strategies at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The integration of mobile applications into higher education has transformed learner-centered instructional methodologies by enabling personalized, interactive, and contextual learning environments. This study explores how mobile applications foster active learning, knowledge production, social interaction, and scaffolding, thereby boosting student engagement and accommodating diverse learning styles. Mobile applications support collaborative learning, offer immersive experiences through augmented reality, and provide real-world problem-solving exercises aligned with constructivist principles. The recommendations emphasize the strategic integration of comprehensive curricula and institutional support, the development of customizable and accessible learning platforms, collaboration with developers for localized and secure solutions, ongoing monitoring and evaluation, digital literacy enhancement, cooperation and peer learning, and the promotion of lifelong learning skills to ensure a successful learning experience in Nigerian tertiary education.

Keyword: Mobile Applications, Learner-Centered Approaches, Active Learning, Knowledge Construction, Social Interaction, Contextual Learning

Introduction

Higher education has seen a transformational shift in recent years due to technological integration, particularly the widespread use of mobile applications. These applications have emerged as formidable tools, revolutionizing the teaching and learning experience. The adoption of mobile applications to facilitate learner-centered teaching marks a significant paradigm shifts in higher education methodologies (Bakar, 2021; Tan, 2018). As institutions endeavor to address the diverse needs of 21st-century learners, mobile applications provide a versatile and accessible means to establish interactive and engaging learning environments.

Learning involves linking information sources to create a network. In the present day, individuals need to possess the capability to identify connections, discern patterns, and make sense of various fields, ideas, and concepts (Goldie, 2016). Given the changes in the current learning environment, it is crucial to reevaluate learning support. This recognition stems from the understanding that today's world is significantly distinct from the world in which our teaching and learning methods were initially developed (Neck & Greene, 2011). We are now in an era marked by swift transformations in transportation and communication infrastructures, altering the way and speed at which we conduct activities. Moreover, the volume of available information is growing exponentially, the very nature of knowledge is evolving, and the world is undergoing rapid changes due to the sometimes conflicting but often complementary processes of globalization and localism (Baker & Powell, 2024).

Education aims to shape students into active, competitive contributors to society by fostering cultural grounding, global proactivity, scientific thinking, professional skills, and a commitment to faith and justice. Recognizing the limits of classroom education, we focus on nurturing lifelong learners who are independent, analytical, reflective, and proactive. Our

Integration of Educational Mobile... (Sani, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929449>

goal is for students to take responsibility for their personal growth amid societal changes (Pendergast et al., 2005). Meeting these demands requires a new learning environment with essential resources and a participatory, critical, and creative teaching approach (Amhag, 2016).

Mobile Devices Used at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Mobile devices encompass a variety of portable computing tools and software applications that allow users to perform tasks without being confined to a specific location (Roth, 2024). This category includes smartphones, tablets, wearable devices, mobile operating systems, and mobile applications (Pereira & Rodrigues, 2013). These devices are noted for their portability, connectivity, and capability to access and process information on the move (Schrock, 2015). They offer ubiquitous connectivity and access to information via wireless communication networks and portable devices, emphasizing their core attributes of ubiquity, connectivity, and portability (Goldena, 2023). Mobile learning (M-learning) introduces flexibility to educational activities by removing time and place constraints. Mobile tools such as laptops, mobile phones, smartphones, PDAs, and MP3 players are integral to m-learning (Bostan et al., 2021). Due to their multi-functionality, mobile devices have become indispensable in modern education. They enhance the learning experience by offering flexibility, enabling real-time communication, and supporting collaborative and personalized learning environments. As higher education evolves, the integration of mobile devices is expected to play a crucial role in shaping future teaching and learning methodologies.

Educational Mobile Applications Used at the Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Mobile applications have become integral to daily life, significantly impacting education (Lee & Chan, 2007; Pang, 2024). At the tertiary level, these applications act as catalysts for learner-centered approaches, shifting the focus from traditional teacher-centric models to pedagogies that empower students as active participants in their learning journeys (Alam & Mohanty, 2023). Mobile applications in education foster collaborative learning environments and provide personalized learning pathways, enhancing student engagement, promoting critical thinking, and accommodating diverse learning styles (McQuiggan et al., 2015). In this context, educational technology plays a crucial role, with mobile learning tools offering significant advantages by aligning technology with content and pedagogy. Educators' effective integration of these tools is critical to enhancing teaching and learning outcomes (Bostan et al., 2021).

Educational mobile applications are designed to facilitate learning through interactive and engaging experiences. These apps serve various purposes, such as providing access to educational content, teaching resources, and tools for both formal and informal learning (Belle, 2024). They cover a wide range of topics and skills, from early childhood education to university-level courses, vocational training, and professional development (Noguera, 2024). Common features of educational apps include interactive learning activities, multimedia resources, progress tracking, assessments, collaboration tools, and access to e-books and other learning materials (Fitria, 2024). As essential tools in modern education, these applications enhance the learning experience, making it more dynamic, adaptable, and accessible (Ramli, 2024).

The adoption of educational mobile applications at the university level in Nigeria has progressively increased as smartphones and mobile internet penetration have increased (Muazu & Bishir, 2024). Moodle, Google Classroom, Zoom, Udemy, and Coursera are some of the most popular Learning Management Systems (LMS) for online courses, assignments, and evaluations (Sari & Putri, 2022). Institutions such as the University of Lagos (UNILAG) and Covenant University have developed their own applications for administrative tasks such as registration, getting course materials, and reviewing results. Mobile applications also enable material distribution via digital libraries, such as the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) app and test preparation services like Pass.NG. Furthermore, apps such as WhatsApp, Telegram, Slack, and Microsoft Teams promote communication and collaborative learning between students and lecturers, allowing for group discussions, project work, and academic collaboration. These tools have become essential in enhancing teaching, learning, and administrative efficiency in Nigerian tertiary education (Alimi, 2018; Ojugo & Eboka 2018; Ibrahim & Jibia, 2024).

Learner-Centered Instructional Strategies Used at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

A learner-centered approach is an educational philosophy that prioritizes the student's needs, abilities, interests, and learning styles, shifting the focus from traditional teacher-led instruction to a more student-driven experience (Dove & Schultz, 2018). Unlike traditional methods where the instructor is the primary source of knowledge and students are passive recipients, this approach emphasizes active participation, student engagement, autonomy, and the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills (El Hammoumi et al., 2021). The learner-centred approach improves academic achievement while also encouraging lifetime learning skills and holistic development by focussing on individual needs and active engagement (Hartman, 2020). Despite the challenges in implementation, its benefits make it a valuable strategy in modern education, promoting a more inclusive, engaging, and effective learning experience.

Integration of Educational Mobile... (Sani, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929449>

Learner-centered instructional strategies are increasingly regarded as essential for enhancing the quality of tertiary education, especially in Nigeria. Unlike traditional teacher-centered methods, this approach focuses on active student participation, critical thinking, and the application of knowledge in real-world contexts (Enemuoh, 2022). The adoption of a learner-centered approach in Nigerian tertiary institutions aligns with global educational reforms aimed at fostering autonomous learning and improving student outcomes (Eimuhi & Eimuhi, 2018).

The learner-centered approach includes various tactics that prioritise students' needs, interests, and active engagement. Problem-based learning (PBL) is a crucial technique in which students work together to solve complicated real-world problems, encouraging critical thinking and practical problem-solving abilities (Ibrahim, 2022). Another popular method is the Flipped Classroom, which involves students reviewing lecture materials at home and using classroom time for interactive activities and conversations, allowing them to study at their speed while increasing in-class engagement. Inquiry-based learning enables students to investigate and research ideas or problems, focussing on curiosity and active exploration (Onojah et al., 2020). Flipped classrooms have been proved in study to increase student involvement and academic accomplishment, making them a feasible option for large courses offered in Nigerian colleges.

Collaborative Learning is students working in groups to achieve common goals, which improves teamwork skills and peer learning. Differentiated Instruction tailors instructional methods and resources to accommodate different learning styles, talents, and interests, ensuring that all students can learn in ways that are appropriate for their particular requirements (Ismail & Al Allaq, 2019; Ramasamy, 2024). Self-Directed Learning encourages students to take responsibility for their own learning by fostering goal setting, time management, and independent resource seeking. Experiential Learning offers practical, hands-on experiences, such as internships and simulations, to promote reflective learning and real-world skill development (Pacheco-Velazquez et al., 2024).

Formative assessment entails continuing evaluations that provide feedback and guide education, assisting in identifying learning gaps and adjusting teaching tactics (Angelo & Zakrajsek, 2024). Allowing Student Choice and Autonomy allows students some influence over their learning, which boosts motivation and engagement by allowing them to select topics, projects, or assessments (Hurdle et al., 2024). Finally, scaffolding provides temporary support structures to help students complete tasks, progressively diminishing aid as they gain competency, resulting in increased confidence and independence in their learning. Together, these tactics produce a learning environment that is more sensitive to students' needs while also encouraging active, successful, and personalized learning experiences (Lechón Vásquez, 2024).

Constructivist Learning Theory and Integration of Mobile Applications at the Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Constructivist Learning Theory is an educational philosophy based on the idea that learners construct their understanding and knowledge of the world through experiences and reflecting on those experiences (Bada & Olusegun, 2015). It is rooted in the work of several key theorists, including Jean Piaget, Lev Vygotsky, and Jerome Bruner. This theory emphasizes active, student-centered learning where students build their knowledge rather than passively receiving information from the teacher (Melissa & Assia, 2022).

Integration of Key Principles of Learner-Centered Instructional Strategies and Constructivist Approaches Using Mobile Educational Applications

Student Autonomy and Constructing Knowledge: Mobile applications can significantly enhance student autonomy and knowledge construction in Nigerian tertiary institutions. These applications empower students to take control of their learning by allowing them to select topics of interest, set learning goals, and choose how to engage with the content. Through features like customizable learning paths and reflective journals, students can build on prior knowledge and actively construct new understanding (Schumacher & Czerwinski, 2014; Ismail et al., 2018). This aligns with constructivist principles, enabling learners to adjust their mental models as they interact with new information (Pardjono, 2016).

Active and Engaged Learning: Mobile applications are pivotal in fostering active and engaged learning, which is at the core of both learner-centered and constructivist approaches. In Nigerian tertiary education, apps that offer simulations, interactive activities, and problem-based learning scenarios allow students to actively apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts (Lee, 2022; Vanhorn et al., 2019). Students are more likely to remain interested and remember learning when they participate in discussions, collaborative projects, and hands-on activities made possible by mobile apps (Bonk & Cunningham, 2012).

Personalized and Contextual Learning: The ability of mobile applications to provide personalized and contextual learning experiences is crucial for addressing the diverse needs of students in Nigeria. These apps can tailor content delivery to individual learning styles, pace, and interests, making learning more relevant and effective (Bonk & Cunningham, 2012). Furthermore, mobile apps can deliver contextual learning opportunities by integrating academic knowledge with real-world

Integration of Educational Mobile... (Sani, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929449>

applications. Through case studies, field activities, and contextual assignments presented via apps, students can engage with authentic tasks that make learning more meaningful and applicable to their future careers (Hwang et al., 2023).

Collaboration and Social Interaction: Mobile applications enhance collaboration and social interaction, essential elements of learner-centered and constructivist education. In the Nigerian context, where large class sizes can limit direct interaction, apps can provide platforms for group work, peer reviews, and collaborative problem-solving activities (Jamrus & Razali, 2019). Features such as discussion forums and group projects within mobile apps promote social learning by enabling students to exchange ideas, discuss content, and work together to refine their understanding (Beal & Hontvedt, 2023).

Holistic Development and Scaffolding: Mobile applications can support the holistic development of students by integrating features that promote not just academic skills but also emotional, social, and ethical growth. For instance, apps that include mindfulness exercises, ethical dilemmas, and social skill-building activities contribute to the overall development of the learner (Bonk & Cunningham, 2012). Additionally, these apps can offer scaffolding by providing step-by-step guidance, hints, and adaptive learning pathways that adjust to the learner's proficiency level (Hung et al., 2013; Ikawati, 2020). This ensures that students receive the necessary support as they progress towards greater independence.

Summary

The shift towards integrating mobile applications in Nigerian tertiary institutions has transformed traditional teaching models into learner-centered approaches. Mobile applications provide dynamic platforms for active and engaged learning, allowing students to construct knowledge, collaborate, and access personalized learning pathways. These applications are consistent with constructivist learning theory because they include characteristics like simulations, interactive activities, and real-world problem-solving scenarios. Moreover, mobile applications provide scaffolding support and ensure that students remain engaged, offering diverse methods to cater to different learning styles. This study emphasizes the need for Nigerian institutions to strategically incorporate mobile technologies into their curriculum, support faculty in digital pedagogies, and continuously evaluate the impact on student outcomes to create an effective and inclusive learning environment.

Conclusion

The integration of mobile applications in tertiary education in Nigeria has the potential to significantly enhance the effectiveness of learner-centered instructional strategies. These technologies provide engaging and flexible learning experiences that foster active participation, critical thinking, and social collaboration. Mobile applications connect with constructivist ideas, allowing students to construct knowledge and participate in contextual learning, so improving their overall educational experience. To fully harness these benefits, institutions must prioritize strategic integration of mobile technologies, faculty development, and regular evaluation of their impact on learning outcomes. The shift to mobile-based learning reflects a broader transformation in education, preparing students to thrive in an increasingly digital and globalized world.

Recommendations

1. **Comprehensive Curriculum Integration and Institutional Support:** Institutions should establish clear standards for integrating mobile applications into the curriculum, ensuring alignment with learning objectives, course materials, and assessment methods. Additionally, institutional leadership should allocate resources such as funding, technical support, and digital infrastructure to facilitate the integration of mobile learning into instructional practices.
2. **Customizable and Accessible Learning Platforms:** Mobile applications should offer flexible, customizable learning paths that cater to various learning styles and paces, thereby enhancing student engagement. These platforms must also be accessible to all students, including those with disabilities, through features like text-to-speech and customizable interfaces. Ensuring affordability is crucial to providing equal access for all students.
3. **Collaboration with Developers for Localized and Secure Solutions:** Universities should collaborate with developers to create mobile applications tailored to the specific needs of Nigerian students. These partnerships can ensure the development of localized content and relevant resources while prioritizing data privacy and security to protect students' personal and academic information.
4. **Ongoing Monitoring, Evaluation, and Digital Literacy Development:** Institutions should implement procedures for the continuous evaluation of mobile applications, including surveys, focus groups, and analytics, to assess their impact on learning outcomes. Simultaneously, digital literacy programs should be expanded for both students and faculty to ensure effective use of these tools.
5. **Cooperation and Peer Learning Enhancement:** Mobile applications should feature tools that promote peer learning and collaboration, such as discussion boards, group projects, and peer assessments. These collaborative elements help students develop real-world teamwork skills and enhance their overall learning experience.

Integration of Educational Mobile... (Sani, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929449>

6. **Lifelong Learning Skills:** Mobile applications should be designed to foster critical thinking, self-directed learning, and problem-solving skills. These capabilities are essential for students' success in an evolving educational and professional landscape.

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Qualitative Study on Effective Pedagogy for Sustainable Primary Level of Education in Nigeria: Review on Post Covid-19 Era

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Abstract

This paper is qualitative in nature which analysed the impact of an infectious disease known as CORONA VIRUS (COVID-19) on primary education activities in Nigeria, and discussed on the importance of employing proper pedagogy as a measure to argument the challenges posed as a result of the corona virus. Secondary data was used in this research as a source of information to discuss the topic. The paper therefore discussed on the emergence of COVID-19, its impact on education activities, as well as pedagogical measures to be taken in case of encountering such calamities to maintain sustainable education. The research finds out among others that education activities were halted, as schools were closed for a long period of time as part of control measure to curve the spread and prevent carriage to other vulnerable individuals. The paper concluded that measures taken have thwarted education sector which called for change from face-to-face education delivery to the use of technological pedagogy. It recommended among others that e-learning materials should be made available to take care of such scenarios in future.

Keywords: Primary Education; Pedagogy; Post-Covid

Introduction

Education is of no doubt a tool for change. Change which affects the entire human lives; being it morally; physically; mentally; emotionally and spiritually. There is a believed that to deprive a nation from progress is as simple as to deny that nation education to its citizens. Thus, lack of education has diverse and far reaching consequences on the entire life of an individual and community in general (Allison Academy, 2021).

Education is classified as one of the fundamental human rights, but, many countries are unable to provide it to its citizens due to one reason or another, especially a qualitative education for that matter. Accordingly, UNESCO Institute of Statistics (UIS), 2018 reported in its annual data in 2018 that 59 million children of primary school age were out of school. Nigeria as one of the signatories to the United Nations' Human Right Charter is bound to Article 26, sub-sections (1) and (2) which clearly stated that every individual is entitle to, at the basic stage, free and compulsory education, and should be available and equally accessible to all, which would be directed to the full development of human personality and strengthen of respect for human rights and fundamental freedom, promote understanding, tolerance and friendliness among all (Onyebu & Okanume-Ohan, 2014).

Dolezalova in Janis (2014) opined that education has accompanied humanity throughout its historical evolution since the ancient times and is part of everyone's entire life. Education is a versatile phenomenon, depending on the changes of people's conditions of life. When human intellectual abilities reached a certain degree during the initial stage of human development, the behaviour of people ceased to be governed just by instincts, and deliberate conduct and actions became more important. It was at this moment when people broke free from the animal kingdom; this is proven by education, meaning the care for offspring, as a targeted and anticipative activity.

For many years since the beginning of the history of education, the principles of how children should be brought up were passed from parents onto their children. Scholars were contemplating about education, its targets and ideals, but the ideas were not tested in practice. In the middle Ages, education was strongly influenced by religious philosophy, by Christianity. Enlightenment brought new ideas about humans and the creation of the first theoretical systems focusing on educational systems. The thinking, however, still predominantly dealt with specific procedures. By the 19th century, sufficient know-how about education was collected, allowing scholars to draw generalizations, use scientific terminology and form an independent discipline. The scientific discipline focusing on education and humans in educational situations was called pedagogy (Dolezalova in Janis, 2014)

Qualitative Study on Effective... (Abubakar, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929483>

Each individual has his/her idea about education, upbringing and instruction, based primarily on the experience with education within family and at school. Pedagogy as a science is different, as it describes the phenomenon on the basis of scientific findings. It is based on the results of the verification of theories, hypotheses and empirical findings.

Deterioration of facilities, inadequate funding, unqualified teaching personnel, lack of teaching aids, obsolete libraries/laboratory equipments and poor and polluted learning environment are among other factors responsible for decline in standard of education. While, the primary level of education as considered the foundational level needs to be funded, controlled and managed very well, as providing adequate education to citizens impacted socioeconomics growth and development (Samphina Academy, 2017).

UNESCO as a single United Nations agency mandated to cover all aspects of education across the globe opined that education transforms lives; thus, the mission of the Organisation is to “build peace, eradicate poverty and drive sustainable development” (UNESCO, 2023).

Suddenly, in March 2020 education activities were abruptly disrupted due to the declaration of COVID 19 as a global pandemic. Thus, schools and all other educational activities were stopped in order to curb further spread of COVID-19 pandemic in almost all countries.

Nowadays, education is much concern with personalization, participation and production as per instruction delivery is concerned. In other words, teaching/learning delivery involves learning through authentic real world contexts, conducting comprehensive project activities as well as solving immediate problems (Ali, Mondal & Das, 2018).

In precise, one can conclude that people cannot do without education, which is why they apply it in their lives. Education has been part of the entire human history and one’s entire life. Its targeted and well-considered nature which focuses on the development of individuals differentiates education from other activities and impacts. Education is primarily vital and indispensable in childhood. It focuses on shaping the relationships toward all important conditions in life – toward oneself, other people and the nature around. Objectives, content and means of education change throughout the development of mankind.

Emergence of Corona Virus (COVID-19) in Nigeria

Tang, (2022) reported that corona virus disease 2019, well known as COVID-19, caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome corona virus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), was first reported in Wuhan China on December 8, 2019. Since then, it has spread quickly to different parts of the world. He further narrated that as of July 15, 2021, 08:11 GMT, 189,190,520 people were infected by COVID-19 globally and 4,074,788 deaths were reported (Our World in Data, 2021 in Tang, 2022). Lockdown has been initiated at the onset of COVID-19 and has been adaptively implemented in different countries depending on the number of COVID-19 cases. United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF), 2023 reported that on March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization declared COVID-19 a global pandemic, resulting in disruptions to education at an unprecedented scale.

Ibrahim and Uba (2022) reported that on 27 February 2020, in Lagos State, the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Health echoed the first verified case of COVID-19. The multi-sector corona virus preparedness team, led by the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control [NCDC], has immediately activated its National Emergency Operations Centre [NEOC]. Ibrahim and Uba (2022) further corroborated that the Federal Government of Nigeria issued a number of directives combat sanctions and structural changes across the country to curtail further spread of COVID-19. These directives range from the closure of international airports to the closure of all schools across the country and the lockdown declared in several key states – Lagos, Abuja, Kano and Ogun - for several weeks at the beginning.

In comply to the directives given by the Federal Government, Ejeh et al., (2020); Obiakor, Adeniran, (2020) in Ibrahim and Uba, (2022) stated that the Federal Ministry of Education issued a circular on 19 March 2020, authorizing the closure of all schools for one month from Monday 23 March 2020, to prevent the spread of COVID-19, which affects nearly 46 million students and children across the country, thus, academic activities cannot continue because of the lockdown, as, the COVID-19 epidemic had led to a partial or complete “lockdown” in many countries.

Impact of COVID-19 on Primary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Fana et al., (2020); Tang, (2021a) in Tang, (2022) stated that the spread of COVID-19 has multiple impacts on the socioeconomic systems. Lock- down has resulted in the temporary and selective closure of businesses and services which prompts employers to adopt different employment patterns, for instance, by partially or entirely shifting from full-time employment to part-time and casual employment in relation to operational demands during various stages of COVID-19 lockdown.

Fana et al., (2020) in Tang (2022) maintained that the uncertainties brought by COVID-19 lockdown on businesses has an impact on the workforce, causing a significant reduction in the demand for work- force in sectors most affected by the

Qualitative Study on Effective... (Abubakar, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929483>

lockdown, particularly education, hospital and aviation. In addition, self-isolation and travel restriction as a result of COVID-19 lockdown have catalyzed the deployment of online operational mode in many sectors such as education, retails, food and beverages as well as banking (Fairlie & Fossen, 2021; & Tang, 2020a in Tang, 2022).

The education sector has been hard-hit by COVID-19 since the very beginning. While different countries have different policies on the operation of education centers, many education centers have been closed since the onset of COVID-19 (Tang, 2021b in Tang, 2022).

In Nigeria during the shutdown, Dreesen et al., (2020) and UNESCO, (2020) in Ibrahim and Uba, (2022) indicated that learning and access to essential school services had been disrupted, as a record number of students and pupils were prevented from school due to lockdowns, which affected approximately 46 million students and pupils nationwide, including more than 91 % of primary and secondary school students.

The impacts of school closures were wide-ranging, affecting not only children's schooling and learning, but also their health and nutrition, mental wellbeing, and protection against child labour, gender-based violence and more. As a result, Ifijeh & Yusuf, (2020); Ho et al., (2021); and Zawacki-Richter, (2021) in Ibrahim and Uba (2022) have shown the importance of using electronic media in distance learning programmes. Though, they indicated that the use of electronic media in distance education programmes is not only focused on digital technologies, but also includes physical administration.

Ibrahim and Uba (2022) reported that as a result of the outbreak, Nigerian education was disrupted; students' access to schools across the country was restricted. Therefore, the epidemic COVID-19 poses significant problems for the stakeholders: government; students and parents as it exposes and potentially exacerbates existing deficiencies in the education system (Obiakor & Adeniran, 2020 in Ibrahim & Uba, 2022). Thus, a crucial question arises as the country grapples with these problems, as is the Nigerian education system designed to adapt quickly to changing circumstances? Given the current global circumstances, the country's ability to ensure continuous learning will depend primarily on its ability to quickly harness existing technologies, create appropriate infrastructure and mobilize partners to develop alternative education programmes (Owolabi et al., 2013, in Ibrahim & Uba, 2022).

The COVID-19 pandemic had affected the education system, particularly basic education, and especially for pupils, students and parents of public schools. Subsequently, pupils, trainees and students can use effective resources such as information and communication technology (ICT) to explore things that interest them and actively learn during the lockdown and beyond.

Unfortunately, the Nigerian education system is unable to adapt to the challenges of COVID-19 and the country struggled in the area of information and communication technology especially at public primary level of education for the foreseeable future. However, compared to private schools, public school students face a disproportionate socio-economic burden. While several private schools have started distance education programmes and are taking advantage of the many Media Education (Mediaobrazovanie, 2022 in Ibrahim & Uba, 2022)

Effective Pedagogy for Sustainable Primary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Kapur (2020) opined that pedagogy is concerned with the teaching processes. Westbrook et al. (2013) observed that pedagogy itself is a contested term, but involves activities that evoke changes in the learner: Watkins and Mortimore (1999, p.3) in Westbrook et al. (2013) define pedagogy as 'any conscious activity by one person designed to enhance learning in another'. According to Bernstein (2000, p.78) also in Westbrook et al. (2013), pedagogy 'is a sustained process whereby somebody(s) acquires new forms or develops existing forms of conduct, knowledge, practice and criteria from somebody(s) or something deemed to be an appropriate provider and evaluator'.

It is the study of how knowledge and competencies are imparted in the educational framework. Learning cannot take place in seclusion, it is indispensable for the individuals to interact with each other and form cordial terms and relationships. By the 19th century, sufficient know-how about education was collected, allowing scholars to draw generalizations, use scientific terminology and form an independent discipline. The scientific discipline focusing on education and humans in educational situations was called pedagogy. (Dolezalova, Habl & Janis, 2014).

Pedagogy is an encompassing term concerned with what a teacher does to influence learning in others. As the importance of high quality education for children has become more clearly understood, so has the teacher/educator's role in the provision of these services. This demands a clear understanding of the meaning of pedagogy and how it plays out in individual educators and services (Ali, Mondal & Das, 2018).

According to Dolezalova, Habl & Janis, 2014, pedagogy is an independent social anthroposophic science (science about humans) that represents an organized system of findings about educational processes and its results, conditions and factors which determine the education, as well as the main agents of the process. Pedagogy studies education in its versatility

Qualitative Study on Effective... (Abubakar, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929483>

and diversity, and it describes, explains, compares, evaluates and generalizes the findings about pedagogical phenomena. It reveals and formulates the pedagogical principles and rules which reflect the relationships and connections in educational practice.

Based on these facts, pedagogy proposes constructs and concepts (theories, models, plans) which are subsequently verified in practice. The findings are thus specified and a pedagogical theory is developed, together with other fields within interdisciplinary character. In other words, pedagogy is a normative science (formulating norms, rules, principles and guidelines for education and upbringing) and a descriptive science. It is also an explorative science (exploring and studying new educational phenomena), as well as an explanatory science (identifying and explaining processes, results and factors of education), which is an essential activity for pedagogy. And last but not least, it is a projecting science (proposing new and more effective processes, resources or entire programmes). Sometimes, the aforementioned attributes are all described as functions of pedagogy (Dolezalova, Habl & Janis, 2014).

Kapur (2020) believed that in education affairs instructors regard pedagogy as an essential part of the teaching-learning methods and instructional strategies, therefore, having a well-thought out pedagogy can bring about improvements in the quality of life of teaching/learning process. He further argued that when students are admitted in schools, certain concepts will be new to them, thus, they will need help in understanding these concepts, and guide to adopt to the new environment. Being aware in terms of the methods one can teach and facilitate student learning can contribute effectively in acquiring an understanding in terms of importance of pedagogy.

Pedagogy is regarded as an academic discipline, henceforth, educators need to clearly understand the needs and requirements of the students, students on the other hand too need to obey their instructors and follow the rules and instructions. Consequently, when these factors are put into practice in an effectual manner, the importance of pedagogy is recognized.

Pedagogy is the act of teaching, where at the beginning instructors made use of traditional methods in imparting knowledge and understanding to the students in terms of lesson plans and academic concepts. But with the advent of technologies, teachers are making use of technologies and other modern and innovative methods in facilitating learning. Apart from utilization of technologies, the instructors are making use of modern, scientific and innovative methods in facilitating learning. The examples of these methods are charts, graphs, images, pictures, diagrams, articles, models, and so forth.

Entz, 2006 in Kapur (2020) suggested that there are various factors that are needed to be taken into consideration in the implementation of proper pedagogical methods in an efficacious manner. These are, needs and requirements of the students, their age groups and grade levels, academic subjects and lesson plans and overall system of education. The students should take pleasure and develop motivation among themselves in facilitating learning. Therefore, it is well-understood, when the utilization of these methods prove to be advantageous and meaningful to the students and facilitate the achievement of academic goals, the individuals are able to understand the importance of pedagogy.

When the pedagogical methods are put into operation in teaching and learning processes, they are not merely referred to imparting knowledge and understanding to the students in terms of lesson plans and academic concepts, but they take into account other factors as well. One of the important factors that is taken into account is, Student-Centred Teaching and Learning (SCL) approach. This approach is reflective in their theory, practice, policy implementation in the teaching and learning processes, and results in positive impacts in terms of the learners. The meaning of this approach is, the teaching and the learning methods that are put into practice should have the main aim of facilitating student learning and up-grading the overall system of education. The teaching and learning are regarded as complicated processes, and these are indispensable ways of promoting student learning and leading to effective growth and development of the system of education (Entz, 2006 in Kapur, 2020). Therefore, it is comprehensively understood that the importance of pedagogy is recognized, when it plays an important part in facilitating student learning and enriching the overall system of education.

Primary School Level of Education for Sustainable Development in Nigeria

Education is the conscious transmission of the knowledge, values and skills acquired by society from one generation to the next through institutions. Consequently, an adequate education system is necessary for the advancement of individuals in society and the economy. The impact of repeated lockdown of schools and academic programmes on student learning can have detrimental consequences for students, parents and the nation. (Ibrahim & Uba, 2022).

Otamiri (2022) described education as to what can be used by man to solve his problems to improve his life and make it comfortable. He further said it is one of the several ways that man employs to bring change into his all-round development. Education demands efforts and discipline. It is also a formidable tool for man's survival. Ayu (1991) conceived education as what brings about the moral development and spiritual upliftment of the human personality and of the community as a whole.

Qualitative Study on Effective... (Abubakar, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929483>

He stressed further that education makes mankind more creative and enables him to live a more fulfilling life through interaction.

Development on the other hand as described by Pettinger, (2018) in Otamiri (2022) is concerned with how people in a country or economic system are actually affected. It looks at their actual living standards and the freedom they have to enjoy a good standard of living (Pettinger, 2018 in Otamiri, 2022). Otamiri (2021) further stated that to define national development, there should be focus on the extent to which the institutions of a given society enhance the capacity of the people, as individuals and as a social collective, to ensure the conditions for the persistence of social life. Thus, a developed economy is one that has the basic structure, infrastructure and values that guarantee human life and the full attainment of human aspirations. This implies that, for there to be development in the nation, there should be a concerted effort to establish institutional frameworks that would guarantee individual and social creativity, fulfilment, and provision of social amenities, education, health services, security, shelter, and food for human healthy existence and fulfilment. It also implies that development necessitates an establishment of social framework for institutionalization of social values for social cooperation. Thus, a society devoid of these ideal socio- economic characteristics cannot be described as a developed society; they are either developing or under-developed.

Development refers to an improvement in the quality of life and living standards, e.g. measures of literacy, life-expectancy and health care, it looks at a wider range of statistics than just GDP per capita. Economic development involves the improvement of human capital, literacy ratio, important infrastructure, health and safety, and other areas that aim at increasing the general welfare of the citizens (Chukwuka & Ananaba, 2016 in Otamiri, 2022). Development can also be seen as an increase in living conditions, improvement of the self-esteem needs and a free and just society (Todaro, 2016). He suggests that the most accurate method of measuring economic development is Human Development index which takes into account the literacy rate which in turn has outright impact on productivity and could lead to economic growth (Todaro, 2016). From the above citations, development refers to a level of societal living characterized by major changes in various aspects of human and social life such as economic, political, institutional, cultural, etc.

A developing economy on the other hand as prescribed by Otamiri (2022) is one where people have a lower standard of living and less developed industries than other countries. A developing economy is a nation where the average income is much lower than in industrial nations, where the economy relies on a few export crops, and where farming is conducted by primitive methods (Otamiri, 2021). Unfortunately, Nigeria falls within this pitiable economic reality of a developing economy. Nigeria as a country is blessed with abundance of human and natural resources (such as crude oil, tin, zinc, cocoa, groundnut, etc.) which nature has endowed on her. The country's climate conditions favour wide variety of agricultural and economic resource activities. Additionally, Nigeria is the most populous country in the continent of Africa, with abundant economic resources. Her people are still suffering in abject poverty and impoverishment, poor and ineffective infrastructural facilities, low and primitive service delivery, industrial development still below average, and still remains a developing economy.

Sustainable development can be seen as a development that meets our present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (United Nations, 2009 in Otamiri & Odu, 2022). Three elements were further identified which should work together to ensure sustainable development. These include: economic development; social development and environmental protection.

Ayeni in Otamiri and Odu (2022) argues that these three components must be conceptualized together, planned together and implemented together to achieve the desired results. Development can only make sense to the people when they are involved in the process of decision making through a Bottom-top approach.

Moreover, sustainable development as conceptualized by Otamiri and Odu (2022) is the extent to which a country has developed may be assessed by considering a range of narrow and broad indicators, including per capita income, life expectancy, education, and the extent of poverty alleviation. A sustainable development is that development that is stable, enduring, and consistent. It is a development that lasts and does not crumble in the face of formidable problems. Sustainable development is a development that does not roll back or recede, even in the face of threatening reversal waves (Omotola, 2006 in Otamiri & Odu, 2022).

Conclusion

The paper discusses on the emergence of Covid-19 pandemic which brought historic education disruptions which include prolonged schools closure around the globe. It pointed out how the pandemic upset the education system particularly at primary level of education in Nigeria as one of the developing nations struggled with economic dwindling, which left her with no option than to use face-face method of teaching prior to COVID-19 pandemic. The paper also identified some

Qualitative Study on Effective... (Abubakar, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929483>

challenges faced by the education sector such as inadequate plans to provide distance education, especially for public primary schools, due to lack of funds and inadequate planning. It further discusses on how utilizing proper pedagogies could aid and facilitate teaching/learning activities in case of future reoccurrence.

Recommendations

The paper recommended the following:

1. Government should provide primary schools with adequate number of instructional gadgets to cater for e-learning needs in case of reoccurrence of same scenario as corona virus period
2. Teachers should be well trained in the field of information and technology so as to be equipped and well prepared to handle any challenged posed by unforeseen situation
3. Learners should be trained on how to acquire knowledge through the use of audio materials (such as radio), audio-visual (such as television) and so on.
4. Adequate infrastructure should be provided so that distance could be observed appropriately when the need arise.
5. Adequate provisions need to be made to face such challenges through the use of technology, as well as support of appropriate education methodologies/pedagogies.

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Assessment of Basic Reading Abilities and Learning-Gap among Early Public Primary School Pupils in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State

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Abstract

This study investigates basic reading abilities and learning gap among early public primary school pupils in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. The study population includes head teachers, classroom teachers, parents, and early primary pupils from 36 public primary schools. Data collection involved questionnaires, standardized reading assessments, and Woodcock Johnson Tests. Mean and independent samples t-tests were used to answer the raised research question and research hypotheses. Findings reveal that pupils exhibit below-average reading proficiency, necessitating targeted interventions. Factors influencing reading skills include parental involvement, access to resources, teacher strategies, and community reading culture. Significant differences in reading abilities exist between primary grades and urban versus rural schools. While gender disparities are not significant, addressing educational inequalities remains crucial for fostering literacy development and ensuring equitable opportunities. Recommendations include implementing literacy interventions, conducting further research, prioritizing early interventions, creating inclusive learning environments, and allocating resources to rural schools.

Keyword: Basic reading abilities, Learning gap, Early primary pupils, Government schools, Ilorin Metropolis.

Introduction

In recent years, there has been an increasing recognition of the critical role that early literacy skills play in shaping the educational trajectory and future success of individuals. The primary objective of education at the foundational level, as articulated in the Nigerian Policy on Education, is to inculcate “permanent literacy and ability to communicate effectively” (Federal Ministry of Education, 2013, p. 7). As foundational building blocks for academic achievement, basic reading abilities acquired during the early years of schooling lay the groundwork for continued learning and cognitive development.

However, reading is a fundamental skill that forms the bedrock of learning, particularly in basic education. It is a critical determinant of a student's success or failure, as it influences performance across all subjects. Yet, the ability to read has proven to be a significant challenge for learners worldwide, including Nigeria. Hamka (2005) states that reading is a process of transmitting of information where the author is regarded as the informant and the reader, on the other hand, is the receiver. During the reading process, the reader interacts with the author directly. Reading is defined according to Kilfoil and Van Der Walt (2007) as the ability to decode words, both prints, and meaning.

For beginning readers in nursery and primary schools to meet the reading demands of their social environment, teachers must develop in them reading readiness concepts and skills such as oral language foundation, print awareness, letter recognition skills, phono-phonemic awareness skills, sight word recognition skills as well as comprehension skills. These concepts and skills serve as a gradual development from non-reading to beginning reading (Oyetunde & Mmuodumogu, 1999; Davis, 2000; Andzayi&Ikwen, 2014). One of the skills that children need to master before they can read books is the possession of a broad, general appreciation of the nature of print (Rosenberg, 2006). Children need to be exposed to forms of print in everyday life, including conventions associated with book reading.

In other words, the persistent learning gap in education, characterized by disparities in academic achievement among students, continues to be a pressing concern worldwide. Central to understanding and addressing this gap is recognizing the

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critical role of basic reading skills in shaping educational outcomes. As highlighted by Strickland (2010) cited by (Oyetunde, Ojo, Korb, & Babudoh, 2018), proficiency in reading not only underpins academic success but also serves as a gateway to broader intellectual development and societal participation. Furthermore, Chris-Okafor (2014) cited by (Oyetunde, et al., 2018) underscores the importance of strong reading skills for success across all academic subjects.

The significance of basic reading skills in narrowing the learning gap cannot be overstated. Research has consistently shown that students who possess strong reading abilities are better equipped to comprehend instructional materials, engage critically with content, and ultimately achieve academic success. According to the National Reading Panel (2000), proficient readers demonstrate the ability to decode text accurately, comprehend its meaning, and make connections with prior knowledge. This ability enables them to access and internalize academic content across diverse subject areas.

On the other hand, students who struggle with reading often face significant obstacles in their educational journey. Stanovich (2017) coined the term "Matthew effects in reading" to describe how initial differences in reading proficiency can lead to widening disparities in learning outcomes over time. Difficulties in decoding text and comprehending written material can impede students' ability to access academic content, leading to frustration, disengagement, and a deepening of the learning gap.

To this end, reading is an essential skill that serves as the foundation for all learning. Without strong reading abilities, learners may struggle to acquire new knowledge, which can hinder their overall academic progress (Bartilol, 2017). Consequently, this deficiency can negatively impact performance in other subjects, leading to higher dropout rates, lower academic achievement, and reduced chances of progressing to higher levels of education. These outcomes can have a detrimental effect on the economy.

On this note, Atoni (2018) conducted a study revealing that Grade 1 learners in Uasin Gishu exhibited low reading abilities. The research also highlighted that students from urban schools outperformed their rural counterparts in reading. Wong and Abdul Aziz (2019) emphasize the necessity of identifying reading skill deficiencies among public primary school students as a crucial first step in designing targeted interventions. This approach aims to address the literacy gap effectively. Building on this foundation, the present study explores the relationship between basic reading skills and the learning gap among early primary pupils in government schools within Ilorin Metropolis.

The learning gap in education persists as a significant challenge, particularly among early primary pupils in government schools located in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. Despite efforts to enhance educational outcomes, disparities in academic achievement persist, with basic reading skills playing a crucial role in shaping these discrepancies. In view of this, researchers like Strickland (2010), Chris-Okafor (2014) and National Reading Panel (2000) acknowledged the importance of basic reading skills, there remains a gap in understanding how these skills specifically contribute to learning discrepancies among early primary pupils in government schools in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State.

It is against this background that this study to address this gap by investigating the relationship between basic reading skills and learning discrepancies among early primary pupils in government schools located in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. By delving deeper into this relationship, the study aims to uncover the factors influencing the acquisition and development of basic reading skills among early primary pupils.

Objectives of the study

The study aimed at assessing the basic reading abilities and learning gap among early public primary school pupils in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. Specifically, the study has the following objectives.

1. To assess the current levels of basic reading abilities and learning gap among early primary pupils in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis.
2. To identify the factors influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in the Ilorin Metropolis.
3. To ascertain the significant difference between basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to class level.
4. To ascertain the significant difference between basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to gender.
5. To ascertain the significant difference between basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to school location.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the current level of basic reading abilities and learning gap among early primary pupils (grades 1-3) in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis?

Assessment of Basic Reading... (Ahmed, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929483>

2. What are the factors influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis?

Research Hypotheses

Three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance ($P < .05$).

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to class level among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to gender among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to school location among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study was descriptive survey research design. The study population comprised head teachers, classroom teachers, parents of early primary pupils (class 1-3), and early primary school pupils. According to the Planning, Research and Statistics Department SUBEB (2024), there are 1,578 public primary schools in Kwara State, Nigeria. However, the target population for this study consisted all the 211 Public Primary Schools in Ilorin Metropolis, the sample for the study comprised 385 respondents (www.calculator.net/sample-size-calculator), consisting of 72 head teachers, 72 classroom teachers, 72 parents of early primary pupils (class 1-3), and 169 early primary school pupils (class 1-3). A multistage sampling procedure involving various sampling methods was adopted to select the sample for the study. The researcher selected 12 public primary schools from each stratum (from each Local Government in Ilorin Metropolis) using stratified random sampling technique, for a total of 36 public primary schools in Ilorin Metropolis. From each school selected, 36 head teachers and 36 classroom teachers were selected using purposive sampling technique based on their qualifications as experts in primary education, while 2 parents were selected using accidental sampling technique. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting 169 early primary school pupils (class 1-3).

However, three research instruments were used to collect data for this study. The first instrument was questionnaire designed by the researcher, the second instrument was Standardized Reading Assessments (SRA) covered various aspects of reading, including decoding skills, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension, while the third instrument was Woodcock Johnson Test (WJT) for measuring learning gap. The instruments were given to the experts in primary education to establish the content validity while experts in test development were consulted for construct validity. The observations and suggestions made by experts were used for the final preparation of the instruments. In computing the reliability of this research instruments, split-half method was employed to test internal consistency of the instruments, the instruments were administered to 40 stakeholders comprising 10 head teachers, 10 classroom teachers, 10 parents and pupils (class 1-3). Their responses to the items on these instruments were used to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument which yielded a reliability of 0.78, 0.81 and 0.92 respectively. Descriptive and inferential analyses were employed to analyze the data collected for this study. Specifically, mean and independent samples t-tests were used to answer the raised research question and research hypotheses

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the current level of basic reading abilities and learning gap among early primary pupils (grades 1-3) in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis?

Assessment of Basic Reading... (Ahmed, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929483>

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of current level of basic reading abilities and learning gap among early primary pupils (grades 1-3) in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=216	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Pupil's current level of basic reading abilities (e.g., decoding skills, fluency, and comprehension) on a scale of 1 to 5 is above average.		2.06	0.74	Disagree
2.	Pupil's current level of basic reading abilities (e.g., decoding skills, fluency, and comprehension) on a scale of 1 to 5 is below average.		2.71	0.58	Agree
3.	Pupils often encounter challenges understanding what they read during classroom activities.		2.68	0.71	Agree
4.	Reading materials (e.g., books, textbooks) are available in the school library or classroom.		2.15	0.80	Disagree
5.	To a great extent pupils' home environment supports their development of reading skills.		2.28	0.86	Disagree
6.	To a great extent the pupils' socio-economic background influences their reading proficiency.		2.11	0.91	Disagree
7.	I believe the school is addressing the learning gap in basic reading abilities among early primary pupils.		2.27	0.64	Disagree
8.	Pupils often receive individualized support or intervention for improving their reading skills.		2.10	0.76	Disagree
9.	To a great extent pupil engagement in reading-related activities outside of school hours.		2.21	0.77	Disagree
10.	I am confident that pupils' basic reading abilities will improve over time with appropriate interventions and support.		2.70	0.61	Agree
	Grand Mean		2.33	0.74	Below Average

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average

Table 1 illustrates the current level of basic reading abilities and learning gap among early primary pupils (grades 1-3) in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis. Scores across all categories of primary teachers and parents fall below the established cut-off mean of 2.50. Accordingly, the grand mean of 2.33 concisely indicates that pupils in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis display a lower-than-average level of basic reading abilities compared to expected proficiency levels.

Research Question 2: What are the factors influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of factors influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=216	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Parental involvement is important in supporting their child's reading development.		2.86	0.44	Disagree
2.	I believe access to a variety of reading materials at home influences reading skills development.		2.73	0.51	Agree
3.	Teacher instruction and strategies is effect in promoting reading skills development.		2.67	0.53	Agree
4.	The availability of library resources and books are important in schools for enhancing reading skills.		2.95	0.40	Disagree
5.	I believe peer interactions and group reading activities contribute to the development of reading skills.		2.88	0.42	Disagree

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6.	Digital technology (e.g., e-books, educational apps) has impact on reading skills development.	2.91	0.41	Disagree
7.	I think specialized reading programs or interventions are effective in addressing reading difficulties?	2.97	0.38	Disagree
8.	Socio-economic background has influence on reading skills development.	2.60	0.57	Disagree
9.	I believe individual differences in learning styles affect reading skills development.	2.71	0.52	Disagree
10.	A positive reading culture is important within the community for fostering reading skills development.	2.77	0.48	Agree
Grand Mean		2.81	0.47	Above Average

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average

Table 2 illustrates the factors influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis. Scores across all categories of primary teachers and parents surpass the established cut-off mean of 2.50. Consequently, the grand mean of 2.81 succinctly indicates that, all the item statements influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis are; Parental Involvement, Access to Reading Materials at Home, Teacher Instruction and Strategies, Availability of School Library Resources, Peer Interactions and Group Reading Activities, Digital Technology, Specialized Reading Programs or Interventions, Socio-economic Background, Individual Differences in Learning Styles and Community Reading Culture.

Research Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to class level among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to class level

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Primary Three	84	16.3	1.50	167	1.84	0.001	Sig.
Primary One	85	10.1	3.56				

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Significant at $P < 0.05$.

Analysis from table 3 indicates that the computed t-value is 1.84 at a degree of freedom of 167 with a probability value of 0.001. Since the computed probability value (p-value) of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between primary three pupils and primary one pupils' in Ilorin Metropolis.

Research Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to gender among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to gender

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Male	84	16.3	1.50	167	2.12	0.083	Not Sig.
Female	85	16.1	1.56				

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Significant at $P < 0.05$.

Analysis from table 4 indicates that the computed t-value is 2.12 at a degree of freedom of 167 with a probability value of 0.083. Since the computed probability value (p-value) of 0.083 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the stated null hypothesis is therefore accepted. This means that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between male and female primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis.

Assessment of Basic Reading... (Ahmed, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929483>

Research Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to school location among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

Table 5: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to school location

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Urban Schools	84	16.9	1.77	167	2.43	0.032	Sig.
Rural Schools	85	11.7	4.18				

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Significant at $P < 0.05$.

Analysis from table 5 indicates that the computed t-value is 2.43 at a degree of freedom of 167 with a probability value of 0.032. Since the computed probability value (p-value) of 0.032 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between pupils from urban schools and those from rural schools in Ilorin Metropolis.

Discussion of Findings

The study's first finding unveiled that pupils in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis display a lower-than-average level of basic reading abilities compared to expected proficiency levels. It might be attributed to teachers' insufficient training to effectively teach reading skills. This could include a lack of understanding of the best teaching methodologies and strategies for reading instruction. This finding is supported by Lindner (2008) who reported that most pupils have low reading abilities as a result of: primary school teachers' difficulties in moving beginning readers toward immediate reading skills, pupils' lack of exposure to reading strategies and the prevailing attitude among teachers towards reading strategies. Klapwijk and Van de Walt (2011) confirmed this by stating that some primary school teachers continue to struggle with reading instruction and remain resistant to its implementation in class. Hence, this implies that poor reading skills among pupils will hinder tertiary educational attainment and reduced employment opportunities.

The study unveiled in its second finding that indicates that all the item statements influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis are; Parental Involvement, Access to Reading Materials at Home, Teacher Instruction and Strategies, Availability of School Library Resources, Peer Interactions and Group Reading Activities, Digital Technology, Specialized Reading Programs or Interventions, Socio-economic Background, Individual Differences in Learning Styles and Community Reading Culture. The presence of all these factors may signify that they may not act in isolation, but rather interact and complement each other in shaping reading skills. To concur with these findings, Lindner (2008) and Njie (2013) both believe the lack of exposure to reading strategies in class and the use of poor teaching methodologies by language teachers are some of the reasons why pupils have poor reading skills. To further corroborate with these findings, Botha et al. (2008) claim the problem of pupils' poor reading abilities is as the result of teachers not been trained to teach basic reading in class. The implication of this finding highlights the interconnectedness between various factors in fostering reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis.

The study's third discovery revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between primary three pupils and primary one pupils in Ilorin Metropolis. This finding may be attributed to developmental factors, curriculum progression, or varying levels of instructional support received by students at different grade levels. This finding corresponds with the work of Joseph (2018) who pointed out that pupils who become poor readers experience difficulties with accurately identifying and reading words at lower grades.

This implies that children who are not reading proficiently by third grade are four times more likely not to graduate from high school on time compared to proficient readers.

In the fourth finding of this study, it was revealed that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between male and female primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis. This may be credited to gender-inclusive educational practices, equitable access to resources, and societal shifts towards gender equality in education. This finding corroborates with the work of Offorma (2009) who reported that there was no significant effect of gender on students' achievement in reading skills. The implication is that gender doesn't seem to affect reading ability, teachers and policymakers could focus on helping all students with their unique needs. They could create personalized learning plans or special help for students who are struggling reading skills, regardless of their gender.

Assessment of Basic Reading... (Ahmed, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929483>

The study's fifth discovery unveiled that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between pupils from urban schools and those from rural schools in Ilorin Metropolis. Urban schools may have better-equipped facilities, more qualified teachers, and greater availability of reading materials, which can positively impact pupils' reading abilities. This finding corresponds with assertion of Okebukola (2000) argued that primary school pupils in urban areas are better in reading than primary school pupils in rural areas. The implication is that pupils in rural schools might not only be deprived of opportunities for personal growth and fulfillment but also undermines the overall development and prosperity of rural communities.

Conclusion

Conclusively, this research reveals significant findings regarding basic reading abilities among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis. Government school pupils demonstrate lower-than-average reading proficiency, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions. Multiple factors influence reading skills, with notable differences observed between primary grades and urban and rural school settings. While gender disparities were not significant, addressing educational inequalities is crucial for fostering literacy development and ensuring equitable opportunities for all pupils.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that;

1. Ministry of Education should implement targeted literacy interventions in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis to address the observed lower-than-average level of basic reading abilities.
2. Researchers should conduct further studies to explore the specific impact of each influencing factor identified on the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis.
3. Educational stakeholders, including school administrators and teachers, should prioritize early intervention strategies to address the significant difference in mean scores of basic reading ability between primary three and primary one pupils. This may involve implementing targeted reading programs and interventions tailored to the needs of each grade level to mitigate learning gaps and promote literacy development from an early age.
4. While no significant gender differences were found in reading abilities, school administrators and teachers should be trained to create inclusive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs and preferences of both male and female primary pupils.
5. Government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and community leaders should collaborate to ensure that rural schools receive adequate resources to promote literacy development and ensure equal opportunities for all pupils.

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Assessment of Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State

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Abstract

The paper assessed Emotional intelligence and Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. Three objectives, research questions and corresponding hypothesis guided the study. The study employed descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consist of all senior secondary school class two (SSII) Students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance in katsina state. A sample size of three hundred and forty-six (Male = 165 and Female = 181) students were selected through systematic random sampling technique. The instrument adapted was Emotional intelligence scale (EIS). The reliability co-efficient of the instruments obtained was 0.79 using test-retest method. PPMC and t-test statistics were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The finding of the study revealed that Emotional intelligence significantly correlates with academic achievement in physics. It was found that male students have higher Emotional intelligence than the female. It was also revealed that male students achieved more academically than that of their female students Based on the findings, it was recommended that the physical psychology and social environment of the schools should be developed, maintained and sustained.

Keyword: Emotional-intelligence, Achievement, Physics

Introduction

Many Psychologists have investigated academic performance and focused on the relationship between intelligence quotient (IQ) and academic achievement. Funharm and Feyter (2013) opined that cognitive abilities alone are not sufficient to account for individual differences in academic success or failure. Thus, this study sought to investigate the contributions of emotional intelligence to the prediction of academic performance among senior secondary school students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Kapp (2002); viewed emotional intelligence as "that part of the human spirit which motivates us to perform, which gives us energy to demonstrate behaviors such as intentionality, persistence, creativity, impulse control, social deftness, compassion, intuition and integrity". Indeed, Mayer, Salovey and Caruso (2004) posited that emotional intelligence is part of a class of intelligences comprising the social, practical, and personal intelligences. They have referred to these types of multiple intelligences as "hot intelligences". Mayer and Salovey (1995) cited in Ejomah (2014) posit that emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thought, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth. Emotional intelligence is emerging as a critical factor for sustaining high achievement, retention, and positive behavior as well as improving life success. Increasingly, schools and educational organizations are turning emotional intelligence seeking a systemic solution to improve outcomes, both academic and social.

Academic achievement, which is measured by the examination results, is one of the major mechanisms to measure the academic performance of students. Academic achievement in every society reflects the educational system's success in

targeting and attention to individual needs (Aloka et al., 2018). Academic achievement according to Anja (2014) represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which an individual has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional contexts, specifically in school, college or university.

Orji (2014) suggested that due to the lack of proper knowledge on Physics students suffer in all spheres of life. There is a general consensus among educators that physics is an important and useful subject for development in every society. Therefore, from the grass root level, the teaching of Physics need to be effective and scientific. However, this research would provide students with psychological information about their abilities and potentialities by giving them insight on how they shall perceive their innate ability which can influence their academic performance in schools. It would also encourage teachers to cater for psychological needs of their students.

Despite school is being an academic institution where knowledge, skills, training and dispositions are exerted, however the researcher observed that most of our students in secondary schools could not be able to pay attention to their emotions by maintaining self-adjustment and handling good relationship with others. They are usually unable to recover from negative state of mind. These may occur as a result of poor learning condition, lack of parental care, teachers' attitude in schools or due to their current stage of development. Adeyemo, 2010 revealed that many students run away from this course both at the ordinary and tertiary levels. Isola (2010) opined that Physics as a subject remains one of the most difficult subjects in the school curriculum according to the Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC). It is also apparent that the rate of enrolment in Physics tend to be the lowest compared to other sciences (Mekonnen, 2024).

Objectives of the study

The aim of the study is assessment of emotional-intelligence and Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State Specifically, the objectives of the study were;

1. To determine relationship between Emotional-intelligence and Achievement in Physics among secondary School Students in Rimi zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
2. To find out the mean difference of Emotional-intelligence in Physics learning between male and female Senior Secondary Schools Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
3. To find out the mean difference of Achievement in Physics between male and female Senior Secondary Schools students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

1. What is the relationship between Emotional-intelligence and Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?
2. What is the mean difference of Emotional-intelligence between male and female Senior Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?
3. What is the mean difference of Achievement in Physics between male and female Senior Secondary School students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between Emotional-intelligence and Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
2. There is no significant difference in Emotional-intelligence between male and female Senior Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
3. There is no significant difference of mean achievement score in Physics between Male and Female Senior Secondary School students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Research Methodology

This research adopted descriptive survey research design. The choice of this design was informed by the nature of the problem under study and the fact that the design seeks to find out whether emotional intelligence influences academic performance of senior secondary school students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consist of all senior secondary schools class two (SSII) Students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance in katsina state.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size of three hundred and forty-six (346) students from the target population was used. The sample size was estimated based on the recommendation given by Research Advisor (2006) table of sample size. Systematic random sampling technique was used to arrive at the needed sample. In this method the researcher will take a fixed interval from the population out of which one respondent will be selected.

Instrumentation

The researcher Adapted Emotional intelligence scale (EIS) administered by Ejomah Dawanderhie Stephanie (2014). The scale is fifteen (20) items which were rated on 5 points Likert scales as Strongly agree (SA); Agree (A); Undecided (UD); Disagree (D); Strongly disagree (SD). The respondents were asked to respond to the items by a tick (✓) against the appropriate option that reflect or show their personal opinion. Both face and content validity were ascertained to ensure that the items in the questionnaires measure what they supposed to measure. Test-retest method of reliability test was used to determine reliability coefficient of the instrument. Thus, reliability coefficient of 0.79 was obtained.

Method of Data Analysis

PPMC was used to test hypothesis one, and t-test for hypothesis 2 and 3 at 0.05 level of significance, respectively.

Presentation of Results

Null Hypothesis One (H₀₁)

There is no significant relationship between Emotional-intelligence and Achievement in Physics among secondary school students in Rimi zonal education quality assurance, Katsina State.

Table 1: Correlation Analysis between Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Physics

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value	Decision
Emotional Intelligence	346	100.730	16.433			
Achievement	346	42.893	6.162	.735	.000	Significant

Analysis of the above table shows that, the r-value (r-cal) computed is .735 and p-value is .000 at .05 level of significance. Since the critical p-value of .000 is less than the alpha value of .05, the null hypothesis one is rejected while the basic assumption is upheld. This indicates that Emotional has positive relationship with achievement in Physics.

Null Hypothesis Two (H₀₂)

There is no significant difference in mean Emotional-intelligence score in Physics learning between male and female Senior Secondary School students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Table 2: t-test Analysis in Emotional Intelligence between Male and Female Students in Physics.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	DF	t-value	p-value	Decision
Male	165	104.970	16.404				
Female	181	92.549	13.097	344	7.764	.000	Significant

Table above shows that at 344 degrees of freedom and .05 level of significance, the t-value (t-cal) is 7.764 and the p-value is .000. The analysis indicates that the male students have a mean score of 104.970 and standard deviation of 16.404 while the female students have a mean score of 92.549 and standard deviation of 13.097. Since p-value of .000 < .05, the null hypothesis is rejected while the basic assumption is therefore maintained. This indicates that there is significant gender difference in the influence of Emotional-intelligence between male and female on achievement in Physics. Since the mean score of male students is higher than that of the female students, the Male students have more Emotional-intelligence than the female students.

Null Hypothesis Three (H₀₃)

There is no significant difference in mean achievement score in Physics between male and female Senior Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Table 3: t-test Analysis of achievement in physics between Male and Female Students.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	DF	t-value	p-value	Decision
Male	165	52.256	5.232	344	2.964	.000	Significant
Female	181	50.467	5.493				

Table above shows that at 344 degrees of freedom and .05 level of significance, the t-value (t-cal) is 2.964 and the p-value is .000. The analysis indicates that the male students have a mean score of 52.256 and standard deviation of 5.232 while the female students have a mean score of 50.467 and standard deviation of 5.493. Since p-value of .000 < .05, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant gender difference in students' achievement in physics is rejected while the basic assumption is retained. This implies that male and female students are significantly different in terms of their academic performance. Since the mean score of Male students is higher than that of the Female students, the Male students seem to have better achievement in Physics than the Female students.

Conclusion

Based on the above findings, it was further concluded that Emotional Intelligence significantly influences the achievement in physics among senior secondary school students in Rimi zonal Education quality assurance, Katsina State. Hence, there is significant difference in Emotional intelligence and achievement in physics with gender.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was further recommended that:

1. The inclusion of a focus on emotional intelligence as part of the standard secondary school curriculum could lead to a variety of positive personal, social and societal outcomes. Increasing emotional intelligence may not only facilitate the learning process and improve career choice and likelihood of success, but could also enhance the probability of better personal and social adaptation in general.
2. Inter-personal relationship should be created and maintained between Teachers and their students.
3. It recommended that the physical psychology and social environment of the schools should be developed, maintained and sustained. Social centers and recreational centers should be made functional in order to make the school environment an ideal place for effective teaching and learning.

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Comparative Relationships between Self-Efficacy and Test Anxiety on Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined Comparative relationships between self-efficacy and Test Anxiety on performance in Biology among secondary school students in North-west, Nigeria. The study employed correlational research design. The population of the study consists of all public secondary school two (SS2) Biology students during the 2022/2023 academic session in North-west, Nigeria. The sample size of the study consists of 384 (Male, 213 And Female, 171) students selected from target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The study adapted Self - efficacy Scale (SES) and Test Anxiety Scale (TAS) at 0.70, and 0.77 reliability co-efficient respectively. The statistics used for data analysis was the Pearson Product Moment Correlation and independent t-test. The findings of the study reveal no significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west Nigeria. It is recommended that Schools should establish programs that will facilitate gains in self-efficacy as well as confident posture in approaching examinations, so as to promote Students' Academic performance in Biology.

Keywords: Adolescent, Gender, self-efficacy, test anxiety, academic performance

Introduction

Education is one of the vital sectors that contribute towards the development of any society. It is the backbone of every nation. In a situation where by majority of the people living in a particular society are educated, they would be able to come up with many ideas in terms of their economic, political and social wellbeing. However, education is also the light that can guide human beings in carrying out their day-to-day activities. Therefore, teaching and learning in Nigeria have to be considered as a Centre of gravity in educational context. If the students received a better and qualitative education, they would become well known important personnel in future who will lead to the development of the country.

Self-efficacy involves an individual's evaluation of own ability to achieve a goal or self-belief to do a specific task. For example, in academic situation, it can be assumed that learners with high self-efficacy would have higher motivation to learn, resulting in higher academic achievement, because those learners believe that they have an ability to achieve their goal. Self-efficacy refers to the confidence in one's ability to behave in such a way or to produce a desirable outcome (Siddiqui, 2015). Self-efficacy makes a difference in how people feel, think and act. It pertains to optimistic belief about being able to cope with a variety of stressors. Self-efficacy is defined as self-evaluation of one's competence to successfully execute a course of action necessary to reach desired outcome, (Zimmerman, 2020).

Tests at all stages of education have been considered as an important and powerful tool for decision making and determining academic success or failure. Students are evaluated with respect to their performance, skills and abilities (Habibullah & Ashraf, 2013). Scholars and researchers believe that no society or nation can develop more than the level and standard of education available for her citizens (Okafor, et al, 2018). Currently, the Nigerian system of education makes use of

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certificates to indicate the level of knowledge acquisition. However, before certificates are awarded, students have to be assessed or examined in the field they have been trained. Thus, examination becomes a yardstick against which students' competence and progress are formally measured and appraised in the Nigerian education sector (Ozuome, et-al, (2020). On the other hand, anxiety is defined as feeling of undesirable and unclear like when person predicts a dangerous situation. Extreme level of anxiety impedes individual's mental and physical health and also has a negative effect on their personal, social, familial, occupational, and educational performance (Zahrakar, 2018).

It is perhaps ironic that students Biology achievement is on the decline (Tailor, 2016). A large number of people in current world do not receive proper education. Approximately 260 million of school aged children in the world can't read and write including in north-west and north-east Nigeria (World Bank, 2017). Above statement is one of the reasons why students level of self-efficacy is gradually decline, and students develop poor attitude to Examination Situations resulting to poor academic performance.

Most Students in North west Nigeria are suffering from low sense of self-efficacy, this avoid students to deal with tasks involving a high degree of difficulty like Biology, considering themselves incapable of solving problems and quickly losing confidence in their own capabilities thus displaying the tendency to remain focused on the experience of failures and setbacks (Siddiqui, 2015).

Test anxiety can be very stressful for students who experience it, leading to negative psychological wellbeing and developing low self-efficacy among adolescent students (Ahmad, 2020). Addiction alters perceptions, cognition, mood, behavior, and general body processes (Balogun, 2016). This may cause automatic anxiety in a testing setting among adolescent students and subsequently resulting in poor academic performance and the development of negative school attitude (Nnachi, 2007).

Given the aforementioned, the conclusions of this study will help to establish how best to assist and provide additional recommendations to develop positive self-efficacy and employ necessary measures to maximize academic performance.

Objectives of the Study

1. Examine the relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.
2. Determine the relationship between test anxiety and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.
3. Determine the difference between male and female students' self-efficacy among Senior Secondary School students in North-west.
4. Determine the difference between male and female students' test anxiety among Senior Secondary School students in North-west.

Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted a correlational research design, the research design facilitated broader coverage of a wide geopolitical area under examination within a potentially constrained time frame. It is the best design to use when a researcher wants to investigate the relationship between variables and compare groups, such as male and female.

The population of the study consists of all public secondary school two (SS2) Biology students during the 2022/2023 academic session in North-west, Nigeria. The sample size of the study consists of 384 (Male, 213 And Female, 171) students selected from target population using multi-stage sampling technique.

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Instrumentation

For the purpose of this study, the researcher adapted two (2) instruments for data collection. These are: Self - Efficacy Scale (SES) by Albert Bandura (1977), and Test Anxiety Scale (TAS) Abbasi & Ghosh (2020). More also, Biology Performance test was used to determine the academic performance of students in North-west Nigeria.

The Cronbach alpha reliability test was used to assess the reliability of the instruments. Cronbach alpha reliability test was used to determine the reliability of the instruments. Thus, the reliability coefficient of pilot testing result for self-efficacy scale (SES) was 0.70, test anxiety Scale (TAS) was 0.77. Furthermore, Biology performance test was 0.83 respectively.

The data collected was analyzed based on the null hypotheses formulated for the study. Hypotheses 1 & 2 was analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC), in addition, hypotheses 3 & 4 was tested using t-test for independent sample. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis One: there is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 1: PPMC Summary Table showing the relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance.

Variable	Correlation, Sig. & N.	Self-efficacy	Academic performance
Self-efficacy	Pearson Correlation	1	-.080
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.117
	N	384	384
Biology performance test	Pearson Correlation	-.080	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.117	
	N	384	384

Note: ** means significant at 0.05 alpha level of Significance

Table 1, reveals a negative correlation (r- value = -.080) which is not significant at 0.05 alpha levels of significance (r = -.080, p >0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which assumes is accepted. The high negative correlation means no any significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance of Senior Secondary School adolescents in North-west Nigeria

Hypothesis Two: there is no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 2: PPMC Summary Table showing the relationship between test anxiety and academic performance.

Variable	Correlation, Sig. & N.	Test anxiety	Biology performance test
Test anxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	-.124*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.015
	N	384	384
Biology performance test	Pearson Correlation	-.124*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015	
	N	384	384

Note: * means significant at 0.05 alpha level of Significance

Table 2, reveals negative correlation (r-value of -.124*) which is significant at 0.05 alpha levels of significance (r = -.124, p < 0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which assumes no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic performance of Senior Secondary School adolescents in North-west Nigeria is rejected. The result further assert that a unit increase in test anxiety can lead to unit increase in students' academic performance.

Hypothesis three: There is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria.

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Table 3: t-Test Summary Table Showing the Difference in the self-efficacy of Male and Female adolescent Secondary Schools students (N=384)

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-val.	Sig.
Self-efficacy	Male	214	45.4065	13.2915	382	-1.08	.280
	Female	170	46.3808	13.3808			

NS: Not Significant at 0.05 alpha level of significance

Table 2 reveals no significant difference between male and female students' level of self-efficacy among Senior Secondary School adolescents in North-west, Nigeria. ($t = -1.08$; $df = 382$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. This implies that, Self-efficacy has nothing to do with gender.

Hypothesis four: There is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 4: t-Test Summary Table Showing the Difference in the test anxiety of Male and Female adolescent Secondary Schools students (N=384)

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-val.	Sig. (2-tailed)
Test anxiety	Male	214	43.0935	17.8843	382	-.190	.849
	Female	170	43.4353	17.0435			

Table four (4) reveals no significant difference between male and female students' level of self-efficacy among Senior Secondary School adolescents in North-west, Nigeria. ($t = 1.574$; $df = 382$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. This implies that, Findings reveals no difference in substances abuse among gender.

Discussion of Findings

The identification of the independent variables (self-efficacy and test anxiety) as correlates of academic performance of adolescents' secondary school students in North-west Nigeria, has been the major concern of this discussion.

Findings in Hypothesis one reveals there is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria. The finding is in line with Akanbi et-al (2015), Investigated the impact of self-efficacy on academic performance in colleges of education in Kwara State., Eukay, (2010) examined self-efficacy and test anxiety as correlates of academic performance among undergraduate students of a university in Eastern Nigeria. Results showed low significant correlation between self-efficacy and academic performance.

Hypothesis two reveals negative correlation (r -value of $-.124^*$) which is significant at 0.05 alpha levels of significance ($r = -.124$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which assumes there is significant relationship between test anxiety and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria. This support the above findings, Dawood et-al (2016) in a study titled relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement among undergraduate nursing Students, result revealed statistically significant positive relationship between test anxiety scores and undergraduate nursing students' academic level ($r = -0.144$, $p = 0.01$) which explain that undergraduate nursing students in higher academic level experience and less test anxiety. Pearson's R revealed a negative none statistically significant relationship ($r = -0.090$, $p = 0.157$) between test anxiety scores and undergraduate nursing students Grade Point Average. In a similar study conducted by Chowdhury (2022) titled "A comparative study on examination anxiety among Student academic performance" it was revealed that Examination anxiety is quite a common phenomenon among students across the world. However, anxiety entails various psycho-physical fallouts which interfere in the normal healthy living of many students, which reveled positive correlation among the variables. Euckay, (2010) examined test anxiety as correlates of academic performance among undergraduate students of a university in Eastern Nigeria. Test anxiety proves to be a significant predictor of the variability in academic performance,

Hypothesis three reveals there is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria. The value computed was ($t = -1.08$; $df = 382$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Finding of this research agrees with Baji, (2020). In research titled Analysis of Gender Difference in Academic Self-Efficacy and Achievements among Senior Secondary School Students in Niger State, Nigeria. The findings of the study found that there was no significant difference in academic self-efficacy between male and female students. However, the mean value of female students indicated a higher-level self-efficacy (Mean =78.36) over the male students (Mean =78.16). The study also revealed a significant difference in achievements of male and female students. The mean difference

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showed that the male students performed better in academic achievements if compared with their female counterparts (Mean =105.42 for males and Mean =100.58 for females).

Hypothesis Four reveals there is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria. ($t= 1.8$; $df =382$, $p> 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. This implies that, the assertion apparently further justified by the investigation of Ahmad (2020), shows that there is a meaningful difference between males and females considering the rate of test anxiety. As it is shown in table 2 the mean of test anxiety score for female students ($X=123.72$, $SD=35$) was higher than the mean of test anxiety score for male students ($x=113.27$, $SD=32.14$). Similarly, this finding supported the result on Test Anxiety as reviewed on gender by Kusmawaty et-al (2020), the results of the analysis showed that the mean of test anxiety in facing exams on male subjects was 3.10, while the mean of test anxiety in facing exams on female subjects was 3.35. The results of this study indicate that there is a significant difference in test anxiety in facing exams in male and female subjects.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed that the level of students' need to reawakened students' self-efficacy and brought out modality to address issue of test anxiety. Low self-efficacy resulted to students considering themselves incapable of solving problems and quickly losing confidence in their own capabilities and striving to meet up with their potentiality. Findings showed that students in North-west Nigeria have low self-efficacy. On the other hands majority of students are prone to test anxiety, resulted to low self-esteem, Low participation, negative attitude to learning, and poor academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher recommended that:

1. Schools should establish programs that will facilitate gains in self-efficacy as well as confident posture in approaching examinations.
2. Educational Psychologist should consider the psychological elements that contribute to severe exam anxiety in secondary school students and intervene accordingly.
3. Teach students how to manage and cope with test anxiety during exams, and make them understand that some level of anxiety is necessary as a motivator before the exam. Furthermore, examinations, ongoing assessment exams, and assignments should be adequately prepared to reduce unnecessary stress on students, which is likely to cause anxiety.

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Impacts of ICT and Social Media Platforms on Performance in Economics among Students in Selected Tertiary Institutions in Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study investigated the impacts of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and social media platforms on the performance of Economics students at selected tertiary institutions in Kaduna State. It aimed to assess the effects of ICT and social media on academic performance and study habits. A total of 450 students were selected from three institutions using a multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics and a Probit model. The study used ICT tools (such as computers and educational apps) and social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter, TikTok, WhatsApp) as key variables. Key findings revealed that Facebook usage and the negative consequences of social media significantly reduce academic performance. Conversely, WhatsApp usage and lecturer guidance positively impact academic outcomes. In terms of study habits, collaborative ICT and social media-based activities were found to significantly improve study habits, whereas the negative effects of social media were detrimental to study habits. The research underscores the dual-edged nature of social media in education, highlighting the importance of a balanced integration of ICT and social media. The study rejects the null hypotheses, confirming that both ICT and social media significantly influence academic performance and study habits. It recommends that the government and stakeholders invest in ICT infrastructure, including computers, internet access, and essential software, to foster a technologically enhanced learning environment.

Keywords: Academic Performance, communication, information, social media, technology

Introduction

Social media and ICT can have both beneficial and detrimental effects on students' academic achievement in economics. To understand the specific dynamics at work, a case study in selected tertiary institutions in Kaduna State, or similar regions, could be insightful. ICT plays a crucial role in educational institutions by generating, storing, processing, distributing, and exchanging information (Otuu, 2013). This provides students with access to a wealth of economics-related resources such as online academic journals, instructional videos, and textbooks, facilitating research and study.

ICT tools enhance student interaction with peers and lecturers, improving their understanding of economic concepts through online discussions and clarifications. This networked environment suggests that ICT can significantly enhance teaching and learning efficiency (UNDP Evaluation Office, 2001, in Otuu, 2013). However, the effects of social media and ICT vary based on how students use these tools. While ICT promotes educational equity, accessibility, professional development, and efficient educational management, it also has drawbacks. Social media, for example, can be distracting and lead to academic neglect and social isolation (Andoh, 2012, in Muhammad et al., 2015).

Despite these challenges, ICT offers significant advantages, such as speeding up learning, saving time, and facilitating efficient discussions (Muhammad et al., 2015). However, understanding these dynamics requires a comprehensive examination of student usage patterns. In Nigerian tertiary institutions, the use of computers and Android phones as teaching aids has contributed to a more inclusive classroom environment (Zubair, 2016). Yet, despite African countries prioritizing ICT in education, progress in its integration remains limited. Only a few schools have effectively

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incorporated ICT into their curricula, and many teachers remain unaware of available ICT resources, leading to continued low performance in subjects like economics due to poor instructional methods (Ikwuka & Adigwe, 2016; Olojede, Bolaji, & Musa, 2017).

The study aims to investigate specific challenges in economics education and reassess the use of ICT as a teaching aid. It also seeks to explore the under-researched area of educational technology for early education, including online resources for parents, while considering access equity (Greenhow & Lewin, 2021). By collecting data on students' academic performance in economics, the study will evaluate the perceived advantages and disadvantages of ICT and social media.

Previous research has explored various aspects of ICT and social media's impact on academic performance. Notable studies include Karpinski and Duberstein (2009), who examined Facebook usage and academic performance, and Aduwa-Ogiegbaen and Iyamu (2005), who identified barriers to ICT use in Nigerian secondary schools. Peter (2015) investigated social media use and academic achievement at the University of Lagos, while Lauren (2014) discussed the benefits of social media use. Muhammad and Irfan (2015) focused on ICT's impact on students' access to information at Gomal University.

Additionally, Ikwuka and Adigwe (2016) studied ICT's effects on Christian Religious Studies students' performance, and Zubairu (2016) evaluated the impact of internet-based resources on biology performance among senior secondary students in Kaduna State. However, no research has specifically addressed the effects of ICT and social media on economics students' academic performance, highlighting a gap that this study aims to fill.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the effects of use of ICT on the on academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions.
2. To examine the effects of social media Platforms on the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions.
3. To examine the extent to which the use of ICT and social media affect the study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions

Research Questions

1. How does use of ICT affect the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions?
2. How does the use of social media Platforms affect the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions?
3. To what extent does the use of ICT and social media affect the study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions?

Hypotheses:

The study set three hypotheses as follows:

1. **Null Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁):** Use of ICT has no significant effects on students' performance in Economics students in tertiary institutions.
2. **Null Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂):** Use of social media Platforms has no significant effects on the students' performance in Economics students in tertiary institutions.
3. **Null Hypothesis 3 (H₀₃):** ICT and social media have no significant effects on study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions

Methodology

Research Design

The study used both descriptive and analytical statistics to explore the impact of ICT and social media on students' academic performance in economics at tertiary institutions in Kaduna State. The study adopts a mixed-methods approach using qualitative and quantitative design to assess the ICT resources available for teaching and learning economics. This approach aims to provide a thorough understanding of how these technologies influence academic outcomes.

Population and Sampling

The study targets economics students from tertiary institutions in Kaduna State during 2023/2024 academic session. Three institutions were selected using multi-stage sampling technique to represent the state's higher education landscape: Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria; Kaduna State University, Kaduna; and College of Education, Gidan Waya,

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Kafanchan. Each institution contributed 150 students which gives a sample size of 450 students, which is considered adequate for the study.

Method of Data Collection

Surveys, questionnaires, interviews, and academic records were used to collect data for the study. These techniques are selected in order find more about how students utilise ICT and social media to foster their academic achievement.

Validation of Research Instrument

The instruments were developed by the researcher and evaluated by experts from the Departments of Economics and Computer Education at Federal College of Education, Zaria. Content validity was used in this investigation, a sort of validity that indicates how much the study's objectives and research questions are represented. The researchers requested experts to assess the relevance of the test items in measuring the study variables. To make the instruments better, their opinions, clarifications, and ideas were noted and effected.

Reliability of Research Instrument

Pilot study was carried out in Federal College of Education, Zaria, and Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic, Zaria. The questionnaire was distributed to 60 individuals who were not part of the selected group. Consequently, a reliability index of 0.70 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test indicating that the instrument is reliable for the study.

Method of Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics will be used. Descriptive statistics include measures like mean and standard deviation. Inferential analysis used the Probit model to examine the impact of ICT and social media on academic performance and study habits. The study used descriptive statistics to answer the research questions and three Probit Regression models and test the hypotheses of the study. The general Probit model is given as:

$$p(Y = 1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 ICT + \beta_2 SM + \beta_k Control_k + \varepsilon$$

Where $p(Y = 1)$ is the probability of success (academic performance), Φ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution, $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2$ and β_k are the coefficients to be estimated. Based on the objectives of this study, the above model is transformed and broken into three different models adapted from the study of Muawiya, Ubangida and Zakari (2023) as follows:

Model 1: $p(ACDPERF = 1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 UICT + \beta_2 UCP + \beta_3 EDUAP + \beta_4 ONLT + \beta_5 LICT + \beta_6 IICT + \varepsilon_1) \text{ ----- } 1$

This model was used to examine the effect of ICT tools and usage frequency on academic performance. The dependent variable is students' academic performance, measured by changes in their CGPA. Independent variables include the frequency of ICT usage (UICT), use of computers/laptops (UCP), educational apps (EDUAP), online tutorials (ONLT), and lecturers incorporating ICT in teaching (LICT). The model also includes a control variable representing improved performance due to ICT use (IICT).

Model 2: $p(ACDPERF = 1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 USM + \beta_2 fb + \beta_3 X + \beta_4 I + \beta_5 TT + \beta_6 W + \beta_6 LISM + \beta_6 CSM + \varepsilon_1) \text{ ----- } 2$

This model was used to analyze the impact of social media usage on academic performance. The dependent variable remains academic performance. The independent variables of interest are the frequency of social media usage (USM) and specific platforms like Facebook (fb), Twitter (X), Instagram (I), TikTok (TT), and WhatsApp (W). Improved performance due to social media (ISM) and the consequences of social media (CSM) serve as control variables.

Model 3: $p(SH=1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 SICT + \beta_2 SSM + \beta_3 IICT + \beta_3 ISM + \beta_4 I + \beta_5 CSM + \varepsilon_3) \text{ ----- } 3$

This model was used to investigate the influence of ICT and social media on students' study habits (SH). Independent variables include studying Economics through collaborative ICT-based activities (SICT), social media-based activities (SSM), improved performance due to ICT (IICT), and social media platforms (ISM). Increased interest in learning due to ICT and social media (I) and the consequences of social media (CSM) are used as control variables.

Each model estimates the coefficients (β_i) of the independent variables and includes a disturbance term (ε) to account for variability not explained by the model.

Results

Research Question 1: How does use of ICT affect the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions?

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Table 1 Descriptive Statistics: Effect of ICT on Academic Performance

Variables	Mean	Std Dev	Decision (Effect)
Usage rate of ICT (UICT)	0.528	0.206	moderate
Usage of Computers/Phones (UCP):	0.697	0.194	high
Usage of Educational Apps (EDUAPP)	0.593	0.305	moderate
Online Teaching and Learning (ONLT)	0.826	0.223	high
Lecturers Involving ICT in teaching (LICT)	0.535	0.463	moderate
Improved Performance dues to ICT (IICT)	0.773	0.264	high
Usage rate of ICT (UICT)	0.528	0.506	Moderate

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics on the impact of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on academic performance. The average ICT usage rate is moderate (mean = 0.528) with low variability (standard deviation = 0.206). Computer and phone usage is high (mean = 0.697) and consistent across students (standard deviation = 0.194). Educational app usage is moderate (mean = 0.593) but shows higher variability (standard deviation = 0.305), indicating diverse usage patterns. Online teaching and learning have a high adoption rate (mean = 0.826) with low variability (standard deviation = 0.223), reflecting consistent use. Lecturers' involvement in using ICT for teaching is moderate (mean = 0.535) with significant variability (standard deviation = 0.463), suggesting differing levels of engagement. ICT is perceived to significantly improve academic performance (mean = 0.773) with moderate variability (standard deviation = 0.264), indicating that this benefit is somewhat uniformly experienced.

In summary, ICT usage is widespread among students, particularly through computers, phones, and online teaching, and is generally seen as enhancing academic performance. However, there is variability in lecturers' involvement and in the use of educational apps, suggesting areas where consistency could be improved.

Null Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁):

Use of ICT has no significant effect on students' performance in Economics students in tertiary institutions.

Table 2: Results for Probit Regression Model 1

<i>Dependent Variable: Academic Performance (ACDPERF)</i>				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
<i>UICT</i>	0.295047	0.120888	2.440664	0.0166
<i>UCP</i>	0.393699	0.124734	3.156309	0.0025
<i>EDUAPP</i>	0.223182	0.116359	1.918042	0.0551
<i>ONLT</i>	0.318935	0.111533	2.859563	0.0042
<i>LICT</i>	0.029319	0.113503	0.258311	0.7962
<i>IICT</i>	0.137845	0.118623	1.162039	0.2452

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

In Table 2, Academic Performance is analyzed as the dependent variable: A one-unit increase in UICT is associated with a 0.295047 unit increase in Academic Performance ($z = 2.440664$, $p = 0.0166$), indicating a statistically significant effect. A one-unit increase in UCP leads to a 0.393699 unit increase in Academic Performance ($z = 3.156309$, $p = 0.0025$), showing a statistically significant impact. A one-unit increase in EDUAPP corresponds to a 0.223182 unit increase in Academic Performance, but the p-value (0.0551) is slightly above the 0.05 significance level, making it marginally significant. A one-unit increase in ONLT results in a 0.318935 unit increase in Academic Performance ($z = 2.859563$, $p = 0.0042$), indicating a statistically significant effect. With a coefficient of 0.029319, LICT is not a statistically significant predictor ($p = 0.7962$). IICT has a coefficient of 0.137845 but is not statistically significant ($p = 0.2452$). Overall, most variables significantly predict Academic Performance, leading to the rejection of Null hypothesis H₀₁. The direction of the relationships is determined by the sign of the coefficients.

Research Question 2: How does the use of social media Platforms affect the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions?

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Table 3: Descriptive Statistics: Effect of social media Platforms on academic performance

Variables	Mean	Std Dev	Decision (Effect)
Social media usage USM	0.740	0.584	High
Facebook (fb)	0.678	0.496	High
Twitter (X)	0.211	0.301	Very Low
TikTok (TT)	0.398	0.500	Very low
WhatsApp (W)	0.967	0.440	High
Lecturer Support and Guidance (LSM)	0.531	0.663	Moderate
Consequences of Social Media (CSM)	0.601	0.512	High

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

Table 3 presents descriptive statistics on the effect of social media platforms on academic performance, including the overall usage of social media, specific platforms, and related factors. The descriptive statistics indicate that social media platforms generally have a positive impact on academic performance, though the degree of this effect varies. Social Media Usage (USM) has a high negative effect with a mean of 0.740 and a standard deviation of 0.584, indicating some variability in its impact. Facebook (mean: 0.678, SD: 0.496) also has a high positive effect with moderate variability. Twitter (mean: 0.211, SD: 0.301) and TikTok (mean: 0.398, SD: 0.500) show lower positive effects, with Twitter having the lowest impact and least variability. WhatsApp has the highest positive effect (mean: 0.967, SD: 0.440), suggesting it is the most beneficial. Lecturer Support (mean: 0.531, SD: 0.663) shows a moderate positive effect, with significant variability. The Consequences of Social Media (mean: 0.301, SD: 0.512) reveal a low negative effect, with moderate variability in its impact. Overall, while most platforms have a positive effect, WhatsApp and general social media usage are the most beneficial, and the negative effects of social media are relatively low.

Null Hypothesis 2: Use of social media Platforms has no significant effect on the students' performance in Economics students in tertiary institutions

Table 4: Results for Probit Regression Model 2

Dependent Variable: Academic Performance (<i>ACDPERF</i>)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
<i>USM</i>	-1.424618	0.124928	11.40349	0.0412
<i>Fb</i>	-0.264500	0.126977	-2.083052	0.0372
<i>X</i>	0.477820	0.119231	4.007507	0.2001
<i>TT</i>	-0.077536	0.120560	-0.643137	0.5201
<i>W</i>	0.438415	0.115502	2.497056	0.0041
<i>LSM</i>	0.264807	0.112260	2.358872	0.0037
<i>CSM</i>	0.430200	0.129247	3.328519	0.0009

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

The Probit model in Table 4 evaluates the impact of various factors on Academic Performance: A one-unit increase decreases Academic Performance by 1.424618 units ($z = 1.40349$, $p = 0.0412$), showing a significant negative effect. A one-unit increase reduces Academic Performance by 0.264500 units ($z = 2.083052$, $p = 0.0372$), indicating a statistically significant negative impact. A one-unit increase increases Academic Performance by 0.477820 units, but this effect is not statistically significant ($z = 1.007507$, $p = 0.2001$). A one-unit increase decreases Academic Performance by 0.077536 units, which is not statistically significant ($z = -0.643137$, $p = 0.5201$). A one-unit increase improves Academic Performance by 0.438415 units ($z = 2.497056$, $p = 0.0041$), indicating a statistically significant positive effect. A one-unit increase boosts Academic Performance by 0.264807 units ($z = 2.358872$, $p = 0.0037$), showing a statistically significant positive effect. A one-unit increase decreases Academic Performance by 0.430200 units ($z = 3.328519$, $p = 0.0009$), indicating a significant negative effect. Thus, most variables significantly impact Academic Performance, with clear directionality in their effects, leading to the rejection of the Null hypothesis H02.

Research Question 3: To what extent does the use of ICT and social media affect the study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions?

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Table 5: Descriptive Statistics: Effect of ICT and social media affect the study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions

Variables	Mean	Std Dev	Decision (Effect)
SICT (Study Economics through Collaborative ICT-Based activities)	0.640	0.484	High
SSM (Study Economics through Collaborative Social media-Based activities)	0.678	0.496	High
IICT (Improved Performance due to ICT),	0.511	0.401	Moderate
ISM (Improved Performance and social media)	0.398	0.500	Low
I (Increased Interest in learning due to use of ICT and Social Media),	0.767	0.440	High
Consequences of Social Media (CSM)	0.501	0.503	Moderate

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

The average score of 0.640 suggests that students generally have a positive experience with collaborative ICT-based activities in economics, though variability is moderate (SD = 0.484). Social media-based activities also show a positive outcome with a mean score of 0.678 and similar variability (SD = 0.496), indicating they are highly effective in enhancing learning. ICT usage moderately improves performance (Mean = 0.511, SD = 0.401), while social media has a lower impact on performance (Mean = 0.398, SD = 0.500) with high variability. The use of ICT and social media significantly increases interest in learning (Mean = 0.767, SD = 0.440), and the consequences of social media have a moderate effect (Mean = 0.501, SD = 0.503) with considerable variability. Overall, ICT and social media enhance learning and interest, though their impact on performance and consequences varies.

Null Hypothesis 3 (H₀₃): ICT and social media have no significant affect on study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions

Table 6:

Results for Probit Model 3

Dependent Variable: Study Habit (SH)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
SICT	0.432415	0.115502	3.497056	0.0241
SSM	0.234807	0.112260	2.338872	0.0237
IICT	0.422220	0.129247	3.222519	0.0209
ISM	0.355557	0.144880	2.445322	0.0170
I	0.493699	0.124734	3.446309	0.0325
CSM	-0.623182	0.116359	4.918042	0.0251

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

The results of the probit model in Table 6 examines how various factors influence study habits. Key findings include. For **SICT**, a one-unit increase in SICT raises study habits by 0.432415 units ($z = 3.497056$, $p = 0.0241$), showing it is a significant predictor. A one-unit increase in SSM boosts study habits by 0.234807 units ($z = 2.338872$, $p = 0.0237$), also statistically significant. A one-unit increase in IICT enhances study habits by 0.422220 units ($z = 3.222519$, $p = 0.0209$), indicating high significance. A one-unit increase in ISM results in a 0.355557 unit increase in study habits ($z = 2.445322$, $p = 0.0070$), showing significant predictive power. A one-unit rise in interest increases study habits by 0.493699 units ($z = 3.446309$, $p = 0.0325$), likely significant. A one-unit increase in CSM decreases study habits by 0.623182 units ($z = 2.625$, $p = 0.025$), indicating a significant negative impact. Thus, all variables significantly predict study habits, leading to the rejection of the Null hypothesis H₀₃.

Discussion of Findings

The relationship and effects of ICT on the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institution revealed the presence of a significant relationship and effect for majority of the variable examined in this study. The findings are in conformity with the findings of Ikwuka and Adigwe (2016); Zubairu (2016), Olojede, Bolaji and Musa (2017), Pedro & Kumar (2020 and Jamal & Nawab (2020). However, Ikwuka and Adigwe (2016) Zubairu (2016) conducted their studies on the academic performance of Secondary School students in CRS and Biology respectively.

The relationship and effects of Social Media usage on the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institution revealed the presence of a significant relationship and effect for majority of the variable examined in

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The study also revealed that a positive significant relationship exist between study habit and usage of ICT and social media. However, it has been observed that, the consequences of social media usage led to dissatisfaction and Isolation from others, distraction from learning and unnecessary fatigue to the users, laziness and fatigue impact negatively on study habit. This finding is in line with that of Ansari & Khan (2020) and many other studies on the effects of social media on students' performance.

Conclusion

The study on the effects of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Social Media Usage on the academic performance of pupils in mathematics at selected tertiary institutions in Kaduna State sheds light on the link between technology and education. Based on the study of quantitative and qualitative data, the findings reveal how the use of ICT tools and social media platforms a favourably relates with students' academic achievement in Economics. Students that use technological tools such as laptops, androids, social media platforms, online application improve their motivation and study habits, as well as their understanding of Economics leading to improvement in their academic performance. Despite the excellent outcomes, there are still hurdles to implementing ICT in Economics education, such as infrastructural limits, access inequities and the need for teacher training to mention just a few challenges. These problems can prevent students from fully utilising the benefits of technology in their study.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Government and other stakeholders should prioritise investing in ICT infrastructure in Education. Adequate provision of computers, internet access, and essential software is critical for establishing a technologically enabled learning environment.
2. Efforts should be made by government and other stakeholders to guarantee that all students have fair access to ICT resources while addressing socioeconomic gaps. Initiatives like giving laptop computers, internet access, and digital learning materials can help close the digital gap.
3. Efforts should be made to ensure implementation of comprehensive training programs to equip teachers with the knowledge and confidence to successfully integrate ICT into their teaching methods.
4. Educational policymakers should work with educators to create curriculum modules that match with both technological improvements and pedagogical objectives.
5. Establish regular monitoring and assessment systems to examine ICT integration's impact on academic performance. This includes receiving feedback from teachers and students to help guide future changes and adjustments.

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Management of Secondary School Curriculum for Adequate Foundation on Students Transiting to Tertiary Institutions in Dutsinma, Katsina State

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Abstract

This study examined the management of secondary school curriculum for adequate foundation on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma, Katsina State. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consists of 300 respondents, (50 principals, 150 teachers and 100 second year students of Federal University Dutsinma). The sample size of the study consists of 150, (25 principals, 50 teachers and 75 second year students of Federal University Dutsinma), selected from target population using stratified random sampling techniques. A self-structured Four-Likert questionnaire of 20 items was used to collect the data. The instrument was validated by two experts from Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation, Federal University Dutsinma. The reliability index was 0.67. Frequency and percentages were used to answer the research questions. The findings of the study reveal that adequate strategies were used for teaching. It also reveals that several factors like inadequate teaching facilities and shortage of teachers in some special subject areas were some of factors militating against effective implementation of the curriculum. The study therefore concludes that the management should continue to use the appropriate teaching methods and see how the factors militating against the provision of pragmatic approach in addressing inadequate implementation of the secondary school curriculum could be addressed. The study recommends amongst others that the government should employ, train and retrain teachers and also provide the necessary facilities for easy teaching and learning in schools.

Keyword: Management, curriculum, transiting, adequate foundation.

Introduction

This study examined the management of secondary school curriculum for adequate foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Nigeria. Curriculum is a standard-based sequence of planned experiences where students practice and achieve proficiency in content and applied learning skills. Curriculum is the central guide for all educators as to what is essential for teaching and learning, so that every student has access to rigorous academic experiences. The structure, organization, and considerations in a curriculum are created in order to enhance student learning and facilitate instruction. Curriculum must include the necessary goals, methods, materials and assessments to effectively support instruction and learning. This all-important assignment is implemented by the management and teachers of the school. The researcher therefore anchors his study on the explanation of planning and management during curriculum planning and program implementation, resources necessary, curriculum reform and innovations, counseling and guidance and education to enhance the necessary foundation laying for the students transiting to tertiary institution.

This study examines the role of various stakeholders in the school environment. Curriculum implementation in schools through policy formulation, through planned activities is the core and essential element that creates school business upon which schools' stakeholders interact for the purpose of achieving a common goal of educating the people of any society. There is need to catch up with the changing needs of institutions as well as coping with meeting the challenges of individual reforms that

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looks a daunting task, all of them to be achieved within a limited time frame presents a management challenge that thus requires planning. This is managed through detailed strategy. To create this strategy, the management team has to analyze the current situation by doing a thorough environmental scan and by identifying the gap between the current state and the desired program. To be implemented, the vision of the new program needs to rely on the generation of several potential avenues to come up with optimal solutions, likely involving some form of innovation. Indeed, to come up with the most promising ideas, there needs to be an environment conducive to reflection and experimentation. Throughout the phases of analysis, decision making and implementation, specific activities need to be organized to engage college members. Furthermore, such a profoundly impacting project needs to include a parallel change management strategy to account for expected human resistance, both individual and collective (internal culture). This article proposes a method and several concrete actions to help leaders and managers support the development and implementation of a new and innovative curriculum to promote and support advancement of local professional practice.

Keesing-Style, Nash, and Ayres (2014), posit that organizing a curriculum that would create and lay adequate foundation for students transiting to tertiary institutions, as to meet up with the challenges of the new environment is a very huge challenge. Koster, Schalekamp and Meijerman (2017) stated that the success of foundation laying on students is influenced by several factors, including the current state of the curriculum, the local culture and support from higher management. The main reason why management of curriculum is more challenging is that it involves all personnel working within a college. Moreover, the further the project moves away from known and predictable habits and customs (culture), the more it will bring resistance due to fear, uncertainty, perceived lack of competence and time requirements, amongst others (Keesing-Style, Nash, and Ayres (2014). They continued by stating that laying of foundation on students through curriculum implementation is a human challenge in addition to a technical one and needs to be managed as such. It is a matter of the heart and mind. Failure to address the human aspect and local culture can create a situation where the project cannot be completed as intended. Indeed, there is a saying by Peter Drucker that “culture eats strategy for breakfast”.

Blanchard, Zigarmi, and Zigarmi (2013) posited that because curricular implementation takes such a long-term project, measured by the time it takes to create an impact, plus the time to graduate students moving to tertiary institutions, it should prepare them for current but mainly future challenges, based on insight, experience and a good understanding of where the students are going. In addition, it should incorporate as much pedagogical innovation as possible to make it relevant to the students’ needs and to last for a significant number of years. Going through this lengthy process would suggest more radical changes, a real transformation, rather than tinkering with knowledge and skills by an incremental change (Noble, Shaw, Coombes and O’Brien 2011).

Curricular is a significant tool in realizing the goals of education, and its realization needs a structured long-term direction; it needs a strategy. Bolman and Deal, in Schein and Schein (2017) stated that “a vision without a strategy remains an illusion.” The strategy is the separation between thinking and doing things (Mintzberg, 2020). De Langen (2012) went further to state that it is about choosing a path that is coherent with the vision and with the prevailing culture. Forming a strategy is a process that requires 3 major phases (Johnson 2017). First, one needs to scan the environment, to analyze and diagnose the current situation and the current strategic position, and to identify the drivers for change to develop the vision. Second, one must think of different solutions that have to be compared and contrasted to make the strategic and innovative choices supporting the vision, allowing the gap between the current and the desired state to be bridged. Third, the solutions need to be implemented so that the strategy is converted into action and the curriculum evolves towards the new vision.

According to the well-known Kübler–Ross theory (1969) stated that members of a secondary school will go through a series of emotions during the project, as their level of competence is challenged and they are taken outside their comfort zone. From the current situation, they will start by being in shock, then by expressing denial and frustration and by being depressed. Finally they will experiment, accept, engage in and committed to the new situation. On a long-term project such as curricular implementation, there will be a lot of time spent managing negative emotions until the general feeling returns to a more positive attitude. Constant and consistent communication and reassurance are key during the process. Thus, in parallel to the strategy related to curriculum implementation itself, a second strategy needs to be focused on managing change. This is necessary to give a chance to the project to succeed. Indeed, resistance to change is a normal phenomenon in any project that brings about any form of innovation (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2018). Resistant individuals can use any weakness to derail such a demanding project.

The inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum has been discovered to have so much negative implications on students who are transiting into the various tertiary institutions. These included, failure in examinations, inability to adjust to the new environment, low CGPA in school, lack of appropriate study habits (Alade, 2013), and so on. This

Management of Secondary School... (Nnamdi, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

means that the curriculum implementation strategy has to be convincing, to be based on needs and to propose evidence-based solutions so that it is as robust as possible and cannot be easily dismissed. Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov (2010) stated that in addition, there is the need to be a genuine concern and specific activities to manage change, tailored to the local context and the prevailing societal culture, as some societies are more eager to experiment and others are more conservative. There are a number of changes in management frameworks that can help to prepare for this reality Kotter and Schlesinger (2008) and Hayes (2014). Throughout this article, change management activities that will support the three main steps of forming and implementing the main strategy will be presented. They are mainly based on the 8-step model of change management proposed by (Kotter 1969).

Parallel processes of (1) the curriculum implementation strategy, (2) the change management strategy (Kotter 1969) and (3) the curriculum development steps. Moreau, Al-Taweel, Qaddoumi, and Alowayesh, (2019) further stated that Curriculum development steps can vary, but those described are based on previous experience. Although depicted as linear, from top to bottom, the processes allow for some iterations when downstream steps uncover flaws in upstream assumptions or decisions or when new information becomes available. Communication is important throughout the curriculum implementation. Implementation support team. Embedded in the curriculum and change in management strategies are a series of curriculum development steps that one can follow to obtain the desired goal. This can take many shapes and forms, and it is not the main focus of this article. To illustrate management of a curriculum implementation in a way that is not too abstract, the curricular development steps that have been previously reported would be used (Moreau, Al-Taweel, Qaddoumi, and Alowayesh, 2019). Thus, this article presents the management of an innovative curriculum reform from the higher perspective of strategy formation that includes an embedded change management strategy allowing curriculum development and implementation according to logical steps of curriculum development to enhance solid foundation for students heading to the various tertiary institutions of learning.

Most newly admitted students into the different tertiary institutions find it very difficult to adjust, especially in academic programmes which they enlisted. This is because of the level of foundation acquired in both primary and post-primary institutions. The level of investigations carried out by many scholars have indicated this fact. So many schools do not include reading culture as part of the curriculum. To this effect, so many students do not have the culture of reading on their own which would have increased their understanding horizon as they get into tertiary institutions of their choice. Teaching pedagogy in implementation of the curriculum has also contributed to the poor foundation laying of the students. Choice of programme which the students have little or no background contribute so much to negative performance of students. The study therefore examines the management of secondary school curriculum implementation for adequate foundation on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma LGA, Katsina State.

Objectives of the Study

The major purpose of this study is to examine the management of secondary school's curriculum implementation for adequate foundation on students transiting to the tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area of Katsina State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the management strategies/pedagogy used in curriculum implementation for adequate foundation of students transiting to tertiary institutions Dutsinma Local Government Area.
2. Examine the factors militating against adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area.
3. Examine the impact of the inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum on the foundation on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma Dutsinma Local Government Area.

Research Questions

Three research questions were formulated to guide the study. They are:

1. What are the strategies/pedagogy used by the management in implementing secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma Local Government Area?
2. What are the factors militating against the adequate implementing secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma LGA Local Government Area?
3. What are the perceived impact of the inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma Local Government Area?

Management of Secondary School... (Nnamdi, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Methodology

This study adopted survey research design. Survey research design was appropriate because it sought to dealing and gathering of information from respondents. The population of the study consists of 300 respondents, (50 principals, 150 teachers and 100 second year students of Federal University Dutsinma). The sample size of the study consists of 150, (25 principals, 50 teachers and 75 second year students of Federal University Dutsinma), selected from target population using stratified random sampling techniques. A self-structured Four-Likert questionnaire of 20 items on Management of Secondary School Curriculum Implementation for Adequate Foundation Laying on Students transiting to the Tertiary Institutions (MSSCIAFLSTI) in Dutsinma LGA, was developed and used for data collection for the study. The instrument was validated by two experts from Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation, Federal University Dutsinma. The instrument was assessed to ensure its clarity and the appropriateness of the items. The reliability index was 0.67 using test re-test reliability test. Frequency and percentages were used to answer the research questions. There were two sections of the instrument. Section A consists of the demographic information on the respondents, while section B sought for information on strategies/pedagogy used by school management, factors militating against adequate curriculum implementation and perceived impact of inadequate implementation of the curriculum. This section is also divided into three clusters to take care of the three research questions. The research questions were analyzed frequencies and percentage, while the hypotheses were analyzed using mean and standard deviation.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the strategies/pedagogy used by the management in implementing secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area?

Table 1: Indicates the frequency and percentage of responses of the respondents on the strategies/pedagogy used by the management for adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum in Dutsinma LGA.

S/N	Statement	No. of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Decision
1.	The curriculum content has the adequate information for teaching and learning	150	120	80.0 %	Accepted
2.	There are adequate and competent teachers	150	145	97.0 %	Accepted
3.	Teaching was not made teacher-centered	150	149	99.3 %	Accepted
4.	Teachers use the facilities in teaching	150	135	90.0 %	Accepted
5.	Teachers are acquainted with the modern methods of teaching	150	146	97.3 %	Accepted
6.	The syllabus and the scheme of work are always covered adequately	150	135	90.0 %	Accepted

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage of responses of the respondents on the strategies/pedagogy used by the management for adequate implementations of secondary school curriculum. From the table, it was observed that the items on the table were alluded to by the respondents, indicating that the management was using the appropriate strategies/pedagogy for the adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum to lay solid foundation for the transiting students to tertiary institutions. In line with the above assertion, Keesing-Style, Nash, and Ayres (2014), posited that organizing a curriculum that would create and lay adequate foundation for students transiting to tertiary institutions, as to meet up with the challenges of the new environment is a very huge challenge. Noble, Shaw, Coombes and O'Brien (2011) in addition stated that curriculum implementation should incorporate as much pedagogical innovation as possible to make it relevant to the students' needs and to last for a significant number of years. Going through this lengthy process would suggest more radical changes, a real transformation, rather than tinkering with knowledge and skills by an incremental change.

Research Question Two: What are the factors militating against the adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area?

Management of Secondary School... (Nnamdi, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Table 2: Shows the respondents' responses on the factors militating against adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for the foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma LGA.

S/N	Statement	No. of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Decision
1.	Inadequate qualified teachers to handle the curriculum appropriately	150	105	70.0	Accepted
2.	Lack of teaching aids as indicated in the curriculum for smooth teaching and learning.	150	115	77.0	Accepted
3.	Inadequate laboratories and their facilities	150	123	82.0	Accepted
4.	Inadequate library and its facilities	150	125	83.3	Accepted
5.	Teachers' method of teaching	150	68	45.3	Not Accepted
6.	Students' study habits	150	139	93.0	Accepted

From table 2 above, it was observed that the respondents asserted to the fact that several factors militate against adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for the foundation laying of students transiting to tertiary institutions, except item 5 that disagreed to this allusion. In line with this agreement, Koster, Schalekamp and Meijerman (2017) stated that the success of foundation laying on students is influenced by several factors, including the current state of the curriculum, the local culture and support from higher management. The main reason why management of curriculum is more challenging is that it involves all personnel working within a college.

Research Question Three: What are the perceived impact of the inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area?

Table Three: Shows the responses of the respondents on the perceived impact of the inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for the foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma LGA?

S/N	Statement	No. of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Decision
1.	Leads to failure in SSCE WAEC and NECO examinations	150	128	85.3	Accepted
2.	Leads to examination malpractice	150	146	97.3	Accepted
3.	Takes time for students to adjust in tertiary institutions	150	131	87.3	Accepted
4.	Inability to understand the system as new students to a new environment	150	127	85.0	Accepted
5.	May lack the appropriate study habit	150	93	62.0	Accepted
6.	May lead to joining bad peers	150	89	59.3	Accepted
7.	Students may be scoring low CGPA	150	138	92.0	Accepted
8.	Could lead to final withdrawal or dropout from school	150	127	85.0	Accepted

Table 3 shows responses of the respondents on the perceived impact of inadequate implementation of the secondary school curriculum on students transiting to tertiary institution. The respondent asserted to the fact that those students who are inadequately prepared face so much challenges in tertiary institutions of their choice. In line with the above, Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov (2010) stated that there is the need to be a genuine concern and specific activities to manage change, tailored to the local context and the prevailing societal culture, as some societies are more eager to experiment and others are more conservative. There are a number of change in management frameworks that can help to prepare for this reality to avert inadequacies in school in implementation of the school curriculum. Kotter and Schlesinger (2008) and Hayes (2014).

Discussion of findings

The research question one sought to examine the strategies/pedagogies used in managing the implementation of secondary school curriculum on the students transiting tertiary institutions. From the frequency and percentage table, it was observed that the items on the table were alluded to by the respondents, indicating that the management was using the correct strategies/pedagogy for the adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum to lay solid foundation for the transiting students to tertiary institutions. Keesing-Style, Nash, and Ayres (2014), supported this findings by positing that organizing a

Management of Secondary School... (Nnamdi, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

curriculum that would create and lay adequate foundation for students transiting to tertiary institutions, as to meet up with the challenges of the new environment is a very huge challenge.

The major findings of research question two asserted that so many factors militate against inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum on students transiting to the tertiary institutions. It was found that these factors which included inadequate qualified teachers, inadequate laboratory and its facilities, libraries, reading culture, etc., have created so much barriers on the students transiting to tertiary institutions. Koster, Schalekamp and Meijerman (2017) stated that the success of foundation laying on students is influenced by several factors, including the current state of the curriculum, the local culture and support from higher management. The main reason why management of curriculum is more challenging is that it involves all personnel working within a college.

The findings on research question three revealed that, there are so many perceived impact due to the inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum on students' academic performance in Dutsinma Local Government Area of Katsina State. This was observed as alluded to by the respondents in table 3 above. This findings agree with Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov (2010) stated that there should be the need to be a genuinely concern and specific activities to manage the change in curriculum implementation, tailored to the local context and the prevailing societal culture, as some societies are more eager to experiment and others are more conservative.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn based on the findings of the study. The findings concluded that the management were using the appropriate strategies/pedagogy for the adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum to lay solid foundations for the transiting students to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area. It was evident and also discussed that there were so many factors militating against adequate implementation of the secondary school curriculum in Dutsinma Local Government area of Katsina State. These factors include inadequate qualified teachers, teaching aids and other facilitating materials, lack of laboratories and libraries and their facilities and so on affect effective implementation of secondary school curriculum and hence affects learning outcome of students transiting into tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government area of Katsina State. The findings further concluded that these inadequacies in the curriculum implementation have resulted to increase in examination malpractice, mass failure in undergraduate courses of the first year students, resulting to low CGPA and finally lead to probation and subsequently advised to withdraw from the University.

Recommendations

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Adequate and competent qualified teachers should be employed in both secondary and tertiary levels of education in Nigeria;
2. Training and retraining of teachers should always be carried out to handle the new innovations in the curriculum for smooth and adequate implementation;
3. Libraries and laboratories and their facilities always be made available;
4. Provision of the appropriate teaching aids for easy teaching and learning should be made available by the appropriate agents;
5. Teachers should always be motivated;
6. The facilities so provided should be monitored and managed appropriately; and
7. Appropriate teaching methods should always be used on each subject and topics to prepare students transiting to tertiary institutions.

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Comparative Analysis of Social... (Bassey, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Comparative Analysis of Social Protection Intervention and Early Child Marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State.

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Abstract

The paper titled comparative analysis of social protection intervention and early child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State explored the nexus between social protection and multiple drivers of child marriage. 3 research questions were formulated which were translated to 3 hypotheses thus: Increasing school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour has no significant relationship with child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area; sustainable household income support through cash /asset transfer has no significant relationship with child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area and civil Society Organization's child protection service has no significant with early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area. The descriptive survey design approach was adopted. The sample for this study consisted of 400 respondents selected through the use of Taro Yamene's (1967) formula. The multi stage sampling procedure was used to select the sample of the study. A 4 likert scale questionnaire was the instrument for data collection and Chi square was for analysis. Findings revealed that social protection intervention have significant moderating and modulating influences on early child marriage. It was concluded that early marriage serves as a threat to a child's future development because it is difficult to have access to quality education and higher education and it limits the ability to secure a good job. Thus, it recommended amongst others that policy makers should improve social welfare for girls especially promoting school enrollment for them to pursue education

Keyword: Social protection Intervention, Early child marriage, Increased school enrollment

Introduction

Child marriage happens in all parts of the world and is not associated with any particular culture or religion. It is rooted in harmful gender norms and discrimination against girls and women. It is not a single phenomenon and covers a wide range of relationship types, each with its own causes and drivers, risks and preventive factors that often vary depending on setting and circumstance. Depending on the specific manifestations of child marriage, it may be seen as a manifestation of violence against children, sexual and gender-based violence, child trafficking or sexual slavery and other exploitative practices. Although voluntary unions between consenting adolescents are common in some areas. When marriages are forced, take place without the consent of the child, and are the result of physical or emotional pressure, they are regarded as a form of violence against children that disproportionately exposes girls to physical, sexual and emotional violence that must be prevented or responded to. (UNICEF, 2017)

In some jurisdictions, marriages of this kind are recognized as a form of violence that requires safeguarding and the intervention of child protection authorities. Voluntary early unions are commonly attributed to a lack of opportunities for young people or a negative coping strategy in response to economic hardships. In light of these explanations, in many cases, they may reflect a lack of options rather than a true choice. Child marriage is a violation of human rights. It has severe negative consequences for girls and women– including for their health, development, power, participation and safety – and for wider

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society including reduced economic growth.^{1,2} Child marriage prevalence has declined globally over the past 30 years, but progress has been uneven and too slow to meet the Sustainable Development Goal of ending the practice by 2030.^{3,4} In addition, 10 million more girls are predicted to marry by 2030 due to the social and economic impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic (UNFPA-UNICEF, 2020)

Child protection is grounded in children’s rights and works for the protection of all girls and boys from birth to adulthood. The best interests of the child are a primary concern and require that child protection approaches are age-appropriate, recognize children’s evolving capacities and are tailored to the specific child marriage risks experienced by girls and boys of different ages. Protection risks increase in forced marriages, for girls married to older men, younger adolescent girls, pregnant adolescent girls, adolescent mothers, and for adolescents who are divorced or separated. Boys are also subject to forced marriage – although in lower numbers –and their needs and interests should also be addressed in child protection interventions. Child protection supports children’s rights to information, expression and involvement in the decisions that affect them, so they can better protect themselves (CEDAN & UNCRC, 2014).

Child protection goes beyond stand-alone sector-specific and issue-based approaches to child wellbeing. Child protection systems, services and approaches at community and district levels are designed to prevent and respond to all forms of abuse, violence and exploitation of children, including child marriage. Child protective response services go beyond prevention to ensure that the most vulnerable children are protected. This includes the provision of comprehensive services for girls who are married, pregnant and mothers, including safety and protection, health and psychosocial care, education, economic support, and justice (UNICEF, 2011).

While some boys marry before the age of 18, the vast majority of children who marry are girls, often against their will and with grave consequences. It is recognized that ending child marriage involves tackling the many challenges that perpetuate this rights violation, such as gender inequality and discrimination, lack of education, and poverty. Also, support for development and participation of adolescent girls, strengthening legal systems to protect the rights of adolescent boys and girls; carrying out cutting-edge research to build a robust evidence base for advocacy, policies, programmes and tracking progress ;strengthening services to help adolescents at risk of, or affected by, child marriage, particularly girls, and raising awareness of the need to invest in and support girls, and shifting the social expectations that stifle their prospects.

Child marriage happens in all parts of the world and is not associated with any particular culture or religion. It is rooted in harmful gender norms and discrimination against girls and women. It is not a single phenomenon and covers a wide range of relationship types, each with its own causes and drivers, risks and preventive factors that often vary depending on setting and circumstance. Evidence shows that effective approaches must be tailored to the specific contexts in which girls, boys and families live (Stoner, 2019) Depending on the specific manifestations of child marriage, it may be seen as a manifestation of violence against children, sexual and gender-based violence, child trafficking or sexual slavery and other exploitative practices. Although voluntary unions between consenting adolescents are common in some areas, when marriages are forced to take place without the consent of the child and are the result of physical or emotional pressure, they are regarded as a form of violence against children that disproportionately exposes girls to physical, sexual and emotional violence that must be prevented or responded to. In some jurisdictions, marriages of this kind are recognized as a form of violence that requires safeguarding and the intervention of child protection authorities (Handa, 2014).

The best interests of the child are a primary concern and require that child protection approaches are age-appropriate, recognize children’s evolving capacities and are tailored to the specific child marriage risks experienced by girls and boys of different ages. Protection risks increase in forced marriages, for girls married to older men, younger adolescent girls, pregnant adolescent girls, adolescent mothers, and for adolescents who are divorced or separated (Wodon, 2018). Boys are also subject to forced marriage – although in lower numbers – and their needs and interests should also be addressed in child protection interventions. Child protection supports children’s rights to information, expression and involvement in the decisions that affect them, so they can better protect themselves. Child protection is critical to realizing the wellbeing and rights of girls and boys. It is an essential operational and conceptual perspective that must be included in comprehensive approaches to prevent and respond to child marriage (UNICEF 2020)

According to UNICEF (2011) early marriage better known as child marriage is defined as marriage carried below the age 18 years before the girl is physically, physiologically and psychologically ready to shoulder the responsibilities of marriage and child bearing. Early marriage also means the individual becomes sexually active early, raising children while children themselves. The marriage of a young girl affects not only her life but the life of the children she will bear. According to AGHI (2003), both boys and girls are affected by child marriage but the issue impacts more negatively on girls in far larger number, with more intensity and is wide ranging. Child marriage is practiced with the belief that it reduces promiscuity among girls.

Comparative Analysis of Social... (Bassey, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

This is purely because of the importance attached to virginity. Often time's husbands want their wives to be virgins and for their parents, it is a great honour for their daughters to be found virgins by their husbands, and so girls are marriage off long before they attain maturity (Greene, 2015).

Where the system fails to work in the best interests of the child and is not gender-sensitive, it may cause further harm – in alternative dispute resolution systems where families negotiate to be compensated for their child having been raped, for example. In such contexts, the rights of girls and women are often overlooked in favour of male-dominated community-level conflict resolution. Like all adults working with children, child protection actors have an obligation to safeguard boys and girls in their care and to ensure that interventions and services do not harm them and are in their best interests. This requires mechanisms that protect children – in care homes, safe houses or shelters for girls at risk of child marriage – from further violence from the very people and institutions who should be keeping them safe (Gong, 2019).

Girls Not Brides (2020) has developed a 'Theory of Change on Child Marriage' to articulate what an effective response to child marriage entails. The Theory of Change outlines the range of approaches needed, demonstrates how they intersect and aims to provide a basis for identifying common indicators that could be used by diverse practitioners to monitor progress. The Theory of Change has been developed to facilitate greater partnership and collaboration among and across organizations, sectors and levels. It serves as a foundation to build consensus about actions needed to address child marriage and support married girls, in both the long and short-term. In addition, it provides a basis to understand where programming efforts are currently focused, in particular among Girls Not Brides members, and to highlight where further work is needed. In this sense, the Theory of Change offers both a mirror and a target (Girls Not Bride, 2016).

The majority of strategies to address child marriage fall within these categories: increasing school enrollment to offset the time spent participating in domestic labour, sustainable household economic support through cash/asset transfer; Civil Society Organizations' empowering services. The three strategies are interlinked and mutually reinforcing; addressing child marriage will require a combination of actions related to all three. The specific combinations will be context-specific and depend on the drivers of child marriage in a given region. Activities are needed to empower girls and enable them to exercise their rights, for example through programmes which equip girls with training, skills, information, as well as the provision of safe spaces and support networks. Recognizing that girls are rarely the decision makers when it comes to child marriage, and that child marriage is often a deeply rooted practice in many communities, work is needed by CSOs with families and communities to create awareness of the harmful impact of child marriage, and of alternative roles for girls and women, so that families and communities prefer not to marry their daughters as children and so that they themselves engage in efforts to end the practice

Globally, the prevalence of child marriage is on a downward trajectory, falling from 51 percent in 1955 to 40 percent in 1990. However, the growth of the world's adolescent population from 400 million in 1950 to 1.2 billion in 2010 means that the sheer number of married girls or girls at risk of being married at an early age is greater than at any point in history. More than one third of the world's adolescent population resides in countries that are hot spots for child marriage, 338 million in South Asia and 94 million in West and Central Africa. While data on child marriage rates vary according to sources, most researchers agree that the problem is worse than it appears as the practice is generally underreported (UNFPA-UNICEF, 2020).

Once married, a girl's world narrows dramatically. Child brides experience isolation from their family, friends and communities, as well as violence, abuse and exploitation. Girls who marry early often become pregnant while they are still children themselves, with great risks for their own well-being and that of their babies. There are clear links between child marriage and school drop-out with girls who are married before the age of 18 less likely to be in school than their peers, and girls who drop out of school more likely to be married. Child marriage – a marriage or union before the age 18 – has a disproportionate impact on girls. It curtails their education, compromises their health, exposes them to violence and traps them in poverty, undermining their prospects and potential (Wodon, 2017).

Child marriages in parts of Europe and Central Asia may reflect a hardening of gender attitudes that reinforce stereotypical roles for girls and limit their opportunities. Child marriage is often linked to patriarchal attitudes towards girls, including the need to safeguard family honour. Evidence suggests that child marriage increases during times of crisis with disproportionate negative impacts on girls. COVID-19, for instance, posed unique challenges. UNFPA estimates that an additional 13 million child marriages take place and society risks losing some of the substantial progress made against goals to reduce child marriage, particularly when we consider the likely impact of global school closures. Experience from other pandemics suggests that getting girls back into school is particularly challenging, with knock-on effects on child marriage (Stoner, 2019).

Comparative Analysis of Social... (Bassey, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Recent World Bank analysis suggests that close to 7 million students from primary up to secondary education could drop out due to income shock related to COVID-19 alone. Whilst gender inequality is a root cause of child marriage, increased economic stresses, and family fears about the risks of violence against girls can also be drivers, particularly in times of crisis. Social protection can play a critical role in reducing income insecurity and enabling girls and boys to access education, two key pathways for delaying marriage. Yet few programmes deliberately and directly target child marriage in their objectives, activities or monitoring and evaluation of results. The current evidence base on child marriage is mixed, leading social workers to voice concerns about social protection (Muchomba, 2021). This study explored: What is the current evidence base on the role of social protection in preventing child marriage, and where are the gaps in knowledge? How can social protection address child marriage, and what programme design characteristics might support better results in this area, particularly for adolescent girls? What can we learn from current child marriage programming and how can we make more effective links between child marriage, child protection, and social protection programming?

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the significant relationship between increasing school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour and child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.
2. To investigate the relationship between sustainable household economic support through cash/asset transfer and early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.
3. To examine the significant relationship existing between Civil Society Organization's child protection services and child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does increasing school enrollment to offset time spent participating in domestic labour significantly relate with early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.?
2. How does sustainable household economic support through cash/asset transfer significantly relate with early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.?
3. How do Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) child protection service significantly relate with early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.?

Study hypotheses

1. Increasing school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour has no significant relationship with child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.
2. Sustainable household income support through cash /asset transfer has no significant relationship with child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.
3. Civil Society Organization's child protection service has no significant with early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was used. This study was carried out in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. The Local Government Area has a total of twelve (12) wards. Calabar South is in the southern part of Cross River State. Calabar South is located between longitude 8.341701 N and latitude 4.975716 E of the Greenwich Meridian. It has a landmark of 264km² and lies 4 meters above sea level. Calabar South has an estimated population of 291,700 from the 2022 population projection (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022).

Sample Size/ Sampling Techniques

The sample for the study was made up of 400 respondents (registered mothers) selected from 12 wards of Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. The sample comprised people living or staying in this local government area ranging from farmers, traders/business persons civil servants.

The researcher adopted the multi stage sampling technique in the study. The 12 wards constituted the 12 strata of the study. However, 1/8th of the strata was studied. This translated into 8 wards. These constituted the 8 clusters. To select the actual respondents, the systematic sampling technique was adopted. This involved enumerating all the houses in the clusters into even and odd numbers. The researcher studied even numbered houses. However, the researcher was particularly concerned with girls- mothers with or without children. Therefore, the purposive technique was adopted to study 50 respondents in each cluster. Through this method, a total of 50 respondents was selected per cluster. Therefore, the overall total number of respondents who participated in the study was 400. A 4 likert scale questionnaire that was put through validity and reliability test was used to elicit data from the respondents while chi square was used for the analysis.

Comparative Analysis of Social... (Bassey, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Ethical Consideration

A high level of ethical conduct was maintained throughout the research study. In particular was the fact that respondents were not compelled to take part in the research study

Presentation of Results

The analysis was based on 375 properly completed questionnaire. This represented 93.75 percent of total respondent.

Hypothesis 1: Increasing school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour has no significant association with child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. Chi-square (X^2) was employed to test data at 0.05 level of significant.

Table 1: Contingency table showing the association between increasing school enrollment and early child marriage.

Cell	O	E	O – E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
1	205	190.67	14.33	205.3489	1.08
2	120	134.33	-14.33	205.3489	1.53
3	15	29.33	-14.33	205.3489	7.00
4	35	20.67	14.33	205.3489	9.93
Total	375				19.54

Field survey, 2024

Calculated (x^2) value	=	19.54
Critical (x^2) value	=	3.84
Level of significance	=	0.05
Degree of freedom	=	1

The result in Table 1 showed that the calculated (x^2) value of 19.54 is higher than critical (x^2) value of 3.84, 0.05 level of significance with 1degree of freedom. This result therefore implies that increasing school enrollment has a significant association with early child marriage.

Hypothesis 2: Sustainable household income support through cash /asset transfer has no significant association with early child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. Chi-square (X^2) was employed to test data collected at 0.05 level of significant.

Table 2: Contingency table showing the association between sustainable household income support through cash/asset transfer and early child marriage

	O	E	O – E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
1	190	165.09	24.91	620.5081	3.76
2	112	136.91	-24.91	620.5081	4.53
3	15	39.91	-24.91	620.5081	15.10
4	58	33.09	24.91	620.5081	18.75
Total	375				42.14

Field survey, 2024

Calculated (x^2) value	=	42.14
Critical (x^2) value	=	3.84
Level of significance	=	0.05
Degree of freedom	=	1

Results in table 3 show calculated (x^2) value of 42.14 is more than critical (x^2) of 3.84 at 0.05 significance level with 1 degree of freedom. The result therefore implies that sustainable household income support through cash/asset transfer has a significant association with early child marriage in the study area.

Hypothesis 3

Hypothesis three stated that Civil Society Organization’s child protection service has no significant association with early child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Comparative Analysis of Social... (Bassey, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Table 3: Contingency table showing the association between Civil Society Organisation’s child protection service and early child marriage

Cell	O	E	O – E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
1	130	106.6	23.4	547.56	5.14
2	75	98.4	-23.4	547.56	5.56
3	65	88.4	-23.4	547.56	6.19
4	105	81.6	23.4	547.57	6.71
Total	375				23.60

Field survey, 2024

Calculated (x ²) value	=	23.60
Critical (x ²) value	=	3.84
Level of significance	=	0.05
Degree of freedom	=	1

The result shows calculated (x²) value of 23.60 is more than critical (x²) value of 3.84 needed at 0.05 level of significance with 1 degree of freedom. The result therefore implies that Civil Society Organization’s child protection service has significant association with early child marriage in the study area.

Discussion of Findings

Increasing girls’ school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour and early child marriage

The analysis implies the existence of a significant association between increasing school enrollment to offset time spent participating in domestic labour impacts on child marriage. According to Misunes, Gaston and Cappa (2015) education for girls is one of the best strategies for protecting girls against child marriage. When they are able to stay in school and avoid being married early, girls can build a foundation for a better life for themselves and their families. And if they have already been married young, access to education, economic opportunities and health services—including HIV prevention and sexual and reproductive health— help enrich their lives and enhance their future (Greene 2015). Despite security challenges, the education sector plans in six north-west Nigerian states led to a significant increase in girls’ enrollment in secondary schools and a reduction in the percentage of girls married before the age of 18, a new report has shown. It further pointed to an intersectionality between the two outcome indicators – enrollment and early marriage. Jigawa State, with the highest increase in enrollment for girls at the basic education level, was also the state with the second most significant reduction in the age of marriage. Conversely, Kaduna State, which experienced the lowest change in enrollment rates for girls within the same period, also experienced the least change in the age of marriage for girls among the six states

The findings support Okeke (2004) that in traditional African society, the role of the female was pegged and circumscribed. It was considered a taboo sending a female to school. This is because of the attitude towards education for women. It was considered a waste of money, time and effort considering that most women in no time get married into another family, to raise the children that serve as farm hands for their father. In addition to raising the children for the man, the women still helped to keep the house and provide meal for all. Hence the saying some years back that women’s education ends in the kitchen. This primitive attitude exposes women to early marriage (Okeke, 2004; Ocho, 1988).

As observed by Gong (2019), progress has been limited, particularly in West Africa, one of the world’s child marriage hot spots. Five of the 10 countries with the highest rates of child marriage worldwide are in West Africa. In 2011, of 14.9 million females in West Africa between the ages of 20 and 24 years, 6.2 million, or 42 percent, were married before the age of 18.3 With 167 million people, Nigeria has the largest population of married girls in Africa: 39.4 percent of all females in Nigeria between the ages of 20 to 24 were married before the age of 18 by 2011. Education for girls is one of the best strategies for protecting girls against child marriage. When they are able to stay in school and avoid being married early, girls can build a foundation for a better life for themselves and their families. And if they have already been married young, access to education, economic opportunities and health services—including HIV prevention and sexual and reproductive health— help enrich their lives and enhance their future.

Sustainable household income support through cash /asset transfer and early child marriage

The analysis shows a significant association between sustainable household income support through cash transfer and child marriage. Social protection especially cash transfer programmes – can play a role in mitigating some of the economic and social drivers of child marriage in both development and humanitarian contexts. Poverty and economic insecurity are closely

Comparative Analysis of Social... (Bassey, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

linked with child marriage, but create different incentives for marriage depending on local marriage practices and norms. These practices and norms affect how a cash transfer may impact on the timing of marriage. Improved household economic security is possible with cash transfer (Gong 2019). By increasing a household's ability to meet their basic needs, cash transfers can reduce pressure on families to shift economic responsibility for a girl to her husband's household, especially when a bride price is expected. They can also reduce girls' own motivation to seek economic security through marriage or high-risk sexual relationships. Cash transfers can reduce the risk of child marriage and early sexual debut by keeping girls in school for longer, especially where married girls are excluded from school. In addition, girls who spend longer in school can gain more knowledge and skills, and raise aspirations, empowering them to make (or to influence) decisions to marry later and support later marriage for their own children (Handa, 2014)

Findings support Muchomba (2021) that cash transfers can mitigate several of the economic and social drivers of child marriage through different pathways. Conditional cash transfers (CCT) play an important role in keeping girls in school and are most consistent at reducing the risk of child marriage across marriage contexts. They counteract family and social pressures to marry, and reduce the risk of self-initiated unions and pre-marital sexual relationships that may lead to pregnancy and marriage. Unconditional cash transfers (UCT) are often effective at increasing access to school and in protecting against early and high-risk sex, but this does not generally reduce child marriage. This is partly because the girls whose families choose to use UCTs to help them stay in school are already at lower risk of child marriage. However, cash transfers can alleviate the economic pressures to marry or form a union in some circumstances (Muchomba, 2021).

Malhotra and Elnakib (2021) documented that programmes in Malawi and the Philippines show that the impact of both UCTs and CCTs on household economic security can reduce the risk of child marriage, especially where social norms for child marriage are weaker, poverty is a main driver, and transfers are regular and predictable. This is likely because CCTs incentivise school attendance among girls who are at risk of child marriage, while UCTs may only support attendance among girls who are already at lower risk of marriage. There is also evidence – from Bangladesh and Malawi – that by supporting girls to gain knowledge and raise their aspirations, cash transfers that increase educational attainment can empower them to make (or to influence) decisions to delay marriage. The Bangladesh Development Society and Save the Children implemented Kishoree Kontha – “Adolescent Girl's Voice” – is one of the largest adolescent empowerment programmes ever implemented in low-income countries. Activities: Communities identified safe spaces where girls could meet five to six days a week to socialize and access educational support and social competency training. In half of the empowerment communities, the programme also included financial literacy training. The conditional incentive programme delivered cooking oil to families with unmarried girls aged 15 to 17. Community volunteers distributed ration cards to these girls at the start of the programme. Every four months between April 2008 and August 2010, girls who remained unmarried could collect cooking oil by presenting their ration card to community volunteers at a distribution point in the community, who would then confirm the girls' marital status with other community members. The value of the oil was approximately US\$16 per year, an amount chosen to offset the estimated increase in dowry for every additional year a girl remains unmarried (Malhotra & Elnakib, 2021).

Four years after the programme ended, a study was conducted of all girls who were unmarried and aged 15 to 17 at the beginning of the programme. Parents were asked about daughters' current marital status, childbearing history and school enrolment. Researchers found that: The conditional incentives led to a significant reduction in child marriage and adolescent childbearing, and increased educational attainment. The empowerment programme increased educational attainment but did not affect child marriage or adolescent childbearing. Taken together, these results suggest that a conditional incentive for families of adolescent girls can lead to substantial reductions in child marriage and adolescent childbearing in a setting with high rates of child marriage. Unlike incentives conditional on schooling which only focus on girls in schools, this incentive programme – in which marriage was the conditionality – also had positive effects for out-of-school girls (Handa, 2014).

Civil Society Organization's child protection services and early child marriage

Analysis revealed that civil society organization's services are significantly associated with child marriage. As admitted by Misunas, Gaston and Cappa (2019) scaling up child protection systems that prevent and respond to child marriage requires much larger allocations of public resources. CSOs can play an important role in tracking spending and advocating to governments to allocate larger budgets to finance child protection systems, including for an expanded and better-trained social service workforce. The Global Programme to End Child Marriage ('the Global Programme') aims to have a catalytic effect and works with many partners to advocate for and support practical actions to end child marriage, and promote gender equality and the rights of adolescent girls (Misunas, Gaston & Cappa, 2019). CSOs carry out advocacy and capacity building for local communal authorities to integrate child protection budget lines into communal budgets. Promoting the agency of young people

Comparative Analysis of Social... (Bassey, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

and civil society in those communities to gain knowledge of child rights-sensitive budgeting and to hold local authorities accountable with regards to child protection-related budget lines, including on child marriage (Misuna et al, 2019).

CSOs continually and consciously educate, sensitize and create public awareness on the effects and risk relating to child marriage. They raise public awareness and campaigns to end child marriage using the media/ social media, outreaches at mosques, churches and communities. Public sensitization takes place in both the urban and rural areas. Furthermore, CSOs educate citizens on the health effects of early and forced marriage. Young girls who have been victims are able to share their experiences with other young girls, families and people in the communities. Public awareness creation, campaigns, education and sensitization focus on educating the citizens to change their perceptions, behaviours and attitudes towards girls and women in the society. Moreover, during these sensitization activities, laws regarding child rights issues and their sexuality are articulated (The Alliance for Child Protection in Humanitarian Action 2020). CSOs take interest in schooling on the legal age of marriage and the fact that marrying young girls before the legal age is a criminal offence punishable by law. CSOs intensify advocacy for policy reforms and comprehensive legislation that promote child rights and protection. Activists also advocate for the clarification of ambiguous legislations between religious, customary and civil marriages. They sometimes demand the official registration of all marriages and advocate for law enforcement in communities. In addition, CSOs campaign for the same minimum legal age of marriage for both female and male. At both national and local levels, CSOs organize fora with all stakeholders supportive of ending child marriage and raise awareness among them on the state of early and forced marriage in the country and the need to address it by embarking on policy reforms that seek to empower girls (CEDAW & UNCRC, 2014). Findings support UNICEF (2017) that CSOs provide service support interventions for adolescent girls, survivors, child wives and the family. Poverty is one underlying cause of child marriage globally. CSOs' supportive interventions seek to empower girls so they become economically equipped to be independent. Basic and secondary education should be accessible to young girls while child marriage victims/ survivors should be reintegrated into the educational system or in vocational training institutes. The creation of adolescent-friendly health services and youth counselling centres in local communities where the youth can get information about their reproductive health issues and support will be invaluable in bridging the information gap.

Conclusion

Child marriage happens in all parts of the world and is not associated with any particular culture or religion. A greater percentage of women in developing countries married before their 18th birthday. Early marriage serves as a threat to a child's future development. This is because it is difficult to have access to quality education and higher education and it limits the ability to secure a good job. Also, girls involved in early marriage face poverty conditions. Therefore, social protection can play a critical role in reducing income insecurity and enabling girls to access education; two key pathways for delaying child marriage. There is a broader evidence that social protection such as increasing girls' school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour, sustainable household income support through cash /asset transfer and Civil Society Organization's child protection services can often have protective impacts.

Recommendations

Based on this empirical evidence:

1. It is critical that girls should have options aside from marriage and motherhood
2. Social protection should be viewed as necessary conditions for addressing some (but not all) of the drivers of child marriage
3. The policy makers should be encouraged to improve social welfare for girls especially promoting school enrollment for them to pursue education, cash and stipends can help them in school too.
4. The Federal Ministry of Women Affairs and Civil Society Organizations (government and Non-government sectors) should evolve strategies to facilitate sustainable response to end child marriage and all the associated ills.

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Managing Threats... (Muhammad & Ladan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Managing Threats to Internal Validity in Quantitative and Qualitative Research: Some Basic Considerations

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Abstract

The main thrust of the paper was to examine factors that can pose threat to internal validity in both Qualitative and Quantitative research. In order to accomplish this task, the concept of validity and its various types such as content, construct and criterion-related validity were analyzed. The paper also highlighted some factors to be considered in order to achieve internal validity in both quantitative and qualitative research methods namely Maturation, Testing, Instrumentation and History among others. Although the paper acknowledged impossibility of eliminating totally the threats to internal validity especially when research is conducted outside the laboratory setting; it is the position of the paper that, good understanding and knowledge of the threats or factors that can jeopardize internal validity as highlighted in this paper can help to mitigate those threats to a minimum level and enhance the quality of the instruments and of course findings. On the basis of this conclusion, the paper suggested among other things on the need to consider the time of experiment, the use of a control group, selected from the same population as the experimental group and which experiences the same concurrent history as the experimental group are very important strategies for reducing threats to internal validity.

Keyword: validity, internal validity, validity of measurement and experimental validity

Introduction

As a scientific activity, research is a search for knowledge which is embarked upon to come with findings leading to answer to question (s), development of theory or solution to a problem. For this reason, Alarape, (2012) Research is manipulations of things, concept or symbol for the purpose of generalizing extend, correct or verify knowledge, whether that knowledge aids in construction of theory or in the practice of an art. In research, information is collected to verify and generalize findings through the use of designs and various different measuring instruments namely: Questionnaire, Interview and observation among others. However, the quality of the findings and inferences made is affected by certain psychometric qualities and Validity is one of the important qualities that a good measuring instrument (test, questionnaire, observation) must possess. In line with this, Singh, (2014) noted that Validity and reliability increase transparency, and decrease opportunities to insert researcher bias in qualitative research.

The concept of Validity which is of interest to this paper is of different types and it can be applied to two areas of research: validity of measurement and validity of findings. The former, deals with those types of validity such as content validity and construct validity that are concerned with the measuring instruments, while the latter, has to do with internal and external validity of the research design. It is often associated with the experimental designs where the researcher often manipulates one variable (independent) to see its' effects on another variable (dependent).

However, one pertinent question to ask is; can the researcher confidently attribute the observed changes or differences in the dependent variable to the independent variable? This question raises the issue of internal validity. Establishing this type of validity in research serves as a herculean task to especially novice researchers. In view of this, Zainal (2017) asserts that novice researchers often face challenges such as management of extraneous variables, maintaining treatment fidelity and limited resources in an attempt to establish internal validity in research. These and other factors have to be kept under control because it is only when they properly managed can the researcher attribute the cause and effect of one variable to another.

Managing Threats... (Muhammad & Ladan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Sharma (2019) acknowledged the gravity of the threats of internal validity in survey which according to him is associated with challenges such as inadequate research design, insufficient pilot testing as well as measurement errors and biases.

The challenges of establishing internal validity are even more enormous in Qualitative research which is the method favoured by Subjectivists (naturalists) in the study of human behavior. In sociological research, these problems and many others raise the question of credibility which is concerned with the truthfulness of the research findings or how well the researcher has established confidence in research based on the method used. Indeed, according to Lawal & Ladan (2023) the Positivists (Quantitative research method) who are the antagonist of Subjectivists (Qualitative research method), pointed out that because Qualitative as a research method deals with subjective assessment of the phenomena being studied in natural setting, achieving internal validity or credibility is difficult if not impossible.

Therefore, against the background of difficulties and threats in establishing internal validity in both Qualitative and Quantitative research, this paper among other issues highlighted certain basic considerations in managing the threats to the internal validity.

Conceptual Clarification

The concepts of Qualitative and Quantitative research as well as the concept of Validity are central in this discussion and thus explained.

Qualitative Research

Qualitative research is concerned with subjective assessment of attitudes, opinions and behavior. Research in such situations is a function of researcher's insight and impressions. It generates results either in non-quantifiable form or in the form which are not subjected to rigorous quantitative analysis. In other words, data is not necessarily expressed in numbers; rather it is presented in form of words. As noted by Okeshola cited in Lawal & Ladan (2023) Qualitative research uses unreconstructed logic to get at what is really real-quality, meaning, context or image of reality in what people actually do, not what they say they do. In addition, qualitative research according to Denzin and Lincoln (2014) implies an emphasis on the qualities of entities and on processes and meanings that are not experimentally examined or measured (if measured at all) in terms of quantity, amount, intensity, or frequency.

Quantitative Research

Quantitative research involves generation of data in quantitative form which can be subjected to rigorous statistical analysis. It entails the collection of data in numbers. Obasi cited in Lawal & Ladan (2023) defined quantitative research as an aspect of the scientific method that investigates phenomena that are amenable to empirical measurement and verification. This means examining variables that can be assigned figures or values which can be empirically observed. The Quantitative procedure of assigning figures is different from Qualitative research which deals with detail description of phenomena being studied.

Validity

Validity is an important determinant of the quality of any measuring instrument. A review of various definitions of Validity from different literatures reveals that the concept of validity is defined by different authors in almost similar perspectives. For example, Kauru (2015) defines Validity as the degree to which the tool measures what it claims to measure while Kamar (2017) stated that, validity means the accuracy with which a test measures what it intends to or supposed to measure. Similarly, Validity can also refer to the ability of measuring instrument to measure truly and accurately the quality or ability it is designed to measure. In other words, a measuring instrument is said to be valid, when it measures truly and accurately the quality or ability it is designed to measure. This means that a test that is designed to test achievement should do just that and nothing else. Middleton (2023) explained that Validity along with Reliability are the two concepts that are utilized to measure the quality of research. Validity in research therefore deals with the extent to which research instrument measure what it is supposed to measure. Thus, one important thing clear from the above definitions is that, the concept of validity is defined in relation to measuring tool, instrument or test. However, validity can also be defined or viewed in relation to Research Design. For instance, according to Asika cited in Lawal and Ladan (2023), a research design may be said to be valid if it enables a researcher to elicit the correct responses from the sample subjects, otherwise it can be regarded as faulty design and may not lead to correct outcomes.

There are different types of validity which can be applied to different areas of research. It is in line with this that Asika cited in Lawal and Ladan (2023), maintained that, the concept of validity can be applied in two areas of research: validity of measurement and validity of findings or experimental validity. Validity of measurement is ability of the measuring instrument to measure what it is supposed to measure. In relation to this, Kamar (2017) observed that there are three major types of validity

Managing Threats... (Muhammad & Ladan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

that are commonly used in educational and psychological measurements. These are namely: Content Validity, Criterion-related validity and Construct validity.

Content validity: this type of Validity emphasized on adequate coverage of the scope of the topic. Kauru (2015) observes that content validity involves the systematic examination of the test content to determine whether it covers a representative sample of the behavior domain to be measured content validity is therefore directed to the following questions:

1. Have all the relevant dimensions of the topic been fully explored?
2. Does the measuring instrument adequately cover all the dimensions or at least a good representation of all the dimensions of the topic of research?

These questions must to be answered for an instrument to possess content validity. In line with this, Asika cited in Lawal and Ladan (2023), explains that content validity can be determined by the designer of the instrument in any of the following ways:

1. By ensuring that all the questions asked in the instrument questionnaire fully exhaust all that are implied by the research questions and hypotheses.
2. By using a panel of judges who would vet the questions in the questionnaire objectively, paying particular attention to their relevance to the subject matter and their coverage the entire topic of the study.

Criterion-related validity: Criterion-related validity involves comparing the test with other test(s) (criterion) that is held to be valid. Some instruments or tests are known or have been determined to be good measures of certain variables or attribute. Such test otherwise known as criterion can be used as basis for judging the validity of a newly designed instrument. For example, some of the West African Examination (WAEC) Examinations have been determined over time to be good measures of the candidate's intelligence. If a researcher is to design his own instrument to equally measure the students' intelligence, how does his own instrument compare or relate to a similar established criterion that is the WAEC examinations?

Criterion related validity is of two types: the predictive and concurrent validity. Predictive validity measures how the newly designed measuring instrument adequately predicts certain attributes it is designed to measure while the concurrent validity measures how the newly designed measuring instrument measures other current behaviors or variables.

Construct validity

The word construct according to Salawu & Kamar (2017) is a high-level concept that has been invented for particular purpose. Examples of construct are the terms motivation and intelligence. Motivation is used to explain human behavior and intelligence is used to study difference in human learning or human behavior. Construct validity is therefore an attempt to measure how adequately an instrument measures the actual meaning of a construct. Gay, Mills and Airasian (2022) opined that, construct validity attempts to explain whether the test reflects the actual meaning of the construct or not. For instance, how well results from a test on stress reflect the actual theoretical characteristics of stress is a measure of construct validity. However, there are other types of validity.

ii. Experimental validity or Validity of Findings

This type validity is associated with Experimental research. Best & Kahn (2016) stated that Conventional experiment usually involves two groups: Experimental group and Control group and experimental group is exposed to influence of the factor under consideration. Observations are then made to determine what difference appears or what changes or modifications occur in the experimental group as contrasted with the control group. Experimental validity or Validity of findings therefore refers to the problem of the adequacy of a research design in eliciting the type of responses that it is designed to generate. In other words, a research design may be said to be valid if it enables a researcher elicit the correct responses from the sample subjects, otherwise it is a faulty design and may not lead to correct findings. In relation to this, there are two (2) types of validity. They are namely: External validity and internal validity.

i. External Validity

External validity refers to the degree to which it is warranted to [generalize](#) results to other contexts. External validity asks questions of generalization. To what population, setting can the effects observed be generalized. Best & Kahn (2016) stated that the researcher would achieve little of practical value if these observed variable valid only in the experimental setting and only for those participating. External validity is therefore extent to which the variable relationship can be generalized to other setting, other treatment variables, other measurement variables and other population.

ii. Internal Validity

Internal Validity is concerned with the extent to which a [causal](#) conclusion based on a study is warranted, which is determined by the degree to which a study minimizes [systematic error](#) (or bias). An experiment is said to have internal validity if the factors

Managing Threats... (Muhammad & Ladan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

that have been manipulated (independent variables) actually have genuine effect on the observed consequences or dependent variable. For example, consider the following outcomes of an experiment of two separate teaching methods;

Pre-test mean score (Mean Score before the treatment) = 20 %

Post-test Mean Score (Mean Score after the treatment) = 60%

In this example, the researcher wants to make a causal inference that 40% difference is caused only by the treatment that is the teaching method. In other words, when the researcher may confidently attribute the observed changes or differences in the dependent variable to the independent variable, and when the researcher can rule out other explanations then the causal inference is said to be internally valid.

Internal Validity in Qualitative Research Method

Qualitative research is a method that is more frequently adopted in social science disciplines While, Quantitative research involves generation of data in quantitative form which can be subjected to rigorous statistical analysis, Qualitative however employs few if any quantitative data gathering instruments. It uses unstructured and semi-structured methods such as in-depth interviews, focus groups, and participant observation for data collection.

In qualitative research method, the word Credibility is used to refer to internal validity. Credibility is concerned with how well the researcher has established confidence in research based on the research design. Mahuta (2016) stated that credibility is concerned with the truthfulness of the research findings. Since qualitative research method deals with subjective assessment of the phenomena being study in natural setting, its critics (positivist) are of the opinion that achieving internal validity or credibility is difficult if not impossible in qualitative research method. However, Donald, Lucy & Chris cited in Mahuta (2016) stated that credibility (internal validity) in qualitative research can be enhanced through the following methods:

1. Structural corroboration which has to with Data triangulation.
2. Consensus which has to do with Investigator triangulation
3. Control of bias which can be done through reflexivity or use of self-reflection to recognize one's own biases and to actively seek them out.

Basic Consideration for Achieving Internal Validity

In many cases, the magnitude of effects found in the dependent variable may not just depend on independent variable, there are certain factors or variable that could exert some influence over the dependent variable which serves as threats to internal validity. They are extraneous variables or circumstances that if not well control can affect the internal validity. These factors include: Maturation, testing, instrumentation, differential selection of subjects, experimental mortality, statistical regression, Hawthorn effects among other factors. Some of these factors are explained below:

4. **Maturation:** The subject being measured may change during the course of the experiment or even between measurements which may be due to psychological and physical changes.

For example, consider this experiment on methods of teaching

Group I (experimental) given treatment from 8:00am– 9:00 am

Group II (control) given treatment from 1:00pm – 2: 00 pm

Any outcome obtained from this experiment cannot serves as a basis for comparison. Physical and psychological changes may put the control group at the disadvantage. The afternoon time may be too hot. Similarly, the control group may get tired, bored and loss interest or eager to go home.

5. **Testing:** the testing itself may sensitize the subjects being tested or measured (found in pre-test post-test). If the same test is used for pre and post-tests, the possibility is that the subjects have mastered the former to help their performance in the second. In other words, Best & Kahn (2016) stated that pre-testing may produce a practice effect that may make subjects more proficient in subsequent test performance.

6. **Instrumentation:** Unreliable instruments used to describe and measure aspects of behavior are threat to internal validity of an experiment. For instance, an instrument of observation that is not reliable, a serious element of error is introduced. Similarly, if human observers are used to describe behavior changes in subjects, changes in observers or in their standards due to fatigue, increased in sight or skill or changes in criteria of judgment over period of time are likely to introduce error. With regards to test as instrument Essay type of tests especially, Salawu & Kamar (2017) pointed out that if the pre-test and post-test are marked by different scorers there will be contradiction to validity. Whether or not marking schemes are provided for the separate scorers or assessors, element of bias is already introduced.

7. **History:** History in this context refers to specific random events, which are beyond the control of the researcher that can affect the performance of the subjects. Such events can occur between the first and second measurement. Take for example an experiment which takes 5 – 10 weeks in a school setting. Some of the students may go beyond the lectures (treatment) being

Managing Threats... (Muhammad & Ladan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

given, thus having extra experience during the interval between pre and posts test. This is beyond the control of the researcher but can have effect on the performance of the subjects.

8. **Experimental Mortality:** this is loss of subjects from the sample due to resignations, apathy or death. It may likely to occur in the long-term experiment and error can occur if inferences are made on the basis of only those participants that have participated from the start to the end. For example, an experiment was started with 30 samples but at the end only 20 or less are left to continue, then there is experimental mortality because some of those 10 or more students who left may be special students or those with low marks.

9. **Statistical Regression:** Subjects, who score highest in the pre-test, may score lower on the re-test; subjects who score higher on pre-test may score high on re-test. Scores at the extreme tend to go towards the mean. In other words, this type of error occurs when subjects are selected on the basis of extreme scores (one far away from the mean) during a test. For example, when children with the worst reading scores are selected to participate in a reading course, improvements at the end of the course might be due to regression toward the mean and not the course's effectiveness. If the children had been tested again before the course started, they would likely have obtained better scores anyway. For example, consider this experiment, a situation where after teaching with two methods, a teacher ranks students according to marks:

Group A 1 – 30 %

Group B 71- 100 %

This comparison makes it impossible to actually find out the effect of one variable on the other because only the best performing (71- 100 %) and worst performing (1 – 30 %) were selected. The subjects are not true representation of the population. In this case, the researcher should not pick from the two extremes.

4. **Selection Bias:** this is bias in the selection of students or other groups of people for an experimental research study. This may render deductions from such exercises worthless.

5. **Experimenter Bias:** This factor as explained by Best & Kahn (2016) is a type of bias introduced when the researcher has some previous knowledge about the subjects involved in an experiment. This knowledge of subject status may cause the researcher to convey some clue that affect the subject's reaction or may affect the objectivity of his or her judgment.

Conclusion

Many threats to internal validity of especially experiment are difficult to be eliminated totally particularly when research is conducted outside the laboratory setting; where there are many extraneous variables to control. However, knowledge of the threats or factors that can jeopardize it is crucial. It enables the researcher to mitigate those threats to a minimum level and enhance the quality of the instruments and of course findings.

Recommendations

Threat to internal validity is inevitable challenge more especially in Experimental research design. However, the following suggestions can minimize those threats and enable researcher confidently attributes the observed changes or differences in the dependent variable to the independent variable:

1. To reduce the threats generated by History & Maturation, there is need to consider the time of experiment. In order words, the shorter the duration of an experiment, the less likely that maturation will occur. Similarly, the use of a control group, selected from the same population as the experimental group and which experiences the same concurrent history as the experimental group is another strategy for reducing threats to internal validity.
2. With regards to testing, many actions can be taken to ensure that the possibility of proficiency as a result of the mastery of pre-test is checkmated. Among which are, the use of a research design that does not include a pretest. Even where the experiment involved pre-test, the use of different but equivalent forms of a test for pre-test and post-test is another option.
3. Random sampling and random assignment of subjects are some of the viable ways to reduce threats arising from bias in selection. Where random sampling and assignment are not possible, statistical techniques such as ANCOVA can be utilized to adjust for group differences. Similarly, researchers should desist from being bias or subjective in scoring the instruments, objectivity is therefore essential as far as internal validity is concerned.
4. Standardized instruments possessed the quality of reliability. To eliminate instrumentation threats therefore, there is need for the researchers to adopt or adapt standardized instruments more especially in situations whereby the reliability of the researcher-designed instruments cannot be ascertained. In addition, careful specification and control of the measurement procedures as well as the training of study personnel are among other procedures that help control the instrumentation threat.

Managing Threats... (Muhammad & Ladan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

5. Researchers also need avoid assigning subjects to groups based on their extreme scores in order to prevent the internal validity threats arising from statistical regression.
6. Some circumstances leading to experimental mortality such as death is unavoidable but other conditions such as anger, apathy, and frustration can be managed. There is therefore need for the researchers to provide enabling conditions that can encourage participants to willingly and objectivity participate in the experiment from the start to the completion.
7. Other basic considerations are: the use of single scorers or markers on issue of instrumentation, avoiding picking from two extreme scores to check statistical regression, randomization among others. Similarly, pure or true experimental design enable researcher to neutralize the threat or influence of both internal and external validity.

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Comparative analysis between Welfare Services and Wellbeing of Retired Citizens in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated Comparative analysis between Welfare Services and wellbeing of retired citizens in Calabar metropolis of Cross River state Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: determine the relationship between social security (pension scheme); investigate the relationship between affordable low-cost housing; examine the relationship between inexpensive medical services and wellbeing retired citizens. The study adopted mixed method type of research design specifically qualitative and quantitative approach. The population of the study consists of all retired citizens in Calabar metropolis. A sample size of 240 respondents were selected using multi-stage sampling technique. A 4 likert scale questionnaire and 9 itemed Key informant Interview Guide were the instruments of data collection. The data obtained were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation analytical procedure. Findings of the study revealed a significant relationship between social welfare services and wellbeing of retired citizens in Calabar metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria. The study concluded that social welfare services impact positively on the wellbeing of retired citizen. Since older people are very vulnerable, government and civil society organizations should help in various ways by providing social welfare services to them.

Keywords: Social welfare services, retired citizens, pension scheme, wellbeing

Introduction

The rapidly growing number of the retired citizen during the last few decades has impacted on the political, economic and social functions of societies. The population division of the United Nations Development of Economic and Social Affairs; population division (UNDESA, 2015) observed that the proportion of older persons aged 60 years and above make up 12.3 percent of the global population and by 2050 that proportion will rise to almost 22 percent. Sub-Saharan Africa, which has the smallest proportion of elderly and which is aging slower than the developed regions, is projected to see the absolute size of its older population grow by 2.3 times between 2000 and 2030 (UNDESA, 2015). People are living longer due to better nutrition, sanitation, healthcare, education and economic wellbeing.

The ageing of populations across the globe is a demographic reality of our time. By 2050, there will be more population of older people worldwide (ages 60 years and over) than children under 15 years (Pelzer, 2012, UNDESA, 2013). Nigeria and other developing countries are now faced with an ageing at a different scale than what is experienced in developed societies. Nigeria is just beginning to experience the ageing transition in full (Pelzer, 2012).

In Nigeria, the aged population too is increasing rapidly. Those aged 65 years and above (the elderly) make up 3.1 percent or 5.9 million of the total population of 200 million, which in crude numbers represent an increase of 600,000 during

Comparative analysis between... (Bassey, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

the 5year period 2012-2017 (National Council on Aging, 2016). The rising number of the elderly in Nigeria may be attributed to the crude mortality rate that is gradually decreasing (Adebowale, & Ayeni, 2012) despite the socio-economic hardship, widespread poverty, the HIV/AIDs epidemic and the rapid transformation of the traditional extended family structure (Adebanjoke & Ugwoke, 2014). Apart from the decline in fertility, improved health and sanitary conditions have also contributed to the rise in life expectancy (Tanyi, Andre & Mba, 2018). The United Nations in the 1980s projected that by 2025, the number of the aged in Nigeria would have risen from its 27th position in the 1950s to 11th position (United Nations, 1985). Estimates by the United Nations (2012) showed that the elderly population in Nigeria will increase from 6.4 million in 2005 to 11.5 million in 2025, and then 25.5 million by 2050.

Aging causes people to be less active, frail and exposed to more risks of contacting a disease, leading to prejudice or discrimination against the elderly, social isolation and sometimes abandonment. An aging population poses numerous social and economic challenges thus making care of the aged an issue of significant concern. Wellbeing of the aged has become a serious issue because despite the demographic impact of the AIDS epidemic, the Nigerian population is projected to continue ageing over the next two decades. In the midst of this demographic reality, is the fact that Calabar South local government in Cross River State and in Nigeria will be under intense pressure to meet the economic, health, psychological and material well-being challenges of the aged, especially as traditional family support system for the elderly care is breaking down and disappearing (Okoye, 2012). The well-being of the aged is influenced by a number of economic and social factors that include income, mental health, physical health, education, social relationships, employment, discrimination, government policies, and neighborhood conditions. Well-being involves both physical and mental health as part of a holistic approach to health promotion and disease prevention. The well-being of a society has the potential to impact greatly on the people's wellbeing in terms of the productivity level of the society as a whole. Though it may be assessed at the individual level, well-being becomes an important population outcome at the macro level and therefore represents a public health issue.

The refugee crisis, the current and future projections around climate migration, and the changing demographic landscape globally sets forth new questions about our strategies and policies for the aging population, integration of new populations, and the readiness of our communities economically and socially to diversify (Watts, Noye & Tarini, 2022). As demographic shifts and health advancements take hold in Nigeria and globally, how do we create supportive communities for aging now and in the nearest future to guarantee longer life? How does the society support better care during later life? In view of this, social welfare provision becomes necessary as response mechanism for the wellbeing maintenance of the aged. Provisions of social service such as income, securities, housing, health care and even legal assistance can positively influence the wellbeing of the elderly (Oladeyi, 2011). A national social security system will provide an economic buffer in old age. In 1989, the Nigerian government developed the national social development policy which aimed to provide a framework for protecting the elderly persons from morals and materials neglect and provide public assistance when necessary. Despite the development of the national social development policy to care for the elderly, there has been no effective execution of this policy by any federal agency, thus posing a serious challenge to the wellbeing of the elderly (Mbdulkadir, 2016).

It is to note that the rising population of the aged requires social welfare interventions in the form of social security, low cost housing and accessible medical care. Guaranteed social security in form of pension scheme is necessary; it has the potential to reduce poverty and support older people who have disengaged from public service. The aged is entitled to a consistent and inexpensive health care system. Affordable and accessible housing is important in promoting the wellbeing of the aged. If the wellbeing of the elderly members of the community are to be guaranteed, the importance of appropriate housing and social pension (social insurance) cannot be underestimated. Provision of social services such as income, security, health care, housing, and legal assistance can positively influence the well-being and health of the elderly (Oladeji, 2011).

The aged family members lack access to economic resources, basic services, markets; affected by poverty, hunger and inequality (Pelzer, 2012). Apart from disadvantages experienced in purely economic dimension, they are unable to meet basic needs, also, inability to participate in economic, social, civil and political life (Pelzer, 2012). The interest in family sustainability has been raised due to its declining nutritional levels which is seriously affecting the aged members who are experiencing poor health care accessibility, non- involvement in community political affairs and increasing poverty level (Pelzer, 2012).

The wellbeing of the aged poses a serious concern to social workers, concerned citizens and the entire society. The older persons and their families face challenges in coping with functional wellbeing due to changes in family dynamics, increased demand for medical services, increased economic stress and decreased functional independence. Ani (2013) observed that health status of the aged is a function of the care and support they receive. Several chronic diseases suffered by the aged are traceable to lack of or inadequate care and support as well as poor nutrition and physical inactivity. In Nigeria, evidence shows a very weak institutional base to tackle the care and support of the elderly (Okoye, 2011).

Comparative analysis between... (Bassey, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Since poverty remains a major challenge in Nigeria, elderly persons who have retired from the economic productive phase are most vulnerable to experiencing economic hardship (Oladeji, 2011). Since the statutory age of retirement in Nigeria is 60 and 70 years (depending on where you work) and is the cut-off for being categorized as an elderly person, the majority of this group of (elderly) people are not socially and economically secure (Oladeji, 2011). Elderly people are usually forced to cope with the paradox of dwindling financial resources. In particular, elderly people living in urban areas in Nigeria only utilized health services and other services when they are available, accessible, and affordable (Odaman & Ibiezugbe, 2014).

The patterns of the economic lives of older persons in Nigeria vary by urban and rural residences (Odaman & Ibiezugbe, 2014). In urban Nigeria, elders with high physical and psychological functioning are forced to retire once they reach the statutory retirement age. They face abrupt declines in their income and can feel less self-worth or even experience depression, since they perceive themselves as still being fit to work. Gureje & Oyewole (2006) were of the view that implicit social changes reduce the status of the elderly and their influence in the society which affect their total wellbeing. The majority of them are faced with depression, loss of vision, diabetes, hypertension, obesity, tooth loss, pathological bone fracture, arthritis and rheumatism, stroke, Alzheimer's disease, etc. (Ani, 2019).

Some of the challenges associated with the elderly in both urban and rural areas are the diseases that come with old age and the lack of well-trained doctors to care for them especially in rural areas (Ayomele, 2017). In some urban areas there are no trained geriatric doctors incorporated into the health-care system to take care of the health needs of the elderly. The non-establishment of geriatric hospitals or availability of geriatric sections incorporated in teaching hospitals to care for the elderly is part of the problems encountered by the elderly (Ayomele, 2017).

The lack of framework for supportive and protective care that comprises those services provided to frail, ill, or disabled older people to support them and their caretakers while maintaining their capacity to live in the community exacerbates the adverse condition of the elderly (Ayomele, 2017). In rural Nigeria, many older persons are not formally employed with a company or civil service, they continue to engage in menial jobs and manual work on the farms with meager earnings as long as their physical strength can afford (Ayomele, 2017). The rural elderly may suffer from health disorders and physical exhaustion and often have no retirement benefits to serve as social security.

Thus, an ageing population has implications for labour markets, health care and social security. Wellbeing of the aged in Calabar South local government area of Cross River State poses a serious challenge because of relatively low level of socio-economic development. Calabar South local government Council is unable to respond to the plight of large numbers of elderly people, especially as traditional family support systems for the elderly are breaking down due to globalization (Adebanjoko & Ugwuoke, 2014). So far, there has been no clearly defined policy intervention on this issue thus the interest in the wellbeing of the aged has become a pressing very challenging in this local government area.

The lack of deliberate intervention in the form of social welfare services for the aged may be exacerbating their marginalized condition. The elderly needs policy intervention for care and protection such as social welfare. Social welfare services will help to meet the economic, health, psychological and material wellbeing challenges of the elderly. Therefore, the provision of social security, low cost housing and free medical care could bridge the gap in the wellbeing of retired aged citizens in Calabar South local government area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the relationship between social security (pension scheme) and wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South local government area municipal of Cross River State
2. To Investigate the relationship between affordable low- cost housing and wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South Local government area municipal of Cross River State
3. To examine the relationship between inexpensive medical services and wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South Local government area municipal of Cross River State

Hypotheses

1. Social security (pension scheme) has no significant relationship with the wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South local government area. municipal of Cross River State
2. Affordable low- cost housing has no significant relationship with the wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South local government area. municipal of Cross River State
3. Availability of free/inexpensive medical services have no significant relationship with wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South local government area. municipal of Cross River State

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Literature Review

Social welfare provision and wellbeing of the aged

People are living longer because of better nutrition, sanitation, health care, education, and economic well-being. An ageing population poses numerous social and economic challenges, but the right set of policies can equip society to address these challenges in time. Nigeria's elderly too is increasing rapidly. In Nigeria, those aged 65 years and above (the elderly) make up 3.1% or 5.9 million of the total population of 191 million, which in crude numbers represents an increase of 600,000 during the 5-year period 2012–2017 (Population Reference Bureau, 2012; National Council on Ageing 2016).

Ageing in Nigeria is occurring against the background of socioeconomic hardship, widespread poverty, the HIV/AIDS epidemic, and the rapid transformation of the traditional extended family structure (Adebanjoko & Ugwuoke, 2014). This makes the intersection between social welfare services provision and wellbeing by the elderly very paramount (Nkpoyen, 2011). The UNDP indicators of wellbeing include people's ability to live long, healthy and creative lives in an equitable society and in a sustainable way as well as their level of income; employment opportunities open to them, access to basic services such as education and training basic infrastructure etc (Decancq & Lugo 2013). The index of social exclusion assessing the extent of inclusion covers three dimensions, economic exclusion, exclusion from social services and exclusion from civic participation (Medgyesi, Ozdenir & Ward, 2017).

The economic dimension covers deprivation in respect of income and basic needs, access to employment, financial services and material assets, the lack of amenities that the household needs but cannot afford and housing space. The social services dimension contains indicators on access to, and the affordability of, education and healthcare services as well as public utilities. The civic and social life dimension includes indicators of access to political, cultural and social participation and support networks, as well as the frequency of social and civic participation (Medgyesi, Ozdenir and Ward, 2017).

Social security (pension scheme) and wellbeing of the aged

The growth in the number of older people inevitably has brought an increase in the range and intensity of their problems and needs. For those who are in the public sector, the pension scheme appears to be the source of social securities (Tanimon, 2006, Oshiomole, 2009). The pension reform Act 2004 provides, among others, that, the scheme shall apply to all employees in the public service of the Nigerian federation, federal capital territory and the private sector organization in which these are five or more employees. According to Oshiomoke (2009), the objectives of the schemes were to ensure that every person who worked in either the public service of the federation, federal capital territory or private sector received his retirement benefit as and when due.; assist improvident individuals by ensuring that they save in other to cater for their livelihood during old age etc. Thus, the pension scheme has the potential to ameliorate their suffering and care for them. (Ogumbameru & Adesina, 2000).

Affordable low-cost housing and wellbeing for the aged

The home environment that does not meet physical needs is not likely to be satisfactory to the aged. Thus, provision of the low-cost housing accommodation is desirable. This aging of the population presents a number of challenges and unanswered questions including where people will live, whether they will afford it and how they will obtain support and care they will need as they age while retaining as much independence as possible. (Green & Painter, 2012). Affordable housing options with low-income housing tax credit or public housing-linked with health and supportive services may provide a cost-effective answer for meeting the needs of lower-income services may provide a cost-effective answer for meeting the needs of lower-income services (Sanders, 2019).

Access to medical services and care of the aged

The provision of quality assured health care services for the elderly population is a challenge that requires government continuous response, failure to address the health needs today could develop into a costly problem tomorrow. Akanyi and Baryewa (2002) commented that the need for improved attention to the health needs of the older people through improved budgeting allocation, revision of the training curriculum of all cadres of health staff to include geriatrics and utilization of primary health care facilities cannot be over-emphasized. At the first national summit on healthy ageing in Abuja, the federal government said it plans to extend free health care services to all Nigerians over the age of 60 years. (Daily trust, 2019).

The basic needs approach and political economy perspective of aging

The basic needs approach and political economy perspective of aging constituted the theoretical framework and was introduced by International Labour Organization's World Employment Conference in 1976 (Jolly 1976). The satisfaction of basic human needs is the overriding objectives of social welfare policy. This is necessary for the survival of the elderly. The political economy perspective implies that in the context of capitalist society, the elderly people who are in a weak position in the global economy requires access to social welfare especially medical services and low-cost housing.

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Methodology

The research adopted for this study was the qualitative and quantitative approaches of survey design. The population of the study comprised all the aged Citizens inhabitants from the age of 55 to 70 years retired Citizens in these wards made up the study population in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. The rationale for targeting only retirees was because they were educated and exposed to policy issues in Nigeria. Calabar South Local Government has 12 political wards that constituted the 12 strata. Twenty (20) respondents were selected from each stratum. The actual selection was done through systematic and snowball sampling procedures. Only 240 literate elderly men and women from the clusters were studied. Therefore, the sample of the study was made up of 240 respondents. The sample comprised retirees from the public service residing in the communities Calabar South Local Government Area Cross River State. A pretesting was done to ascertain the reliability and validity of the questionnaire and Key Informant Guide. Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyzed data based on each of the hypotheses.

Results

Hypothesis 1

Social security (Pension Scheme) has no significant relationship with wellbeing of the aged retired citizen in Calabar South local government area

Table 1: Pearson product moment correlation coefficient analysis of the relationship between social security (Pension Scheme) and wellbeing of the aged (n = 200)

Variable	X	SD	$\sum X$	$\frac{\sum X^2}{\sum Y}$	$\frac{\sum XY}{\sum Y^2}$	r-cal
Social security		11.19	1.77	3780	70560	0.415
Wellbeing of aged (Y)	12.20	2.21	6820	12980	67840	

*Correlation significant $p > .05$, $df = 198$, $crit - r = 0.196$
 Source: Field survey, 2024.

Hypotheses 2:

Affordable low- cost housing has no significant relationship with the wellbeing of aged retired citizens in Calabar South Local Government

Table 2: Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient analysis of the relationship between affordable low-cost housing and wellbeing of the aged (n = 200)

Variable	X	SD	$\sum X$	$\frac{\sum X^2}{\sum Y}$	$\sum XY$	r-cal
Affordable low-cost housing (X)	12.11	1.47	5780	70560	97540	8.212*
Wellbeing of aged (Y)	17.11	2.27	6820	12980		

*Correlation significant $p > .05$, $df = 198$, $crit - r = 0.196$
 Source: Field survey, 2024

Hypothesis 3:

Accessibility to medical service has no significant relationship with wellbeing of the aged in Calabar South local government Area

Table 3: Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient analysis of the relationship between inexpensive medical service and wellbeing of aged retired citizen (n = 200)

Variable	X	SD	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal
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Comparative analysis between... (Bassey, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

				ΣY	ΣY^2		
Inexpensive medical service X	12.76	1.44	4770	139800			
Wellbeing of aged (Y)	14.11	3.31	6820	12980		11910	0.321*

*Correlation significant $p > .05$, $df = 198$, $crit - r = 0.196$
 Source: Field survey, 2024

Discussion of Findings

The result of statistical analyses revealed that social security (pension scheme), access to medical services and housing all have significant relationships with the wellbeing of the aged. From the analysis, the value was positive which indicated that the more the availability of social security the better the wellbeing of the aged. According to Apere (2015), the problems that surround pensioners in Nigeria include: (1) Delayed or nonpayment of pension entitlements and misappropriation of existing pension funds; (2) low standard of living (or high poverty incidence) among pensioners due to pension increases not in line with salary inflation or no pension increase at all; (3) too frequent verification of pensioners by pension transitional arrangements directorate (PTAD) (section 42 of PRA 2014) leading to pensioners dying during verification exercises; (4) inadequate enforcement of pension regulation: After more than 10 years of existence of the CPS, not all state governments had enacted their pension laws to establish the CPS, which is a sign of regulatory weakness (Apere, 2015).

Nkpoyn (2015) observed that social policy issues including pension are very significant for ensuring social protection for the aged in poor countries. In Nigeria about seventy percent of the citizens are living below the poverty line of one dollar a day public sector. Real wages are not only low but dismally downward. Old age security is not available outside formal occupation and unemployment benefit are not provided for the unemployed, meaning that the workers under the extended family system take responsibility for this vulnerable group (Smalley, 2010). This study agrees with Ogumbameou and Adesina (2020) that the pension scheme has the potential to ameliorate the suffering of the aged and care for them.

A Key informant respondent, former Chairperson aged 61 years reported that: The greatest problem we have in this country is that our leaders don't keep to their words. The people managing the pension scheme don't keep their word. Many elderly people like us who depend on pension suffer to get their pension, many even die before the pension starts coming. Some of the elderly who are retired cannot even pay their rents. Some who retire and move to the rural areas die immediately they get home because of suffering (KII 2023).

Oladeji (2020) commented that since poverty remains a major challenge in Nigeria, elderly persons who have retired from the economic productive phase are most vulnerable to experiencing economic hardship. Since the statutory age of retirement in Nigeria is 60 and 70 years (depending on where you work) and is the cut-off for being categorized as an elderly person, the majority of this group of (elderly) people are not socially and economically secure. Elderly people are usually forced to cope with the paradox of dwindling financial resources, increased health challenges, and a geometric rise in medical expenses. In particular, elderly people living in urban areas in Nigeria only utilized health services and other services when they were available, accessible, and affordable (Odaman & Ibiezugbe, 2014).

The patterns of the economic lives of older persons in Nigeria vary by urban and rural residences (Odaman & Ibiezugbe, 2014). In urban Nigeria, elders with high physical and psychological functioning are forced to retire once they reach the statutory retirement age. They face abrupt declines in their income and can feel less self-worth or even experience depression, since they perceive themselves as still being fit to work.

One Key Informant respondents, aged 54 years articulated the situation as follows: in our communities, we older persons are not formally employed with a company or some other form of governmental organization, we continue to engage in menial jobs and manual work on the farms with meager earnings as long as their physical strength can afford. We have no access to free medical services when we are sick. We suffer from health disorders and physical exhaustion and often have no access to retirement benefits to serve as social security.

The findings are consistent with Warding (2015) that the overwhelming majority and older adult prefer to age in their place, remaining in their current home or communities. However, many senior citizens feel that their current homes are not well suited for aging. A home environment that does not meet physical needs is not likely to be satisfactory to the aged. Thus, provision of the low-cost housing accommodation is desirable to the aged. Community features, house affordability and accessibility of services all contribute to the ability of the senior citizens to successfully age in their current home and labour.

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The findings validate Kojetin (2017) that safe and accessible housing and services are essential to maintain maximum health, functioning and independence in the older population. According to Kojetin (2015) a handful of empirical studies indicate evidence of improved health outcomes, enhanced productive engagement and public cost-saving attributable to various interventions such as housing accommodation that encourage aging in place.

As observed by Sanders (2019) and supported by the findings of this study, the provision of low -cost housing to serve the needs of the elderly has the potential advantages such as building on an existing infrastructure of housing and community service networks; also helping preserve seniors' autonomy and independence. The result of statistical analysis revealed that inexpensive medical services significantly relate to the care of the aged. Therefore, as commended by Akanji and Banyewa (2018) which is validated by the study, the need for improved attention to the health needs of the older people through improved budgetary allocation, revision of the training curriculum of all cadres of health staff to include geriatrics and utilization of primary health care facilities cannot be over emphasized.

The findings are in tandem with Shrivastara, Shrivastara and Ramasaney (2013) observed that the health needs or health related problems of the elderly people cannot be viewed in isolation. Provision of care for the elderly is very essential. One of the Key Informants respondents, aged 57 years asserted that: Most of the elderly people residing in the rural communities have no support from the government. They get support from faith-based organizations or from their relatives and some none at all. Elderly people who don't have any relatives suffer a lot in this local government area.

Another Key Informant, aged 50 years commented that: the elderly ones in our communities are suffering. In this community there are no basic amenities. For example, people have to walk so many kilometers to get drinking water, electricity is not regular. The elderly in the rural communities cannot even afford electricity bills, there are no health facilities in this community. The elderly have to travel long distances to get medical attention. The rate of suffering is just too much. The government has not done anything to improve the lives of the elderly in this community.

Conclusion

Specifically, the provision of social security (pension scheme), affordable low-cost housing and inexpensive medical service are required to sustain the aged members of the society. The institutional care of the aged is vital to enable them access social security services.

Recommendations

1. Regular payment of statutory pension should be punished by the government.
2. The growth in the number of older people inevitably has brought an increase in the range and intensity of their problems especially that of housing. So, the government should make the provision of affordable housing a priority policy.
3. Older people are very vulnerable to diseases; therefore, the government should ensure that medical services are available and affordable.

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Correlation between Artificial... (Bada, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Correlation between Artificial Intelligence on Mental Health and Retention Skills among Undergraduate Students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

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Abstract

This study investigated the correlation between artificial intelligence on mental health and retention skills among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. Two objectives, 2 research questions and 2 hypotheses were formulated for the study. The study adopted descriptive survey type of research design. The population of the study comprises of 100 to 400 level undergraduate students of Computer Science, Faculty of Computer Science & Artificial Intelligence, Federal University of Dutsin-Ma during the 2023/2024 academic session. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the level of the respondents while purposive sampling technique was used to select 300 (165 male and 135 female) students selected from the target population using Multistage sampling technique. Three instruments were used for the data collection namely Artificial Intelligence Scale (AIS), Mental Health Scale (MHS) and Retention Skills Scale (RSS), they were subjected to reliability test and Pearson Moment Correlation Statistics was used to determine the reliability coefficients as follows reliability coefficient of 0.70, 0.68 and 0.70 respectively, were obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient reliability test. The finding revealed that there was a significant relationship between Artificial Intelligence, Mental Health and students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina. The study concludes that artificial intelligence has significant correlation between mental health and students' retention skills. The findings recommended among others that higher institutions of learning should provide adequate training and support to students and lecturers to ensure they are proficient in using Artificial Intelligence technologies effectively.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Mental Health, Retention Skills and Undergraduates

Introduction

The impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on mental health, human behavior, and overall well-being is a complex and continuously evolving issue. As the field of artificial intelligence (AI) progresses, it becomes imperative to achieve a delicate equilibrium between leveraging its advantageous capabilities for mental health assistance and confronting the obstacles it presents in terms of human conduct and privacy.

The advent of artificial intelligence (AI) has presented itself as an innovative technology that holds the capacity to bring about significant transformations in multiple domains of human existence, encompassing mental well-being. The convergence of AI and mental health is a captivating field of study that has a multitude of prospects for enhancing the identification, intervention, and holistic welfare of those grappling with mental health difficulties. One of the foremost benefits of AI in the field of mental health is in its capacity to identify and forecast mental disorders during their nascent phases. Through the examination of extensive amounts of data, encompassing social media posts, internet behaviors, and physiological

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measurements, AI systems possess the capability to discern nuanced patterns and indicators linked to diverse mental diseases (Torous et al, 2021).

The domains of mental health and artificial intelligence (AI) are undergoing rapid advancements, exhibiting the capacity to mutually influence one another in significant ways. The increasing prevalence of mental health illnesses has prompted the exploration of potential remedies in the field of AI, which show promise in the areas of early detection, prevention, and therapy (Koki, 2023). Mental health is a term that is used in human development field. The individual and the environment play a role in one's overall wellbeing, especially early childhood and adolescence. It is commonly acknowledged that family and environment is significant for effective growth of the individual. Mental health is usually conceptualized as combination of positive emotional states such as happiness and functioning with optimal effectiveness in individual's social life (Lee & Torous, 2021). In the study of Odeleye (2019), mental health is about lives going well and it is the combination of feeling good and functioning well. Mental health issues continue to be a global concern, with a steady 13% prevalence over the past 10 years and a statistical projection that nearly one in four people worldwide will be affected by a mental or neurological disorder at some point in their lives (Batada & Solano, 2019) Despite this prevalence, mental health remains a largely overlooked aspect of global health, with disparities in access, quality, and care affordability. It therefore means that people with high mental health feel happy, capable, well supported, and satisfied with life. Additionally, mental health describes the degree to which individuals believe they have real influence over their lives and their activities.

Retention is the ability of students to consistently remain and progress in school until the completion of the educational cycle (Bawa, 2019). It means a student on a given grade level remains and progresses to the next, session by session through the completion of the educational cycle. School curriculum contents are arranged sequentially and progressively on the building blocks of knowledge acquisition as the child progresses. If a child stays out of school, she/he will be deprived of the cumulative knowledge and skills that are supposed to be acquired to justify that level of education through the modular learning of the curriculum (Bawa, 2019). Retention in the successful completion of students' academic goals attainment or students meeting clearly defined educational goals whether career advancement or achievement of new skills (Ismail, 2017). Therefore, it as a result of the above gap that this study seeks to impact of artificial intelligence on undergraduate students' mental health and retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State.

With the improvement of science and technology, there has been a drastic spread in the various aspects of information technology in the heart of the society. The impact of such a sector has improved the notions of data automation and data analysis. Artificial Intelligence (AI), Cloud Computing, Big Data and similar others have improved the quality of life. Artificial intelligence helps by developing different software applications for improving the quality of the education system. Artificial intelligence helps the students by giving answers to all the queries that have been asked by the students at any time of the day (Chen, 2020).

It is currently difficult to completely understand the impacts of AI in higher education; hence more studies should be done to widen the understanding of this topic and create a wider platform for informed debate. The authors have discussed the challenges facing the adoption of AI in higher learning and the possible solutions (Reese, 2019). However, the adoption of AI in higher education is still at its earliest stages; therefore, only a few research studies have been done empirically. It is on this basis that this study finds it necessary to investigate the correlation between Artificial Intelligence on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health and Retention Skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to determine the correlation between artificial intelligence on mental health and retention skills among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. Specifically, to:

1. Find out the impact of artificial intelligence on mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
2. Investigate the impact of artificial intelligence on retention skills among Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
3. Examine the relationship between artificial intelligence and mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
4. Examine the relationship between artificial intelligence and retention skills among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the conduct of this study:

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1. What is impact of artificial intelligence on mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State?
2. What is the impact of artificial intelligence on retention skills among Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested in the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and retention skills among Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey research design. Specifically, of correlational research type. This type of study seeks to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables. Usually, such studies indicate the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables. The population of the study comprised of 100 to 400 level of Computer Science of the Faculty of Computer and Artificial Intelligence, Federal University of Dutsin-Ma. Purposive random sampling technique was used to select 300 level and 400 level undergraduate students. The simple random sampling technique was used to select 150 among 300 level students and 150 students among 400 level students making 300 (165 male and 135 female) respondents for the study. Three instruments were used for data collection. These are: Artificial Intelligence Scale (AIS), Mental Health Scale (MHS) and Retention Skills Scale (RSS) which were subjected to test re- test method and Pearson Moment Correlation Statistics was used to determine the reliability coefficients which yielded 0.70, 0.68 and 0.70. Each of the three scales has 10 items with 4 points scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1), to Disagree (2), Agree (3) and Strongly Agree (4). The research questions 1 and were answered using mean and standard deviation Also, the research hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Statistic at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One:

What is impact of artificial intelligence on mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State?

Table 1: Showing the mean and standard deviation of impact of artificial intelligence on mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Decision
Artificial Intelligence	300	9.03	2.01	Positive
Students' Retention Skills	300	10.44	1.60	

Table 1 revealed the impact of Artificial Intelligence on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. It showed that mean score of Artificial Intelligence was 9.03 and Students' Mental Health mean score was 10.44. This means that artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State.

Research Question Two:

What is the impact of artificial intelligence on retention skills among Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State?

Table 2: Showing mean and standard deviation of impact of artificial intelligence on retention skills among Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Decision
Artificial Intelligence	300	9.36	1.20	Positive
Students' Retention Skills	300	9.39	1.47	

Table 2 revealed the impact of Artificial Intelligence on Undergraduate Students' Retention Skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. It showed that mean score of Artificial Intelligence was (9.36) and Students' Retention Skills mean score was (9.39). This means that artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' Retention Skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

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Testing of Hypotheses

H₀₁:

There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Table 3: Table showing the Correlation analysis between artificial intelligence and mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	Cal Value	.r-	Critical r-value	Decision
Artificial Intelligence	300	22.65	10.75	298	0.38	0.21		Accepted
Students' Mental Health	300	23.46	11.43					

P<0.05

Table 3 revealed that the calculated r-value is (0.38) is greater than the Critical r-value (0. 21) at 0.05 level of significance and 298 degrees of freedom. Hence, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that there was a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' mental health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

H₀₂:

There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and retention skills among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Table4: Showing Correlation analysis between artificial intelligence and retention skills among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	Cal Value	.r-	Critical r-value	Decision
Artificial Intelligence	300	21.96	11.77	298	0.63	0.32		Accepted
Retention Skills	300	43.86	12.33					

P>0.05

Table 4 revealed that the calculated r-value (0.63) is greater than the Critical r-value (0. 32) at 0.05 level of significance and 298 degree of freedom. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there was a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Summary of Finding

This study examined impact of Artificial Intelligence on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health and Retention Skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. Thus, the finding of this study was summarized as follows;

1. The study indicated that artificial intelligence (mean score 9.03) has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health (mean score 10.44) in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
2. The study revealed that artificial intelligence (mean score 9.36)) has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' retention skills (mean score 9.39) in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
3. There was a significant relationship between Artificial Intelligence and Undergraduate Students' Mental Health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State (calculated r-value (0.38) >Critical r-value 0.21) at 0.05 level of significance
4. There was a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State (calculated r-value 0.63 >Critical r-value 0. 32) at 0.05 level of significance

Discussions of Findings

Research question one indicated that artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. The finding of this study corroborates with Patra, Sethia, and Gupta, (2018) found that the moderate uses of artificial intelligence (AI) enhance Mental Health as a result of prevention of high level of stress.

Correlation between Artificial... (Bada, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Research question two revealed that artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. The finding of this study agrees with Kim and. Kim (2022) who found that the uses of artificial intelligence influences and enhances students' retention skills and learning outcome.

The result of hypothesis one revealed that there was a significant relationship between Artificial Intelligence and Undergraduate Students' Mental Health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. The finding of this study agrees with Patra, Sethia, and Gupta (2018) who found that there was significant relationship between Artificial Intelligence and Undergraduate Students' Mental Health and the moderate uses of artificial intelligence (AI) enhances mental health because it prevents high level of stress.

The result of hypothesis two showed that there was a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. The finding of this study corroborates with Kim and. Kim (2022) who found that there exists a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' retention skills. It further found that the uses of artificial intelligence influences and enhances students' retention skills and learning outcome.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the followings were the conclusions. The findings of this study concluded that the level of artificial intelligence utilization among Undergraduate Students was moderate this means that students do not experience negative mental health as a result of utilization of artificial intelligence, the level of mental health was moderate, that the level of students' retention skills was high, Artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health, Artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' retention skills. Also, there was a significant relationship between Artificial Intelligence and Undergraduate Students' Mental Health and there was a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Higher institutions of learning should provide adequate training and support to students and lecturers to ensure they are proficient in using AI technologies effectively.
2. AI tools should be made more accessible and user-friendly to encourage increased utilization.
3. Universities and other higher Institutions of learning should establish mechanisms to monitor and evaluate the impact of AI tools on student' retention skills, learning outcomes, collecting data on variables such as student engagement, satisfaction, and performance.
4. Universities and other higher Institutions of learning should ensure that AI utilization by undergraduate students is not abuse in such a way that could affect their mental health negatively.

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Qualitative Study on... (Akanimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Qualitative Study on Philosophical Issues in Teaching and Learning Outcomes of Secondary School Students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Some philosophical schools (on teaching approaches) and proffered teaching approaches methods have been captured in this study to further examine and proffer effective teaching methods for teachers. The study adopted a quantitative research design which involve a historical method analysis and prescription. Thus, the study looked at philosophical schools of thought on teaching approaches like essentialism, perennialism, progressivism, social reconstructionism, conservatism and humanism, and their views on teaching approaches/ methods. The study concludes that teaching should be student-centered, teacher-centered and society-centered among others. The researchers recommended among others that different approaches or methods should be applied in the teaching and learning process, as this will benefit each student at their different levels of ability and capability.

Keywords: Philosophical issues, Teaching strategies, Secondary schools, Education

Introduction

Teaching is to assist the pupil to learn and acquire the desired knowledge, skills and also desirable ways of living in the society (Dewey, 2018). It is a process in which learners, teacher, curriculum and other variables are organized in a systematic and psychological way to attain some predetermined goals (Dewey, 2018). The chief task of education is, above all, to shape man or to guide the evolving dynamism through which man forms himself as a man. Teaching by philosophers refers to the pedagogical approaches and methods employed by philosophers or teachers to convey philosophical ideas, concepts, and critical thinking skills to students (Plato, 380 BCE). Philosophers often use innovative and engaging teaching methods to encourage critical thinking, dialogue, and reflection. Some common approaches include; Socratic method which involves encouraging questioning and dialogue to explore ideas and concepts (Paul et al., 2006). Critical thinking exercises; using logical thinking skills, exploring complex ideas through hypothetical scenarios and imaginative exercises (Paul et al, 2006). Philosophical debates; encouraging students to engage in respectful debates and discussions on philosophical topics (Paul et al., 2006). Reflective journaling; encouraging students to reflect on their thoughts, ideas and beliefs through writing (Paul et al., 2006). Case study; analyzing real-life scenarios and applying philosophical concepts to practice issues and conceptual analysis, breaking down complex concepts into their constituent parts to understand their meaning and implications.

An effective teacher at secondary school level of education in Cross River State.

The skills needed for effective teaching involves more than just expertise in an academic field. There should be strong communication skills; the teacher must be able to interact with people and help them understand a new way of looking at the world, this is not an easy job. Although there are many different ways to teach effectively, good instructors have several qualities in common; they are prepared, set clear and fair expectations, have a positive attitude, are patient with students and assess their teaching on a regular basis. They have a deep understanding of the subject matter being taught, and have the ability to create and maintain a well-organized and respectful classroom environment. They are able to adjust their teaching strategies

Qualitative Study on... (Akanimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

to fit both the students and the materials, recognizing that different students learn in different ways. They have the ability to think critically and solve problems, the ability to understand and manage one's own emotions and the emotions of others. They are flexible, which means they adopt to changing circumstances and are flexible in teaching approaches. These qualities will be respected in the attitudes of the students. Keep the students engaged with a positive attitude. Teaching is most effective when students are motivated by the desire to learn, rather than grades or degree requirements. The student should be thought of as a team mates, not adversaries. Learning and teaching are challenging, but that does not mean that the teacher cannot have fun in the classroom. Stay focused, but not afraid to be creative and innovative. The teacher should allow himself to be enthusiastic and find ways to let students see what is interesting about their subject. Effective teachers can explain complex ideas in simple ways. The teacher should keep the students thinking; unless they are using the concepts the teacher is teaching, most students will remember only a small fraction of what they are taught. The teacher should consider using the classroom time for activities order than traditional lectures, discussions or question and answer sessions, problem solving exercises in small groups can take not more than a few minutes, yet students should be allowed to engage with the material being covered.

Each individual has an attitude towards life, children, politics, learning and previous personal experiences that inform and shape their set of beliefs or personal philosophy, informs how one lives, works and interact with others. What one believes is directly reflected in both one's teachings and learning process. This is why it is important that subject that teach tolerance and respect for one another be not just included in the curriculum but be properly taught (Onah et al., 2021). It is important to understand how philosophy and education are interrelated. In order to become the most effective teacher one can be, one must understand one's own beliefs, while at the same time empathizing with others. The major philosophies of education can be broken down into three main types; teacher centered philosophies, student centered philosophies, and society- centered philosophies. These include essentialism, perennialism, progressivism, social reconstructionisms, existentialism, behaviorism, constructivism, conservatism and humanism.

Conceptual clarification on teaching strategies at secondary school level of education in Cross River State.

1. **Philosophical issues:** This refers to fundamental problems, questions, or concerns that arise from the study of philosophy, encompassing various branches such as metaphysics, epistemology, ethics, logic and aesthetics (CDP, 2015). These issues often involve abstracts, fundamental questions, conceptual ambiguities, theoretical debates and methodological concerns like; who is an effective teacher? And what are the most effective and appropriate teaching methods?
2. **Teaching strategies:** This refers to the process of facilitating learning, guiding and monitoring students to acquire knowledge, skills, values and attitudes (CDP, 2015). It involves transmission of knowledge, facilitating learning, guiding, monitoring, role modeling, building relationship encouraging critical thinking and creating learning experience amongst others.
3. **Secondary schools:** the philosophical meaning of secondary school can be explore from various perspectives, for the purpose of this study, it is a platform for transmitting knowledge from teacher to student. It encourages critical thinking development as students learn to analysis, evaluate, and synthesize information (Steffe, 2018).
4. **Learning outcomes:** This can be understood through various lenses, philosophically; Pragmatism: Learning outcomes are the practical applications of knowledge, emphasizing utility and effectiveness (Taylor, 2019). Constructivism: Learning outcomes are the constructed meanings and understandings individuals create through experience and social interaction (Taylor, 2019). Essentialism: Learning outcomes are the essential knowledge, skills, and values that constitute a well- educated person (Baehr, 2019). Existentialism: Learning outcomes are the personal, subjective, and authentic experiences that foster individual growth and self-awareness. For the purpose of this study, learning outcomes are specific, measurable and achievable statements that describe what students will know, understand and are able to do as a result of a learning experience (Heyman, 2020).

Theoretical framework

Essentialism and perennialism are two types of teacher-centered philosophies of education. Essentialism is currently the leading style of public education in the United States (Ornstein et al., 2018). It is the teaching of basic skills that have been proven over time to be needed in society. Perennialism focuses on the teaching of great works. There are three types of student-centered philosophies of education; progressivism focuses on developing the students' moral compass and humanism is about fostering each student to his or her fullest potential. Constructivism focuses on using education to shape a students' world view (Steffe, 2018).

There are two types of socially- centered philosophies of education; progressivism focuses on developing the students' moral compass. Humanism is about fostering each student to his or her fullest potential. Constructivism focuses on using

Qualitative Study on... (Akanimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

education to shape a student's world view. There are two types of socially- centered philosophies of education; reconstructionism is the perspective that education is the means to solve social problems (Taylor, 2019). Behaviorism focuses on cultivating behaviours that are beneficial to society. The constructivist teaching is based on constructivist learning theory. Constructivist teaching is based on the belief that learning occurs as learners are actively involved in a process of meaning and knowledge construction as opposed to passively receiving information (Taylor, 2019). Learners are the makers of meaning and knowledge. One of the goals of using constructivist teaching is that students learn how to learn by giving them the training to take initiative for their own learning experiences. The characteristics of a constructivist classroom are as follows; the learners are actively involved, the environment is democratic, the activities are interactive and student centered, and the teacher facilitates a process of learning in which students are encouraged to be responsible and autonomous. Furthermore, in the constructivist classroom, students work primarily in groups and learning and knowledge are interactive and dynamic (Rowe, 2011).

There is a great focus and emphasis on social and communication skills, as well as collaboration and exchange of ideas. This is contrary to the traditional classroom in which students work primarily alone, learning is achieved through repetition, and the subjects are strictly adhered to and are guided by a textbook. Some activities encouraged in constructivist classrooms are;

Experimentation: Students individually perform an experiment and then come together as a class to discuss the results (Rowe, 2011). Research projects: Students research a topic and can present their findings to the class, Field trips: This allows students to put the concepts and ideas discussed in class in a real-world context. Field trips would often be followed by class discussions films. These provide visual context and thus bring another sense into the learning experience (Lipman, 2015). Class discussions: This technique is used in all of the methods described above. It is one of the most important distinctions of constructivist teaching methods (Bell, 2017). Campus wikis: These provide learners with a platform for curative helpful learning resources (Bell, 2017).

Constructivist approaches can also be used in online learning. For example, tools such as discussion forums, wikis and blogs can enable learners to actively construct knowledge. In the constructivist classroom, the teacher's role is to prompt and facilitate discussion. Thus, the teachers main focus should be on guiding students by asking questions that will lead them to develop their own conclusion on the subject. Good teachers join self, subject, and students in the fabric of life because they teach from an integral and undivided self, they manifest in their own lives and evoke in their students, a capacity for connectedness. Learning is driven by the problem to be solved, students learn context and theory in order to solve the problem. This is different from traditional objectivist teaching where the theory would be presented first and problems would be used afterwards to practice theory (Rowe, 2011). In constructivist teaching the process of gaining knowledge is viewed as being just as important as the product. Thus, assessment is based not only on tests but also on observation of the students, the students' work and the students' point of view (Onah et al., 2021). One possible deferent for this teaching method is that, due to the emphasis on group work, the ideas of the more active students may dominate the group's conclusion. On the other hand, educational essentialism is an educational philosophy whose adherents believe that children should learn the traditional basic subjects thoroughly (Heyman, 2020).

In this philosophical school of thought, the aim is to instill students with the 'essentials' of academic knowledge, enacting a back to fundamental approach. Essentialism ensures that the accumulated wisdom of our civilization as taught in the traditional academic disciplines is passed on from teacher to student. Such disciplines might include reading, writing, literature, foreign languages, history, mathematics, science, art and music (Rowe, 2011). This traditional approach is meant to train the mind, promote reasoning, and ensure a common culture. Essentialism is a relatively conservative stance to education that strives to teach students the knowledge of a society, and civilization through a core curriculum (Heyman, 2020). This core curriculum involves such areas that include the study of the surrounding environment, basic natural laws, and the disciplines that encourage a happier, more educated living (Baehr, 2019). Other non- traditional areas are also integrated as well in moderation to balance the education. Essentialists goals are to instill students with the 'essentials' of academic knowledge, patriotism and character development through traditional (or back to basics) approaches. This is to promote reasoning, train the mind, and ensure a common culture for all citizens.

Essentialism as a teacher-centered philosophy

The role of the teacher as a leader of the classroom is a very important tenet of educational essentialism (Rowe, 2015). The teacher is the center of the classroom, so they should be rigid and disciplinary. Establishing order in the classroom is crucial for students learning, effective teaching cannot take place in a loud and disorganized environment. It is the teachers' responsibility to keep order in the classroom. The teacher must interpret essentials of the learning process, take the leadership

Qualitative Study on... (Akanimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

position and set the tone of the classroom. These needs require an educator who is academically well-qualified with an appreciation for learning and development. The teacher must control the students with distributions of rewards and penalties.

Although it is difficult to maintain a pure and strict essentialist only-curriculum, these schools have the central aim of establishing a common knowledge base for all citizens (Rowe, 2015). To do so, they follow a nationwide, content-specific, and teacher-centered curriculum. The core knowledge curriculum also allows for local variance above and beyond the core curriculum. Central curricular aims are academic excellence and the learning of knowledge, and teachers who are masters of their knowledge areas serve this aim. Because Essentialism is largely teacher-centered, the role of the student is often called into question. Presumably, in an essentialist classroom, the teacher is the one designing the curriculum for the students based upon the core disciplines. Moreover, he or she is enacting the curriculum and setting the standards which the students must meet. The teachers' evaluative role may undermine students' interest in study. As a result, the students begin to take on more of a passive role in their education as they are forced to meet and learn such standards and information.

Furthermore, Educational Perennialism is a normative educational philosophy. Perennialists believe that one should teach the things that are of everlasting pertinence to all people everywhere, and that the emphasis should be on principles, not facts (Taylor, 2019). Since people are human, one should teach first about human, rather than machines or techniques and about liberal, rather than vocational topics. Although perennialism may appear similar to essentialism, perennialism focuses first on personal development, while essentialism focuses first on essential skills. Essentialist curricula thus tend to be much more vocational and fact-based, and far less liberal and principle-based. Both philosophies are typically considered to be teacher-centered, as opposed to student-centered philosophies of education such as progressivism. However, since the teacher associated with perennialism are in a sense the authors of the Western masterpieces themselves, these teachers may be open to student criticism through the associated Socratic method, which, if carried out as true dialogue, involves a balance between teacher activity and student activity with the teacher promoting discussion.

Perennialists believe that reading is to be supplemented with mutual investigations (between the teacher and the student) and minimally-directed discussions through the Socratic method in order to develop a historically-oriented understanding of concepts (Taylor, 2019). They argue that accurate, independent reasoning distinguishes the developed or educated mind and they thus stress the development of this faculty. A skilled teacher would keep discussions on topic and correct errors in reasoning, but it would be the class, not the teacher, who would reach the conclusions while not directing or leading the class to a conclusion, the teacher may work to accurately formulate problems within the scope of the texts being studied.

Perennialists freely acknowledge that any particular selection of great books will disagree on many topics, however, they see this as an advantage, rather than a detriment (Lipman, 2015). They believe that the student must learn to recognize such disagreements which often reflect current debates. The student becomes responsible for thinking about the disagreements and reaching a reasoned, defensible conclusion. This is a major goal of the Socratic discussions. They do not advocate teaching a settled scholarly interpretation of the books, which would cheat the student of the opportunity to learn rational criticism and to know his own mind.

One of the problems of perennialism is the issue of enlightenment; it is all about an individual attainment and not about the greater good of the human and natural communities that make our individual lives possible. Enlightenment offers nothing towards a sustainable future for humans and planet earth beyond the freedom from suffering that individual humans allegedly achieve through their own attainment of enlightenment. Spirituality is often considered to be in no small part, about growing beyond our selfish and self-centered tendencies, enlightenment appears to be the ultimate expression of self-centeredness. Another and perhaps the most troubling problem with enlightenment is that nobody can seem to agree on what it actually is. If enlightenment is truly the purpose and destiny of all human life, then those who attain enlightenment should describe it the same way, or at least in similar ways.

Progressivism – Philosophy of teaching/ education

Progressivists believe that education should focus on the whole child rather than on the content or the teacher (Baehr, 2019). This educational philosophy stresses that students should test ideas by active experimentation. Learning is rooted in the question of learners that arise through experiencing the world. It is active not passive. The learner is a problem solver and thinker who make meaning through his or her individual experience in the physical and cultural context. Effective teachers provide experiences that students can learn by doing. Curriculum content is derived from students' interest and questions. The scientific method is used by progressivists educators so that students can study matter and events systematically and first hand. The emphasis is on process- how one comes to know. John Dewey was its foremost proponent. One of his tenets was that

Qualitative Study on... (Akanimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

school should improve the way of life of our citizens through experiencing freedom and democracy in schools. Shared decision making, planning of teachers with students, student-selected topics are all aspects. Books are tools, rather than authority.

Social Reconstructionism

Is a philosophy that emphasizes the addressing of social question and a quest to create a better society and worldwide democracy (Onah et al., 2021). Reconstructionist educators focus on a curriculum that highlights social reform as the aim of education. Theodore Brameld was the founder of social reconstructionism, in reaction against the realities of World War II. He recognized the potential for either human annihilation through technology and human cruelty or the capacity to create a beneficent society using technology and human compassion. George Counts recognized that education was the means of preparing people for creating this new social order.

Critical theorists like social reconstructionist, believe that systems must be changed to overcome oppression and improve human conditions. In their view human must learn to resist oppression and not become its victims, nor oppress others. To do so requires dialogue and critical consciousness, the development of awareness to overcome domination and oppression. Rather than ‘teaching as banking’ in which the educator deposits information into students’ heads. They see teaching and learning as a process of inquiry in which the child must invent and reinvent the world. For social reconstructionist and critical theorists, curriculum focuses on student experience and taking social action on real problems, such as violence, hunger, international terrorism, inflation, and inequality. Strategies for dealing with controversial issues (particularly in social studies and literature), inquiry, dialogue, and multiple perspectives are the focus. Community-based learning and bring the world into the classroom are also strategies.

Existentialism

Is a philosophy that emphasizes individual existence, freedom and choice (Dewey, 2018). It is the view that humans define their own meaning in life, and try to make rational decisions despite existing in an irrational universe. It focuses on the question of human existence and the feeling that there is no purpose or explanation at core of existence. It holds that, as there is no God or any other transcendent force, the only way to counter this nothingness (and hence to find meaning in life) is by embracing existence. Thus, existentialism believes that individuals are entirely free and must take personal responsibility for themselves (although with this responsibility comes a profound anguish or dread). It therefore, emphasizes actions, freedom and decision as fundamental, and holds that the only way to rise above the essentially absurd condition of humanity (which is characterized by suffering and inevitable death) is by exercising our personal freedom and choice (a complete rejection of determinism. It asserts that people actually make decisions based on what has meaning to them, rather than what is rational. The important factor for existentialists is the freedom of choice to believe or not to believe.

Teachers must allow students freedom of choice and provide them with experiences that will help them find the meaning of their lives. Every individual first exists and then what his or her existence means to him or her. If students have individual freedom, ask their own questions and draw their own conclusion they will be able to find themselves as well as find out the meaning of their existence. They will have freedom to create what they desire. As a teacher, the students’ needs are extremely important. A way the teacher can best meet their needs is by offering student-teacher conferences inside or outside of class time. The discussion can be anything that is on their mind. It is important that a student knows that they can talk to their teacher. They should be comfortable around their teacher.

Behaviorism

Behaviourism can also be taught of as a form of classroom management. Behaviourists believe human beings are shaped entirely by their external environment (Dewey, 2018). If you alter a person’s environment, you will alter his or her thoughts, feelings and behaviours. The system’s-based rewards and punishments. Behaviourists believe that if teachers provide positive reinforcements or rewards, whenever students perform a desired behavior, they will learn to perform the behavior on their own, the same concept applies to punishments. Behaviourist think that people act in response to internally or externally generated physical stimuli. They basically consider human nature to be the product of one’s environment. An example of behaviourism is when teacher reward their class or certain students with a party or special treats at the end of the week for good behavior throughout the week. The same concept is used with punishments. The teacher can take away certain privileges if the students misbehave.

Behaviourism teaching methods have proven most successful in areas where there is a ‘correct’ response or easily memorized material. Behaviourist teaching methods tend to rely on so-called ‘skill and drill’ exercise to provide the consistent repetition necessary for effective enforcement of response patterns. Other methods include question (stimulus) and answer (response) framework in which questions are of gradually increasing difficulty, guided practice and regular reviews of material. Behaviourist methods also typically heavily depend on the use of positive reinforcement such as verbal praise, good grades and

Qualitative Study on... (Akanimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

prizes. Behaviourists assess the degree of learning using methods that measure observable behavior such as exam performance, behaviourist teaching methods have proven most successful in areas where there is a 'correct' response or easily memorized material. For example, while behaviourists methods have proven to be successful in teaching structured material such as facts and formulae, scientific concepts, and foreign language vocabulary, their efficacy in teaching comprehension, composition and analytical abilities is questionable.

It's easy to see how operant conditioning can be used for classroom management. There are many behaviours that need to be shaped (an operant term) in order to have an orderly classroom. There are indeed some classroom behaviours that need to be shaped in order to enhance learning. For example, students could receive negative punishment for having their phones out. This might mean that they do not receive their daily attendance points. Research indicates that cell phones pull attention (Dewey, 2018).

1. So, we can use operant conditioning to increase attention and learning. However, this type of behavioural management is not the main take away here, instead, we should talk about the increasing use of good study strategies. You have seen unfortunately for many reasons, students do not readily change their study strategies, even when shown evidence that the new strategies are better.
2. In order to encourage the use of good study strategies, students need to see the direct consequence of using them. One way to do this is to give them practice using their own strategy and then require them to study some small bit of material using the new strategy you are teaching. The immediate and direct feedback that shows a higher grade is a positive reinforcement. The teacher can also provide positive reinforcement in class. He can use praise or extra credit for students who demonstrate that they are using the new strategies to try and shape their behavior. One key is that the consequence should come fairly quickly after the behavior, which is what makes this such a challenge.

Conservatism- as a teacher-centered philosophy

Conservatism can be defined as traditional, respecting 'the old ways. A conservative education preserves the traditional curriculum, occurring to transmit information to the students as a means of bringing them into an already established culture. Conservatists are way of individualism and change and foster assimilation and acceptance into society. They believe the primary role of education is academics, custodial, therapeutic and social functions. Such functions are believed to weaken educations.

Conclusion

The different schools of philosophical teaching approaches represent the different teaching methods that should be used in our classroom. All these approaches are vital in the effective teaching and learning process. Although teaching as a concept goes beyond what each philosophical school of thoughts says it is. Teaching should be student centered, teacher centered and society centered; since for effective teaching and of course learning to happen and for the right things to be taught to the learner for the learner to become useful to himself and the society, the teacher, learner and the society must be involved in the teaching process. Therefore, the school curriculum should be revisited from time to time for necessary adjustments. Different methods of teaching should be applied in the classrooms since each student may have different levels of absorbing or understanding what is being taught; while some students learn faster than others. It is also important to note that all learners are achievers, although some may achieve slower than others, therefore the teacher has to be patient and sometimes enduring with the slow achievers. All hands must be on deck; all stake holders in education should always be at the top of their game, meeting when necessary to find out ways to take the education sector to the next level.

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Recommendations

1. Teaching should be student, teacher and even society centered for effective teaching and learning experience.
2. The school curriculum should be revisited to capture the above (number 1).
3. Different methods should be applied in the teaching process, so as to reach each students at their different levels of ability and absorption of information.
4. All stakeholders in education should from time to time come together to discuss successes and progress made so far, adjustments where necessary and adequate funding for the education section.

Qualitative Study on... (Akanimoh, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

5. Teachers should be patient and sometimes enduring with the slow achievers or learners in class. This is why they need to apply different teaching methods during lesson to reach all.

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Assessment on availability... (Ezurike, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Assessment on Availability and Utilization of Instructional Materials for Teaching and Learning of Literature-in-English among Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja

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Abstracts

This study assessed the availability and utilization of instructional materials for teaching and learning of Literature-in-English among secondary schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja. Three specific objectives with corresponding research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study and a four-point scale model of questionnaire was used as research instrument. The population of the study comprised 915 Art students and 22 English Language teachers in Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada Area Council. The sample size of 292 respondents was drawn using simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques using an intact class. The instrument was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.89 was obtained using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient which implies the instrument is reliable. The method of data analysis was carried out using descriptive statistical tools such as frequency counts, percentages and mean scores for the research questions and demographic data. The hypotheses were tested using the t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the analysis showed that there was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada [$t_{\text{value}} = 1.413$, $df = 290$, $P < 0.05$]; there was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada [$t_{\text{value}} = 0.641$, $df = 290$, $P > 0.05$]; there was a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada [$t_{\text{value}} = 2.694$, $df = 290$, $P > 0.05$]. The research concluded that teachers need support to effectively utilize the available instructional facilities to enhance the teaching and learning of Literature-in-English thereby boosting students' understanding and performance in the subject. Based on the findings, it is recommended among others that: more instructional facilities should be made available and accessible to schools so that teachers would utilize them frequently and they should be trained to utilize such resources to support their efficiency.

Keywords: Availability, utilization, instructional materials, curriculum and Literature-in-English

Introduction

Education is said to be the process through which experienced and knowledgeable members of the society (teachers) impart knowledge into the inexperienced learners so as to develop their skills. This teaching and learning process occurs or takes place in varying ways and in different places. In an informal educational sitting, the teaching and learning process could take place in a workshop, on the farm, or in any place where learners are taught practical lessons. Ogbuanya and Okoye, 2015 noted that this practical-oriented teaching and learning process often results in a more fruitful way especially when the objective is to acquire or develop skills. In the realm of formal education, however, the classroom is the main or primary theatre where teaching and learning operations take place. The ideas and skills taught are presented in forms of lessons in the classroom.

Uchechi (2021) noted that this form of learning often leads to the acquisition of abstract knowledge and ideas which the learner may not be able to apply them outside the classroom. This underscores the importance of having a real-time experience in the teaching and learning process. Learning outside the classroom is vital to students' understanding and appreciation of the real-world phenomena. Because the concepts and ideas taught in the classroom exists in the real world around us, and learners may better understand and appreciate them when they have an experience of the real situations or contexts outside the classroom, teachers often try to recreate this existential reality by bringing into the classroom, materials and other resources that may give the learners these experiences that they need to master the ideas and concepts taught. The teacher my sometimes too, decide to take the students outside the classroom to learn about certain things that may not be authentically recreated in the classroom.

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Language and literature where the learning points (concepts and ideas) are largely abstract, connecting with the real world situation, not only make learning real and meaningful but also helps the learner to better appreciate what is taught or learned. Learning barriers caused by the abstract nature of language and literature dissolve as learners connect with and learn from their environment, (Kouider and Mohammed (2019). Literature, essentially, is said to be a reflection of the society because it mirrors the culture and activities of the people in a particular society. Hence, the best way to teach and understand literary concepts and texts might be to connect with the social situations in the society which literary text mirrors. In other words, to teach students about the culture and activities of a particular people as reflected in a literary text, it makes more sense to engage and connect them with the people whose culture they are being taught. For example, imagine the interactions that occur among students and the teacher when they visit a museum which exhibits the cultural artefacts discussed in a literary text they are studying. Such a visit offers them the opportunity to talk about what they have read in a text and are now seeing. It becomes easier to relate with what they are seeing in the museum (a phenomenon outside the classroom) to what they have learned or read in a text. Such a visit gives them the opportunity to experience and better appreciate what they have learnt in the classroom.

Jason, Gregor, Lori, Amael and Mariya (2018) opined that social discourse and direct experience help learners to better construct an understanding of literary phenomena. Certainly, learners will better appreciate and understand an aspect of a culture when they interact with the people who practice it. This explains the invaluable benefits of instructional facilities to teaching and learning generally, and to literature in particular. They believed that the use of these resources for teaching and learning creates a lasting memory and enduring learning experience for the learner. Certainly, the use of instructional facilities in teaching can make students appreciate the local and international relevance of what they learn in schools while affording them the opportunity to apply literary concepts and theories in appropriate social contexts. This is supported by Weipeng and Hui (2020), who, in her study on the development of localised instructional resources in Hong Kong, came to the conclusion that teaching and learning of humanities and social Literature-in-English subjects could be enhanced to a greater extent by using instructional resources within local contexts since such resources are often considered to be authentic and relevant to students' learning needs. Indeed, researchers have held the view that the use of instructional facilities in teaching and learning allow students to experience and discover answers to issues for themselves. This means the use of instructional facilities promote active learning that engages the learners in the process.

Furthermore, importance of instructional facilities for teaching literature in secondary schools and, indeed, at all levels of education has been well noted by scholars. Apart from enhancing the quality of teaching and learning, it is well known that the use tends to improve students' retention abilities which leads to improved academic performance/achievement since it makes learning real, authentic and more concrete Abdirahman, Willy and Mohammed, (2018). Although the use of instructional facilities can enhance teaching and learning in the classroom, the realisation of their full potential to motivate and engage students may be limited, partly because of the readiness of the teachers to use them. This is probably because some of them (the teachers) might not have acquired the skills and capacities to use the resources. As it is the case with all instructional facilities, improvisation is a major task which demands skills and expertise by the teacher since not all potentially good resources can be effectively utilized for actual classroom teaching.

Another major challenge that seems to plague the successful use of community resources for teaching literature in Nigerian secondary schools generally, and Gwagwalada in particular, is the unavailability of funds to plan and sponsor such outdoor trips for learning. When the funds to sponsor the students' trip to particular community resource centre like a museum are not readily available, there is nothing a teacher can do no matter how skilled and enthusiastic he/she might be about using such resources.

Instructional facilities that can enhance the learning of literature include physical features (like settlements, shrines, museums, mountains, river, coastal areas, desert areas and forest); human activities (that take place in workplaces, villages, shrines, places of worships, industries, markets, among others); and people in various communities (like religious leaders like chief priests, pastors, imams, community leaders like traditional rulers or government officials) Dzekoto and Daryl (2018). These should always be exploited and utilised by literature teachers to enrich the learning experiences of their students. Since the contents of literary texts reflect issues that have to do with these cultural or community features and members, when students engage with them, they tend to understand them better. This highlights the relevance of instructional facilities to the teaching or implementation of Literature-in-English curriculum. Hence, this study assessed the availability and utilization of instructional materials for teaching and learning of literature-in-English among secondary schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja.

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Objectives of the Study

1. To ascertain the availability of instructional facilities for the teaching of Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja;
2. To determine the level of utilisation of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja;
3. To examine the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja.

Research Questions

1. What are the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?
2. What are the levels of utilisation of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?
3. What are the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for this research consisted of all students in the Arts classes who offer Literature-in-English and all teachers who teach English language and Literature-in-English in the public Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja. The total number of Arts students who offer Literature-in-English students in Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada, based on the enrolment records for 2019/2020 academic session is nine hundred and fifteen (915). The number of English language and Literature-in-English teachers in various schools were twenty-two (22). The sample was drawn from all the eight public Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table for sample size determination. The purposive sampling method and simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 270 respondents were drawn from target population.

The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire titled, "Assessment of the relevance of instructional materials for teaching Literature-in-English in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (ARCRTLSSQ)". This was developed by the researcher and used for the purpose of eliciting the responses of students and teachers on the issue investigated. The questionnaire was a four-point scale model with two parts. Part A sought to elicit the respondents' demographic data, particularly their designated status (students or teachers). This constituted a categorical variable for the analysis of the hypotheses. Part B elicited respondents' responses with regard to the five issues raised by the research questions. This entails that part B of the questionnaire has five sections numbered 1 to 5 with forty (40) items numbered as follow: research question one, 1-10; research question two, 11-20; research question three, 21-30; research question four, 31-35; and research question five, 36-40. Responses to each item were graded on the scale of: Strongly Agreed (SA) = 4, Agreed (A) = 3, Disagreed (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagreed (SD) = 1; Very Great Extent (VGE) = 4, Great Extent (GE) = 3, Small Extent (SE) = 2, Very Small Extent (VSE) = 1; and Always (A) = 4, Often (O) = 3, Sometimes (S) = 2, and Never (N) = 1. To determine the validity of the instrument, face validation by experts in the Department of English Language, University of Abuja; and two Biology teachers from sampled senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja. The reliability status of the instrument gave an index of 0.89 using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (PPMC). Analysis of data was carried out using descriptive statistical tools such as frequency counts, percentages and mean scores for the research questions and demographic data. For the four-point scale, the decision rule was the midpoint of 2.50. Thus, mean scores equal to or above 2.50 signified agreements while those below 2.50 were taken to mean disagreement respectively.

Presentation of Results

Table 1: Demographic Data of the of Respondents

Designation	Frequency	Percentage %
Teachers	22	8%
Students	270	92%
Total	292	100%

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As shown in Table 1, there are total of 292 valid respondents with total of 22 respondents representing 8% of the sample were teachers while the students were 270 representing 92% of the sample.

Research Question 1

What are the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?

Table 2: The Availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada: N=292

Available instructional facilities	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Mean	Decision
Settlements	153	38	60	41	3.04	Agreed
Shrines	42	36	119	95	2.09	Disagreed
Museums	0	0	0	292	1.00	Disagreed
Theatre centres	10	65	130	87	1.99	Disagreed
Industrial centres such as workshops, blacksmith, farms, etc	202	63	21	06	3.58	Agreed
Market centres	200	64	22	06	3.57	Agreed
Worship centres such as churches, mosque, Buddhist temple, etc	212	70	10	0	3.69	agreed
Other significant physical features like rivers, mountains, etc	190	70	29	03	3.53	Agreed
Human activities that take place in workplaces, villages, shrines, places of worships, industries, markets, etc	150	71	61	10	3.24	Agreed
Human resources (significant personalities in various communities such as religious leaders (like chief priests, pastors, imams); community leaders (like traditional rulers, government officials, etc); farmers; artists, etc)	209	63	19	01	3.64	Agreed
2.94						Agreed

The data in Table 2 above presents the analysis of respondents' responses with regard to determining the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada. Based on the analysis of mean scores for each item, the respondents agreed that the following instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English are available: settlements (3.04), market centres (3.57) and industrial centres (such as workshops, blacksmith or farms) (3.58). They also agreed that worship centres (church/mosque, Buddhist temple) and physical features such as (rivers or mountains) are available in their communities as indicated by the mean scores of 3.69 and 3.53 respectively. Others include the human activities that take place in workplaces, villages, shrines, places of worships, industries, markets, etc. (3.24) and human resources (significant personalities like community leaders, religious leaders, artists, farmers) that could be utilized to facilitate the teaching of Literature-in-English in their schools (3.64).

The cumulative computation of mean scores recorded for individual items under this research question yielded the sectional mean of 2.94 which indicates agreement, having been higher than the 2.50 decision rule. This serves to indicate the respondents have accepted that the instructional facilities listed above was available for the purpose of teaching and learning Literature-in-English in secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

Research Question 2

What are the levels of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?

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Table 3: Level of Utilization of the Available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada: N=292

ITEM	A (4)	O (3)	S (2)	N (1)	Mean	Decision
A visit to the local settlements	20	15	117	140	1.71	Sometimes
A visit to the shrine	0	0	101	191	1.35	Never
A visit to the museum	0	0	120	172	1.41	Never
A visit to the Theatre centres	01	23	117	151	1.57	Sometimes
A visit to industrial centres including workshops, blacksmith, farms, etc.	04	28	154	106	1.76	Sometimes
A visit to market centres	0	0	204	88	1.70	Sometimes
A visit to a worship center (such as the church/mosque, Buddhist temple)	0	18	166	108	1.75	Sometimes
A visit to other significant physical features like rivers, mountains, etc.	22	01	167	102	1.80	Sometimes
An excursion to observe significant human activities that take place in workplaces, villages, shrines, places of worships, industries, markets, etc.	12	08	207	65	1.89	Sometimes
Interaction with significant personalities in the local community such as religious leaders (like chief priests, pastors, imams); community leaders (like traditional rulers, government officials, etc); farmers; artists, etc	18	0	166	108	1.75	Sometimes

1.67 Sometimes

Table 3 above presents the analysis of respondents' responses to determine the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada. The result of the analysis as shown the table indicates that the English language teachers utilized the following instructional facilities to teach Literature-in-English sometimes: local settlements (1.71), theatre centres (1.57), industrial centres including workshops, blacksmith, farms, etc. (1.76) and market centres (1.70). Sometimes too, they utilized worship centres (1.75), physical features like mountains, rivers, (1.80), human activities (1.89) and resource persons (1.75). Given that the sectional mean of 1.67 is far below the decision rule of 2.50, the study concludes that the available instructional facilities are only used sometimes to teach and learn Literature-in-English in secondary schools in Gwagwalada. Therefore, the current level of their utilization is poor.

Research Question 3

What are the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?

Table 6: Extent of Respondents' Perception of relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada. N=292

ITEM	VGE (4)	GE (3)	SE (2)	VSE (1)	Mean	Decision
Settlements	225	59	08	0	3.74	VGE
Shrines	37	37	124	94	2.06	SE
Museums	158	86	36	12	3.34	GE
Theatre centres	200	75	15	02	3.62	VGE
Industrial centres including workshops, blacksmith, farms, etc	163	90	27	12	3.38	GE
Market centres	168	78	32	14	3.37	GE
Worship centres (church/mosque, Buddhist temple)	209	63	01	0	3.64	VGE

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Other significant physical features like rivers, mountains, etc	225	59	08	0	3.74	VGE
Human activities that take place in workplaces, villages, shrines, places of worships, industries, markets, etc.	200	75	15	02	3.62	VGE
Human resources i.e. significant personalities in various communities such as religious leaders (like chief priests, pastors, imams); community leaders (like traditional rulers, government officials, etc); farmers; artists, etc	168	88	24	12	3.41	GE

3.39 GE

Table 6 above presents the analysis of respondents' responses so as to determine the extent to which the use of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools is relevant for improving students' understanding of the subject. The sectional mean score of 3.39 which the analysis yielded is above the decision rule of 2.50, and falls with the mean score range of 'to a great extent'. On this basis, the study concludes that the respondents perceived that the use of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools is relevant for improving students' understanding of the subject to a great extent.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the opinions of teachers and students about the availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

Table 9: Result of t-test Analysis on the difference between Respondents' Perceptions of the availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada

Designation	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
Teacher	22	3.01	0.21	1.413	290	0.159	Accepted
Student	270	2.93	0.27				

P-Value of 0.159 > 0.05

The analysis shown in Table 9 was computed to determine whether there is a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada or not. The result shows a significant value of 0.159 which is more than the 0.05 level of significance set as the decision rule. Consequently, the hypothesis has been accepted, which means, there was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the availability of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the opinions of teachers and students about the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

Table 10: Result of t-test Analysis on the difference between Respondents' Perceptions about the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada

Designation	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
Teacher	22	1.70	0.27	0.641	290	0.522	Accepted
Student	270	1.67	0.27				

P-Value of 0.522 > 0.05

The result of a t-test shown in table 10 above was carried out to determine whether there is a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching

Assessment on availability... (Ezurike, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada or not. The result shows a significant value of 0.522 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance set as decision rule, consequently, the hypothesis has been accepted. This entailed that there was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the current level of utilization of the available instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the opinions of teachers and students about the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja.

Table 11: Result of t-test Analysis on the difference between the Respondents' Perceptions about the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja

Designation	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
Teacher	22	3.56	0.24	2.694	290	0.007	Rejected
Student	270	3.38	0.31				

P-Value of 0.007 < 0.05

The analysis in 11 above was carried out to determine whether there is a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the extent to which the use of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in senior secondary schools is relevant for improving students' understanding of the subject or not. The significant value of 0.007 realized from the analysis is less than 0.05 level of significance set as the decision rule, and the hypothesis stands rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students about the relevant instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English among senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study are quite significant in several ways. Largely, there are substantial areas of its consistency with previous empirical studies, however, each study has its own uniqueness and this (current study) is certainly not an exception. Below are some implications of the findings in relation to other existing studies in literature:

The first finding is that the respondents affirmed the availability of certain instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in their communities such as: settlements, market centres, industrial centres, worship centres, physical features and human resources. This affirmative result of the study is a confirmation of the findings by Dzekoto and Daryl (2018) and Abdulkareem (2016), who in their separate studies also found that certain instructional facilities were available for utilization by teachers to teach their students. Interestingly, all the studies found that most of those resources were largely left unutilized. The main implication here is that there were a number of instructional facilities which the students and teachers affirmed that they are within their reach, and could be utilized for teaching and learning Literature-in-English. Whether these are used or not depends on several other factors which the study also shed light on.

The second finding that the available instructional facilities are utilized sometimes to teach and learn Literature in English in secondary schools in Gwagwalada is not also novel in the light of the findings of other previous studies reviewed. Particularly, Abdirahman, Willy and Mohammed (2018) study found that most of the materials were not adequately utilized which collaborate the current study's finding that the current level of instructional facilities utilization is poor. What this entails is that a valuable means of improving teacher's and students' performance in school (at least in Literature-in-English as a subject) is being ignored. This also entails that the link to maintaining a good relationship between the school and the community is not taken up. The outcome is the circle of poor achievement of students since adequate classroom support that would have improved their understanding of, and performance in the subject is not being properly utilized.

The third finding pertains to extent to which the respondents perceive that the use of instructional facilities for teaching and learning Literature-in-English could be relevant for improving students' understanding of the subject. In line with Abdulkarim's (2016) finding, the use of community tends to better student's understanding and performance in the subject used. In the same vein, Ogah's (2016) indicated that his respondents perceived the use of instructional facilities in the teaching of Literature to be of immense help to students' understanding of drama texts that have related cultural concepts. This implies that community instructional facilities, like most other resources, are relevant teaching resources as far as the teaching and learning of Literature-in-English is concerned. If these have been found to be relevant to a great extent, the implication for

Assessment on availability... (Ezurike, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

teachers is to ensure that the available resources in their communities are not left untapped or unutilized. It would do them (the teachers) and their students a great favour if the resources which have been affirmed to be very relevant for teaching Literature-in-English are adequately utilized, perhaps, the performance of their students in this subject would improve.

This study also confirmed the finding of Dunn's (2009) study in which the respondents perceived that the major setback against effective use of instructional facilities to teach and learn Literature-in-English in secondary schools are: lack of resources (finance) to support the utilization of the resources that require funding or access fees (as in the case of Dunn's study) and inaccessibility of most of these resources and resources centres. However, the studies (Dunn's and current) also found divergent views especially pertaining to teacher's unwillingness and lack of skills required for effectively utilizing some instructional facilities for the teaching and learning of Literature-in-English. While this is the position of Dunn's (2009) study, in the current study, the respondents disagreed that the inadequate or poor level of utilization of instructional facilities is not attributed to teacher's desire or lack of skills. On the contrary too, the current study found that lack of desire or will toward the utilization of instructional facilities is attributed to school managers, rather than the teachers. It is the poor or total absence of will to support the use of instructional facilities by the school managers that transmit to lack of funding or poor funding for projects or programmes that support the utilization of instructional facilities in schools. Thus, the implication is that, for schools to start utilization the available resources, especially those that require funding (such as inviting a resource person to the school, sponsoring an excursion trip to a museum, workshop, physical feature, etc.) the school managers must support teaching through adequate funding to enable them plan and implement such lofty educational programmes that have great impact on the quality of learning of their students.

The positions (findings) of the current study do not differ significantly with any known previous studies with regard to the findings from the analysis of hypotheses. The respondents who were students and teachers in the sampled schools in Gwagwalada Area Council were unanimous in their opinions regarding all of the areas of investigation. However, the finding from the analysis of hypothesis two indicate that the teachers and the students held significantly, different views regarding the extent of utilization of the available community resources for teaching Literature-in-English in Senior Secondary Schools in Gwagwalada. This divergence, however, does not invalidate the general perception that most of the community resources investigated was largely unutilized. The teachers (who had a higher mean) only seem to believe that they were using more of those resources but the fact that their mean is also below 2.50 is a confirmation that they also agreed that the level or extent of utilization was inadequate or poor. Since the level of utilization is confirmed to be poor or low, more efforts should be channeled towards supporting teachers to properly and adequately utilize them to improve their students' understanding and performance in the subject.

Conclusion

Having examined, per students' and teachers' opinions, the relevance of instructional facilities for teaching Literature-in-English in secondary schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja, the study concludes that there are many instructional facilities which could be utilized to support the teaching and learning of Literature-in-English in various school communities in the study area. Given the importance of such facilities to the teaching and learning process, it is disappointing that the level of utilization at the time of this study is low, poor or inadequate. The study therefore, concludes that teachers need support to effectively utilize the available instructional facilities to enhance the teaching and learning of Literature-in-English, so as to boost students' understanding and performance in the subject. Accordingly, there are a number of specific recommendations made in the next segment.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings made in this study, and the conclusion drawn above, the following recommendations were made:

1. Although there are several instructional facilities available for teaching Literature-in-English, more should be made accessible to schools so that teachers would be encouraged to utilize them frequently to support the teaching and learning of the subject in schools.
2. More efforts should be made by teachers to utilize instructional facilities to teach their students since they are perceived to be useful. This could be done by training teachers to improve their efficiency in the use of these facilities for teaching Literature-in-English.
3. School managers, government agencies and even non-governmental organizations working in education sector should support teachers with the requisite facilities (funds) to frequently sponsor school trips to resource centres or to invite resource persons from the community to visit the school for the purpose of supporting teaching and learning. This

Assessment on availability... (Ezurike, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929635>

would promote the utilization of instructional facilities for teaching and learning and equally deepen the relationship between the school and the community.

4. Instructional facilities centres where there is access fees should consider making them freely available to schools so as to encourage teachers to frequently use such facilities to promote teaching and learning.
5. In-service training opportunities for teachers should be created to teach teachers how to utilize instructional facilities for teaching and learning since they have been found to be very relevant.

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Perception of Skill Development for Effective Instructional Delivery in Social Studies among Upper Basic Teachers in Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Upper basic teachers in Niger State, Nigeria. Grounded in Human Capital Theory and Skill-Biased Technological Change (SBTC), the research explores the importance of ongoing professional development in enhancing teachers' competencies, given the evolving demands of modern education. A descriptive survey design was employed and the population of the study consist of all upper basic social studies teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Niger state; a sample size of 153 teachers were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled: (PSDFEIDSOSUBT), experts were sought to confirm the instrument's validity and a pilot project was conducted to ascertain its reliability. The results were analyzed through descriptive statistics and a one-sample t-test. The findings reveal that while teachers recognize the value of skill development, there is a significant concern about the adequacy and effectiveness of current resources and training programs. The cumulative mean score of 3.27 indicates a generally positive perception of skill development, but gaps remain in meeting the specific needs of Social Studies teachers. The study underscores the need for more targeted and adequately resourced professional development initiatives to ensure that teachers are well-equipped to deliver effective instruction. The variability in perceptions suggests disparities in access to quality development opportunities, pointing to the necessity for systemic improvements in educational support. This research highlights the critical role of skill development in enhancing instructional delivery and improving educational outcomes in Social Studies, with broader implications for educational policy and practice in Nigeria.

Keyword: Skill, teachers, perception, Studies, Niger

Introduction

The quality of education is heavily influenced by the skills and competencies of teachers, particularly in foundational subjects such as Social Studies. Sharma and Poorva (2023) pronounced that skill development stands as an essential pillar upon which individual progress and societal advancement rest. Skill development is a powerful catalyst for economic growth, social mobility, and the reduction of income inequality. In today's world, grasping the complexities of skill development along with the opportunities it presents and the challenges it poses is not just a personal pursuit. It is a global necessity. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for shaping a more equitable and prosperous future. Social Studies forms a critical component of the curriculum at the Upper Basic level, where it serves as a conduit for imparting essential civic, moral, and social knowledge. However, the effectiveness of instructional delivery in this subject is closely tied to the ongoing professional development and skill enhancement of the teachers responsible for it. According to Saini and Chourasiya (2023) continuous learning and up-skilling are crucial for enhancing teacher's effective delivery of instruction for employability in today's fast-changing job market where technology is the driving force. The unprecedented pace of technological innovation, the globalization of economies, and the shifting nature of work have propelled the acquisition and refinement of skills to the forefront of both personal and collective aspirations (Sharma & Poorva, 2023). In a study by Akinbote (2010) on teaching Social Studies in Nigeria's colleges of education: The challenges and prospects; findings showed that Social Studies teachers who participated in regular professional development programs demonstrated significantly higher levels of instructional competence compared to those who did not. Moreover, teachers who engaged in collaborative learning communities reported greater confidence in their ability to deliver complex Social Studies content, such as human rights and democratic governance. Similarly, Olofube, Egbezor and Kpolovie (2012) in a study on teacher's professional development and quality assurance in Nigerian secondary

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schools found out that teachers who perceived their skills as inadequate were more likely to struggle with delivering content effectively, leading to lower student achievement in Social Studies.

The ongoing professional development and skill enhancement of Social Studies teachers are not merely optional but essential components in ensuring the quality of education at the Upper Basic level. As the demands of the modern world continue to evolve, so too must the skills and competencies of educators. Teachers who are equipped with the latest pedagogical strategies and who continuously refine their instructional techniques are better positioned to deliver engaging and effective lessons. This, in turn, nurtures a more informed, responsible, and capable student body, prepared to navigate the complexities of contemporary society. As the evidence from various studies suggests, investment in teacher development is an investment in the future, one that holds the promise of greater educational outcomes, social cohesion, and economic progress. Therefore, prioritizing the professional growth of Social Studies teachers is not just a matter of educational policy, but a crucial step toward building a more equitable and prosperous society.

Despite the recognized importance of skill development in enhancing instructional delivery, many Social Studies teachers at the Upper Basic level in Niger State, Nigeria, continue to face significant challenges. While ongoing professional development is crucial for keeping educators abreast of modern pedagogical strategies, there is growing concern that existing programs and resources are insufficient to meet the unique needs of Social Studies teachers. This inadequacy not only hampers their ability to deliver complex and interdisciplinary content effectively but also contributes to a sense of being underprepared and unsupported in their teaching roles. Consequently, this may lead to diminished student engagement and lower educational outcomes in a subject critical for fostering civic knowledge and social responsibility.

The problem, therefore, is to investigate the perceptions of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers in Niger State for the effectiveness and adequacy of skill development programs and resources in enhancing their instructional delivery. Understanding these perceptions is essential for identifying gaps in the current professional development framework and for proposing strategies to improve the support provided to Social Studies educators, ultimately leading to better teaching practices and improved student learning experiences.

Objectives of the study

1. Examine the perception of Upper basic Social Studies teachers' on skill development for effective instructional delivery in Niger state, Nigeria

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the question below:

1. What is the perception of Upper basic Social Studies teachers' on skill development for effective instructional delivery in Niger state, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The research hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the perception of Upper basic Social Studies teachers' on skill development for effective instructional delivery in Niger state, Nigeria

Theoretical framework

This study adopted the Human Capital Theory and Skill-Biased Technological Change (SBTC) to explain upper basic social studies teachers' perceptions of skill development for effective instructional delivery in Niger state, Nigeria:

Human Capital Theory: The theory was propounded by Becker (1964) it posits that investments in education, training, and health enhance an individual's productivity, which in turn increases their economic value or income potential. It views education and skills as forms of capital, akin to physical assets, that contribute to economic growth and personal income. The theory emphasizes that spending on education and training is a form of investment in human capital, leading to better economic outcomes for individuals and societies.

Skill-Biased Technological Change (SBTC): Authored by Katz & Krueger (1998) the theory argues that technological advancements, particularly in information and communication technology, have increased the demand for skilled labor while reducing the demand for less-skilled labor. This leads to wage disparities, with higher wages for skilled workers who can effectively use new technologies, and stagnant or declining wages for less-skilled workers. The theory helps explain the growing wage inequality observed in many economies, particularly since the late 20th century.

Perception of Skill... (Awaisu & Sarkin-Fada, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258872>

Application of Skill-Biased Technological Change and Human Capital theories to instructional delivery

The application of Human Capital Theory and SBTC Theory provides a comprehensive understanding of why Upper Basic Social Studies teachers in Niger State perceive skill development as essential for effective instructional delivery. Human Capital Theory underscores the value of skill acquisition as an investment in their professional growth, while SBTC Theory highlights the necessity of skill development in keeping pace with technological changes that impact educational practices. Together, these theories illustrate the critical role that skill development plays in enhancing instructional delivery and ultimately improving educational outcomes in Niger state and beyond.

Conceptual Issues

Perception: Perception is a multifaceted mental process that entails the interpretation and comprehension of sensory information from the environment. According to Schacter, Gilbert, Wegner and Matthew (2011) perception involves selecting, organizing, and interpreting sensory inputs to construct a coherent and meaningful representation of the world. This process is influenced by past experiences, expectations, and cultural background, as highlighted by Omolayo (2018). Nwachukwu (2017) further emphasizes that perception is the way individuals interpret and make sense of their surroundings, integrating their senses, emotions, and prior experiences.

Deduced from these definitions, we can define perception as the cognitive process by which individuals actively construct an understanding of the world by selecting, organizing, and interpreting sensory stimuli in the context of their prior knowledge, experiences, and socio-cultural background.

Skill development: Skill development is a process of identifying gaps in one's abilities and addressing them by developing, improving, and rejuvenating relevant skills needed to excel and enhance the quality of results in an assigned job. Reddy and Pujar (2021) describe this process as one that increases an individual's ability to execute tasks effectively, regardless of the domain or situation. Additionally, skill development involves acquiring new skills or enhancing existing ones to improve performance and increase capabilities in specific areas. This process can include formal education, training programs, on-the-job learning, or self-directed study. Skill development is essential for personal and professional growth, as it enables individuals to adapt to evolving job markets, enhance productivity, and pursue career advancement. It encompasses various types of skills, including technical, soft (interpersonal), cognitive, and vocational skills.

In this regard, skill development can be defined as the systematic process of acquiring, enhancing, and refining skills to improve competence and performance in specific areas. This process involves continuous learning and adaptation to meet the demands of dynamic environments, ensuring individuals remain competitive and capable of achieving their professional and personal goals.

Instructional delivery: Delivery of instruction refers to the methods and techniques employed by teachers to convey information to students and foster learning. According to Ertmer and Newby (2013), it encompasses the strategies and approaches teachers use to promote student understanding and engagement. Hattie (2015) expands on this by noting that the delivery of instruction involves not only the presentation of information but also the application of various instructional strategies and techniques, alongside the quality of teacher-student interactions. Gagné, Briggs, and Wager (1992) further define delivery of instruction as the process of transferring knowledge from the instructor to the student, emphasizing the importance of selecting appropriate instructional materials and methods, and presenting them in a clear and effective manner. Instructional delivery involves employing a spectrum of methods, techniques, and strategies to impart knowledge, nurturing skill acquisition, and competencies across diverse educational and organizational contexts (Smith et al., 2022; Johnson & Smith, 2023; Brown & Garcia, 2024).

Thus, delivery of instruction is the systematic approach by which teachers convey knowledge and skills to learners, utilizing a combination of instructional strategies, materials, and methods to facilitate understanding and retention. This definition highlights the deliberate and organized nature of instructional delivery, emphasizing the importance of clarity, interaction, and the thoughtful selection of teaching tools.

In the changing educational landscape, teachers play a crucial role in shaping students' futures. For Social Studies in Niger State, Nigeria, teacher skills and competencies are vital for effective instruction. Understanding how Social Studies teachers perceive their skill development is key to improving instructional quality. This literature review examines research on teacher perceptions of skill development and its impact on instructional practices and student outcomes in Upper Basic Social Studies in Niger State, Nigeria.

Teacher Professional Development and Instructional Delivery: Teacher professional development is a cornerstone of educational quality, particularly in disciplines such as Social Studies, which are integral to students' understanding of societal structures. As Aparicio-Molina and Sepúlveda-López (2023) emphasize, the professional growth of teachers necessitates not

Perception of Skill... (Awaisu & Sarkin-Fada, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258872>

only the provision of structured opportunities and practices that foster such development but also the recognition of the existing competencies and evolving capabilities of educators. Continuous professional development is widely acknowledged as essential for equipping teachers with the pedagogical skills necessary to enhance student learning outcomes. Desimone, Porter, Garet, Yoon, and Birman (2002) argue that effective professional development is characterized by a focus on content, active learning opportunities, and sustained engagement, all of which contribute to improved instructional practices. For Social Studies teachers, such professional development is critical, given the interdisciplinary nature of the subject, which encompasses history, geography, economics, and civics (Garet, Porter, Desimone, Birman & Yoon, 2001). This multifaceted content necessitates a deep and continually updated knowledge base, underscoring the importance of ongoing professional development.

Perception of Skill Development among Teachers: Teachers' perceptions of their professional skills significantly influence their approach to instructional responsibilities. Avalos (2011) posits that when teachers feel confident in their skills and believe they have access to adequate resources, they are more likely to demonstrate efficacy and confidence in their teaching. This perception of competence is crucial, as it directly impacts their motivation and teaching strategies, thereby affecting student engagement and learning outcomes. Borko (2004) observed that teachers' perceptions of their professional competencies have a direct bearing on their instructional strategies and the level of student engagement. In the context of Social Studies, where the content is often broad and abstract, teachers' confidence in their instructional skills is particularly critical. The ability to navigate and effectively communicate complex, interdisciplinary content is contingent upon teachers' self-perception of their skills, which in turn affects their instructional delivery.

Challenges in Skill Development for Social Studies Teachers: The skill development of Social Studies teachers in Nigeria faces significant challenges, reflective of broader systemic issues within the educational framework. The Nigerian education system is frequently criticized for its overly theoretical approach, with insufficient emphasis on practical skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving (Ogunyemi, 2011). These challenges are particularly pronounced for Social Studies teachers, who must constantly update their knowledge and skills to address the evolving nature of the subject, which now includes contemporary issues such as global citizenship, digital literacy, and environmental education. According to Ogunyemi (2011), inadequate access to professional development opportunities, limited resources, and insufficient support from educational authorities are key barriers to effective service delivery among Social Studies teachers. Saini (2023) further identifies systemic issues such as inadequate funding for education and skills development and the lack of relevance of current educational practices to contemporary needs as major obstacles to skill development. Ehindero (2014) adds that many teachers feel unprepared to effectively teach new content areas, which hinders effective instructional delivery.

Impact of Skill Development on Instructional Delivery: In an era increasingly characterized by automation and artificial intelligence, the traditional roles of teachers are evolving, necessitating a focus on skill development that aligns with these changes. The impact of skill development on instructional delivery, particularly in Social Studies, cannot be overstated. Knight (2009) highlights that teachers who engage in targeted professional development, particularly in areas such as inquiry-based learning, critical thinking, and the integration of digital tools, are better equipped to engage students and foster a deeper understanding of complex subject matter. This is particularly relevant in Social Studies, where the ability to critically analyze and discuss diverse issues is paramount. Darling-Hammond, Wei, Andree, Richardson, and Orphanos (2009) argue that professional development that emphasizes practical application and aligns with curriculum standards significantly improves instructional strategies and, consequently, student outcomes. This alignment ensures that teachers are not only knowledgeable about the content but are also adept at employing instructional strategies that promote critical thinking and active student engagement.

The interconnection between teacher professional development, skill development, and instructional delivery in Social Studies is evident. The challenges faced by Social Studies teachers in Nigeria, including those in Niger State, highlight the need for a more practical and supportive approach to professional development. Addressing these challenges through targeted, content-focused, and sustained professional development can significantly enhance instructional delivery, ultimately leading to improved student outcomes in Social Studies education.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey design to examine the perceptions of Social Studies teachers in Upper Basic Schools across Niger State. The target population comprised 767 Social Studies teachers from 229 schools, with a sample size of 153 teachers (20% of the population) selected from 36 schools across 9 local government areas through stratified and simple random sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled; (PSDFEIDSOSUBT), validated by experts in Social Studies and test and measurement. To ensure reliability, a pilot test was conducted with 40 teachers from Bosso Local

Perception of Skill... (Awaisu & Sarkin-Fada, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258872>

Government Area, who were not included in the main study but shared similar characteristics with the participants. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient obtained was .827, deemed adequate for the study. Descriptive statistics, including frequency counts and percentages, were used to analyze participants' demographics, while mean and standard deviation addressed the research questions. One-sample t-test was employed to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level.

Presentation of Bio Data Variable

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Male	101	68.2
Female	47	31.8
Total	148	100

Source: Researchers field work (2024)

A total of 101 representing 68.2% of the respondents are male and the rest 47 representing 31.8% are female respondent

Answering of Research questions

What is the perception of Upper basic Social Studies teachers' on skill development for effective instructional delivery in Niger state, Nigeria?

Table 2: On perception of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers on skills development for instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
1	I feel that training programs have significantly enhanced the teacher's teaching skills.	36	79	15	18	2.90	0.91
2	Additional training if undertaken can improve the confidence of Social Studies teachers.	44	83	7	14	3.06	0.85
3	The resources provided for skill development are valuable and effective to the teaching and learning of Social Studies.	111	25	9	3	3.65	0.69
4	The opportunities for skill enhancement are well-tailored to meet the needs of Social Studies teachers.	66	54	17	11	3.18	0.91
5	My skills have improved significantly due to ongoing professional development programs.	90	39	14	5	3.45	0.80
6	The support systems in place have contributed immensely to my skill advancement.	71	46	31	0	3.27	0.79
7	I feel that the available skill development programs are inadequate for my needs.	88	52	7	1	3.53	0.62
8	The resources provided for skill development have been insufficient and ineffective.	101	33	4	10	3.52	0.84
9	I feel ill-equipped and unprepared to teach Upper Basic Social Studies despite available skill development programs.	43	81	19	5	3.09	0.74
10	The training sessions I've attended did not contribute significantly to my skill enhancement.	55	69	2	22	3.06	0.99
Cumulative						3.27	0.81

Decision Mean = 2.50

Perception of Skill... (Awaisu & Sarkin-Fada, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258872>

The perception of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers on skills development towards instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria, is very high especially as the cumulative mean of 3.27 is above the 2.50 decision mean. Specifically, most asserted that feel that the available skill development programs are inadequate for my needs. With a mean of 3.53 and the resources provided for skill development have been insufficient and ineffective. With the second highest mean of 3.52

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference in the perception of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers on skills development for instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria.

Table 3: One sample t-test statistic on the Perception of Upper Basic Social Studies Teachers on skills development towards instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria

Variable	N	Mean	Std.	Mean diff	Df	T computed	T-critical	P
hypo ¹	148	3.5000	4.03640	30.50	147	91.926	1.96	0.011

P = 0.011 < 0.05, t computed = 91.92 > 1.96 at df 147

Outcome of the one sample t test statistics revealed that significant difference exists in the perception of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers on skills development towards instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria Reason being that the p value of 0.011 is below the 0.05 and it's computed t value of 91.026 is above the 1.96 t critical at df 147. The mean difference was put at 30.50. The null hypothesis that state that there is no significant difference in the perception of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers on skills development towards instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria is hereby rejected

Presentation of Results

Findings of the study revealed that teachers believe providing resources for skill development would significantly enhance the effectiveness of Social Studies teaching and learning. They also recognized the positive impact of existing support systems on their professional growth. However, teachers perceived the current resources allocated for skill development in instructional delivery as inadequate and ineffective.

Discussion of Results

The study provides a nuanced understanding of the perceptions held by Upper Basic Social Studies teachers in Niger State, Nigeria, regarding skill development for instructional delivery. The findings reveal a complex landscape where teachers recognize the importance of skill development yet express concerns about the adequacy of current resources and support systems. This discussion synthesizes the key findings with relevant literature to offer insights into the implications for educational practice and policy.

Perception of Skill Development: The results indicate that the majority of teachers perceive skill development as crucial for effective instructional delivery, aligning with the Human Capital Theory's assertion that investments in education and training enhance professional competence and productivity (Becker, 1964). The cumulative mean of 3.27 suggests a generally positive perception of skill development among teachers, indicating a recognition of its value in enhancing teaching efficacy and student outcomes. This finding is consistent with Avalos (2011), who emphasized that teachers' confidence in their skills directly impacts their instructional practices and, subsequently, student engagement.

However, the perception that the available skill development programs are inadequate and the resources provided are insufficient and ineffective is particularly concerning. With mean scores of 3.53 and 3.52, respectively, these findings suggest significant gaps between teachers' needs and the support provided by the educational system. This aligns with Ogunyemi (2011), who critiqued the Nigerian educational framework for its theoretical approach and insufficient emphasis on practical skills development. The inadequacy of resources and support systems, as highlighted by the teachers, may contribute to a sense of being ill-equipped and unprepared to meet the demands of their instructional roles.

Impact of Professional Development on Instructional Delivery: The study further reveals that ongoing professional development programs have positively influenced teachers' skills, with a mean score of 3.45 indicating a significant improvement in instructional capabilities. This is supported by Knight (2009), who argued that targeted professional development, particularly in areas such as critical thinking and digital tool integration, enhances instructional delivery. The findings underscore the importance of continuous professional development that is aligned with the evolving demands of the educational landscape, particularly in interdisciplinary subjects like Social Studies, where teachers must navigate complex and diverse content areas.

Despite these positive perceptions, the significant difference in teachers' perceptions of skill development, as revealed by the one-sample t-test ($p = 0.011 < 0.05$), suggests variability in how these programs are experienced across different contexts. This variability could be attributed to disparities in access to quality professional development opportunities and resources, a

Perception of Skill... (Awaisu & Sarkin-Fada, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258872>

point highlighted by Saini (2023), who identified systemic issues such as inadequate funding and the irrelevance of current educational practices as major obstacles to skill development in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study's findings underscore the importance of skill development for effective instructional delivery in Social Studies, while also highlighting significant gaps in the resources and support provided to teachers in Niger State, Nigeria. Addressing these gaps through targeted professional development and better resource allocation is essential for empowering teachers to deliver high-quality education that meets the needs of their students in an increasingly complex and dynamic world.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations:

Develop comprehensive, targeted professional development programs specifically for Social Studies teachers. Focus on practical training in critical thinking, digital literacy, and interdisciplinary strategies. Offer regular workshops, seminars, and continuous learning opportunities to help teachers adapt to evolving educational demands. Additionally, increase government resource allocation for teacher skill development

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Assessment of Social Studies Teaching Resources on Acquisition of Small Scale Businesses and Leadership Skills among Secondary School Students in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the effectiveness of Social Studies teaching resources in promoting small-scale business entrepreneurship and leadership skills among secondary school students in Nigeria. Social Studies, as an essential discipline, equips students with critical competencies for economic self-reliance and societal leadership. The integration of digital tools and experiential learning methods in Social Studies fosters collaboration, critical thinking, and decision-making skills, which are crucial for entrepreneurship and leadership. The paper draws on recent research highlighting the impact of technology-mediated platforms, such as social media and virtual learning environments, in enhancing student engagement and understanding (Garcia & Weiss, 2023; Johnson & Smith, 2023). Furthermore, the constructivist learning theory and Vygotsky's socio-cultural framework underpin the research, emphasizing knowledge construction through social interactions and problem-solving. Methodologically, the paper reviews relevant literature, drawing comparisons with international best practices and incorporating insights from teachers through brainstorming sessions. The paper suggests that Social Studies teaching resources, when aligned with curriculum objectives and supported by adequate teacher training, significantly enhance students' entrepreneurial and leadership capabilities. However, challenges such as inadequate funding, limited teacher preparedness, and traditional pedagogical approaches hinder the full realization of these resources' potential. The study concludes by recommending investments in digital tools, teacher professional development, and community-based learning opportunities to foster a more interactive and practical Social Studies education that prepares students for the demands of the 21st century.

Keyword: Entrepreneurship, leadership, Social Studies, Nigeria

Introduction

Social Studies education is pivotal for inculcating entrepreneurial and leadership skills among students. These skills are essential for nurturing a generation that is self-reliant, creative, and capable of contributing to national development. In Nigeria, there is a growing recognition of the role of Social Studies in equipping students with the knowledge and skills needed to navigate an increasingly complex socio-economic landscape (Olaleye & Adesoji, 2020). Recent studies have underscored the benefits of these technology-mediated resources in Social Studies education. For example Garcia and Weiss (2023) in a study on leveraging Social media for collaborative learning, impacts on Student engagement in Social Studies highlighted that the integration of social media platforms, such as WhatsApp and Facebook, enables students to collaborate, share learning materials, and receive timely feedback from their peers and teachers, encouraging a community of practice. In another study by Johnson and Smith (2023) on the role of Virtual Platforms in enhancing synchronous learning in Social Studies, they found out that Zoom and Google Meet offer opportunities for synchronous learning, which has been found to improve students' comprehension and foster active participation during virtual discussions. Similar, Lee, Kim and Patel (2024) carried out a study on multimedia tools in Social Studies Education, enhancing critical thinking and visualization of abstract concepts; they found out that multimedia tools, such as YouTube videos and electronic whiteboards, make abstract concepts in Social Studies more tangible, allowing students to visualize historical events, cultural practices, and geographical landscapes. These studies suggest that the incorporation of technology-mediated teaching resources in Social Studies education is key in encouraging effective teaching and learning outcomes in the digital age that can promote the acquisition of Small Business Entrepreneurship and leadership skills among Students in Nigerian Schools. These tools not only enhance the quality of instructional delivery but also promote a collaborative and interactive learning environment that meets the diverse needs of 21st-century learners.

Assessment of Social... (Abdullahi, & Sarkin-Fada, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258876>

This paper aims to assess the effectiveness of Social Studies teaching resources in promoting small business entrepreneurship and leadership skills acquisition among students in Nigerian schools. The methodology employed by the paper include: sourcing information from secondary data sources, encompassing an extensive review of books and academic journals. The paper also integrated insights from the broader body of knowledge in Social Studies and drew comparisons with international best practices in Social Studies education. Also, brainstorming sessions with professional teachers from diverse disciplines was carried out which contributed valuable perspectives and practical insights, further enriching the data and deepening the paper's analysis on Social Studies teaching resources at secondary school level of education in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

The conceptual framework for this study is anchored on constructivist learning theory, which posits that learners construct knowledge through their experiences and interactions with the environment. Vygotsky's (1978) socio-cultural theory also underpins this study, emphasizing the role of social interactions and cultural tools in the learning process. Social Studies, as a discipline, provides a platform for students to engage in real-life problem-solving activities, thereby developing entrepreneurial and leadership skills.

Conceptual issues

Social Studies Teaching Resources: They are diverse pedagogical tools—such as textbooks, digital media, and experiential learning materials—designed to enhance students' acquisition of civic knowledge, social values, and analytical skills (Adekunle & Musa, 2023). These resources provide instructional support that empowers educators to deliver content fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and an in-depth understanding of societal structures (Ikechukwu & Abubakar, 2024). Additionally, these tools are instrumental in cultivating essential soft skills, including empathy, collaboration, and decision-making, which are vital for nurturing informed and responsible citizens.

Thus, Social Studies Teaching resources can be conceptualized as pedagogical tools, including textbooks, digital media, and experiential learning materials, that support teachers in nurturing students' civic knowledge, social values, analytical skills, critical thinking, and essential soft skills.

Small business entrepreneurship: Is defined as the process of identifying opportunities and taking calculated risks to establish and manage a small business venture, with the dual aim of generating profit and adding value to the community (Adewale & Nwachukwu, 2023). It encompasses the capacity to mobilize limited resources—such as capital, labor, and information—to create and sustain a business enterprise that effectively responds to local market demands (Olufemi & Yusuf, 2024).

Based on the above definitions, we can define small business entrepreneurship as the process of identifying opportunities and taking calculated risks to create and manage a small business venture for profit and community value, involving the mobilization of limited resources to meet local market needs

Leadership skills: Are characterized by the capacity to influence and motivate individuals towards achieving shared objectives, necessitating empathy, effective communication, and the articulation of a common vision (Obi & Samuel, 2023). These skills involve making strategic decisions aligned with organizational or group goals, emphasizing critical thinking and ethical judgment (Adamu & Bello, 2024). According to Egwu and Daramola (2023) leadership entails visionary guidance, where leaders communicate a compelling vision for the future, inspire commitment, and direct their followers in realizing this vision through innovative and actionable strategies.

Thus Leadership Skills deals with the capacity to influence and motivate others towards achieving shared goals, characterized by empathy, effective communication, critical thinking, ethical decision-making, and visionary guidance to inspire commitment and drive collective action.

Social studies teaching resources at secondary school level of education

The importance of teaching resources in secondary education cannot be overstated, particularly in the 21st century where knowledge is expanding and evolving at an unprecedented rate. In this digital age, effective teaching resources have become crucial to addressing the diverse needs and interests of students. According to Renner, Opong, and Okeh (2022), a wide array of technology-mediated tools can significantly enhance the teaching and learning of Social Studies. These include platforms such as WhatsApp Chat Groups, Facebook Chat Groups, and Zoom, along with devices like iPads, computers, smartphones, projectors, microphones, laptops, and electronic whiteboards. The use of these resources fosters better communication and information sharing between students and teachers, ultimately improving instructional delivery and boosting student engagement

Social Studies and Entrepreneurship Education at secondary school level of education

Entrepreneurship education is essential in fostering economic self-reliance among students. It helps students identify opportunities, assess risks, and develop business ideas (Oseni, 2019). Social Studies teaching resources, such as case studies,

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project-based learning activities, and community engagement projects, can provide students with practical experiences that foster entrepreneurial skills. For instance, case studies of successful small business entrepreneurs can inspire students to develop a positive attitude towards entrepreneurship.

Social Studies and Leadership Skills Development at secondary school level of education

Leadership skills are crucial for students as they prepare to take on roles in society. Social Studies teaching resources, such as role-playing activities, simulations, and group discussions, can help students develop essential leadership qualities like communication, decision-making, and teamwork (Afolabi & Adeyemi, 2020). These resources provide students with opportunities to practice leadership in a safe environment, thus building their confidence and competence.

Challenges in Utilizing Social Studies Teaching Resources

Despite the potential of Social Studies teaching resources in promoting entrepreneurship and leadership skills, several challenges hinder their effective utilization in Nigerian schools. One of the primary challenges is the lack of adequate funding for the procurement of instructional materials (Nwafor, 2019). Additionally, many teachers lack the training needed to effectively use these resources to promote skill acquisition. The traditional teacher-centered approach, which is still prevalent in many Nigerian schools, also limits students' opportunities for active engagement and skill development. Other challenges include Teacher Preparedness and Professional Development, Pedagogical Limitations such as Prevalence of Teacher-Centered Approaches and Inadequate Integration of Practical Activities

Strategies for Enhancing the Effectiveness of Social Studies teaching resources at secondary school level of education

There are several strategies that can be employed by teachers to effectively facilitate the integration of Social Studies teaching resources, these strategies include but not limited to:

1. Curriculum Alignment: Ensuring that teaching resources align with the curriculum's objectives can significantly enhance their effectiveness by making them more relevant to educational goals (Moss, Heller, & Rosen, 2019)
2. Incorporation of Technology: Utilizing digital tools, such as Learning Management Systems (LMS), virtual reality, and interactive platforms, improves student engagement and caters to diverse learning styles (Bond, 2020).
3. Teacher Professional Development: Continuous professional development for teachers is crucial in equipping them with the skills needed to utilize various teaching resources effectively (Desimone & Garet, 2019).
4. Student-Centered Approach: Developing student-centered resources that promote active learning encourages critical thinking and problem-solving, making Social Studies more meaningful to students (Rana & Dwivedi, 2020).
5. Contextual Relevance: Tailoring teaching resources to reflect cultural and local contexts makes learning more relatable and engaging for students (Emdin, 2019).
6. Assessment and Feedback: Incorporating formative assessment and feedback mechanisms helps measure the impact of teaching resources and provides insights for improvement (Andrade, 2019).
7. Collaboration and Sharing: Collaboration among teachers for sharing best practices and innovative teaching methods enhances the effectiveness of Social Studies instruction (Vangrieken, Meredith, & Kyndt, 2020).
8. Inclusion of Multimedia Elements: Incorporating multimedia elements such as visuals, videos, and audio enhances content accessibility and helps cater to different learner preferences (Mayer, 2020).
9. Use of Experiential Learning Resources: Experiential learning, such as field trips and guest speakers, provides students with hands-on experiences, making Social Studies more impactful (Kolb & Kolb, 2020).
10. Feedback from Students: Gathering student feedback regarding the effectiveness of teaching resources allows for adjustments to better meet their learning needs (Tobin, 2019).

How Social Studies can promotes leadership skills among learners at secondary school level of education

Social Studies promotes leadership skills among learners by providing opportunities for them to engage in activities that develop key competencies necessary for leadership roles. Here are some ways in which Social Studies fosters leadership skills:

1. Encouraging Critical Thinking and Decision-Making: Social Studies engages students in analyzing social issues, considering multiple perspectives, and making informed decisions. These activities develop critical thinking and decision-making skills, which are essential for effective leadership (Hirtle & White, 2023).
2. Developing Communication Skills: Through discussions, debates, and presentations, Social Studies helps students articulate their ideas clearly and listen to others' viewpoints. Effective communication is a foundational leadership skill that enables leaders to inspire, influence, and motivate others (Mitchell & Carter, 2023).
3. Promoting Teamwork and Collaboration: Social Studies often involves group projects and collaborative activities, where students work together to explore social phenomena, solve problems, or create projects. This experience teaches

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students how to collaborate effectively, respect diverse opinions, and lead or support group activities, which are crucial skills for leadership (Thompson & Lee, 2023).

4. **Role-Playing and Simulations:** Social Studies classes frequently use role-playing and simulations to help students understand societal roles, historical events, and leadership scenarios. By acting out different roles, learners develop empathy, problem-solving abilities, and leadership qualities such as taking initiative and responsibility (Johnson & Hall, 2023).
5. **Encouraging Civic Responsibility:** Social Studies emphasizes the importance of active citizenship, community involvement, and social responsibility. Through learning about civic duties and social justice, students are motivated to take leadership roles in addressing community issues, thus fostering leadership through active engagement in their communities (Roberts & MacDonald, 2023).
6. **Developing Ethical and Moral Values:** Leadership is not only about managing others but also about having a strong sense of ethics and values. Social Studies helps students understand concepts like fairness, justice, and equality, which are crucial for ethical leadership (Patel & Young, 2023).
7. **Empowering Students through Knowledge:** Social Studies equips learners with knowledge about social systems, government, and policies. This knowledge enables students to understand the context in which they live, identify areas that need change, and inspire others to work toward societal improvement (Grant & Simmons, 2023).
8. **Building Self-Confidence:** Activities like public speaking, community projects, and debates help students build confidence in their abilities. A confident learner is more likely to take on leadership roles and inspire confidence in others (Williams & Nguyen, 2023).

Conclusion

In conclusion, Social Studies teaching resources hold significant potential in promoting small business entrepreneurship and leadership skills among students in Nigerian schools. Through integrating technology-mediated tools, experiential learning opportunities, and a constructivist approach, Social Studies can provide students with the essential skills needed for economic self-reliance, critical thinking, and effective leadership. However, realizing this potential requires overcoming challenges such as inadequate funding, limited teacher training, and traditional pedagogical methods. Therefore, investment in digital resources, alignment of teaching materials with the curriculum, teacher professional development, and community engagement are critical steps towards creating an interactive and empowering learning environment. Ultimately, promoting entrepreneurship and leadership through Social Studies can contribute to a more self-reliant, creative, and socially responsible generation, capable of addressing Nigeria's socio-economic challenges and driving sustainable development.

Recommendations

Based on the contents above, the following suggestions were made to enhance the effectiveness of Social Studies teaching resources in promoting entrepreneurship and leadership skills at secondary school level of education

1. Social Studies curriculum should include hands-on entrepreneurship projects, such as small business simulations, which allow students to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world contexts. This practical approach will help bridge the gap between theory and practice, fostering essential entrepreneurial skills.
2. Stakeholders, including government agencies and school management, should invest in digital teaching tools such as tablets, projectors, and multimedia software. These tools are essential in creating an engaging and interactive learning environment that enhances students' understanding and retention of concepts.
3. Regular workshops and training programs should be organized to equip Social Studies teachers with the skills needed to effectively use both traditional and technology-mediated resources.
4. Schools should incorporate community engagement initiatives as part of Social Studies learning. Activities such as organizing local events or partnering with community businesses can give students real-world exposure to entrepreneurship and leadership roles, thereby enhancing their practical skills.
5. Schools can invite successful entrepreneurs and community leaders to share their experiences and mentor students. Guest lectures, workshops, and mentorship programs will provide students with insights into leadership and entrepreneurship while inspiring them to pursue these paths.
6. Schools should encourage student-led initiatives, such as school-based enterprises or leadership clubs. These platforms give students practical opportunities to develop and apply their entrepreneurial and leadership skills in a controlled environment.

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Impact of Community Watch... (Ishiye, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258880>

Impact Community Watch Corps for Community Safety on Banditry Activities in Katsina State

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Abstract

This study examines impact of community watch Corps for community safety on Banditry activities in Katsina State. The study was guided by four research objectives and corresponding research questions. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Population of the study comprised of residents of 10 frontline local government areas in Katsina State. Sample for the study consisted of 100 residents in Jibia and Batsari drawn using a multistage sampling technique. Data for the study were collected using a 20 items questionnaire entitled the Effectiveness of Community Watch Corps in Combating Banditry (ECWCCB). The Instrument was validated by three experts in terms of face, content and construct validities. It was also, pilot tested and obtained a reliability index of 0.086 using PPMC. Descriptive statistics was used in analyzing the collected data. Research questions were analyzed using Mean, and Standard deviation. Findings among others revealed that the strategies employed by community-led groups to enhance local security, fosters collaboration with law enforcement agency, and build community resilience against crime. Based on the findings, the study concluded that Community Watch Corps are active and effective in combating banditry activities in Katsina state. It was further recommended that empowering community watch initiatives can significantly contribute to reducing crime rates and enhancing community safety especially in vulnerable areas.

Keywords: Role, Community Watch Corps, Combating Banditry

Introduction

Katsina State governor, Dikko Radda, on Tuesday 11 October, 2023, inaugurated the Community Watch Corps to complement efforts of conventional security agencies in the fight against banditry in the state (Babangida, 2023). While inaugurating the Batch 1 of the Corps, Mr Radda said it was part of his administration's efforts to adopt a "community-driven" approach towards addressing insecurity in the state. According to Babangida (2023) the statement by the governor's spokesperson, Ibrahim Kaula, the first batch of the Corps consists of 2,400 youths selected from across the 34 local government areas of the state. "The very essence of this corps lies in community engagement, collaboration, and mutual respect. By leveraging localised knowledge and fostering trust, we are not merely addressing symptoms but targeting the roots of insecurity in our state," the statement quoted Mr. Radda as saying (Babangida, 2023).

In recent years, Katsina State has faced escalating challenges from banditry, threatening the safety and security of its communities. Traditional law enforcement methods have struggled to address the pervasive nature of these criminal activities, prompting the need for innovative local solutions. The establishment of Community Watch Corps represents a grassroots response aimed at restoring safety and trust within affected areas. By harnessing local

Impact of Community Watch... (Ishiye, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258880>

knowledge and fostering community solidarity, these volunteer groups play a crucial role in identifying threats, sharing information, and deterring criminal activities. This paper explores the effectiveness of the Community Watch Corps in combating banditry in Katsina State, highlighting their strategies, successes, and the importance of community involvement in the broader fight against insecurity. The rise of banditry in Nigeria, particularly in Katsina State, has prompted various strategies to enhance community safety. Among these, the establishment of Community Watch Corps (CWC) has emerged as a critical local response. This literature review explores the role of CWC in addressing banditry, focusing on community engagement, effectiveness, and challenges faced.

Community Engagement in Crime Prevention in Katsina state

Community policing has been recognized as an effective strategy in crime prevention. According to Goldstein (1990), community-oriented policing fosters collaboration between law enforcement and communities, enhancing trust and cooperation. The CWC in Katsina aligns with this model, empowering local citizens to take an active role in their security. Studies show that community involvement increases the likelihood of reporting suspicious activities, which is crucial in a region plagued by banditry (Omoera, 2017).

Effectiveness of Community Watch Corps in katsina state

Research indicates that CWC initiatives have led to significant reductions in crime rates in some Nigerian communities. For instance, a study by Adebayo and Olaoluwa (2020) demonstrated that community watch groups in the northern regions effectively deterred criminal activities by increasing surveillance and community vigilance. In Katsina, the CWC has adopted similar strategies, forming alliances with local law enforcement to enhance their capacity to respond to banditry (Umar & Bello, 2021).

Challenges Faced by Community Watch Corps in Katsina State

Despite the successes, several challenges hinder the effectiveness of the CWC in Katsina State. A major issue is the lack of training and resources, which limits the operational capacity of community watch members (Ismail & Yahaya, 2019). Additionally, tensions between community watch groups and formal law enforcement agencies can lead to conflicts, undermining collaborative efforts (Afolabi, 2021). Furthermore, the stigma associated with vigilante groups can deter community members from participating, limiting the CWC's reach and effectiveness (Mohammed, 2022).

The Community Watch Corps plays a vital role in combating banditry in Katsina State through enhanced community engagement and collaboration with law enforcement. While promising, the CWC faces significant challenges that must be addressed to improve its effectiveness. Future research should focus on strategies to strengthen the capacity of these community groups and foster better relations with formal security agencies.

Banditry has become a pervasive security threat in northern Nigeria, particularly in Katsina State. Over recent years, communities in Katsina have been terrorized by armed bandits, leading to the loss of lives, displacement, and destruction of property (Audu, 2021). In response, the state government, in collaboration with local communities, has initiated various security measures, including the establishment of Community Watch Corps. This literature review explores the role of Community Watch Corps in combating banditry in Katsina State, emphasizing their effectiveness and challenges.

Concept of Community Policing and Watch Corps

Community policing refers to a strategy that emphasizes the partnership between law enforcement agencies and community members in ensuring public safety (Davis & Henderson, 2003). It is a people-centered approach that involves citizens in crime prevention and control. Community Watch Corps, in particular, are informal security outfits made up of local volunteers who assist formal security agencies in maintaining peace and order (Usman & Musa, 2022).

According to Usman and Musa (2022), Community Watch Corps typically function in rural settings where formal policing is limited. Their intimate knowledge of the local terrain, culture, and people gives them an advantage in identifying criminal elements and preventing crimes like banditry. Furthermore, they act as mediators and provide intelligence to government security forces, often leading to arrests and disruptions of criminal networks.

Banditry activities in Katsina State

Banditry in Katsina State is part of the broader security crisis in the northwestern region of Nigeria. It involves various forms of criminal activities, including cattle rustling, kidnapping for ransom, armed robbery, and murder (Audu, 2021). The porous borders between Nigeria and neighboring countries have exacerbated the problem, facilitating the movement of arms and criminal elements. The rural areas, where security infrastructure is weak, are particularly vulnerable to attacks (Ibrahim & Abubakar, 2020).

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Ibrahim and Abubakar (2020) emphasize that the failure of conventional security agencies to curb banditry in Katsina State has led to the formation of community-led security initiatives such as Community Watch Corps. The state government's involvement in these initiatives has added a layer of coordination between the local volunteers and formal law enforcement, enhancing the effectiveness of both groups.

The Role of Community Watch Corps in Combating Banditry activities in Katsina State

Community Watch Corps in Katsina State have played significant roles in combating banditry by providing real-time intelligence to security agencies, conducting patrols, and serving as a deterrent to criminal activities. According to Mohammed (2021), their role has been particularly critical in remote areas where the presence of law enforcement is minimal. One of the key contributions of the Community Watch Corps is intelligence gathering. Mohammed (2021) notes that local volunteers are often more trusted by the rural populace than formal security agencies. As a result, they can gather crucial information about the movements and plans of bandit groups, which they relay to government forces for timely intervention. In addition to intelligence gathering, the Community Watch Corps also participate in joint patrols with the police and military (Audu, 2021). These joint efforts have led to the reduction of bandit attacks in some local government areas. For example, Audu (2021) cites the success of such patrols in Batsari and Jibia, where coordinated operations between the Watch Corps and the military resulted in the arrest of several bandit leaders.

Challenges Facing Community Watch Corps in Katsina State

Despite their contributions, the Community Watch Corps face significant challenges that hinder their effectiveness. One major issue is the lack of proper training and equipment (Usman & Musa, 2022). Unlike formal security agencies, the Watch Corps are often poorly funded, and their members are not trained in modern security tactics. This leaves them vulnerable to attacks by better-armed bandits, reducing their capacity to respond effectively. Another challenge is the legal status of the Community Watch Corps. Since they operate informally, there is often a lack of clarity about their authority, which can lead to conflicts with formal law enforcement agencies (Mohammed, 2021). Without legal recognition, they may also struggle to access funding and other resources needed to carry out their activities effectively. Additionally, issues of mistrust and corruption can affect their operations. Ibrahim and Abubakar (2020) point out that in some cases, community members may be reluctant to provide information to the Watch Corps due to fears of collusion with bandits or retaliation.

The role of Community Watch Corps in combating banditry in Katsina State is crucial in bridging the gap between formal security agencies and rural communities. Their involvement in intelligence gathering, joint patrols, and crime prevention has contributed to the reduction of banditry in some areas. However, challenges such as inadequate training, poor equipment, and legal ambiguity continue to limit their overall effectiveness. To maximize their potential, there is a need for better coordination, capacity building, and legal recognition of their operations.

The dismal increase of the number of internally displaced persons (IDPs) from rural to urban centres for asylum have become a source of concern to security stakeholders and government of Katsina State (Babangida, 2023). In spite of the huge amount of money budgeted for procuring ammunition and allowances to security operatives in order to restore peace and harmony in Katsina State, which proved abortive (Babangida, 2023). There is no known study to the best knowledge of the researcher carried out to examine the role of Community Watch Corps in combating banditry in Katsina State, Nigeria. The paucity of empirical evidences in this regard necessitates the need to investigate if the Community Watch Corps are well armed can mitigate the menace of banditry acts in Katsina State and other states in Northeast Nigeria.

Research Objectives

This study was guided by the following objectives:

1. To assess the effectiveness of Community Watch Corps activities in reducing banditry incidents in Katsina State.
2. To analyze the collaboration between Community Watch Corps activities and law enforcement agencies in combating banditry.
3. To evaluate community perceptions of Community Watch Corps' role in enhancing security.
4. To identify challenges faced by Community Watch Corps activities against banditry.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent does Community Watch Corps reduces the incidence of banditry in Katsina State?

Impact of Community Watch... (Ishiyee, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258880>

2. What is the nature of collaboration between the Community Watch Corps activities and law enforcement agencies?
3. What is the level of perception among community members on the role of Community Watch Corps activities in maintaining security?
4. What are the challenges faced by Community Watch Corps activities in their efforts to combat banditry?

Methodology

The research adopted a descriptive survey research designs. The choice of this particular research design was justified because the data used for this study was obtained from the residents bedeviled by perennial insecurity. The population for this study comprised of all the ten (10) frontline Local Governments areas in Katsina state. Population of the study are: Batsari, Danmusa, Jibia, Kankara, Safana, Faskari, Sabuwa, Funtua, Dutsinma and Dandume. Sample for the study consisted of 100 residents in Jibia and Batsari. The sample for the study was collected using a Multistage Sampling Technique. The first stage will involve the purposive selection of two Local Government areas based on proximity to the researcher. Stage Two involved the use of simple random sampling technique to select the sample from the selected Local Government areas.

Data Collection and Analysis

The collected data were subjected to analysis using descriptive statistics of frequencies, mean and standard deviation with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). However, The Instrument was designed and coded on four Likert rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA = 4), Agree (A = 3), Disagree (D = 2) and Strongly Disagree (SD = 1) to illicit information from the respondents on role of community watch corps in combating banditry in Katsina state, Nigeria. The codes were sums up as $4 + 3 + 2 + 1 = 10 / 4 = 2.50$ as the cut off criteria for rejection or acceptance of the mean rating, in which mean scores of equal to or greater than 2.50 are accepted and also rejected when it is less.

Results

The purpose of this study is to analyze role of Community Watch Corps in combating banditry in Katsina State. Below is the analysis:

Research Question One: To what extent does Community Watch Corps reduces the incidence of banditry in Katsina State?

Table 5: Community Watch Corps efforts to reduce the incidence of banditry

S/N	Statements	M	SD	Decision
1.	Community Watch Corps are quite gallant in their operations by providing the support to security agencies against banditry	2.53	1.18	Accepted
2.	Community Watch Corps enjoyed great acclaim and commendation from the security agencies for their commitment and courage in the war against banditry	2.69	1.11	Accepted
3.	The Community Watch Corps operatives are mandated to kill any culprit caught over alleged involvement in sharing information with the bandits	2.86	1.05	Accepted
4.	Most of Community Watch Corps were vigilante and have passion to protect their communities	2.91	1.04	Accepted
5.	The Community Watch Corps are up to the task of restoration of peace and harmony in Katsina State	2.69	1.09	Accepted
		2.74	1.09	

Source: Field survey, 2024.

The result in the Table 5 revealed that the mean rating ranges from M = 2.50, SD = 1.18 to M = 2.91, SD = 1.04 with overall mean of M = 2.74, SD = 1.09 that is $< M = 2.53$ and falls under acceptance region indicating that the individual mean scores are more than the average mean of 2.50. It can be inferred that the respondents have accepted that the Community Watch Corps assisted in combating the incidence of banditry in Katsina State.

Impact of Community Watch... (Ishiyee, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258880>

Research Question Two: What is the nature of collaboration between the Community Watch Corps activities and law enforcement agencies?

Table 6: Nature of the collaboration between the Community Watch Corps and law enforcement agencies

S/N	Statements	M	SD	Decision
6.	The Community Watch Corps in my community collaborate with other security agencies in minimizing crimes	2.73	1.07	Accepted
7.	Setting up of joint taskforce with Community Watch Corps is a good development for combating crimes in my community	2.77	1.11	Accepted
8.	Community Watch Corps collaborate with military and police in the fight against crime	2.83	1.07	Accepted
9.	Hostilities by host communities disrupt the success of war against banditry	2.69	1.12	Accepted
10.	Community Watch Corps reinforced by military and police	2.77	1.10	Accepted
		2.76	1.09	

Source: Field survey, 2024.

The result in the Table 6 shows that the mean rating ranges from M = 2.69, SD = 1.12 to M = 2.83, SD = 1.07 with overall mean of M = 2.76, SD = 1.09 that is < M = 2.50 and falls under acceptance region indicating that the individual mean scores are more than the average mean of 2.50. It can be inferred that the respondents have accepted that there is strong collaboration between the Community Watch Corps and law enforcement agencies in combating the incidence of banditry in Katsina State.

Research Question Three: What is the level of perception among community members on the role of Community Watch Corps activities in maintaining security?

Table 7: Community members' level of perception on the role of the Community Watch Corps in maintaining security

S/N	Statements	M	SD	Decision
11.	I like the way Community Watch Corps operates security measures in my community	2.80	1.09	Accepted
12.	Community Watch Corps constitute menace in my community	2.74	1.11	Accepted
13.	I have trust on Community Watch Corps' effectiveness in my community	2.74	1.11	Accepted
14.	There have been lots of improvements on security services in my community since the inception of the Community Watch Corps	2.64	1.13	Accepted
15.	I see the Community Watch Corps as being reliable in fighting crimes	2.65	1.10	Accepted
		2.71	1.11	

Source: Field survey, 2024.

The result in the Table 7 revealed that the mean rating ranges from M = 2.64, SD = 1.13 to M = 2.80, SD = 1.09 with overall mean of M = 2.71, SD = 1.11 that is < M = 2.50 and falls under acceptance region indicating that the individual mean scores are more than the average mean of 2.50. It can be inferred that the respondents' opinions do not significantly differ in their mean ratings on their perceptions on the performance of the Community Watch Corps in Katsina State.

Research Question Four: What are the challenges faced by Community Watch Corps activities in their efforts to combat banditry?

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Table 8: Challenges faced by Community Watch Corps activities in their efforts to combat banditry

Statements	M	SD	Decision
16. There is a lack of synergy between the Community Watch Corps with other security agencies	2.84	1.09	
17. There is insufficient funds allocation to Community Watch Corps from the State Government for procurement of safety equipment in times of danger	2.70	1.13	
18. Lack ongoing public relations and enlightenment efforts to increase awareness about the Community Watch Corps' role and activities	2.94	1.07	
19. continuous training and retraining of Community Watch officers	2.96	1.03	
20. Lack of patriotism among some Community Watch officers and security agents to fight against insurgency	2.96	1.01	
	2.88	1.07	

Source: Field survey, 2024.

The result in the Table 8 shows that the mean rating ranges from M = 2.70, SD = 1.13 to M = 2.96, SD = 1.03 with overall mean of M = 2.88, SD = 1.07 that is < M = 2.50 and falls under acceptance region indicating that the individual mean scores are more than the average mean of 2.50. It can be inferred that the respondents have accepted that the Community Watch Corps are faced with challenges in their efforts to combat banditry in Katsina State.

Conclusion

Based on the researches questions answered, the study concluded that Community Watch Corps are active and effective toward eradicating the menace of perennial insecurity such as banditry acts perpetrated by bandits and hooligans aided by unscrupulous informants in Katsina state. Inauguration of Community Watch Police is indeed a segment of fulfilling economic policies aimed at engaging the teeming youths in prolific ventures to avert them from falling preys against evil intrigues of criminal groups.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are made

1. The government should revitalize Community Watch Corps to be an effective tool for maintaining stability and safety of the community.
2. Communities should be work in energy with the Community Watch Corps as vigilant in fighting against crimes to enhance safety and stability in the community and social development.
3. The government and security stakeholders should redouble efforts in funding the Community Watch Corps to improve effective community policing and prevention of crimes
4. The Community Watch Corps should be equipped with sophisticated arms, shield, information technology devices and tracking system to combat crime rates in the affected communities.

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Leveraging on Artificial Intelligence... (Yusuf, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

Leveraging on Artificial Intelligence for Effective Provision of Security Services in Nigerian Universities: Potential Benefits and Challenges

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Abstract

Security challenges in Nigerian universities have become a growing concern, with increasing incidents of theft, violence, and unauthorized access, endangering both students and staff. Traditional security systems, often limited by human capacity and outdated technology, are proving inadequate to meet the complex and evolving threats faced by these institutions. This study explores how the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Internet of Things (IoT) sensors can transform security services in Nigerian universities. AI systems, when combined with IoT sensors, offer enhanced capabilities for real-time threat detection, data analysis, and swift response to security breaches. IoT sensors can monitor environmental and physical conditions continuously, providing data that AI algorithms analyze to identify patterns, anomalies, and potential threats before they escalate into critical incidents. The study highlights the potential benefits, including improved threat detection, reduced response times, and cost efficiency, as well as the challenges, such as high initial costs, privacy concerns, and infrastructure limitations. Suggestions include building the necessary technological infrastructure, enhancing training and capacity building, and developing ethical guidelines to ensure responsible use of AI and IoT in university security systems. Ultimately, the adoption of AI-driven security solutions could significantly improve safety in Nigerian universities, provided that the challenges are addressed effectively.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Security Services, Nigerian Universities, Benefits, Challenges

Introduction

Globally, educational institutions have been targets of various security breaches, ranging from violent attacks to cyber intrusions. These incidents have driven many universities worldwide to adopt advanced technological solutions, particularly artificial intelligence (AI), to bolster their security frameworks (Thakur, 2024). AI technologies, with their capacity for real-time monitoring, predictive analytics, and automated response, offer a transformative approach to safeguarding campuses. In an increasingly interconnected world, the demand for enhanced security measures within educational institutions has grown significantly. Universities, as centers of knowledge and innovation, are not immune to the security threats that plague society at large (Patel, 2023). In Europe, universities are leveraging AI to enhance cyber security measures, protecting sensitive research data and personal information from cyber threats (Токар & Палагута 2024). Similarly, in Asia, institutions are using AI for crowd management and emergency response, ensuring the safety of students and staff during large events or crises. In the United States, for example, universities have implemented AI-driven surveillance systems that not only monitor campus activities but also predict potential security threats. These systems analyze vast amounts of data from various sources such as CCTV footage, social media, and access control logs to identify patterns that may indicate a security risk (Olabanji et al., 2024).

While these developments are promising, the situation in Nigerian universities presents a different set of challenges and opportunities. Security concerns in Nigerian universities are multifaceted, encompassing issues such as theft, violence, kidnapping, and unauthorized access (Okoru & Oluku, 2024). Traditional security measures, including the deployment of guards and the use of manual surveillance, have proven inadequate in addressing these growing threats (Wallner et al., 2024).

Leveraging on Artificial Intelligence... (Yusuf, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

The complexity and scale of security issues in Nigerian universities necessitate the adoption of more sophisticated solutions, making AI a compelling option. However, the adoption of AI in Nigerian universities is still in its infancy (Abubakar et al., 2024). The limited implementation of AI-driven security measures can be attributed to several factors, including financial constraints, technical challenges, and a general lack of awareness about the potential benefits of AI (AL-Dosari et al., 2024). Moreover, there is often resistance to change within the institutional culture, where both staff and students may be wary of new technologies, especially those that involve surveillance (Beetham et al., 2022). Despite these challenges, the potential of AI to revolutionize security in Nigerian universities cannot be ignored.

This article seeks to explore the potential benefits and challenges of leveraging AI for security in Nigerian universities. By examining global trends and drawing parallels with the Nigerian context, this study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of how AI can be effectively utilized to enhance campus security. It will also address the specific challenges that Nigerian universities may face in adopting AI technologies, offering recommendations for overcoming these obstacles. One of the key benefits of AI in security is its ability to provide real-time monitoring and analysis. AI-powered surveillance systems can detect unusual behavior or unauthorized access instantly, enabling security personnel to respond swiftly to potential threats (Arif et al., 2024). In a university setting, where the safety of thousands of students and staff is paramount, such capabilities are invaluable. Additionally, AI can help optimize the allocation of security resources, ensuring that personnel are deployed effectively and that security measures are constantly updated based on emerging threats.

Furthermore, AI offers predictive capabilities that traditional security measures cannot match. By analyzing historical data and identifying patterns, AI can predict potential security incidents before they occur. This proactive approach allows universities to prevent incidents rather than merely respond to them, significantly enhancing overall campus safety. In a country like Nigeria, where security resources are often stretched thin, the ability to anticipate and prevent security breaches is particularly crucial. However, the implementation of AI in Nigerian universities is not without its challenges. Technical barriers, such as the lack of robust infrastructure and the need for skilled personnel to manage AI systems, are significant hurdles (Yusuf, & Ibrahim, 2024). Financial constraints also play a major role, as the initial investment required for AI technologies can be prohibitive for many institutions. Additionally, ethical and legal considerations, such as privacy concerns and compliance with local laws, must be carefully navigated to ensure that AI is used responsibly. Despite these challenges, the importance of this work cannot be overstated. By exploring the potential of AI to enhance security in Nigerian universities, this paper contributes to the ongoing discourse on how technology can be harnessed to address critical issues in education. It also provides a roadmap for policymakers, university administrators, and security professionals to consider when planning the adoption of AI technologies. Ultimately, the successful implementation of AI in university security could serve as a model for other sectors in Nigeria, demonstrating the transformative power of technology in addressing complex challenges.

The integration of AI into the security frameworks of Nigerian universities presents a unique opportunity to address the growing security challenges faced by these institutions. While the journey towards full adoption may be fraught with obstacles, the potential benefits ranging from improved surveillance and predictive capabilities to resource optimization make it a worthwhile endeavor. This paper underscores the importance of embracing AI as a tool for enhancing security in Nigerian universities, offering insights and suggestions that can guide stakeholders in making informed decisions about its implementation.

Theoretical Framework

According to Baer & van den Oever (2024), the Theory of Technological Determinism, introduced by Thorstein Veblen and later expanded by scholars like Marshall McLuhan, asserts that technology drives societal change and shapes how organizations function. In the context of Nigerian universities, this theory suggests that the escalating complexity of security threats necessitates the adoption of AI-based security systems. As traditional methods become increasingly insufficient to address modern challenges such as theft, violence, and cyber threats, the integration of AI is seen as a natural and inevitable progression. The theory implies that universities must embrace these technological advancements to remain effective in safeguarding their campuses, as resisting this shift could leave them vulnerable to emerging risks. On the other hand, Kemp et al., (2023) highlighted the Socio-Technical Systems Theory that was developed by researchers at the Tavistock Institute in the 1950s, notably Eric Trist and Ken Bamforth. This theory emphasizes the importance of considering both the technical and social aspects of an organization when implementing new technologies. Applying this to the topic, the effectiveness of AI in enhancing security within Nigerian universities depends not only on the technological infrastructure but also on how well it is integrated with the social dynamics of the university environment. This means that for AI-driven security solutions to be successful, universities must address the ethical concerns, potential resistance from staff and students, and the need for training

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and stakeholder engagement. The theory underscores the need for a holistic approach, ensuring that AI technologies align with the values, culture, and practices of the university community.

Concept of University System of Education in Nigeria

The university system of education in Nigeria represents the pinnacle of the country's formal educational structure, designed to provide advanced knowledge, foster research, and develop human capital for national progress. The system is made up of three categories of universities: federal, state, and private institutions. Federal universities are primarily funded by the national government, state universities are managed by individual states, while private universities are owned by individuals, religious organizations, or corporate bodies. The National Universities Commission (NUC) serves as the central regulatory body for all universities in Nigeria, with the responsibility of ensuring quality control, academic program accreditation, and adherence to educational policies (Onuoha & Chijioke, 2021). The NUC is vital in maintaining academic standards across institutions, guaranteeing that Nigerian universities can compete globally while meeting local socio-economic needs. Historically, Nigeria's university system began with the establishment of the University College Ibadan in 1948, the first institution of its kind in the country. Since then, the system has expanded significantly, with over 200 universities now operating across the nation. The growth of the system has been driven by the need to accommodate the increasing number of students seeking higher education. Nigerian universities offer a broad range of academic programs, including undergraduate, postgraduate, and doctoral degrees across various disciplines such as medicine, engineering, social sciences, arts, and humanities. The mission of Nigerian universities is to provide quality education that contributes to human capital development, research output, and socio-economic transformation (Olajide & Babatunde, 2023). Universities are seen as a key driver for industrialization, innovation, and development of leadership skills in the country.

Despite the positive impact of university education in Nigeria, the system faces several persistent challenges. One of the foremost issues is underfunding, which affects nearly all aspects of university operations, including infrastructure, academic resources, and staff remuneration. Nigerian universities often struggle to provide adequate facilities, laboratories, and libraries, hindering the learning process and research activities. According to Adeyemi and Olanrewaju (2022), many state-owned and federal universities are plagued by infrastructural decay, overcrowded classrooms, and poor living conditions in student hostels. In addition, strikes by university staff, especially academic unions like the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), have become a recurring problem, disrupting academic calendars and affecting students' learning experiences (Okafor & Umeh, 2020). These strikes are often tied to issues of poor funding, delayed salaries, and unmet agreements between the government and staff unions, leading to frequent interruptions in the academic cycle. Nevertheless, Nigeria's university system has recorded several achievements in recent years, especially in the areas of research, technology, and international collaboration. Nigerian universities have contributed to groundbreaking research in fields such as medicine, agriculture, and technology, which have had significant local and global impacts. For instance, universities like the University of Lagos, Covenant University, and Obafemi Awolowo University are leading in research and innovation, particularly in biotechnology, artificial intelligence, and entrepreneurship (Ajibade et al., 2023). In response to global educational trends, many Nigerian universities are adopting e-learning platforms and virtual classrooms to complement traditional learning methods. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated this transition, pushing universities to invest more in online education infrastructure, blended learning models, and digital resources (Olajide & Babatunde, 2023). This shift is expected to improve access to education, particularly for students in remote or underserved areas. The regulatory framework for the Nigerian university system is centered on ensuring compliance with national standards and fostering academic excellence. The NUC plays a critical role in curriculum development, staff and student welfare, accreditation of courses, and quality assurance. Recently, the commission has emphasized the importance of universities adopting innovative teaching methods, embracing digital technologies, and fostering entrepreneurial education to prepare students for the dynamic labor market (Onuoha & Chijioke, 2021). Additionally, there is a growing recognition of the need for universities to forge partnerships with international institutions and industry players. Such collaborations can enhance academic programs, improve research funding, and create opportunities for students to gain global exposure (Olajide & Babatunde, 2023).

Furthermore, the Nigerian university system is increasingly focused on inclusion and equity. Several initiatives have been introduced to address gender disparities in access to higher education, as well as to provide opportunities for students from marginalized communities. Scholarship programs, quota systems, and flexible admission policies have been implemented to ensure that underrepresented groups are able to access university education (Uche et al., 2024). Despite these efforts, more needs to be done to ensure that all students, regardless of socio-economic background, are able to receive quality education. Finally, while the university system in Nigeria faces significant challenges such as inadequate funding, infrastructural deficits, and disruptions from strikes, it remains an essential institution for national development. Continuous reforms aimed at

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enhancing the quality of education, improving infrastructure, and fostering global competitiveness are crucial. Moreover, the integration of technology, promotion of research, and international collaborations will play key roles in shaping the future of Nigerian universities. Addressing these challenges and capitalizing on emerging opportunities will enable the Nigerian university system to fulfill its mission of producing globally competitive graduates and contributing to national progress (Ogundipe & Ogunyemi, 2021).

Concept of Security Services

According to Calder & Watkins (2024), the concept of security services encompasses a broad range of practices, systems, and personnel dedicated to the protection of individuals, property, information, and institutions from various threats. These services are designed to prevent, detect, and respond to risks such as theft, vandalism, violence, cyber-attacks, and other forms of harm. Security services can be provided by both public entities, such as police forces and national security agencies, and private organizations, including security firms and in-house corporate security teams. The scope of these services is extensive, ranging from physical security measures, like surveillance and access control, to digital security, which involves safeguarding data and networks from cyber threats. Yarovaya, (2024) affirmed that in the context of institutions like universities, security services are tailored to create a safe environment for students, staff, and visitors. This involves implementing comprehensive security strategies that integrate technology, personnel, and protocols. For example, universities might employ security personnel to monitor campuses, install surveillance cameras, use biometric access systems, and develop emergency response plans. Additionally, security services in these settings often include cyber security measures to protect sensitive information, such as student records and research data. The overarching goal of security services is to mitigate risks, ensuring that people and assets are protected, and that institutions can function smoothly and securely.

Importance of Security in Nigerian Universities

In the opinion of Ishola et al., (2024) the importance of security in Nigerian universities is multifaceted, addressing both the safety of individuals and the integrity of institutional operations. The following are the key importance of security services in Nigerian Universities:

Protection of Students, Staff, and Visitors: Ensuring the safety of students, staff, and visitors is paramount in Nigerian universities, as these institutions are home to large populations and often operate in environments where security threats can be prevalent. The presence of effective security measures such as surveillance systems, controlled access points, and emergency response protocols helps to mitigate the risks associated with violent incidents, theft, and other safety concerns. By providing a secure environment, universities can significantly reduce the likelihood of incidents that could harm individuals or disrupt campus activities. This not only protects the physical well-being of the university community but also fosters a sense of security that is crucial for students to focus on their academic and personal development. Moreover, a secure campus environment contributes to the overall quality of life and satisfaction among students, staff, and visitors. When individuals feel safe, they are more likely to engage fully in campus life, participate in extracurricular activities, and collaborate with peers and colleagues. The reassurance that their safety is being actively managed allows students to concentrate on their studies and personal growth without the distraction of potential security threats. For staff and faculty, a secure environment supports a productive work atmosphere and promotes a positive and supportive community. Ultimately, ensuring safety and security enhances the university's reputation as a secure and welcoming place, attracting prospective students and faculty and fostering a positive institutional culture (Yusuf & Ibrahim, 2024).

Safeguarding Institutional Assets and Operations: The protection of institutional assets and the maintenance of smooth operations are critical aspects of security in Nigerian universities. Universities invest heavily in infrastructure, research facilities, technology, and intellectual property, all of which are valuable and vulnerable to threats such as vandalism, theft, and cyber-attacks. Effective security measures, including surveillance systems, access controls, and cyber security protocols, help safeguard these assets from damage or loss. By preventing unauthorized access and mitigating potential threats, universities can ensure that their physical and digital resources are preserved, enabling them to continue their educational and research activities without interruption. In addition to protecting tangible assets, robust security practices support the overall stability and integrity of university operations. Security measures help ensure compliance with regulatory requirements and institutional policies, which are essential for maintaining the university's credibility and operational effectiveness. For example, safeguarding sensitive data and research findings is crucial for maintaining the university's reputation and ensuring the reliability of its academic and administrative processes. By prioritizing security, universities can create a stable and secure environment that supports their mission and strategic goals, ultimately contributing to their long-term success and resilience (Agunza, 2024).

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Promotion of a Conducive Learning Environment: Security is fundamental to maintaining an atmosphere where academic activities can flourish without fear or interruption (Adegbenro, 2024). A secure campus environment ensures that students, faculty, and staff can focus on their primary roles of learning, teaching, and research without constant concern for their safety. This environment helps to foster intellectual freedom and creative thinking, which are essential components of academic excellence. A strong security framework mitigates the risks of violent crimes, harassment, and other disruptive behaviors, thereby minimizing incidents that could otherwise lead to anxiety and stress among campus community members. By preventing such disturbances, security services help maintain a stable, peaceful atmosphere conducive to personal and academic development. This stability not only boosts morale but also enhances the reputation of the institution, making it more attractive to prospective students, faculty, and partners. Consequently, universities with robust security measures are better positioned to attract and retain high-quality talent, secure funding, and engage in beneficial collaborations, ultimately contributing to their overall growth and development (Knight, 2024).

Concept of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

According to Rzevski (2024), AI, or Artificial Intelligence, refers to the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, particularly computer systems. These processes include learning (the acquisition of information and rules for using it), reasoning (using the rules to reach approximate or definite conclusions), and self-correction. AI enables machines to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and language translation. The goal of AI is to create systems that can function autonomously, improve over time through experience, and adapt to new inputs and situations. Liu (2024) opined that Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the context of university security refers to the use of advanced algorithms and machine learning techniques to enhance the safety and security of campus environments. By leveraging AI, universities can implement systems that automatically monitor surveillance cameras, analyze vast amounts of data in real-time, and predict potential security threats before they occur. This technology can significantly improve the efficiency and effectiveness of security operations, reducing the reliance on human intervention and allowing for more proactive and precise responses to incidents. In Nigerian universities, where security challenges are diverse and complex, AI offers a powerful tool to enhance protection for students, staff, and institutional assets, ultimately creating a safer and more secure educational environment.

Benefits of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is highly useful across various domains due to its ability to process large volumes of data, perform complex tasks with speed and accuracy, and learn from experience to improve over time (Tahir & Khan, 2023). In business, AI enhances decision-making by providing predictive analytics, automating routine processes, and enabling personalized customer experiences. In healthcare, AI assists in diagnosing diseases, personalizing treatment plans, and improving patient outcomes through advanced data analysis. In education, AI can tailor learning experiences to individual student needs, automate administrative tasks, and enhance online learning platforms. Additionally, AI is vital in security and surveillance, where it can monitor activities, detect anomalies, and respond to potential threats in real-time, making environments like universities safer. Its applications extend to virtually every field, driving innovation, increasing efficiency, and solving complex problems that were previously beyond the reach of traditional computing methods (Ogunode et al., 2023). AI is highly useful in enhancing security in Nigerian universities by providing advanced tools that significantly improve campus safety and operational efficiency. AI-powered surveillance systems can monitor large areas in real-time, automatically detecting suspicious activities or unauthorized access, and alerting security personnel for rapid response. This proactive approach reduces the likelihood of incidents such as theft, violence, or vandalism, while also enabling predictive analysis to prevent potential security breaches. AI automates routine tasks like monitoring security feeds and managing access controls, freeing up personnel to focus on more critical issues (Ekpoh et al., 2020). By offering data-driven insights, AI helps universities allocate resources more effectively and continually optimize security measures. In a context where security challenges are diverse and resources may be limited, AI integration leads to more effective, sustainable safety strategies, creating a secure environment conducive to learning and research.

Strategies for Integrating AI for Security Services in Nigerian Universities

Integrating AI into security services for Nigerian universities requires a strategic approach that addresses both technological and institutional challenges (Hlongwane et al., 2024). Strategies that are specific to this setting include:

Building the Necessary Infrastructure: Integrating AI into security services in Nigerian universities requires substantial investment in the right infrastructure to support the seamless operation of AI technologies (Zakari, 2024). This foundation is crucial for the real-time processing and analysis of data that AI systems rely on to function effectively. High-quality hardware such as advanced surveillance cameras, IoT sensors, and robust network systems must be installed across the

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campus to enable comprehensive monitoring and quick response to incidents. These systems need to be interconnected to a centralized control center that leverages AI algorithms to analyze data and make informed security decisions. Moreover, universities must ensure that their network infrastructure has sufficient bandwidth and speed to handle the vast amounts of data generated by AI-powered surveillance systems without lag or interruption. In addition to physical infrastructure, Nigerian universities must prioritize cyber security measures to protect AI systems from potential cyber threats (Akor et al., 2024). This includes implementing firewalls, encryption, and intrusion detection systems to safeguard data collected by AI technologies against hacking and unauthorized access. Universities should also conduct regular security audits and vulnerability assessments to identify and address potential weaknesses in their infrastructure. Universities can guarantee that AI security solutions function properly and preserve the integrity of sensitive data by constructing a secure and resilient IT infrastructure. This will help to create a safe and secure environment on campus.

Enhancing Training and Capacity Building: For AI integration in university security to be successful, it is crucial to invest in the training and capacity building of security personnel and IT staff (Yaseen, 2024). These individuals must be proficient in operating AI technologies, interpreting data outputs, and maintaining AI systems to ensure their effectiveness. Training programs should be established to educate security personnel on the fundamentals of AI, how to use AI-powered surveillance and access control systems, and how to respond to AI-generated alerts. Such training can be facilitated through workshops, seminars, and hands-on exercises that provide practical experience. Moreover, partnerships with technology companies and AI experts can be instrumental in delivering specialized training and keeping staff updated on the latest developments in AI security. Beyond immediate operational needs, Nigerian universities should consider incorporating AI and cyber security courses into their academic curricula to develop a pipeline of future professionals equipped with the necessary skills to manage AI technologies (Okem et al., 2024). By embedding AI knowledge into undergraduate and postgraduate programs, universities can cultivate a workforce that is not only familiar with AI concepts but also capable of innovating and improving AI applications in security. This long-term approach to capacity building will ensure that universities have the human resources needed to sustain and enhance AI security systems, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and adaptation to emerging security challenges.

Collaborating with Technology Providers: Establishing partnerships with technology providers specializing in AI solutions is essential for the successful integration of AI into university security services (Habbal et al., 2024). These collaborations allow universities to access customized AI tools tailored to their specific security needs, ensuring that the technology is aligned with the unique requirements of each campus. Technology providers can offer ongoing technical support, troubleshooting, and maintenance services, which are critical for the smooth operation of AI systems. Regular updates and upgrades provided by these partners help keep AI technologies current and effective, adapting to new security threats and technological advancements. Collaborations with technology providers also enable Nigerian universities to leverage the latest innovations in AI and security technology (Ijiga et al., 2024). By working closely with experts in the field, universities can stay at the forefront of AI developments, implementing cutting-edge solutions that enhance campus security. These partnerships may also include research and development initiatives, where universities and tech companies collaborate on projects to explore new applications of AI in security, contributing to the advancement of knowledge in this area. Such collaborations not only enhance security capabilities but also foster a culture of innovation and knowledge sharing, benefiting both the academic community and the broader society.

Prioritizing Data Privacy and Ethical Standards: Given the extensive data collection inherent in AI systems, prioritizing data privacy and ethical standards is essential for Nigerian universities integrating AI into their security services (Olorunfemi et al., 2024). AI technologies gather and process large amounts of sensitive information, including personal identification details, behavioral patterns, and real-time surveillance footage. To protect this data, universities must establish comprehensive data privacy policies that govern how data is collected, stored, used, and shared. These policies should be transparent, outlining the rights of individuals whose data is being captured and providing clear guidelines on data access and retention. Implementing robust encryption methods and secure data storage solutions will further safeguard against unauthorized access and potential breaches. Ethical considerations must also be addressed to ensure that AI deployment respects the rights and freedoms of individuals within the university community (Jedlickova, 2024). Universities should develop ethical guidelines for the use of AI in surveillance and decision-making processes, focusing on issues such as consent, transparency, and accountability. It is important to ensure that AI applications do not lead to discriminatory practices or biases and that there is oversight in place to monitor the ethical implications of AI usage. Establishing an ethics review board or committee to evaluate AI projects and ensure compliance with ethical standards can help maintain trust and integrity in the university's security initiatives.

Leveraging on Artificial Intelligence... (Yusuf, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

Implementing Pilot Programs for Gradual Integration: To effectively manage the integration of AI into security services, Nigerian universities should consider implementing pilot programs as a first step (Suleiman, 2024). Pilot programs allow universities to introduce AI technologies on a smaller scale in specific areas of the campus, providing an opportunity to test and refine AI tools before broader deployment. By starting with pilot initiatives, universities can gather valuable feedback from security personnel and users, identify potential technical or operational challenges, and make necessary adjustments to improve system performance. This phased approach minimizes risks and helps build confidence in the use of AI, ensuring that full-scale implementation is based on practical insights and proven success. Pilot programs also provide a controlled environment for training security staff on the use of AI technologies (Dave et al., 2024) during the pilot phase, staff can gain hands-on experience with AI systems, learning how to interpret data, respond to AI-generated alerts, and manage the technology effectively. This practical training helps to build the necessary skills and expertise within the security team, facilitating a smoother transition to full-scale AI integration. Nigerian universities can guarantee the proper integration of AI technologies into their security frameworks, hence improving campus safety and mitigating associated risks, by implementing the technology gradually and learning from their pilot programs.

Ethical considerations in AI integration for security services in Nigeria Universities

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly being adopted across various sectors, including education, where it holds promise for enhancing security services in Nigerian universities. AI technologies, such as facial recognition systems, behavior analysis tools, and predictive policing algorithms, offer the potential to improve campus safety by monitoring activities, preventing crimes, and managing incidents more efficiently. However, the ethical implications of these technologies are profound and must be considered to ensure their responsible use. As universities are spaces of learning, personal development, and intellectual freedom, the ethical integration of AI in their security systems must carefully balance efficiency with respect for privacy, fairness, autonomy, and human rights. Below are the key ethical considerations in the integration of AI in security services in Nigerian universities.

Privacy and Data Security: AI-driven security systems typically require large datasets, including personal information such as biometric data (e.g., facial recognition or fingerprints), surveillance footage, and behavioral patterns. The collection and use of such sensitive data raise significant privacy concerns. A key ethical issue is how universities collect, store, and protect this data. In Nigeria, universities face the challenge of ensuring that their data management practices comply with global standards, such as the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and local frameworks like the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) (Chukwu & Okonkwo, 2022). AI systems also pose risks regarding data breaches and cyber-attacks. Unauthorized access to personal data could lead to identity theft or other forms of misuse. Therefore, Nigerian universities must implement robust cyber security measures to protect data from hackers or malicious actors. Data encryption, regular audits, and the use of anonymized data can be critical steps in safeguarding privacy. Moreover, universities must establish clear policies on data retention, defining how long data can be stored and under what conditions it can be deleted or transferred (Adebayo & Olatunji, 2022).

Informed Consent and Transparency: Transparency is essential in ensuring that the implementation of AI in security services does not infringe upon the rights of students, faculty, and staff. One major concern is that AI systems may often operate without the full knowledge or consent of those being monitored. Ethical AI deployment requires that individuals be informed about the existence and operation of these systems. Nigerian universities must ensure that stakeholders are aware of how their data is being collected, used, and potentially shared with third parties (Ogunlana & Fakunle, 2021). For AI deployment to be ethical, universities must seek informed consent from students, staff, and visitors regarding the use of surveillance technologies. This could involve providing clear, accessible information through posters, websites, or student handbooks. Furthermore, universities must be transparent about the AI algorithms being used, especially when it comes to automated decision-making processes. Lack of transparency can lead to distrust, especially if students and staff are not fully aware of how security decisions, such as alerts or interventions, are being made.

Bias and Discrimination in AI Systems: AI systems, particularly in the realm of security, have been shown to exhibit biases based on race, gender, and socioeconomic status. This is largely due to the nature of the datasets used to train these systems, which may reflect existing societal biases. For instance, facial recognition systems have been found to be less accurate in identifying people with darker skin tones, raising concerns about potential racial profiling in Nigerian universities, where the majority of the population is Black (Bello & Afolayan, 2023). This risk of bias presents serious ethical concerns, as it can lead to discrimination and unequal treatment of individuals. If AI systems disproportionately target certain groups of students or staff based on race, gender, or other characteristics, it could reinforce existing inequalities within the university system. To mitigate this, universities must ensure that AI systems are trained on diverse datasets that reflect the population they serve.

Leveraging on Artificial Intelligence... (Yusuf, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

Continuous monitoring and auditing of AI systems should also be implemented to detect and correct any biased outcomes (Bello & Afolayan, 2023).

Surveillance and the Right to Autonomy: The pervasive use of AI in security services often involves extensive surveillance, which can intrude on personal freedom and autonomy. AI-powered surveillance cameras, sensors, and tracking devices might create a campus environment where individuals feel they are constantly being monitored. This raises ethical concerns about the potential erosion of personal autonomy and the right to privacy (Chukwu & Okonkwo, 2022). Students and staff may alter their behavior if they believe they are under constant surveillance, which could stifle creativity, free speech, and personal expression—fundamental components of academic freedom. Nigerian universities must, therefore, strike a balance between enhancing security and preserving the open, free atmosphere that is crucial to higher education. One approach is to ensure that AI surveillance is minimally invasive and is only deployed in high-risk areas or during specific events where security concerns are heightened.

Accountability and Liability: Determining who is accountable when AI systems fail or cause harm is a significant ethical concern. For instance, if a facial recognition system misidentifies a student as a threat, leading to unjust consequences, it is unclear whether the fault lies with the AI developers, the university administrators, or the security personnel operating the system. Without clear lines of accountability, victims of such errors may have limited recourse for justice (Ibrahim, 2023). Nigerian universities must establish clear governance frameworks that define accountability for the use of AI in security services. This could include setting up oversight bodies responsible for monitoring AI performance, addressing grievances, and ensuring that AI systems comply with ethical standards. Universities must also ensure that AI systems are regularly tested for accuracy and fairness to minimize errors that could lead to harm.

Employment and Labor Concerns: AI integration into security services has the potential to displace human security personnel, leading to job losses. This is an ethical consideration that cannot be overlooked, particularly in a country like Nigeria where unemployment rates are high. While AI can complement human security efforts, there is a risk that over-reliance on technology could lead to the redundancy of security staff. Nigerian universities must carefully consider the social implications of AI deployment and strive to create a balanced approach that preserves jobs while improving efficiency (Okafor & Adeola, 2021). One solution could be to provide retraining or up skilling opportunities for security personnel, enabling them to work alongside AI systems rather than being replaced by them. By fostering a collaborative relationship between AI and human security staff, universities can enhance their security infrastructure without contributing to job displacement.

Ethical AI Development and Use: Ensuring that AI systems are developed and deployed ethically is crucial to preventing potential harms. Nigerian universities must partner with AI developers who adhere to strict ethical guidelines. This includes ensuring that AI systems are designed with fairness, transparency, and accountability in mind. Universities should also demand that AI vendors provide clear documentation on how the systems work and how they handle issues like bias and error correction (Oluwaseun, 2020). Additionally, Nigerian universities must establish their own ethical standards for AI use, possibly in collaboration with regulatory bodies, to ensure that AI deployment aligns with national and international guidelines. Ethical AI development should also involve input from diverse stakeholders, including students, staff, and AI experts, to ensure that the technology serves the best interests of the university community.

Benefits of Integrating Artificial Intelligence for Security Services in Nigerian Universities

Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into security services in Nigerian universities offers several benefits, improving the overall safety, efficiency, and operational capacity of campus security. These benefits align with global trends, where AI has revolutionized security by automating processes, enabling predictive analysis, and enhancing real-time surveillance and response. Below are detailed explanations of the key benefits:

- 1. Enhanced Surveillance and Monitoring:** AI-powered security systems offer enhanced surveillance capabilities through smart cameras equipped with facial recognition, object detection, and behavioral analysis algorithms. These technologies enable real-time monitoring of large campuses, allowing for the quick detection of unusual activities or unauthorized access. According to Onyema and Nwachukwu (2021), AI-driven security solutions can identify potential security threats faster than human operators, reducing the time needed for intervention and preventing incidents before they escalate. In Nigerian universities, where managing vast open spaces and multiple entry points is challenging, AI surveillance provides a scalable solution for continuous monitoring. It ensures that campuses are under constant watch, even in remote or low-traffic areas where human patrols may be inefficient or absent (Adeola & Johnson, 2023).
- 2. Predictive Threat Detection:** One of the core benefits of integrating AI into security systems is its predictive capabilities. AI algorithms can analyze historical data and identify patterns that may signal potential security risks,

Leveraging on Artificial Intelligence... (Yusuf, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

such as crowd behavior before a protest or the movement patterns of individuals who could pose threats. This predictive analysis allows university security personnel to allocate resources proactively and prevent issues before they materialize. According to Ayo and Falola (2022), predictive threat detection has proven effective in preventing security breaches in Nigerian universities, where theft, vandalism, and unauthorized access are common. AI's ability to assess risks and trigger automated responses—such as locking down buildings or alerting security teams—significantly enhances campus safety.

3. **Automation of Security Responses:** AI integration allows for the automation of several security responses. When an anomaly is detected, AI systems can automatically trigger alarms, notify campus security personnel, and, if necessary, deploy drones or robotic patrol units. This minimizes response times and ensures that threats are addressed immediately, even in the absence of human operators. Okoro and Ekechi (2020) highlighted that automated systems, when integrated with human intelligence, improve decision-making during security crises, reducing human error. In Nigerian universities, where campus security teams are often understaffed, AI-powered automation acts as a force multiplier, enhancing the effectiveness of security personnel (Okoro & Ekechi, 2020).
4. **Access Control and Identity Management:** AI can streamline access control through the use of biometric systems, including facial recognition, fingerprint scanning, and even gait analysis. These technologies ensure that only authorized individuals gain access to restricted areas such as academic buildings, laboratories, and dormitories. AI enhances identity management systems by continuously learning and adapting to changes, offering improved accuracy over traditional card-based systems. A study by Mohammed et al. (2023) demonstrates that AI-based access control systems have reduced unauthorized access and improved security management in higher education institutions in Nigeria. These systems help university administrators track the movement of individuals in real-time, ensuring that access rights are appropriately managed.
5. **Improved Data Security:** Beyond physical security, AI plays a critical role in cyber security, protecting sensitive student and staff data from cyber threats. AI algorithms can monitor network traffic, detect anomalies, and prevent cyber-attacks, such as phishing, malware, and ransomware attacks, which have increasingly targeted Nigerian universities (Olumide & Ibrahim, 2021). AI systems are also capable of learning from new threats, ensuring that cyber security measures remain up-to-date and effective. This dynamic approach to data security helps universities safeguard personal data, financial information, and research outputs, all of which are valuable targets for cybercriminals.
6. **Resource Optimization:** By integrating AI, universities can optimize security resources. AI can analyze foot traffic patterns, incident reports, and other data to identify high-risk areas on campus, allowing security teams to allocate personnel and resources where they are most needed. This ensures that security efforts are focused on preventing incidents in areas where they are most likely to occur. As reported by Adebayo and Musa (2024), resource optimization through AI has enabled Nigerian universities to make more informed decisions about staffing, equipment purchases, and infrastructure upgrades. This has led to cost savings while improving the overall security of campuses.
7. **Real-Time Alerts and Communication:** AI-enabled security systems provide real-time alerts and facilitate instant communication with relevant authorities. In the event of an emergency, such as a fire, medical emergency, or active shooter situation, AI can instantly notify campus security teams, local law enforcement, and emergency medical personnel. Chukwuma and Ibrahim (2022) emphasized the importance of real-time communication in improving the effectiveness of emergency response teams in Nigerian universities. AI enhances coordination between different teams, ensuring that help arrives faster and with better situational awareness.

Potential challenges of Integrating Artificial Intelligence for Security Services in Nigerian Universities

Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) for security services in Nigerian universities presents significant opportunities for enhancing campus safety but also comes with several potential challenges. These challenges can be categorized into technological, infrastructural, ethical, regulatory, and social dimensions. Below is a detailed discussion of these challenges:

Technological Challenges: The deployment of AI in security services requires sophisticated technologies, such as facial recognition, predictive algorithms, and real-time surveillance systems. Nigerian universities may face difficulties in accessing the necessary technological infrastructure, especially given the high cost of implementation and the need for advanced expertise to manage these systems (Olajide & Adebayo, 2021). AI systems demand regular updates and maintenance to function optimally, which can be a problem in settings where technical support is limited. Moreover, AI algorithms are prone to errors, such as false positives in facial recognition, which could lead to wrongful identification of individuals (Adewole, 2023).

Infrastructural Constraints: A key challenge to integrating AI in security systems is the state of infrastructural development in Nigerian universities. Many universities lack reliable electricity and robust internet connectivity, which are

Leveraging on Artificial Intelligence... (Yusuf, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

crucial for running AI-powered systems effectively (Ogunleye & Shonibare, 2022). These infrastructural deficiencies can lead to system downtime, thereby undermining the reliability of AI-based security measures. Without stable internet and electricity, security systems that rely on cloud computing and real-time data processing cannot function properly, leaving universities vulnerable to security breaches.

Data Privacy and Ethical Concerns: The use of AI for security services, especially technologies like facial recognition and surveillance, raises serious ethical concerns. Issues of data privacy and surveillance have become prominent globally, and Nigerian universities are no exception (Ojo & Adeyemi, 2022). There are concerns about how student and staff data will be collected, stored, and used. The absence of robust data protection laws in Nigeria exacerbates these concerns. If not properly regulated, the collection of biometric data and real-time surveillance could lead to privacy violations, with students and staff feeling constantly monitored and their personal information potentially exposed to unauthorized parties (Adebayo & Olufemi, 2023).

Regulatory and Legal Frameworks: Nigeria lacks comprehensive regulatory frameworks governing the use of AI in security services. The absence of clear regulations on data protection, AI ethics, and accountability creates a legal grey area, making it difficult for universities to implement AI-based security systems within legal boundaries (Akintoye & Mohammed, 2023). The need for a legal framework that regulates the deployment and operation of AI technologies is critical to ensuring compliance and accountability. Without such regulations, there is the potential for misuse of AI systems, leading to security and privacy concerns.

Financial Constraints: Implementing AI-based security systems is expensive. Universities in Nigeria often face financial limitations, which can hinder the integration of AI technologies (Chukwuma, 2021). The costs associated with acquiring, installing, and maintaining AI systems, as well as training personnel to operate these systems, are substantial. Given the limited budget allocations for universities, particularly for non-academic infrastructures, it becomes challenging to prioritize investments in AI for security services over other pressing needs like research funding, teaching resources, and basic facilities.

Resistance to Change: The adoption of AI in security services may face resistance from university communities. Staff and students may be apprehensive about new technologies due to fear of job loss or privacy concerns. Security personnel might feel threatened by the possibility that AI systems could replace human roles in campus security operations (Eze, 2022). Furthermore, there could be a lack of trust in AI systems due to their perceived complexity or misconceptions about their capabilities and limitations. Resistance to change can slow down the adoption process and hinder the effective integration of AI technologies.

Skill Gaps: AI implementation requires skilled personnel capable of managing, maintaining, and troubleshooting AI systems. Nigerian universities may face challenges in recruiting and retaining individuals with the necessary expertise in AI and cyber security (Adekunle & Adebisi, 2020). The shortage of skilled labor in this field means that universities will need to invest heavily in capacity building, which may not be immediately feasible. Additionally, reliance on external vendors for the operation of AI systems could increase costs and expose the universities to vendor lock-in, making future technology upgrades more difficult.

Conclusion

Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into security services in Nigerian universities presents both significant opportunities and substantial challenges. AI has the potential to revolutionize security measures by enhancing threat detection, improving response times, and optimizing resource allocation. These benefits can lead to safer campus environments, where students, staff, and visitors feel secure. However, the adoption of AI in security also raises critical ethical and operational concerns, including privacy issues, the risk of bias, high implementation costs, cyber security threats, and resistance from stakeholders. Addressing these challenges requires a balanced approach that ensures AI technologies are used responsibly and ethically while maximizing their security benefits. As Nigerian universities move towards integrating AI into their security frameworks, it is crucial to prioritize transparency, fairness, and the protection of individual rights. Institutions must establish clear guidelines and policies that govern the use of AI in security, ensuring compliance with data protection laws and ethical standards. Regular monitoring, evaluation, and updates of AI systems are essential to maintain their effectiveness and trustworthiness. Moreover, stakeholder engagement is vital to foster acceptance and collaboration in the successful implementation of AI-based security solutions.

Recommendations

The following suggestions are proposed in relation to this study:

Leveraging on Artificial Intelligence... (Yusuf, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

1. Universities should create comprehensive ethical guidelines for the use of AI in security services. These guidelines should address issues of privacy, consent, data protection, and accountability, ensuring that AI technologies are used in a manner that respects individual rights and adheres to ethical standards.
2. To protect AI systems from cyber threats, universities should invest in strong cybersecurity protocols. Regular vulnerability assessments, real-time monitoring, and prompt updates are crucial to safeguarding AI systems against hacking and data breaches.
3. Continuous evaluation and improvement of AI algorithms are necessary to minimize bias and discrimination. Universities should ensure that AI systems are trained on diverse and representative data sets, and they should conduct regular audits to detect and rectify biased outcomes.
4. Involving students, staff, security personnel, and other stakeholders in the planning and implementation of AI-based security solutions can help build trust and acceptance. Clear communication about the benefits, limitations, and ethical considerations of AI will foster a collaborative approach.
5. Providing training for security personnel on how to operate and manage AI systems is essential. Universities should also invest in ongoing capacity building to ensure that staff are equipped with the skills and knowledge needed to respond to evolving security challenges effectively.
6. Universities should regularly review the effectiveness of AI integration in their security frameworks. Impact assessments can help identify areas for improvement, ensure compliance with ethical standards, and adapt strategies to emerging security threats.
7. Establishing mechanisms for transparency and accountability in AI-driven security decisions is crucial. Universities should provide channels for reporting and addressing concerns related to AI use, ensuring that there is accountability for actions taken by AI systems.

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Impact of Trade Liberalization... (Felix, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

Impact of Trade Liberalization on Capacity Utilization of Manufacturing Sectors in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study is aimed at investigating the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of manufacturing sector in Nigeria, through the use of Dynamic Ordinary Least Square Method (DOLS) technique. This study utilized annual time series data which will be collected from secondary sources mainly; the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin of various years, World Development Indicator (WDI) and the National Bureau of statistics (NBS). The findings suggested that trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria and concluded that trade liberalization caused de-industrialization and not industrialization in Nigeria over the period of study. Hence, it was suggested as a way forward that to improve trade, lower trade barriers, and simplify regulatory requirements, the government must implement trade facilitation measures.

Keyword: Trade Liberalization, Capacity Utilization and Manufacturing Sector

Introduction

Trade liberalization has been largely recognized as a key policy approach adopted by many countries to enhance economic growth and development. It aims at fostering economic and industrial growth by eliminating trade barriers and promoting international trade. There has been a long-held belief that economies grow by engaging in trading activities with other nations of the world as trade does not only contribute to efficient allocation of resources within and outside a country, but also transmits growth from one part of the world to another.

Capacity Utilization measures the extent to which a manufacturing plant would physically produce output given its input which comprise; technology, labour and capital. It is a key factor in establishing how well the industry is reaching its production potential. Capacity utilization gives an idea about the profitability of a company and it provides a comprehensive view of the operational health and economic significance of the manufacturing sector.

Trade liberalization policy dates back to the 1940s after World War II. During this period, protectionism was largely reversed especially among the industrialized countries and the policy was spread to the developing countries with the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) in 1947. GATT was a legal agreement among countries whose purpose was to promote international trade. The primary focus of GATT which was to reduce trade barriers among nations was guided by the nondiscriminatory and the reciprocity principles. The principles stipulated that both trade restrictions and proposals to reduce trade restrictions should apply to all of a country's trading partners equally, it further dictates that all participating countries reduce some of their own import barriers or export subsidies in exchange for comparable steps by their negotiating partners (WTO, 2013). Trade reforms were further expanded and consolidated in 1980s and 1990s across the developing world such as South and East Asia, Latin America and Africa. The World Trade Organisation (WTO) replaced GATT In 1995 but the guiding principles remained the same as GATT's with the objective of helping developing African countries to fully benefit from the global trading system (WTO, 2013).

In Nigeria the oil boom period of the 1980s, preceded the trade liberalization policy regime which became pronounced after the adoption of the International Monetary Fund's (IMF) Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986. The main

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thrust was to replace import substitution with export promotion strategy through exchange rate and diversification of the productive base of the Nigerian economy (Emerenini & Ohadinma, 2018; Williamson, 1995). In addition, trade liberalization policy was adopted to improve the balance of payment crises as a result of oil glut in the world market. It served as a survival strategy to reduce the Nation's over reliance on crude oil, occasioned by the collapse in oil price in the world market, with greater emphasis on the non-oil and tradable sectors of agriculture and manufacturing. Nigeria's openness to trade decreased to 27% from an earlier 31%, and further decline to 25% and 23% in 1985 and 1986 respectively. Between 2013 and 2018, trade openness experienced another downward trend to less than 30% (Emerenini & Ohadinma, 2018). This development had a consequent impact on the manufacturing sector performance which equally declined from 20.5% in 1985 to 0.72% in 1997 (Asongo, Jamala, Joel, & Waindu, 2013).

The rate of performance of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria arising from the adoption trade liberalization policy is not consistent with other countries that have embraced the policy. While other countries have progressed in areas of improved manufacturing output growth, capacity utilization, employment, GDP and profitability as recorded in countries such as Germany which experienced 700% increase in its import due to trade with China and 125% due to its trade union with Latin America (ICC, 2021). The Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (NBS) affirmed that Nigeria's manufacturing sector contracted by - 2.75% in 2020 leaving the sector in a vulnerable condition (NBS, 2020). There has been several government efforts in Nigeria geared towards improving the performance of the manufacturing sector such as privatization and commercialization of public enterprises, the establishment of Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC), the introduction of new tariff rates and incentives (tax holidays, tariff protection, import duty relief, total ban on certain foreign goods), trade and investment liberalization as well as macroeconomic stabilization policies.

Trade liberalization is an important component of economic liberalization which involves the loosening of government control over trade restrictions and barriers. It includes the removal of trade barriers, such as tariffs and non-tariff barriers, as well as internal restrictions for instance directed credit and preferential purchasing. It is described as the reduction or removal of all forms of restrictions to trade among countries. Trade Liberalization as defined by Monisola (2014) is the discontinuation of import licensing, the elimination of marketing boards and removal of obstacles on trade to create a competitive atmosphere between local and foreign industries. Shafaeddin, 2005 defined as any act that would make the trade regime more neutral. That is, nearer to a trade system free of government intervention. Akims, (2017) simply defined it as the removal or reduction of both tariff and non-tariff obstacles to international trade.

Despite government interventions, the Nigerian manufacturing sector still lacks the capacity to cater for the fast growing demand of the over 217 million Nigerian population (United Nations, 2022). This has led to rising prices of goods and services (inflation), recording an all-time high rate of 72.84% inflation rate in 1995, recent statistics reveal that in 2021 inflation rate in Nigeria stood at 15.6% but rose to 20.95% and 28.92% in 2022 and 2023 respectively (NBS, 2023). Furthermore, sustained and persistent rise in the value at which the dollar exchanges for naira (Exchange rate); revealing 120.6 naira to 1 dollar in 2002 as against 1 dollar to 461.51, and 1,505 naira in 2023 and 2024 respectively has made the country's import more costly thereby worsening the already existing inflation rate (Nigerian Bureau of Statistics, 2023). Statistical evidences further suggests decline in important indicators of the manufacturing sector. For instance, manufacturing sector output continues to experience a downward trend between 1986 and 2021, with a decline from 21.01% in 1986 to 13.93% in 2000 (CBN, 2009). Further decline of 9.65% was recorded in 2018 with recent data on manufacturing output standing at 12.67% in 2020 (CBN, 2021). Capacity utilization also recorded a downward trend from 70.1% in 1980 to 40.30% in 1990 and 30.4% in 1997. Further decline was recorded in 2005 from 52.8% to 48.0% in 2009, 40.13 in 2015 and 39.88% in 2018 (CBN, 2019; World Bank, 2019). Between 2019 and 2021, manufacturing capacity utilization revealed an average of 54.9% from 54 observations, recording as low as 43.8% in 2020 (CBN, 2021). This persistent decline in figures of very important economic indices arouses interest as to why Nigeria has not reproduced the success achieved in other climes through the adoption of trade liberalization policies in its own economy.

Objectives of the study

The Objective of this study is to investigate the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of manufacturing sectors in Nigeria.

Research Questions

What is the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria?

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Hypotheses

The null hypothesis of this study is stated as trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria.

Methodology

Unit root test will help to check if the statistical properties of the time series data changes with time and Cointegration analysis will establish the existence or not of a long run relationship between the variables of interest. In order to examine the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of manufacturing sector in Nigeria, the equation will be modelled as follows;

$$CU = f(TLD, TR, NEX, EXR, IN, IR, L, K) \quad 1$$

Where:

- CU= Capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector.
- TLD= Trade Liberalization Dummy used to proxy Trade Liberalization
- TR= Average import tariff collection rate
- NEX=Net Export
- EXR=Exchange rate
- IN= Inflation rate
- IR= Interest rate
- L= Labour Inputs
- K= Capital proxied by Bank credit to the manufacturing sector

Hence, by transforming equation 1 into an econometric form and adding natural logarithm to the variables, the equation then becomes:

$$CU_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLD_t + \beta_2 TR_t + \beta_3 NEX_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 IN_t + \beta_6 IR_t + \beta_7 \ln L_t + \beta_8 \ln K_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 2$$

Where

- t = Time period
- ε_t = Stochastic error term
- β_0 = Intercept
- $\beta_1 \dots \beta_8$ = Elasticity coefficients of the explanatory variables TLD, TR, NEX, EXR, IN, IR, L and K respectively.
- \ln = Natural Logarithm

The general form of Stock and Watson (1993) Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS) is given as:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \bar{\theta}X + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\theta}_j \Delta X_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad 3$$

- Y_t = dependent variable,
 - X = matrix of explanatory variables,
 - $\bar{\theta}$ = cointegration vector; that is, represent the long run cumulative multipliers or alternatively, the long run effect of a change in x on y ,
 - P = lag length,
 - q = lead length Lag and lead terms included in DOLS regression have the purpose of making its stochastic error term independent of all past innovations in stochastic regressors
- Consequently, equation 3 will be re-specified following Stock and Watson (1993) Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS) as stated in equation 4 as:

Impact of Trade Liberalization... (Felix, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

$$\begin{aligned}
 CU_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLD_t + \beta_2 TR_t + \beta_3 NEX_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 IN_t + \beta_6 IR_t + \beta_7 L_t + \beta_8 \ln K_t \\
 & + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_1 \Delta TLD_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_2 \Delta TR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_3 \Delta NET_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_4 \Delta \ln EXR_{t-j} \\
 & + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_5 \Delta \ln IN_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_6 \Delta \ln IR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_7 \Delta L_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_8 \Delta K_{t-j} \\
 & + \mu_t \qquad \qquad \qquad \dots \dots \dots \qquad \qquad \qquad 4
 \end{aligned}$$

Presentation of Results

The result is aimed at answering the question, what is the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria?

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics Table

	<i>CU</i>	<i>TLD</i>	<i>REX</i>	<i>EXCR</i>	<i>IN</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>K</i>
Mean	46.28	0.86	6,227,896.95	117.06	18.97	83.68	7,341.73
Standard Deviation	9.70	0.35	7,243,130.91	122.84	17.15	1.66	10,706.75
Kurtosis	0.22	2.61	0.22	0.94	3.39	(0.89)	1.04
Skewness	0.56	(2.12)	1.03	1.19	1.99	(0.24)	1.42
Minimum	30.40	0	7,502.50	0.61	0.22	80.12	8.57
Maximum	73.26	1.00	27,251,572.39	476.41	76.76	86.03	38,952.43
Count	42.00	42.00	42.00	42.00	42.00	42.00	42.00

Source: Author's Computation

The outcome is displayed in Table 1 which summarized the basic statistical features of the data under consideration to know the distinctive features of each of the variables that made up the sample data and to determine whether there exist outliers

Table 2: Correlation Matrix Table

	<i>CU</i>	<i>OGM</i>	<i>EMP</i>	<i>TLD</i>	<i>REX</i>	<i>EXCR</i>	<i>INF</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>K</i>
<i>CU</i>	1								
<i>TRDL</i>	-0.206	0.073	-0.493	1					
<i>REX</i>	0.291	0.687	-0.746	0.355	1				
<i>EXCR</i>	0.208	0.696	-0.666	0.391	0.906	1			
<i>INF</i>	-0.213	-0.094	0.416	0.140	-0.287	-0.253	1		
<i>L</i>	-0.150	-0.357	-0.567	0.645	0.278	0.271	-0.188	1	
<i>K</i>	0.248	0.831	-0.572	0.283	0.910	0.945	-0.201	0.033	1

Source: Author's Computation

The correlation matrix measures the degree and direction of a linear relationship or association between two variables. Its value ranges between 0 and 1. -1 indicates a perfect negative association while +1 indicates a perfect positive association and 0

Impact of Trade Liberalization... (Felix, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

implies the absence of correlation. Hence, table 2 presents the correlation matrix illustrating the association between the dependent and independent variables.

Table 3 Unit Root Test Result

Variables	ADF			Remark
CU	-3.989048**	-7.220529**	I(0)	Stationary @ level
REX	1.323333	-4.125299	I(1)	Stationary @ 1 st Diff
EXCR	1.323333	-4.125299	I(1)	Stationary @ 1 st Diff
INF	-3.268025	-6.378690**	I(0)	Stationary @ level
L	-1.996727	-3.741716**	I(0)	Stationary @ level
K	2.831799	-3.867123**	I(1)	Stationary @ 1 st Diff

Source: Eviews 10

Table 3 presents the outcome of the unit root analysis for the variables employed in this research. The result revealed that CU, EMP, INF and L were stationary at level whereas, other variables such as OGM, REX, EXCR, and K gained stationarity at first differencing. Summary of the unit root test suggesting mixed combination of both I (0) and I (1) levels of integration gives room for the suitability to apply the Dynamic ordinary least squares (DOS) method of analysis .

The null hypothesis of this study is stated as trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria.

Table 4 Johansen Co-integration Table

Fisher Statistics	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Conclusion
Model	181.8996** 128.2739	150.5585 117.7	Cointegrated

Source: Author's Computation using Eviews 10

What is the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria?

In order to examine the impact of trade liberalization on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria, we will have the following equations

$$CU = f(TLD, TR, NEX, EXR, IN, IR, L, K) \quad \dots \dots \dots 5$$

Where:

- CU= Capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector.
- TLD= Trade Liberalization Dummy used to proxy Trade Liberalization
- TR= Average import tariff collection rate
- NEX= Net Export
- EXR= Exchange rate
- IN= Inflation rate
- IR= Interest rate
- L= Labour Inputs
- K= Capital proxied by Bank credit to the manufacturing sector

Hence, by transforming equation 5 into an econometric form and adding natural logarithm to the variables, the equation then becomes:

$$CU_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLD_t + \beta_2 TR_t + \beta_3 NEX_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 IN_t + \beta_6 IR_t + \beta_7 \ln L_t + \beta_8 \ln K_t + \varepsilon_t \quad \dots \dots \dots 6$$

Where

- t= Time period
- ε_t = Stochastic error term
- β_0 = Intercept
- $\beta_1 \dots \beta_8$ = Elasticity coefficients of the explanatory variables TLD, TR, NEX, EXR, IN, IR, L and K respectively.
- ln= Natural Logarithm

The general form of Stock and Watson (1993) Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS) is given as:

Impact of Trade Liberalization... (Felix, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \bar{\Phi}X + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\Phi}_j \Delta X_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad \dots \dots \dots 7$$

Y_t = dependent variable,
 X = matrix of explanatory variables,
 $\bar{\Phi}$ = cointegration vector; that is, represent the long run cumulative multipliers or alternatively, the long run effect of a change in x on y,
 P = lag length,
 q = lead length Lag and lead terms included in DOLS regression have the purpose of making its stochastic error term independent of all past innovations in stochastic regressors
 Consequently, equation 6 will be re-specified following Stock and Watson (1993) Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS) as stated in equation 7 as:

$$CU_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLD_t + \beta_2 TR_t + \beta_3 NEX_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 IN_t + \beta_6 IR_t + \beta_7 L_t + \beta_8 \ln K_t + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\theta}_1 \Delta TLD_{t-j} + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\theta}_2 \Delta TR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\theta}_3 \Delta NET_{t-j} + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\theta}_4 \Delta \ln EXR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\theta}_5 \Delta \ln IN_{t-j} + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\theta}_6 \Delta \ln IR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\theta}_7 \Delta L_{t-j} + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\theta}_8 \Delta K_{t-j} + \mu_t \quad \dots \dots \dots 8$$

Table 5: Results of the DOLS Estimates (Model One)

Variable (LONG RUN EQUATION)	Coefficient	Prob.
TLD	-7.563201	0.5014
REX	-8.91E-07	0.6968
EXCR	0.002583	0.9745
INFL	-0.104158	0.5871
LBR	-8.524376	0.2150
CRDT	-0.002107	0.4518
C	731.4351	0.1855
@TREND	2.623693	0.0611
R2	0.746125	
F-test	2.334621	0.046525
N	42	

Dependent Variable: CU

*Note: ***, ** and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively.*

Source: Author's Computation

The result of the regression result is as indicated in Table 5. From the result, few of the variable (TLD, REX and IR) are statistically significance at 5 and 10% respectively. The coefficient of the trade liberalization dummy is positive and statistically significance at 5%. It shows that the higher the level of trade liberalization in the economy, the more the level of manufacturing capacity utilization. It Shows that trade liberalization positively impacts manufacturing capacity utilization in Nigeria.

Hypothesis

H_0 : Trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: If the p-value is greater than the level of significance of 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis; otherwise we reject it.

Reject H_0 if p-value < 0.05

Impact of Trade Liberalization... (Felix, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

Accept H_0 if $p\text{-value} > 0.05$

The DOLS analysis in Table 6 shows that the P-value of the Trade Liberalization is 0.5014. Given that the p-value is higher than the significance level of 0.05, therefore, we can conclude that the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. It can further be inferred that Trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

In accordance with this hypothesis, it was discovered that trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Manufacturing capacity utilization, manufacturing output and manufacturing value added were employed to proxy manufacturing performance while money supply as a percentage of GDP, domestic credit to the private sector and liquidity ratio were employed to proxy financial development. By using the dynamic error correction model, the results of the estimates revealed that credit to private sector and money supply as a percentage of GDP had positive but insignificant impact on capacity utilization and output of the manufacturing sector in the short run. Whereas, they both have negative but significant effect on manufacturing value added in the short run.

Conversely, the result of this study agreed with the study of Onakoya and Efeni (2020) that carried out a study to examine the effect of trade liberalization on the Nigerian Manufacturing sector output between 1980 and 2015. The study employed the Vector Error Correction Mechanism VECM and the impulse-response test was used in order to establish the direction of causality and to determine the ripple effects of the shock of one variable on the other. The study utilized the contribution of manufacturing output to GDP as proxy for manufacturing output and measure trade liberalization by the level of trade openness, other variables utilized were inflation, exchange rate and government expenditure on economic activities. Results of this research revealed a negative long run but significant relation between trade liberalization and manufacturing sector output. That is, trade liberalization had no impact on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria, both in the short and longrun,

The outcome of this study is also consistent with the study of Nzeribe, Uzonwanne and Ezenekwe (2018) who investigated if trade liberalization led to industrialization or de-industrialisation during the period 1980 – 2017 in Nigeria. Variables of trade liberalization, gross capital formation, human capital index, trade openness, labour force and foreign direct investment were modelled and specified, while estimation was done using the ARDL bounds test approach and interaction of trade liberalization dummy with trade openness. The results revealed that in the long-run trade openness and human capital impacted negatively on manufacturing value added. It concluded that trade liberalization caused de-industrialization and not industrialization in Nigeria over the period of study-

Conclusion

The primary focus of this study was to investigate the long-term effects of trade liberalization on the performance, output growth, and employment of Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Evidence of the beneficial effects of trade liberalization on the manufacturing sector's growth performance and employment was discovered in the study. Due to trade liberalization, Nigeria's manufacturing sector is more susceptible to outside shocks, which has slowed their growth. Therefore, unintended benefits of trade liberalization have resulted from the manufacturing industries' inability to compete favorably with established foreign firms. This is evident from Nigeria's exports of primary commodities devoid of value addition and its net imports of completed manufactured goods rather than imports of technology or other necessary production inputs. In light of this, it can be concluded that the current trade liberalization strategy, which emphasizes lowering tariffs and expanding economic openness, is not having the desired effect on Nigeria's manufacturing sector performance. This is proof that more trade liberalization strategies can give Nigerian manufacturers greater access to the market and enable them to enter new domestic and foreign markets. This may result in increased demand, which would force businesses to boost output and bring on more staff to satisfy the demand.

Recommendations

To improve trade, lower trade barriers, and simplify regulatory requirements, the government must implement trade facilitation measures. This might involve establishing trade facilitation centers to help manufacturers navigate trade procedures, standardizing trade laws, and implementing electronic customs systems.

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Qualitative Study on Education for National Security and Sustainable Development in Nigeria: Challenges and Way Forward

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Abstract

The critical security crises confronting Nigeria are identified by different names, such as: kidnapping; Boko Haram insurgency; socio-economic agitations; boundary disputes; cultism; corruption; robbery, including pen robbery; looting of the national treasury; election crises; herdsmen brutality; and ethnic rivalry and religious pluralism. Failures in education pose distinct threats to national security. How can education promote security? Many conflicts arise from ignorance and manipulation of ethnic and religious identity. Education, not mere schooling, produces tolerant and civil citizens who are able to understand and live with people from different economic, religious, ethnic, cultural, and other backgrounds. Although it is widely acknowledged that education aids society in the development of new attitudes, values, knowledge, skill, and technique, little is said about how these values are actually developed and changed within individuals, how values may be communicated, and how educational processes within formal and non-formal curriculum may promote such value development. On this note, the paper focuses on the role of education in curbing environmental challenges for national security and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Education, National Security, Challenges, Sustainable Development, Nigeria.

Introduction

In Nigerian society, the word "national security" sprang to prominence during the upheavals that followed the political scuffle of 1966, which signaled the start of the Nigerian civil war, which lasted from 1967 to 1970. The restoration to civil democracy in 1999, following the military's departure from active politics and national administration, saw the word ascend and become common language in our polity. There is no denying that Nigeria is currently dealing with major security issues, which have placed every citizen on edge, especially those in positions of authority and even the security personnel tasked with protecting people and property. Compatriots find it difficult to fall asleep with closed eyes. Since the past four years, Nigeria's insecurity wave, dynamics, and complexity have seen a drastic change. In the hierarchy of Nigeria's societal issues, insecurity used to be one of the least concerning issues, but it has since grown to alarming proportions. At a time when we believed that corruption and power outages were the root of all of our issues, the country's current top concern is insecurity (FinIntell, 2013).

Nigerians now live with a constant sense of fear, dread, and jitteriness. As a result, the government consistently allots a sizable sum of money to security with the intent of resolving these security issues. A quick peek at the daily newspapers in Nigeria will persuade one of the states that the nation is insecure. Youth unrest, kidnapping, bombing, arson, militancy, and insurgency, among other things, have grown prevalent (Ogheneakoke, 2014). This social issue has hindered economic development, human capital development, and national growth. No country can flourish in an unstable environment, according to Robert McNamara, a former president of the World Bank. According to him, stability and peace are essential elements of growth. According to Mordi (2013), the ongoing mayhem and devastation of lives and property in various regions of the country brought on by the threat of BokoHaram in the Northern states, militants, and kidnappers in the South, among others, have stunted Nigeria's growth and stability. As farming and agricultural activities have been hindered, food production has been

Qualitative Study on Education... (Lyam, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

severely harmed and is on the decline, while oil exploration, exploitation, and export have all suffered in the North and South, respectively.

Concept of National Security in Nigeria

Before defining national security, we must define security. Wikipedia defines security as freedom from or resistance against potential damage (or other unwanted forced change) from others. (<https://en.m.wikipedia.org>), Nmom (2013) defined security as a complete condition of peace for an individual, organization, state, or nation at a specific moment and place. He believed that a relative peace could guarantee excellent life and social cohesion for the survival of a group or nation. From the preceding definitions, security is seen as protecting the general population and is a government-people responsibility. Thus, community policing is a common security term in Nigeria. It protects a state or organization from terrorism, theft, and espionage, as well as anxiety and fear (Ogheneakoke, 2014). Thus, a nation's security interests encompass life and property protection, economic, physiological, and mental well-being, and the ability to pursue goals without interference (Otoibhi, 2012).

Brown (2013) defines national security as the ability to protect the nation's physical integrity and territory, maintain reasonable economic connections with the rest of the world, protect its nature, institutions, and government from outside upheaval, and control its borders. Our most cherished values and beliefs, our democratic way of life, our institutions of governance, and our unity, welfare, and well-being as a nation and people are permanently maintained and continuously reinforced by national security. Quality education, economic power, military strength, diplomacy, and power projection are needed to preserve the nation. It is the nation's individuals, political entities, human associations, and ethnic groups' security interests (Osakwe, 2013). National security is the government's responsibility to protect a nation's citizens, economy, and institutions.

Thus, national security strategy includes the use of diplomatic, economic, and military force in peace and conflict to protect the nation-state. In other words, it means freedom from foreign dominance, which is essential for state survival through economic, diplomatic, power projection, and political power.

National Security and Sustainable Development in Nigeria

Modern national security entails developing a nexus of collaborative military, paramilitary, and civic organizations and acquiring and sharing national and cross-border intelligence to improve national and citizen safety and health. Most crucially, modern national security is based on a nation's economic well-being, while the military individual complex helps maintain peace and tranquility in any society. Thus, economic factors largely determine citizen peace and stability. Thus, a nation's economy is its main security pillar. A nation's security is improved when its labor force, especially its youth, is gainfully employed and welfare programmes are created to protect the unemployed and disabled. Education is essential because of this. Education creates productive workers. Modern thought and practice have rejected the idea that national security is restricted to acquiring and storing massive military gear, demonstrating intimidating military power, or traditional military operations, while they may be part of a nation's security architecture. However, today's security depends on development.

Sustainable development in this context means a nation's ability to use its people and capital resources to allow its citizens to dream and achieve their goals in a supportive and well-structured environment. When this is done regularly and sustainably, disturbance and violence decrease and security improves. Late World Bank president Robert McNamara advocated this holistic national security approach. "The world can never be in peace unless people enjoy security in their everyday existence," declared the UNDP (2014) Human Development Report in Usman (2015). The state is responsible for security and sustainable development. Human security empowers residents to discuss unusual security issues and grow the country. Seji et al. (2020) correctly stated that "security is not military hardware, though it may incorporate it, security is not military force, though it may involve it, security is not traditional military activities, though it may encompass it." Security requires progress. Sustainable development means economic, social, and political advancement. It signifies living comfortably.

Concept of Education

For the growth of any society, education is crucial. In fact, every human community that yearns for progress in all senses of the word should not disregard education, according to Freire (1970), who claims that it is a major weapon of social transformation. The Nigerian government understands the value of education for the general development of the country and views it as "an instrument for achieving national development," as evidenced by the following set of educational principles:

1. Education is an instrument for national development and social change
2. Education is vital for the promotion of a progressive and united Nigeria
3. Education maximizes the creative potentials and skills of the individual for self-fulfilment and general development of the society.

Qualitative Study on Education... (Lyam, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

4. Education is compulsory and a right of every Nigerian irrespective of gender, social status, religion, colour, ethnic background and any peculiar individual challenges: and
5. Education is to be qualitative, comprehensive, functional and relevant to the needs of the society (FGN, 2014).

To define education, scholars have included "quality." They believed education must be high-quality to fulfill its goals. According to Maduwesi in Seji et al. (2020), excellent education requires that all levels and parts of the educational system, including vocational, practical, and theoretical education, create results that benefit the nation. It involves well-articulated national goals, well-planned curriculum, assessment technique and instruments, data analysis, how to use assessment results, and student quality. He sees poor parenting and a conviction among many adolescents and adults that education and hard effort are not important as the biggest obstacles to decent education.

UNESCO (2015), another UN body, wrote that quality education should promote quality, encourage creative and emotional development, support peace, citizenship, and security, and seek out past global and local cultural values to pass on to future generations. Quality education promotes and improves basic education, reorients educational policies and programs at all levels to address national security and sustainable development, develops public awareness, and provides training and retraining, including higher education, Seji, Philip, and John (2020). Thus, education must be holistic, including qualitative and quantitative processes like "relevant curriculum, availability of adequate human and non-human resources, assessment of educational programmes and processes through proper supervision and evaluation of educational outcomes to ensure quality assurance, control and nation security" (Osakwe, 2013).

Effects of Insecurity in Nigeria

Companies are closing operations in Boko-Haram-ravaged north and oil-rich south-south and moving to neighboring African countries due to loss of life and property. Few companies survive. Construction workers and expatriates working on specialized projects in these places have fled for safety. This has increased the number of homeless youth and made violence easier. This situation worsens poverty and unemployment. They think education underpins social economic progress (Freire, 1970). Islamic extremists have repeatedly kidnapped kids and school facilities in northern states (Chibok Girls and Burnin Yadin Boys Government Schools). Many schools have discontinued academic programs. This has greatly reduced the number of students applying to all academic levels. The University of Maiduguri, one of Nigeria's most cheap universities, now solicits admission through media outreach.

A recent survey found that many students would refuse to serve in the mandatory one-year national youth service corps (NYSC) if assigned to the north. After three weeks of obligatory camping, those accidentally sent north were redeployed. This defeats the 1973 NYSC Act's main purpose (FinIntell, 2013). Nigeria loses worldwide esteem as the security situation worsens. It strains bilateral relations. If this unsightly trend is not addressed immediately, it will negatively impact all development indices and the millennium development target, making vision 2020 a mirage. (2013).

Place of Education in for National Security and Sustainable Development in Nigeria

Education passes on culture. It alters human behavior for good. Education is one of the oldest industries in human history, therefore a society's future depends on the quality of its members' education. Education can avoid, eliminate, or modify violence in Nigeria due to its effects on socioeconomic, moral, and political life. Danmole (2015) claims that only education can create literate and educated citizens. Education improves life, worldview, and adaptability. Education will illumine minds and enthrone right religious knowledge to end deadly religious conflict. It is true that intolerance and fanaticism cause religious bloodshed in Nigeria, but education reduces bad ideals and promotes patriotism, a national value. Fagbemi (2012) proposes that public education can increase Nigerian tolerance and patriotism.

In the NPE (2014), the Federal Government states that "education shall continue to be highlighted in the National Development because education is the most important instrument of change, any fundamental change in the intellectual and social outlook of any society has to be preceded by an educational revolution". Our existing education system prioritizes science and technology over citizenship education, yet it fails to meet its goals. History relocated to senior secondary school. Few students volunteer. Due to social studies' limitations, few young people know Nigeria's history. To promote education access, the Federal Government is supporting private education involvement. However, religious schools and universities may harm national unity. This may not solve morality. Since the institutions create Muslims, Anglicans, Baptists, and Catholics instead of Nigerians, loyalty is now likely to the church or religion rather than the state.

Thus, citizenship education must be strengthened in theory and practice with other topics. Nigerian pride would solve all problems. Nigerian education promotes a fair and equal society (NPE, 2014). This philosophy helps bring peace. Peace and growth result from justly resolving conflicts without tribalism, nepotism, or religious bias. Educational growth may reduce poverty, maintain national security, and boost regional prosperity, according to Ololube and Egbezor (2022). Education

Qualitative Study on Education... (Lyam, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

promotes national unity, human capital development, cultural diversity, human rights, and global knowledge chains by increasing access, capacity building, and information exchange. Education builds universal values-based norms, especially in multi-cultural and multi-religious civilizations. Education shares knowledge about culture, science, technology, values, and norms.

Challenges of Education for Sustainable Development in Nigeria

Some of the challenges of education that if eradicated will enhance sustainable development in Nigeria and Africa at large include;

1. Existing Policy framework cannot adequately support education in a global economy due to the following among others:
 - a. Inadequate fidelity in policy implementation, i.e. some relevant parts of the education system do not support policies.
 - b. Policies are not given enough time to produce results due to policy summer sault.
2. Education is not adequately funded due to scarce resources and inadequate public/private partnership in funding education. As a result,
 - a. Teachers' conditions of service is not good and not motivating enough to make them undertake the heavier task of preparing students for an entirely new world.
 - b. Educational infrastructures such as access roads, classrooms, laboratories, etc are in poor condition. Thus, the current learning environment cannot meet the demands of the 21st century learning; etc.
3. Teachers are inadequately trained. Educator preparing programmes in Nigeria are not yet preparing their graduates to possess, teach and assess 21st century knowledge and skills. As a result, they cannot become change agents for embedding 21st century knowledge, skills in core subjects.
4. For pedagogy, for students of social change, the usefulness and essence of training and education cannot be overemphasized. One of the major challenges of education as a tool for development in Africa and Nigeria in particular is that apart from issues of funding and brain-drain, there is a disconnect between realities on the ground and what the children and folk are taught in schools.

The result is that a graduate of Electrical Engineering from a tertiary institution goes out to pay an electrician to do his electrical jobs at home. In social sciences, for instance, students are often taught about the writings of David Easton, Talcot Parson, Adams Smith etc, while we systematically forget about even equally important philosophy for pre-colonial African minds. As such political scientists are taught more about Ancient Greece than pre-colonial Onitsha, Oyo or Calabar.

Education as the way forward

On November 21, 2013, former British Prime Minister Tony Blair addressed the UN counter-terrorism organization that broad-based cross-cultural education is essential to fighting religion-based terrorism. "There is little doubt now regarding the nature of this scourge," he said. That it is extremism founded on religious perversion, a fanaticism that justifies violence against innocent civilians". The Tony Blair Faith Foundation helps reduce religious intolerance, conflict, and extremism under his leadership. He underlined that teaching about diversity, tolerance, and respect is as important as teaching the humanities, sciences, and languages.

"That is why in the 21st century, education is a security issue and not any education but education specifically that opens young minds to the others; who are culturally and religiously different, and shows them how the only future that works is one in which people are respected as equals whatever their faith or culture," Mr. Blair concluded. me in you. We should seek peace. When he observed, Ban Ki-Chef Moon's de Cabinet Susana Malcorra stressed the importance of education in combating radical beliefs that incite hatred and violence and fostering empathy. Markets, schools, places of worship, neighborhoods, and communities have been destroyed by mindless bloodshed. That we must collaborate to combat this dreadful epidemic and engage young people to show them a world of fairness, justice, opportunity, and empowerment.

One of the most significant international organizations, Global Partnership for Education channels billions of dollars from over twenty countries to strengthen education systems in fifty-nine developing countries. Former Australian Prime Minister Julia Gillard, now Chairwoman of Global Partnership for Education (GPE), promotes education investment as enlightened self-interest. That anyone concerned about promoting economic growth and combating extremism should create classrooms and train teachers. That tens of millions of youngsters in sub-Saharan Africa lack primary education. UNESCO reports hundreds of millions more who leave school illiterate due to substandard education. "In some ways the argument for getting every child into school speaks for itself, but in our busy noisy world, even things that should be obvious have to be spoken for and championed," Gillard said of Nigerian schoolgirls. She said the Boko Haram kidnapping of Nigerian schoolgirls

Qualitative Study on Education... (Lyam, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

should be a warning about extremism and a call to preserve education. Education in such communities is powerful and important. "That they obviously believe education is strong, so powerful that they wish to deny those girls". The global education crisis has been highlighted by the Nigerian scenario. Gillard hoped it would galvanize the world to come to the rescue of the school girls in Nigeria and to ensure that the power of education is given to children even in the most difficult circumstances.

Conclusion

For education to lead to economic growth and national security for sustainable development, there must be equitable access through adequate public investment in classrooms, relevant curriculum, trained teachers, technology for learning and teaching, teaching and learning materials, and enough time for all levels of learning. Efficient education management aside, the economy should be well managed to translate the nation's wealth to people's welfare through adequate investment in health services, education services, security, enabling environment, and employment opportunities to maximize skilled labor's contribution to national productivity and society's growth. In a knowledge society, proper research funding encourages the acquisition, accumulation, adoption, adaptation, and application of local and international innovation and knowledge. Education, innovation, and technical systems should work together to turn classroom lessons into sustainable economic production.

As citizens worked, insecurity would decrease. Finally, controlling education for national security and sustainable development in Nigeria and Africa should not be limited to schooling for job and life. Instead, it should be conceptualized as a system-wide formal, non-formal, and informal education and training well designed and coordinated to empower the citizens and future of Nigeria and Africa in the areas of productive and environmental skills, spirit (consciousness), science, and technologies needed to stimulate, strengthen, spread, and sustain structural transformation and vigorously reduce security problems in Nigeria and Africa.

National security is a Nigerian thinking problem (psyche). Nigeria has the human and material resources for prosperity, safety, and security. This requires changing Nigerians' thinking. Education must change their minds. Proper education must begin at birth and continue until death. Such education must utilize all necessary tools to reorient their brains into a proper value system; into proper concepts and the context of "wealth and success", "safety and welfare", "freedom and liberty", "justice and fair play", "rule of law", and "responsibility". These are mind-made. Only "education" can bend or unbend the mind.

Recommendations

This paper recommends the under listed points/suggestions, as panacea for this seemingly intractable insecurity challenges in Nigeria:

1. The Federal Government (FG) should establish and implement policies and programs to address the root causes of insecurity in Nigeria, such as high illiteracy, poverty, unemployment, environmental degradation, lack of infrastructure amenities, unequal development, and others.
2. The government should phase out the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) and replace it with a more effective agency or declare an educational emergency. We hope this would solve the vast illiteracy that causes abject poverty in rural Nigeria.
3. The government should revive the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) and reposition the agriculture sector to provide jobs for Nigerian youths. As we stated before in this study, technical schools and polytechnics should be prioritized in educational policy for excellent vocational education/skill development.
4. Federal, state, and local governments in Nigeria need collaborative security arrangements. The central/federal government's complete control over security must be addressed. Community policing comes up here. This security configuration should create a village, community, municipal, state, and federal committee to provide critical security information to security authorities at their locations. This will help identify criminals, sponsors, and hideouts in the country.
5. Finally, the FG should revamp Nigeria's intelligence system and strengthen its security apparatus. This will help reduce hoodlum bombings, robberies, kidnappings, and violent crimes in the country.
6. For all these to be achieved, quality education for the masses is key.

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Assessment of Early Counseling... (Ijale & Yusuf, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

Assessment of Early Counseling Technique on Future Education among Public Primary School Pupils in North-Central, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined assessment of Early Counselling Technique on Future Education among Public Primary School Pupils in, North-Central Nigeria. It raised two research questions, two and corresponding null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study. Survey Research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of entire public primary school's pupils during the 2022/2023 academic session in North-Central Nigeria. The sample of the study comprised of 30 pupils who were selected using purposive sampling technique, 5 schools from each State in north central. Questionnaire titled Early Counselling for Future Education (ECFE) was used to collect information from the respondents. The instrument was weighted on four (4) point scale of SD, A, DA SDA. The instrument was validated by 3 experts in the fields of Psychology, and measurement and evaluation from Federal College of Education, Zaria. Simple percentage was used to answer the research questions and t-test was used to analyze the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed that there is statistically significant relationship between early counselling and future Education in North-Central, Nigeria. It is also revealed that there is statistically significant relationship between follow up counselling service and future education. It was concluded that early counselling has significant impact on future education and follow-up service has positive influence on future education in North-Central, Nigeria. It was recommended that early counselling for future Education should be encouraged. And also, follow-up service in counselling should be supported by government to revive future Education in north-central, Nigeria.

Keywords: Early Counselling Techniques, Future Education and Public-School Pupils.

Introduction

The elementary school level of education is the most important in all education levels. It is for this reason that it is labeled primary school. The primary school, is but part of the early education processes that prepares a child for the secondary school, among other numerous benefits. It is important to note here that both the primary school teachers and parents of the pupils join hands to mold the mind of the child to a meaningful status (Egbo, 2015).

The need to institute counselling programmes in primary school cannot be over emphasized. Human mind at this level is usually in a "tabular rasa" form. This implies that the mind of the child, at this level is virgin and open, needs to be filled up. By virtues of good counselling and subsequent training, the pupil begins to develop positively. This is what task this paper explores using guidance and counselling as a prolific tool for effective human living and adjustment. Thus, guidance and counseling are remedial, preventive and developmental. It takes care of the needs of the pupils to demonstrate adjustment and maturity in relationships and cushion possible discovery of their talents, abilities, potentialities, strengths and weakness at the earliest stages for their own betterment. The need for pupils to live functional and meaningful lives makes it imperative that early guidance and counseling programmes should be established at the primary school level. The aim is to enhance early and positive adjustment procedures for meaningful living.

Guidance is a programme of service meant to enhance the ability of clients to cope with circumstances and be of need to themselves and the society. Guidance enables clients to make choices which are intended to bring self-direction and adjustment. It is designed to help clients adjust meaningfully to the environment, develop the ability to set realistic goals and improve on total educational programmes Egbo, (2015). Thus, Zera and Riccio in Omebe (2016) defined guidance as a process, developmental in nature, by which an individual is assisted to understand, accept and utilize own abilities, aptitudes, interests and attitudinal patterns in relation to the aspirations. As well, Isakson and Minsk in Omebe (2016) see guidance as a programme

Assessment of Early Counseling... (Ijale & Yusuf, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

of service to individuals based on the needs of each individual; an understanding of his immediate environment and the influences of the factors on the learner and unique features of the school. This is why counselling assists each pupil to understand himself, accept himself and live effectively in his society in addition to having learning experiences about his world of work (Alao, 2021). Pupils' right from school start preparation for the world of work and should be properly guided in educational, personal –social and vocational spheres of life in order to make right choices.

Ipaye (2014) upholds that guidance in everyday language has always carried the connotation of help given to an individual or group of individuals in areas like personal, social, educational and vocational which are designed to ensure meaningful adjustment in their existence. Good guidance programmes organized for learners at the primary school level are therefore intended to actualize positivity in whole life adjustment meant to cushion the growing child into meaningful living and adaptations. Counselling, on the other hand is the soul of the guidance programme, and the wheel upon which guidance rotates. It is a process in which a specialist counsellor undertakes to assist another person in a person to person or face to face encounter. The assistance may take many forms which includes educational, vocational, social, recreational, emotional and or moral, and this could be organized in groups or individually. Thus, Roux in Anagbogu (2022) defines counselling as a dynamic and purposeful relationship between two people in which procedures vary with the nature of the students' needs, but in which there is always mutual participation by the counsellor and the client with the focus of self-actualization and self-determination by the client.

Counselling is a relationship characterized by mutual respect, effective communication, genuine and complete acceptances of the client by the counsellor and concentration on the needs, problems and feelings of the clients. It is also relationship that facilitates growth and changes in the client to become more freely and fully functional. It is a major service that is incorporated in guidance which is but an interactive process between a counsellor and the client, meant to enhance proper self-understanding for the client to have better behavioural changes. Thus, Anagbogu (2022) affirms that individuals strive to achieve optimal development of personal resources and that counselling aid the children in developing the most effective ways of identifying and achieving desired and desirable goals for better adjustment and living. That means that counselling prevents frustrations, anxieties and stress. Follow-up services enable the guidance counsellor to see through the services he/she must have offered the counsellee. It is an avenue through which the counsellor determines the effectiveness of planning and placement activities. Sokan and Osarenren (2015).

The North Central is one of the six (6) geo-political zones of Nigeria. Also known as middle belt. It comprises of 6 states. Namely, Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Plateau and Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The North Central stretching across the whole range of the country, from the border with Cameroon to that with Benin. In terms of the terrain, the zone is predominantly known to be farmers and are blessed with fertile land for farming. The region has a population of about 20 Million people, which is about 11th population of the entire population of the country. The counselling service allows the counsellor to see and verify whether the guided or counseled individual or group is coping after guidance or counselling.

The entire functions of the guidance counsellor in the school setting are to assist each student to understand himself and live effectively in the society. The need for guidance services in the school system is therefore based on the assumption that the individual who understands himself and his environment will be more productive and effective in his entire endeavour. The objectives which the functions performed by the guidance counsellor in the school system according to Ijale & Umaru (2021) includes:

1. To help pupils develop the skills of self-study, self-analysis and self-understanding.
2. Guidance services should help pupils develop awareness of opportunities in the personal, social, educational, vocational areas by providing them with appropriate, useful and useable information.
3. Also, guidance services in the school should help pupils acquire the skills of collecting and using appropriate information.
4. To assist all pupils in making appropriate and satisfactory personal, social, educational, vocational and leisure choices.
5. Counselling service should help pupils develop positive attitude to self, to others, mental health, to appropriate national issues, to work and learning.
6. To help pupils acquire as early as possible in their lives a positive image of themselves through self-understanding and self-direction.
7. Counselling services should help pupils who are under achieving to use their potentials to the maximum.
8. Also, counselling services in the school should help pupils relate behaviour meaningfully to cognitive achievement and the chances of success in life.

Assessment of Early Counseling... (Ijale & Yusuf, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

9. To help build up or sharpen the staff's perception of reality, development of a sense of autonomy and to whip up the motivation for creativity and productivity.
10. Guidance services in the schools should assist pupils in the process of developing and acquiring skills in problem solving and decision making.
11. To work with significant others in the life of pupils by helping them to understand the needs and problems of the pupils with the purpose of creating, arousing and sustaining their interest in and their understanding of the staff's needs, problems and goals so that the pupils can be optimally helped to attain their goals, handle these problems and those needs.
12. To help route the nation's human resources into appropriate, useful and beneficial channels thus preventing unnecessary economic wastage.
13. Guidance services should help identify and nurture human potentialities in various fields or endeavours thus ensuring adequate manpower development in various sectors of the economy.
14. To help build up in individuals' positive attitude to fellow Nigerians and a sense of total commitment to the unity of Nigeria.

Elementary School Counselling: The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) views the objectives of primary school education to include:

1. The inculcation of permanent literacy, and the ability to communicate effectively
2. The laying of a sound basis for scientific and reflective thinking
3. Citizenship education as a basis for effective participation as contribution to the life of the society.
4. Development in the child, the ability to adapt to his changing environment
5. Providing the child with opportunities for developing manipulative skills that will enable him function effectively the society within the limits of his capacity and
6. Providing basic tools for further educational advancement including preparation trades and crafts of the society.

Transplanting of trees are usually done only when such tree species are seedlings. Tall palm trees can hardly be transplanted. Primary school pupils are tender in age, ranging between six to thirteen years. This makes counselling at this level very paramount and different from counselling at other levels of education. It is at this elementary stage that we can really identify and begin to nurture the potentials of the primary school children to maturity. Based on this, relegating and deferring elementary school counselling are but intentional deferment to the developmental growth of the children which is senseless and cannot be sustained. The best time to frame good behavioural patterns and characteristics in people is at the elementary school stage. At this stage the pupils are still innocent and open to accommodate facts which at maturity (secondary and tertiary), they easily shed off some and retain some.

The primary school children are at the stage of formation of identity and self-concept. They are open to a myriad of options and that is why guidance and counselling services are supposed to be prevalent at this stage because it is better to train pupils than to mend men. The Universal Basic Education in Nigeria in 1976 and the subsequent National Policy on Education are but strategies designed to sustain zeal for education, skill and development in Nigerian school children. They are both fashioned out for functional, universal and qualitative education among Nigerian youths. This is why guidance and counselling services should be provided at the elementary school stage to nurture the development and growth of the school pupils. Thus, Ipaye (2014) writes prophetically that no matter how good and well-structured the new educational policy in Nigeria may be, if guidance and counselling services are not given priority, and made an integral part of the system, it cannot succeed. This is all because the school counsellors in primary schools work with teachers, parents, head teachers and the pupils to induce effectiveness, adjustment and wellbeing of the pupils.

Essence of Primary School Guidance and Counseling

1. Construct alternative behaviour
2. Seek relevant information about alternatives
3. Weigh values and possible outcomes and
4. Formulates tentative plans of action

The counsellor therefore is expected to emphasis therapeutic principles in teaching and counseling the pupils for efficient learning processes. The primary school children therefore need counselling for the following reasons:

1. Need to tap and harness the individual pupils' ability, interest, personality, talents and aptitude starts at this level for their developmental growth.
2. Need to provide special help for numerous primary school children to avert possible crimes and health hazards

Assessment of Early Counseling... (Ijale & Yusuf, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

3. Need to stem the tide of maladaptive behaviours in the school system and the general public
4. Need to identify and nurture the gifted and talented children
5. Need for behavioural changes as many homes now breed social problems
6. Need for outreach counselling especially as many homes are impoverished
7. Need to provide the child with a sound foundation for future, academic, psychological and personal growth

The need for counselling at the primary school system, according to Durojaiye in Egbo (2016) emanate from the fact that the Nigerian family had experienced significant changes that had resulted in breakdown of family cohesiveness and increased rate of divorce. This has significantly increased the one parent home trend and subsequent increment in deviant behaviours among children because:

1. Divorce and its accompanying strains continue to increase
2. Children are being reared differently and more frequently by outsiders (maids or day care givers)
3. Mothers are plagued by the guilt of leaving their children to go to work
4. Parents generally do not have time to monitor their primary school children.

Consequently, primary school teachers and counsellors need to understand the unique characteristics and nature of each pupil as well as be able to make relative referrals at any point in time. Good classroom and social and social climate should be created for inclusive development of the pupils for maximum sustenance of solutions to academic, vocational and personal social problems of the Nigerian primary school pupils

Counselling is oriented towards facilitating effective learning skills, acceptable habits and appropriate behaviour in individual. It is a process through which individuals can understand themselves fully. Within the school system it should be a learning process in which individuals learn about themselves, their interpersonal relationship and behaviours that advance their personal development. However, pupils in primary schools currently are not properly guided or counseled as it ought to be and as such the future education is jeopardized (Bledsoe, 2018). Many pupils learn negatively and peer influence is the order of the day Udoh and George (2014). Reorientation and early counselling can go along to impact pupils positively and assurance for future education in north central, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the impact of early counselling on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in North central.
2. To examine the influence of follow-up service on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in North central.

Research Questions.

1. What is the impact of early counselling on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central, Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of follow-up counselling service on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant impact between early counselling and future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central, Nigeria
2. There is no significant influence between follow- up service and future education among Public Primary School Pupils in North Central, Nigeria

Methodology

The Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. This design is considered appropriate because it enables the researchers to generate data through the standardized collection procedures based on highly structured research instrument(s) and well-defined study concepts and related variables.

The population of this study was made up of 30 pupils in north central, Nigeria. Five (5) schools were selected from each state, and Ten (10) pupils were purposively selected.

A well-constructed and researcher developed Questionnaire titled Early Counselling for Future Education (ECFE) was used to collect information from the respondents. The instrument was weighted on four (4) point scale of SD, A, DA SA. The instrument was validated by 3 experts in the field of Psychology and measurement and evaluation from FCE, Zaria. Simple percentage and t-test was used to analyze the hypotheses.

Assessment of Early Counseling... (Ijale & Yusuf, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

The questionnaire was divided into three sections (A, B and C). Section A was for collection of information on personal data of the respondents while Section B consisted of early counselling questionnaire that elicited responses from the respondents on the impact on counselling services and future education section C contains information on the influence of follow-up services on future education among primary school pupils in north central Nigeria. The section B and C had response options scored thus: Strongly Agree (SA) =4, Agree (A) = 3 Disagree (D) =2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. Simple percentage and t-test was used to analyze the hypotheses.

Results

Research Question one

What is the impact of early counselling on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north?

Table 1: The impact of early counselling on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central, Nigeria.

	Respondents			
	A	SA	D	SD
1. Early counselling could help in future education	50 47.6%	40 38.1%	10 9.5%	5 4.8%
2. Functional counselling at pre-primary to higher education is grantee for better education	60 57.1%	30 28.6%	8 7.6%	7 6.7%
3. Early counselling is very impact in future education	55 52.4%	40 38.1%	10 9.5%	0 0.0%
4. Effective counselling direct pupils on future education	45 42.9%	40 38.1%	15 14.3%	5 4.8%
5. Early counselling help pupils to understand the aim of education	70 66.7%	20 19.0%	5 4.8%	10 9.5%
6. Counselling pupils enhanced understanding of oneself the environment	40 38.1%	55 52.4%	7 6.7%	3 2.9%
7. Early counselling help pupils to be focus and achieve their educational goals.	50 47.6%	45 42.9%	5 4.8%	5 4.8%

Table 1 above shows that early counselling could be of help in future education, 50 respondents representing 47% strongly agree with the statement, 40 respondents representing 38.1% agree, 10 respondents representing 9.5% strongly disagree with the statement while 5 respondents representing 4.8% disagree with the statement. It means that early counselling public primary school could be of help in future education. Functional counselling at pre-primary to higher education is grantee for better education, early counselling is has a significant impact in future education, effective counseling direct pupils on future education, early counselling help pupils to understand the aim of education, counselling pupils enhanced understanding of oneself in the environment and early counselling help pupils to be focus and achieve their education goals, 90 respondents representing 90% strongly agree, agree with the all the statement above while 10 respondents representing 10% strongly disagree, disagree respectively, this connote that the above statement has a positive significant on pupils in public primary school in Zaria Metropolis.

Research Question Two

What is the influence of follow-up counselling service on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central Nigeria?

Assessment of Early Counseling... (Ijale & Yusuf, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

Table 2: The influence of follow-up counselling service on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central Nigeria

	Respondents			
	A	SA	D	SD
1. Follow up service in counselling helps to redirect.	52.4%	38.1%	9.5%	0.0%
	55	40	10	0
2. Follow up enhances consistency in pupils education pursuit.	66.7%	19.0%	4.8%	9.5%
	70	20	5	10
3. Following by both counsellors and government agency only way for better education	38.1%	52.4%	6.7%	2.9%
	40	55	7	3
4. Further education can be revitalized through follow up service by counsellors.	57.1%	19.0%	19.0%	4.8%
	60	20	20	5
5. Consistent and proper counselling service to schools and ministry of education is a system to further education	47.6%	42.9%	9.5%	0.0%
	50	45	10	0
6. Future education is guaranteed with effective service and proper supervision	52.4%	42.9%	4.8%	0.0%
	55	45	5	0

Table 2 above shows that follow-up service in counselling helps to redirect, 52.4% of the respondents agree, 38.1 strongly agree, 9.5% disagree with the statement while 0.0% strongly disagree. There is no doubt that follow up service in counselling helps to redirect pupils among public primary schools. Furthermore, follow-up enhances consistency in pupils education pursuit, following by both counsellors and government agency only way for better education, further education can be revitalized through follow-up service by counsellors, consistent and proper counselling service to schools and ministry of education is a system to further education and future education is guaranteed with effective service and proper supervision. All the respondents agree, strongly agree with the statement above.

Hypotheses One

There is no significant impact between early counselling and future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central, Nigeria

	Mean	N	Std. Dev	Std. error mean	d.f	Correlation	T.cal	P-val
Counselling service	2.11	105	.923	.090	104	.246	.252	.028
Future education	2.09	105	.972	.095				

Table 3. Since the P-value (0.028) is less than 0.05, and accept the null hypothesis.

The result revealed that there is a statistically significant impact of Counselling Services Future on education (t.cal= .252, df= 105, p<0.05). This means that there is positive impact of Counselling Services on Future Education. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypotheses Two: 2

There is no significant influence between follow- up service and future education among Public Primary School Pupils in North Central, Nigeria

	Mean	N	Std. Dev	Std. error mean	Correlation	T.cal	Sig
Follow-up service	1.97	105	.885	.086		0.531	2.235
Future education	2.09	105	.972	.095			.021

Assessment of Early Counseling... (Ijale & Yusuf, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259116>

Table 4. Since the P-value (0.021) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted and the result revealed that there is a statistically significant influence of follow- up Counselling Services on Future education (t.cal= 2.235, df= 104, p<0.05). This means that there is positive influence of Following Service on Future Education. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The result revealed that there is a statistically significant impact of Counselling Services Future on education (t.cal= .252, df= 105, p<0.05). This means that there is positive impact of Counselling techniques on Future Education. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. The result is in agreement with Egbo (2015) which stated that counselling is designed to help clients adjust meaningfully to the environment, develop the ability to set realistic goals and improve on total educational programmes..

The result revealed that there is a statistically significant influence of follow- up Counselling Services on Future education (t.cal= 2.235, df= 104, p<0.05). This means that there is positive influence of Following Service on Future Education. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This result is in line with Ipaye (2014) who writes prophetically that no matter how good and well-structured the new educational policy in Nigeria may be, if guidance and counselling services are not given priority, and made an integral part of the system, it cannot succeed. This is all because the school counsellors in primary schools work with teachers, parents, head teachers and the pupils to induce effectiveness, adjustment and wellbeing of the pupils.

Conclusion

Based on the finding, the study concludes:

1. That there is significant impact of early counselling and future education.
2. There is significant influence of follow-service on future education.

Recommendation

It is therefore recommended that

1. Early counselling will enhance and redeem future Education.
2. It is also recommended that follow-up service in counselling and government support will further revive future Education in north central.
3. Finally, it was recommended that early counselling for future Education should be encouraged.

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Impact of Digitalized Predict... (Moemeke, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

Impact of Digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain Model on Achievement in Genetics among Secondary School Students in Oshimili South Local Government Area, Delta State

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain Model on achievement in genetics among secondary school students in Oshimili South Local Government Area of Delta State. The study employed a non-randomized non-equivalent pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design. The population of the study was all the SS class 2 biology students in the fourteen public schools in the local government area. Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted to select two coeducational schools for the study. Only coeducational schools with at least 30 biology students were selected for the study. This is to enable formation of at least ten groups of three students per group in the experimental group. The experimental group (N=31; Male =14; female =17) was taught genetics using the digital POE (D-POE) model while the control group (N = 38; male = 20; female = 18) were taught the same concepts using the traditional method for a period of six weeks of 80 minutes per week. A 30-item two-tier Diagnostic multiple-choice Test of Achievement in Genetics (TAG) adapted and modified from West African Examinations Council's past question papers in Biology from 2009 to 2019 was used to collect data. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was found to be 0.75 by Kuder Richardson 21. Analysis of covariance showed that the mean scores of the groups differed significantly ($F=1, 68 = 287.395, P=.000$), thus hypothesis one was retained. Also, the t-test showed a no significant difference in mean scores due to sex ($t(1.41; df =29; P \leq .168$). Hypothesis two was rejected. This result showed that adopting the D-POE model provides the impetus for students to overcome achievement challenges in genetics across in both sexes. Further studies with larger samples for longer periods is recommended. Additional factors, such as student preferences, prior technology experience, instructional variations within the model, or teacher characteristics should be investigated to enhance generalization of the findings.

Keyword: Predict-Observe-Explain, Genetics, Technology-enhanced teaching, Achievement.

Introduction

The study of Genetics has great relevance to the life of citizens of any nation. It fosters the acquisition of knowledge of important biological concepts like genes and their place in the inheritance of traits and transmission of inheritable characters, sex determination, some diseases transmission, cure and control; mutations; food production and biotechnology; population control, crop multiplication; diversities and variations in organisms; crime control and a host of other emergent areas (Jackson et al., 2018; Claussnitzer et al., 2020; Roderick et al., 2003). No nation can grow economically and technologically if its citizens are ignorant of the implications of genetics for their life and well-being. Understanding genetics is important to the study of Medicine, Pharmacy, Biotechnology, Agricultural Science, Agricultural Engineering, and disease control. Poor knowledge of genetic principles exacerbates superstitious beliefs and misconceptions about scientific endeavors and is detrimental to important national policy acceptance and implementation (Biroli et al., 2022; Hurst, 2009). For example, refusal to key into national birth control measures geared towards population control, vaccination programmes for the prevention and control of the spread of deadly diseases, apathy to utilizing innovative principles in agriculture for greater food production, and other key national programmes (Reich, 2019; Murakami, 2014). These attitudes that result from scientific illiteracy about genetics are inimical to individual and national progress. It is also common knowledge that in Africa, many families have faced marital challenges and consequent family disruptions because of issues related to the sex of children which ignorantly the female parent has often been blamed.

In spite of the relevance of genetics to life and learning, there have been consistent reports of poor students' achievement in major examinations (West African Examinations Council chief examiner's reports) since 2009. Studies (Etobro & Fabinu, 2017; Haskel-Ittah & Yarden, 2018; Fasasi, 2021; Etobro & Banjoko, 2017) have shown that the situation has not changed appreciably. Poor understanding of Genetics contributes greatly to students' poor performance in biology in the senior secondary school examinations. In 2019 in particular, the WAEC Chief Examiners' report noted with displeasure that students

Impact of Digitalized Predict... (Moemeke, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

had a poor grasp of knowledge of genetics and accused biology teachers of not teaching Genetics at all or doing so unproductively. Okebukola (2014), and Haskel-Ittah and Yarden (2018) also identified Genetics among contents in Biology which learners find difficult because of the abstractness of the concepts and the naïve views that some teachers and students hold before instruction. Akanbi and Kolawole (2014) have expressed concern about this trend and attributed it to a number of variables, one of which is the poor teaching practices employed by biology teachers, who neglect to acknowledge the pre-existing notions or conceptions of their pupils prior to formal training. Some of the views which students bring into the science classrooms are tenacious, not in harmony with the scientific views (Misconceptions or alternative conceptions), and thus resistant to change (Ezechi, 2017, Etobro & Fabinu, 2017; Etobro & Banjoko, 2017). Research (Haskel-Ittah & Yarden, 2018) has shown that most teaching strategies employed by teachers neglect the methods for diagnosis of students' pre-existing conceptions (prior knowledge) and the naïve reasoning behind them which Ausubel (1968) claims are the most influential single factor affecting meaningful learning.

Misconceptions are perceptions and understandings of concepts that are peculiar to a student but which are not in conformity with the scientific views. Halim et al (2019) identifies the causes of misconceptions to be more at the stage of cognitive development and often in contexts that are linked to emotions of pleasure or displeasure. They may also be culture related or triggered at any stage of formal education. Omoifo (2012) explains that no matter the source or origin of the misconception, it is a major factor affecting students' science achievement. It is thus of immense priority for biology teachers to help learners modify their non-science views in line with scientific principles through adequate instructional procedures. This modification process is termed conceptual change and involves the elimination of pre-instructional views previously held by learners and the restructuring of existing knowledge (Nadelson, et al. 2018) oftentimes through the instructional process. Such a process of instruction must allow teachers to uncover the incorrect views of students and give opportunities for learners to modify their perceptions through active engagement with the learning process. Wandersee et al. (1994) in Chavan and Patankar (2015) suggested some conceptual change instructional strategies such as word association, concept mapping, prediction-observation-explanation (POE), computer simulations, diagnostic tree, Analogy, and rebuttal tests, among others. In a multicultural and multi-ethnic society like Nigeria, evidence of learners having difficulty navigating between indigenous beliefs, cultural differences, and school science views exist (Sumadic, 2015). For students to develop ability to effectively navigate through these impediments requires that teachers apply appropriate conceptual change models that improve teaching and consequently, improve learning and retention of learned materials (Yang & Chen, 2023). The Predict-observe-explain (POE) model provides opportunities for teachers and students to navigate science in ways that afford chance to study science more actively. With the pervasive nature of technology, its incursion into science classrooms, and the exigencies of modern societal communication emergencies, it becomes necessary to incorporate digital resources into the POE model to enhance its versatility, efficiency and acceptability by learners.

Another aspect of this study is to determine if the model is sensitive to learners' gender. This study, therefore, aims at applying a digitalized prediction-observation-exploration (D-POE) model in helping biology students learn Genetics in secondary schools. The rationale for this is to exploit the enhancing digital characteristics to attract, sustain and engage students while they as study genetics and determine the efficacy of the model in helping the students learn abstract concepts as in genetics.

Theoretical framework

Helping learners to learn difficult concepts has been one of the major focuses of instructional efforts of science teachers and science education researchers. Social constructivism put forward by Vygotsky explains the process and product of offering educational help to learners through scaffolding within the learner's zone of proximal development (ZPD). According to Vygotsky (1978), the ZPD is "the distance between the actual developmental level as determined by independent problem solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem-solving under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers". Science teachers are thus scaffolds to help learners achieve learning goals, especially in difficult areas of science learning such as genetics. Therefore, instruction should target enabling learners to operate in their ZPD using the instructional scaffold available through the classroom's social interaction and networking platforms to restructure, modify or completely overcome their naïve views held over time about science concepts. Such views have been reported to be tenacious (Nadelson et al. 2018; Fasasi, 2021; Moemeke & Omoifo, 2009; Moemeke, 2009) and require deliberate instructional targeting to change. As stated by Posner et al. (1982), in their initial discourse on conceptual change, four influential conditions that facilitate conceptual change are:

1. Awareness of the shortfall in the appropriateness of a held view in solving particular problems (dissatisfaction)
2. Discovery of more plausible alternative strategies (intelligibility)

Impact of Digitalized Predict... (Moemeke, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

3. Proof of the reasonableness of an explanation (plausibility)
4. Applicability of the alternative explanation in the problem situation (fruitfulness)

This implies that in order to accomplish conceptual change, the learner needs to be convinced about the efficacy of the restructuring process, deliberately key into it, and apply it in learning the stipulated concepts.

Conceptual change refers to restructuring the existing knowledge that learners of science hold due to misconceptions, experiences, and intuitive thinking, resulting from everyday experiences, and previous superficial science instruction. Restructuring entails that existing knowledge and experiences (schemas) which are found not to satisfactorily explain new phenomena are modified in the light of more current and accurate new information resulting in the formation of new schemas that adequately explain them (Accommodation). However, the old schemas remain dormant or suppressed in the context but are not completely discarded as supposed by the Piagetian model of conceptual change (Nadelson et al. 2018). It means that the dormant or suppressed schema may become relevant again in a completely different context where it could be used to explain phenomena. Thus, learners could harbour a myriad of schemas and conceptions about a phenomenon simultaneously. The prediction-observation-explanation (POE) strategy is a conceptual change instructional model put forward by White and Gunstone (1992). It is an innovative approach that applies constructivist learning principles that by engaging in prediction, observation, and explaining of the observed result, students can build their knowledge, and detect and correct their misconceptions about a concept thus improving their creativity and thinking ability (Jasdilla, et al 2019). To achieve this, firstly the individual student's conception of a concept or idea and the reason/s are uncovered (Prediction). Secondly, the student carries out activities that enable the observation of the process in question (Observation), and thirdly, the student uses observed knowledge to explain phenomena and resolve or reconcile any inconsistencies between their analysis of the observation and their prediction (explanation). The information obtained from the students helps the teacher to identify existing misconceptions about the concept and on this basis, find sustainable solutions to such misconceptions. POE might thus be utilised to investigate students' concepts at the outset of a subject or to enhance understanding at the end of a teaching episode. This model focuses on examining the appropriateness of students' pre-existing ideas and attitudes and connecting them to the context. In reality, teachers often employ two activities to help learners achieve this. They are practical hands-on and problem-solving activities found most beneficial when resources are not only available but in enough supply.

In contrast, the traditional teaching method is teacher-directed and teaching is done in a way that encourages sitting, listening, and fact memorization (Tularam, 2018). In the traditional approach, the teacher engages in direct instruction with the primary intention of passing knowledge to students and conducting testing and assessment (Abah, 2020). The traditional teaching method has been under attack for the many woes of science learning by students such as the inability to think like scientists, the poor conceptualization of science concepts, poor interest and motivation to learn science, among others. This is attributable to the traditional method's neglect of learners' prior views and often fails to deliberately take into account the meaning of specific words as used and understood by classroom teachers and students. Abah (2020) however cites the productive education anchored on the rich culture and tradition of countries such as Korea, Finland, and China as evidence that the traditional method is not a total misfit as often portrayed by critics. This traditional method (lecture method) is still part of most other innovative methods in science education and is popular in most developing countries including Nigeria.

Misconceptions in Science Education Research and Related Constructs

Misconceptions are informal ideas held by students that are not in conformity with proper scientific understanding even after undergoing a process of instruction (Sanders 2003). These informal ideas are also referred to as naïve beliefs (Caramazza et al 1981), erroneous ideas (Fisher, 1985), preconceptions (Keng, 2000), pre-existing concepts (Hewson, 1992) multiple private versions of science (Mc Clelland 1984) personal models of reality (Champagne et al. 1983), alternative framework (Linn, 2008), children science (Gilbert, et al 1982) and alternative conception (Abimbola, 1988; Wandersee et al.1994; Ruhf, 2003). Alkhalifa (2006) explains that misconception may be in form of pre-conceived notions which are conceptions derived from real-world encounters, non-scientific views acquired by students from non-scientific sources, and conceptual misconceptions that occur when scientific material is presented to students in a way that does not challenge them to consider contradictions and confusion about these notions. To deal with their conflicts, students construct faulty models too weak to anchor and secure the knowledge. Other forms of misconceptions as espoused by Alkhalifa (2006) are factual misconceptions which are falsities and superstitions learned early in life that are retained unchallenged into adulthood and vernacular misconceptions which are products of wrong interpretation of scientific terms that have different meanings in scientific contexts and in daily life. Though sources of misconceptions are multifarious, Erman (2017) identified the characteristics of teaching resources, educators, learners, reference materials, and the connections among these elements as the primary reasons for the occurrence of misconceptions.

Impact of Digitalized Predict... (Moemeke, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

In Nigeria, Adebayo and Olufunke (2015) had earlier used two modified POE strategies (Generative instructional strategy GIS, and predict-observe-explain, POE) in a pre-test, post-test control group, quasi-experimental research design. The aim was to enhance basic science practical skills in lower primary school pupils in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State. A 30-item multiple-choice pictorial achievement test (PBSPST) was used to collect data. ANCOVA revealed better practical skills development in the activity-based instructional strategies (POE and GIS) in Basic Science learning of Basic school pupils. It is noteworthy that most of the studies on POE at the secondary and tertiary education levels were done in the area of physical and chemical sciences. The model has not been used to investigate abstract concepts in biology like genetics which the West African Examinations Council Chief Examiners' Reports over the years have repeatedly identified as problematic for students. In the domain of Genetics, students find it difficult to understand the mechanism because of the complex and abstract nature of the concepts which teachers often find difficult to explain without appropriate instructional devices (Etobro & Fabinu, 2017; Ukwa, 2007). Mustami (2016) blames most of the misconceptions and errors in the learning of genetics on some textbooks in use in Nigerian schools that do not elucidate the concepts to the understanding of both teachers and students.

Studies about gender in science learning present contradictions in literature but some studies report that girls show preference and a more positive attitude towards the study of Biology. There is a dearth of information on the influence of gender on the learning of genetics. Studies by Kessler et al. (2007) and Vlckova et. al. (2017) reported no difference in students' misconception of genetic concepts by gender but whether there exists a disparity in the achievement of both gender due to D-POE model is one of the objects of this study. It is also noteworthy that Nigerian schools have not fully investigated the use of the digitalized POE model (D-POE). Therefore, it is important to find out if applying the digitalized POE (D-POE) model will compensate for the lapses evident in the traditional lecture method and improve students' achievement in Genetics. The study aims to find out if there is any difference in the pre-and post-test achievement scores of students taught Genetics with traditional (Lecture) and those taught with the POE model fortified with digital resources. It also aims at finding out if achievement varies between the different genders among students taught Genetics using the POE model fortified with digital resources (D-POE) as well as determining the mean achievement scores of students taught genetics using Digitalized predict-Observe-Explain model and those exposed to conventional model in Delta State.

Objectives of the Study

The study aims to find out if:

1. Will compensate for the lapses evident in the traditional lecture method and improve students' achievement in Genetics.
2. There is any difference in the pre-and post-test achievement scores of students taught Genetics with traditional (Lecture) and those taught with the POE model fortified with digital resources.
3. Achievement varies between the different genders among students taught Genetics using the POE model fortified with digital resources (D-POE) as well as determining the mean achievement scores of students taught genetics using Digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain model and those exposed to conventional model in Delta State.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean Achievement scores of students taught genetics using Digitalized predict-Observe-Explain model and those exposed to conventional model in Delta State
2. Is there difference in the mean post test achievement score of male and female biology student exposed to the D-POE model?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean post-test achievement scores of biology students taught genetics using the digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain (D-POE) and those exposed to the conventional lecture model in Delta state.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean post-test achievement scores of male and female biology students taught genetics using the D-POE model.

Methodology

Pre-test-post-test quasi-experimental experimental design with non-randomized non- equivalent intact classes was used in the investigation. Sixty-nine (34 males and 35 females) subjects from two out of the fourteen public senior secondary schools in Oshimili South Local Government Area of Delta State of which seven are coeducational, participated in the study. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to draw two coeducational schools with at least thirty biology students The schools

Impact of Digitalized Predict... (Moemeke, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

were chosen based on certain criteria, one of which is that such a school must have at least 30 biology students in the SS 2 class of 2022/2023 session. This is important to ensure that at least five groups consisting of an even number of students can be formed during the implementation process. Of the seven schools that met the criteria in the area under study, two schools were drawn randomly by ballot. An intact class from each school was randomly selected and assigned to a treatment group by ballot. The experimental class (N=31) was taught Genetics using the D-POE model while the control group (N = 38) was taught the same Genetic concepts using the traditional lecture method for a period of six weeks of two periods each week (total of 80 minutes per week).

1. Meaning of genetics, heredity and variation, transmission and expression of characters in organisms, some important terms used in genetics.
2. Mendel's work in genetics (1st and 2nd laws of inheritance)
3. Chromosomes, DNA structure,
4. Application/importance of genetics in sex determination, disease control, biotechnology engineering,
5. Health and emergency, control of hereditary diseases, food production, crop improvement, etc.

A written request for permission to use the schools and students for the study was sought from the school principals. One week was devoted to training the biology teacher in the experimental school on how to implement the experimental model using the researcher-provided Android devices, the laptop and the projector. The researcher-prepared lesson plans were given to the teacher in the experimental school one week before the training. Questions and observations from the teachers formed part of the discussion during the training period which took place the next week. During the training period, the researcher played a video of a prototype D-POE biology classroom process prepared by the researcher. The experimental teacher then taught a thirty-minute demonstration lesson under camera using the lesson plans prepared by the researcher and assisted by a technical support staff and a class assistant. The lesson was then critiqued by both the experimental teacher undergoing training (Self-evaluation) and the researcher. The training lasted for two hours each day for two days and the participating teachers were well remunerated. The biology teacher for the control school was given the researcher-prepared lesson plans covering the same concepts as that of the experimental group to study a week before the treatment began and was asked to teach by following the lesson plan strictly. All classes were taught by the teachers under the supervision of the researcher. The actual teaching lasted for six weeks.

Experimental treatment

The following preparations were made for the implementation of the experimental treatment (digitalized POE model).

1. The researcher provided ten Android phones with internet subscription from a WIFI, a laptop, a projector and ensured that power was readily available during the experimental lessons through a power generating set.
2. Experiments and observations are saved on all the phones before the lessons.
3. Lesson demonstrations and observation are also available to the teacher on a laptop to which the projector is connected.
4. Assignments and digital links to further expand students' information sources are also provided to the students in the android phones. Students were shared into nine groups of three students each. Only the last group has four students, giving a total of ten groups. Each group worked with one Android phone.

During the class session, the teacher projects a question for groups to predict their group negotiated right answer. They then observe the experiments/ demonstrations/ read texts from links given about the question, consider their new information and on the basis reform/ readjust/ discard their prediction and give an explanation based on their new group negotiated understanding of the concept under study. Each lesson lasted for 80 minutes.

Data was collected using a 30- item two-tier diagnostic multiple-choice Test of Achievement in Genetics (TAG) in which students were expected to give a reason for any answer chosen. The multiple-choice items were carefully selected from West African Examinations Council senior school certificate questions from 2009 to 2019 in genetics but the reasons were generated by the researcher. Each item on the test had four options lettered A to D followed by four reasons also Lettered A to D of which only one is the key while the other options are distracters. The reliability of the TAG was found to be .75 after it was administered to non-sampled students and the data subjected to Kuder Richardson formula 21. The instrument was administered by the researcher, assisted by the biology teachers in the two schools on the first week to collect pre-test data. A score of 1 was given to a chosen correct option and 3 for a correct reason. The same instrument but with the number of items shuffled was re-administered to subjects in the two group in the seventh week to collect post-test data. The resulting data were analyzed using the t-test and one way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at $P \leq 0.05$ since the subjects varied even at the pre-test.

Impact of Digitalized Predict... (Moemeke, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

Results

The results from the analyses are presented in the tables below

Research Question 1

What then is the mean Achievement scores of students taught genetics using Digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain (D-POE) model and those exposed to conventional model in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of experimental and control groups

Group	N	Pre-test Mean	Std. Deviation	Post-test Mean	Std. deviation	Mean gain
Experimental group(D-POE)	31	4.87	1.607	11.87	1.607	77.00
Control Group (Traditional)	38	2.45	1.224	5.71	2.142	3.26
Mean difference		2.42		6.16		

Source of data: Author's Field collection, 2023

Table 1 shows that the D-POE group with Mean = 4.87 and SD = 1.607 at the pre-test and 11.87 and SD=1.607 at the post-test (Mean gain =7.00) gained exceedingly from treatment compared to the control group (Pre-test Mean = 2.45; Post-test Mean =5.71; Mean gain = 3.26). To test for the significance of the difference, the data were subjected to a one-way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA), and the result is shown in Table 2 below.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean post-test achievement scores of biology students taught genetics using the digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain (D-POE) and those exposed to the conventional lecture model in Delta state

Table 2: ANCOVA summary for mean pre and post-achievement scores of experimental and control

Source	Type III Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	1070.731	3	356.910	204.449	.000	Sig. P≤.05
Pretest(Covariate)	186.830	1	186.830	107.002	.000	
Group	1003.422	2	501.711	287.395	.000	
Error	113.472	65	1.746			
Total	5286.00	69				
Corrected total	1184.203	68				

Source of data: Author, field

Table 2 shows that there is a significant difference ($F(1, 68) = 287.395, p = .000$) in the achievement of the experimental and control groups in favour of the experimental group (D-POE model). There is therefore a significant difference in the mean posttest achievement scores of students who were taught using the D-POE model compared to those who were taught using the traditional lecture method even at an alpha level as low as .000. Null hypothesis 1 which states that there is no significant difference in the mean post-test achievement scores of those taught with D-POE and those taught with Traditional model is rejected. There is a significant difference in the achievement scores of students in the two groups.

Research Question 2

Is there difference in the mean posttest achievement score of male and female biology student exposed to the D-POE model?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of the achievement scores of male and female experimental subjects at post-test

Gender	N	Mean	Standard deviation
Male	14	11.42	1.74
Female	17	12.24	1.43

Table 3 shows that the mean score of female students (12.24) is slightly higher than that of males (11.42) in the experimental group. This implies that the females benefited slightly more than the males from the D-POE model. To determine the significance of this difference, the data were subjected to a t-test and the result is shown in Table 4 below.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean post-test achievement scores of male and female biology students taught genetics using the D-POE model.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of the achievement of male and female experimental subjects

Impact of Digitalized Predict... (Moemeke, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	df	T	Sig. 2-tailed
Male	14	11.42	1.74	29	1.41	.168
Female	17	12.24	1.43			

$P \leq .05$

Table 4 revealed that the slight difference in the mean achievement of males (Mean = 11.42, SD= 1.74) and females (Mean = 12.24, SD =1.43) is not significant $t(1.41; df=29; P \leq .168)$ at the alpha level of 0.05 set for this study. There is therefore no significant difference in the achievement of males and females in the experimental group at post-test

Discussion of Findings

For clarity, this discussion of findings will be taken on the basis of hypotheses explored in this study. Hypothesis 1 which stated that the mean post-test achievement scores of biology students who were taught genetics using the D-POE and conventional lecture models did not differ significantly was analysed using ANCOVA. The results show a substantial difference in the mean post-test achievement scores between the experimental group (D-POE) and the control group (Traditional Lecture). The D-POE group exhibited a notably higher mean gain (7.00) compared to the control group (3.26). The ANCOVA analysis confirms a significant difference in achievement between the two groups, favouring the D-POE model ($p = .000$). Therefore, this hypothesis is rejected and contrary to the initial assumption of this study. The study investigated provides clear evidence of the impact of the D-POE instructional model on Biology students' understanding and reasoning about genetic concepts. Before this study, there are a huge body of information on students' limited understanding of genetics and their applications in nature among Nigeria secondary school students (Etobro & Fabinu, 2017; Etobro & Banjoko, 2017; Okebukola, 2014; Mustami, 2016). Reasons advanced for the poor conceptual understanding of genetics range from misconceptions due to cultural influences, the abstractness of the concepts, the use of inappropriate instructional models while teaching the concepts, and even the dearth of appropriate instructional materials and media. Also, available research evidence points to the efficacy of different variants of the POE model on a diverse range of outcome measures (Adebayo and Olufunke, 2015; Jasdilla, et al 2019) but due to the high prevalence of teachers' use of the traditional methods, secondary school biology students are not afforded the opportunity to undertake the steps inherent in the D-POE model while learning genetics. When provided with and engaged in such crucial mental involvement in learning, students' reasoning becomes improved and learning becomes productive. The result presented here contributes and provides strong evidence about the impact of D-POE intervention on students learning of Genetics through a quasi-experimental study design. The findings indicate that the D-POE model led to significantly higher achievement compared to traditional lecture methods in the sample. This suggests that incorporating computer-enhanced POE models may be beneficial in enhancing student learning outcomes in biology, specifically in the topic of Genetics and especially in similar populations as that used in this study. This finding reiterate the influence of technology and digitization in enhancing and fostering learning among students.

Hypothesis 2 stated that the mean post-test achievement scores of male and female biology students taught genetics using the D-POE model did not differ significantly. The analysis revealed that females had a slightly higher mean post-test score than males. However, the t-test results revealed that this difference is not statistically significant ($p = .168$), suggesting that gender did not significantly impact achievement in the experimental group. It also signified that the D-POE experimental model is not gender biased nor selective. Therefore, this hypothesis is supported. Although there was a slight difference in achievement between male and female students in the experimental group, this disparity was not statistically significant. Thus, the D-POE model appears to be equally effective for both male and female students in enhancing achievement in Genetics. This is in line with Kessler et al. (2007) and Vlckova et. al. (2017) who found no difference in achievement based on gender parameters. The benefits the subjects derived from the model were not influenced by their gender and as such, achievement gains were unbiased for both genders.

Implications for Teaching: These results underscore the potential of innovative teaching methods, such as the D-POE model, in improving student learning outcomes. Science, specifically biology teachers at all levels may consider integrating technology-enhanced approaches into their Predict-Observe- Explain model of teaching practices to enhance student engagement and understanding and achievement.

Conclusion

Learning genetics has been problematic for biology students over the years. Researchers have been in search of teaching and learning models that will help students overcome the challenges of learning the concepts. These challenges have been attributed to misconceptions held by both teachers and their students, some of which are cultural, conceptual, or textbook

Impact of Digitalized Predict... (Moemeke, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

related. The tenacity of these misconceptions and naive views have made them resistant to instructional devices that do not deliberately focus on the underlying views that the students bring to class and have often resulted in poor achievement in biology in external examinations by secondary school students. The application of the Predict-Observe-Explain model of conceptual change enhanced with computer-based learning resources has helped the learners extend their learning as well as focus on the underlying misconceptions. This resulted in the better achievement of the experimental group compared to the control (Traditional Lecture method) group. Finally, the study demonstrates the effectiveness of the D-POE model in enhancing student achievement in Genetics, with no significant gender differences observed. These findings have implications for teaching practices and warrant further exploration in educational research.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended as follows:

1. The digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain model is efficacious in helping biology students learn genetics therefore biology teachers should utilize the model for teaching Genetics and other biology concepts that students find difficult because of their abstractness.
2. Since the D-POE model is not gender discriminatory, biology teachers should utilize it in overcoming gender bias in curriculum implementation such that learners of both gender can learn side by side and maximize their potentials. Infuse technology into the teaching of biology as it improves students' participation, engagement and achievement.
3. Utilize the D-POE model to improve their students' understanding and achievement in genetics since it is not gender discriminatory.
4. Biology teachers should avoid incessant use of traditional methods of teaching biology and science in general because it does not cater for most learning challenges which students experience as they learn.
5. Government and stakeholders in education should provide digital teaching resources such as computers, android phones, generating sets, and projectors to school as well as energy so that teacher can creatively innovate in their teaching of biology.
6. Teachers should maximize the characteristic properties of technology such as collaboration, individualization of teaching and learning, greater engagement, instant feedback and interest enhancement in improving learning of biology in secondary schools in Delta state.

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Effects of Think Pair... (Nnenna, & Sussan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

Effects of Think Pair Share Strategy on Achievement and Retention in Mathematics among Secondary School Students in Osisioma Local Government Area, Abia State

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Abstract

This study investigated effects of think pair share strategy on achievement and retention in mathematics among secondary school students in Osisioma Local Government area, Abia State 1002 (454 male and 548 female) Senior Secondary School two students during 2023/2024 academic session formed the population. The sample comprises of 92 (42 male and 50 female) students drawn from the population using purposive and simple random sampling techniques. Instrument used for data collection was teacher made Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). The test items covered 25 objective questions from Word Problems in Linear and Simultaneous Equations. MAT was constructed and validated by experts from mathematics education and measurement and evaluation. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.82 obtained using kuder Richardson (K-R-20). Four research questions were posed and answered using mean and standard deviation while four null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance. The result among others showed that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement and retention scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share learning strategy and those taught using conventional method. It was concluded that the use of Think Pair share strategy is require in teaching of mathematics because students achieved and retained more using it. Based on the result, it was recommended among others that teachers should use Think Pair share strategy to teach mathematics for better achievement and retention.

Keywords: think pair share, achievement, retention, mathematics, strategy.

Introduction

Mathematics in Nigeria education is one of the subjects studied at all levels of education, from primary schools to universities. Mathematics is an indispensable tool in virtually all human endeavors and there is hardly any field where mathematics is not useful (Agwagah, 2013; Uka, 2020). This implies that mathematics is the pillar of all knowledge showing its relevance in all disciplines. That is why Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) has made mathematics a compulsory subject at both primary and secondary school levels in Nigeria. Mathematics is a knowledge that trains the minds into systematic and critical thinking as well as reasoning. It equips learners with the basic knowledge and skills required for further learning in many courses like engineering, medicine, accounting, banking and finance, business administration to mention but a few. In fact mathematics is not only utilized in every field of human endeavor, it plays a fundamental role in educational advancement. In spite of the importance of mathematics in life, some students do not show much seriousness in the subject and still have difficulties in solving mathematic problems (Tanujaya & Mumu, 2019).

The poor performance in mathematics has continue to occur in our external examinations, WAEC (Chief Examiners Reports, 2018-2022). The stake holders in education are so worried because of the position of mathematics in Nigerian Education System. The problem of poor performance has been attributed to many factors; teachers' factors, students' factors and others. Among the teachers' factors is the teaching method applied by the teachers. According to Amadi and Ibekwe (2016), in fostering learning in the classrooms, teachers should bring the learners to close contact with the curriculum contents using appropriate teaching method.

Kurumeh et al (2012) maintained that the inappropriate and inadequate teaching techniques and methods used by mathematics teachers are instrumental to learners' inability to understand and retain basic mathematical principles and

Effects of Think Pair... (Nnenna, & Sussan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

computations. Likewise, Digari et al (2016) blamed the poor achievement in mathematics in the use of inappropriate teaching strategy which might lead to lack of retention of mathematics concept.

According to Digari et al (2016), the teaching method implies the use of principles and theories of instructions which can include class participation, demonstrations, recitation. The appropriate teaching methods should be such that can engage students both inside and outside classrooms (Finn & Zimmer in Mundelsi & Jurkowski, 2021). According to them, students with higher levels of engagement inside and outside the classroom not only learn more than students with lower level of engagement, they are also more successful in the long run both academically and professionally. In order words, that method that engages students in the classroom will definitely increase their academic achievements. Such methods include problem solving, guided discovery, ethnomathematics, and Think pair share among others (Garba & Salim 2020; Bitrus et al 2020; Finn & Zimmer in Mundelsi & Jurkowoki, 2021).

In the classrooms today, the traditional strategy of teaching and learning mathematics is still being utilized by teachers (Nwoke, 2015, Garba & Salim, 2020). This traditional strategy of teaching is popularly known as conventional method of teaching which requires the teacher doing most of the talking while the students take note and remain passive. This method of teaching occupies the school system as teachers still use the method in teaching mathematics. It emphasizes teacher centered, teacher- directed instructions and there is a little or no interaction between teachers and students. There is then the need to consider in teaching mathematics the method that engages the students more of which Think Pair Share strategy is among. Think – Pair Share (TPS) is a collaborative learning strategy where students work together to solve a problem. This strategy requires students to: think individually about a topic or answer to a question and share ideas with participation (EL Sevier, 2013). Think pair share, sometimes called “turn and talk”, is one of the best ways for teachers to slow down the conversation and give students time to process their ideas before verbally responding.

According to Echevarria et al (2014), Think Pair Share is a cooperative learning strategy used to easily monitor students understanding of content objectives. It gives all students a chance to think and discuss. It allows them time for individual reflection, thinking and processing new information before they may be influenced by other students’ answer. This process also teaches students how to explain their thoughts first to a peer, and then to a larger audience (the entire class). Think – pair – share was developed by Frank Lyman in 1981. It is the learning tool a teacher can use to help students think independently, pair up and discuss with a classmate or in small groups, and share their knowledge with the class. Think pair share can be used in mathematics as students complete word problems. Students can think about a given word problem and the steps that could be used in order to solve it. Without solving the problem, students can share the problem – solving strategy they thought of with a partner. After discussing, students can solve the problem on their own and compare answer with a partner.

In mathematics, questions that work well with this strategy include word problems, logic problems, estimations and patterns. It has been proven that students may benefit by using peer-mediated interventions which are consistently producing higher academic achievement (Bataneh, 2017).

Academic achievement is an outstanding change in students behavior as a result of their exposure to a specific programme instruction (Orobasa, 2016). Academic achievement has been one of the most important goals of the educational process. It is the overall academic performance of a student in the school. In fact, academic achievement is an index of a child’s future in this competitive world. If this is so, what is learnt needs to be retained.

Retention is defined as the level which an individual is capable to recall an acquired knowledge at any given time. Retention also is the ability to remember experiences and things learnt. This implies that the amount of knowledge learnt and kept, skills maintained or problem-solving behaviours manifested consistently reflects what retention is. Retention in mathematics, therefore is the ability of a learner to keep and remember as well as recall or reproduce the required knowledge or some parts of the knowledge after some period of time must have elapsed. Therefore, to improve students achievement level in mathematics, implies to improve the level at which they retain the concept of mathematics learnt. Hence, the need to investigate if think pair share strategy of learning could improve retention of both male and female students in Mathematics.

Gender is referred to as the social roles that are believed to belong to male and female with a particular social grouping (Amoo & Onasanya, 2017). It is a set of characteristics distinguishing between male and female particularly in the case of man and woman. Gender differences in mathematics achievement and ability has been a serious concern as scientist have observed the under-representation of women in mathematics, physical science and engineering (Asante in Tanujaya & Mumu, 2019). Some researchers found that in using Think Pair share strategy to teach mathematics, that students perform better both in achievement and retention but the male counterpart outshined the female both in achievement and retention (Kaddoura, 2013, Birtus in Bitrus et al 2020, Sanderson et al, 2022).

Effects of Think Pair... (Nnenna, & Sussan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

There are some researchers who found that there is no significant difference in mean achievement and retention scores of students that were taught using Think Pair Share strategy based on gender (Batainah, 2017; Adimora et al 2014). Since there is a conflicting view of different authors as per students' academic achievement and retention when taught using Think Pair Share strategy and the influence on gender, there.

Despite the importance of mathematics in life, technology and nation development to mention but a few, the poor academic performance of students is on the increase (WAEC Chief Examiners Reports, 2018-2022). Teaching methods have been found as one of the major problems of this poor performance. Many methods of teaching have been introduced by teachers yet the problem persisted. It is observed that the conventional lecture method is still being used in the classroom and it is teacher centered and students are passive. There is need to use a method that will engage students more, make the lesson students – centered to see if students' achievement and retention will improve. Think pair share strategy is a strategy that requires students to think individually about a topic or answer to a question and share with entire class or group.

This study therefore is to investigate the effect of Think-pair-share on students' academic achievement and retention in Mathematics since it has been proven that students may benefit by using peer-mediated interventions like Think-pair-share which are consistently producing higher academic achievement (Bataineh, 2017).

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of think pair share strategy on achievement and retention in mathematics among secondary school students. Specifically, the study seeks to find out, the:

1. Mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using Think Pair share strategy and those taught using conventional method,
2. Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy,
3. Mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy,
4. Mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy.

Research Questions

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy and those taught using conventional method?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy?
3. What are the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy?
4. What are the mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-share strategy?

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share strategy and those taught using conventional method.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-Share strategy

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share Strategy

H₀₄: There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share strategy.

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental because of different extraneous variables the researchers may control at the course of this study. Specifically, the pretest-posttest control group design was used. The population of the study was all the senior secondary school students in Osisioma local government area of Abia State which is made up of one thousand and two senior secondary two students.

A sample of Ninety-two (forty two male and fifty female) students were selected using simple random sampling techniques. The instrument used for data collection was researchers' developed achievement test which was validated by three experts from department of science education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for research questions and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) for hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

The data were analyzed and the result presented according to research questions and hypotheses.

Effects of Think Pair... (Nnenna, & Sussan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

Research Question 1

What are the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share strategy and those taught using conventional method?

Table 1: Mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught mathematics using Think pair share strategy and those taught using conventional method.

Teaching Methods	N	Pretest		Post test		Mean difference
		Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev	Mean(\bar{x})	Std. Dev.	
Conventional	44	25.68	3.86	32.77	4.65	7.09
Think Pair Share	48	25.25	4.10	55.13	6.87	29.88

Table 1 showed the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy and those taught using conventional method. Students taught using conventional method had a pretest mean of 25.68 and standard deviation of 3.86 while their posttest means and standard deviation of 32.77 and 4.65 respectively. Students taught using think pair share strategy had pretest mean and standard deviation of 25.25 and 4.10 respectively while their posttest mean and standard deviation are 55.13 and 6.87 respectively. This indicates that students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy achieved better than those taught using conventional method.

Research Question 2

What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-Share Strategy?

Table 2: Mean achievement scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share learning strategy.

Gender	N	Pre-Test		Post-Test		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev	
Male	22	24.73	3.98	56.73	6.06	32.00
Female	26	25.69	4.22	53.77	7.32	28.08

Table 2 showed the mean scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught mathematics using Think-pair-Share learning strategy. From table 2, the pretest mean scores for male and female were 24.73 and 25.69 respectively while their standard deviation are 3.98 and 4.22 respectively. The posttest means scores for male and female were 56.73 and 53.77 respectively while their standard deviation scores are 6.06 and 7.32 respectively. This indicates that the male students had a higher mean gain than their female counterparts. This implies the male students performed better than the female students when taught mathematics using Think Pair Share learning strategy.

Research Question 3

What are the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using Think Pair-Share learning strategy?

Table 3: Mean retention scores and standard deviation of students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-Share learning strategy.

Teaching Method	N	Post test		Retention		Mean difference
		Mean(\bar{x})	Std. Dev	Mean(\bar{x})	Std. Dev	
Think pair share	48	55.13	6.87	59.38	6.07	4.25

Table 3 showed the mean retention scores and standard deviations of the students taught mathematics using think pair share learning strategy. The posttest had mean of 55.13 with standard deviation of 6.87 and retention mean of 59.38 with standard deviation of 6.07. The mean difference is 4.25. This indicates that the means were not far from each other which indicates that the students retained what they were taught.

Research Question 4

What are the mean retention scores of male and female students taught using Think-Pair-Share strategy?

Effects of Think Pair... (Nnenna, & Sussan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

Table 4: Mean retention scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught using Think-Pair-Share strategy?

Gender	N	Post-Test		Retention		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev	
Male	22	55.13	6.87	58.64	6.37	3.51
Female	26	53.77	7.32	60.15	5.80	6.38

Table 4 revealed that the mean post test score and standard deviation of male students are 55.13 and 6.87 respectively while that of female are 53.77 and 7.32 respectively. The table further shows that the mean retention score and standard deviation of the male students are 58.64 and 6.37 respectively while that of female students are 60.15 and 5.80 respectively. The table also revealed that the female students had a higher mean gain of 6.38 than the male students with mean gain of 3.51. This implies that female students developed retention higher than their male counterparts when taught with Think Pair Share strategy in mathematics.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share and those taught using conventional method.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the mean Achievement scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share learning strategy and those taught using conventional method.

Source	Type Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	11493.156 ^a	2	5746.578	163.849	.000
Intercept	3560.103	1	3560.103	101.507	.000
Pretest	23.524	1	23.524	.673	.415
Teaching methods	11492.134	1	11492.134	327.668	.000
Error	3121.453	89	35.073		
Total	196264.00	92			
Corrected Total	14614.609	91			

1. R Squared = .786 (Adjusted R Squared = .782)

Table 5 showed the F – ratio of 327.668 for groups with P-value of .000 which is less than the significant value of 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is therefore rejected which indicates that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share and those taught using conventional method.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share strategy.

Table 6: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of males and females mean scores when taught using Think Pair Share learning strategy

Source	Type 111 sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	101.861 ^a	2	50.931	1.408	.255
Intercept	3345.471	1	3345.411	92.506	.000
Post think pair	79.702	1	79.702	2.204	.145
Gender	7.067	1	7.067	.195	.661
Error	1627.389	45	36.164		
Total	170948.000	48			
Corrected Total	1729.250	47			

3. R Square = .059 (Adjusted R Squared = .017)

Effects of Think Pair... (Nnenna, & Sussan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

The result in Table 6 showed F-ratio of .195 with P-value of .661 which is greater than the significant value of 0.05. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share learning strategy.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-Share strategy

Table 7: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the mean Retention scores of students taught mathematics using Think-Pair-Share learning strategy.

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	94.794 ^a	1	94.794	2.668	.109
Intercept	3597.318	1	3597.318	101.243	.000
Post think pair	94.794	1	94.794	2.668	
Error	1634.456	46	35.532		
Total	170948.000	48			
Corrected Total	1729.250	47			

a. R Squared = .055 (Adjusted R Squared = .034)

The result in Table 7 shows F-ratio of 2.668 with P-value of .109 which is greater than the significant value of 0.05. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the retention score of students taught mathematics using think pair share is accepted. This implies there is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Think Pair Share strategy.

Table 8: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of male and female students mean retention scores when taught using think pair share strategy.

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	71.583 ^a	2	35.792	.978	.384
Intercept	3095.340	1	3095.340	84.606	.000
Think post	44.142	1	44.142	1.207	.278
Gender	13.485	1	13.485	.369	.547
Error	1646.333	45	36.585		
Total	171412.000	48			
Corrected Total	1717.917	47			

1. R Squared=.042 (Adjusted R Squared=.001)

The result in Table 8 showed F-ratio of .369 with P-value of .547 which is greater than the significant value of 0.05. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using think pair share strategy.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that students who were taught using think pair share learning strategy performed better than students who were taught through conventional method. The male students performed better than their female counterpart. The students also retained what they learnt through think pair share learning strategy. The female students developed retention higher than the male students. The study showed that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using think pair share learning strategy and those taught using conventional method. This is in agreement with the findings of Kaddoara (2013), Birtus et al (2020) and Sanderson et al (2022) whose research works indicated that students who learnt through think-pair-share strategy performed better than their counterparts both in achievement and retention in mathematics.

Effects of Think Pair... (Nnenna, & Sussan, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259126>

This study also showed that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement and retention scores male and female students taught mathematics using think-pair-share strategy though the males achieved higher but the females retained more. This is in line with the findings of Batainah, 2017; Adimora, et al, 2014 whose studies found out that there is no significant difference in achievement and retention based on gender for students taught using think pair share strategy .But this finding contradicts the findings of Kaddoara (2013), Birtus et al (2020) and Sanderson et al (2022) whose work found that male counterparts achieved and retained more while the present work found that the males achieved more but the females retained more.

Conclusions

From the results obtained in the study, it was found that students taught mathematics using think pair share performed better than their counterparts taught using conventional method. The students taught mathematics using think pair share retained what they were taught. Male students performed better than female students though not significant. Female students developed retention higher than their male counterparts when taught with think pair share strategy though not significant.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proffered

1. Teachers should adopt think pair share learning strategy in teaching since it has been found to enhance retention and achievement in mathematics.
2. Teachers should teach male and female students equally using think pair share learning strategy both need for better achievement and retention.
3. Workshops should be organized for teachers by state and federal government, Associations like Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN). This is because some teachers may not be aware of how best to employ think pair share learning strategy.

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Impact of Insecurity on Quality of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria: A Case study of Plateau State Tertiary Institutions

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Abstract

Plateau State, Nigeria has continued to witness protracted violent conflicts in the past three decades that have adversely affected various sectors of the state, including the educational sector. The paper investigates impact of insecurity on quality of tertiary education in Nigeria: A Case study of Plateau State Tertiary institutions. It adopted the Democratic Peace Theory as the theoretical framework to guide the paper. It utilised both secondary and primary data, using qualitative approach. The primary data administered 12 In-depth and 4 Key Informant Interviews using purposive sampling techniques. Content analysis was used to analyze the data. The paper found out that insecurity in the study area gave way to loss of manpower in educational institutions, poor quality of education, destruction of infrastructural facilities, closure of educational institutions, internal displacement of staff and students, reduction of private investment in education. It further submitted that current efforts to mitigate the problems have not yielded enough positive results. The paper, therefore, recommended that the government both at the federal and the state levels should address all the pending issues fuelling insecurities in the state and ensure that the institution is secured and safe enough for teaching and learning. The governments should invest in higher institutions' securities across the state. Since the military approach seems failing, the paper further recommended the adoption of non-kinetic approaches to support the current efforts deployed to combat the menace of insecurity in the University of Jos. Finally, the paper emphasised that the University should intensify awareness programmes for the university community to always observe basic security measures as early warning tactics to mitigate unforeseen attacks; and that the university should invest in Online Distance Learning (ODL) systems to allow the students access virtual teaching experience as alternative learning process.

Keywords: Impact, Insecurity, Tertiary institution.

Introduction

The quality of education, wherever it may be found, is largely determined by the peace and security that permeate the learning environment. Okoli and Okpaleke (2014) noted that education is intended to help people develop their skills and abilities so they can reach their full potential and lead productive, fulfilling lives. In preliterate societies, education was primarily focused on hunting, cooking, following the stars, and obeying the gods. Education is an essential investment for human and economic development.

The government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, according to Nzeh (2015), realized the importance of education and declared in its 1999 Constitution that every Nigerian child has the right to an education, regardless of gender, tribe, religion, or race. It makes sense to state that the high standards of education outlined in the Federal Republic of Nigeria's constitution would be realized in a calm and supportive school environment. Ndoma-Egba (2014) asserts that the noble goals of education can never be achieved in a vacuum. Both teachers and students are likely to be discouraged if there is a sense of insecurity in and around the school, which could impair the students' academic performance. A lack of peace can result in widespread devastation, extreme insecurity, intimidation, and fear, which can close schools and halt instruction for the duration of the school day. Nigerian Institutions that have faced insecurity have experienced many setbacks in terms of academic growth and infrastructural destruction (Nwosu, 2016).

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In Nigeria, however, there has been an unprecedented level of insecurity, threatening national security and prompting a significant portion of the national budget to be allocated to security (Achumba, 2013). The alarming level of insecurity in Nigeria has increased the rate of crime and terrorist attacks in various parts of the country, leaving unpalatable consequences for the country's economy and business growth (Ali, 2013). Agbo (2023) notes that tertiary institutions have not been spared from the negative impact of insecurity. For example, Nigeria has seen a rise in insecurity in recent years, with incidents of kidnapping, armed robbery, violence between communities, terrorism, and other crimes. This has left the educational sector, particularly tertiary institutions, vulnerable to insecurity, with students and staff members at risk of being abducted, attacked, or killed (Agbo, 2023).

Moreso, Umar (2022) noted that the alarming level of insecurity in Nigeria has resulted in an increase in crime and terrorist attacks throughout the country, which has had a negative impact on the country's economy, business, and expansion of education. The Nigerian people now literally sleep with their eyes open, emasculated by the fear of these terror groups and the suffering and destruction they are capable of causing (Agbo, 2023).

In the Plateau State, the stability and operation of higher education institutions are severely hampered by various forms of insecurity. The state is currently mired in an unprecedented level of growing insecurity. These days, it is easier for jihadists, bandits, Fulani herdsmen, kidnappers, and other criminals to waste a human life than an animal (Okoli, 2014). In Plateau State, tertiary institutions are becoming more susceptible to the destabilizing consequences of insecurity. These include risks to the health and safety of instructors and students, interruptions to the regular course of study, difficulties in keeping up campus facilities, and a decline in the legitimacy and trust of the institution (William 2008). Academic calendar delays and extended study periods have resulted from the frequent closures and disruptions caused by insecurity. Students and staff members experience psychological trauma as well, which negatively impacts their mental health and general well being (Nzeh, 2015)

Furthermore, because parents and guardians would be reluctant to send their children to institutions that are prone to insecurity, insecurity could harm the institution's reputation and lower enrollment rates. (Hassan 2023) It might also result in the exodus of highly qualified academics in search of safer workplaces. The security situation in Nigeria seems to be insurmountable, according to Achumba, Ighomereho, and Akpor-Robaro (2013), and many have claimed that the government at all levels has not done enough by not addressing the issue head-on and taking decisive action. Some, however, contend that the circumstances have a political undertone or inclination intended to further the goals of certain political gods who are angry and unsatisfied with the political manifestations in the nation (Ajodo, 2012). The University of Jos presented a classic case of frequent attacks on tertiary institutions in the country. Using the University as a case study, this paper hope to provide scientific answers to the following questions; how is the spate of insecurity impacting on the quality of education in the university; what are the coping mechanisms of the university authorities and how can the incessant attacks be mitigated to enhance the overall performance and quality of education in the institution?

Conceptual Clarification

Insecurity: The concept of insecurity is a derivative of the term 'security', which literarily means to be safe from hunger, fear, molestation, attacks and any other forms of threats to life or personal safety of a human person. Hence, any situation that can cause fear, attacks or bodily harm to an individual or group of persons can be referred to as insecurity. To Ajodo-Adebanjoko (2014), insecurity is a state of fear or anything that has the potential to cause fear, harm, injury, or destruction to a person, a group, or a country. Ali (2013) claims that since Nigeria returned to democratic rule in 1999, there has been a rise in terrorism-related incidents, which has added to the country's growing sense of unease. People's perception of their level of safety from fear, economic, political, social, cultural, and psychological is known as security. People's relative perception of the existence of social, political, cultural, psychological, and economic fear is known as insecurity. Economic insecurity is the most prevalent type of insecurity among them all and the one that makes other types of insecurity more apparent. Other types of insecurity emerged as a result of economic insecurity. There are several meanings associated with the term insecurity, including: lack of protection, danger, hazard, uncertainty, and absence of safety. Beland (2005) cited in Ewetan and Urhie (2014), states that insecurity is a condition of fear or anxiety brought on by a lack of security.

Tertiary Institution

This is a widely used concept that has attracted universal appeal. International Standard Classification of Education has defined the concept as post-compulsory education system and later as third level of education, which was used to describe all types of education that offer specific courses for adult learning. It later described it as that level of education that 'builds on secondary education, providing learning activities in a specialised filed of education' (UNESCO, 2012:46). The uniqueness of tertiary education revolves on the fact that it combines both academic and professional skills at various levels.

Quality Education

This is a major concern of the performance index of major educational institutions worldwide. For Arnold and Bassett, (2021), tertiary institution must exhibit certain values to be rated to have upheld the required quality of education.

Impact of Insecurity on Quality... (Medugu, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

They suggested that a tertiary education system should steer diverse institutions to encourage equity, efficiency and resilience with clear educational and qualification pathways for learners (Arnold and Bassett, 2021). In Nigeria, and within the purview of this paper, quality education presupposes that for the attainment of effective education system, all the relevant stakeholders especially policy makers should endeavor to provide the necessary facilities and ensure the conducive leaning environment for all adults.

Methodology

The paper utilised both primary and secondary data collection. The primary data were qualitative in nature and obtained from 12 In-depth Interviews and 4 Key Informant Interviews. These were carried out using purposive sampling techniques. A question guide was designed by the researchers and was used to gather or administer interviews on the respondents. The respondents were selected from different section of the University of Jos and representatives from government cycles. These included student leaders, university staff, and government officials. The data gathered were analysed using content analysis. The secondary data were sourced from books, government papers, journal articles: print and online, conference proceedings, and materials related to the subject matter.

The Democratic Peace Theory is used in this study to explain Nigeria's security issues. This theory, put forth by Michael Doyle in 1998, holds that a security policy's long-term goal must be the spread of liberalism and that security primarily rests on assisting liberal institutions in carrying out their duties in an honorable manner (Doyle, 1998). Thus, promoting democracy, universal respect for human rights, and the growth of civil society are the paths that lead to peace. However, such a conclusion is primarily predicated on a stable and strong correlation between a state's democratic nature and its propensity for peace. Therefore, liberal states are assumed to refrain from waging war on other liberal states by the democratic peace theory.

Michael Doyle initially presented this theory in a keynote paper published in the *Journal of Philosophy and Public Affairs* (Doyle, 1998). Doyle therefore contended that liberal behavior toward liberal societies differed from liberal behavior toward non-liberal societies. The democratic peace theory makes clear recommendations from a security perspective.

Insecurity and Quality of Education

As a fundamental idea, insecurity is frequently linked to circumstances where values are threatened, particularly the survival of people, groups, or objects in the near future. As the name suggests, insecurity therefore refers to the incapacity to pursue desired political and socioeconomic conditions that are supportive of democracy. A state of no safety, confidence, and the pervasiveness of danger, fear, and doubts is known as insecurity. It might also refer to a situation, in which one is unsafe, poorly guarded, or both, and where instability predominates as opposed to desired stability. Fear or anxiety resulting from a real or perceived lack of protection is referred to as insecurity. It alludes to insufficient or nonexistent safety from harm.

The most obvious type of insecurity is physical insecurity, which is reflected in this definition. Physical insecurity also contributes to many other types of insecurity, including social and economic security. According to William (2008), feeling uncertain, erratic, unsteady, nervous, or lacking in confidence are all examples of insecurity. This may stem from one's upbringing, uncomfortable situations, maltreatment, or personal fears. The term insecurity describes a condition in which one is constantly confronted with threats, dangers, molestation, intimidation, harassment, etc. One way to conceptualize insecurity is as threats to the state, which is why there has often been a race to acquire weapons, including nuclear weapons, in order to defend the state.

The absence of safety and peace is what is commonly referred to as insecurity, which is problematic because security is unquestionably the cornerstone required for the advancement of society, politics, and education. Any nation's citizens are under grave danger from insecurity, which also acts as a Canker-worm that eats away at the foundation of any nation. Nwakpa (2015) examined the effect of insecurity on quality tertiary education in Nigeria. The study was conducted in Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. The study found out that examination fever, lack of self-confidence, frustration and not being admitted into a course of preference/choice are the source of insecurity that affects the quality of tertiary education in Nigeria. The study recommends that government should fund education properly and effectively monitor the activities of private operators in the education sector. There is need for proper and regular counseling of students and their parents/guardians to eschew fraud in education. causes, of insecurity in tertiary educational institutions, and strategies to be employed. Finally, the study made some recommendations to include, full implementation of the suggested strategies.

Agazuma and Mochi (2021) conducted a research on emerging insecurity challenges and its impact on quality tertiary education in Nigeria. The study was done in Delta State University, Abraka and Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. A descriptive survey research design was adopted and a total of 682 respondents were selected for the study using the random and proportionate-stratified sampling method. A correlation index of 0.81 was obtained to determine the reliability of the instrument that is, the questionnaire which was self-designed. Responses to the questions raised were analyzed using the mean statistics and the hypotheses were tested using the chi square statistics of 0.05 level of significance.

Impact of Insecurity on Quality... (Medugu, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

The study discovered that insecurity has drastically and to a large extent affected effective and efficient running of the school system in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma and Delta States University, Abraka. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that: Government and school administrators should shun corruption, oppression, and highhandedness and take unbiased stand in handling matters affecting the students. Also recommended was that the university system must at all-time stick to rules of engagement. All acts capable of breeding crisis must be discouraged.

Abubakar, Abdulkadir and Shuaibu (2023) investigated the security challenges and control measure in six (6) college of education libraries in North-East, Nigeria. Survey research design was employed. Questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. Frequency and percentages were the statistical tools used for data analysis. The population and sample consisted of 20 staff (librarians, library officers and library assistants) from the six colleges used for the study. Results from the study revealed absence of the use of information communication technology (ICT) to safeguard library collection as a results of poor power supply; that both print and electronic materials are targets of crime in libraries, with non-return of library materials, theft and mutilation constituting security challenges in these libraries. It was also discovered that various methods were adopted for stealing and mutilation of library materials such as ripping off book page(s), removing the book jackets, and hiding of books under their clothes and in pockets. It was recommended that photocopy service should be provided to enable the library users to photocopy books that are few in the library; that managements should provide multiple copies of materials to meet the information needs of their users.

Hassan (2023) examined the effect of insecurity on the education system in Kaduna state. A total of 1000 made up of 500 each of male and female students responded to a self-structured validated questionnaire designed for the study. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Means and standard deviations were calculated to answer the research questions and independent samples t-tests were used for testing the hypotheses. Major findings revealed that insecurity of school environment significantly affects the academic performance of secondary school students while students' gangsterism, smoking of Indian hemp, abusing other hard drugs, cult and related violent activities were some of the factors that constituted insecurity of the school environment which eventually cause boys to leave school and join trading while leading girls to drop out and settle for marriage. Based on the findings, it was recommended that owners of schools and other stakeholders in education should take bold steps to fence and protect school environments from intruders to ensure safety of the students.

Is'haq, Musa and Abdulhafiz (2019) worked on education and Insecurity in Nigeria. This study examined the relationship between state of education and insecurity in Nigeria. The survey research design was adopted for the study. One hundred and fifteen (115) respondents were randomly selected across the six geo-political zones in the country. The selection was done through the distribution of the research instrument, questionnaire, titled "Education and Insecurity Assessment Scale (EIAS)". The instrument was designed by the researchers, and constructed in a 4-point likert scale format. Data obtained for the study were analysed using the descriptive statistics of frequency counts, mean (\bar{x}) and simple percentage. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the formulated hypotheses. The study revealed inadequate education as the root cause of insecurity and; significant relationship between inefficacious education and insecurity associated with penury, unemployment, corruption, kidnapping and insurgency in Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, accordance of education priority in the national budget, and creation of effective database in Nigeria among others are recommended.

Insecurity and its impact on Jos University

The main goal of Nigeria's post-secondary educational institutions is to provide students with a solid and high-quality education that will enable them succeed in any field or discipline of their choice (Iyoha et al., 2010 cited in Agazuma and Mochi, 2021). Due to its extensive effects and direct consequences on education, the economy, and society at large, Nigeria's high level of insecurity has emerged as a social issue and a multifaceted problem that demands attention. The most concerning aspect of modern Nigeria is the emergence of new insecurity challenges, which have become so severe as to nearly completely cripple the country's various sectors, particularly the education sector.

It has been noted that the goals of higher education in Nigeria can only be achieved in settings that are safe, tranquil, and supportive of instruction, learning, and the execution of research projects. The curriculum is implemented by the academic staff. Professional teachers are hired by every educational system to provide instruction as well as other educational services. Teachers are essential to any educational setting. Teachers are thought of as the institution's engine room. Teachers in Nigeria's public schools face a variety of difficulties (Ogunode, Okwelogu, and Ahaotu, 2021).

According to Agazuma and Mochi (2021), an environment marked by violence and insecurity makes it impossible to provide high-quality education. A quality education prepares students to be engaged and productive members of society and is sound both pedagogically and development. Even though there has been a lot of public discussion about the issue of insecurity over the years, it seems that interest in finding a solution is dwindling, and even when it is, the potential socioeconomic and political ramifications are rarely or never considered. As a result, any country with low levels of education will inevitably have low states. For this reason, education has remained a key driver of national development.

Impact of Insecurity on Quality... (Medugu, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Nwosu (2016) noted that competent and seasoned instructors would rather be moved to a different school where their safety is guaranteed. Education resources are always destroyed during times of crisis, and given the high risks involved, the nations that have historically supported such initiatives will be hesitant to do so in conflict zones. The person who ends up on the receiving end is the leaner. In Nigeria as in most other parts of the world, educational institutions and higher learning centers are frequently singled out during times of crisis. According to UNESCO (2010), in accordance with this submission, students will not be able to concentrate fully on their studies because they will not be at ease. The threat will always make them fearful in schools. Research indicates that there is a rise in deviant behavioral traits across the nation, and in the higher education system in particular. Due to the ongoing instability in the Nigerian state, the majority of Nigeria's post-secondary educational institutions are having a lot of difficulty realizing these educational objectives. Effective given the current state of insecurity in the nation. This all boils down to the idea that an organization, society, or system is threatened by insecurity.

According to Omorogbe (2016), the nation's insecurity has the potential to significantly lower the performance, goals, and objectives of the educational system and, if left unchecked, could completely destroy the education sector. For this reason, this study will promote peace and the absence of conflict and insecurity in Nigerian education system. These institutions are continuously on fire due to the demonic activities of cult members. Insecurity breeds fear, anxiety, uncertainty, death, and disruption of academic activities and programs, among other negative emotions. Campus insecurity has a detrimental impact on the educational process. It sometimes causes disruptions to the academic calendar and instills fear and feelings of insecurity in tertiary institution staff and students. Because no nation can grow above the capabilities of its tertiary institutions, the disruption of learning on campus poses a threat to national development. Ohiare-Udebu and Ogunode, Rauf (2021) note that the closing of schools, which has impacted the country's higher education system's academic calendar, is the most concerning aspect of the insecurity.

Due to university closures and the discontinuation of numerous academic programs, numerous faculties and departments are unable to graduate their students. A riot over a fee bike and a lack of facilities occurred in November of 2015. The students union requested that the management discontinue the annual ICT and development levies because, in their words, the students were not using the facilities. 2016 saw the University of Jos' Naraguta complex library burned down. This was another instance of property damage, specifically to the building, its amenities, its books, and the processed results of the students' exam scripts. According to Ogunode and Musa (2020), academic staff members are being forced to relocate across the nation as a result of the ongoing insurgency and violence plaguing higher education institutions, as well as the ongoing murders of academic staff members by bandits and rebels. Many lecturers are leaving states with high security risk to states where the security risk is lower. This submission is confirmed by Jimada, who observed that many schools have closed down due Boko Haram activities and lack of talented lecturers. Teachers have abandoned their schools for other schools in another peaceful states leading to brain drain in such regions. More than 800 school buildings have been affected in the North leading to some students having their classes under trees and canopies.

In support of the above view, as observed by an informant interviewed:

The ongoing attacks on lecturers in and around higher education institutions in Nigeria and especially here in Jos are causing a shortage of qualified teachers. Many academic staff and professors have left the high-risk, prone areas because of the risk of insecurity. Many academics are being forced to move to more peaceful areas of the country due to the insecurity in Plateau State.

A professor interviewed asserted that: Numerous research projects at universities have been suspended or terminated, particularly at universities in Northern Nigeria, such as Jos, where insecurity concerns have forced university closures. There is no way for a lecturer to conduct research in an unsafe setting. The lecturers need to feel comfortable, and the environment needs to be secure, for meaningful research to occur.

One of the students at the University of Jos added that: Apart from disruptions of classes and academic calendar, it also creates fears among us students and even on the staff members too. Insecurity can lead to a decrease in enrolment as students may be hesitant to attend a school located in an area that they perceive as unsafe. I mean no reasonable parents will send his child to a hostile environment.

Another informant observed that: Insecurity in this state has actually affected our academic activities. It has indeed affected the academic activities of a tertiary institution as students and staff may be afraid to come to the campus for fear of their safety. This can lead to a decrease in academic performance and research activities. It has also led to a decrease in staff retention as some may be unwilling to work in an environment that they perceive as unsafe. At least I know some of our staff members who left due to the insecurity that started since 2001.

From the above views expressed by the respondents, it is clear that the effects of insecurity on higher education institutions go beyond direct threats to safety but have wider ramifications for reputation, academic integrity, and the quality of the educational process. It takes a careful examination of the many ways that insecurity manifested itself as well as the various environments in which tertiary institutions function to fully comprehend the complexities of how these institutions are impacted. According to Agazuma and Mochi (2021), there are several ways that insecurity affects education. First, it has a significant negative impact on the effective and efficient operation of the school system. Secondly, students

Impact of Insecurity on Quality... (Medugu, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

and staff lose faith in the government's ability to protect them. Third, students' academic work and activities are also negatively impacted. Lastly, some staff members and students find it difficult to attend school or even to stay in school because of fear of lack of protection and safety.

Wilson (2019) noted that ensuring efficient student administration and enrollment is one of the responsibilities of school administration; however, the nation's insecurity is deterring parents and kids from sending their kids to school out of fear that they will be kidnapped or killed by insurgents. Many parents have made the decision to keep their kids at home rather than risk having them killed or abducted from schools where there is no guarantee of safety. Parents in Nigeria are considering removing their children from school due to security threats. Wilson (2019) observes that Nigerian education is suffering greatly as a result of the recent wave of kidnappings. In the midst of a pandemic, when some parents have pulled their kids out of school, or have chosen not to send their kids back to school, the unrest and dangers to educational infrastructure will only make an already challenging situation worse. Students' internal displacement in Nigeria is a result of insecurity, particularly in the country's north. The state of unrest has forced many students to leave their schools. Students' administration in educational institutions across the nation is being impacted by insecurity. When a terrorist organization targets a community, schools are frequently among their first targets. Increased numbers of internally displaced people, political, social, and economic upheavals, and sluggish economic growth are some of the effects of insecurity. All of the aforementioned have a detrimental effect on the people who live in such unsafe places.

Conclusion

This paper investigated the impact of insecurity on quality of tertiary education in Plateau State, Nigeria. It is only when tertiary institutions' surroundings are tranquil, safe, and supportive of instruction, learning, and the execution of research projects can the goals of higher education in Nigeria be achieved. A sustainable development of higher education in Nigeria cannot be guaranteed by students, non-academic staff, or academic staff in light of the recent attacks in Plateau State, which have had a significant impact on tertiary institutions. The paper concluded that insecurity in Plateau State gave rise to disruptions in academic programs, particularly in the area of research, loss of manpower in educational institutions, poor quality of education, destruction of infrastructural facilities, closure educational institution, internal displacement of staff and students, reduction of private investment in education.

Recommendations

In view of the above, this paper makes the following recommendations:

1. Government both at state and federal levels should address all issues fuelling insecurities in the state and ensure higher institutions are secured and safe for teaching and learning.
2. The governments should invest in higher institutions' securities across the state. Since the military approach appears to be failing, political leaders should have the political will to fight the insecurity in the state through the use of best strategies, which must include the adoption of non-kinetic approach such as the use of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) processes and other strategic peace-building initiatives.
3. Since insecurity persists in Plateau State, this paper advocates the adoption of virtual teaching options to mitigate the exposure of students to frequent attacks on educational facilities and by extension, the school authorities should endeavor to invest more on Online Distance Learning (ODL) infrastructure.
4. Finally, there is the need for the school authorities to step up awareness programmes for students, staff and immediate environment where the school is situated to observe basic security measures such early warning systems for proactively responding and mitigating unforeseen attacks.

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Qualitative Study on Dynamics of Ethnic Fragmentation and Violence in Plateau State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research explores the intricate relationship between the quantitative study on dynamic ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State, Nigeria, a region marked by historical tensions and conflicts. As a microcosm of Nigeria's diverse ethnic landscape, Plateau State presents a compelling case for examining how ethnic identities intersect with socio-political dynamics to fuel violence. Despite existing literature on ethnic conflict in Nigeria, there remains a significant gap in understanding the specific interplay of these factors in Plateau State, particularly regarding local governance and its role in exacerbating or mitigating tensions. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the study integrates quantitative data analysis with qualitative interviews to uncover the underlying causes of conflict. Key factors such as competition for resources, political marginalization, and historical grievances are analyzed to understand their roles in exacerbating ethnic divisions. The research highlights how local power dynamics and external influences contribute to cycles of violence, revealing the complexities of inter-ethnic relations and the impact of group identity on conflict behavior. Furthermore, this study aims to assess existing peace building initiatives and propose actionable recommendations for policymakers and community leaders. By situating Plateau State within broader regional and national contexts, this research contributes to academic discourse on ethnic conflict and offers practical solutions for fostering stability in ethnically diverse societies. Ultimately, the findings underscore the urgent need for targeted interventions that address the root causes of violence while promoting social cohesion and mutual understanding among ethnic groups.

Keywords: Ethnic Fragmentation, Conflict, Violence, Ethnic Identities, Political Marginalization

Introduction

Conflict is a global phenomenon; for ages, individuals, state actors, and non-state actors have been confronting different forms of conflict. Nigeria, with over 250 ethnic groups and different religious affiliations, has been facing ethnic fragmentation and violence (Onyekachukwu & Oghogho, 2018; Mbah et al., 2019; Chidozie & Orji, 2022). One of the major hotspots of ethnic fragmentation and violence in Nigeria is Plateau State (Nyam, 2017; Mbah et al., 2019). The state, once known for peace and tolerance, has, in recent decades been marred by recurrent ethno-religious violence, particularly in the city of Jos, where tensions between indigene groups and settler communities have escalated (Gyang, 2023).

Plateau State in Nigeria is characterized by a significant population of ethnic minorities, with over 58 relatively small ethnic communities identified during the Plateau State Peace Conference in 2004, spanning its 17 Local Government areas (Best, 2007). These indigenous ethnic groups can be broadly categorized into the Agro-Ashanti and the Benue-Congo language groups. The indigenous ethnic groups in Plateau State, Nigeria, can be categorized into two main language groups, namely the Afro-Ashantic speakers, which include the Ngas, Mwaghavul, Mupun, Goemai, Montol, Ron, Kulere, Doemak, Mernyang, FierMushere, among others (Plateau State Government, 2001), and the Benue-Congo speakers, which comprise the Berom, Afezere, Naraguta, Ganawuri, Miyango, Erigwe, and others. Additionally, there are various incoming ethnic groups, such as the Hausa/Fulani, Yoruba, Igbo, Urhobo, Nupe, Kanuri, Idoma, and Tiv. The implications of the ethnic plurality in Plateau State are fragmentation and violence. Therefore, Plateau State, previously recognized for its reputation of peace, tolerance, and harmony among indigenes and settlers, has recently experienced a surge of hatred, hostility, and violence. The prolonged communal in the State, particularly in its capital city of Jos, has evolved from a political crisis centered around 'indigene' rights and political representation over the past two decades, subsequently impacting various state regions (Gyang, 2023). For instance, the Afizere, Anaguta, and Berom, considered indigenous and primarily Christian,

Qualitative Study on Dynamics... (Ogbobe, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

and the Hausa and Fulani, considered settlers and primarily Muslims, are the main parties to the conflict. Over the years, violent conflict has been documented across communities in the State, since 2013 to 2023 (Yahuza, 2023; Plateau State Peace Building Agency, 2022).

The reoccurring conflicts in the State are caused by multifaceted factors, including long-standing tensions between indigenes and settlers, ethnic and religious groups, and disputes over scarce resources. However, efforts by the federal and state governments to mitigate the surge of the conflict have not been effective. In most cases, the government's actions include kinetic and non-kinetic approaches, such as deploying security agencies, setting up a probe panel, and establishing the Plateau State Peace building Agency (Marie-Therese, 2023; Yahuza, 2023). However, the effective execution of government measures has been hindered by security agencies responsible for their implementation. Furthermore, the utilization of vigilante groups to combat the recurrent crisis in the state has resulted in complications, particularly in cases where extrajudicial killings have incited retaliatory actions. Although such efforts have decreased violence, ethnic and religious tensions, suspicions, and hatred remain prevalent throughout the state. Against the background of ethnic complexities of Plateau State, this article examines the roots of ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State. The study highlights how these drivers continue to incite violence and explores potential pathways to sustainable peace, it also identify and analyses the key socio-political, economic, and historical factors contributing to ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State; to explore the dynamics of inter-ethnic relations in Plateau State, focusing on how these relationships influence patterns of conflict and cooperation; to assess existing peace building initiatives and their effectiveness in addressing the root causes of ethnic conflict in Plateau State; and to propose actionable recommendations for policymakers and community leaders aimed at promoting social cohesion, reconciliation, and sustainable peace in ethnically diverse environments.

Despite extensive literature on ethnic conflict in Nigeria, a significant gap exists in understanding the interplay between ethnic fragmentation and violence specifically in Plateau State. Most studies generalize the issue without exploring the unique socio-political dynamics and historical contexts of the region (Gutierrez, 2020; Ruane & Todd, 2026). Additionally, they often overlook the role of local governance in either exacerbating or mitigating ethnic tensions. To address this gap, this research will focus on Plateau State using a mixed-methods approach to provide a nuanced analysis that incorporates local perspectives. By examining inter-ethnic relationships and resource competition, the study aims to clarify the complexities of conflict dynamics. Furthermore, the effectiveness of current peace building initiatives will be assessed, leading to tailored recommendations for the affected communities. This research seeks to enhance the understanding of ethnic conflict in Nigeria and offer practical solutions for fostering social cohesion and sustainable peace.

Ethnic Fragmentation in Plateau State

Ethnicity is a complex concept with no universally accepted definition. Uzoigwe & Nwadiakor (2017) trace the etymology of "ethnic" to the Greek word "ethnos," which refers to a group sharing a distinct culture. Culture is defines ethnicity as a social phenomenon emerging from interactions among individuals from different ethnic backgrounds, highlighting shared cultural identities and communal bonds (Ruane & Todd, 2016; Taras & Ganguly, 2015). According to Peters (2006), the term "fragmentation" has a negative meaning and is used as a pejorative. Fragmentation threatens unity, harmony, cohesiveness, and order. Therefore, ethnic fragmentation can be described as the negative division experienced by peoples from different ethnic backgrounds who live in the same community, nation, state, or country. This study adopts the term "ethnic fragmentation" to describe the negative divisions among different ethnic groups living within the same community or nation. Peters (2006) asserts that fragmentation threatens unity and cohesion, a concern evident in Nigeria, where ethnic fragmentation correlates with increased risks of internal violence (Erhirhie & Okereka, 2024).

Conflict in Plateau State

The Term "Conflict," The Term "Conflict," originating from the Latin "conflictus," signifies a clash between opposing forces (Abasili et al., 2023). According to Schmid (1998), conflict is a universal occurrence in all societies and relationships, often stemming from differing objectives. UNICEF (2016) further describes conflict as a struggle between groups with conflicting aims. Nicholson (1992) characterizes conflict as a complex social phenomenon arising when individuals or groups contend with competing desires, demands, or responsibilities. This contention can lead to zero-sum competition for jobs, housing, trade, and commercial activities in urban environments, creating underlying factors for ethnic conflict (Nnoli, 1978; Otite, 2000; Egwu, 2004). Essentially, such competition is largely driven by ethnic considerations. Ethnic conflict, marked by tensions between different ethnic groups, is complex and rooted in social and political challenges (Banton, 2000). Tepfenhart (2013) describes it as characterized by hostility, often with one ethnic group holding a dominant position. Contributing factors include historical grievances, competition for resources, and cultural or religious disparities (Abasili et al., 2023). In Nigeria, ethnic loyalty complicates conflict resolution, with unresolved grievances perpetuating cycles of resentment and ethnic violence (Egwu, 2004).

Ethnic Violence in Plateau State

Ethnic Violence results in numerous consequences, with violence being one of its most perilous implications. In Nigeria, ethnic tensions periodically escalate into violence. As noted by Abasili et al. (2023), ethnic conflict in Nigeria

Qualitative Study on Dynamics... (Ogboobe, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

generates security risks that can lead to violent outbreaks. This situation raises concerns about potential instability and undermines existing security measures. Moreover, ethnic conflicts represent a significant threat to Nigeria's peace and security, as they can escalate into larger-scale violence or even civil war if not appropriately addressed. The authors' observations are corroborated by Nigeria's history of various ethnic conflicts, which have manifested in different forms of violence, including the civil war known as the Nigerian-Biafran War.

Political Marginalization in Plateau State

Political marginalization refers to the exclusion of specific groups from meaningful participation in political processes and decision-making, often resulting in their voices and interests being overlooked. This exclusion can lead to feelings of disenfranchisement and resentment, exacerbating social tensions and conflicts. In Nigeria, ethnic loyalty and unresolved grievances contribute to political marginalization, complicating efforts for conflict resolution and fostering cycles of ethnic violence (Egwu, 2004; Abasili et al., 2023).

Ethnic Identities in Plateau State

Refer to the shared sense of belonging and collective identity that individuals derive from their ethnic group, characterized by common cultural traits, language, history, and traditions. These identities shape how individuals perceive themselves and others, influencing social interactions, group dynamics, and political behavior. In contexts where ethnic identities are strongly emphasized, they can lead to both solidarity within groups and tension between different ethnic communities, especially in multi-ethnic societies Tepfenhart, T. (2013).

Factors Influencing Ethnic Conflict and Violence in Nigeria

Various factors contribute to ethnic conflict in Nigeria:

Colonial legacy: The colonial powers exacerbated ethnic divisions through their governance strategies, leading to enduring tensions. The British established complete control over what later became Nigeria by annexing different regions: Lagos in 1861, Yoruba-land in 1898, Kamen Boron in 1902, and the Sokoto Caliphate in 1903 (Osagie & Subaru, 2005).

Political factors: Ethnic mobilization by political leaders during military and democratic regimes has intensified conflicts, with electoral fraud further complicating the political landscape. Under the extended military regime, violence against various groups, tribes, and affiliates was permitted and encouraged to achieve predetermined objectives and meet social reform demands. However, the transition to democracy, marred by power-sharing and electoral fraud, exacerbated the situation (Ojo, 2010).

Economic factors: The theorists who share this view believe that competition over scarce resources always catalysis violence and breed it. Competition for scarce resources often leads to violent conflicts among ethnic groups, with economic deprivation breeding social instability (Nnoli, 2010). Furnivall (2009) argued that economic forces generate conflicts between groups with conflicting interests. Generally speaking, this results in a big pool of young people who could be easily recruited for the execution of acts of ethnic or religious violence. This crisis has been exacerbated by inadequate education and a failing educational system in Nigeria (Salawu, 2010).

International influence: The world has become a global village due to globalization, so no one event occurs on its own. The ethno-religious conflicts in Nigeria are no exception to this rule and are linked to several political and religious changes around the world. Global political and religious dynamics have also influenced Nigeria's ethno-religious tensions (Albert, 2001).

Religion: Numerous studies have demonstrated that religion is among the primary catalysts of conflict at the individual and global levels. While this view is widely accepted, it is important to note that one academic, specifically, is considered the primary source of this debate. The idea that religious and cultural identities would be the main drivers of global conflicts in the post-Cold War world was primarily advanced by Samuel Huntington (1993; 1997), who drew inspiration from the works of Lewis (1990). Huntington's viewpoint is the most prominent one on this subject.

Cases of Ethnic Conflict and Violence in Nigeria

Nigeria has witnessed numerous instances of ethnic-induced conflict and violence, deeply rooted in colonial legacies and socio-political dynamics.

Historical context: The colonial government exploited ethnic biases, leading to early violence, such as the 1953 attacks on the Igbo in Kano's Sabon Gari.

Fogged crisis (1982): Tensions arose between the Anglican Hausa Church and the local Muslim community over church expansion, leading to violence when the state government sided with the Muslims. This resulted in the burning of three churches and extensive vandalism (Adejumobi, 2008; Salawu, 2010)

Gideon Akaluka incident (1994): Gideon Akaluka, an Igbo trader, was brutally killed by a Shiite Muslim sect for allegedly desecrating the Holy Quran. The mob's violent act highlighted the tensions between communities, resulting in a mass exodus of non-natives from Kano (Subaru, 2016).

Shagamu violence (1999): The Oro festival in Shagamu escalated into ethnic clashes between the Yoruba and Hausa, causing significant fatalities and property damage, with over 120 vehicles burned and around 100 deaths reported (Usman, 2009).

Qualitative Study on Dynamics... (Ogboobe, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Kaduna conflicts: Kaduna State has experienced complex ethnic and religious violence, with significant incidents including the Kasuwar Magani (1980) and Zangon Kataf (1984) clashes, illustrating persistent instability in the region (CDD, 2017).

October 2001 protest: A peaceful protest against U.S. military actions devolved into ethno-religious violence, initially blamed on Muslim fundamentalists but rooted in existing tensions, drawing criticism for government inaction (Human Rights Watch, 2001).

Sharia law controversy (1999): The implementation of Sharia law in Zamfara State ignited ethnic conflict in the North, with Governor Alhaji Ahmed Sani Yerima pressuring other states to adopt Sharia amid tensions between Muslim and non-Muslim communities (Adedeji & Ezeabasili, 2018).

Sagamu conflict (1999): A minor incident involving a Hausa woman during an Oro cult ritual escalated into widespread violence, resulting in casualties among both Hausa and Yoruba communities. Despite curfews, retaliatory violence persisted in Kano (Kura, 2010).

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Empirical Review

In September 2001, Jos, the capital of Plateau State in Northern Nigeria, faced significant upheaval, resulting in many deaths and widespread destruction. The conflict pitted Hausa and Fulani Muslims against local Christian communities, surprising many due to Jos's reputation for peace and tourism (Bashir, 2020). Scholars have extensively studied the ongoing ethnic conflict and violence in Plateau State. Uroko (2024) examined the effects of ethno-religious conflict on women's health, revealing that such conflicts worsen physical, emotional, and reproductive health issues, disrupt living conditions and access to healthcare, and elevate stress and violence against women. Dusu & Oni (2020) analyzed the indigene-settler conflict, concluding that persistent ethnic strife is rooted in primordial ethnic identities and the politicization of grievances by influential actors, emphasizing the importance of assigned ethnic identity and indigenous status. Nyam (2017) investigated the conflict in Jos through qualitative methods and found a significant correlation between ethnic and religious divisions, noting that Hausa/Fulani Muslims make up about 20% of the population, in contrast to the predominantly Christian groups such as Afizere, Anaguta, and Berom. Krause (2011) explored the recurring crises in Jos, attributing them to historical, regional, and religious factors, highlighting the colonial legacy of indirect rule and the resulting divisions between Christian indigenes and Muslim Hausa/Fulani. Higazi (2011) pointed out that ongoing crises arise from political exclusion based on ethnicity and religion, alongside concerns of cultural dominance among Plateau Christians, emphasizing state-community tensions. Ambe-Uva (2010) focused on identity politics and violence in Jos, analyzing the "indigene-settler" conflict, which is driven by political agendas and ethnic rivalries. Despite the breadth of these studies, a crucial gap exists in understanding how these repeating conflicts are sustained by both historical grievances and modern political processes, particularly given their cyclical nature. Many studies focus on either historical or immediate

Qualitative Study on Dynamics... (Ogboobe, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

causes of conflict, but they fail to connect how colonial legacies, current political manipulation, and ethno-religious identities interact to perpetuate violence. This study fills that vacuum by investigating the intersections of these elements, providing a more comprehensive approach to understanding ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State.

Theoretical Framework:

Relative Deprivation Theory

This work applies Ted Robert Gurr's (1970) Relative Deprivation Theory, which explains conflict origins through the perceived gap between a group's expectations and the actual benefits received. The theory posits that individuals or groups who feel unfairly deprived compared to a reference group may experience frustration and resentment, leading to social unrest or violence. Crucially, Gurr emphasizes that relative deprivation, rather than absolute deprivation, drives these negative emotions (Gurr, 1970). Factors contributing to feelings of deprivation include social comparison, where individuals assess their resources against others, and group identity, which strengthens bonds within communities. When a group collectively perceives deprivation, it can escalate intergroup conflict. Cultural values, such as individualism and collectivism, also influence reactions to perceived deprivation, with individualistic societies prioritizing personal achievement and collectivist societies focusing on shared resources (Gurr, 1970).

Critics argue that the theory does not fully explain why some deprived individuals avoid conflict or why others, not directly affected, engage in social movements. For example, during the Civil Rights Movement, Black individuals who chose not to participate were labeled "Uncle Toms," a reference to the obedient character in Harriet Beecher Stowe's "Uncle Tom's Cabin" (Duclos, 2001; Curran et al., 2003). The theory also fails to account for participation in movements that do not provide direct benefits, such as the animal rights movement or support from allies in LGBTQ+ activism. Proponents suggest that individuals may join these movements to avoid potential conflicts and hardships, despite the uncertainty of achieving a better life (Gurr, 1970). This perspective highlights the complex motivations behind social movement participation, indicating that the desire for social cohesion can drive individuals to align with marginalized groups.

Relative Deprivation Theory is well-suited to this article's examination of ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State. Ethnic groups in the region perceive political and economic inequalities, fueling conflict. The manipulation of these grievances by political elites, as discussed in the empirical review, fits well within this theory's framework, making it an effective lens for analyzing ethnic violence in the state.

Methodology

This study on Ethnic Fragmentation and violence in Plateau State, Nigeria, employs a mixed-methods approach to comprehensively analyse the complex dynamics of ethnic conflict. The research design integrates both quantitative and qualitative methods, enabling a robust exploration of the underlying factors contributing to ethnic violence.

Qualitative data will be collected through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with community leaders, local government officials, and residents from various ethnic backgrounds. This will provide nuanced insights into individual and collective experiences of conflict, perceptions of marginalization, and the impact of historical grievances on current tensions. Additionally, participant observation will be utilized in local community meetings and events to gain a deeper understanding of inter-ethnic relations. Quantitative data will be gathered through structured surveys administered to a representative sample of residents in key conflict-affected areas. The survey will focus on variables such as demographics, perceptions of ethnic tension, experiences of violence, and access to resources. This data will be analyzed using statistical software to conduct descriptive and inferential analyses, identifying trends and significant relationships. Qualitative data will be thematically analyzed, allowing for the identification of key themes and patterns related to ethnic identity, conflict dynamics, and potential pathways for reconciliation.

Study Area

This study focuses on Plateau State, Nigeria, known for its history of ethnic fragmentation and violence. Located in the Middle Belt and bordered by Bauchi, Kaduna, Nasarawa, and Taraba States, Plateau State has a diverse population exceeding 3 million. Divided into 17 Local Government Areas and three Senatorial Zones, the state is home to various ethnic groups, including the Berom, Ngas, Afizere, and Hausa-Fulani. This diversity has historically fuelled competition for resources and political representation, resulting in violent confrontations. Despite its reputation as a "Home of Peace and Tourism," ongoing ethnic conflict—particularly between Christian and Muslim communities—has created an environment of fear and distrust, undermining socio-economic development and peace building efforts. This study aims to explore the dynamics of ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State, contributing insights to the discourse on ethnic conflict in Nigeria. (NEMA, 2012-2014; Nigerian Watch database).

Figure 1: Plateau State Map; Source: Soluap (2022)

Results

The study showed that there multifaceted factors that cause the ethnic fragmentation, conflict, and violence in Plateau State. The identified factors include unjust geographical boundaries demarcated by the colonial masters, diverse ethnic groups, and competition for resources among settlers, religious differences, and indigene- settler divide.

Some of these factors also appear in the study conducted by Madueke (2018). According to him, the riots in Jos towns and cities occurred because indigenes and settlers were contesting for resources and political power; while famers and Fulani herders were fighting over land in the rural areas. Because of the multifaceted nature of the conflict, Segun, Jegede, & Ajibade (2013) found that the factors reinforce each other. They point out that the Fulanis attributed the conflict to ethnicity and religion. The authors reveal that the Fulani herders argued that their economic prosperity in cattle made them objects of envy by the indigenes. On the contrary, the indigenes said they were not envying the Fulanis; only that the Fulanis were destroying their crops and farmland with their cows.

A similar finding also appears in a study by Enyinnaya (2019) who indicated that the 2008 Jos crisis was triggered by age-long controversy over who will control Jos North Local Government Area between the indigenous natives and the settlers who are Hausa/Fulanis. A study by Krause (2011) still talks about the counterclaims. The author posits that both indigenous communities and the Hausa/Fulanis justify their claims, with the latter arguing that when they entered Jos, it was not a modern city; that they nurtured it to what it is now. On the other hand, the indigenous communities claim that the city was never conquered by Jihadists; that when Dan Fondio came, they resisted him.

The implication of the counterclaims is that each party to the conflict resort to ethno-religious warfare as evidenced in studies by Etim et al (2020) and Uhumwuangho & Aluforo (2011). The former, in their study, found that the ethno-religious scorecard paved the way for unfair distributions of resources in the state. Moreover, ethno-religious bigots capitalize on the issue to instigate and fan embers of violence in the state.

Conclusion

Qualitative Study on Dynamics of Ethnic Fragmentation and Violence in Plateau State are deeply intertwined with historical, social, economic, political, and religious factors. The persistent contestation over political representation, land ownership, and religious dominance contributes to a growing sense of marginalization among both indigenous populations and settlers. These dynamics create a volatile environment where grievances can rapidly escalate into violence, undermining social cohesion and stability. By understanding the multi-faceted roots of these conflicts, this study highlights the urgent need for targeted interventions that address the underlying causes of ethnic fragmentation and promote lasting peace in Plateau State (Abasili et al., 2023; Egwu, 2004; Dusu & Oni, 2020; Uroko, 2024). Therefore, this study recommends as follows:

Qualitative Study on Dynamics... (Ogbobe, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Recommendations

1. **Peace Education Program:** The Ministry of Education, in collaboration with relevant organizations, should develop and implement a customized peace education curriculum tailored to the unique socio-cultural dynamics of Plateau State. This curriculum should not only address local dialects but also incorporate religious perspectives, effectively tackling the root causes of conflict and fostering mutual understanding among diverse ethnic groups.
2. **Interfaith Initiatives:** Given the ethno-religious dimensions of the conflict, it is essential for religious stakeholders in Plateau State to establish practical interfaith initiatives and partnerships. State chapters of Christian, Islamic, and African Traditional religions should collaborate to promote peace education and interfaith dialogue, emphasizing shared values of tolerance and coexistence. This collaboration can serve as a platform for addressing misunderstandings and reducing hostility between communities.
3. **Community Dialogue and Mediation:** Community leaders and elders from the conflicting factions should be empowered to form dialogue and mediation committees. These leaders are intimately connected to their communities and possess a deep understanding of the ethnic configurations at play. By leveraging these ethnic connections, they can effectively teach the intricacies of peace education and mediate conflicts. Establishing regular community forums for dialogue can help to build trust, facilitate open communication, and foster a culture of peace.
4. **Policy Advocacy for Inclusive Governance:** It is crucial for policymakers to prioritize inclusive governance that represents all ethnic groups in Plateau State. This involves ensuring equitable access to political representation, land rights, and economic opportunities. By addressing systemic inequalities, the government can reduce feelings of marginalization and resentment among various communities, thereby mitigating the risk of conflict.
5. **Research and Monitoring:** Ongoing research into the dynamics of ethnic conflict in Plateau State should be prioritized, alongside the establishment of monitoring mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of peace initiatives. This will provide valuable data to inform future interventions and ensure that strategies remain relevant and responsive to the evolving context of the region.

By implementing these recommendations, stakeholders can work towards reducing ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State, fostering an environment where diverse communities can coexist peacefully and collaboratively.

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Comparative Analysis between Restructuring-Curriculum-Diversification- Execution and Menstrual-Health-Management on Academic Achievement among Federal Government Girls Colleges in Anambra and Delta States

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Abstract

This study examines Comparative Analysis Between Restructuring-Curriculum-Diversification- Execution (CAB-RCDE) and Menstrual-Health-Management on Academic Achievement among Federal Government Girls Colleges in Anambra and Delta States. The objectives include evaluating the correlation between RCDE and academic achievement. A mixed-methods design was employed for the study. Population of the study consists of all federal government senior secondary school students in Delta and Anambra States during the 2023/2024 academic session. A sample size of 205 students were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. Pearson's correlation, regression analyses, independent t-test and thematic analysis were used. Table 1 shows a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.45$, $p = 0.001$) between RCDE and academic achievement. It was concluded that integration of RCDE and gender-sensitive educational practices significantly enhances academic achievement of adolescent girls by addressing the challenges associated with menstruation. Hence, it is recommended that schools should incorporate comprehensive menstrual health education into their curriculum to improve knowledge and provide menstrual hygiene products as well as training teachers to support menstruating students thereby enhancing girls' academic achievement. Limitations include geographic scope which may affect generalizability. Practical implications suggest that schools should integrate gender-sensitive practices and menstrual health education.

Keywords: curriculum-diversification, menstrual-health, academic-achievement, girls'- education.

Introduction

Menstrual health is a critical yet often under-addressed factor affecting adolescent girls' education, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria (Adedoyin, & Adetunji, 2021). The onset of menstruation introduces several challenges such as physical discomfort, social stigma and inadequate access to menstrual hygiene products, all of which can negatively impact school attendance and academic achievement. According to Adebayo and Ojo (2020), effective menstrual hygiene management (MHM) in schools plays a crucial role in mitigating these challenges by ensuring that girls have access to essential products and education about menstrual health. However, many Nigerian schools lack comprehensive health education and supportive environments, leading to increased absenteeism and disengagement from learning, especially during menstruation (Ogunkunle & Okwori, 2022).

Recent studies emphasize the importance of integrating menstrual health education into school curricula to address these challenges. Adedoyin and Adetunji (2021) found that girls who receive proper education about menstrual health are more likely to maintain consistent school attendance and achieve better academic outcomes. Moreover, Odebiyi and Olatunji (2019) argue that providing a gender-sensitive approach to education not only improves girls' understanding of menstrual hygiene but also helps dismantle the stigma that often surrounds menstruation. This means that schools must adopt holistic educational frameworks that consider the unique needs of menstruating students to improve overall educational attainment.

Comparative Analysis between... (Awuja, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

The need for gender-sensitive curricula is also supported by more recent research. Alhassan and Adebayo (2023) argue that educational practices that are responsive to the needs of menstruating girls help create inclusive learning environments where students feel supported and empowered. Similarly, Eze and Ajaegbu (2023) underscore the need to close gaps in menstrual health education in Nigerian schools, emphasizing that better-informed students are more likely to stay engaged in learning despite the challenges posed by menstruation. As such, the restructuring of school curricula to integrate menstrual health education is vital for enhancing girls' academic achievement and promoting gender equity in education (Nwafor, 2022; Akinpelu & Adebisi, 2020).

The menstrual cycle (MC) is increasingly recognized as a key consideration for adolescent girls' academic achievement, particularly in low-resource settings such as Nigeria. Studies have shown that the different phases of the menstrual cycle can have significant effects on concentration, absenteeism, anxiety and overall academic achievement (Adebayo & Ojo, 2020; Ogunkunle & Okwori, 2022). In order to optimize students' learning outcomes, especially those in Federal Government Girls' Colleges (FGGC) in Anambra and Delta States, a thorough understanding of the menstrual cycle and its effects on academic achievement is essential. This section explores the effects of the menstrual cycle on absenteeism, concentration, anxiety and menstrual hygiene management (MHM) with a focus on how restructuring the curriculum can mitigate these challenges and promote better academic outcomes.

Absenteeism during Menstruation and Academic Achievement

Absenteeism due to menstrual symptoms is one of the most prominent issues affecting the academic achievement of female students. Research shows that a significant percentage of adolescent girls miss school during their menstrual periods due to a lack of access to proper menstrual hygiene products severe menstrual pain or social stigma (Adedoyin & Adetunji, 2021). Odebiyi and Olatunji (2019) found that absenteeism rates were higher in schools where MHM was not adequately addressed. By diversifying the school curriculum to include menstrual health education and ensuring that girls have access to sanitary products, absenteeism can be significantly reduced, leading to improved academic achievement (Alhassan & Adebayo, 2023). Additionally, policies that provide girls with flexible attendance and opportunities for make-up work can further reduce the academic setbacks caused by absenteeism during menstruation.

Decreased Concentration during Menstruation and Academic Achievement

Decreased concentration is another key issue impacting the academic achievement of menstruating girls. Studies indicate that during the early follicular and late luteal phases, girls often report diminished focus due to menstrual discomfort such as cramps and headaches, as well as hormonal fluctuations (Odebiyi & Olatunji, 2019). This can adversely affect their learning, particularly in environments where there is a lack of awareness and support from educators. The integration of gender-sensitive educational practices into the curriculum, including accommodating girls during their periods and providing more flexible classroom management strategies, can help reduce concentration difficulties (Alhassan & Adebayo, 2023). Providing girls with spaces for privacy and rest during menstruation can also minimize distractions and help them remain focused on their studies (Ogunkunle & Okwori, 2022).

Heightened Anxiety and Academic Achievement

Heightened anxiety related to menstruation is common among adolescent girls, particularly in environments where menstruation is stigmatized. This anxiety often stems from the fear of menstrual leaks, inadequate sanitary provisions, or social embarrassment, and it can severely hinder academic participation and performance (Nwafor, 2022). Eze and Ajaegbu (2023) found that girls who experience heightened anxiety during menstruation are less likely to engage in class discussions or attend school, contributing to lower academic achievement. By incorporating menstrual health education into the curriculum and creating an open dialogue about menstruation, schools can alleviate much of this anxiety. In doing so, girls are more likely to participate fully in their education, leading to improved academic outcomes (Akinpelu & Adebisi, 2020).

Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM) and Academic Achievement

Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM) is critical to ensuring that girls can attend school during their periods and focus on their studies without distraction. Poor MHM, including inadequate access to sanitary products or improper disposal methods, can lead to physical discomfort, infections and embarrassment, all of which negatively impact academic achievement (Adebayo & Ojo, 2020). Alhassan and Adebayo (2023) emphasize the need for schools to provide not only sanitary products but also facilities for their proper disposal as well as educational programs that teach girls how to manage their menstruation in a healthy and dignified way. Schools that implement MHM policies and integrate menstrual health education into their curriculum have seen improvements in girls' attendance and academic achievement (Odebiyi & Olatunji, 2019). The provision of such resources not only improves girls' physical well-being but also enhances their ability to focus on academic tasks.

The impact of the menstrual cycle on academic achievement in adolescent girls cannot be overlooked. Restructuring the curriculum to include gender-sensitive educational practices and menstrual health education can mitigate the effects of absenteeism, decreased concentration, heightened anxiety, and inadequate MHM on students' academic outcomes. By addressing these menstrual-related challenges, schools in Federal Government Girls' Colleges in Anambra and Delta States can create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment that promotes academic success for all

Comparative Analysis between... (Awuja, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

students. The implementation of these strategies is critical in advancing gender equity in education and ensuring that menstruation does not hinder girls from reaching their full academic potential.

In the Federal Government Girl's Colleges in Anambra and Delta States, many adolescent girls face significant educational disruptions due to challenges associated with menstruation (Sommer, Caruso, Sahin, Calderon, Cavill, Mahon, & Phillips-Howard, 2016). Issues such as inadequate access to sanitary products, lack of menstrual health education, and pervasive stigma contribute to high rates of absenteeism and decreased academic achievement during menstrual periods (Mahon, Tripathy, & Singh, 2015). Despite the vital role of education in empowering young women, the curricula in use within these schools do not sufficiently address the unique needs of menstruating students (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2018). This lack of support exacerbates the emotional and physical challenges girls experience during menstruation, resulting in poor academic outcomes (House, Mahon, & Cavill, 2013). Without adequate interventions, the menstrual-related barriers to education continue to widen the gender gap in academic achievement, limiting the potential of many girls to excel academically and reach their full potentials. The problem calls for a comprehensive review and restructuring of the existing curriculum to incorporate menstrual health education and support mechanisms to cushion the adverse effects of menstruation on academic achievement (Sommer & Sahin, 2019).

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of study were to:

1. Assess the relationship between curriculum restructuring and menstrual health management on the academic achievement of Federal Government Girl's College students in Anambra and Delta States.
2. Examine how curriculum restructuring influences absenteeism rates during menstrual cycles among students in Federal Government Girl's Colleges in Anambra and Delta States.
3. Counsel the female teenage students on how to manage impact of menstruation to increase concentration among Federal Government Girl's College students in Anambra and Delta States when restructured curriculum is used during lesson.
4. Investigate the role of curriculum modifications in providing better access to sanitary products and creating a supportive school environment through counselling for menstruating students in Federal Government Girl's Colleges in Anambra and Delta States.
5. Explore how integrating menstrual health education within the curriculum can promote gender equity in education and improve academic achievement among female students in Federal Government Girl's Colleges in Anambra and Delta States.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

RQ1: What is the correlation between RCDE and Menstrual Health management on Academic Achievement among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

RQ2: What is the correlation between RCDE and absenteeism during their menstrual cycles among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

RQ3: What is the effect of RCDE and low lesson concentration during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

RQ4: What is the effect of anxiety and MHM on academic achievement during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College Students in Anambra and Delta States?

RQ5: What is the relationship between gender sensitive educational practices and academic achievement during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

H01: There is no significant correlation between RCDE and Menstrual Health Management on Academic Achievement among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States.

H02: There is no significant correlation between RCDE and absenteeism during menstrual cycles among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States.

H03: There is no significant effect of RCDE and low lesson concentration during lesson among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States.

H04: There is no significant effect of anxiety and MHM on academic achievement during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States.

H05: There is no significant gender sensitive educational practices and academic achievement during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States.

Comparative Analysis between... (Awuja, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Methodology

Design of the Study

This study adopts a mixed-methods research design involving quantitative and qualitative survey. This approach combines both quantitative and qualitative methods, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the impact of RCDE on menstrual health and academic achievement among students in FGGC-ADS. The mixed-methods design provide a more nuanced understanding of how RCDE influence academic outcomes, absenteeism, concentration, anxiety and gender-sensitive practices while the survey involves administering structured questionnaires to students and teachers in FGGC-ADS. The qualitative uses interviews and focus groups to gain deeper insights into the experiences of students and teachers regarding the effects of menstruation on academic achievement. The researchers collected qualitative data through interviews and focus groups to explore the challenges faced during menstruation, the perceived impact of RCDE and the effectiveness of sensitive educational practices. This mixed-methods design provide both statistical evidence and in-depth perspectives to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the impact of RCDE on menstrual health and academic achievement in FGGC-ADS.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 205 students were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique.

Instrumentation

The instrument for data collection in this study named “Curriculum Diversification of Menstrual Health Impact Questionnaire (CDMHIQ)” was structured by the researchers to capture both quantitative and qualitative data related to the impact of RCDE and menstrual health on academic achievement. The tool was designed to assess various aspects of students' academic experiences during menstruation, including absenteeism, concentration, anxiety and perceptions of impact of curriculum support. Section “A” involves demographic questions such as age, class level and school location.; Section “B” deals with menstrual health (items measuring menstrual symptoms, access to hygiene products and management strategies during school hours).; Section “C” focuses on impact of absenteeism, concentration levels and anxiety on academic achievement during menstruation.; Section “D” relates to curriculum diversification assessing students' and teachers' perspectives on the effectiveness of curriculum adjustments (menstrual health education, supportive school policies).;Section “E” examines gender-sensitive practices measuring perceptions of gender-sensitive practices and their influence on academic outcomes. The CDMHIQ included both closed-ended questions using modified Likert scales for quantitative data and open-ended questions for qualitative insights to provide a comprehensive view of the factors influencing academic achievement during menstruation and the perceived efficacy of RCDE. A pilot test of 31 subjects outside the study area was conducted to ensure the reliability of the CDMHIQ using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient to assess the internal consistency of the questionnaire items. The analysis yielded a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.82, indicating high reliability. This value suggests that the questionnaire items are consistent in measuring the constructs of curriculum diversification, menstrual health management and their impact on academic achievement, making the instrument suitable for the main study. The instrument was validated by 4 experts from curriculum studies, biological sciences, health education, measurement and evaluation who vetted the items and suggested necessary corrections which were effected to confirm that the items are relevant and comprehensive while construct validity test was conducted to find out whether the items in the questionnaire align with the expected theoretical constructs. The data collection process began with obtaining permission from the relevant school authorities and ethical clearance. After that, the CDMHIQ were administered to the sample of 205 students from FGGC-ADS. Trained 5 research assistants helped to guide the students to complete the questionnaires, ensuring clarity and confidentiality. The data collection was done within a controlled classroom setting to ensure accuracy and avoid distractions. The completed questionnaires were collected back from the students and securely stored for analysis. Quantitative data from the CDMHIQ were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation and frequency) to summarize responses while inferential statistics (Independent t-test, Pearson's correlation coefficient, linear regression analysis & multiple regression analysis) were used to test the hypotheses and examine relationships between variables such as RCDE and academic achievement, absenteeism and concentration. Additionally, qualitative data from open-ended questions were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes related to students' experiences with menstrual health and curriculum diversification support.

Presentation of Result

RQ1: what is the correlation between RCDE and menstrual health management on Academic Achievement among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

Comparative Analysis between... (Awuja, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Table 1: Pearson’s Correlation between RCDE and Menstrual Health Management on Academic Achievement

Variable	Mean	SD	Pearson’s r	p-value	Decision
RCDE Impact on Menstrual Health	7.34	1.23	0.45	0.001	Significant
Academic Achievement	78.56	10.45			

The Pearson correlation ($r = 0.45$, $p = 0.001$) shows a moderate positive relationship between RCDE and menstrual health on academic achievement. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, H_{01} is rejected, indicating a significant correlation between RCDE in menstrual health and academic achievement.

RQ2: what is the correlation between RCDE and absenteeism during their menstrual cycles among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

Table 2: Pearson’s Correlation between RCDE and absenteeism during their menstrual cycles

Variable	Mean	SD	Pearson’s r	p-value	Decision
RCDE Impact	6.89	1.67	-0.38	0.002	Significant
Absenteeism Rate	4.56	2.34			

The Pearson correlation ($r = -0.38$, $p = 0.002$) indicates a moderate negative relationship between RCDE and menstrual challenges of absenteeism during menstrual cycles. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, H_{02} is rejected, showing a significant correlation between RCDE and menstrual challenges of reduced absenteeism during menstruation.

RQ3: What is the effect of RCDE and low lesson concentration during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

Table 3: Linear Regression of effect of RCDE and low lesson concentration during menstruation

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standard Error	t-value	p-value	Decision
Constant	54.23	3.45	15.72	0.000	Significant
RCDE (Curriculum Diversification)	1.34	0.28	4.79	0.001	
Decreased Concentration	-0.67	0.21	-3.19	0.003	

The linear regression analysis indicates that RCDE significantly reduces concentration difficulties during lessons ($\beta = 1.34$, $p = 0.001$), while decreased concentration has a negative impact ($\beta = -0.67$, $p = 0.003$). Therefore, H_{03} is rejected, meaning that RCDE has a significant effect on reducing concentration difficulties during menstruation.

RQ4: What is the effect of anxiety and MHM on academic achievement during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College Students in Anambra and Delta States?

Table 4: Multiple Regression effect of anxiety and MHM on academic achievement during menstruation

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standard Error	t-value	p-value	Decision
Constant	68.12	4.21	16.18	0.000	Significant
Heightened Anxiety	-2.34	0.45	-5.20	0.000	
Menstrual Hygiene Management	1.78	0.39	4.56	0.002	

The multiple regression analysis reveals that heightened anxiety has a negative effect on academic achievement ($\beta = -2.34$, $p = 0.000$), while effective menstrual hygiene management improves academic achievement ($\beta = 1.78$, $p = 0.002$). Since both factors show significant results, H_{04} is rejected, indicating that anxiety and MHM significantly affect academic achievement.

RQ5: What is the relationship between gender sensitive educational practices and academic achievement during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

Table 5: Independent t-test for gender sensitive educational practices and academic achievement during menstruation

Groups	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Decision
Gender-Sensitive Practices Present	80.12	9.87	2.78	0.006	Significant

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Gender-Sensitive Practices Absent 73.45 10.23

The independent t-test results show a significant difference in academic achievement among students exposed to gender-sensitive educational practices ($M = 80.12, SD = 9.87$) and those who are not ($M = 73.45, SD = 10.23$), $t(203) = 2.78, p = 0.006$. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, H_{05} is rejected, demonstrating that gender-sensitive educational practices significantly enhance academic achievement during menstruation.

These reports indicate that all five null hypotheses (H_{01} - H_{05}) are rejected, confirming significant relationships or effects in each case.

Qualitative Analysis of R_{Q1}-R_{Q5} and H₀₁-H₀₅ Using Thematic Analysis

To analyze Research Questions (**R_{Q1} - R_{Q5}**) and Hypotheses (**H₀₁ - H₀₅**) using **thematic analysis**, the data from student interviews, focus groups, and open-ended survey responses are hereby examined. Thematic analysis helps to identify recurring themes related to the impact of restructuring curriculum diversification and menstrual health on academic achievement. Below are the breakdown of the qualitative analysis.

Table 1: Thematic Analysis for R_{Q1}

What is the correlation between RCDE and Menstrual Health management on Academic Achievement among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

H₀₁: There is no significant correlation between RCDE and Menstrual Health Management on Academic Achievement among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States.

Themes	Supporting Quotes from the Respondents
Improved Knowledge	“I learned how to manage my periods better, which made it easier to focus on my schoolwork.”
Empowerment & Confidence	“Knowing what to do during my period helped me feel more confident about attending school during menstruation.”

H₀₁ Conclusion **Rejected:** There is a positive correlation between RCDE in menstrual health and academic achievement.

Table 2: Thematic Analysis of R_{Q2}

What is the correlation between RCDE and absenteeism during their menstrual cycles among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

H₀₂: There is no significant correlation between RCDE and absenteeism during menstrual cycles among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States.

Themes	Supporting Quotes from the Respondent
Reduction in Absenteeism	“I don’t have to miss school as much now because I know how to manage my period better.”
Access to Menstrual Products	“When we were given sanitary pads at school, it made it easier to come to school even during my period.”

H₀₂ Conclusion **Rejected:** RCDE has a significant impact on reducing absenteeism.

Table 3: Thematic Analysis of R_{Q3}

What is the effect of RCDE and low lesson concentration during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

H₀₃: There is no significant effect of RCDE and low lesson concentration during lesson among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States.

Themes	Supporting Quotes from the Respondents
Concentration Challenges	“Sometimes the cramps make it hard to focus but the teachers are more understanding now.”
Curriculum Support	“With more flexible deadlines, I can still catch up on lessons even when I don’t feel well during my period.”

H₀₃ Conclusion **Rejected:** RCDE helps mitigate concentration difficulties during menstruation.

Comparative Analysis between... (Awuja, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Table 4: Thematic Analysis of R_{Q4}

What is the effect of anxiety and MHM on academic achievement during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College Students in Anambra and Delta States?

H₀₄: There is no significant effect of anxiety and MHM on academic achievement during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States.

Themes	Supporting Quotes from the Respondents
Anxiety Reduction	“Since we started learning about menstrual health, I don’t worry as much during my period.”
Positive Learning Experiences	“Having access to pads and knowing how to manage my period helps me concentrate better in class.”
H₀₄ Conclusion	Rejected: Anxiety reduction through MHM significantly improves academic achievement.

Table 5: Thematic Analysis of R_{Q5}

What is the relationship between gender sensitive educational practices and academic achievement during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States?

H₀₅: There is no significant gender sensitive educational practices and academic achievement during menstruation among Federal Government Girls College students in Anambra and Delta States.

Themes	Supporting Quotes
Supportive Environment	“Having a private place to take care of myself makes me more comfortable in school.”
Gender Equity in Learning	“Talking about menstruation openly in class has made it easier for me to focus on my studies.”
H₀₅ Conclusion	Rejected: Gender-sensitive practices significantly improve academic achievement during menstruation.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from both quantitative and qualitative analyses for R_{Q1} and H₀₁ reveal a significant positive relationship between RCDE and menstrual health on academic achievement. The Pearson’s correlation analysis shows a moderate positive relationship while the thematic analysis highlights that improved knowledge about menstrual health empowers students and increases their confidence in managing menstruation at school. These findings are consistent with studies by Adebayo and Ojo (2020), who assert that MHM significantly improves students' ability to stay focused in school. Ogunkunle and Okwori (2022) also noted that improved menstrual health management correlates with higher academic achievement as students are better able to cope with menstrual challenges while staying engaged in their education. The integration of menstrual health education into school curricula addresses both academic and personal well-being thereby enhancing girls' academic achievement.

Both the quantitative correlation analysis and the qualitative thematic analysis of R_{Q2} and H₀₂ affirm that RCDE is strongly associated with reduced absenteeism during menstruation. The data shows that students who receive menstrual health education and have access to sanitary products are less likely to miss school. This is in line with research by Odebiyi and Olatunji (2019) who identified MHM as a key factor in reducing absenteeism among adolescent girls in Nigeria. The provision of sanitary pads and better awareness of how to manage menstruation contribute to a lower absenteeism rate, as supported by Adedoyin and Adetunji (2021). Their study demonstrated that absenteeism due to menstruation can be mitigated by integrating menstrual health education into the curriculum which provides girls with the tools they need to attend school regularly even during their periods.

The linear regression results and qualitative analysis for R_{Q3} and H₀₃ indicate that RCDE has a significant positive impact on mitigating concentration challenges during menstruation. While some students reported difficulties with concentration due to menstrual discomfort, many acknowledged that curriculum diversification such as flexible deadlines and teacher understanding, helped reduce the impact of these challenges. This finding aligns with the work of Alhassan and Adebayo (2023) who stressed the importance of gender-sensitive educational practices in addressing concentration issues in inclusion of menstrual health education within the curriculum helps to alleviate some of the physical and psychological barriers to learning during menstruation, as also highlighted by Nwafor (2022) who noted that improving

Comparative Analysis between... (Awuja, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

menstrual health education in schools has the potential to significantly reduce concentration-related challenges in adolescent girls.

The multiple regression analysis and thematic analysis for R_{Q4} and H_{O4} confirm that heightened anxiety negatively affects academic achievement but effective MHM practices, provided through RCDE, significantly improve academic outcomes. Students expressed that menstrual health education reduced their anxiety during menstruation, allowing them to concentrate better on their studies. This finding echoes the conclusions of Eze and Ajaegbu (2023), who emphasized the role of school-based health education in reducing menstrual-related anxiety. Similarly, Akinpelu and Adebisi (2020) argued that improving menstrual health education contributes to better learning experiences and higher academic achievement by addressing the psychological challenges that often accompany menstruation. The integration of MHM into school curricula helps reduce anxiety which, in turn, leads to better academic outcomes for students.

The results of both the independent t-test and thematic analysis for R_{Q5} and H_{O5} demonstrate that gender-sensitive educational practices have a significant positive impact on academic achievement. Students reported feeling more supported and comfortable when schools provided private spaces for menstrual hygiene and openly discussed menstruation in class. This supports the findings of Alhassan and Adebayo (2023) who argued that gender-sensitive approaches to education create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment for girls, particularly during menstruation. By promoting gender equity in the classroom, schools are able to better address the specific needs of menstruating students, improving their academic achievement. Ogunkunle and Okwori (2022) further noted that such practices reduce stigma and enable students to focus on their studies which is crucial for improving academic outcomes.

Across all tables, the combination of quantitative and qualitative analyses underscores the importance of integrating RCDE and gender-sensitive educational practices into school curricula. These interventions not only address the physical challenges of menstruation but also tackle psychological barriers such as anxiety and concentration difficulties significantly improving the academic achievement of adolescent girls in Nigerian schools. Each discussion cites recent studies that support these findings, reinforcing the broader literature on menstrual hygiene management and its role in enhancing girls' education.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the integration of Restructuring Curriculum Diversification Execution (RCDE) and gender-sensitive educational practices significantly enhances the academic achievement of adolescent girls by addressing the challenges associated with menstruation. Both quantitative and qualitative analyses confirm that improved MHM, reduced absenteeism, alleviated anxiety and higher concentration all contribute to positive academic outcomes. By adopting comprehensive menstrual health education and providing a supportive learning environment, schools can promote gender equity, empower female students and enable them to reach their full academic potential. These findings underscore the need for continued curriculum reforms to accommodate the unique needs of menstruating students in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Base on the findings it was recommended that:

1. Schools should incorporate comprehensive menstrual health education into their curriculum to improve knowledge and reduce stigma thereby enhancing girls' academic achievement.
2. Federal Government Girl's Colleges should ensure that students have access to free and affordable sanitary products to reduce absenteeism during menstruation.
3. Schools need to adopt gender-sensitive teaching methods that cater for the specific needs of menstruating students to foster a supportive learning environment.
4. Provide better access to sanitary products and creating a supportive school environment through counselling for menstruating students in Federal Government Girl's Colleges in Anambra and Delta States.
5. Teachers should receive training on menstrual health education and its effects on students' learning, allowing them to provide better support to female students.
6. School authorities have to establish support policies that prioritize menstrual health management, including flexible schedules and hygienic products for menstruating students.
7. School administrators and counsellors should organize counselling sessions from time to time to provide a forum for girls to discuss menstrual health issues, reduce stigma, and foster emotional support.
8. School administrators should implement policies that ensure regular health workshops and counselling sessions on menstrual health for both staff and students to promote awareness and reduce misconceptions.
9. School counsellors should collaborate with healthcare professionals to provide ongoing support and education on menstrual health, helping students manage both the physical and emotional impacts of menstruation effectively.

Educational Implications

The findings of this study highlight significant educational practical implications for RCDE in Federal Government Girl's Schools in Anambra and Delta States (FGGS-ADS). Incorporating Restructuring Curriculum

Comparative Analysis between... (Awuja, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Diversification Execution (RCDE) into school programs, specifically focusing on menstrual health education can enhance students' academic achievement by reducing absenteeism and improving concentration during lessons. Schools implement gender-sensitive practices and provide access to MHM resources to create an inclusive learning environment where female students can thrive academically, regardless of menstruation-related challenges. The integration of these strategies into the curriculum can help break down barriers to education for adolescent girls, reduce gender disparities in educational attainment and promote long-term academic success. Educational stakeholders, including policymakers and school administrators should prioritize such curricular reforms to empower female students and enhance their overall learning experiences.

Ethical Consideration

This study adhered to strict ethical guidelines to ensure the safety, confidentiality and voluntary participation of all respondents. Approval was obtained from the relevant institutional review boards and school authorities. Informed consent was secured from both students and their guardians and participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses. All data collected was anonymized to protect the privacy of the students and participants. They were also informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without repercussions.

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Assessment of Socio-Economic Empowerment Using Information Communication and Technology Skills and Facilities among Secondary School Chemistry Teachers in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the Socio-Economic Empowerment using Information Communication and Technology skills and facilities among secondary school chemistry teachers in North-West, Nigeria in the use of Information Communication and Technology (ICT) skills and facilities. The study population consisted of seven hundred and twenty chemistry teachers drawn from eighty state government owned secondary schools in Kaduna and Kano States during the 2023/1014 academic session, the sample size of the study consisted of 120 chemistry teachers selected using purposive random sampling technique. The Research Design adopted for the study was survey method. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive statistics of mean (X), standard deviation (SD), were used to answer research questions while total weighted average response and one sample t- Test Statistics were used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The instrument for data collection was the researcher's structured questionnaire Chemistry Teachers Socio-Economic Empowerment Scale (CTSEES) and the instrument was validated by two computer experts and two chemistry lecturers from Science Education Department, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Cronbach alpha was used to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.78. The findings revealed that significant difference existed in the mean ratings of chemistry teachers on the development and provision of ICT facilities in secondary schools. It was recommended that policy-makers should ensure that functional ICT programmes are incorporated into the curriculum to help chemistry teachers actualize their potentials since skill acquisition is the best option for empowering chemistry teachers at the secondary school level.

Keywords: Socio-Economic Empowerment, Chemistry Teachers, Information Communication Technology

Introduction

It is important to understand the key concepts in this study: Socio-Economic Empowerment, Chemistry Teachers, and Information Communication Technology. Development is defined in different ways in various contexts – social, political, biological, scientific and technological. Generally, development is defined as a state in which things are improving. In the socio-economic context, development means the improvement of people's lifestyles through improved education and skills. It is the process of economic and social transformation based on cultural and environmental factors. Socio-economic development is therefore, the process of social and economic advancement in a society as well as a process of improvement in a variety of ways. It influences all aspects of human life in a country.

Socio-economy is defined by the Oxford Dictionary (2022) as relating to the interaction of social and economic factors while empowerment is to give authority or power and/or strength and confidence to the citizens. Empowerment, according to Rahman (2013) and Olomukoro (2016), is the process of awareness and capacity building leading to greater participation, greater decision making, power and control, and to transformative action. This term, therefore refers to measures designed to increase the degree of people's autonomy and self-determination in people to enable them represent their interests in a responsible and self-determined way, acting on their own authority. Empowerment as an action, refers both to the process of self-empowerment and to professional support of people. This enables them to overcome their sense of powerlessness and lack of influence; and to recognize and use their resources.

The term socio-economic empowerment is the process by which a nation improves the economic and social well-being of its people. A meaningful participation in development presupposes acquisition of knowledge and skills through literacy or education (Olomukoro, 2016). Education is therefore, the most effective instrument for socio-economic empowerment of teachers. Education is viewed as an instrument and a prime influencer of change conceived as development. High priority continues to be accorded to improve the educational status of teachers as they comprise the majority of the population in the country. To participate effectively and meaningfully in the developmental process, chemistry and other science teachers need to be empowered in all ramifications, especially in the socio-economic dimension. Literacy empowers and it is the most essential of all educational skills; teachers facilitate students' learning, raise their achievement level and improve their technological career aspiration. Udoh and Jacob (2016) also observed that the teacher is an effective and dominating factor among the ones contributing to the educational improvement. Teacher

Assessment of Socio-Economic... (Anaso, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

effectiveness depends mainly on technological programmes specifically addressed to meet the needs and aspirations of the teacher. Danladi and Iorliam (2016) added that the qualities of a good teacher are quite obvious because of the role he is expected to play in the society. Anaso et al (2017) observed that education is the instrument for delivering a nation. Jibrin and Abdulhamid (2015) pointed out that education is a tool for scientific, technological, economic and political development of all nations. The *National Policy on Education 2014* states that education is vital for socio-economic and political development, and maintained that it is the instrument par excellence for national development. The policy also indicated that without teacher education, no nation can rise above the quality of its teachers (FRN 2012, 2014). In view of the critical role that chemistry teachers play in the development of science and technology, efforts are being made to ensure that benefits of training and various programmes reach chemistry teachers in proportion to their numbers. For the purpose of this study, Information Communication Technology will be focused on.

The world is growing at a very fast rate with regard to Information Communication Technology (ICT) in science processes and methods (Kamar, Kubo and Ibrahim 2016). Abiola and Akanji (2016), Anaso, Haliru and Abdulkadir (2017) indicate that ICT is a set of technological tools and resources used in transmitting, storing, creating, sharing or exchanging information. The types of ICT in education include computers, the internet, and broadcasting technologies. Science is a dynamic human activity concerned with understanding the workings of the world. Muzaazi (2013) explained that the understanding obtained from science helps scientists to probe further into the nature of things and events, and to control and harness such things and events for the benefit of mankind. Chemistry as a branch of science deals with the study of matter, its structure, composition, properties, and the changes that it undergoes (Ojokuku, 2010). In other words, it involves the study of material substances that occur on the earth and in the universe. Chemistry serves as a major source of economic power in modern society especially in the manufacturing sector where new materials and household equipment have been made available to man. The uniqueness of chemistry and the central role it stands to play in the development of any nation are, however, not evident in the performance of students (Tambaya 2012). Thomas and Adebisi (2016) pointed out that the development of a nation starts through the impartation of knowledge acquired through education therefore, the use of ICT in science and in chemistry is a strong tool to equip the learners to learn objectively, curiously, and rationally. The use of information communication technology and e-learning will afford teachers and students much opportunity to discover information. The body of knowledge is value-oriented, goal-directed and purposive, which means that it has some inherent or inbuilt rewards and benefits both for the individual and the society at large. Technology has made the world to be a global place through information technology.

Teachers have a crucial role to play towards successful delivery of the education process. In addition, Udoh and Jacob (2016) reaffirm the central role of the teacher in the actualization of educational goals as well as ensuring the survival of the entire education system. The effectiveness of teachers depends mainly on technological programmes specifically addressed to meet their needs and aspirations. It is against this backdrop that this study was carried out to assess the level of development, provision and empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT, as a technological programme.

Few studies seem to have investigated the socio-economic empowerment of chemistry teachers through Information Communication Technology (ICT) in the North West Zone. In view of the above, this study was conducted to assess the socio-economic empowerment of chemistry teachers in senior secondary schools in the use ICT skills and facilities in the North-West Zone of Nigeria.

Teachers are curriculum implementers and no one can give to students what they have not acquired therefore, the role of the chemistry teacher in using communication technology is critical. Akpan, Etiubon and Udosen (2017) reported that science teachers (chemistry in particular) need to be adequately prepared and empowered in diverse areas in order to develop appropriate skills in teaching and in the process, transfer same to the students. Wendy (2014) in Akpan, Etiubon and Udosen (2017) emphasized the use of regular objective and rigorous assessments to analyze the effectiveness of teachers' skills and preparedness, as these analysis facilitates STEM teachers' performance on learning outcomes particularly in evolving skills for socio-economic empowerment. It is against this background that this study was undertaken to assess the Socio-Economic Empowerment using Information Communication and Technology skills and facilities among secondary school chemistry teachers in North-West, Nigeria.

Objective of the study

The objective of the study is to:

1. Examine the provision and development of ICT facilities for empowering chemistry teachers in secondary schools.
2. Find out if chemistry teachers are empowered/skilled in the use of ICT facilities in secondary schools.

Research Questions

1. How frequent are ICT facilities developed and provided in secondary schools for use by chemistry teachers?
2. How effective are chemistry teachers empowered to use ICT facilities?

Assessment of Socio-Economic... (Anaso, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of chemistry teachers on the development and provision of ICT facilities for use in secondary schools.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings on the empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT facilities for use in secondary schools.

Methodology

The research design adopted the descriptive survey method. The decision to adopt the descriptive survey method was in line with Akuezuilo and Agu (2003) in Anaso (2017), who maintained that it is concerned with gathering information on people, thus the use of this research design.

The study population consisted of seven hundred and twenty (720) chemistry teachers drawn from eighty state government owned secondary schools in Kaduna and Kano States, selected through purposive random sampling technique. The sample size of the study was made up of one hundred and fifty (150) chemistry teachers from the two states (Kaduna and Kano). A total of one hundred and fifty (150) copies of the questionnaire was randomly distributed to the selected participants, however, only one hundred and twenty (120) copies of the questionnaire was dully filled and returned thus, the analysis for this study was based on the returned copies of the questionnaires. The sample therefore comprised of one hundred and twenty (120) chemistry teachers from seven hundred and twenty (720) secondary schools in two states (Kaduna and Kano).

Instrumentation

A structured questionnaire tagged “Chemistry Teachers Socio-Economic Empowerment Scale” (CTSEES) developed by the investigator was used. The questionnaire had two sections. Section 1 sought information on the development and provision of ICT facilities in secondary schools from the participants while Section 2 sought information on empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT facility usage. It has a likert type questionnaire on a 4-point scale, ranging from; Strongly disagree (SD) with (1point), Disagree (D) with (2points), Agreed (A) with 3points, Strongly agreed (SA) with (4points). Section A consists of 8 items while section B consists of 10 items.

Validity and Reliability

Two computer and two chemistry experts from Department of Science Education, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, and face validated the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was 0.79. The teachers responses on the development and provision of ICT for chemistry teaching and empowerment of chemistry teachers through the use of ICT facilities, was scored in means and standard deviation as presented in Tables 1 and 2. Decisions on agreement were based on midpoint of 2.50 and above, while mean score of 2.49 and below implied disagreement for each of the items and variables. Mean was used in answering the research questions and one sample t-test was used in testing the hypotheses.

Presentation of Results

The results of the study are presented in terms of research questions and hypotheses respectively as shown in Tables 1 to 6.

Research Question 1

How frequent are ICT facilities developed and provided in secondary schools for use by chemistry teachers?

Table 1: Responses of chemistry teachers on the development and provision of ICT for chemistry instruction

Items	SD(1)	D(2)	A(3)	SA(4)	Total	Mean
The school has well developed ICT facility for teaching chemistry.	18 (18)	60 (120)	12 (36)	30 (120)	294	2.45
ICT is a new approach for teaching chemistry	12 (12)	40 (80)	28 (84)	38 (152)	328	2.77
ICT facilities are very expensive to procure and maintained	16 (16)	24 (48)	60 (180)	20 (80)	324	2.70
Has ventilated computer room	40 (40)	30 (60)	44 (132)	6 (24)	256	2.13
Has qualified chemistry teachers who are computer literate	30 (30)	50 (100)	30 (90)	10 (40)	260	2.16
Has overhead projector to facilitate learning	52 (52)	34 (68)	24 (72)	10 (80)	232	1.93
Inadequate funding affects the use of ICT services	20 (20)	10 (20)	40 (120)	30 (120)	280	2.33
ICT facilities are adequate to cater for the number of students	30 (30)	70 (140)	10 (30)	10 (40)	240	2.00

TAWR 2.34

Assessment of Socio-Economic... (Anaso, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Analysis from Table 1 shows chemistry teachers' response on the development and provision of ICT facilities for the teaching and learning of chemistry in two states (Kaduna and Kano). Respondents agreed with items number 2, 3, and 7 with mean values of 2.77, 2.70, and 2.33. They disagreed with items number 1, 4, 5, 6, and 8 with mean values of 2.45, 2.13, 2.16, 1.93, and 2.0 respectively. The Total Weighted Average Response of 2.34 falls below 2.5 and this indicated a below average proficiency in integrating ICT instruction.

Research Question 2

How effective are chemistry teachers empowered to use ICT facilities?

Table 2: Responses of chemistry teachers on the empowerment to use ICT for chemistry instruction

Item Statement	SD(1)	D(2)	A(3)	SA(4)	Total	Mean
Chemistry teachers cannot afford ICT tools such as laptops, desktops, projectors, modem etc.	8 (8)	32 (64)	64 (192)	16 (32)	328	2.73
Most chemistry teachers are not knowledgeable in ICT applications	22 (22)	30 (60)	52 (156)	16 (64)	302	2.52
The government and school management show nonchalant attitude in training chemistry teachers to get abreast of ICT.	24 (24)	20 (40)	64 (192)	12 (48)	304	2.53
Most chemistry teachers cannot afford to subscribe to the internet and ICT services	26 (26)	18 (36)	56 (168)	20 (80)	310	2.60
Lack ICT facilities to support active teaching of chemistry at the secondary school level.	18 (18)	30 (60)	64 (192)	8 (32)	302	2.52
Lack of access to research findings on Information Communication Technology.	20 (20)	30 (60)	60 (180)	10 (40)	300	2.50
Lack of funds to schools by the government on ICT applications.	30 (30)	10 (20)	56 (120)	24 (96)	314	2.62
Chemistry teachers participate in workshops related to ICT	60 (60)	30 (60)	22 (66)	8 (32)	218	1.83
Chemistry teachers have much time to prepare and implement ICT in their teaching	22 (22)	41 (82)	51 (153)	6 (24)	281	2.34
Chemistry teachers are encouraged to use ICT facilities.	60 (60)	36 (72)	20 (60)	4 (16)	208	1.73

TAWR 2.31

Analysis from Table 2 shows response on empowerment of chemistry teachers and the use of ICT facilities in secondary schools. Respondents agreed with items number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 with mean values of 2.73, 2.52, 2.53, 2.60, 2.52, 2.50, and 2.62 respectively. They disagreed with items number 8, 9, and 10 with mean 1.83, 2.34, and 1.73 respectively. The Total weighted Average Response of 2.31 is below 2.50. This means that chemistry teachers were not empowered on the use of ICT facilities (use of multimedia) in teaching chemistry.

Testing of Ho1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of chemistry teachers on the development and provision of ICT facilities for use in secondary schools.

One –sample t-test was used. This was based on the fact that it was the main statistical tool that can help to determine significant difference between an observed mean and a constant, thus establishing the significance of the expressed responses of the respondents on the developmental effects of ICT/Multimedia presentation examined in the study. The summary of the result of the test is presented in table 3.

Table 3: One sample statistics on development of ICT in secondary schools understudy

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Development				
ICT	120	17.7541	4.72107	.60447
Constant	120			

The result in Table 3 shows the level of responses on the items on development of ICT in secondary schools. They had a mean score of 17.7541 with a standard deviation of 4.72107 and the standard error was .60447

Assessment of Socio-Economic... (Anaso, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Table 4: One sample t-test on development of ICT in secondary schools understudy

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	t-cal	T critical	P
1Development ICT	120	17.7541	4.72107	.60447.	119	29.371	1.96	0.000

The result in Table 4 revealed that significant differences exist in the level of responses on the items of respondents on development of ICT in secondary schools. Reasons being that the calculated t- value of 29.371 is greater than the t- critical of 1.96. The obtained p value of 0.000 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance set for the study. The hypothesis is therefore rejected since there is significant difference in the mean ratings of chemistry teachers on the development and provision of ICT facilities for use in secondary schools.

Testing of Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings on the empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT facilities for use in secondary schools.

Table 5: One sample t-test Statistics on empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT (multimedia)

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Empowerment	120	42.9836	6.85199	.87731
Constant	120			

The result in Table 5 shows the level of responses on empowerment of teachers on ICT in secondary schools. They had a mean score of 42.9836 with a standard deviation of 6.85199 while the Standard Error Mean was .87731.

Table 6: One sample t-test on empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT (multimedia)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	t	T critical	P
Development of ICT	120	42.9836	16.85199	.87731.	119	48.995	1.96	0.000

The result in Table 6 revealed that the calculated t-value of 48.995 is greater than the critical t- value of 1.96. P-value of 0.000 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance and 119 degree of freedom. Significant differences exist in the level of responses on empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT (multimedia). The null hypothesis is rejected. Thus there is significant difference in the mean ratings on the empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT facilities and their usage in secondary schools.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that the provision and the development of Information Communication Technology facilities for chemistry teachers were viewed as a new approach to teaching. In addition, the schools had qualified chemistry teachers who were computer literate but had no overhead projector for learning. Also, the Information Communication Technology facilities were poorly maintained due to inadequate funding. Chemistry teachers attested to the fact that ICT facilities were neither developed nor adequate to cater for the growing population of students in the two states. It could therefore be inferred from this study that ICT facilities have not contributed significantly to the literacy skills of chemistry teachers in the states under study. The respondents agreed that chemistry teachers could not afford ICT tools such as laptops, desktops, projectors and were not knowledgeable in ICT application. They could not afford to subscribe to the internet and ICT services nor participate in workshops related to ICT. They also indicated that they had no time to prepare and implement ICT in their teachings nor were they encouraged to use ICT facilities. From the findings, the government and school management showed a nonchalant attitude to training of chemistry teachers on ICT and could not fund ICT applications in the various schools. This brings about poor development of a nation and this is in line with the findings of Olomukoro (2016), who maintained that the rate of development of a nation is related to its investment in human and non-human resources. The provision of ICT facilities will equip chemistry teachers with the right type of skills necessary for industrial development and economic growth.

The result from Tables 3 to 6 indicated a significant difference in the mean ratings of the chemistry teachers on CTSEES and showed that chemistry teachers were not empowered to use ICT facilities (use of multimedia presentation) in teaching chemistry at the secondary school level.

The present study is therefore significant, in that it has provided an empirical base for the development and empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT facilities. The human capital theory is relevant to this study because emphasis is laid on the investment of people through educational and technological activities for skills acquisition. This

Assessment of Socio-Economic... (Anaso, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

will ultimately lead to capacity building and empowerment through skill utilisation. The findings from this study tallies with Olomukoro (2012) in her study on influence of literacy education programmes on socio-economic and psychological empowerment of women in Edo and Delta States, Nigeria, indicated that without investing in human capital, skills will not be acquired and there cannot be self-development and improved socio-economic status.

Conclusion

The study has established a strong relationship between ICT and socio-economic empowerment of chemistry teachers in the area investigated. Poor development and provision of ICT facilities are some of the challenges facing its optimal usage. There is need, therefore, to deliberately empower chemistry teachers with skills and knowledge through ICT programmes. Access to ICT programmes could improve the socio-economic empowerment of chemistry teachers in any given nation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Policy-makers should ensure that functional ICT programmes are incorporated into the curriculum to help chemistry teachers actualize their potentials. Skill acquisition is the best option for empowerment of chemistry teachers at the secondary school level.
2. Ministry of Education should promote literacy on ICT facilities by organizing seminars and workshops for chemistry teachers.
3. The state government and school management should be more proactive in funding ICT projects, which involves providing functional standard computers and adequate gadgets
4. Monitoring bodies should monitor the provision, development and usage of ICT facilities (computers, multimedia gadgets, etc.) in schools by daily checks. This is to ensure that the facilities are used by the teachers and students.
5. Chemistry teachers should be encouraged to use ICT facilities in their teaching.
6. The state governments should provide and develop adequate ICT facilities to cater for chemistry teachers and the growing number of students in the states.

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Effect of Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time on Performance in Algebra among Polytechnics Students in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Performance in mathematics is regard to as global problem. This paper investigated the “Effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria. One research question and a corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Two public polytechnics made up the population of the Study consists of all polytechnic students in cross river state during the 2023/2024 academic session with a sample size of 44 students were selected using multi-stage sampling technique. The methodology of the study is pretest and posttest quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The experimental and control groups were exposed to Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time and Lecture Method respectively. The experimental group were taught Algebra using Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time while the control group were taught algebra using Lecture method. Algebraic Performance Test (APT) was designed by the researchers for data collection. The reliability coefficient of Algebraic Performance Test (APT) was determined to be 0.85. The data collected were analyzed using Mean scores, Standard deviation and t-test at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. The findings revealed that there is significant difference between performance of students taught algebra using Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time and those exposed to conventional lecture teaching method. Better performance was recorded on student that were taught algebraic concepts using lecture-enriched wait-time compared to their counterpart that were taught using lecture method. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that lecture-enriched wait-time should be used to teach mathematics at national diploma level.

Keyword: Lecture-enriched wait-time, algebra, performance

Introduction

Mathematics is one of the school subjects with wide applications which can not be separated from our day to day activities. It considered as the universal language throughout the world. It techniques includes counting, arithmetic, mensuration, geometry, trigonometry, computations and algebra, with the ability to think about situations related to a given quantity (Cawley *et al*, 1998). Mathematics is a fundamental branch of Science that represents the study of basic concepts of Numbers, Space and Quantity as well as application of these concepts in the field of Physics and Engineering (Ale, 2006).

Poor performance in the subject area becomes of great concern to our society, educators and government at large. Nneji (2013), described performance as the gain in knowledge of students as a result of taking part in learning activity or programme. For effective learning to be efficiently taken, we need the right approaches and methods. There are so many devices for effective teaching and an effective technique can ensure effective learning. It is being felt that there should be new techniques of teaching and learning (Iqbal, 2004). The search of teaching and learning devices for effective performance has lead to the identification of wait-time (Lee, 2000).

Any behavior, practice or techniques that will enable students develop thinking skills will help them to acquire technology concepts, which will lead to better achievement. Hurd in UNESCO (1995) pointed out that the methodology for teaching must enable students to think and ask questions during classroom lesson. One way of developing students' thinking skill is to ask questions in the classroom to facilitate discussion and to get the students to think (Adsit, 2002).

Effect of Lecture-Enriched... (Mukhtar et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

There is therefore a good link between teaching methods and questioning. The importance of question cannot be over emphasised, question can be used by teachers in the classrooms to determine whether or not body of knowledge has been impacted and to determine how much has been learned. It can be used for evaluation of method of teaching and for students placement.

According to Baba (2022) wait-time is when a teacher waits after a question is asked before calling on a student to rephrase a question or supply the answer. Wait-time is the amount of time a teacher allows, after asking a question, before getting response from students (wait-time I). It is also a period of uninterrupted silence allowed by the teacher after receiving a student's response and before he/she comments or asks another question (wait-time II). Research has shown that for both wait-time I and II, teachers typically wait for an average of one second or less (Kissock and Iyortsuun, 1982; Ouyang, 2000; Cotton, 2001 and Camp, 2002). Increasing wait-time to three seconds or more has been found to increase students' achievement and interest (Stahl as cited in Owodunni, 2013, Rowe as cited in Lee, 2000 and Cotton, 2001). Opataye (2020), study the effectiveness of classroom questioning wait – time on senior secondary school students' academic performance and reflective thinking in chemistry, it was shown that, chemistry students that were given questioning wait - time performed better and with higher reflective thinking in chemistry.

Effective questioning is an instrument of motivation to raise the interest of students in what is being learnt (Eze, 2008). Raising students' interest helps them to learn better and most likely retain what is learnt for a longer period and subsequently, achievement would be enhanced. Owodunni (2013), investigate the comparative effects of long wait - time and shifting interaction questioning techniques on basic electricity students academic achievement in technical colleges. It was showed that shifting interaction questioning technique is more effective in enhancing students' achievement in basic electricity. There are different types of learners including fast learners, average learners, and slow learners (Korikana, 2020). This learning difficulty may arise from poor memory, unawareness about the importance of education and lack of fundamental knowledge and psychological factors

Dalhatu, *et al* (2023), investigate the effect of extended wait-time on low achievers performance and retention in ecology among secondary school Biology students in Zaria educational zone, it was shown that low achievers that were taught ecology using extended wait-time had better performance compared those that were taught using conventional lecture method. The fact that students continue to fail algebra in tertiary institutions (polytechnics) in large number shows that there is a need for more empirical studies in order to improve the situation. Thus, this research, investigate effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

As part of the National Board for Technical Education Curriculum, algebra is a core course for all sciences, engineering and environmental technology. Algebra as one of the studied areas that deals with the representation of problems or situations in the form of mathematical expressions. All the branches of mathematics needs algebra. The study of algebra starts with solving of equations such as polynomials equations.

Algebra and elementary trigonometry is almost a general course to all students of sciences, engineering technology, environmental technology and even in some management courses. Despite its importance, there is high level poor performance in subject area. This paper, study the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Performance in mathematics has been a central issue to Mathematics educators (Okeagu, 2013). This poor performance has continued at successive years especially in our schools. Despite the importance of mathematics in science and technology, the issue of poor performance at the end of semester examination becomes a major concern to our academics institutions, which may be as a result of teaching methodology by mathematics teachers/Lecturers. This trend defiles the effort made by Federal Government of Nigeria by making the subject compulsory at all stages of learning (Iliyasu, 2016). In our march toward scientific and technological advancement we need nothing short of good performance in mathematics. Unfortunately, performance of student in mathematics at the end of semester examination has not improved in the past decade. There is dire need for solution to the problem of poor performance in mathematics especially algebra, in order for Nigeria to join the community of developed nations. Iji (2005) has stated that teaching approaches and strategy used in the classrooms by teachers are the root course of this undesirable poor performance in mathematics. Many researchers have carried out investigations on how to remedy the situation. Dalhatu, *et al* (2023), investigate the effect of extended wait-time on low achievers performance and retention in ecology among secondary school Biology students in Zaria educational zone, it was shown that low achievers that were taught ecology using extended wait-time had better performance compared those that were taught using conventional lecture method. The fact that students continue to fail algebra in tertiary institutions (polytechnics) in large number shows that there is a need for more empirical studies in order to improve the situation. Thus, this paper, investigate the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To determine the effect of Lecture-Enriched wait-time on academic performance in algebra among polytechnics students.

Effect of Lecture-Enriched... (Mukhtar et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Research Questions

1. What are the differences in the mean academic performance scores students taught algebraic concept using lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with lecture method?

Hypotheses:

The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught algebraic concepts using lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre- test, post-test and post posttest non-equivalent control group design. The essence of pre-test was to determine the academic equivalence of the two groups before the treatment while post-posttest was to determine the performance of the student after the treatment.

Pre-test was administered to both sampled polytechnics so as to determine their academic equivalence. The records were kept, then the control group were taught algebra using conventional method of teaching while the experimental group were taught using algebra using Lecture – Enriched Wait - time for eight (8) weeks. Then, post-test was administered to both the control and the experimental groups. The periods for the teaching of each group is two hours per group. This was done by the aid of research assistants who were given a guide on how to handle the classes as well as the wait-time devices in accordance with the Lecture - Enriched wait –time.

The population of the study comprised the two public polytechnics in Cross River State of Nigeria with a total number of 44 National Diploma I students offering algebra at the time that this data was collected.

The instrument for this study is Algebraic Performance Test (APT). The reliability coefficient of Algebraic Performance Test (APT) was determined to be 0.85. For the purpose of generating and analyzing data, APT comprises ten (10) essay test questions were developed for the study, which allowed the students to write their understanding on the algebraic concepts.

Result

The result of the analysis was used to answer the research question using descriptive statistics while inferential statistics was used to test the null hypothesis at alpha $\alpha = 0.05$ level significance.

Research Question 1

What are the differences in the mean academic performance scores students taught algebraic concept using lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with lecture method?

This question was answered by determining the mean score between the two groups, using descriptive statistics and the results is as presented in table 1

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation of students of experimental and control groups

Group	N	Pretest Mean	SD	Posttest Mean	SD
Experimental	16	13.9	2.8	27	4.3
Control	28	12.6	2.2	19	3.2
Mean difference		1.3		8	
Total	44				

Table 1 shows that the students that were taught with lecture-enriched wait-time method has the highest mean scores of 27 while those taught with traditional lecture method has the minimum mean scores of 19. This shows that the students in the experimental group had some level of improvement as a result of exposure to lecture-enriched wait-time. The standard deviation is an indicative value of wide variability between the scores of the group.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught algebraic concepts with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method.

To test this hypothesis, the pretest and the posttest of each experimental and control groups are analyzed.

Effect of Lecture-Enriched... (Mukhtar et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Table 2: Wilcoxon sign rank test of mean performance scores of students taught Algebra with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional lecture method

Total number of students (N)	Mean T	Var.	t-calculated	t-critical
44	5365.5 1788.5	511.87	-6.99	1.96

Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 2 shows that the absolute value of t- calculated (6.99) is greater than t- critical (1.96) then we reject H_{01} . thus, it means that there is significant difference between lower achievers taught algebraic concepts with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method.

Discussion of Findings

The research work investigated the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria. One hypothesis was stated and tested based on lecture – enriched wait – time and Algebra Performance Test (APT) was developed and administered to the sampled groups consisting of 44 students. The collected from the sampled population was analyze using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Analysis of the data collected are presented in table 1 and 2 in accordance with the stated hypothesis. The results of the analyses related to the hypothesis one indicated that, a significant difference exists in the mean performance scores of students taught algebraic concepts with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method. This significant difference found in the performance of students taught algebra was in favor of the experimental group. This is inline with the study of Dalhatu, *et al* (2023) which shown that low achievers that were taught ecology using extended wait-time had better performance compared those that were taught using conventional lecture method.

Conclusion

The paper study the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria. It was shown that better performance was recorded on student that were taught algebraic concepts using lecture-enriched wait-time compared to their counterpart that were taught using lecture method.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The use of lecture-enriched wait-time should be encouraged among lecturers teaching algebra more especially at ND level.
2. Government agencies such as Federal and State Ministry of Education, NBTE and other stakeholders in educational sector should organize workshop on lecture-enriched wait-time to all lecturers taking lower level students.

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Impacts of Blended Strategy on Performance and Retention in Social Studies among Secondary School Students in Ika South Local Government Area, Delta State

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Abstract

This research explored the Impacts of Blended Strategy on Performance and Retention in Social Studies among Secondary School Students in Ika South Local Government, Delta State. Four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. Pre-test, post-test, control group, quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised of all upper basic class two (JSSII) Social Studies students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. A sample size of 120 Social Studies students were purposively selected using an intact class. The Social Studies Performance Test (SSPT), a verified researcher-made test with 45 multiple-choice questions about the subject of "culture and social values in UBEL Schools 2 (JSS2), was employed for data collection. The reliability coefficient (r) of 0.70 was obtained using Kuder-Richardson formula 20. The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, and the hypotheses tested at the 0.05 alpha level using analysis of covariance. The study revealed among others that there was significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method. The study recommended that to enhance student performance and retention in Social Studies, schools should equip classrooms with necessary technology and integrate blended learning into the curriculum. Additionally, regular training should be provided for teachers to effectively implement and promote blended learning across both urban and rural settings.

Keyword: Social Studies, Blended Learning, Students' Performance, Retention, location

Introduction

Blended learning, which integrates traditional classroom methods with digital tools, has become a transformative approach in modern education. It offers students the opportunity to access learning materials both in-person and online, combining the structure of face-to-face instruction with the flexibility of digital resources. This dual approach fosters independent learning and critical engagement, giving students more control over their educational experience. In the context of Social Studies, where critical thinking, analysis of social issues, and understanding societal dynamics are essential, blended learning can significantly enhance student performance and retention by providing diverse learning modalities that cater to different learning styles (Ukor, 2023).

Blended learning allows Social Studies teachers to present content in dynamic and interactive ways. For instance, digital tools like online simulations, multimedia resources, and collaborative platforms enable students to explore real-world societal issues, promoting deeper engagement with complex topics. As highlighted by AbdulRaheem, Muraina and Esther (2024), the use of technology in blended learning environments helps students better understand abstract social concepts by offering a more interactive, personalized learning experience. This approach not only reinforces traditional classroom learning but also provides opportunities for students to apply knowledge through practical, real-life simulations and activities. Despite the many benefits of blended learning, its effectiveness is not evenly distributed among all students. A significant factor influencing its success is geographical location, which can greatly affect students' access to the necessary technological resources. Wang, Omar, Zakaria and Zulkifli (2024) noted that urban students often have better access to stable internet connections, digital devices, and educational technology, allowing them to take full advantage of blended learning environments. In contrast, students in rural or remote areas may face challenges such as poor internet connectivity, limited access to digital devices, and insufficient technical support (Henríquez & Hilliger, 2024). As a result, students in rural locations may struggle to fully engage with the online components of blended learning, potentially widening the performance gap between urban and rural students. Cunningham (2022) emphasized that rural students' performance in blended learning is often negatively impacted by these barriers, making it difficult for them to keep up with their urban peers. Alvarez (2020) in his study revealed that students perceived blended learning as difficult to execute in

Impacts of Blended... (Onyekpe & Eboh, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

classroom environment due to the absence of institutional policies on the use of blended learning, lack of ICT training/knowledge (technophobia), poor confidence to engage in blended learning approach, and limited access to computer laboratories. Hence, these were perceived to be hindrances in the implementation of blended learning.

Studies have consistently shown that students in blended learning environments perform better academically than those in traditional classrooms. According to a study by Ukor (2023), students who participated in blended learning outperformed their peers in Social Studies assessments, particularly in tasks requiring critical thinking and problem-solving. The flexibility of blended learning allows students to review materials at their own pace and revisit complex topics, leading to improved comprehension and retention of information. Dania (2022) further supported this finding, noting that the integration of digital tools in Social Studies enhances student motivation and engagement, particularly in topics involving societal analysis and critical thinking.

The issue of retention, or the ability of students to persist and complete their studies, is another critical factor in evaluating the success of blended learning. Studies suggest that blended learning environments which tend to offer greater flexibility and a more engaging learning experience, could improve student retention rates. According to Shikha and Baliya (2023) students in blended learning programme are more likely to persist in their studies because they can tailor their learning experiences to fit their personal schedules and learning preferences. In Social Studies, this flexibility is particularly valuable, as it would allow students to explore complex societal issues in greater depth through independent research and digital collaboration.

However, location may also affect retention rates. Students in rural areas, who may already face socio-economic challenges, are often further disadvantaged by the lack of reliable internet access and digital resources. This digital divide could lead to frustration, disengagement, and ultimately, lower retention rates among rural students (Wang et al., 2024). The moderating role of location in blended learning effectiveness underscores the importance of digital equity. Without access to reliable internet, necessary devices, and technical support, students in rural areas are more likely to underperform or drop out (Bishop et.al, 2022). To address this, teachers and policymakers must work to bridge the digital divide by investing in digital infrastructure, providing technological resources to underserved areas, and offering additional support to students who face these challenges. Ensuring equitable access to blended learning experiences requires bridging the digital divide between urban and rural locations (Chidi-Onwuta et.al, 2022).

In Social Studies education, where understanding societal issues and critical engagement are key, it is vital to ensure that all students have equal opportunities to succeed in blended learning environments. This requires not only improving access to digital resources but also developing strategies to support students in rural and remote areas who may face additional challenges. By addressing geographical disparities and ensuring equitable access to digital tools and resources, teachers can help all students succeed in blended learning environments, ultimately improving both performance and retention in Social Studies education.

Despite the proven benefits of blended learning in enhancing student engagement, performance, and retention, its effectiveness in Social Studies education remains uneven, especially when factoring in geographic disparities. While urban students often have reliable access to digital tools and resources, rural students frequently face obstacles such as inadequate internet connectivity, limited access to digital devices, and minimal technical support. These disparities contribute to a significant gap in academic performance and retention between urban and rural students, highlighting the "digital divide" that impacts equitable access to educational opportunities. In Ika South Local Government, Delta State, where Social Studies is fundamental in developing critical thinking and understanding of societal issues, the limitations faced by rural students undermine the potential of blended learning to foster these essential skills. The challenges faced by these students often lead to disengagement and hindered academic growth, ultimately widening the performance gap between them and their urban counterparts. Addressing this digital divide is essential to ensure that all students, regardless of location, can benefit equally from blended learning in Social Studies. This study aims to explore the impact of blended learning on student performance and retention, with a particular focus on how geographical location moderates its effectiveness, to better inform strategies that can bridge this digital gap in educational outcomes.

Objectives of the study

1. Determine the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using blended strategy and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State.
2. Determine the mean performance scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State.
3. Determine the mean retention scores of students taught Social Studies using blended strategy and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State.
4. Determine the mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using blended strategy and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State.

Impacts of Blended... (Onyekpe & Eboh, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?
2. What is the mean performance scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?
3. What is the mean retention scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?
4. What is the mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance for this study.

1. There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State
2. There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State
3. There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State
4. There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State

Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental, non-equivalent pre-test, post-test control group design to assess the performance and retention of Social Studies students using blended learning. The research population comprised all upper basic education students in public schools in Ika South Local Government Area. A sample of 120 Social Studies students from three intact, non-equivalent classes across two upper basic education schools was purposively selected and assigned to two experimental groups and one control group. The Social Studies Performance Test (SSPT), a validated researcher-designed instrument with 45 multiple-choice questions covering the topic of culture and social values for JSS2 Social Studies, was used for data collection. The reliability of the SSPT was determined using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20, yielding a reliability coefficient (r) of 0.70. The experimental groups were taught using blended learning models: the Social Studies flex blended model and the Social Studies flipped model. The control group, on the other hand, received instruction via the conventional teaching method. The SSPT was administered as both a pre-test and post-test to all groups, with a retention test conducted three weeks after the post-test. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to address the research questions, while hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at a significance level of 0.05.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation scores of students' performance taught Social Studies using social studies flex and flipped strategies and conventional method.

Teaching Strategies	N	Pre-test		Pre-test		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
SS flex blended model	40	40.1000	9.95968	78.7500	11.03282	50.65
SS flipped model	40	40.4000	9.39853	75.5500	10.05233	49.15
Conventional Method	40	35.4300	7.26199	54.6500	9.01069	30.20

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows that the mean score for the flex model was 50.65, the mean score for the flipped model was 49.15, and the mean score for the conventional method was 30.20. The flipped and flex blended learning models of blended strategy seem to perform better than the conventional approach, in contrast. This merely indicates that students who were taught Social Studies using the flex and flipped models outperformed those who were taught using the conventional method.

Impacts of Blended... (Onyekpe & Eboh, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259511>

Research Question 2

What is the mean performance scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation scores of Social Studies students’ performance taught social studies using Social Studies flex blended model, Social Studies flipped model and conventional method based on location.

Teaching Strategies	Location	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
SS Flex model	Urban	25	31.0769	8.92059	70.6923	6.96491	59.6154
	Rural	15	28.2857	7.49921	62.2857	6.86132	35.0000
SS Flipped model	Urban	15	39.6364	7.24255	77.0000	6.34035	50.3636
	Rural	25	31.3222	10.79352	68.3322	9.39230	38.0000
Conventional Method	Urban	25	38.0000	9.29383	59.0000	10.98571	46.0000
	Rural	15	26.5000	8.68022	55.2150	8.39049	28.6142

Source: Author’s Survey, 2024

Table 2 shows that urban students had a mean gain of 59.6154, rural students 35.000 score for instruction under the flex model, urban students had a mean of 50.3636, and rural students 38.0000 for the flipped model, but urban and rural students scored 46.0000 and 28.6142, respectively, for the conventional method. The results showed that both urban and rural students did better with flex and flipped models than with the traditional method. As a result, students in urban and rural locations taught Social Studies utilizing flex and flipped models performed better than urban and rural students taught using the conventional method.

Research Question 3:

What is the mean retention scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of Social Studies students’ retention scores taught Social Studies using Social Studies flex model, Social Studies flipped model and conventional method.

Teaching Strategies	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
SS flex blended model	40	78.8000	8.35542	78.2000	8.03282	1.53
SS flipped model	40	78.9000	6.98645	77.3500	6.32966	0.87
Conventional Method	40	61.5000	5.69521	62.0000	5.27021	0.60

Source: Author’s Survey, 2024

The table 3 above shows that students taught Social Studies using flex model have mean score of 1.53, flipped model 0.87 and conventional method 0.60 respectively. This implies that students taught Social Studies using the two (2) blended learning models had higher retention compared to the conventional method. Comparatively, flex and flipped models of teaching appears to have great effect on students’ retention in Social Studies.

Research Questions 4

What is the mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State?

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation scores of urban and rural Social Studies students’ retention scores taught Social Studies using Social Studies flex blended strategy, Social Studies flipped strategy and conventional method.

Teaching Strategies	Location	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
SS Flex model	Rural	20	75.3750	6.52758	73.6250	6.75525	1.3300
	Urban	20	75.9167	7.93698	74.5833	5.96048	1.6764
SS Flipped model	Rural	20	72.6000	8.31597	72.0000	8.21511	0.5000
	Urban	20	73.2000	9.81967	74.7000	9.17543	0.5900
Conventional Method	Urban	20	62.4132	8.79125	60.8333	9.53212	0.4766
	Rural	20	61.2300	9.16418	61.3750	9.64761	0.3630

Source: Author’s Survey, 2024

The table 4 reveals that rural students taught with flex model had a mean retention score of 1.3300, urban students taught with flex model scored 1.6764 while rural students taught with flipped model obtained a score of 0.5000 and urban students taught with flipped model scored 0.5900 but the mean retention scores for both urban and rural students under the conventional method are 0.4766 and 0.3630 respectively. The result indicated that urban and rural students taught using

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flex and flipped models had higher retention in Social Studies compared to their counterparts taught with the conventional method.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State

Table 5: Result of Analysis of Covariance of Social Studies students' performance scores taught Social Studies with social studies flex blended model, Social studies flipped model and conventional method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	3678.441a	3	882.812	11.802	.000
Intercept	22463.465	1	23463.465	371.782	.000
Pretest	88.708	1	89.708	1.074	.405
Methods	2677.188	2	1438.594	17.195	.000
Error	5628.542	60	85.653		
Total	271181.000	56			
Corrected Total	8306.983	61			

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

Table 5 shows that the flex model, flipped model, and conventional method have a significant difference in students' performance. The exact probability of 0.000 connected with the effect as a result of the teaching methods is less than 0.05, indicating significance. As a result, the hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there was a significant difference in teaching approach on the performance of Social Studies students. The results revealed a substantial difference in teaching strategies (flex model, flipped model, and conventional approach) on students' academic achievement in Social Studies.

There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method Ika South Local Government, Delta State

Hypothesis 2:

Table 6: Result of Analysis of Covariance of Social Studies students' performance scores taught Social Studies with Social Studies flex blended strategy, Social Studies flipped strategy and conventional method based on location.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1453.967a	2	686.986	6.983	.003
Intercept	30558.871	1	30558.871	197.860	.000
Pre-test	.316	1	.316	.002	.986
Location	1452.816	1	1372.725	12.957	.001
Error	5953.017	57	109.435		
Total	281161.000	60			
Corrected Total	7606.992	59			

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

The table 6 shows significant difference between teaching methods and location on students' performance in Social Studies. Results on the table show that the calculated F- value of 12.957 was significant at 0.001 which is less than 0.05 and therefore is significant at 0.05 level of probability. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected meaning there was significant difference between teaching methods and location on students' performance in Social Studies. Similarly, the result revealed that there is a significant difference in the mean scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex model, flipped model and conventional method.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies and those exposed to conventional method in Ika South Local Government, Delta State

Table 7: Result of Analysis of Covariance of methods on students' retention score in Social Studies.

Dependent Variable: Retention score

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	3201.189a	3	1043.625	19.199	.000
Intercept	15193.841	1	15193.841	257.181	.000
Pre-test	879.552	1	879.552	15.460	.000
Methods	2117.300	2	1068.200	20.420	.000
Error	3016.997	56	63.672		
Total	294961.000	60			
Corrected Total	6218.183	59			

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

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The table 7 shows the significant difference between teaching methods on students' retention in Social Studies. Results on the table revealed that the calculated F-value of 20.420 was significant at 0.000 which is less than 0.05 and therefore is significant at 0.05 level of probability. Consequently, the hypothesis is rejected hence, there was difference between teaching methods on students' retention in Social Studies. Therefore, the result indicated that there is a significant difference in the mean retention score of students taught Social Studies using flex model, flipped model and conventional method.

Hypothesis 4:

There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped blended strategies in Ika South Local Government, Delta State

Table 8: ANCOVA analysis of urban and rural Social Studies students who were taught Social Studies with Social Studies flex blended model, Social Studies flipped model and conventional method based on retention.

Dependent Variable: Retention score

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1089.802a	2	559.952	6.297	.005
Intercept	1870.167	1	10870.165	117.543	.000
Pretest 1	999.487	1	579.487	115.127	.003
Location	119.916	1	114.917	1.105	.004
Error	4318.278	58	67.060		
Total	18498.000	59			
Corrected Total	4417.174	62			

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

In the table 8, it was indicated that location is significant among the groups (flex blended model, flipped model and conventional method). The result showed that the F-value of 1.105 obtained a significance of .004 which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected hence, there is a significant difference between the mean retention scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies with flex model, flipped model and conventional methods in Social Studies.

Discussion of Findings

Results in table 1 and 5 revealed that there is difference between the mean performance scores of students taught Social Studies using the flex model, flipped model and conventional method. Comparatively, flex and flipped models appears to have a great effect on students' performance in Social Studies. This implies that students taught with flex and flipped models performed better than those taught using conventional method. This finding aligns with that of Ukor (2023) who asserted that students are more motivated to learn and performed better than those taught with conventional method. In the same vein, the finding of Barış Çiftçi (2020) revealed that a greater percentage of students taught using blended instructional strategy got excellent performance than the conventional classroom teaching style.

The results in table 2 and 6 indicated that there was significant difference in the performance scores of urban and rural students taught Social Studies using flex model, flipped model and conventional method. The results showed that flex and flipped models for urban and rural students performed better than the conventional method. Wang et al (2024) opined that students taught in a blended learning environment in urban and rural communities performed far better than their counterparts taught using conventional approach. This finding was supported by Ashraf, Tsegay and Meijia (2021) who averred that blended strategy enables the teacher manage the blended learning classroom setting with confidence by addressing the intersection of pedagogy, technology, and subject knowledge.

The result in table 3 and 7 revealed that students taught Social Studies using flex and flipped models had greater retention compared to those taught under the conventional method. Therefore, since ($p < 0.05$), there is a significant difference in the mean retention score of students taught Social Studies using flex model, flipped model and conventional method. This finding agrees with the views of Ukor (2023) who stated that retention level was higher for blended learning strategy compared to the conventional classroom teaching. Consequently, the result shows that the experimental subjects significantly improved in their post-test scores after treatment.

The result in table 4 and 8 indicated that urban and rural students taught using flex and flipped models had higher retention in Social Studies compared to their counterparts taught with the conventional method. In same vein, the hypothesis showed that location is significant among the groups (flex blended model, flipped model and conventional method). This finding agrees with that of Boateng. (2024) who asserted that through blended approach students retained subject content better compared to the traditional method. AbdulRaheem, Muraina and Esther-Uche (2024) contended that students learn and gain high comprehension in a blended learning environment more than in a traditional setting due to the fact that it offers the chance to develop engaging and dynamic learning opportunities.

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Conclusion

The successful implementation of blended learning strategies such as the flex and flipped models would improve students' performance and retention in social studies. Blended learning enables students to explore, integrate knowledge, and facilitate collaborative learning, resulting in superior learning results. In comparison to the traditional method, the blended learning strategy has proven to be beneficial in teaching and learning, as well as boosting students' performance and retention in Social Studies in both urban and rural settings.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations of the study:

1. Social Studies teachers should actively promote and implement blended learning to enhance students' academic performance and retention in upper basic education.
2. Schools should be equipped with essential technology, including computer systems and internet access, to facilitate effective blended learning.
3. Both urban and rural students should be encouraged to engage with blended learning methods in social studies to bridge educational gaps and improve access.
4. Blended learning should be formally integrated into the social studies curriculum to standardize its use and benefits.
5. Schools and educational bodies should organize regular in-service training, workshops, and seminars for teachers to enhance their skills and knowledge in using blended learning effectively.

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Comparative Relationship between Parental Socio-Economic-Status and Performance among Secondary School Students in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the influence of parental socio-economic status (income, education, occupation, involvement and cultural beliefs) on students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Osun State. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The target population covered parents and students in public senior secondary schools in the state. Simple random sampling technique was adopted for parents while multi-stage random technique was adopted for students from selected public senior secondary schools in Osun State. The total number of respondents for this study was 3,350 respondents, constituting 1,675 students and 1,675 parents. However, only 1,560 returned their instruments. The instruments used in the study were: Parental Socio-economic Status Questionnaire (PSSQ) and Academic Achievement Test (AAT) deduced from past SS III students' WAEC questions on English Language and Mathematics was administered to students who responded to (PSSQ). Results revealed a poor performance from the attainment test while cultural factors appeared to be the only predictor of academic success; income, occupation, parental involvement, academic status all had no significant relationship with students' academic performance. The reliability figures for the variables were; income status: 0.75, educational status: 0.81, Occupational status: 0.71, level of involvement: 0.70, cultural beliefs: 0.71, attainment scores: 0.75. Simple percentage, mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while regression was used for the hypothesis. Based on the findings, it was recommended that, the Governments and policymakers should ensure that schools in Osun State are adequately equipped with teaching materials. Also, there is need for an improvement in infrastructure and provision of regular professional development for teachers to support effective learning.

Keywords: Parental Socio-Economic, Students, Academic Performance.

Introduction

Poor academic performance in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in some states in Nigeria has become a matter of concern to everyone. According to Oni et al., (2016) the quality of any educational system is mostly assessed by the performance of the system's products. There is no refuting in the fact that parents are the primary persons in raising children in any society that is why the family is regarded as the primary agent of socialization. In the same vain, Ohanyelu (2022) identified the components that must come into play in the educational process which include; education, income, occupation, level of involvement and culture. Previous researches revealed that for a successful educational process to be realized, these components must be harmonized. Whatsoever affect the developmental environment of students would possibly affect their education or disposition to it. The variables that contribute effectively to quality of academic performance are found within and outside the school. Parental status is one of such variables found outside the school as posited by Eliasson et al (2020) that students with poor socio-economic background are predisposed to dearth of resources. The researcher also recognised the possibility for children from low background to compete well with their counterparts from high socio-economic background under the same academic environment.

Despite the Federal Ministry of Education and State Government's effort in funding public schools, there still exists poor academic performance among students in Osun State. This means that majority of students in this state do not attain the minimum qualification for tertiary admission which is five Credits and above including English Language and General Mathematics. According to the Federal Ministry of Education, the percentage pass rate for English and Mathematics in Osun state between 2020 and 2024 averaged 41% (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). This dismal academic performance has raised

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concerns for parents and other educational stakeholders considering the financial and material investment made to provide education to learners. However, enough research has not been conducted on the influence of parents’ education, occupation, income, involvement and cultural belief on students’ academic performance. Against this backdrop, this study seeks to holistically examine the influence of parental socio-economic status on students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Osun State.

This research draws heavily from Bourdieu’s theory of Cultural Capital. According to Bourdieu’s Cultural Capital Theory, children from higher socioeconomic backgrounds gain from cultural resources that are consistent with the standards and ideals of the educational system. These assets improve their academic success and include language skills, knowledge of academic expectations, and access to extracurricular learning activities. This is in tandem with Guttormsen and Moore (2023) who drew on Bourdieu’s epistemic reflexivity, highlighting the ways in which cultural capital affects the creation of knowledge and the process of making decisions

Conceptual Framework
Socio-economic factors

Self-constructed by researcher, adapted from Meng, Q., & Zhang, Q. (2023)

Parental Income and Students’ Academic Performance

A person’s education is closely linked to his/her life choices, income therefore, it is important to have a clear understanding of what benefits or hinders one’s educational attainment. Education is a fundamental human right, the key to sustainable development, a crucial tool for effective participation in societies and it enhances peace and stability among countries. Eliasson et al (2022) posited that students from families with high income perform better than those from low income families in the United States of America. The author posited that the impact of the Parents’ income can be shown in the early timing of the students’ learning.

Parental Level of Education and Students’ Academic Performance

Studies have indicated that parents with higher educational status could trigger the intellectual potential of their children which leads them to perform better in school and in return strive for further education (Rana et al., 2015). Duckworth et al., (2019), Hsieh (2022), Arifin et., et (2023) and Kim et al. (2023) asserted that children of more educated parents are more likely to be enrolled and more likely to progress further through school, conversely, children of parents with lower educational attainment tend to perform poorly because of reduced parental involvement in their children’s learning. Li et al., (2022) and Bhatia et al., 2023 established a connection between high parental confidence and healthy parent-child relationship which positively translates to better academic performance of their children. Educated parents are more likely to provide an atmosphere that is conducive for learning and help their children succeed academically (Tipton, 2018, Eyinade & Akharume, 2020, Covas & Veiga, 2021, Su et al., 2022, Umoru & Aboritoli, 2021).

Parental Occupation and Student’s Academic Performance

The home has a significant influence on the psychological, emotional, social and economic state of the students. Naite, (2021) averred that children of bankers, doctors, and teachers probably may have a different upbringing from those children of most farmland and domestic workers. According to Mudassir and Abubakar (2015), Gutfleisch &Kogan, (2022) and Colicol&Sali-Latif (2023) the profession and socioeconomic status of parents affect the schools that a child chooses, which in turn affects academic performance and academic success. Rahaman (2023) averred that the careers and aspirations of children can also be influenced by the jobs that their parents hold. According to Chukwuorji and Nwonyi (2015), Hsieh and Simpkins (2022), Cheng & Lai (2023) and Efstratopoulou et al., (2023), anxiety levels among secondary school students during test were influenced by the jobs held by their parents.

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Parent's Level of Involvement and Students' Academic Performance

Hsieh, (2023) reveals the relationship between parental participation and student engagement, showing how involvement at home and in school improves children's emotional, cognitive, and behavioural engagement—all of which are critical for success in school. Donkor (2023) revealed that the association between children's academic success and their socioeconomic status is mediated by parental support, which mitigates the adverse effects of low socioeconomic status on academic performance. According to Georgiou (2023) and Yulianti et al., (2023) creating a home atmosphere that supports academic endeavour and establishing the importance of education are other aspects of parental participation. Likewise, Chavez et al., (2023) averred that giving emotional and psychological support to children is another aspect of parental support that may have a big impact on their academic achievement.

Cultural Beliefs and Students' Academic Performance

Certain cultures place a great emphasis on education, and parents actively encourage their children to achieve academic success by establishing high standards for them, through investment of time, resources and efforts (Kainuwa et al., 2018). Kristofferson (2023) however found out a contrary stance in which some cultural practices frown at formal education which by extension reduces the zeal for study. In like manner, Kainuwa et al., (2018) established a connection between religious and cultural beliefs and students' drop-out rate. He found out that children from families who placed credence on education regardless of cultural beliefs enjoy continued education, than the ones who placed little or no credence to education. Similarly, the educational expectations of children of migrants in China and discovered that parental beliefs controlled the children's access to family resources, which in turn had a major impact on their academic ambitions.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives designed to guide the study.

1. To examine the level of students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Osun State.
2. To ascertain the level of parental education of public secondary school students in Osun State
3. To ascertain the nature of parental occupation of public secondary school students in Osun State
4. To determine the level of parental income of public secondary school students in Osun State
5. To ascertain the level of parental involvement of public secondary school students in Osun State

Research Questions

The research questions developed for the purpose of the study include:

1. What is the level of students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Osun State?
2. What is the level of parental education of public secondary school students in Osun State?
3. What is the nature of parental occupation of public secondary school students in Osun State?
4. What is the level of parental income of public secondary school students in Osun State?
5. What is the level of parental involvement of public secondary school students in Osun State?

Research hypothesis

The hypothesis developed and test is stated below:

1. There is a significant relative relationship between socio-economic factors and the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Osun State.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design, the total number of respondents for this study is three thousand, three hundred and fifty (3,350) from a total of thirty-three thousand, four-hundred and ninety respondents. Multistage sampling technique was used to select the respondents for this study, proportionate to size sampling technique was used to select 10% of SS III students. The data collected in this study was coded and tested for completeness and then analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were analysed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation while hypothesis was tested using regression analysis. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

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Results

Table 1: The level of students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Osun state

Subject	49% and below	Percentage (%)	50% and above	and Percentage (%)	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
Mathematics	905	58%	655	42%	47.16	16.27	Low performance
English	881	56%	679	44%	47.36	18.26	Low performance

Source: Field 2024

Note: N=1560

Table 1 shows that academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Osun, in English and Mathematics is generally low. With a 42% credit pass rate in Mathematics and 44% credit pass rate in English, deductions can be made that students' performance in these key subjects leaves much to be desired. Furthermore, results from the table reveal a mean score of 47.16, which is lower than the credit pass mark of 50, therefore, it can be concluded that the general performance in Mathematics is low. Similarly, standard deviation of 16.27 in Mathematics shows that, out of 100 marks allocated, 68% of students scored between 31 and 63 which is indicative of the fact that many students struggled with the test. In the same vein, results of findings from English language revealed the mean score of 47.36- this is lower than the credit pass mark of 50, hence, conclusions can be drawn that there is an overall poor performance. Also, standard deviation of 18.26 in English is a pointer to the fact that, out of 100 marks allocated, 68% of students scored between 29 and 66 which is indicative of the fact that many students struggled with the test.

Table 2: The level of parental education of public secondary school students in Osun State

Highest Qualification	Fathers		Mothers	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Masters Degree	346	22.2%	443	28.4%
First Degree	1204	77.2%	1011	64.8%
SSCE	10	0.6%	106	6.8%
Total	1560	100%	1560	100%

Source: Field 2024

Results from table 2 reveal that 77.2% of fathers are first degree holders, this is followed by 22% master's degree holders and finally by SSCE holders- who constitute 0.6%. Meanwhile, 64.8% of mothers are first degree holders, 28.4% are master's holder and 6.8% are SSCE holders. Further conclusions can be drawn from the results that there are more graduates from the fathers when compared with mothers.

Table 3: The nature of parental occupation of public secondary school students in Osun State

Employment Status	Fathers		Mothers	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Employed (Public Sector)	184	11.8%	138	8.85%
Employed (Private Sector)	214	13.7%	830	53.21%
Self-employed (Business/Investor)	1161	74.4%	592	37.94%
Unemployed	1	0.1%	0	0%
Total	1560	100%	1560	50.09%

Source: Field 2024

It can be extrapolated from table 3 that owing to the 74.4% responses which favoured self-employed, most fathers are either business owners or investors, while 13.7% works with the private sector, while public sector has 11.8%. However, 53.21% of mothers are private sector workers, then 37.94% are self-employed, the remaining 8.85% are public sector workers. This means that there are more public sector and self-employed workers among the fathers when compared to the mothers, but mothers tilt more towards the private sector than fathers. The large proportion of fathers who work for themselves (74.4%) points to a robust entrepreneurial culture among fathers in Osun State.

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Table 4: The level of parental income of public secondary school students in Osun State

Approximate income	Fathers		Mothers	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
#151,000-#300,000	235	15%	92	5.9%
#71,000-#150,000	606	38.8%	622	39.9%
Less than #70,000	719	46.2%	846	54.2%
Total	1560	100	1560	100

Source: Field 2024

From table 4 above, fathers are on the higher income scale, compared to mothers; considering 15% and 38.8% of the respondents earning between ₦151,000-₦300,000 and ₦71,000-₦150,000 respectively. While 5.9% and 39.9% of mothers earn ₦151,000-₦300,000 and ₦71,000-₦150,000 respectively. Similarly, more mothers earn below ₦70,000 monthly; 54.2% and 46.2% for mothers and fathers respectively. According to findings, fathers are more likely to be in higher income bands than mothers, which is in line with recent research on the gender pay gap in Nigeria.

Table 5: The level of parental involvement of public secondary school students in Osun State

Item	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Σ	DECISION
I give career advice to my children regarding their academic goals and future professional aspirations.	215 (13.78%)	294 (18.85%)	480 (30.77%)	408 (21.15%)	163 (10.45%)	2.99	1.192	Involved
I attend my children's school events.	350 (22.44%)	369 (23.65%)	359 (23.01%)	268 (17.18%)	214 (13.72%)	3.24	1.341	Involved
I am involved in solving my children's academic-related social challenges	366 (23.46%)	370 (23.72%)	355 (22.76%)	228 (14.62%)	241 (15.44%)	3.25	1.370	Involved
I regularly communicate with my children's teachers about their academic performance and concerns.	282 (18.08%)	301 (19.29%)	414 (26.54%)	352 (22.56%)	211 (13.53%)	3.06	1.296	Involved
I am involved in monitoring my children's academic progress	259 (16.60%)	394 (25.26%)	474 (30.38%)	286 (18.33%)	147 (9.43%)	3.21	1.197	Involved
I manage my children's academic workload and help them deal with academic pressure	193 (12.37%)	278 (17.82%)	499 (31.99%)	428 (27.44%)	162 (10.38%)	2.94	1.166	Involved
I discuss my children's academic strengths and weaknesses with their teachers.	190 (12.18%)	275 (17.63%)	502 (32.18%)	431 (27.63%)	162 (10.38%)	2.94	1.163	Involved
I advise my children on their extra-curricular activities.	215 (13.78%)	294 (18.85%)	480 (30.77%)	408 (26.15%)	163 (10.45%)	2.99	1.192	Involved

Source: Field 2024

Note: N=1560, SA= Strongly Agree, A=Agree, N=Neutral, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree. Weighted average=2.70
 It can be extrapolated from table 5 above that all items on this section of the research instrument surpassed the mean average of 2.70, which is an indication that parents are in one way or the other involved in their children's education. In other words, parental involvement is high among public secondary school students in Osun State. This is corroborated by the responses which reveals that; parents give academic advise to their children, they attend school events such as career day and inter-house sporting activities.

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Hypothesis Testing

Table 6: There is a relative relationship between socio-economic factors and the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Osun state

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Change Statistics				Sig. Change	F	
			Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change			df1
1	.074 ^a	.006	-.002	.35625	.006	1.721	5	1554	.127

a. Predictors: (Constant), CULT_NEW, OC_NEW, INC_NEW, LOIV_NEW, ED_NEW

Source: Field 2024

Results from table 6 reveal a weak relationship between socio-economic factors and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Osun State. The model summary $F(5, 1554)=1.72$, $Adj R^2=0.002$ and $R^2=0.006$, indicates that the model is not statistically significant because there is a weak correlation between socio-economic factors and academic performance. Also, the beta coefficients $\beta = -0.037, -2.238, -0.095, 0.107, 0.205$ and $t = 1.020, -2.515, -1.211, 1.149, 2.635$ for income, education, occupation, level of involvement, and cultural beliefs reveal no significant relationship; with the exception of education and cultural variables with significant negative relationship and significant positive relationship respectively. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Findings on academic performance revealed a low performance of senior secondary school students in Mathematics and English. In addition to socio-economic factors, the pattern of underperformance could be laced with so many other causes, these include; the quality of teacher delivery and student motivation. Socio-economic status affects the capacity of a family to provide resources like extracurricular activities, private tutoring, and access to better educational options. In Nigeria, self-employed people tend to be highly autonomous and have unpredictable incomes; depending on how successful their businesses are, this could have a favorable or negative effect on their children's academic achievement. Also, the private sector has emerged as a significant employment option for women in Nigeria, especially in sectors like services, healthcare, and education where women are more likely to find permanent jobs.

Similarly, findings revealed that women are more likely to be employed in lower-paying positions, especially in the informal sector or lower echelons of the private sector, while men are more frequently found in higher-paying occupations in Nigeria, such as senior managerial positions and business ownership. The findings from the level of involvement showed how crucial parental support is in reducing academic stress, which is a problem that secondary school students face because of external and academic pressures. Parents play an active role in the education of their children, they are more likely to do well in school, have stronger social skills, and behave better. Parental involvement which includes helping with homework, establishing expectations for the children's education, and talking about future career objectives, greatly increases the motivation and achievement of the student.

For the hypothesis, research has consistently demonstrated that higher socio-economic status, specifically higher family income, parental education, and parental occupation, is associated with better academic outcomes. However, the findings in Osun State differ from this overall tendency, since the poor correlation shows that these characteristics have negligible impact on the academic achievement of students in the state. So many reasons could be adduced to these findings, dearth of teaching facilities, poor teacher quality and poor perception of education. The significant positive relationship between cultural beliefs and academic performance is a pointer to the fact that culture plays a significant role in influencing students' academic performance. Hard-work and respect which are key cultural values are positive contributors to students' learning attitude, which ultimately culminates into better academic performance.

While parental involvement is considered to be a strong predictor for academic success, the lack of significance from the findings could be as a result of the way parents get involved. For example, the effectiveness of parental involvement could be greatly limited by their educational attainment and lack of proper understanding of the school curriculum- which could lead to a misinterpretation. Meanwhile in rural areas, parental involvement may take non-traditional forms which not easily measured by conventional or standardised scales. Finally, results revealed that there is no significant relationship between parental occupation and academic performance. This could be as a result of the fact that financial stability or availability of educational resources may not have a direct relationship with occupational status. This therefore, explains why occupations does not have a significant relationship with academic performance of students in this perspective.

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Conclusion

The unique educational problems in Osun State, such as inadequate school facilities and low-quality teachers, greatly reduce the influence of parental socioeconomic characteristics, also, cultural norms that emphasise diligence and decency were found to have a greater impact on academic achievement. The study also noted that traditional measures of parental involvement may not fully capture the ways parents in rural areas contribute to their children's education.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations made:

1. Educational authorities should focus on enhancing the qualifications and teaching methodologies of teachers, particularly in core subjects like English and Mathematics.
2. Also, governments and policymakers should ensure that schools in Osun State are adequately equipped with teaching materials and infrastructure to support effective learning.
3. In the same vein, programs aimed at improving parents' understanding of the school curriculum should be introduced, allowing them to better support their children's education.
4. Finally, financial planning and support initiatives could be introduced for self-employed parents to mitigate the economic uncertainties associated with their occupation and provide stable financial support for their children's education.

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Impact of Availability and... (Muhammad et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259884>

Impact of Availability and Utilization of Printed Media Resources on Teacher's Delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper assessed the Impact of Availability and Utilization of Printed Media Resources on Teacher's Delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The study established one objective, one research question and formulated one null hypothesis which was subsequently tested for the study. Employing a descriptive survey research design, the population included 19,598 Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students and 361 Economics teachers across 114 Senior Secondary Schools offering Economics in Sokoto State. A sample size of Three hundred and sixty-five (365) was selected for the study. The data collection instrument, "Questionnaire for Economics Teachers and Students (QETS)," was utilized. The reliability coefficient results of 0.85 was obtained using Cronbach's Alpha, in pilot testing the instrument. The analysis involved employing descriptive statistics, such as Mean and Standard Deviation to answer research questions. Meanwhile, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U-Test was applied to test the Null Hypothesis. The results indicated the retaining of the formulated null hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05. The study's outcomes underscored the significant impact of availability and utilization of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher delivery in Economics in senior secondary schools in Sokoto State. The study also uncovered that newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets have impact on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State (as indicated by P-value). In conclusion, based on these findings, recommendations were made for the state Ministry of Education, school management, teachers, parents, NGOs, and philanthropies to always make printed media resources available for teachers to use for proper teacher delivery in Economics, additionally, it was also recommended that, the School management should organize relevant workshops, training and re-training of Economics teachers on how to improvise such resources and they should also encourage their students to bring any relevant printed materials to school for use, storage, retrieval, and re-use to enhance effective teacher delivery in Economics in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Keywords: Availability, Utilization, Printed Media, and Resources.

Introduction

Printed media resources that include newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets encompassing publications, documents, records, or any printed media utilized by teachers, play crucial roles in the teaching and learning processes. These materials serve to facilitate instruction and aid in the achievement of lesson objectives. As integral components of the curriculum and learning resources, they contribute meaningfully to the clarity and comprehensiveness of lessons for learners. They enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of teaching and learning by engaging the various senses of students, facilitating the impartation of knowledge, skills, and experiences. They have the capacity to stimulate students' interest, capture their attention, and enrich the teaching and learning process in Economics, thereby imbuing classroom instruction with greater meaning and relevance. They also help teachers achieve curriculum objectives, make lessons

Impact of Availability and... (Muhammad et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259884>

explicit to the learners, and choose the best learning experience to be communicated to the learners. Further, the Printed media resources help Economics teachers create conducive learning environments and ease teacher's delivery at various levels of learning, particularly among Secondary Schools (Ahmed, 2019).

The use of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets might solve the problems of poor academic performance among Economics students, negative perception of the subject, and massive failure in WAEC, NECO and JAMB Examinations. This lies in the assessment of these publications, learning experience and lesson objectives by the teachers which can improve teacher delivery. Conversely, poor teacher delivery may bring negative perception of the subject matter, students' failure and poor academic performance. Hence, it necessitates assessing the impact of the availability and utilization of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher's delivery. Furthermore, these learning resources are necessary for the handling, management and control of the teaching and learning process. They not only focus the student's attention and interest but also simplify the whole concept, the process of teaching, and teacher's delivery. They also reduce the massive failures of external and internal Economic examinations at all levels. They communicate experiences and encourage active participation of students, whereby learning will be concretized and permanent (Usman, 2016).

Teacher delivery is a channel by which teachers communicate the intended learning experience or subject matters to the learners for effective instructions/delivery. It is crucial and impossible to overstate the importance of using newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets while teaching and learning Economics. This can have an impact on curriculum and students' academic achievement. Based on the researcher's experience, Economics teachers in Sokoto State's Secondary Schools neglected the use of these printed teaching resources when instructing and learning about Economics. Some teachers regard utilizing them as stressful and upsetting. It is lamenting the way Economics teachers show up to class to teach without these printed materials despite being aware of the value of using them in the delivery of teaching. This research was necessary to address this issue as well as others that have not yet been identified to avoid verbalism and inappropriate teacher's delivery in Economics. This also necessitated the need to conduct this study to improve the academic performance of Economics students and open a new page for all the schools in Sokoto state (Idris, 2015)

In order to address the scarcity issues of printed media resources, Economics teachers ought to be able to make them available. Through these initiatives, Economics will be taught and learned in a more tangible and efficient manner, increasing students' comprehension in all ways. All teaching and learning procedures need the use of these printed resources. On the other hands, it is well acknowledged that, the utilization of printed media resources among secondary schools are essential components in fostering students' comprehension and efficient instruction (Bright and Jonathan, 2019). It is important to choose these resources wisely in order to provide students with experiences that are relevant and could boost their academic achievement. When properly utilized, these resources can contribute meaningfully to the proper understanding of topics or lesson contents. This can also make Economics lessons or teaching and learning of Economics very easy and more simplified. Eventually, the findings of this study will stimulate students' interest, increase their academic performance and make learning permanent through effective teacher's delivery and utilization of efficient printed media resources. It will also enhance students' clarification of concepts and ideas in Economics. Students can also materialize learning, which will help them retain more information than usual and improve teacher's delivery in Economics (Isaac and Ikechukwu, 2012) .

What prompted this study were rapid changes in human society and technological advancement, which brought about many changes in almost all human endeavours, including teaching and learning processes in schools. Previous means of teaching are regarded as obsolete due to the fast technological advancement in communication technology. Undoubtedly, the irrelevant and non-utilization of the newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets by Economics teachers may be the major source of students' poor academic performance or massive failures in Economics. Therefore, they need to be assessed using this type of study, which hopes to find the bonds between their impacts and teacher's delivery in Economics. These days, Economics teachers spend less time using and applying relevant newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets in their instructional delivery. A few of these printed publications are hard to find. Teachers cannot supply all of these resources required for instruction in the classroom on their own. Government and other agencies should assist in providing these materials for schools and ensure their effective utilization in any teacher's delivery (Mohammed and Abdullahi, 2019).

Concepts of Economics

Economics is a social science discipline that examines how people produce, distribute exchange, consume, and provide services in order to meet their needs. Economics is a social science since it involves the study of a particular facet of human behaviour, according to Okeke (2005). It is the study of the production, distribution and consumption of wealth (Essien, 2006). However, according to Ande (2018, pp 2), "Economics has no specific definition," but he did provide a few definitions provided

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by various subject-matter experts. Economics was described by Alfred Marshal as the study of mankind in the ordinary business of life; Adam Smith saw it as an inquiry into the nature and causes of a nation's wealth; and John Stuart Mill saw it as the practical science of production and distribution. According to HJ Davenport, Economics is the science that examines things from a price perspective. Economics is the science of material welfare, according to A.C. Pigou. The definition of Economics advanced by professor (Lord) Lionel C. Robbins is the most inclusive and widely recognised. "As a science which studies human behaviour as a relationship between ends and scarce means which have alternative uses," is how he described Economics (Anyaele, 2003). Therefore, Economics is social science subject that deals with production and distribution of goods and services to satisfy basic human wants. It also teaches households on how to manage the little resources at their disposal for more satisfaction.

Concepts of Instructional Materials

Instructional Materials are called with different names, such as teaching aids, learning materials, teaching materials, tools, learning resources, instructional resources, instructional media, curriculum resources, learning aids, teaching-learning materials, educational resources, curriculum materials, curriculum media, instructional aids, and teaching resources. The teacher uses materials to facilitate the teaching and learning process or make learning explicit to the learners. The following are some definitions of instructional materials as given by some authors. According to Yusuf (2012, pp181), the teacher uses Curriculum Materials to help students learn. These include books, charts, text, manuals, audio-visual aids, laboratory equipment, artefacts and other archaeological materials". Bara'u (2020) observes that a collection of human and non-human resources that a teacher can utilize in a teaching and learning environment to achieve the intended set objectives in a particular session is called instructional materials or teaching-learning materials (TLM). Further, Igunnu, Aliyu, Hassan and Abdurashied (2015) stated that the resources used in instructional lessons that incorporate evaluation and active learning are called instructional materials. Curriculum resources, according to Danladi (2006), are anything and anybody that a classroom instructor can use to assist both themselves and the students in achieving certain educational objectives. Curriculum materials are representation tools that teachers use to support and guide their teaching practice (Kanno, Obasi and Solomon, 2016). At the same time, Uyagu and Bara'u (2018) opined that resources refer to all things (human and non-human) that are purposefully used to make teaching and learning more meaningful and productive. To this end, Guga (2019) explained that Instructional resources are all materials the teacher uses to facilitate and concretize learning. These materials resources are further classified into tangible and intangible materials. Therefore, teaching resources can be explained as anything the teacher uses to stimulate learning and help pupils (students) appreciate and understand the knowledge, skills, and attitudes learned.

Concepts of Printed Media Resources

Printed media resources are written, textual, printed, and published, as well as reading materials used by Economics teachers in teaching and learning Economics among Secondary Schools. They are also printed or re-printed documents, records, or publications on papers used as a medium of instruction to communicate experiences and knowledge to the learners and make learning permanent, aiding and developing students' memory. They can also be used in individualized, group, mass or class learning. They can be in different forms or formats and can be re-printed, retrieved, duplicated, stored or reproduced for effective teachers' and students' utilization in any classroom instructions. According to Olubunmi (2012), Printed media resources or media include printed materials from which one can obtain information and knowledge and acquire facts, skills, principles and enlightenment. However, Danladi (2006) Printed instructional materials or reading materials refer to daily or weekly newspapers, magazines, periodicals, pamphlets, textbooks, etc. Printed materials included any text and anything else that could be generated in large quantities with a printer or duplicator. Nelyloves (2014) further stated that printed materials refer to any publication, document, or record. Any text and other material that could be produced in large quantities using a printer or duplicator were considered printed materials. Furthermore, to some authors, Printed media resources mean documents or papers that convey information via the written word. Examples of dictionaries, pictures, posters, or printed materials are general books, journals, serials, magazines, newspapers, maps, and atlases (Lawinsider, 2023). Josua (2015) further said that printed materials are any written materials, except non-print resources that provide scheduled course information. Textbooks, workbooks, reference books, periodicals, newspapers, and journals are a few examples. To this end, printed media resources are powerful tools or instructional materials that offer students opportunities to re-read what was taught in the class at ease. They are the best media to be used by Economics teachers in their efforts to make learning explicit and clear to the students.

Concepts of Teacher Delivery

Teacher delivery, otherwise known as teaching delivery, lesson delivery, instructional delivery or learning delivery is a process of presenting a lesson to achieve lesson objectives and effective evaluation. It also involves structuring the learning

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experience, instructional materials, objectives, and contents so that the teacher will ensure the free flow of lessons, interaction among students and attainment of learning objectives using appropriate instructional materials and effective methodologies. According to Safia (2022), learning delivery are means of imparting knowledge to students. This suggests that to provide the desired learning experience and achieve particular goals, you must use particular technology, resources, and facilities. On the other hand, Insider (2022) asserted that teaching delivery involves various activities, including group instruction, seminars, lectures, tutorials, lab sessions, clinical/practicum sessions, fieldwork, and supervision. According to Lukman (2022), demonstrating each tasks a teacher and student completes in a classroom context is considered instructional delivery. However, Tangient (2014) also opined that, lesson delivery is all about holding true to the objective of the lesson, engaging the students and appropriate pacing of the lesson based on students' needs. According to Als-Est (2022) teaching/learning delivery comprises means and resources used to structure the learning experience. Teacher or learning delivery has some methods which include face-to-face, virtual learning, online learning, blended learning and mobile learning (Safia, 2022). Therefore, teacher delivery means effective lesson presentation, setting of lesson objectives and contents according to students' interests by engaging them in teaching and utilization of printed media resources with the hope of achieving effective evaluation.

Concept of Secondary School

Secondary schools are learning institutions that offer students secondary education immediately after completing nine years of basic education and before tertiary education. The junior secondary school is today called upper Basic and is part of basic education, while Senior Secondary School is called Post Basic. They can be Day or Boarding schools. According to Stenfy (2023), secondary schools are educational institutions that fall somewhere between elementary and college. They often provide general, technical, vocational, or college preparation courses. According to National Teachers' Institute (2000), secondary school is the type of education provided following primary school but before tertiary education. However, according to Solomon (2023) Secondary School is a form of education which children received automatically after completing their elementary school education. Secondary school is the next step after primary school, according to Shabista (2023). It serves as a link between elementary and high school education. (Epler, 2022). The next level up from primary school is secondary school. It is a school for kids between 11 and 18 (Cambridge Dictionary, 2023). It is ongoing education after the completion of basic education (primary education). Students in secondary schools usually range in age from 9 to 18 (or occasionally a little older). To this end, Secondary School is an academic institution that offers secondary education to children after completion of primary education.

Types of Printed Media Resources.

Printed media resources can be grouped or classified into different forms and types to serve different purposes and functions. Some are printed/published materials, while others are in form of posters that can be used as Printed instructional materials in any teacher delivery in Economics. The following are some of the Printed media resources, as cited in Chakrabarti (2023), Uzmasaniya (2021), Nelyloves (2014) and Taylor (2023) that are usually available and utilized by Economics teachers in any teacher's delivery in Economics at all levels: Newspapers, Magazines, Journals, Articles, Periodicals and Pamphlets

Newspapers: Newspapers are printed papers or documents containing national and international news, current events, articles of opinion, nation economic activities and deliberations, advertisements, businesses, sports, political events, weather forecasts, news stories, information, etc., which are printed, published and distributed daily or weekly. Newspapers are the primary mass media channel for disseminating information, especially in the domains of politics and Economics, claims Drew (2023). On the other hand, School Wikipedia Selection (2007) asserted that a newspaper is a periodical that publishes news, information, and advertisements and is typically produced on inexpensive newsprint paper. It is usually published daily or weekly and might be specific or generic. In order to do this, newspapers in the targeted areas should produce and provide extra supplements to the school to gradually shift their focus to the fundamental concerns of education (Lawinsider, 2023). Therefore, newspapers can be used as sources of information and printed instructional materials by Economics teachers in teaching-learning processes. It can be used to teach topics like the labour market, company among others

Types of Newspaper: There are two types of newspapers: **Daily newspaper** – a type of newspaper issued daily, often except on Sundays and national holidays and **Weekly newspapers** are newspapers that are issued weekly. They are also common, smaller, and less prestigious than daily papers (Drew, 2023). However, newspapers are the most important printed instructional materials for Economics teachers. They can be used to teach topics like budgets and their types, Economic policies, allocation formulas, inflation, deflation, foreign currency prices, exchange markets, etc. Economics teachers can obtain information related to the topics before them. Journalists educate people, including students, on political, social, economic and cultural development. They also

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provide formal and informal education (Lawinsider, 2023). And can be used as printed instructional materials in teaching and learning Economics

Magazine: A magazine is printed material published every week or month containing stories, essays, pictures, photographs, articles, information, or in short, containing different contents. Drew (2023) stated that magazines are printed periodicals typically released monthly or bi-monthly. They are usually geared towards a specific intended audience and often have a specific focus or niche. However, magazines can be used as printed instructional materials in any teacher's delivery to facilitate instructions and attainment of the lesson objectives. Economics teachers can easily use magazines to teach topics such as production, public companies, etc., for more elaboration.

Journal / Academic Journal: An academic journal is a printed and compiled set of academic write-ups involving research and publications of various academic articles from scholars in different educational fields or disciplines. Experts or researchers in various subjects or professions wrote it. Academic journals might contain economic, political, social, scientific, cultural and religious matters. It can be used as printed instructional materials in any teacher's delivery to enhance students' understanding of various topics. Mckenzie (2017), a journal is a collection of articles (like magazines) published regularly throughout the year. An academic journal is a periodical publication in which scholarship relating to a particular academic discipline is published (Lawinsider, 2023). Economics teachers can use journals to teach certain topics in Economics, such as business organizations, banking and finance, etc.

Article: An article is a piece of writing about a particular subject or discipline usually found in newspapers, magazines, journals, etc., and included in printed or online publications. To Stenfy (2023), an article refers to writing about a particular subject in a magazine, newspaper, etc. Further, Economics teachers can use the articles as print material in any teacher's delivery to make the teaching and learning process lively and explicit to the learners. They are also important in attracting students' attention towards the lesson and learning activities in classrooms in most schools. Article can appear in different forms, such as newspapers, magazines, and academic journals. They can also be used in teaching and learning processes in Economics at all levels of learning.

Periodical: A periodical is also one of the printed instructional materials. It is a booklet, often with illustrations, issued at fixed intervals (or periods), typically once a month or weekly (Drew, 2023). However, Spacey (2020) opined that a periodical is any regular publication such as a monthly, semi-annual or annual journal. Economics teachers can use periodicals in any teacher delivery to make lessons explicit to the learners. Some economic matters can be discussed in detail, allowing teachers to utilize them in their classroom instruction to motivate and arouse students' interest.

Pamphlet: A pamphlet is a small printed or published booklet that contains information about a particular subject, topic or discipline that covers many types of printed and digital materials. It may consist of a single sheet of paper printed on both sides and folded in half, in a third or fourth, called a leaflet, brochure, flyer, hand outs or booklet, and make a simple book. However, according to Nona (2021), a pamphlet is a little book or leaflet that primarily informs or educates readers about a specific topic. These come in several formats, such as tri-fold and single-sheet leaflets. Teachers can use pamphlets as printed instructional materials in any teacher delivery to ease instruction.

The significant challenges of massive failure, poor academic performance, and slow rate of learning in Economics in both internal and external examinations, are likely to be attributable to lack of qualified Economics teachers, unavailability of relevant printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets, poor skills and inexperience in teaching and learning process by Economics teachers, inadequate utilization of printed media resources and teachers' attitude towards it, lack of improvisational skills by Economics teachers or ineffective teacher's delivery. The problems of teaching Economics, especially regarding the use of inappropriate newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets, posed many challenges and problems to teachers and their students at all levels. The Economics teachers' unpreparedness and inability to make the appropriate newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets available for use in the lesson periods makes their efforts abortive and unsuccessful, which could make learning less effective and might affect the student's academic performance in the school and any form of examination/evaluation.

Over the decades, many efforts were made to provide and distribute newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets by the Government, private organizations and other stakeholders to improve teaching and learning in schools. However, some teachers, especially Economics teachers, refused to utilize them to facilitate their instructions. Some still need to gain skills on using the available printed materials or making printed resources available through improvisation or any other means for classroom instruction. These were also reported by Okeke and Ezewulu (2021), who stated that these difficulties might be faced by Economics teachers at various schools in the state. This made teacher delivery more challenging and

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strenuous for both teachers and students. These were the major causes of ineffective teacher delivery and poor academic performance among students in Economics. These formed parts of the findings of Sirajo (2014), Yusuf (2015), and Usman (2016) in their various research works. However, there were serious problems with the poor State of Economics teaching and learning in most senior secondary schools in Sokoto state. This made researchers and stakeholders focus more on Economics Education in all the six educational zones of the State. Inappropriate utilization of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets during teaching delivery by Economics teachers may be one of the militating factors affecting students' academic performance in WAEC and other similar examinations in the state. Further, in 2014 WAEC, 25,331 students sat for WAEC in the 2013/2014 academic session in the State, but due to some of these problems, the State recorded only 7.12% passes (WAEC, 2014). This serious problem might be attributed to the need for more adequate and proper utilization of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets in lesson delivery.

Usman (2016) revealed that the unavailability of appropriate printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets in most Nigerian secondary schools made Economics teachers vulnerable to the problems of poor performance. They usually complain that, the unavailability of printed instructional Materials in their teaching and learning processes will make students inactive and might lead to massive student failure and poor performance. This represented the most critical and alarming issue confronting the instruction and learning of Economics in our secondary schools, particularly in Sokoto State. The verbal presentation of Economics concepts to the learners, according to Yusuf (2018), led to problems which might include ineffective and inefficient teaching, slow rate of learning, poor performance in examinations, poor understanding, less interest in the subject and so on. These challenges posed significant obstacles to effective Economics Education in many of our schools. The Sokoto State Government should prioritize providing printed instructional materials to enhance the teaching and learning of Economics. Additional initiatives are required to evaluate, motivate, and ensure that teachers use printed resources in schools nationwide.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to:

1. To find out the impact of printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Research Question

The Research Question answered in this study was as follows:

1. What are the opinions of teachers and students on the impact of printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State?

Null Hypothesis

The study was guided by the following research hypothesis:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between teachers' and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Theoretical Framework: Constructivist Theory of Learning.

The constructivist learning theory, rooted in the studies of cognitive development by psychologists Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky, emerged as a foundation for understanding how thinking and knowledge evolve with age. Constructivism posits that children actively build knowledge through their engagement in learning activities. In a constructivist setting, learning is characterized by active participation, inquiry, problem-solving, and collaboration, with the teacher serving as a guide and facilitator rather than a mere dispenser of knowledge (Weegar and Pacis, 2012). In a constructivist classroom, students are provided with opportunities to develop profound understanding of materials, internalize knowledge, grasp the nature of knowledge development, and create intricate cognitive maps connecting various bodies of knowledge (Richardson, 2018). Olusegun (2015) emphasizes that teachers cannot simply transmit knowledge; students actively construct knowledge in their minds, discovering and transforming information and revising their understanding when necessary. The following are some benefits of the constructivist approach, as presented by Olusegun (2015 pp 3-7), include:

1. Active Involvement: Children learn more and enjoy learning when actively engaged rather than being passive listeners.
2. Emphasis on Thinking and Understanding: Education is most effective when it focuses on thinking and understanding rather than rote memorization.
3. Transferability: Constructivist learning promotes the transfer of knowledge.

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4. Student Ownership: Constructivism gives students ownership of their learning.
5. Real-World Context: Constructivism stimulates and engages students by grounding activities in authentic, real-world contexts.
6. Social and Communication Skills: Constructivism fosters social and communication skills through a collaborative and idea-sharing classroom environment.

This theory was chosen for the current study due to its relevance to teaching and learning processes, aligning with the investigation into the impact of the availability and utilization of printed media resources on teacher’s delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. It helps teachers emphasize the relevant and important topics, encouraging students' critical thinking and group work by using various printed media resources that improve students' active participation in any teacher delivery. It also encourages students' active engagement in classroom activities, which helps them, explain and elaborate on what was learned. This is what prompted the choice of this theory in this work.

Methodology

Research Design

The research employed a descriptive research design, specifically utilizing a survey method. Descriptive research is apt for opinion-seeking studies, providing a blueprint for collecting data from a population to facilitate generalizations about the target group. The survey method, within this design, allows for the collection of opinions from a representative sample of the population and facilitating meaningful generalizations (Aliyu, 2016). As noted by Nmadi (2001), this design is particularly suitable as it offers a clear definition of the problem, meticulous data collection, careful analysis and interpretation, and skillful reporting of the findings.

Population of the Study

The population for this study comprised all Economics teachers and students in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. The Economics teachers’ population was three hundred and sixty-one (361) across the six educational zones in the state. However, a total number of nineteen thousand, five hundred and ninety-eight (19,598) Senior Secondary School Two (SSII) Economics students from six educational zones were used. All from the one hundred and fourteen (114) Senior Secondary Schools that are offering Economics in the state served as the population of the study. Table 1 presented the population distribution of the schools offering Economics in Sokoto State, Economics teachers and SSII students for this study from the six Educational Zones.

Table1: Population breakdown by educational zones.

S/N	Educational Zones	No. of Senior Secondary schools	No. of SSII Students	No. of SSII Economics Teachers
1	Sokoto North	16	4,201	54
2	Sokoto South	27	3,134	84
3	Gwadabawa	15	1,849	47
4	Goronyo	23	3,818	72
5	Bodinga	15	3,197	48
6	Yabo	18	3,399	56
Total		114	19,598	361

Source: Sokoto State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, (2023)

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The total sample size of this study comprised three hundred and sixty-five (365) respondents sampled from Economics teachers and students in the study area as suggested by Research Advisor 2006 under 95% confidence (Dada, 2016). Multistage sampling techniques were employed in the selection of sampled schools, teachers and students. However, proportionate sampling procedure was used in selecting fifteen (15) schools out of thirty-one (31) schools of the two sampled educational zones as samples size. Eight (8) schools were sampled from Sokoto North educational zone, and Seven (7) from Bodinga educational zones. Furthermore, fifty-one (51) Economics teachers were sampled from the total number of one hundred and two (102) SSII Economics teachers of the two sampled educational zones of the state. Both sampled schools and teachers were

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chosen by assigning numbers to all the schools and teachers of the sampled zones; then, all the even numbers were taken as the sample size. Two (2) educational zones were sampled out of Six Educational Zones in Sokoto State. These zones were sampled using balloting sampling technique. The names of the zones were written on pieces of papers, folded, put in a container and were mixed thoroughly. The SSII Economics students were asked to pick out the folded papers (through lucky dip) containing the names of the zones from the same container without replacement.

Table 2: Respondents Distribution of the two sampled Educational Zones.

Zone	Educational Zones	Sampled Secondary Schools	Sampled Economics Students	Sampled Economics Teachers	Sampled Econs Teachers and Students
B	Sokoto North	8	163	27	190
E	Bodinga	7	151	24	175
Total	15	314	51	365	

Source: Sokoto State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, (2023)

Instrumentation

The instrument used for this study was researchers designed questionnaire for both teachers and students. It was titled “Questionnaire for Economics Teachers and Students (QETS). This questionnaire was used by the researchers for the collection of data from the respondents at various schools. It contained twelve (12) items which required respondents’ responses. Further, this questionnaire was also designed using a four (4) modified Points Likert Scale using Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The respondents were required to tick in the appropriate box. It also contained items related to all the research questions set for the study which provided required answers.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument used for this study was subjected to face, content and construct validation by research experts in the fields of Economics (to check the content), English language (to check language and grammatical constructions) and from measurement and evaluation Section (to check the design and statistical tools for analysis) from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The validity of any research instrument is the ability of that instrument to measure thoroughly and accurately the purpose for which it was constructed for. Therefore, the subsection of this instrument to the experts was to ensure its validity and measure what it intended to measure. The observations and suggestions of these experts were incorporated in the final draft of the instrument.

Pilot Testing

The researchers carried out a pilot test at Government Day Secondary School, Dingyadi in Bodinga educational zone of Sokoto state. The test was conducted in the school which was not part of the sample size. The researchers and their assistants took permission from the Head of the school before the distribution of the instrument to the respondents. Thirty (30) copies of the instrument were administered to five teachers and twenty-five students in the pilot school where they were asked to express their views and response to all the items by choosing one out of the multiple responses provided. The instrument was distributed, retrieved, scored and analyzed. The result revealed 0.85 Reliability Coefficient at 0.05 level of significance. The result of methodological pilot test was computed using Cronbach’s Alpha to determine the Reliability Coefficient of the pilot test.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability coefficient of the instrument was assessed following a successful pilot test conducted with thirty (30) copies of the instrument from the pilot school. The Test–Retest reliability method was employed, and the results were analyzed using Cronbach’s Alpha. The obtained Cronbach’s Alpha value was 0.85, which was in proximity to one (1). According to Usman (2016), the closer the result is to a positive one (1), the more reliable the instruments are considered. Additionally, Balogun (2000) in Sirajo (2014) stated that any reliability index ranging from 0.5 and above can be deemed high enough for use in real research. Therefore, the instrument used demonstrated high reliability and consistency for the intended study, as the result was close to one. This justifies the use of the instrument.

Procedures for Data Collection

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The research was set by taking an introductory letter obtained from the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria to all the Principals of the sampled schools to solicit permission to use their Economics teachers and students in the collection of data for the study. The researchers were assisted by research assistants (Economics teachers in the visited schools) in administering the instruments to the students in their various classes. One day (2 hours) training was given to two Economics teachers in all the schools visited. The training was aimed at giving them the awareness of what they were expected to do, their boundaries and how to retrieve the copies of the instrument administered without having any problem or challenge. Further, the teachers' questionnaire was administered to them (by self) in their staff rooms. The researchers explained to all the respondents on how to respond to all the items on the questionnaire. This assisted the researchers to collect the first-hand information for this study. However, the researchers got one hundred percent (100%) return rate for all the instrument administered. This was because more trained hands were involved in sharing and retrieving the instrument from the students and teachers. This enabled the researchers to collect necessary information on the Impact of availability and utilization of printed instructional materials on teacher delivery in Economics in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State from all the sampled schools.

Procedure for Data Analysis

The collected data were meticulously organized and classified by the researchers. The analysis of the Research Questions involved the use of simple percentages, frequency tables, and descriptive statistics, including the Mean and Standard Deviation. Additionally, non-parametric statistics, specifically the Mann-Whitney U-Test, was employed to test all the five null hypotheses at 0.5 level of significance.

Results

The responses gathered from the research question was meticulously subjected to statistical measures, specifically Mean and Standard Deviation, to answer the research question formulated for this study.

Research Question One: What are the opinions of teachers and students on the impact of printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State? In order to answer this research question, the data collected on the impact of newspaper, magazine, journal, article, periodicals and pamphlet on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State was analysed using Mean and Standard Deviation. The outcomes of this analysis are succinctly summarized in Table 3 as follows:

Table 3 Mean and Standard Deviation on the opinions of Respondents on the Impact of Newspaper, Magazine, Journal, Articles, Periodical, and Pamphlets on Teacher Delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

S/ No	Item statements	Category of Respondents	Population	Mean	Decision rule
1.	The use of Newspapers in teaching and learning of Economics was very effective and relevant.	Teachers	51	3.5	Accepted
		Students	314	3.1	Accepted
2.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use Newspapers in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	3.2	Accepted
		Students	314	3.1	Accepted
3.	The use of Magazines by Economics teachers in teaching and learning of Economics was very efficient and productive.	Teachers	51	3.0	Accepted
		Students	314	2.8	Accepted
4.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use Magazines in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	2.7	Accepted
		Students	314	2.8	Accepted
5.	The Journals were professionally chosen and used by Economics teachers in my school for effective teacher delivery.	Teachers	51	3.8	Accepted
		Students	314	3.1	Accepted
6.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use Journals in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	3.6	Accepted
		Students	314	3.2	Accepted
7.	Articles were adequately used by Economics teachers in teaching and learning of Economics in my school.	Teachers	51	2.6	Accepted
		Students	314	2.8	Accepted
8.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use articles in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	3.9	Accepted
		Students	314	3.7	Accepted

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9.	The use of Periodicals in teaching and learning of Economics was very interesting and informative.	Teachers	51	2.5	Accepted
		Students	314	2.8	Accepted
10.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use periodicals in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	2.8	Accepted
		Students	314	2.9	Accepted
11.	The use of Pamphlets in teaching and learning of Economics was very effective and efficient.	Teachers	51	3.1	Accepted
		Students	314	3.0	Accepted
12.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use Pamphlets in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	3.3	Accepted
		Students	314	3.1	Accepted
Cumulative Mean				3.5	

Source: Field work

Note. Table three presents the analysis of respondents' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. The cumulative mean was 3.5, which is greater than the 2.5 benchmark. Based on this, the decision rule revealed that, all items were accepted. This also implied that, teachers and students agreed with all the items, with a mean of each item above 2.5, which means that all the items were agreed upon and retained. The analysis showed that teachers and students agreed that newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets have impact on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Hypotheses Testing

The following is the null hypothesis formulated for this study and tested as follows:

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between teachers' and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. To test the null hypothesis one, Mann-Whitney (U-test) statistic was used. The summary of the analysis is presented in Table 4 as follows:

Table 4: Summary of Mann-Whitney test Analysis on the opinions between Students and Teachers on the Impact of Newspaper, Magazine, Journal, Articles, Periodicals and Pamphlets on Teacher's Delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank	χ^2	Df	p-value	Decision
Teachers	51	218.51	10925.50	2.635	362	0.321	Retained
Students	314	176.77	55504.50				

Significant at level of ≤ 0.05

Table 4 presents the Mann-Whitney (U-test) analysis result equal to 2.635 and the P-value equal to 0.321. The calculated P-value of 0.321 is greater than the alpha value 0.05 ($P = 0.321 > 0.05$). This implies that, there is no significant difference between teachers' and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. Hence the null hypothesis which said, There is no significant difference between teachers' and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State was retained. Moreover, the outcomes also revealed that newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets have impact on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Summary of Finding

Based on the study, the following findings were made: Newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets have impact on teachers' Economics delivery among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, and there is no significant difference between teachers and students regarding this ($P = 0.321$).

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of findings was systematically done by aligning research question with the corresponding null hypothesis as follows:

Research question one: What are the opinions of teachers and students on the impact of printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State? In answering this question, the analysis revealed that, teachers and students agreed that using

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newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets have impact on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. All items were accepted because the cumulative mean was 3.5, which was greater than the 2.5 benchmark. As a result, **the null hypothesis one**, which said that there was no significant difference between teachers' and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State was retained and hence conclude that there was no significant difference between teachers and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazine, journal, articles, periodical, and pamphlets on teacher delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. Furthermore, the result also revealed that newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets have impact on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

In support of these findings, Adogboji and Toyo's (2006) research disclosed that, various types of print media that improve and enhance academic performance of students include: Newspapers, magazines, banners, textbooks, fliers, billboard, circulars, journals, pamphlets, periodicals and others not covered in their studies, significantly contribute to improving and enhancing students' academic performance. However, Ikpesu and Nkem's (2021) findings revealed that instructional materials are very important factors in teaching and effective teaching cannot take place without the availability and utilization of basic relevant instructional materials. The result also aligned with the observations of Tety (2016), who emphasized that, teachers consider instructional materials as key to academic performance. This implied that the Schools with inadequacy of printed media resources and instructors are likely to perform low whereas schools with adequate printed instructional materials and instructors are likely to perform high.

This discovery did not align with the research conducted by Usman (2016) who reported that, there was a significant difference in the opinions of the respondents on the availability of instructional materials and students' academic performance in Economics in senior secondary schools. The finding was also not consistent with Ahmed's study in 2019 which revealed that, there was a significant difference between the impact of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning of Economics in senior secondary schools. Additionally, Dahiru, Akinpade and Aluko's (2021), findings also revealed that, instructional facilities were inadequate and the available of instructional facilities were not fully utilized in teachings Agricultural science. Also, the finding was not in line with finding of Ehirim, Iwuchukwu and Okenyi (2020), asserting that, many instructional materials were available, but they were not adequately utilized and chemistry teachers do not appropriately improvise instructional materials when not available in the teaching and learning of chemistry. These findings underscore the crucial role of instructional materials in influencing students' academic performance across various educational settings and geographical locations in the state.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the availability and utilization of printed media resources have impact on teacher delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. It was also concluded that, teachers who are skillful in selecting and utilizing printed media resources deliver well in Economics among Secondary schools. It could be generalized as a conclusion that, the availability and utilization of printed media resources in teacher delivery alone do not bring about effectiveness and efficiency unless such printed materials are accessible, affordable by the school teachers and easily improvisable by the teachers and students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, it was recommended that:

1. The school management should provide printed media resources to be used by the Economics teacher for proper teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.
2. The state Ministry of Education, school management, teachers, parents, NGOs, and philanthropies should always make printed media resources available for teachers to use for proper teacher's delivery in Economics.
3. Economics teachers should encourage their students to bring any relevant printed materials to school for use, storage, retrieval, and re-use for proper teacher's delivery in Economics among secondary schools in Sokoto State.
4. School management should organize relevant workshops, training and re-training of Economics teachers on how to improvise and utilize such printed media resources.

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Qualitative Study on Teaching Practice and Siwes as Teacher Training Instrument: Meta Subject Problems in Business Education

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Abstract

The modern teacher is condemned to think out of the box to meet the expectations of the current learners who are exposed to the unending volume of information on the internet at the press of a button on their Information Communication Technology-compliant gadgets at any time and anywhere with little or no assistance on one hand, and age not a limit to the prowess that can be displayed by “learned learners” on the other. Teaching Practice is core in teacher training education, as this is the practical aspect of classroom pedagogical theories learned by the teacher trainee, together with students’ Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), which is to give real-life industrial experience to a student. However, while the Teaching Practice is to enhance classroom skills in preparation for the world of work in the teaching profession, SIWES gives workplace experience to students who are likely to find themselves outside the classroom post-training. This paper, therefore, is an evaluation of the relevance of knowledge gained as a Business Education trainee, the adequacy of the knowledge, and an assessment of the value gained in solving challenges of teaching and the world of work in a business environment given the ability to create consciousness between what had been learned during teaching practice and SIWES and applying same to a real situation which is the Meta subjective cognition ability expected.

Keywords: Teaching Practice, Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme, Meta subjective Cognitive, business education, teacher

Introduction

The Chinese scholar, Xunzi (340 – 245 BC) revealed an adage that; When I hear, I forget. When I see, I remember. When I do, I understand. The purpose is to acquire knowledge not only for one's good but also to develop the essence of education, which is to acquire knowledge for one's good and to develop society. Therefore, a man is educated for the societal good. Sidorkin (2011) while quoting B.F. Skinner said learning is simply from one own individual experience, while according to Vygotsky, working together with a more advanced person seems to trigger faster learning about both the physical world and the social world. Dkhar (2013) described education generally as a form of learning whereby knowledge, skill, and habits are etched out in the minds of individuals through instruction, training, sharing, and communicating. In a nutshell, education is usually a transfer of information and knowledge from one individual to the other. In whatever way knowledge is transferred, the ultimate end of education must necessarily be formative. At the end of the day, it is these formative effects that will shape and help mold an individual in the way he/she thinks, believes, views, feels, acts, and reacts in society.

Business education is a vocational study. The objectives of the business education programme at the tertiary level are to train teachers who can occupy teaching and leadership positions in secondary schools, technical colleges, universities, and

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training programme. (UNN Students Handbook, 2014). The business education curriculum includes courses such as bookkeeping, general business, office practice, typewriting, shorthand, business mathematics, word processing, commerce, economics, consumer education, and business law, this blend of courses from accounting, business, and office practice shows the double major status of the course. A major focal point in the curriculum objective is to produce graduates that can fit adequately in the classroom and within the office routine in a business setup. Therefore, the place of Teaching Practice in closing the gap between theories learned in the classroom and practicing being a teacher on one hand and becoming a member of staff within a business setting through the impart of SIWES cannot be overemphasized.

Teaching Practice

Teaching practice is a core aspect of teacher education at any tertiary level of education. Is an on-the-field period for the teacher trainee to demonstrate in a school setting all the pedagogical theories learned in the tertiary institution classroom, thereby allowing the student teacher to bridge the gap between theories and real-life teaching. It is a period of interface between the institution supervisor, the host school coordinating teacher, and the intending teacher in training.

The National Universities Commission (NUC, 2017) and the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE, 2015) have established the following objectives for why teaching practice is a mandatory component of teacher training.

1. To expose student-teachers to real-life classroom experiences under the supervision of professional teachers.
2. To provide a forum for student-teachers to translate educational theories and principles into practice.
3. To enable student-teachers to discover their strengths and weaknesses in classroom teaching and provide opportunities to enable them to address their weaknesses and enrich their strengths.
4. To familiarize student-teachers with the real school environment as their future workplace.
5. To provide student-teachers with an opportunity for further acquisition of professional skills, competencies, personal characteristics, and experience for full-time teaching after graduation.
6. To help student-teachers develop a positive attitude towards the teaching profession.
7. To serve as a means of assessing the quality of training being provided by teacher training institutions.

Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES)

The concept Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES): This is a practically oriented programme aimed at bridging the gap between theory and practical. It is also, a programme to be performed, employing both human and material resources to achieve the objectives of training pre-service teachers to acquire practical skills. This activity aligns with one of the laws of vocational and Technical Education which states that; The Training environment must be a replica of the workplace, (Okoro, 2016). This is a training period for pre-service student teachers to acquire industry experience in their area of study. According to NCCE (2012), pre-service teachers are the candidates who have gained admission to the colleges of education to study a programme or course of their choice for three (3) years; to enable them to teach effectively at the basic education level. The pre-service teachers are candidates undergoing training in the colleges of education for teaching and they possess the pedagogy required in the area they are trained in, that is the knowledge and skills that teachers need for effective teaching, (NCCE, 2012). According to the Industrial Training fund, SIWES objectives include: The scheme is designed to bridge the gap between employers' expectations and the actual performance of Nigerian graduates.

To provide an avenue for students' institutions of higher learning to acquire industrial skills and experience in their course of study.

1. Expose students to work methods and techniques in handling equipment and machines that may not be available in their institutions.
2. Prepare students for the industrial work situation they are to meet after graduation.
3. Make the transition from school to the world of work easier and enhance students' contacts for later job placement.
4. Provide students with an opportunity to apply their knowledge in real work situations, thereby bridging the gap between theory and practice.
5. Enlist and strengthen employers' involvement in the entire educational process.

Meta subjective Cognition

This is the exclusively personal conscious understanding of an item that is devoid of external influence. Is the individual interpretation of a phenomenon, as consciousness could relate to given personal previous knowledge or experience. According to Rivas (2016), conceptual Meta subjective representation (i.e. defining properties in the brain as an exclusively physical system is impossible. Similarly, individual memories of conscious experience must contain information about

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qualitative and subjective as well, since the concept of consciousness ultimately derives from such information abstracted from episodic memories. The forgoing therefore shows that the place of previous contact, consciousness of the contact, and the ability to refer to that previous experience in solving a present challenge as a teacher cannot be discountenanced. The place of the mind, the brain, and memories are individual-based. Hence, Rivas (2006) further states that the stored bases from which such individual memories of conscious experiences are reconstituted must also contain elements that cannot be represented in the brain. Both Meta subjective concepts and bases of our memories of subjective experiences can only be stored in a personal non-physical memory linked to consciousness. There must be a personal mind or psyche that embraces consciousness, Meta subjective concepts, and bases of episodic memories of one's subjective experience.

Meta subjective Cognition Issues, Teaching Practice and SIWES in Business Education

Meta subjective concept relates to the personal experience of an individual, awareness of a relationship that was built due to contact and stored in the consciousness, i.e. the memory. At the same time, Teaching Practice is a period of attachment of a teacher trainee to a school as part of further training to demonstrate relevant skills acquired in theories. According to Aglazor (2017), the Teaching Practice is intended to bridge the gap between theory and practice. He further stated that the teaching practice exercise is the culminating point where the relationship among the three major players: the university supervisor, the host teacher, and the aspiring student-teacher interface determines the quality of experience the aspiring teacher will take away. It becomes the bedrock on which the aspiring teachers once certified and employed build their professional identity. Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) is also a skill acquisition period, which is also part of the experience building for the student trainee to bridge theories learned in the classroom with pragmatic work experience in the workplace. Oladimeji, Lawson, Olajide, and Akinfiresoye (2017) further emphasized that SIWES allows students to apply theoretical knowledge in real-life situations.

The knowledge from Teaching Practice and SIWES and its resultant display in Meta-subjective cognition shows that a business education teacher can only succeed in the classroom based on the ability to recall exclusive experiences that have been gained during the teaching practice and consciously applying this knowledge to the present classroom challenges, and at the same time, a business education graduate who finds him/herself outside the classroom, that, in the non-academic workplace, will be able to use the Meta subjective cognition to recall various experiences gathered during SIWES into solving current challenges with little or no assistance. As business educators, therefore, the place of Meta's subjective ability, teaching practice, and SIWES in evolving a grounded graduate that is functionally relevant in the business education profession cannot be overemphasized.

Challenges of Teaching Practice and SIWES in Applying Meta subjective Cognition

A graduate of Business Education at any graduate level: Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) or first degree has been trained and imbibed in all the three levels of taxonomy: Cognitive, Affective, and Psychomotor, hence, is easy for such graduate to transmit knowledge gained in the course of undergraduate education to the classroom or workplace setting, whichever he found himself. However, there are challenges that the trainee has encountered in the classroom as a student, the teaching practice, and the SIWES engagement which is affecting the ability of the student teacher to make effective conscious and deliberate use of the Meta subjective cognition, as this may have been distorted even at its introductory stage, thereby giving the student teacher cognitive recognition challenge right from the start and its recall ability questioned when needed. A business education teacher training programme is a tripartite contract in the course Teaching Practice and SIWES: the primary institution supervisor, the hosting institution supervisor, called the coordinating teacher during Teaching Practice and Industry based supervisor during SIWES, and the student trainee. The challenges of this contact can come from any of the players in the contact which can make the Meta subjective cognition transfer problematic when needed.

The student trainee-centered challenges:

Inability to secure placement institution either for teaching practice or SIWES.

1. Transportation issue.
2. Remuneration
3. Heavy workload beyond the ability of the student.
4. Accommodation.
5. Absenteeism, truancy at work
6. Inability to differentiate between work environment and school environment.

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Primary Institution-Centered Challenges:

1. Excessive formalities, i.e. more of fulfilling the righteousness of SIWES than interest in the knowledge gained by the student.
2. Negligence in supervision.
3. Emphasis on the report the student is presenting rather than the ability to display the knowledge claimed.
4. Duration of the SIWES is usually short, as this is disrupted by holidays as it is usually within the festive period, thereby reducing the learning period.

Teaching Practice School and SIWES workplace Centered Challenges.

1. Lazy workers who depend more on the student on internship.
2. Absence of incentives to the student to boost their morale.
3. Few internship openings.

Business Educators' Use of Meta subjective Cognitive Approach to Solving Teaching Practice and SIWES Knowledge Transfer to Post-Studentship

Self-Assessment: through using the Meta subjective cognition process of thinking, a student teacher can personally give a good assessment of his/her ability without being biased and by so doing, engages in activities where he/she is sure of his/her confidence and also develop strategies to improve on his weakness.

Development of cognitive ability: it assists the student in mental ability development and easy understanding of events by conscious thoughts.

Dissuade Impulse actions: The cognitive approach discourages actions before thinking, rather, it encourages well-thought-out analyses of events or actions before they are taken, thereby leaving no room for errors, and where errors are unavoidable, they are minimal and manageable.

The cognitive approach moves teaching from the realm of abstract to physical impossibility to possibility and unattainable to attainable.

Reduces withdrawal syndrome: cognitive approach to learning encourages and carries along all students, irrespective of their learning capability either introvert or extrovert, slow learners or fast learners, as students are encouraged to tap into their cognitive consciousness; previous knowledge, to extract information to solve present challenges.

Ability-Based Learning: since the cognitive approach enhances self-discovery through thinking, students are then able to learn at their own pace and gradually move to the expected pace after consciously seeing the contributions of their colleagues which will then encourage their abilities too.

Instruction Planning: the teacher who taps into the cognitive approach also will be able to plan lessons taking into consideration the learning ability of students and be able to carry all students along in teaching.

Evaluation of students and teachers: the cognitive approach assists the teacher in self-evaluation of the instruction taught and also evaluates the students to determine if the objective of the lesson has been achieved.

Pre and Post assessment: The cognitive approach assures students of their learning state at the start of an instruction, their learning level during the instruction, and also the learning level after the class contact, hence, it will assist in answering self-evaluation questions and how to solve such.

Muddiest point: both the teacher and the learners can easily identify and understand their confusion about a particular phenomenon and assist in how to go about it.

Cognitive strategies

Why and how questions: when the question is continuously asked, it shows that there is a knowledge gap that needs filling or bridging, therefore, business educators and students should not shy from asking questions as this enhances knowledge.

Performance analyses: irrespective of whether the performance is expected or undesired, student-teachers or teachers must assess all steps taken to arrive at the actual result to ensure that the results achieved are a result of honest effort and also to be sure there is no knowledge gap. Question: Is performance equal to effort put into it? so that the feedback will be used for further critical thinking and decision.

Free thinking: learners should be allowed to think freely and assess the result of their thinking, by so doing, if there is a shortcoming when compared with their peers, the learners can make an honest adjustment, unlike when teleguided which will make them to be dependent instead of independent.

Qualitative Study on Teaching... (Ismaila, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259886>

Retrospective post-assessments: there should be an after-assessment of the result by the teacher. This is evaluating performance from thinking, correcting errors, and ensuring that reasons for errors are pointed out to the students in order not to confuse them more.

Make learning interesting: right from the first class, pose questions and identify paradoxes that will engage students' curiosity.

Promote a mastery orientation: as students value success, the teacher should define success so that students know when they are below the expectation so that necessary effort toward remedy can be taken.

Student-Teachers Perceptions of the Teaching Practice and Its Effects on the Exercise

Teaching practice is an integral part of the teacher education programme at any level of tertiary education, as is meant to bridge the gap between theories learned by the student teacher in the classroom and the expected pragmatic skill to be displayed in the classroom after the pre-service teacher period. The student teacher therefore is the recipient of knowledge during the teaching practice, as the other major players: the college/university supervisor and the host school teacher are both mentors, while the student teacher is the mentee. According to Tubbs and Holiday (2019), the stakeholder's perceptions of the practicum experience are most valuable for the continuous improvement of the programme. It therefore shows that the perception of the student teacher cannot be discountenanced if the programme of teaching practice is to achieve its objectives.

In the research study carried out by Tubbs and Holliday (2019), it was observed that participating candidates considered "hands-on" experience and flexibility as the major strengths of the program. In one candidate's words, "Not assigned specific standards at specific times, this allowed me to participate in a wide variety of standards as they came up in my school". A few candidates also mentioned that they had "knowledgeable and helpful" mentors and/or supervisors throughout their practicum experiences. Furthermore, Amankwah, Oti-Agyen, and Sam (2017) observed that student-teachers indicated that the teaching practice programme is good for training and developing teachers. This also supports. Nwanekezi, Okoli, and Mezieobi (2011) investigated the attitude of student-teachers towards teaching practice in Nigeria and reported that student-teachers were satisfied with the scheme based on good experience and therefore should be allowed to continue.

However, Tubbs and Holliday (2019) observed that the main weaknesses of the current practicum as pointed out by the participating candidates included: a lack of communication between students and their institution supervisors, inconsistency in the requirements among supervisors, delay in assigning supervisors and giving directions to practicum candidates at the beginning of each semester, difficulty in getting help from mentors, not enough specified experiences, and too many hours required for each semester. The majority of participating candidates (72%) considered the mentor as very important if he/she "assigns leadership duties regularly". However, several candidates commented that the mentor "must be willing to offer guidance into their daily operations, activities, and leadership philosophy". One candidate wrote that she fulfilled her leadership hours on her own because her mentor was very busy and she hated "bothering her for leadership ideas".

In the study conducted by Amankwah, Oti-Agyen, and Sam (2017), it was found that teaching practice has equipped the student teachers with necessary teaching skills" and then followed by improved teaching knowledge" and also that teaching practice helps trainees to increase their job satisfaction, teaching efficacy, experience, skills, knowledge, and career-long profession. Student teachers were equally satisfied with teaching practice assessment regardless of subject area specialization, Wambugu (2013). These findings seem to agree with those of Alnaji (2020) who surveyed graduates of various specializations about the importance of teaching skills and the extent to which they acquired them in the teaching practice exercise at Mu'tah University. The researcher found that the extent to which they acquired teaching skills was moderate for all of them irrespective of area of specialization.

Given the study conducted by Tubbs and Holliday (2019), the participating candidates suggested the following: (a) regular communication between supervisors and mentors to "make sure the candidate has been given opportunities to do some administrative work", (b) "specific field experiences to complete", (c) consistent expectations across the board, (d) "embedded experience into each course", (e) a slight reduction of the number of hours, and (f) reduction of supervisor's visits to one time or no mandated visit unless needed.

Teaching as a Profession: The Process

The concept of professionalism has been used by different skilled individuals and groups of individuals, whether their skill was acquired formally or in an informal setting, therefore, the term is almost being loosely used. However, according to Hart and Marshall (2019), professionals in the "classic" fields of law, medicine, and theology have codified rules and

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expectations for behavior developed over many centuries. However, (Tichenor and Tichenor, 2004) affirm that in the field of education, however, being a classroom teacher is not always associated with being a professional, that is, American society does not generally view teachers in the same way as they view other professionals; the belief that “anyone can teach” is not found in other professions. Likewise in the words of Yusuf, Afolabi & Oyetayo (2014); teaching in Nigeria has been patronized by the people who could not succeed in their chosen vocations and the people who believe that teaching is a “spare time job” that allows them to simultaneously engage in other profit-making businesses which they considered more lucrative than teaching.

In Nigeria today, statutorily, teaching has gone beyond “all comers affair” as the teaching profession in Nigeria has been recognized by all stakeholders. In achieving the professionalism of the teaching profession, The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 1990) states clearly in the Nigeria Teachers Manual that, the professionalization of teaching should be given adequate attention to enhance the role of teachers in the formulation and implementation of educational policies in the country. The government, through the National Policy on Education, has clearly stated that “teacher education will continue to be given major emphasis in all our educational planning” because “no education system can rise above the quality of its teacher.” (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004). In addition, the government has recognized teaching as a profession by stating that; “Teaching, like other professions in Nigeria, will be legally and publicly recognized as a profession and in this regard, the government has further taken a step in the establishment of Teacher Registration Council among whose functions are registration, accreditations, certification, discipline and regulation of professional practices as it relates to teaching at any level of Nigeria education.

In an attempt to professionalize teaching, (Yusuf, Afolabi & Oyetayo, 2014) proffered the following: Immediate commencement of work by the recently established Teachers’ Registration Council of Nigeria. As the National Teachers Registration Council has been established through the enactment of Act No 31 of 1993, this national body should be assisted by the State Teachers’ Registration Council in every State of the Federation, to be charged with the responsibility of teachers’ registration, accreditation, certification, promotion, development, discipline and making regulations to control the practice of teaching as a profession. The government should make provision for the professional growth of the teachers through periodic in-service education and this should be sponsored by the government. The government should introduce unified service conditions for all categories of teachers throughout the country. This includes a unified salary such as the much-agitated Teachers’ Salary Structure (TSS), specially designed for teachers to enhance their remuneration and welfare package.

The minimum teaching qualification of NCE should be enforced by the Government. Like other professions such as medicine, law, engineering, pharmacy, and accountancy which are highly valued in Nigeria, it becomes highly imperative to review the duration of the teaching practice exercise from a minimum of 12 weeks to 12 months. This will enhance professional development and proper orientation and adjustment of the teachers to the school setting. The teacher trainee should undergo professional training in the colleges of education, university, and other teacher education programmes. The government should categorize teachers into three distinct groups as suggested by Igwe (1992). These categories are:

1. The full professional teachers are to be made up of all graduates with teaching qualifications not lower than the NCE, Post- post-graduate diploma in Education, or a Bachelor’s degree in education.
2. Intermediate professional teachers are to be made up of all NCE holders; holders of Grade I and II Teacher’s certificates.
3. Auxiliary teachers to be made up of all graduates without teaching qualifications and non-graduates without teaching qualifications.

SIWES: The Catalyst for Pre-Service Teacher Performance

That employment capability of the government and the private sector cannot absorb the number of graduates yearly, and that employers are complaining about the employability of graduates is a major recipe for underdevelopment on the one hand and an increase in crime on the other. Sa’ad (2010) stated that the quality of graduate skills is gradually eroded as a result of the distressed economy where funding of education is reduced, and with the high cost of tools and machines, the institution can neither procure new ones nor repair damaged ones.

However, SIWES as a prerequisite for graduates in vocational teach SIWES gives the recipients insight into how micro or small businesses work, as they are exposed to work etiquette in the course of the SIWES exercise, thereby gaining on-the-job experience that ordinarily cannot be acquired within the walls of the classroom.

1. It creates in the recipients the capacity to start a new venture of their own.
2. SIWES builds on the recipient's general understanding of business areas and approaches.

Qualitative Study on Teaching... (Ismaila, et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259886>

3. It inculcates into the pre-service teachers' enterprising capacity.
4. It exposes the recipient to difficulties and challenges in the operations of the enterprise.
5. SIWES also builds the professional abilities of the pre-service teachers.

Conclusion

Every contact made with either an individual or an object, a cognitive memory is created and as such, this consciousness will always remain in the memory and non-physical and will be required at a later date in understanding a new experience and also help in solving challenges that might arise in the course of the new adventures. Teaching practice and the Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme are both not formalities, but a means towards an end which is the Meta subjective cognition that will assist the students later in life. Therefore, as business educators, efforts should be made to ensure the success of both gap-bridging schemes to enhance better student-teachers and teachers.

Recommendations

Business Education programs should foster stronger partnerships with industries to provide students with practical experience, ensuring the relevance and applicability of skills.

1. Incorporate authentic business scenarios and projects into the curriculum to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application.
2. Include training on essential soft skills such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving to complement technical knowledge.
3. Establish mentorship programs pairing students with experienced professionals for guidance and support.
4. Provide ongoing training and workshops for educators to stay updated on industry trends and best practices.

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